

Factorial-Type Selfie Numbers in Reverse Order of Digits

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Abstract

Numbers represented by their own digits by certain operations are considered as *selfie numbers*. Some times they are called as *wild narcissistic numbers*. There are many ways of representing *selfie numbers*. They can be represented in digit's order, reverse order of digits, increasing and/or decreasing order of digits, etc. These can be obtained by use of *basis operations* along with *factorial, square-root, Fibonacci sequence, Triangular numbers, binomial coefficients, s-gonal values, centered polygonal numbers*, etc. In this work, we have re-written *selfie numbers* in reverse order of digits using, *factorial*. The work is up to 6 digits numbers. The *digit's order selfie numbers with factorial* can be seen in authors's another work [35]

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1 Introduction

Let's analyse historical aspects of some numbers:

- (i) Consider the following classical number famous as **printer's error** (Dudeney, 1917, pp. 379 [2]):

$$2592 := 2^5 \times 9^2. \quad (1)$$

Actually it is not a **printer's error**, it represents number in its own digits. The first number similar property is $25 = 5^2$, but is in reverse order.

- (ii) Let consider another examples (Madachy, 1966, pp.167-275 [10]):

$$\begin{aligned} 34425 &:= 3^4 \times 425 \\ 73942 &:= 73 \times 9 \times 42 \\ 312325 &:= 31^2 \times 325 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Above three are represented their own digits. Moreover, if we multiply by both sides by 10, they continued with property of same digits both sides. These kinds of numbers are famous as **number patterns**.

- (iii) Madachy, 1966, pp.167-275 [10] also gave an interesting property with factorials know by **sum of factorials**:

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &:= 1! \\ 2 &:= 2! \\ 145 &:= 1! + 4! + 5! \\ 40585 &:= 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5! \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Above numbers also have the property of same digits on both sides, but with factorial and addition.

In all the three situations (5), (6) and (7), we observe that we are dealing with numbers those have same digits on both sides, where one side is number another with same digits with certain operations. Based on above idea of numbers, the author studies numbers calling **selfie numbers**, i.e., numbers represented by their own digits by certain operations. Some times they are called as **wild narcissistic numbers**. Some old studies in this direction can seen in the works of Friedman [3, 4] and Rose [11, 12, 13].

There are many ways of representing **selfie numbers**. They can be represented in digit's order, reverse order of digits, increasing and/or decreasing order of digits, etc. These can be obtained by use of basis operations along with **factorial, square-root, Fibonacci sequence, Triangular numbers, binomial coefficients, s-gonal values, centered polygonal numbers**, etc. In the end, the section 3 brings author's work on **selfie numbers**. Below are few examples, of **selfie numbers with basic operations, factorial and square-root**.

• Basic Operations

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** by use of **basic operations**. See below some examples in both orders, i.e., in digit's order and in reverse order of digits:

$$\begin{aligned} 13825 &:= 1 + (3 \times 8)^{-2+5} &= ((5 - 2) \times 8)^3 + 1 \\ 14641 &:= (1 + 4 + 6)^4 \times 1 &= (1 + 4 + 6)^4 \times 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 15552 &:= (1^5 + 5)^5 \times 2 &= 2 \times (6^5 + 5) \times 1 \\
 16377 &:= (1 + 6 - 3)^7 - 7 &= -7 + (7 - 3)^{6+1} \\
 23328 &:= (2 \times 3^3)^2 \times 8 &= (8 - 2)^{3+3} / 2 \\
 116565 &:= (-1 + 16) \times (-5 + 6^5) &= 5 \times (3 \times 6^{6-1} - 1) \\
 131072 &:= (1 + 3)^{1+0+7} \times 2 &= 2^{(7+0-1) \times 3-1} \\
 147419 &:= -1 + (4^7 - 4) \times 1 \times 9 &= 9 \times (1 \times 4^7 - 4) - 1 \\
 147429 &:= 1 + (4^7 - 4/2) \times 9 &= 9 \times (2 + 4^7 - 4 - 1) \\
 147491 &:= 1 \times (4^7 + 4) \times 9 - 1 &= 1 \times 9 \times (4^7 + 4) - 1 \\
 156252 &:= 1 \times 5^6 \times 2 \times 5 + 2 &= 2 \times (5^{2 \times 6-5} + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

• Factorial

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of **factorial**. See below some examples:

$$\begin{aligned}
 145 &:= 1! + 4! + 5! & 361469 &:= 3! - 6! - 1! + 4! - 6! + 9! \\
 733 &:= 7 + 3!! + 3! & 363239 &:= 36 + 323 + 9! \\
 1463 &:= -1! + 4! + 6! + 3!! & 363269 &:= 363 + 26 + 9! \\
 5177 &:= 5! + 17 + 7! & 364292 &:= 3!! + 6! - 4! - 2! + 9! - 2! \\
 10077 &:= -1! - 0! - 0! + 7! + 7! & 397584 &:= -3!! + 9! - 7! + 5! + 8! + 4! \\
 40585 &:= 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5! & 398173 &:= 3! + 9! + 8! + 1! - 7! + 3! \\
 80518 &:= 8! - 0! - 5! - 1! + 8! & 403199 &:= 40319 + 9! \\
 317489 &:= -3! - 1! - 7! - 4! - 8! + 9! & 408937 &:= -4! + 0! + 8! + 9! + 3!! + 7! \\
 352797 &:= -3! + 5 - 2! - 7! + 9! - 7! & 715799 &:= -7! - 1! + 5! - 7! + 9! + 9! \\
 357592 &:= -3! - 5! - 7! - 5! + 9! - 2! & 720599 &:= -7! - 2! + 0! - 5! + 9! + 9! \\
 357941 &:= 3! + 5! - 7! + 9! - 4! - 1!
 \end{aligned}$$

• Square-Root

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of **square-root**. See below some examples in both orders, i.e., in digit's order and in reverse order of digits:

$1764 := 1 \times (7 \times 6)^{\sqrt{4}}$ $2378 := -23 + \sqrt{78}$ $19454 := 19 \times 4^5 - \sqrt{4}$ $19459 := 19 \times 4^5 + \sqrt{9}$ $19684 := 1 + \sqrt{9\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}/4}}$ $839793 := (-8 + (-3 + 9)^7 + \sqrt{9}) \times 3$ $839795 := -8 + (-3 + 9)^7 \times \sqrt{9} - 5$ $839804 := (-8 + (3 - 9)^8 + 0) / \sqrt{4}$ $839816 := (8 + (3 - 9)^8) / \sqrt{\sqrt{16}}$ $995544 := ((9 + \sqrt{9})^5 + 54) \times 4$ $999916 := -9 \times 9 - \sqrt{9} + (9 + 1)^6$ $999976 := -\sqrt{9} \times 9 + \sqrt{9} + (\sqrt{9} + 7)^6$	$64 := \sqrt{4^6}$ $1024 := \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{20}} \times 1}$ $1296 := 6^{\sqrt{9+2}-1}$ $2189 := \sqrt{9^{8-1}} + 2$ $3867 := (-7 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times 3$ $9375 := \sqrt{5^{7+3} \times 9}$ $12289 := \sqrt{9} \times 8^{2 \times 2} + 1$ $19693 := 3^9 + 6 + \sqrt{9} + 1$ $42436 := (6 \times 34 + 2)^{\sqrt{4}}$ $59051 := \sqrt{-1 + 5} + 0 + 9^5$ $999901 := (10^{9-\sqrt{9}}) - 99$ $999991 := (1^9 + 99)^{\sqrt{9}} - 9$
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First column numbers are in **digit's order** and second columns are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details refer [19, 18, 20, 22, 23, 24].

1.1 New Project: Selfie Numbers

This new project is to re-write and extend the **selfie numbers** in **digit's order**, and **reverse** with following aspects:

- (i) **Basic Operations** - up to 7 digits (previous work is up to 6 digits: [21], [27]);
- (ii) **Factorial** - up to 6 digits (previous work is up to 6 digits is incomplete: [17]-[21], [27])
- (iii) **Square-root** - up to 7 digits (previous work is up to 6 digits: [17]-[21])
- (iv) **Factorial and Square-root** - up to 5 digits: [17]-[21], [27];
- (v) **Fibonacci sequence** - up to 6 digits: [32], [33]);
- (vi) **Triangular numbers** - up to 5 digits: [29], [33];
- (vii) **Binomial coefficients** - up to 6 digits: [31];
- (viii) **S-gonal** - up to 5 digits: [25];
- (ix) **Centered Polygonal** - up to 5 digits: [25];
- (x) **Concatenation-Type** in digit's order: [26];
- (xi) **Quadratic numbers** in digit's order and reverse: [34];
- (xii) **Cubic numbers** in digit's order and reverse: (under preparation).

In this paper, we worked with **selfie numbers** in **reverse order of digits** using **factorial** along with **basic operations**.

2 Factorial-Type Selfie Numbers

This section brings **factorial-type selfie numbers** in reverse order of digits. It is divided in different categories according following subsections.

2.1 Specific-Type Selfie Numbers

This subsection brings **factorial-type selfie numbers** only with addition and subtraction. Again we have divided in two subsections. One without brackets and another with brackets. The results are limited up to 6 digits.

2.1.1 Without Positive and Negative Coefficients

$$36 := 6 \times 3!$$

$$624 := 4! \times 26$$

$$0132 := (2 \times 3!)/10!$$

$$1704 := 4! \times 071$$

$$3456 := 6!/5 \times 4 \times 3!$$

$$4096 := (6!/90)^4$$

$$6048 := 8!/40 \times 6$$

$$01296 := 6! \times 9 \times 2/10$$

$$02688 := 8 \times 8!/(6 \times 20)$$

$$32544 := 4! \times 452 \times 3$$

$$48384 := 4! \times 8 \times 3 \times 84$$

$$104976 := 6^7 \times 9/4! \times 01$$

$$120504 := 4! \times 05021$$

$$243648 := 846 \times 3! \times 4! \times 2$$

$$289737 := 73 \times (7 \times 9!/8!)^2$$

$$368316 := 61386 \times 3!$$

$$419328 := 8^2 \times 3 \times 91 \times 4!$$

$$532224 := (4 \times 2)! \times 22 \times 3/5$$

$$592704 := 4 \times 07^2 \times 9!/5!$$

$$627264 := 4! \times 6^2 \times 726$$

$$627984 := 4! \times 89 \times 7^2 \times 6$$

$$653184 := 4! \times 81 \times 3! \times 56$$

$$756864 := 4! \times 6 \times 8 \times 657$$

$$786432 := 2 \times 3! \times (4!/6)^{8!/7!}$$

2.1.2 Positive and Negative Coefficients: Without Brackets

• Symmetric

$$362910 := 0 + 1 + 9! + 26 + 3$$

$$362911 := 1 + 1 + 9! + 26 + 3$$

$$362912 := 2 + 1 + 9! + 26 + 3$$

$$362913 := 3 + 1 + 9! + 26 + 3$$

$$362914 := 4 + 1 + 9! + 26 + 3$$

$$362915 := 5 + 1 + 9! + 26 + 3$$

$$362916 := 6 + 1 + 9! + 26 + 3$$

$$362917 := 7 + 1 + 9! + 26 + 3$$

$$362918 := 8 + 1 + 9! + 26 + 3$$

$$362919 := 9 + 1 + 9! + 26 + 3$$

$$362950 := 0 + 5 + 9! + 2 + 63$$

$$362951 := 1 + 5 + 9! + 2 + 63$$

$$362952 := 2 + 5 + 9! + 2 + 63$$

$$362953 := 3 + 5 + 9! + 2 + 63$$

$$362954 := 4 + 5 + 9! + 2 + 63$$

$$362955 := 5 + 5 + 9! + 2 + 63$$

$$362956 := 6 + 5 + 9! + 2 + 63$$

$$362957 := 7 + 5 + 9! + 2 + 63$$

$$362958 := 8 + 5 + 9! + 2 + 63$$

$$362959 := 9 + 5 + 9! + 2 + 63$$

• **Nonsymmetric**

$$145 := 5! + 4! + 1$$

$$733 := 3!! + 3! + 7$$

$$0154 := 4! + 5! + 10$$

$$0629 := -92 + 6! + 0!$$

$$0638 := -83 + 6! + 0!$$

$$0647 := -74 + 6! + 0!$$

$$0674 := -47 + 6! + 0!$$

$$0683 := -38 + 6! + 0!$$

$$0692 := -29 + 6! + 0!$$

$$1463 := 3!! + 6! + 4! - 1$$

$$4317 := 7! + 1 - 3!! - 4$$

$$4957 := 7! - 59 - 4!$$

$$4967 := 7! - 69 - 4$$

$$5175 := 5! + 7! + 15$$

$$5637 := 7! - 3 + 6! - 5!$$

$$6476 := 6! + 7! - 4 + 6!$$

$$00593 := 3!! - 9 - 5! + 0! + 0!$$

$$00716 := 6! + 1 - 7 + 0! + 0!$$

$$01466 := 6! + 6! + 4! + 1 + 0!$$

$$04327 := 7! + 2 - 3!! + 4 + 0!$$

$$04337 := 7! - 3!! - 3! + 4! - 0!$$

$$04997 := 7! - 9 - 9 - 4! - 0!$$

$$05773 := 3!! + 7! + 7 + 5 + 0!$$

$$05873 := 3!! + 7! - 8 + 5! + 0!$$

$$10077 := 7! + 7! - 0! - 0! - 1$$

$$35875 := -5 - 7! + 8! - 5! + 3!!$$

$$38753 := -3!! - 5! - 7 + 8! - 3!!$$

$$38864 := -4! - 6! + 8 + 8! - 3!!$$

$$38866 := -6! - 6! - 8 + 8! - 3!$$

$$39538 := 8! - 3!! - 59 - 3$$

$$40287 := -7 + 8! - 2 - 04!$$

$$40288 := 8! - 8 - 20 - 4$$

$$40289 := -9 + 8! + 2 - 04!$$

$$40318 := 8! - 1 + 3 + 0 - 4$$

$$40585 := 5! + 8! + 5! + 0! + 4!$$

$$41038 := 8! + 3!! + 0! + 1 - 4$$

$$80585 := -5 + 8! - 50 + 8!$$

$$316798 := -8! + 9! - 7! - 6! + 1 - 3$$

$$317498 := -8! + 9! - 4! - 7! - 1 + 3$$

$$322589 := 9! - 8! + 52 - 23$$

$$323968 := -8! + 6! + 9! - 32 + 3!!$$

$$323989 := -9 - 8! + 9! + 3!! - 2 + 3!!$$

$$326879 := 9! + 7! - 8! - 6! + 2 - 3$$

$$356997 := -7! - 9 + 9! - 6! - 5! + 3!$$

$$357239 := 9! - 3!! + 2 - 7! + 5! - 3$$

$$357589 := 9! - 8 - 5! - 7! - 5! - 3$$

$$357592 := -2 + 9! - 5! - 7! - 5! - 3!$$

$$357598 := -8 + 9! - 5! - 7! - 5! + 3!$$

$$357699 := 9! - 9 - 6 - 7! - 5! - 3!$$

$$357739 := 9! + 3! - 7! + 7 - 5! + 3!$$

$$357792 := -2 + 9! - 7! + 7 - 53$$

$$357829 := 9! - 2 - 8 - 7! + 5 - 3!$$

$$357879 := 9! - 7! - 87 + 5! + 3!$$

$$357906 := -60 + 9! - 7! + 5! + 3!$$

$$357915 := -51 + 9! - 7! + 5! + 3!$$

$$357924 := -42 + 9! - 7! + 5! + 3!$$

$$357942 := -24 + 9! - 7! + 5! + 3!$$

$$357951 := -1 + 5! + 9! - 7! - 5 - 3$$

$$357953 := -3! + 5! + 9! - 7! + 5 - 3!$$

$$357954 := -4 + 5! + 9! - 7! - 5 + 3$$

$$357956 := -6 + 5! + 9! - 7! + 5 - 3$$

$$357959 := -9 + 5! + 9! - 7! + 5 + 3$$

$$357969 := 9! - 6 + 9 - 7! + 5! + 3!$$

$$357981 := 18 + 9! - 7! + 5! + 3$$

$$357992 := 29 + 9! - 7! + 5! + 3$$

$$358479 := 9! - 7! + 4 - 85 + 3!!$$

$$359273 := 3!! - 7! - 2 + 9! - 5 + 3!!$$

$$361469 := 9! - 6! + 4! - 1 - 6! + 3!$$

$$361489 := 9! + 8 + 41 - 6! - 3!!$$

$$361899 := 9! - 981 - 6 + 3!$$

$$361989 := 9! - 891 - 6 + 3!$$

$$361994 := 4! + 9! - 916 + 3!$$

$$362749 := 9! + 4 - 72 - 63$$

$$362901 := 10 + 9! + 2 + 6 + 3$$

$$362921 := 12 + 9! + 26 + 3$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 362923 &:= 32 + 9! + 2 + 6 + 3 & 367859 &:= 9! - 58 + 7! - 6 + 3 \\
 362932 &:= 23 + 9! + 26 + 3 & 367895 &:= -5 + 9! - 8 + 7! - 6 - 3! \\
 362934 &:= 43 + 9! + 2 + 6 + 3 & 367904 &:= -4 + 09! + 7! - 6 - 3! \\
 362939 &:= 9! + 3 - 9 + 2 + 63 & 367908 &:= -8 - 0! + 9! + 7! - 6 + 3 \\
 362945 &:= 54 + 9! + 2 + 6 + 3 & 367909 &:= 9! + 0! - 9 + 7! - 6 + 3 \\
 362961 &:= 16 + 9! + 2 + 63 & 367973 &:= -3 + 7! + 9! - 7 + 63 \\
 362965 &:= 56 + 9! + 26 + 3 & 367985 &:= 5! + 8 + 9! + 7! - 63 \\
 362967 &:= 76 + 9! + 2 + 6 + 3 & 367991 &:= -1 + 9 + 9! + 7! + 63 \\
 362969 &:= 9! + 6 + 92 - 6 - 3 & 368579 &:= 9! + 7! - 58 + 6! - 3 \\
 362972 &:= 27 + 9! + 2 + 63 & 372967 &:= 7! + 6 + 9! - 2 + 7! + 3 \\
 362976 &:= 67 + 9! + 26 + 3 & 377997 &:= 7! - 9 + 9! + 7! + 7! + 3! \\
 362978 &:= 87 + 9! + 2 + 6 + 3 & 397438 &:= 8! - 3!! + 4 - 7! + 9! - 3! \\
 362983 &:= 38 + 9! + 2 + 63 & 397487 &:= -7! + 8! + 47 + 9! + 3!! \\
 362987 &:= 78 + 9! + 26 + 3 & 397584 &:= 4! + 8! + 5! - 7! + 9! - 3!! \\
 362994 &:= 49 + 9! + 2 + 63 & 398173 &:= 3! - 7! + 1 + 8! + 9! + 3! \\
 362998 &:= 89 + 9! + 26 + 3 & 398275 &:= 5! - 7! - 2 + 8! + 9! - 3 \\
 363059 &:= 9! + 5! - 0! - 3 + 63 & 398755 &:= -5 - 5! - 7! + 8! + 9! + 3!! \\
 363239 &:= 9! - 3! + 2 + 363 & 398871 &:= -1 - 7! - 8 + 8! + 9! + 3!! \\
 363249 &:= 9! + 4 + 2 + 363 & 398879 &:= 9! - 7! + 8! + 8 - 9 + 3!! \\
 363593 &:= -3 + 9! + 5 - 3! + 6! - 3 & 398973 &:= 3!! - 7! + 9! + 8! - 93 \\
 363599 &:= 9! - 9 + 5 - 3 + 6! + 3! & 398978 &:= 8! - 7! + 98 + 9! + 3!! \\
 363639 &:= 9! + 3! + 6! + 36 - 3 & 402988 &:= -8 + 8! + 9! - 204 \\
 363649 &:= 9! + 46 - 3 + 6! + 3! & 403198 &:= 8! + 9! - 1 + 3 - 04 \\
 363689 &:= 9! + 86 - 3 + 6! + 3! & 403889 &:= 9! + 8! - 8 + 3!! + 0! - 4! \\
 364292 &:= -2 + 9! - 2 - 4! + 6! + 3!! & 403918 &:= 8! + 1 + 9! + 3!! + 0! - 4 \\
 364293 &:= 3!! + 9! - 24 + 6! - 3 & 403938 &:= 8! + 3!! + 9! - 3! + 04! \\
 364359 &:= 9! + 5 + 34 + 6! + 3!! & 403948 &:= 8! + 4 + 9! + 3!! + 04! \\
 364369 &:= 9! + 6! + 3!! + 46 + 3 & 408937 &:= 7! + 3!! + 9! + 8! + 0! - 4! \\
 366479 &:= 9! + 7! - 4 - 6! - 6! + 3 & 683995 &:= -5 + 9! + 9! - 3!! - 8! - 6! \\
 366597 &:= 7! + 9! + 5! - 6! - 6! - 3 & 685399 &:= 9! + 9! - 35 - 8! - 6 \\
 367193 &:= -3 + 9! - 1 + 7! - 6! - 3 & 715799 &:= 9! + 9! - 7! + 5! - 1 - 7! \\
 367194 &:= -4 + 9! + 1 + 7! - 6! - 3 & 725799 &:= 9! + 9! + 7 + 5 + 27 \\
 367196 &:= -6 + 9! - 1 + 7! - 6! + 3 & 725899 &:= 9! + 9! - 8 + 5! + 27 \\
 367197 &:= 7! + 9! + 1 - 7 - 6! + 3 & 725995 &:= 5! + 9! + 9! + 5! + 2 - 7 \\
 367795 &:= -3! - 6 + 7 + 7! + 9! + 5! & 726499 &:= 9! + 9! + 4! + 6! + 2 - 7 \\
 367829 &:= 9! - 28 + 7! - 63
 \end{aligned}$$

2.1.3 Positive and Negative Coefficients: With Brackets

- Symmetric

$$\begin{aligned}0120 &:= 0 + ((2 + 1)! - 0!)! \\0121 &:= 1 + ((2 + 1)! - 0!)! \\0122 &:= 2 + ((2 + 1)! - 0!)! \\0123 &:= 3 + ((2 + 1)! - 0!)! \\0124 &:= 4 + ((2 + 1)! - 0!)! \\0125 &:= 5 + ((2 + 1)! - 0!)! \\0126 &:= 6 + ((2 + 1)! - 0!)! \\0127 &:= 7 + ((2 + 1)! - 0!)! \\0128 &:= 8 + ((2 + 1)! - 0!)! \\0129 &:= 9 + ((2 + 1)! - 0!)!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}0720 &:= 0 + ((-2 + 7) + 0!)! \\0721 &:= 1 + ((-2 + 7) + 0!)! \\0722 &:= 2 + ((-2 + 7) + 0!)! \\0723 &:= 3 + ((-2 + 7) + 0!)! \\0724 &:= 4 + ((-2 + 7) + 0!)! \\0725 &:= 5 + ((-2 + 7) + 0!)! \\0726 &:= 6 + ((-2 + 7) + 0!)! \\0727 &:= 7 + ((-2 + 7) + 0!)! \\0728 &:= 8 + ((-2 + 7) + 0!)! \\0729 &:= 9 + ((-2 + 7) + 0!)!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}5160 &:= 0 + (6 + 1)! + 5! \\5161 &:= 1 + (6 + 1)! + 5! \\5162 &:= 2 + (6 + 1)! + 5! \\5163 &:= 3 + (6 + 1)! + 5! \\5164 &:= 4 + (6 + 1)! + 5! \\5165 &:= 5 + (6 + 1)! + 5! \\5166 &:= 6 + (6 + 1)! + 5! \\5167 &:= 7 + (6 + 1)! + 5! \\5168 &:= 8 + (6 + 1)! + 5! \\5169 &:= 9 + (6 + 1)! + 5!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}04920 &:= 0 + (-2 + 9)! - (4 + 0!)! \\04921 &:= 1 + (-2 + 9)! - (4 + 0!)! \\04922 &:= 2 + (-2 + 9)! - (4 + 0!)! \\04923 &:= 3 + (-2 + 9)! - (4 + 0!)! \\04924 &:= 4 + (-2 + 9)! - (4 + 0!)! \\04925 &:= 5 + (-2 + 9)! - (4 + 0!)! \\04926 &:= 6 + (-2 + 9)! - (4 + 0!)! \\04927 &:= 7 + (-2 + 9)! - (4 + 0!)!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}04928 &:= 8 + (-2 + 9)! - (4 + 0!)! \\04929 &:= 9 + (-2 + 9)! - (4 + 0!)!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}39480 &:= 0 + 8! - (-4 + 9)! - 3!! \\39481 &:= 1 + 8! - (-4 + 9)! - 3!! \\39482 &:= 2 + 8! - (-4 + 9)! - 3!! \\39483 &:= 3 + 8! - (-4 + 9)! - 3!! \\39484 &:= 4 + 8! - (-4 + 9)! - 3!! \\39485 &:= 5 + 8! - (-4 + 9)! - 3!! \\39486 &:= 6 + 8! - (-4 + 9)! - 3!! \\39487 &:= 7 + 8! - (-4 + 9)! - 3!! \\39488 &:= 8 + 8! - (-4 + 9)! - 3!! \\39489 &:= 9 + 8! - (-4 + 9)! - 3!!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}40440 &:= 0 + (4 + 4)! + (0! + 4)! \\40441 &:= 1 + (4 + 4)! + (0! + 4)! \\40442 &:= 2 + (4 + 4)! + (0! + 4)! \\40443 &:= 3 + (4 + 4)! + (0! + 4)! \\40444 &:= 4 + (4 + 4)! + (0! + 4)! \\40445 &:= 5 + (4 + 4)! + (0! + 4)! \\40446 &:= 6 + (4 + 4)! + (0! + 4)! \\40447 &:= 7 + (4 + 4)! + (0! + 4)! \\40448 &:= 8 + (4 + 4)! + (0! + 4)! \\40449 &:= 9 + (4 + 4)! + (0! + 4)!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}362980 &:= 0 + 8 + 92 + (6 + 3)! \\362981 &:= 1 + 8 + 92 + (6 + 3)! \\362982 &:= 2 + 8 + 92 + (6 + 3)! \\362983 &:= 3 + 8 + 92 + (6 + 3)! \\362984 &:= 4 + 8 + 92 + (6 + 3)! \\362985 &:= 5 + 8 + 92 + (6 + 3)! \\362986 &:= 6 + 8 + 92 + (6 + 3)! \\362987 &:= 7 + 8 + 92 + (6 + 3)! \\362988 &:= 8 + 8 + 92 + (6 + 3)! \\362989 &:= 9 + 8 + 92 + (6 + 3)!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}363000 &:= 0 + (0! + 0! + 3)! + (6 + 3)! \\363001 &:= 1 + (0! + 0! + 3)! + (6 + 3)! \\363002 &:= 2 + (0! + 0! + 3)! + (6 + 3)! \\363003 &:= 3 + (0! + 0! + 3)! + (6 + 3)! \\363004 &:= 4 + (0! + 0! + 3)! + (6 + 3)! \\363005 &:= 5 + (0! + 0! + 3)! + (6 + 3)!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 363006 &:= 6 + (0! + 0! + 3)! + (6 + 3)! \\
 363007 &:= 7 + (0! + 0! + 3)! + (6 + 3)! \\
 363008 &:= 8 + (0! + 0! + 3)! + (6 + 3)! \\
 363009 &:= 9 + (0! + 0! + 3)! + (6 + 3)! \\
 \\
 363720 &:= 0 + (-2 + 7)! + 3!! + (6 + 3)! \\
 363721 &:= 1 + (-2 + 7)! + 3!! + (6 + 3)! \\
 363722 &:= 2 + (-2 + 7)! + 3!! + (6 + 3)!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 363723 &:= 3 + (-2 + 7)! + 3!! + (6 + 3)! \\
 363724 &:= 4 + (-2 + 7)! + 3!! + (6 + 3)! \\
 363725 &:= 5 + (-2 + 7)! + 3!! + (6 + 3)! \\
 363726 &:= 6 + (-2 + 7)! + 3!! + (6 + 3)! \\
 363727 &:= 7 + (-2 + 7)! + 3!! + (6 + 3)! \\
 363728 &:= 8 + (-2 + 7)! + 3!! + (6 + 3)! \\
 363729 &:= 9 + (-2 + 7)! + 3!! + (6 + 3)!
 \end{aligned}$$

• **Nonsymmetric**

$$\begin{aligned}
 715 &:= -5 + (-1 + 7)! \\
 \\
 0695 &:= -(-5 + 9)! + (6! - 0!) \\
 0712 &:= (2 + 1)!! - 7 - 0! \\
 0714 &:= (4 - 1)!! - 7 + 0! \\
 0742 &:= -2 + 4! + (7 - 0)! \\
 1435 &:= -5 + 3!! + (4 - 1)!! \\
 1464 &:= 4! + 6! + (4 - 1)!! \\
 4296 &:= -6! + (9 - 2)! - 4! \\
 5016 &:= (6 + 1)! - (-0! + 5)! \\
 5017 &:= 7! + 1 - (-0! + 5)! \\
 5034 &:= (4 + 3)! - 0! - 5 \\
 5184 &:= 4! + (8 - 1)! + 5! \\
 \\
 00123 &:= (3 + 2)! + 1 + 0! + 0! \\
 00694 &:= -4! + (9 - 6)!! - 0! - 0! \\
 00715 &:= (5 + 1)! - 7 + 0! + 0! \\
 00783 &:= 3!! + (-8 + 70) + 0! \\
 01433 &:= 3!! + 3!! - (4 - 1)! - 0! \\
 05016 &:= (6 + 1)! - (05 - 0)! \\
 05017 &:= 7! + 1 - (05 - 0)! \\
 05029 &:= -9 - 2 + (0! + 5 + 0)! \\
 05038 &:= -8 + 3! + (0! + 5 + 0)! \\
 05039 &:= (9 + 3 - 05)! - 0! \\
 05062 &:= -2 + (6 + 0)! + (5 - 0)! \\
 05085 &:= -5 + (8 - 0)! + 50 \\
 05137 &:= 7! - (3 + 1)! + 5! + 0! \\
 05734 &:= 4! + 3!! + (7! - 50) \\
 05748 &:= -8 - 4 + 7! + (5 + 0)! \\
 05793 &:= 3!! + 9 + 7! + (5 - 0)!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 35274 &:= -4 - 7! - 2 + (5 + 3)! \\
 35276 &:= -6 - 7! + 2 + (5 + 3)! \\
 35304 &:= 4! - (0! + 3)! + (5 + 3)! \\
 39624 &:= 4! + (2 + 6)! - (9 - 3)! \\
 40175 &:= -5! + (7 + 1)! - 0! - 4! \\
 40195 &:= -5! + (9 - 1)! - 0! - 4 \\
 40584 &:= 4! + 8! + 5! + (0! + 4)! \\
 40309 &:= (9 - 0)! - 3! - 0! - 4 \\
 40313 &:= -3 + (1 + 3! + 0)! - 4 \\
 40314 &:= -(4 - 1)! + (3 + 0! + 4)! \\
 40315 &:= -5 + (13 - 0! - 4)! \\
 40316 &:= (6 - 1 + 3)! + 0 - 4 \\
 40319 &:= (9 - 1)! + 3 + 0 - 4 \\
 40285 &:= -5 + 8! - (2 + 0)! - 4! \\
 40458 &:= 8! + 5! - (4 - 0)! + 4! \\
 41036 &:= 6! + (3! + 0! + 1)! - 4 \\
 44637 &:= 7! - 3 - 6! + (4 + 4)! \\
 45377 &:= 7! - 7 + (3 + 5)! + 4! \\
 45384 &:= 4! + 8! + (3! + 5 - 4)! \\
 80518 &:= (8! - 1 - (5! + 0!)) + 8! \\
 80519 &:= (9 - 1)! - 5! - 0! + 8! \\
 80635 &:= (5 + 3)! - 6 + 0! + 8! \\
 80755 &:= 5! - 5 + (7 + 0)! + 8! \\
 \\
 321769 &:= 9! - 6! - 71 - (2 + 3)! \\
 322494 &:= -4! + 9! - 42 - (2 + 3)! \\
 322508 &:= (8 + 0)! - 52 - (2 + 3)! \\
 322509 &:= 9! + 0! - 52 - (2 + 3)! \\
 322539 &:= 9! - (3 + 5)! + 2 - 23 \\
 323998 &:= -8! + 9! + (9 - 3)! - 2 + 3!!
 \end{aligned}$$

352079 := $9! - 7! - 0! - (2 + 5)! - 3!!$
352789 := $9! - 8 - 7! - (2 + 5)! - 3$
352792 := $-2 + 9! - 7! - (2 + 5)! - 3!$
352798 := $-8 + 9! - 7! - (2 + 5)! + 3!$
357087 := $-7! + (8 + 0)! - 753$
357087 := $-7! + (8 + 0)! - 753$
357237 := $-7! - 3!! + (2 + 7)! + 5! - 3$
357719 := $9! - 1 - 7! + (7 + 5 - 3)!$
357787 := $-7! + (8 + (7 - 7)!)! - 53$
357832 := $(-2 + 3 + 8)! - 7! + 5 + 3$
357918 := $-(8 - 1)! + 9! + 75 + 3$
358547 := $-7! + (4 + 5)! - 8 - 5 + 3!!$
361435 := $-5 - 3!! - (4 - 1)!! + (6 + 3)!$
361456 := $-6! + (5 + 4)! + 16 - 3!!$
361464 := $4! - 6! - (4 - 1)!! + (6 + 3)!$
361481 := $(1 + 8)! + 41 - 6! - 3!!$
361893 := $-3! - 981 + (6 + 3)!$
362039 := $9! - 3!! - 0! - (2 + 6 - 3)!$
362134 := $(4 + 3! - 1)! - 26 - 3!!$
362145 := $(5 + 4)! - 12 - 6! - 3$
362148 := $-8 - 4 - (1 + 2)!! + (6 + 3)!$
362153 := $-3!! + 5 - 12 + (6 + 3)!$
362156 := $-6 - (5 + 1)! + 2 + (6 + 3)!$
362157 := $(7 + 5 - 1 - 2)! - 6! - 3$
362172 := $(2 + 7)! + (1 + 2)! - 6! + 3!$
362179 := $9! + 7 + (1 + 2)! - 6! + 3!$
362182 := $-2 + (8 + 1)! + (-2 + 6)! - 3!!$
362183 := $-3 + (8 + 1)! + 26 - 3!!$
362275 := $5! + (7 + 2)! - 2 - 6! - 3$
362279 := $9! + (7 - 2)! + 2 - 6! - 3$
362745 := $(5 + 4)! - 72 - 63$
362752 := $-2 - 5! + (7 + 2)! - (6 - 3)!$
362755 := $-5 - 5! + (72 - 63)!$
362758 := $-8 - 5! + (7 + 2)! + (6 - 3)!$
362763 := $(3 + 6)! - (7 - 2)! + (6 - 3)$
362772 := $(2 + 7)! - (7 - 2)! + 6 + 3!$
362773 := $3! + 7 - (7 - 2)! + (6 + 3)!$
362789 := $9! - 87 + 2 - (6 - 3)!$
362803 := $3! - 0! - 82 + (6 + 3)!$
362804 := $(4 - 0)! - 82 + (6 + 3)!$

362813 := $-3! + (1 + 8)! + 2 - 63$
362822 := $(2 + 2)! - 82 + (6 + 3)!$
362827 := $(7 + 2)! + 8 + 2 - 63$
362873 := $3! - 7 - 8 + 2 + (6 + 3)!$
362936 := $(6 + 3)! - 9 + 2 + 63$
362944 := $-4 - 4! + 92 + (6 + 3)!$
362947 := $(7 - 4)! + 9! - 2 + 63$
362948 := $-(8 - 4)! + 92 + (6 + 3)!$
362963 := $(3 + 6)! + 92 - 6 - 3$
362991 := $19 + 92 + (6 + 3)!$
363039 := $9! + (3! - 0)! + 36 + 3$
363063 := $(3 + 6)! + (-0! + 3!)! + 63$
363069 := $9! + (6 - 0)! + 3! + 63$
363243 := $(3 + 4 + 2)! + 363$
363245 := $(5 + 4)! + 2 + 363$
363479 := $-97 - 4! + 3!! + (6 + 3)!$
363488 := $-88 - 4! + 3!! + (6 + 3)!$
363497 := $-79 - 4! + 3!! + (6 + 3)!$
363498 := $-8 - 94 + 3!! + (6 + 3)!$
363504 := $4! - 05! + 3!! + (6 + 3)!$
363543 := $3!! - 4 - 53 + (6 + 3)!$
363547 := $(7 - 4)!! - 53 + (6 + 3)!$
363574 := $-4! - 7 + 5 + 3!! + (6 + 3)!$
363613 := $3! + 1 + 6! + 3! + (6 + 3)!$
363616 := $6! + 16 + (3 + (6 - 3)!)!$
363623 := $3!! + 26 - 3 + (6 + 3)!$
363626 := $6! + 26 + (3 + (6 - 3)!)!$
363633 := $3!! + (3 + 6)! + 36 - 3$
363636 := $6! + 36 + (3 + (6 - 3)!)!$
363643 := $3!! + 46 - 3 + (6 + 3)!$
363646 := $6! + 46 + (3 + (6 - 3)!)!$
363653 := $3!! + 56 - 3 + (6 + 3)!$
363656 := $6! + 56 + (3 + (6 - 3)!)!$
363663 := $3!! + (6 + 6 - 3)! + 63$
363669 := $9! + 6! + (6 - 3)! + 63$
363673 := $3!! + 76 - 3 + (6 + 3)!$
363676 := $6! + 76 + (3 + (6 - 3)!)!$
363683 := $3!! + 86 - 3 + (6 + 3)!$
363686 := $6! + 86 + (3 + (6 - 3)!)!$
363693 := $3!! + 96 - 3 + (6 + 3)!$

$$\begin{aligned}
 363696 &:= 6! + 96 + (3 + (6 - 3))! \\
 363963 &:= (-3 + 6)!! + 9! + 363 \\
 364195 &:= -5 + 9! - (1 + 4)! + 6! + 3!! \\
 364315 &:= -5 + (13 - 4)! + 6! + 3!! \\
 364318 &:= (8 + 1)! + 3!! + 4 + 6! - 3! \\
 364337 &:= -7 + 3!! + 3!! + 4! + (6 + 3)! \\
 364354 &:= (4 + 5)! + 34 + 6! + 3!! \\
 364366 &:= 6! + (6 + 3)! + 46 + 3!! \\
 364366 &:= 6! + (6 + 3)! + 46 + 3!! \\
 366476 &:= -6! + 7! - 4 - 6! + (6 + 3)! \\
 367187 &:= -7 + (8 + 1)! + 7! - 6! - 3! \\
 367460 &:= (3 + 6)! + 7! - 460 \\
 367785 &:= -5! - 8 - 7 + 7! + (6 + 3)! \\
 367856 &:= -6 - 58 + 7! + (6 + 3)! \\
 367898 &:= -8 + 9! - 8 + 7! - (6 - 3)! \\
 367901 &:= -10 - 9 + 7! + (6 + 3)! \\
 367905 &:= -5 - 0! - 9 + 7! + (6 + 3)! \\
 367906 &:= -6 + 0! - 9 + 7! + (6 + 3)! \\
 367922 &:= -2 - 2 + 9! + 7! + (6 - 3)! \\
 367924 &:= -4 + 2 + 9! + 7! + (6 - 3)! \\
 367931 &:= -1 + 3 - 9 + 7! + (6 + 3)! \\
 367959 &:= -(9 - 5)! + 9! + 7! + 63 \\
 372952 &:= (2 + 5)! + 9! - 2 + 7! - 3! \\
 372954 &:= (4 + 5)! + (9 - 2)! + 7! - 3! \\
 372959 &:= 9! + 5 + (9 - 2)! + 7! - 3! \\
 372961 &:= (1 + 6)! + 9! - 2 + 7! + 3 \\
 372969 &:= 9! + 6 + (9 - 2)! + 7! + 3 \\
 373675 &:= -5 + 7! + (6 + 3)! + 7! + 3!! \\
 398037 &:= -7! - (3! - 0)! + 8! + 9! - 3 \\
 398158 &:= 8! + 5 - (-1 + 8)! + 9! + 3 \\
 398163 &:= -3 - (6 + 1)! + 8! + 9! + 3! \\
 402598 &:= 8! + 9! + 5! - 2 - (-0! + 4)!! \\
 402958 &:= 8! - 5! + 9! - 2 - (0! + 4)! \\
 403179 &:= 9! + (7 + 1)! + 3 - 04! \\
 403195 &:= -5 + 9! + (1 + 3 + 04)! \\
 403880 &:= -40 + 3!! + 8! + (8 + 0)! \\
 403917 &:= (7 + 1)! + 9! + 3!! + 0! - 4 \\
 403923 &:= (3! + 2)! + 9! + 3!! - 0! + 4 \\
 403926 &:= (6 + 2)! + 9! + 3!! + (-0! + 4)! \\
 403928 &:= 8! + 2 + 9! + 3!! + (-0! + 4)! \\
 403944 &:= (4 + 4)! + 9! + 3!! + 04! \\
 443519 &:= 9! - 1 + (5 + 3)! + (4 + 4)! \\
 720719 &:= 9! - 1 - 7! + (02 + 7)! \\
 725519 &:= 9! - 1 - 5! - 5! + (2 + 7)! \\
 725635 &:= -5 + (3 + 6)! - 5! + (2 + 7)! \\
 725679 &:= 9! - 76 - 5 + (2 + 7)! \\
 725772 &:= (2 + 7)! + 7 + 5 + (2 + 7)! \\
 725779 &:= 9! + 7 + 7 + 5 + (2 + 7)! \\
 725819 &:= 9! + (1 + 8)! + 52 + 7 \\
 725839 &:= 9! - 3! + 85 + (2 + 7)! \\
 725845 &:= (5 + 4)! + 85 + (2 + 7)! \\
 725849 &:= 9! + 4 + 85 + (2 + 7)! \\
 725872 &:= (2 + 7)! - 8 + 5! + (2 + 7)! \\
 725879 &:= 9! + 7 - 8 + 5! + (2 + 7)! \\
 725904 &:= 4! + 09! + 5! + (2 + 7)! \\
 726497 &:= -7 + 9! + 4! + 6! + (2 + 7)! \\
 726595 &:= 5! + 9! - 5 + 6! + (2 + 7)! \\
 730919 &:= 9! - 1 + 9! + (-0! + 3)! + 7!
 \end{aligned}$$

2.2 General Representations

2.2.1 Symmetric

- Consecutive

$$\begin{aligned}
 0360 &:= 0 - 6! / (-3 + 0!) \\
 0361 &:= 1 - 6! / (-3 + 0!) \\
 0362 &:= 2 - 6! / (-3 + 0!) \\
 0363 &:= 3 - 6! / (-3 + 0!) \\
 0364 &:= 4 - 6! / (-3 + 0!) \\
 0365 &:= 5 - 6! / (-3 + 0!) \\
 0366 &:= 6 - 6! / (-3 + 0!) \\
 0367 &:= 7 - 6! / (-3 + 0!) \\
 0368 &:= 8 - 6! / (-3 + 0!) \\
 0369 &:= 9 - 6! / (-3 + 0!)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2160 &:= 0 + 6! \times (1 + 2) \\2161 &:= 1 + 6! \times (1 + 2) \\2162 &:= 2 + 6! \times (1 + 2) \\2163 &:= 3 + 6! \times (1 + 2) \\2164 &:= 4 + 6! \times (1 + 2) \\2165 &:= 5 + 6! \times (1 + 2) \\2166 &:= 6 + 6! \times (1 + 2) \\2167 &:= 7 + 6! \times (1 + 2) \\2168 &:= 8 + 6! \times (1 + 2) \\2169 &:= 9 + 6! \times (1 + 2)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2520 &:= 0 + (2 + 5)!/2 \\2521 &:= 1 + (2 + 5)!/2 \\2522 &:= 2 + (2 + 5)!/2 \\2523 &:= 3 + (2 + 5)!/2 \\2524 &:= 4 + (2 + 5)!/2 \\2525 &:= 5 + (2 + 5)!/2 \\2526 &:= 6 + (2 + 5)!/2 \\2527 &:= 7 + (2 + 5)!/2 \\2528 &:= 8 + (2 + 5)!/2 \\2529 &:= 9 + (2 + 5)!/2\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}3600 &:= 0 + (-0! + 6) \times 3!! \\3601 &:= 1 + (-0! + 6) \times 3!! \\3602 &:= 2 + (-0! + 6) \times 3!! \\3603 &:= 3 + (-0! + 6) \times 3!! \\3604 &:= 4 + (-0! + 6) \times 3!! \\3605 &:= 5 + (-0! + 6) \times 3!! \\3606 &:= 6 + (-0! + 6) \times 3!! \\3607 &:= 7 + (-0! + 6) \times 3!! \\3608 &:= 8 + (-0! + 6) \times 3!! \\3609 &:= 9 + (-0! + 6) \times 3!!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}7920 &:= 0 + (2 + 9)!/7! \\7921 &:= 1 + (2 + 9)!/7! \\7922 &:= 2 + (2 + 9)!/7! \\7923 &:= 3 + (2 + 9)!/7! \\7924 &:= 4 + (2 + 9)!/7! \\7925 &:= 5 + (2 + 9)!/7! \\7926 &:= 6 + (2 + 9)!/7!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}7927 &:= 7 + (2 + 9)!/7! \\7928 &:= 8 + (2 + 9)!/7! \\7929 &:= 9 + (2 + 9)!/7!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}00730 &:= 0 + 3^{7-0!} + 0! \\00731 &:= 1 + 3^{7-0!} + 0! \\00732 &:= 2 + 3^{7-0!} + 0! \\00733 &:= 3 + 3^{7-0!} + 0! \\00734 &:= 4 + 3^{7-0!} + 0! \\00735 &:= 5 + 3^{7-0!} + 0! \\00736 &:= 6 + 3^{7-0!} + 0! \\00737 &:= 7 + 3^{7-0!} + 0! \\00738 &:= 8 + 3^{7-0!} + 0! \\00739 &:= 9 + 3^{7-0!} + 0!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}01440 &:= 0 + (4!/4)! \times (1 + 0!) \\01441 &:= 1 + (4!/4)! \times (1 + 0!) \\01442 &:= 2 + (4!/4)! \times (1 + 0!) \\01443 &:= 3 + (4!/4)! \times (1 + 0!) \\01444 &:= 4 + (4!/4)! \times (1 + 0!) \\01445 &:= 5 + (4!/4)! \times (1 + 0!) \\01446 &:= 6 + (4!/4)! \times (1 + 0!) \\01447 &:= 7 + (4!/4)! \times (1 + 0!) \\01448 &:= 8 + (4!/4)! \times (1 + 0!) \\01449 &:= 9 + (4!/4)! \times (1 + 0!) \\01452 &:= 2 \times (5 + (4 - 1)!! + 0!)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}01680 &:= 0 + 8!/(-6 + 10)! \\01681 &:= 1 + 8!/(-6 + 10)! \\01682 &:= 2 + 8!/(-6 + 10)! \\01683 &:= 3 + 8!/(-6 + 10)! \\01684 &:= 4 + 8!/(-6 + 10)! \\01685 &:= 5 + 8!/(-6 + 10)! \\01686 &:= 6 + 8!/(-6 + 10)! \\01687 &:= 7 + 8!/(-6 + 10)! \\01688 &:= 8 + 8!/(-6 + 10)! \\01689 &:= 9 + 8!/(-6 + 10)!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}02400 &:= 0 + (0! + 4)! \times 20 \\02401 &:= 1 + (0! + 4)! \times 20 \\02402 &:= 2 + (0! + 4)! \times 20\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}02403 &:= 3 + (0! + 4)! \times 20 \\02404 &:= 4 + (0! + 4)! \times 20 \\02405 &:= 5 + (0! + 4)! \times 20 \\02406 &:= 6 + (0! + 4)! \times 20 \\02407 &:= 7 + (0! + 4)! \times 20 \\02408 &:= 8 + (0! + 4)! \times 20 \\02409 &:= 9 + (0! + 4)! \times 20\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}02880 &:= 0 + 8! / (8 + (2 + 0!)!) \\02881 &:= 1 + 8! / (8 + (2 + 0!)!) \\02882 &:= 2 + 8! / (8 + (2 + 0!)!) \\02883 &:= 3 + 8! / (8 + (2 + 0!)!) \\02884 &:= 4 + 8! / (8 + (2 + 0!)!) \\02885 &:= 5 + 8! / (8 + (2 + 0!)!) \\02886 &:= 6 + 8! / (8 + (2 + 0!)!) \\02887 &:= 7 + 8! / (8 + (2 + 0!)!) \\02888 &:= 8 + 8! / (8 + (2 + 0!)!) \\02889 &:= 9 + 8! / (8 + (2 + 0!)!)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}03590 &:= 0 - 9 + 5 \times 3!! - 0! \\03591 &:= 1 - 9 + 5 \times 3!! - 0! \\03592 &:= 2 - 9 + 5 \times 3!! - 0! \\03593 &:= 3 - 9 + 5 \times 3!! - 0! \\03594 &:= 4 - 9 + 5 \times 3!! - 0! \\03595 &:= 5 - 9 + 5 \times 3!! - 0! \\03596 &:= 6 - 9 + 5 \times 3!! - 0! \\03597 &:= 7 - 9 + 5 \times 3!! - 0! \\03598 &:= 8 - 9 + 5 \times 3!! - 0! \\03599 &:= 9 - 9 + 5 \times 3!! - 0!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}03600 &:= 0 + 06! \times (3! - 0!) \\03601 &:= 1 + 06! \times (3! - 0!) \\03602 &:= 2 + 06! \times (3! - 0!) \\03603 &:= 3 + 06! \times (3! - 0!) \\03604 &:= 4 + 06! \times (3! - 0!) \\03605 &:= 5 + 06! \times (3! - 0!) \\03606 &:= 6 + 06! \times (3! - 0!) \\03607 &:= 7 + 06! \times (3! - 0!) \\03608 &:= 8 + 06! \times (3! - 0!) \\03609 &:= 9 + 06! \times (3! - 0!)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}03840 &:= 0 + 4 \times 8 \times (3! - 0!)! \\03841 &:= 1 + 4 \times 8 \times (3! - 0!)! \\03842 &:= 2 + 4 \times 8 \times (3! - 0!)! \\03843 &:= 3 + 4 \times 8 \times (3! - 0!)! \\03844 &:= 4 + 4 \times 8 \times (3! - 0!)! \\03845 &:= 5 + 4 \times 8 \times (3! - 0!)! \\03846 &:= 6 + 4 \times 8 \times (3! - 0!)! \\03847 &:= 7 + 4 \times 8 \times (3! - 0!)! \\03848 &:= 8 + 4 \times 8 \times (3! - 0!)! \\03849 &:= 9 + 4 \times 8 \times (3! - 0!)!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}04350 &:= 0 + (5 + 3!!) \times (4 - 0!)! \\04351 &:= 1 + (5 + 3!!) \times (4 - 0!)! \\04352 &:= 2 + (5 + 3!!) \times (4 - 0!)! \\04353 &:= 3 + (5 + 3!!) \times (4 - 0!)! \\04354 &:= 4 + (5 + 3!!) \times (4 - 0!)! \\04355 &:= 5 + (5 + 3!!) \times (4 - 0!)! \\04356 &:= 6 + (5 + 3!!) \times (4 - 0!)! \\04357 &:= 7 + (5 + 3!!) \times (4 - 0!)! \\04358 &:= 8 + (5 + 3!!) \times (4 - 0!)! \\04359 &:= 9 + (5 + 3!!) \times (4 - 0!)!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}04360 &:= 0 + 6! \times 3! + 40 \\04361 &:= 1 + 6! \times 3! + 40 \\04362 &:= 2 + 6! \times 3! + 40 \\04363 &:= 3 + 6! \times 3! + 40 \\04364 &:= 4 + 6! \times 3! + 40 \\04365 &:= 5 + 6! \times 3! + 40 \\04366 &:= 6 + 6! \times 3! + 40 \\04367 &:= 7 + 6! \times 3! + 40 \\04368 &:= 8 + 6! \times 3! + 40 \\04369 &:= 9 + 6! \times 3! + 40\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}04480 &:= 0 + 8! / (4 + 4 + 0!) \\04481 &:= 1 + 8! / (4 + 4 + 0!) \\04482 &:= 2 + 8! / (4 + 4 + 0!) \\04483 &:= 3 + 8! / (4 + 4 + 0!) \\04484 &:= 4 + 8! / (4 + 4 + 0!) \\04485 &:= 5 + 8! / (4 + 4 + 0!) \\04486 &:= 6 + 8! / (4 + 4 + 0!) \\04487 &:= 7 + 8! / (4 + 4 + 0!) \\04488 &:= 8 + 8! / (4 + 4 + 0!)\end{aligned}$$

$$04489 := 9 + 8! / (4 + 4 + 0!)$$

$$04560 := 0 + (-6 + 5!) \times 40$$

$$04561 := 1 + (-6 + 5!) \times 40$$

$$04562 := 2 + (-6 + 5!) \times 40$$

$$04563 := 3 + (-6 + 5!) \times 40$$

$$04564 := 4 + (-6 + 5!) \times 40$$

$$04565 := 5 + (-6 + 5!) \times 40$$

$$04566 := 6 + (-6 + 5!) \times 40$$

$$04567 := 7 + (-6 + 5!) \times 40$$

$$04568 := 8 + (-6 + 5!) \times 40$$

$$04569 := 9 + (-6 + 5!) \times 40$$

$$05040 := 0 + (40/5 - 0)!$$

$$05041 := 1 + (40/5 - 0)!$$

$$05042 := 2 + (40/5 - 0)!$$

$$05043 := 3 + (40/5 - 0)!$$

$$05044 := 4 + (40/5 - 0)!$$

$$05045 := 5 + (40/5 - 0)!$$

$$05046 := 6 + (40/5 - 0)!$$

$$05047 := 7 + (40/5 - 0)!$$

$$05048 := 8 + (40/5 - 0)!$$

$$05049 := 9 + (40/5 - 0)!$$

$$05760 := 0 + 6! + (7 + 5 \times 0)!$$

$$05761 := 1 + 6! + (7 + 5 \times 0)!$$

$$05762 := 2 + 6! + (7 + 5 \times 0)!$$

$$05763 := 3 + 6! + (7 + 5 \times 0)!$$

$$05764 := 4 + 6! + (7 + 5 \times 0)!$$

$$05765 := 5 + 6! + (7 + 5 \times 0)!$$

$$05766 := 6 + 6! + (7 + 5 \times 0)!$$

$$05767 := 7 + 6! + (7 + 5 \times 0)!$$

$$05768 := 8 + 6! + (7 + 5 \times 0)!$$

$$05769 := 9 + 6! + (7 + 5 \times 0)!$$

$$06240 := 0 + 4! \times 260$$

$$06241 := 1 + 4! \times 260$$

$$06242 := 2 + 4! \times 260$$

$$06243 := 3 + 4! \times 260$$

$$06244 := 4 + 4! \times 260$$

$$06245 := 5 + 4! \times 260$$

$$06246 := 6 + 4! \times 260$$

$$06247 := 7 + 4! \times 260$$

$$06248 := 8 + 4! \times 260$$

$$06249 := 9 + 4! \times 260$$

$$09360 := 0 + 6! \times (3 + 9 + 0!)$$

$$09361 := 1 + 6! \times (3 + 9 + 0!)$$

$$09362 := 2 + 6! \times (3 + 9 + 0!)$$

$$09363 := 3 + 6! \times (3 + 9 + 0!)$$

$$09364 := 4 + 6! \times (3 + 9 + 0!)$$

$$09365 := 5 + 6! \times (3 + 9 + 0!)$$

$$09366 := 6 + 6! \times (3 + 9 + 0!)$$

$$09367 := 7 + 6! \times (3 + 9 + 0!)$$

$$09368 := 8 + 6! \times (3 + 9 + 0!)$$

$$09369 := 9 + 6! \times (3 + 9 + 0!)$$

$$10080 := 0 + (8 - 0)! \times (0! + 1)$$

$$10081 := 1 + (8 - 0)! \times (0! + 1)$$

$$10082 := 2 + (8 - 0)! \times (0! + 1)$$

$$10083 := 3 + (8 - 0)! \times (0! + 1)$$

$$10084 := 4 + (8 - 0)! \times (0! + 1)$$

$$10085 := 5 + (8 - 0)! \times (0! + 1)$$

$$10086 := 6 + (8 - 0)! \times (0! + 1)$$

$$10087 := 7 + (8 - 0)! \times (0! + 1)$$

$$10088 := 8 + (8 - 0)! \times (0! + 1)$$

$$10089 := 9 + (8 - 0)! \times (0! + 1)$$

$$12960 := 0 + 6! \times 9 \times 2 \times 1$$

$$12961 := 1 + 6! \times 9 \times 2 \times 1$$

$$12962 := 2 + 6! \times 9 \times 2 \times 1$$

$$12963 := 3 + 6! \times 9 \times 2 \times 1$$

$$12964 := 4 + 6! \times 9 \times 2 \times 1$$

$$12965 := 5 + 6! \times 9 \times 2 \times 1$$

$$12966 := 6 + 6! \times 9 \times 2 \times 1$$

$$12967 := 7 + 6! \times 9 \times 2 \times 1$$

$$12968 := 8 + 6! \times 9 \times 2 \times 1$$

$$12969 := 9 + 6! \times 9 \times 2 \times 1$$

$$13440 := 0 + (4 + 4)! / 3 \times 1$$

$$13441 := 1 + (4 + 4)! / 3 \times 1$$

$$13442 := 2 + (4 + 4)! / 3 \times 1$$

$$13443 := 3 + (4 + 4)! / 3 \times 1$$

$$\begin{aligned}13444 &:= 4 + (4 + 4)!/3 \times 1 \\13445 &:= 5 + (4 + 4)!/3 \times 1 \\13446 &:= 6 + (4 + 4)!/3 \times 1 \\13447 &:= 7 + (4 + 4)!/3 \times 1 \\13448 &:= 8 + (4 + 4)!/3 \times 1 \\13449 &:= 9 + (4 + 4)!/3 \times 1\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}13680 &:= 0 + (8! + 6!)/3 \times 1 \\13681 &:= 1 + (8! + 6!)/3 \times 1 \\13682 &:= 2 + (8! + 6!)/3 \times 1 \\13683 &:= 3 + (8! + 6!)/3 \times 1 \\13684 &:= 4 + (8! + 6!)/3 \times 1 \\13685 &:= 5 + (8! + 6!)/3 \times 1 \\13686 &:= 6 + (8! + 6!)/3 \times 1 \\13687 &:= 7 + (8! + 6!)/3 \times 1 \\13688 &:= 8 + (8! + 6!)/3 \times 1 \\13689 &:= 9 + (8! + 6!)/3 \times 1\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}14400 &:= 0 + (0! + 4)! \times (4 + 1)! \\14401 &:= 1 + (0! + 4)! \times (4 + 1)! \\14402 &:= 2 + (0! + 4)! \times (4 + 1)! \\14403 &:= 3 + (0! + 4)! \times (4 + 1)! \\14404 &:= 4 + (0! + 4)! \times (4 + 1)! \\14405 &:= 5 + (0! + 4)! \times (4 + 1)! \\14406 &:= 6 + (0! + 4)! \times (4 + 1)! \\14407 &:= 7 + (0! + 4)! \times (4 + 1)! \\14408 &:= 8 + (0! + 4)! \times (4 + 1)! \\14409 &:= 9 + (0! + 4)! \times (4 + 1)!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}15120 &:= 0 + 21 \times (5 + 1)! \\15121 &:= 1 + 21 \times (5 + 1)! \\15122 &:= 2 + 21 \times (5 + 1)! \\15123 &:= 3 + 21 \times (5 + 1)! \\15124 &:= 4 + 21 \times (5 + 1)! \\15125 &:= 5 + 21 \times (5 + 1)! \\15126 &:= 6 + 21 \times (5 + 1)! \\15127 &:= 7 + 21 \times (5 + 1)! \\15128 &:= 8 + 21 \times (5 + 1)! \\15129 &:= 9 + 21 \times (5 + 1)!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}17280 &:= 0 + (8/2)! \times (7 - 1)! \\17281 &:= 1 + (8/2)! \times (7 - 1)! \\17282 &:= 2 + (8/2)! \times (7 - 1)! \\17283 &:= 3 + (8/2)! \times (7 - 1)! \\17284 &:= 4 + (8/2)! \times (7 - 1)! \\17285 &:= 5 + (8/2)! \times (7 - 1)! \\17286 &:= 6 + (8/2)! \times (7 - 1)! \\17287 &:= 7 + (8/2)! \times (7 - 1)! \\17288 &:= 8 + (8/2)! \times (7 - 1)! \\17289 &:= 9 + (8/2)! \times (7 - 1)!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}20160 &:= 0 + (6 + 1 + 0)!/2 \\20161 &:= 1 + (6 + 1 + 0)!/2 \\20162 &:= 2 + (6 + 1 + 0)!/2 \\20163 &:= 3 + (6 + 1 + 0)!/2 \\20164 &:= 4 + (6 + 1 + 0)!/2 \\20165 &:= 5 + (6 + 1 + 0)!/2 \\20166 &:= 6 + (6 + 1 + 0)!/2 \\20167 &:= 7 + (6 + 1 + 0)!/2 \\20168 &:= 8 + (6 + 1 + 0)!/2 \\20169 &:= 9 + (6 + 1 + 0)!/2\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}23040 &:= 0 + (4 - 0)!! \times 32 \\23041 &:= 1 + (4 - 0)!! \times 32 \\23042 &:= 2 + (4 - 0)!! \times 32 \\23043 &:= 3 + (4 - 0)!! \times 32 \\23044 &:= 4 + (4 - 0)!! \times 32 \\23045 &:= 5 + (4 - 0)!! \times 32 \\23046 &:= 6 + (4 - 0)!! \times 32 \\23047 &:= 7 + (4 - 0)!! \times 32 \\23048 &:= 8 + (4 - 0)!! \times 32 \\23049 &:= 9 + (4 - 0)!! \times 32\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}23340 &:= 0 + (4! + 3!^{3!})/2 \\23341 &:= 1 + (4! + 3!^{3!})/2 \\23342 &:= 2 + (4! + 3!^{3!})/2 \\23343 &:= 3 + (4! + 3!^{3!})/2 \\23344 &:= 3 + (4! + 3!^{3!})/2 \\23345 &:= 5 + (4! + 3!^{3!})/2 \\23346 &:= 6 + (4! + 3!^{3!})/2\end{aligned}$$

$$23347 := 7 + (4! + 3!^{3!})/2$$

$$23348 := 8 + (4! + 3!^{3!})/2$$

$$23349 := 9 + (4! + 3!^{3!})/2$$

$$26880 := 0 + 8 \times 8!/(6 \times 2)$$

$$26881 := 1 + 8 \times 8!/(6 \times 2)$$

$$26882 := 2 + 8 \times 8!/(6 \times 2)$$

$$26883 := 3 + 8 \times 8!/(6 \times 2)$$

$$26884 := 4 + 8 \times 8!/(6 \times 2)$$

$$26885 := 5 + 8 \times 8!/(6 \times 2)$$

$$26886 := 6 + 8 \times 8!/(6 \times 2)$$

$$26887 := 7 + 8 \times 8!/(6 \times 2)$$

$$26888 := 8 + 8 \times 8!/(6 \times 2)$$

$$26889 := 9 + 8 \times 8!/(6 \times 2)$$

$$30240 := 0 + 42 \times (0 + 3!!)$$

$$30241 := 1 + 42 \times (0 + 3!!)$$

$$30242 := 2 + 42 \times (0 + 3!!)$$

$$30243 := 3 + 42 \times (0 + 3!!)$$

$$30244 := 4 + 42 \times (0 + 3!!)$$

$$30245 := 5 + 42 \times (0 + 3!!)$$

$$30246 := 6 + 42 \times (0 + 3!!)$$

$$30247 := 7 + 42 \times (0 + 3!!)$$

$$30248 := 8 + 42 \times (0 + 3!!)$$

$$30249 := 9 + 42 \times (0 + 3!!)$$

$$33840 := 0 + 48 \times 3!! - 3!!$$

$$33841 := 1 + 48 \times 3!! - 3!!$$

$$33842 := 2 + 48 \times 3!! - 3!!$$

$$33843 := 3 + 48 \times 3!! - 3!!$$

$$33844 := 4 + 48 \times 3!! - 3!!$$

$$33845 := 5 + 48 \times 3!! - 3!!$$

$$33846 := 6 + 48 \times 3!! - 3!!$$

$$33847 := 7 + 48 \times 3!! - 3!!$$

$$33848 := 8 + 48 \times 3!! - 3!!$$

$$33849 := 9 + 48 \times 3!! - 3!!$$

$$34560 := 0 + 6! \times (5 + 43)$$

$$34561 := 1 + 6! \times (5 + 43)$$

$$34562 := 2 + 6! \times (5 + 43)$$

$$34563 := 3 + 6! \times (5 + 43)$$

$$34564 := 4 + 6! \times (5 + 43)$$

$$34565 := 5 + 6! \times (5 + 43)$$

$$34566 := 6 + 6! \times (5 + 43)$$

$$34567 := 7 + 6! \times (5 + 43)$$

$$34568 := 8 + 6! \times (5 + 43)$$

$$34569 := 9 + 6! \times (5 + 43)$$

$$35280 := 0 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)!$$

$$35281 := 1 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)!$$

$$35282 := 2 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)!$$

$$35283 := 3 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)!$$

$$35284 := 4 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)!$$

$$35285 := 5 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)!$$

$$35286 := 6 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)!$$

$$35287 := 7 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)!$$

$$35288 := 8 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)!$$

$$35289 := 9 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)!$$

$$37440 := 0 + (4! + 4 \times 7) \times 3!!$$

$$37441 := 1 + (4! + 4 \times 7) \times 3!!$$

$$37442 := 2 + (4! + 4 \times 7) \times 3!!$$

$$37443 := 3 + (4! + 4 \times 7) \times 3!!$$

$$37444 := 4 + (4! + 4 \times 7) \times 3!!$$

$$37445 := 5 + (4! + 4 \times 7) \times 3!!$$

$$37446 := 6 + (4! + 4 \times 7) \times 3!!$$

$$37447 := 7 + (4! + 4 \times 7) \times 3!!$$

$$37448 := 8 + (4! + 4 \times 7) \times 3!!$$

$$37449 := 9 + (4! + 4 \times 7) \times 3!!$$

$$37464 := 4! + 6! \times 4 \times (7 + 3!)$$

$$38160 := 0 + (61 - 8) \times 3!!$$

$$38161 := 1 + (61 - 8) \times 3!!$$

$$38162 := 2 + (61 - 8) \times 3!!$$

$$38163 := 3 + (61 - 8) \times 3!!$$

$$38164 := 4 + (61 - 8) \times 3!!$$

$$38165 := 5 + (61 - 8) \times 3!!$$

$$38166 := 6 + (61 - 8) \times 3!!$$

$$38167 := 7 + (61 - 8) \times 3!!$$

$$38168 := 8 + (61 - 8) \times 3!!$$

$$38169 := 9 + (61 - 8) \times 3!!$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39600 &:= 0 + (0! + 6 \times 9) \times 3!! \\ 39601 &:= 1 + (0! + 6 \times 9) \times 3!! \\ 39602 &:= 2 + (0! + 6 \times 9) \times 3!! \\ 39603 &:= 3 + (0! + 6 \times 9) \times 3!! \\ 39604 &:= 4 + (0! + 6 \times 9) \times 3!! \\ 39605 &:= 5 + (0! + 6 \times 9) \times 3!! \\ 39606 &:= 6 + (0! + 6 \times 9) \times 3!! \\ 39607 &:= 7 + (0! + 6 \times 9) \times 3!! \\ 39608 &:= 8 + (0! + 6 \times 9) \times 3!! \\ 39609 &:= 9 + (0! + 6 \times 9) \times 3!! \\ 39636 &:= 6 \times (3! + 6! \times 9) + 3!! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39680 &:= 0 + 8! + 6!/9 - 3!! \\ 39681 &:= 1 + 8! + 6!/9 - 3!! \\ 39682 &:= 2 + 8! + 6!/9 - 3!! \\ 39683 &:= 3 + 8! + 6!/9 - 3!! \\ 39684 &:= 4 + 8! + 6!/9 - 3!! \\ 39685 &:= 5 + 8! + 6!/9 - 3!! \\ 39686 &:= 6 + 8! + 6!/9 - 3!! \\ 39687 &:= 7 + 8! + 6!/9 - 3!! \\ 39688 &:= 8 + 8! + 6!/9 - 3!! \\ 39689 &:= 9 + 8! + 6!/9 - 3!! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39840 &:= 0 + 4! + 8! - 9!/3!! \\ 39841 &:= 1 + 4! + 8! - 9!/3!! \\ 39842 &:= 2 + 4! + 8! - 9!/3!! \\ 39843 &:= 3 + 4! + 8! - 9!/3!! \\ 39844 &:= 4 + 4! + 8! - 9!/3!! \\ 39845 &:= 5 + 4! + 8! - 9!/3!! \\ 39846 &:= 6 + 4! + 8! - 9!/3!! \\ 39847 &:= 7 + 4! + 8! - 9!/3!! \\ 39848 &:= 8 + 4! + 8! - 9!/3!! \\ 39849 &:= 9 + 4! + 8! - 9!/3!! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 40320 &:= 0 + ((2 + 30)/4)! \\ 40321 &:= 1 + ((2 + 30)/4)! \\ 40322 &:= 2 + ((2 + 30)/4)! \\ 40323 &:= 3 + ((2 + 30)/4)! \\ 40324 &:= 4 + ((2 + 30)/4)! \\ 40325 &:= 5 + ((2 + 30)/4)! \\ 40326 &:= 6 + ((2 + 30)/4)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 40327 &:= 7 + ((2 + 30)/4)! \\ 40328 &:= 8 + ((2 + 30)/4)! \\ 40329 &:= 9 + ((2 + 30)/4)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 40480 &:= 0 + 8! + 40 \times 4 \\ 40481 &:= 1 + 8! + 40 \times 4 \\ 40482 &:= 2 + 8! + 40 \times 4 \\ 40483 &:= 3 + 8! + 40 \times 4 \\ 40484 &:= 4 + 8! + 40 \times 4 \\ 40485 &:= 5 + 8! + 40 \times 4 \\ 40486 &:= 6 + 8! + 40 \times 4 \\ 40487 &:= 7 + 8! + 40 \times 4 \\ 40488 &:= 8 + 8! + 40 \times 4 \\ 40489 &:= 9 + 8! + 40 \times 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 48960 &:= 1 + 6! \times (9 \times 8 - 4) \\ 48961 &:= 1 + 6! \times (9 \times 8 - 4) \\ 48962 &:= 2 + 6! \times (9 \times 8 - 4) \\ 48963 &:= 3 + 6! \times (9 \times 8 - 4) \\ 48964 &:= 4 + 6! \times (9 \times 8 - 4) \\ 48965 &:= 5 + 6! \times (9 \times 8 - 4) \\ 48966 &:= 6 + 6! \times (9 \times 8 - 4) \\ 48967 &:= 7 + 6! \times (9 \times 8 - 4) \\ 48968 &:= 8 + 6! \times (9 \times 8 - 4) \\ 48969 &:= 9 + 6! \times (9 \times 8 - 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 49680 &:= 0 + 8! + 6! \times (9 + 4) \\ 49681 &:= 1 + 8! + 6! \times (9 + 4) \\ 49682 &:= 2 + 8! + 6! \times (9 + 4) \\ 49683 &:= 3 + 8! + 6! \times (9 + 4) \\ 49684 &:= 4 + 8! + 6! \times (9 + 4) \\ 49685 &:= 5 + 8! + 6! \times (9 + 4) \\ 49686 &:= 6 + 8! + 6! \times (9 + 4) \\ 49687 &:= 7 + 8! + 6! \times (9 + 4) \\ 49688 &:= 8 + 8! + 6! \times (9 + 4) \\ 49689 &:= 9 + 8! + 6! \times (9 + 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 53240 &:= 0 + (4! - 2)^3 \times 5 \\ 53241 &:= 1 + (4! - 2)^3 \times 5 \\ 53242 &:= 2 + (4! - 2)^3 \times 5 \\ 53243 &:= 3 + (4! - 2)^3 \times 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}53244 &:= 4 + (4! - 2)^3 \times 5 \\53245 &:= 5 + (4! - 2)^3 \times 5 \\53246 &:= 6 + (4! - 2)^3 \times 5 \\53247 &:= 7 + (4! - 2)^3 \times 5 \\53248 &:= 8 + (4! - 2)^3 \times 5 \\53249 &:= 9 + (4! - 2)^3 \times 5\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}53880 &:= 0 + 8! + 8!/3 + 5! \\53881 &:= 1 + 8! + 8!/3 + 5! \\53882 &:= 2 + 8! + 8!/3 + 5! \\53883 &:= 3 + 8! + 8!/3 + 5! \\53884 &:= 4 + 8! + 8!/3 + 5! \\53885 &:= 5 + 8! + 8!/3 + 5! \\53886 &:= 6 + 8! + 8!/3 + 5! \\53887 &:= 7 + 8! + 8!/3 + 5! \\53888 &:= 8 + 8! + 8!/3 + 5! \\53889 &:= 9 + 8! + 8!/3 + 5!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}57961 &:= 1 + 69 \times 7 \times 5! \\57962 &:= 2 + 69 \times 7 \times 5! \\57963 &:= 3 + 69 \times 7 \times 5! \\57964 &:= 4 + 69 \times 7 \times 5! \\57965 &:= 5 + 69 \times 7 \times 5! \\57966 &:= 6 + 69 \times 7 \times 5! \\57967 &:= 7 + 69 \times 7 \times 5! \\57968 &:= 8 + 69 \times 7 \times 5! \\57969 &:= 9 + 69 \times 7 \times 5!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}59050 &:= 0 + (5 \times 0)! + 9^5 \\59051 &:= 1 + (5 \times 0)! + 9^5 \\59053 &:= 3 + (5 \times 0)! + 9^5 \\59054 &:= 4 + (5 \times 0)! + 9^5 \\59055 &:= 5 + (5 \times 0)! + 9^5 \\59056 &:= 6 + (5 \times 0)! + 9^5 \\59057 &:= 7 + (5 \times 0)! + 9^5 \\59058 &:= 8 + (5 \times 0)! + 9^5 \\59059 &:= 9 + (5 \times 0)! + 9^5\end{aligned}$$

$$60480 := 0 + 84 \times (0 + 6!)$$

$$\begin{aligned}60481 &:= 1 + 84 \times (0 + 6!) \\60482 &:= 2 + 84 \times (0 + 6!) \\60483 &:= 3 + 84 \times (0 + 6!) \\60484 &:= 4 + 84 \times (0 + 6!) \\60485 &:= 5 + 84 \times (0 + 6!) \\60486 &:= 6 + 84 \times (0 + 6!) \\60487 &:= 7 + 84 \times (0 + 6!) \\60488 &:= 8 + 84 \times (0 + 6!) \\60489 &:= 9 + 84 \times (0 + 6!)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}64840 &:= 0 + 4^8 + 4! - 6! \\64841 &:= 1 + 4^8 + 4! - 6! \\64842 &:= 2 + 4^8 + 4! - 6! \\64843 &:= 3 + 4^8 + 4! - 6! \\64844 &:= 4 + 4^8 + 4! - 6! \\64845 &:= 5 + 4^8 + 4! - 6! \\64847 &:= 7 + 4^8 + 4! - 6! \\64848 &:= 8 + 4^8 + 4! - 6! \\64849 &:= 9 + 4^8 + 4! - 6!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}69120 &:= 0 + (2 + 1)!! \times 96 \\69121 &:= 1 + (2 + 1)!! \times 96 \\69122 &:= 2 + (2 + 1)!! \times 96 \\69123 &:= 3 + (2 + 1)!! \times 96 \\69124 &:= 4 + (2 + 1)!! \times 96 \\69125 &:= 5 + (2 + 1)!! \times 96 \\69126 &:= 6 + (2 + 1)!! \times 96 \\69127 &:= 7 + (2 + 1)!! \times 96 \\69128 &:= 8 + (2 + 1)!! \times 96 \\69129 &:= 9 + (2 + 1)!! \times 96\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}72590 &:= 0 + 9!/5 + 2 \times 7 \\72591 &:= 1 + 9!/5 + 2 \times 7 \\72592 &:= 2 + 9!/5 + 2 \times 7 \\72593 &:= 3 + 9!/5 + 2 \times 7 \\72594 &:= 4 + 9!/5 + 2 \times 7 \\72595 &:= 5 + 9!/5 + 2 \times 7 \\72596 &:= 6 + 9!/5 + 2 \times 7 \\72597 &:= 7 + 9!/5 + 2 \times 7 \\72598 &:= 8 + 9!/5 + 2 \times 7 \\72599 &:= 9 + 9!/5 + 2 \times 7\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 80640 &:= 0 + (-4 + 6) \times (0 + 8!) \\ 80641 &:= 1 + (-4 + 6) \times (0 + 8!) \\ 80642 &:= 2 + (-4 + 6) \times (0 + 8!) \\ 80643 &:= 3 + (-4 + 6) \times (0 + 8!) \\ 80644 &:= 4 + (-4 + 6) \times (0 + 8!) \\ 80645 &:= 5 + (-4 + 6) \times (0 + 8!) \\ 80646 &:= 6 + (-4 + 6) \times (0 + 8!) \\ 80647 &:= 7 + (-4 + 6) \times (0 + 8!) \\ 80648 &:= 8 + (-4 + 6) \times (0 + 8!) \\ 80649 &:= 9 + (-4 + 6) \times (0 + 8!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 81360 &:= 0 + 6! + (3 - 1) \times 8! \\ 81361 &:= 1 + 6! + (3 - 1) \times 8! \\ 81362 &:= 2 + 6! + (3 - 1) \times 8! \\ 81363 &:= 3 + 6! + (3 - 1) \times 8! \\ 81364 &:= 4 + 6! + (3 - 1) \times 8! \\ 81365 &:= 5 + 6! + (3 - 1) \times 8! \\ 81366 &:= 6 + 6! + (3 - 1) \times 8! \\ 81367 &:= 7 + 6! + (3 - 1) \times 8! \\ 81368 &:= 8 + 6! + (3 - 1) \times 8! \\ 81369 &:= 9 + 6! + (3 - 1) \times 8! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 90720 &:= 0 + 2 \times 7! \times (0 + 9) \\ 90721 &:= 1 + 2 \times 7! \times (0 + 9) \\ 90722 &:= 2 + 2 \times 7! \times (0 + 9) \\ 90723 &:= 3 + 2 \times 7! \times (0 + 9) \\ 90724 &:= 4 + 2 \times 7! \times (0 + 9) \\ 90725 &:= 5 + 2 \times 7! \times (0 + 9) \\ 90726 &:= 6 + 2 \times 7! \times (0 + 9) \\ 90727 &:= 7 + 2 \times 7! \times (0 + 9) \\ 90728 &:= 8 + 2 \times 7! \times (0 + 9) \\ 90729 &:= 9 + 2 \times 7! \times (0 + 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 115920 &:= 0 + (-2 + 9)! \times ((5 - 1)! - 1) \\ 115921 &:= 1 + (-2 + 9)! \times ((5 - 1)! - 1) \\ 115922 &:= 2 + (-2 + 9)! \times ((5 - 1)! - 1) \\ 115923 &:= 3 + (-2 + 9)! \times ((5 - 1)! - 1) \\ 115924 &:= 4 + (-2 + 9)! \times ((5 - 1)! - 1) \\ 115925 &:= 5 + (-2 + 9)! \times ((5 - 1)! - 1) \\ 115926 &:= 6 + (-2 + 9)! \times ((5 - 1)! - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 115927 &:= 7 + (-2 + 9)! \times ((5 - 1)! - 1) \\ 115928 &:= 8 + (-2 + 9)! \times ((5 - 1)! - 1) \\ 115929 &:= 9 + (-2 + 9)! \times ((5 - 1)! - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 120960 &:= 0 + 6! \times (9 - 0!) \times 21 \\ 120961 &:= 1 + 6! \times (9 - 0!) \times 21 \\ 120962 &:= 2 + 6! \times (9 - 0!) \times 21 \\ 120963 &:= 3 + 6! \times (9 - 0!) \times 21 \\ 120964 &:= 4 + 6! \times (9 - 0!) \times 21 \\ 120965 &:= 5 + 6! \times (9 - 0!) \times 21 \\ 120966 &:= 6 + 6! \times (9 - 0!) \times 21 \\ 120967 &:= 7 + 6! \times (9 - 0!) \times 21 \\ 120968 &:= 8 + 6! \times (9 - 0!) \times 21 \\ 120969 &:= 9 + 6! \times (9 - 0!) \times 21 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 120990 &:= 0 + (9! + 90) / (2 + 1) \\ 120991 &:= 1 + (9! + 90) / (2 + 1) \\ 120992 &:= 2 + (9! + 90) / (2 + 1) \\ 120993 &:= 3 + (9! + 90) / (2 + 1) \\ 120994 &:= 4 + (9! + 90) / (2 + 1) \\ 120995 &:= 5 + (9! + 90) / (2 + 1) \\ 120996 &:= 6 + (9! + 90) / (2 + 1) \\ 120997 &:= 7 + (9! + 90) / (2 + 1) \\ 120998 &:= 8 + (9! + 90) / (2 + 1) \\ 120999 &:= 9 + (9! + 90) / (2 + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 122880 &:= 0 + 8! \times 8^2 / 21 \\ 122881 &:= 1 + 8! \times 8^2 / 21 \\ 122882 &:= 2 + 8! \times 8^2 / 21 \\ 122883 &:= 3 + 8! \times 8^2 / 21 \\ 122884 &:= 4 + 8! \times 8^2 / 21 \\ 122885 &:= 5 + 8! \times 8^2 / 21 \\ 122886 &:= 6 + 8! \times 8^2 / 21 \\ 122887 &:= 7 + 8! \times 8^2 / 21 \\ 122888 &:= 8 + 8! \times 8^2 / 21 \\ 122889 &:= 9 + 8! \times 8^2 / 21 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 125280 &:= 0 + 8! + (-2 + 5!) \times (2 + 1)!! \\ 125281 &:= 1 + 8! + (-2 + 5!) \times (2 + 1)!! \\ 125282 &:= 2 + 8! + (-2 + 5!) \times (2 + 1)!! \\ 125283 &:= 3 + 8! + (-2 + 5!) \times (2 + 1)!! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}125284 &:= 4 + 8! + (-2 + 5!) \times (2 + 1)!! \\125285 &:= 5 + 8! + (-2 + 5!) \times (2 + 1)!! \\125286 &:= 6 + 8! + (-2 + 5!) \times (2 + 1)!! \\125287 &:= 7 + 8! + (-2 + 5!) \times (2 + 1)!! \\125288 &:= 8 + 8! + (-2 + 5!) \times (2 + 1)!! \\125289 &:= 9 + 8! + (-2 + 5!) \times (2 + 1)!!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}131040 &:= 0 + (4! + 0! + 1) \times (3! + 1)! \\131041 &:= 1 + (4! + 0! + 1) \times (3! + 1)! \\131042 &:= 2 + (4! + 0! + 1) \times (3! + 1)! \\131043 &:= 3 + (4! + 0! + 1) \times (3! + 1)! \\131044 &:= 4 + (4! + 0! + 1) \times (3! + 1)! \\131045 &:= 5 + (4! + 0! + 1) \times (3! + 1)! \\131046 &:= 6 + (4! + 0! + 1) \times (3! + 1)! \\131047 &:= 7 + (4! + 0! + 1) \times (3! + 1)! \\131048 &:= 8 + (4! + 0! + 1) \times (3! + 1)! \\131049 &:= 9 + (4! + 0! + 1) \times (3! + 1)!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}136080 &:= 0 + (8! + (0! + 6!)) \times 3 \times 1 \\136081 &:= 1 + (8! + (0! + 6!)) \times 3 \times 1 \\136082 &:= 2 + (8! + (0! + 6!)) \times 3 \times 1 \\136083 &:= 3 + (8! + (0! + 6!)) \times 3 \times 1 \\136084 &:= 4 + (8! + (0! + 6!)) \times 3 \times 1 \\136085 &:= 5 + (8! + (0! + 6!)) \times 3 \times 1 \\136086 &:= 6 + (8! + (0! + 6!)) \times 3 \times 1 \\136087 &:= 7 + (8! + (0! + 6!)) \times 3 \times 1 \\136088 &:= 8 + (8! + (0! + 6!)) \times 3 \times 1 \\136089 &:= 9 + (8! + (0! + 6!)) \times 3 \times 1\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}138240 &:= 0 + (4 + 2)! \times 8 \times (3 + 1)! \\138241 &:= 1 + (4 + 2)! \times 8 \times (3 + 1)! \\138242 &:= 2 + (4 + 2)! \times 8 \times (3 + 1)! \\138243 &:= 3 + (4 + 2)! \times 8 \times (3 + 1)! \\138244 &:= 4 + (4 + 2)! \times 8 \times (3 + 1)! \\138245 &:= 5 + (4 + 2)! \times 8 \times (3 + 1)! \\138246 &:= 6 + (4 + 2)! \times 8 \times (3 + 1)! \\138247 &:= 7 + (4 + 2)! \times 8 \times (3 + 1)! \\138248 &:= 8 + (4 + 2)! \times 8 \times (3 + 1)! \\138249 &:= 9 + (4 + 2)! \times 8 \times (3 + 1)!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}146160 &:= 0 + (6 + 1)! \times (6!/4! - 1) \\146161 &:= 1 + (6 + 1)! \times (6!/4! - 1) \\146162 &:= 2 + (6 + 1)! \times (6!/4! - 1) \\146163 &:= 3 + (6 + 1)! \times (6!/4! - 1) \\146164 &:= 4 + (6 + 1)! \times (6!/4! - 1) \\146165 &:= 5 + (6 + 1)! \times (6!/4! - 1) \\146166 &:= 6 + (6 + 1)! \times (6!/4! - 1) \\146167 &:= 7 + (6 + 1)! \times (6!/4! - 1) \\146168 &:= 8 + (6 + 1)! \times (6!/4! - 1) \\146169 &:= 9 + (6 + 1)! \times (6!/4! - 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}149040 &:= 0 + (4! - 0!) \times 9 \times (4 - 1)!! \\149041 &:= 1 + (4! - 0!) \times 9 \times (4 - 1)!! \\149042 &:= 2 + (4! - 0!) \times 9 \times (4 - 1)!! \\149043 &:= 3 + (4! - 0!) \times 9 \times (4 - 1)!! \\149044 &:= 4 + (4! - 0!) \times 9 \times (4 - 1)!! \\149045 &:= 5 + (4! - 0!) \times 9 \times (4 - 1)!! \\149046 &:= 6 + (4! - 0!) \times 9 \times (4 - 1)!! \\149047 &:= 7 + (4! - 0!) \times 9 \times (4 - 1)!! \\149048 &:= 8 + (4! - 0!) \times 9 \times (4 - 1)!! \\149049 &:= 9 + (4! - 0!) \times 9 \times (4 - 1)!!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}149640 &:= 0 - (4! - 6!) \times (9 \times 4! - 1) \\149641 &:= 1 - (4! - 6!) \times (9 \times 4! - 1) \\149642 &:= 2 - (4! - 6!) \times (9 \times 4! - 1) \\149643 &:= 3 - (4! - 6!) \times (9 \times 4! - 1) \\149644 &:= 4 - (4! - 6!) \times (9 \times 4! - 1) \\149645 &:= 5 - (4! - 6!) \times (9 \times 4! - 1) \\149646 &:= 6 - (4! - 6!) \times (9 \times 4! - 1) \\149647 &:= 7 - (4! - 6!) \times (9 \times 4! - 1) \\149648 &:= 8 - (4! - 6!) \times (9 \times 4! - 1) \\149649 &:= 9 - (4! - 6!) \times (9 \times 4! - 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}149760 &:= 0 + 6! \times (-7 + 9 \times 4! - 1) \\149761 &:= 1 + 6! \times (-7 + 9 \times 4! - 1) \\149762 &:= 2 + 6! \times (-7 + 9 \times 4! - 1) \\149763 &:= 3 + 6! \times (-7 + 9 \times 4! - 1) \\149764 &:= 4 + 6! \times (-7 + 9 \times 4! - 1) \\149765 &:= 5 + 6! \times (-7 + 9 \times 4! - 1) \\149766 &:= 6 + 6! \times (-7 + 9 \times 4! - 1) \\149767 &:= 7 + 6! \times (-7 + 9 \times 4! - 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$149768 := 8 + 6! \times (-7 + 9 \times 4! - 1)$$
$$149769 := 9 + 6! \times (-7 + 9 \times 4! - 1)$$

$$152640 := 0 + 4 \times 6! \times (2 + 51)$$
$$152641 := 1 + 4 \times 6! \times (2 + 51)$$
$$152642 := 2 + 4 \times 6! \times (2 + 51)$$
$$152643 := 3 + 4 \times 6! \times (2 + 51)$$
$$152644 := 4 + 4 \times 6! \times (2 + 51)$$
$$152645 := 5 + 4 \times 6! \times (2 + 51)$$
$$152646 := 6 + 4 \times 6! \times (2 + 51)$$
$$152647 := 7 + 4 \times 6! \times (2 + 51)$$
$$152648 := 8 + 4 \times 6! \times (2 + 51)$$
$$152649 := 9 + 4 \times 6! \times (2 + 51)$$

$$152880 := 0 + (8! + (8 + 2)!)/(5 - 1)!$$
$$152881 := 1 + (8! + (8 + 2)!)/(5 - 1)!$$
$$152882 := 2 + (8! + (8 + 2)!)/(5 - 1)!$$
$$152883 := 3 + (8! + (8 + 2)!)/(5 - 1)!$$
$$152884 := 4 + (8! + (8 + 2)!)/(5 - 1)!$$
$$152885 := 5 + (8! + (8 + 2)!)/(5 - 1)!$$
$$152886 := 6 + (8! + (8 + 2)!)/(5 - 1)!$$
$$152887 := 7 + (8! + (8 + 2)!)/(5 - 1)!$$
$$152888 := 8 + (8! + (8 + 2)!)/(5 - 1)!$$
$$152889 := 9 + (8! + (8 + 2)!)/(5 - 1)!$$

$$153360 := 0 + (6^3 - 3) \times (5 + 1)!$$
$$153361 := 1 + (6^3 - 3) \times (5 + 1)!$$
$$153362 := 2 + (6^3 - 3) \times (5 + 1)!$$
$$153363 := 3 + (6^3 - 3) \times (5 + 1)!$$
$$153364 := 4 + (6^3 - 3) \times (5 + 1)!$$
$$153365 := 5 + (6^3 - 3) \times (5 + 1)!$$
$$153366 := 6 + (6^3 - 3) \times (5 + 1)!$$
$$153367 := 7 + (6^3 - 3) \times (5 + 1)!$$
$$153368 := 8 + (6^3 - 3) \times (5 + 1)!$$
$$153369 := 9 + (6^3 - 3) \times (5 + 1)!$$

$$158400 := 0 + 04 \times (8! - (5 + 1)!)$$
$$158401 := 1 + 04 \times (8! - (5 + 1)!)$$
$$158402 := 2 + 04 \times (8! - (5 + 1)!)$$
$$158403 := 3 + 04 \times (8! - (5 + 1)!)$$

$$158404 := 4 + 04 \times (8! - (5 + 1)!)$$
$$158405 := 5 + 04 \times (8! - (5 + 1)!)$$
$$158406 := 6 + 04 \times (8! - (5 + 1)!)$$
$$158407 := 7 + 04 \times (8! - (5 + 1)!)$$
$$158408 := 8 + 04 \times (8! - (5 + 1)!)$$
$$158409 := 9 + 04 \times (8! - (5 + 1)!)$$

$$161280 := 0 + 8! \times (2 + 1^6 + 1)$$
$$161281 := 1 + 8! \times (2 + 1^6 + 1)$$
$$161282 := 2 + 8! \times (2 + 1^6 + 1)$$
$$161283 := 3 + 8! \times (2 + 1^6 + 1)$$
$$161284 := 4 + 8! \times (2 + 1^6 + 1)$$
$$161285 := 5 + 8! \times (2 + 1^6 + 1)$$
$$161286 := 6 + 8! \times (2 + 1^6 + 1)$$
$$161287 := 7 + 8! \times (2 + 1^6 + 1)$$
$$161288 := 8 + 8! \times (2 + 1^6 + 1)$$
$$161289 := 9 + 8! \times (2 + 1^6 + 1)$$

$$165840 := 0 + 4 \times (8! - 5!) + (6 + 1)!$$
$$165841 := 1 + 4 \times (8! - 5!) + (6 + 1)!$$
$$165842 := 2 + 4 \times (8! - 5!) + (6 + 1)!$$
$$165843 := 3 + 4 \times (8! - 5!) + (6 + 1)!$$
$$165844 := 4 + 4 \times (8! - 5!) + (6 + 1)!$$
$$165845 := 5 + 4 \times (8! - 5!) + (6 + 1)!$$
$$165846 := 6 + 4 \times (8! - 5!) + (6 + 1)!$$
$$165847 := 7 + 4 \times (8! - 5!) + (6 + 1)!$$
$$165848 := 8 + 4 \times (8! - 5!) + (6 + 1)!$$
$$165849 := 9 + 4 \times (8! - 5!) + (6 + 1)!$$

$$173520 := 0 + 2 \times 5! \times (3 + (7 - 1)!)$$
$$173521 := 1 + 2 \times 5! \times (3 + (7 - 1)!)$$
$$173522 := 2 + 2 \times 5! \times (3 + (7 - 1)!)$$
$$173523 := 3 + 2 \times 5! \times (3 + (7 - 1)!)$$
$$173524 := 4 + 2 \times 5! \times (3 + (7 - 1)!)$$
$$173525 := 5 + 2 \times 5! \times (3 + (7 - 1)!)$$
$$173526 := 6 + 2 \times 5! \times (3 + (7 - 1)!)$$
$$173527 := 7 + 2 \times 5! \times (3 + (7 - 1)!)$$
$$173528 := 8 + 2 \times 5! \times (3 + (7 - 1)!)$$
$$173529 := 9 + 2 \times 5! \times (3 + (7 - 1)!)$$

$$174960 := 0 + 6! \times 9 \times (4 \times 7 - 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 174961 &:= 1 + 6! \times 9 \times (4 \times 7 - 1) \\ 174962 &:= 2 + 6! \times 9 \times (4 \times 7 - 1) \\ 174963 &:= 3 + 6! \times 9 \times (4 \times 7 - 1) \\ 174964 &:= 4 + 6! \times 9 \times (4 \times 7 - 1) \\ 174965 &:= 5 + 6! \times 9 \times (4 \times 7 - 1) \\ 174966 &:= 6 + 6! \times 9 \times (4 \times 7 - 1) \\ 174967 &:= 7 + 6! \times 9 \times (4 \times 7 - 1) \\ 174968 &:= 8 + 6! \times 9 \times (4 \times 7 - 1) \\ 174969 &:= 9 + 6! \times 9 \times (4 \times 7 - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 201480 &:= 0 + (8! - 4!) \times 10/2 \\ 201481 &:= 1 + (8! - 4!) \times 10/2 \\ 201482 &:= 2 + (8! - 4!) \times 10/2 \\ 201483 &:= 3 + (8! - 4!) \times 10/2 \\ 201484 &:= 4 + (8! - 4!) \times 10/2 \\ 201485 &:= 5 + (8! - 4!) \times 10/2 \\ 201486 &:= 6 + (8! - 4!) \times 10/2 \\ 201487 &:= 7 + (8! - 4!) \times 10/2 \\ 201488 &:= 8 + (8! - 4!) \times 10/2 \\ 201489 &:= 9 + (8! - 4!) \times 10/2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 201580 &:= 0 + 8! \times 5 - 10 \times 2 \\ 201581 &:= 1 + 8! \times 5 - 10 \times 2 \\ 201582 &:= 2 + 8! \times 5 - 10 \times 2 \\ 201583 &:= 3 + 8! \times 5 - 10 \times 2 \\ 201584 &:= 4 + 8! \times 5 - 10 \times 2 \\ 201585 &:= 5 + 8! \times 5 - 10 \times 2 \\ 201586 &:= 6 + 8! \times 5 - 10 \times 2 \\ 201587 &:= 7 + 8! \times 5 - 10 \times 2 \\ 201588 &:= 8 + 8! \times 5 - 10 \times 2 \\ 201589 &:= 9 + 8! \times 5 - 10 \times 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 201600 &:= 0 + (-0! + 6) \times (10 - 2)! \\ 201601 &:= 1 + (-0! + 6) \times (10 - 2)! \\ 201602 &:= 2 + (-0! + 6) \times (10 - 2)! \\ 201603 &:= 3 + (-0! + 6) \times (10 - 2)! \\ 201604 &:= 4 + (-0! + 6) \times (10 - 2)! \\ 201605 &:= 5 + (-0! + 6) \times (10 - 2)! \\ 201606 &:= 6 + (-0! + 6) \times (10 - 2)! \\ 201607 &:= 7 + (-0! + 6) \times (10 - 2)! \\ 201608 &:= 8 + (-0! + 6) \times (10 - 2)! \end{aligned}$$

$$201609 := 9 + (-0! + 6) \times (10 - 2)!$$

$$\begin{aligned} 207360 &:= 0 + 6 \times (3!! + 7!) \times (0! + 2)! \\ 207361 &:= 1 + 6 \times (3!! + 7!) \times (0! + 2)! \\ 207362 &:= 2 + 6 \times (3!! + 7!) \times (0! + 2)! \\ 207363 &:= 3 + 6 \times (3!! + 7!) \times (0! + 2)! \\ 207364 &:= 4 + 6 \times (3!! + 7!) \times (0! + 2)! \\ 207365 &:= 5 + 6 \times (3!! + 7!) \times (0! + 2)! \\ 207366 &:= 6 + 6 \times (3!! + 7!) \times (0! + 2)! \\ 207367 &:= 7 + 6 \times (3!! + 7!) \times (0! + 2)! \\ 207368 &:= 8 + 6 \times (3!! + 7!) \times (0! + 2)! \\ 207369 &:= 9 + 6 \times (3!! + 7!) \times (0! + 2)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 211680 &:= 0 + (8! - (6 + 1)!) \times (1 + 2)! \\ 211681 &:= 1 + (8! - (6 + 1)!) \times (1 + 2)! \\ 211682 &:= 2 + (8! - (6 + 1)!) \times (1 + 2)! \\ 211683 &:= 3 + (8! - (6 + 1)!) \times (1 + 2)! \\ 211684 &:= 4 + (8! - (6 + 1)!) \times (1 + 2)! \\ 211685 &:= 5 + (8! - (6 + 1)!) \times (1 + 2)! \\ 211686 &:= 6 + (8! - (6 + 1)!) \times (1 + 2)! \\ 211687 &:= 7 + (8! - (6 + 1)!) \times (1 + 2)! \\ 211688 &:= 8 + (8! - (6 + 1)!) \times (1 + 2)! \\ 211689 &:= 9 + (8! - (6 + 1)!) \times (1 + 2)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 224640 &:= 0 + 4! \times 6! \times (4! + 2)/2 \\ 224641 &:= 1 + 4! \times 6! \times (4! + 2)/2 \\ 224642 &:= 2 + 4! \times 6! \times (4! + 2)/2 \\ 224643 &:= 3 + 4! \times 6! \times (4! + 2)/2 \\ 224644 &:= 4 + 4! \times 6! \times (4! + 2)/2 \\ 224645 &:= 5 + 4! \times 6! \times (4! + 2)/2 \\ 224646 &:= 6 + 4! \times 6! \times (4! + 2)/2 \\ 224647 &:= 7 + 4! \times 6! \times (4! + 2)/2 \\ 224648 &:= 8 + 4! \times 6! \times (4! + 2)/2 \\ 224649 &:= 9 + 4! \times 6! \times (4! + 2)/2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 225840 &:= 0 + (4! + (8!/5!)^2) \times 2 \\ 225841 &:= 1 + (4! + (8!/5!)^2) \times 2 \\ 225842 &:= 2 + (4! + (8!/5!)^2) \times 2 \\ 225843 &:= 3 + (4! + (8!/5!)^2) \times 2 \\ 225844 &:= 4 + (4! + (8!/5!)^2) \times 2 \\ 225845 &:= 5 + (4! + (8!/5!)^2) \times 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$225846 := 6 + (4! + (8!/5!)^2) \times 2$$

$$225847 := 7 + (4! + (8!/5!)^2) \times 2$$

$$225848 := 8 + (4! + (8!/5!)^2) \times 2$$

$$225849 := 9 + (4! + (8!/5!)^2) \times 2$$

$$233280 := 0 + (8 - 2)^{3!} \times (3 + 2)$$

$$233281 := 1 + (8 - 2)^{3!} \times (3 + 2)$$

$$233282 := 2 + (8 - 2)^{3!} \times (3 + 2)$$

$$233283 := 3 + (8 - 2)^{3!} \times (3 + 2)$$

$$233284 := 4 + (8 - 2)^{3!} \times (3 + 2)$$

$$233285 := 5 + (8 - 2)^{3!} \times (3 + 2)$$

$$233286 := 6 + (8 - 2)^{3!} \times (3 + 2)$$

$$233287 := 7 + (8 - 2)^{3!} \times (3 + 2)$$

$$233288 := 8 + (8 - 2)^{3!} \times (3 + 2)$$

$$233289 := 9 + (8 - 2)^{3!} \times (3 + 2)$$

$$234220 := 0 + 22^4 - 3!^2$$

$$234221 := 1 + 22^4 - 3!^2$$

$$234222 := 2 + 22^4 - 3!^2$$

$$234223 := 3 + 22^4 - 3!^2$$

$$234224 := 4 + 22^4 - 3!^2$$

$$234225 := 5 + 22^4 - 3!^2$$

$$234226 := 6 + 22^4 - 3!^2$$

$$234227 := 7 + 22^4 - 3!^2$$

$$234228 := 8 + 22^4 - 3!^2$$

$$234229 := 9 + 22^4 - 3!^2$$

$$236880 := 0 - 8!/8 + 6 \times (3! + 2)!$$

$$236881 := 1 - 8!/8 + 6 \times (3! + 2)!$$

$$236882 := 2 - 8!/8 + 6 \times (3! + 2)!$$

$$236883 := 3 - 8!/8 + 6 \times (3! + 2)!$$

$$236884 := 4 - 8!/8 + 6 \times (3! + 2)!$$

$$236885 := 5 - 8!/8 + 6 \times (3! + 2)!$$

$$236886 := 6 - 8!/8 + 6 \times (3! + 2)!$$

$$236887 := 7 - 8!/8 + 6 \times (3! + 2)!$$

$$236888 := 8 - 8!/8 + 6 \times (3! + 2)!$$

$$236889 := 9 - 8!/8 + 6 \times (3! + 2)!$$

$$238860 := 0 + 6 \times (8! - 8^3 + 2)$$

$$238861 := 1 + 6 \times (8! - 8^3 + 2)$$

$$238862 := 2 + 6 \times (8! - 8^3 + 2)$$

$$238863 := 3 + 6 \times (8! - 8^3 + 2)$$

$$238864 := 4 + 6 \times (8! - 8^3 + 2)$$

$$238865 := 5 + 6 \times (8! - 8^3 + 2)$$

$$238866 := 6 + 6 \times (8! - 8^3 + 2)$$

$$238867 := 7 + 6 \times (8! - 8^3 + 2)$$

$$238868 := 8 + 6 \times (8! - 8^3 + 2)$$

$$238869 := 9 + 6 \times (8! - 8^3 + 2)$$

$$241680 := 0 + 8! \times 6 - (1 + 4)! \times 2$$

$$241681 := 1 + 8! \times 6 - (1 + 4)! \times 2$$

$$241682 := 2 + 8! \times 6 - (1 + 4)! \times 2$$

$$241683 := 3 + 8! \times 6 - (1 + 4)! \times 2$$

$$241684 := 4 + 8! \times 6 - (1 + 4)! \times 2$$

$$241685 := 5 + 8! \times 6 - (1 + 4)! \times 2$$

$$241686 := 6 + 8! \times 6 - (1 + 4)! \times 2$$

$$241687 := 7 + 8! \times 6 - (1 + 4)! \times 2$$

$$241688 := 8 + 8! \times 6 - (1 + 4)! \times 2$$

$$241689 := 9 + 8! \times 6 - (1 + 4)! \times 2$$

$$241830 := 0 + 3! \times (8! + 1 - 4^2)$$

$$241831 := 1 + 3! \times (8! + 1 - 4^2)$$

$$241832 := 2 + 3! \times (8! + 1 - 4^2)$$

$$241833 := 3 + 3! \times (8! + 1 - 4^2)$$

$$241834 := 4 + 3! \times (8! + 1 - 4^2)$$

$$241835 := 5 + 3! \times (8! + 1 - 4^2)$$

$$241836 := 6 + 3! \times (8! + 1 - 4^2)$$

$$241837 := 7 + 3! \times (8! + 1 - 4^2)$$

$$241838 := 8 + 3! \times (8! + 1 - 4^2)$$

$$241839 := 9 + 3! \times (8! + 1 - 4^2)$$

$$241860 := 0 + 6 \times 8! - (1 + 4)!/2$$

$$241861 := 1 + 6 \times 8! - (1 + 4)!/2$$

$$241862 := 2 + 6 \times 8! - (1 + 4)!/2$$

$$241863 := 3 + 6 \times 8! - (1 + 4)!/2$$

$$241864 := 4 + 6 \times 8! - (1 + 4)!/2$$

$$241865 := 5 + 6 \times 8! - (1 + 4)!/2$$

$$241866 := 6 + 6 \times 8! - (1 + 4)!/2$$

$$241867 := 7 + 6 \times 8! - (1 + 4)!/2$$

$$241868 := 8 + 6 \times 8! - (1 + 4)!/2$$

$$241869 := 9 + 6 \times 8! - (1 + 4)!/2$$

$$241950 := 0 + (5 + (9 - 1)!) \times (4 + 2)$$

$$241951 := 1 + (5 + (9 - 1)!) \times (4 + 2)$$

$$241952 := 2 + (5 + (9 - 1)!) \times (4 + 2)$$

$$241953 := 3 + (5 + (9 - 1)!) \times (4 + 2)$$

$$241954 := 4 + (5 + (9 - 1)!) \times (4 + 2)$$

$$241955 := 5 + (5 + (9 - 1)!) \times (4 + 2)$$

$$241956 := 6 + (5 + (9 - 1)!) \times (4 + 2)$$

$$241957 := 7 + (5 + (9 - 1)!) \times (4 + 2)$$

$$241958 := 8 + (5 + (9 - 1)!) \times (4 + 2)$$

$$241959 := 9 + (5 + (9 - 1)!) \times (4 + 2)$$

$$241980 := 0 + (8! + 9 + 1) \times (4 + 2)$$

$$241981 := 1 + (8! + 9 + 1) \times (4 + 2)$$

$$241982 := 2 + (8! + 9 + 1) \times (4 + 2)$$

$$241983 := 3 + (8! + 9 + 1) \times (4 + 2)$$

$$241984 := 4 + (8! + 9 + 1) \times (4 + 2)$$

$$241985 := 5 + (8! + 9 + 1) \times (4 + 2)$$

$$241986 := 6 + (8! + 9 + 1) \times (4 + 2)$$

$$241987 := 7 + (8! + 9 + 1) \times (4 + 2)$$

$$241988 := 8 + (8! + 9 + 1) \times (4 + 2)$$

$$241989 := 9 + (8! + 9 + 1) \times (4 + 2)$$

$$243360 := 0 + 6! + 3!! + 3! \times (4 \times 2)!$$

$$243361 := 1 + 6! + 3!! + 3! \times (4 \times 2)!$$

$$243362 := 2 + 6! + 3!! + 3! \times (4 \times 2)!$$

$$243363 := 3 + 6! + 3!! + 3! \times (4 \times 2)!$$

$$243364 := 4 + 6! + 3!! + 3! \times (4 \times 2)!$$

$$243365 := 5 + 6! + 3!! + 3! \times (4 \times 2)!$$

$$243366 := 6 + 6! + 3!! + 3! \times (4 \times 2)!$$

$$243367 := 7 + 6! + 3!! + 3! \times (4 \times 2)!$$

$$243368 := 8 + 6! + 3!! + 3! \times (4 \times 2)!$$

$$243369 := 9 + 6! + 3!! + 3! \times (4 \times 2)!$$

$$246240 := 0 + ((4 \times 2)! + 6!) \times (4 + 2)$$

$$246241 := 1 + ((4 \times 2)! + 6!) \times (4 + 2)$$

$$246242 := 2 + ((4 \times 2)! + 6!) \times (4 + 2)$$

$$246243 := 3 + ((4 \times 2)! + 6!) \times (4 + 2)$$

$$246244 := 4 + ((4 \times 2)! + 6!) \times (4 + 2)$$

$$246245 := 5 + ((4 \times 2)! + 6!) \times (4 + 2)$$

$$246246 := 6 + ((4 \times 2)! + 6!) \times (4 + 2)$$

$$246247 := 7 + ((4 \times 2)! + 6!) \times (4 + 2)$$

$$246248 := 8 + ((4 \times 2)! + 6!) \times (4 + 2)$$

$$246249 := 9 + ((4 \times 2)! + 6!) \times (4 + 2)$$

$$247680 := 0 + 8! \times 6 + 7! + (4 + 2)!$$

$$247681 := 1 + 8! \times 6 + 7! + (4 + 2)!$$

$$247682 := 2 + 8! \times 6 + 7! + (4 + 2)!$$

$$247683 := 3 + 8! \times 6 + 7! + (4 + 2)!$$

$$247684 := 4 + 8! \times 6 + 7! + (4 + 2)!$$

$$247685 := 5 + 8! \times 6 + 7! + (4 + 2)!$$

$$247686 := 6 + 8! \times 6 + 7! + (4 + 2)!$$

$$247687 := 7 + 8! \times 6 + 7! + (4 + 2)!$$

$$247688 := 8 + 8! \times 6 + 7! + (4 + 2)!$$

$$247689 := 9 + 8! \times 6 + 7! + (4 + 2)!$$

$$253440 := 0 + (4!/4)! \times 352$$

$$253441 := 1 + (4!/4)! \times 352$$

$$253442 := 2 + (4!/4)! \times 352$$

$$253443 := 3 + (4!/4)! \times 352$$

$$253444 := 4 + (4!/4)! \times 352$$

$$253445 := 5 + (4!/4)! \times 352$$

$$253446 := 6 + (4!/4)! \times 352$$

$$253447 := 7 + (4!/4)! \times 352$$

$$253448 := 8 + (4!/4)! \times 352$$

$$253449 := 9 + (4!/4)! \times 352$$

$$255960 := 0 + (6! - 9) \times 5! \times (5 - 2)$$

$$255961 := 1 + (6! - 9) \times 5! \times (5 - 2)$$

$$255962 := 2 + (6! - 9) \times 5! \times (5 - 2)$$

$$255963 := 3 + (6! - 9) \times 5! \times (5 - 2)$$

$$255964 := 4 + (6! - 9) \times 5! \times (5 - 2)$$

$$255965 := 5 + (6! - 9) \times 5! \times (5 - 2)$$

$$255966 := 6 + (6! - 9) \times 5! \times (5 - 2)$$

$$255967 := 7 + (6! - 9) \times 5! \times (5 - 2)$$

$$255968 := 8 + (6! - 9) \times 5! \times (5 - 2)$$

$$255969 := 9 + (6! - 9) \times 5! \times (5 - 2)$$

$$256320 := 0 + (2^3)! \times 6 + 5!^2$$

$$256321 := 1 + (2^3)! \times 6 + 5!^2$$

$$\begin{aligned}256322 &:= 2 + (2^3)! \times 6 + 5!^2 \\256323 &:= 3 + (2^3)! \times 6 + 5!^2 \\256324 &:= 4 + (2^3)! \times 6 + 5!^2 \\256325 &:= 5 + (2^3)! \times 6 + 5!^2 \\256326 &:= 6 + (2^3)! \times 6 + 5!^2 \\256327 &:= 7 + (2^3)! \times 6 + 5!^2 \\256328 &:= 8 + (2^3)! \times 6 + 5!^2 \\256329 &:= 9 + (2^3)! \times 6 + 5!^2\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}256380 &:= 0 + ((-8 + 3!!) \times 6! + 5!)/2 \\256381 &:= 1 + ((-8 + 3!!) \times 6! + 5!)/2 \\256382 &:= 2 + ((-8 + 3!!) \times 6! + 5!)/2 \\256383 &:= 3 + ((-8 + 3!!) \times 6! + 5!)/2 \\256384 &:= 4 + ((-8 + 3!!) \times 6! + 5!)/2 \\256385 &:= 5 + ((-8 + 3!!) \times 6! + 5!)/2 \\256386 &:= 6 + ((-8 + 3!!) \times 6! + 5!)/2 \\256387 &:= 7 + ((-8 + 3!!) \times 6! + 5!)/2 \\256388 &:= 8 + ((-8 + 3!!) \times 6! + 5!)/2 \\256389 &:= 9 + ((-8 + 3!!) \times 6! + 5!)/2\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}257760 &:= 0 + 6! - 7! + 7! \times 52 \\257761 &:= 1 + 6! - 7! + 7! \times 52 \\257762 &:= 2 + 6! - 7! + 7! \times 52 \\257763 &:= 3 + 6! - 7! + 7! \times 52 \\257764 &:= 4 + 6! - 7! + 7! \times 52 \\257765 &:= 5 + 6! - 7! + 7! \times 52 \\257766 &:= 6 + 6! - 7! + 7! \times 52 \\257767 &:= 7 + 6! - 7! + 7! \times 52 \\257768 &:= 8 + 6! - 7! + 7! \times 52 \\257769 &:= 9 + 6! - 7! + 7! \times 52\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}259200 &:= 0 + 02 \times 9 \times 5!^2 \\259201 &:= 1 + 02 \times 9 \times 5!^2 \\259202 &:= 2 + 02 \times 9 \times 5!^2 \\259203 &:= 3 + 02 \times 9 \times 5!^2 \\259204 &:= 4 + 02 \times 9 \times 5!^2 \\259205 &:= 5 + 02 \times 9 \times 5!^2 \\259206 &:= 6 + 02 \times 9 \times 5!^2 \\259207 &:= 7 + 02 \times 9 \times 5!^2\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}259208 &:= 8 + 02 \times 9 \times 5!^2 \\259209 &:= 9 + 02 \times 9 \times 5!^2\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}260640 &:= 0 + (4 + 6!) \times 06!/2 \\260641 &:= 1 + (4 + 6!) \times 06!/2 \\260642 &:= 2 + (4 + 6!) \times 06!/2 \\260643 &:= 3 + (4 + 6!) \times 06!/2 \\260644 &:= 4 + (4 + 6!) \times 06!/2 \\260645 &:= 5 + (4 + 6!) \times 06!/2 \\260646 &:= 6 + (4 + 6!) \times 06!/2 \\260647 &:= 7 + (4 + 6!) \times 06!/2 \\260648 &:= 8 + (4 + 6!) \times 06!/2 \\260649 &:= 9 + (4 + 6!) \times 06!/2\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}261360 &:= 0 + (6! + 3!) \times 1 \times 6!/2 \\261361 &:= 1 + (6! + 3!) \times 1 \times 6!/2 \\261362 &:= 2 + (6! + 3!) \times 1 \times 6!/2 \\261363 &:= 3 + (6! + 3!) \times 1 \times 6!/2 \\261364 &:= 4 + (6! + 3!) \times 1 \times 6!/2 \\261365 &:= 5 + (6! + 3!) \times 1 \times 6!/2 \\261366 &:= 6 + (6! + 3!) \times 1 \times 6!/2 \\261367 &:= 7 + (6! + 3!) \times 1 \times 6!/2 \\261368 &:= 8 + (6! + 3!) \times 1 \times 6!/2 \\261369 &:= 9 + (6! + 3!) \times 1 \times 6!/2\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}262180 &:= 0 + 8^{(1+2)!} + 6^2 \\262181 &:= 1 + 8^{(1+2)!} + 6^2 \\262182 &:= 2 + 8^{(1+2)!} + 6^2 \\262183 &:= 3 + 8^{(1+2)!} + 6^2 \\262184 &:= 4 + 8^{(1+2)!} + 6^2 \\262185 &:= 5 + 8^{(1+2)!} + 6^2 \\262186 &:= 6 + 8^{(1+2)!} + 6^2 \\262187 &:= 7 + 8^{(1+2)!} + 6^2 \\262188 &:= 8 + 8^{(1+2)!} + 6^2 \\262189 &:= 9 + 8^{(1+2)!} + 6^2\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}262850 &:= 0 + 5^8 \times 2 - 6!^2 \\262851 &:= 1 + 5^8 \times 2 - 6!^2 \\262852 &:= 2 + 5^8 \times 2 - 6!^2 \\262853 &:= 3 + 5^8 \times 2 - 6!^2\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}262854 &:= 4 + 5^8 \times 2 - 6!^2 \\262855 &:= 5 + 5^8 \times 2 - 6!^2 \\262856 &:= 6 + 5^8 \times 2 - 6!^2 \\262857 &:= 7 + 5^8 \times 2 - 6!^2 \\262858 &:= 8 + 5^8 \times 2 - 6!^2 \\262859 &:= 9 + 5^8 \times 2 - 6!^2\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}263520 &:= 0 + (2 + 5!) \times 3! \times 6!/2 \\263521 &:= 1 + (2 + 5!) \times 3! \times 6!/2 \\263522 &:= 2 + (2 + 5!) \times 3! \times 6!/2 \\263523 &:= 3 + (2 + 5!) \times 3! \times 6!/2 \\263524 &:= 4 + (2 + 5!) \times 3! \times 6!/2 \\263525 &:= 5 + (2 + 5!) \times 3! \times 6!/2 \\263526 &:= 6 + (2 + 5!) \times 3! \times 6!/2 \\263527 &:= 7 + (2 + 5!) \times 3! \times 6!/2 \\263528 &:= 8 + (2 + 5!) \times 3! \times 6!/2 \\263529 &:= 9 + (2 + 5!) \times 3! \times 6!/2\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}267530 &:= 0 + (-3!! - 5 + 7!) \times 62 \\267531 &:= 1 + (-3!! - 5 + 7!) \times 62 \\267532 &:= 2 + (-3!! - 5 + 7!) \times 62 \\267533 &:= 3 + (-3!! - 5 + 7!) \times 62 \\267534 &:= 4 + (-3!! - 5 + 7!) \times 62 \\267535 &:= 5 + (-3!! - 5 + 7!) \times 62 \\267536 &:= 6 + (-3!! - 5 + 7!) \times 62 \\267537 &:= 7 + (-3!! - 5 + 7!) \times 62 \\267538 &:= 8 + (-3!! - 5 + 7!) \times 62 \\267539 &:= 9 + (-3!! - 5 + 7!) \times 62\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}267840 &:= 0 + (-(4!/8)!! + 7!) \times 62 \\267841 &:= 1 + (-(4!/8)!! + 7!) \times 62 \\267842 &:= 2 + (-(4!/8)!! + 7!) \times 62 \\267843 &:= 3 + (-(4!/8)!! + 7!) \times 62 \\267844 &:= 4 + (-(4!/8)!! + 7!) \times 62 \\267845 &:= 5 + (-(4!/8)!! + 7!) \times 62 \\267846 &:= 6 + (-(4!/8)!! + 7!) \times 62 \\267847 &:= 7 + (-(4!/8)!! + 7!) \times 62 \\267848 &:= 8 + (-(4!/8)!! + 7!) \times 62 \\267849 &:= 9 + (-(4!/8)!! + 7!) \times 62\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}268560 &:= 0 + 6! \times (5 + 8 + 6!/2) \\268561 &:= 1 + 6! \times (5 + 8 + 6!/2) \\268562 &:= 2 + 6! \times (5 + 8 + 6!/2) \\268563 &:= 3 + 6! \times (5 + 8 + 6!/2) \\268564 &:= 4 + 6! \times (5 + 8 + 6!/2) \\268565 &:= 5 + 6! \times (5 + 8 + 6!/2) \\268566 &:= 6 + 6! \times (5 + 8 + 6!/2) \\268567 &:= 7 + 6! \times (5 + 8 + 6!/2) \\268568 &:= 8 + 6! \times (5 + 8 + 6!/2) \\268569 &:= 9 + 6! \times (5 + 8 + 6!/2)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}272160 &:= 0 + (6 + 1)! \times 27 \times 2 \\272161 &:= 1 + (6 + 1)! \times 27 \times 2 \\272162 &:= 2 + (6 + 1)! \times 27 \times 2 \\272163 &:= 3 + (6 + 1)! \times 27 \times 2 \\272164 &:= 4 + (6 + 1)! \times 27 \times 2 \\272165 &:= 5 + (6 + 1)! \times 27 \times 2 \\272166 &:= 6 + (6 + 1)! \times 27 \times 2 \\272167 &:= 7 + (6 + 1)! \times 27 \times 2 \\272168 &:= 8 + (6 + 1)! \times 27 \times 2 \\272169 &:= 9 + (6 + 1)! \times 27 \times 2\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}276480 &:= 0 + 8! \times 4 \times 6/7 \times 2 \\276481 &:= 1 + 8! \times 4 \times 6/7 \times 2 \\276482 &:= 2 + 8! \times 4 \times 6/7 \times 2 \\276483 &:= 3 + 8! \times 4 \times 6/7 \times 2 \\276484 &:= 4 + 8! \times 4 \times 6/7 \times 2 \\276485 &:= 5 + 8! \times 4 \times 6/7 \times 2 \\276486 &:= 6 + 8! \times 4 \times 6/7 \times 2 \\276487 &:= 7 + 8! \times 4 \times 6/7 \times 2 \\276488 &:= 8 + 8! \times 4 \times 6/7 \times 2 \\276489 &:= 9 + 8! \times 4 \times 6/7 \times 2\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}279360 &:= 0 + (6! + 3!) \times 97 \times 2 \\279361 &:= 1 + (6! + 3!) \times 97 \times 2 \\279362 &:= 2 + (6! + 3!) \times 97 \times 2 \\279363 &:= 3 + (6! + 3!) \times 97 \times 2 \\279364 &:= 4 + (6! + 3!) \times 97 \times 2 \\279365 &:= 5 + (6! + 3!) \times 97 \times 2 \\279366 &:= 6 + (6! + 3!) \times 97 \times 2 \\279367 &:= 7 + (6! + 3!) \times 97 \times 2 \\279368 &:= 8 + (6! + 3!) \times 97 \times 2\end{aligned}$$

$$279369 := 9 + (6! + 3!) \times 97 \times 2$$

$$279720 := 0 + ((-2 + 7)! - 9) \times 7!/2$$

$$279721 := 1 + ((-2 + 7)! - 9) \times 7!/2$$

$$279722 := 2 + ((-2 + 7)! - 9) \times 7!/2$$

$$279723 := 3 + ((-2 + 7)! - 9) \times 7!/2$$

$$279724 := 4 + ((-2 + 7)! - 9) \times 7!/2$$

$$279725 := 5 + ((-2 + 7)! - 9) \times 7!/2$$

$$279726 := 6 + ((-2 + 7)! - 9) \times 7!/2$$

$$279727 := 7 + ((-2 + 7)! - 9) \times 7!/2$$

$$279728 := 8 + ((-2 + 7)! - 9) \times 7!/2$$

$$279729 := 9 + ((-2 + 7)! - 9) \times 7!/2$$

$$282170 := 0 + 7 \times (-12 + 8! + 2)$$

$$282171 := 1 + 7 \times (-12 + 8! + 2)$$

$$282172 := 2 + 7 \times (-12 + 8! + 2)$$

$$282173 := 3 + 7 \times (-12 + 8! + 2)$$

$$282174 := 4 + 7 \times (-12 + 8! + 2)$$

$$282175 := 5 + 7 \times (-12 + 8! + 2)$$

$$282176 := 6 + 7 \times (-12 + 8! + 2)$$

$$282177 := 7 + 7 \times (-12 + 8! + 2)$$

$$282178 := 8 + 7 \times (-12 + 8! + 2)$$

$$282179 := 9 + 7 \times (-12 + 8! + 2)$$

$$282240 := 0 + (4^2 - 2) \times 8!/2$$

$$282241 := 1 + (4^2 - 2) \times 8!/2$$

$$282242 := 2 + (4^2 - 2) \times 8!/2$$

$$282243 := 3 + (4^2 - 2) \times 8!/2$$

$$282244 := 4 + (4^2 - 2) \times 8!/2$$

$$282245 := 5 + (4^2 - 2) \times 8!/2$$

$$282246 := 6 + (4^2 - 2) \times 8!/2$$

$$282247 := 7 + (4^2 - 2) \times 8!/2$$

$$282248 := 8 + (4^2 - 2) \times 8!/2$$

$$282249 := 9 + (4^2 - 2) \times 8!/2$$

$$282270 := 0 + 7 \times (2 + 2 + 8!) + 2$$

$$282271 := 1 + 7 \times (2 + 2 + 8!) + 2$$

$$282272 := 2 + 7 \times (2 + 2 + 8!) + 2$$

$$282273 := 3 + 7 \times (2 + 2 + 8!) + 2$$

$$282274 := 4 + 7 \times (2 + 2 + 8!) + 2$$

$$282275 := 5 + 7 \times (2 + 2 + 8!) + 2$$

$$282276 := 6 + 7 \times (2 + 2 + 8!) + 2$$

$$282277 := 7 + 7 \times (2 + 2 + 8!) + 2$$

$$282278 := 8 + 7 \times (2 + 2 + 8!) + 2$$

$$282279 := 9 + 7 \times (2 + 2 + 8!) + 2$$

$$282960 := 0 + ((6! + 9!)/2 - 8!) \times 2$$

$$282961 := 1 + ((6! + 9!)/2 - 8!) \times 2$$

$$282962 := 2 + ((6! + 9!)/2 - 8!) \times 2$$

$$282963 := 3 + ((6! + 9!)/2 - 8!) \times 2$$

$$282964 := 4 + ((6! + 9!)/2 - 8!) \times 2$$

$$282965 := 5 + ((6! + 9!)/2 - 8!) \times 2$$

$$282966 := 6 + ((6! + 9!)/2 - 8!) \times 2$$

$$282967 := 7 + ((6! + 9!)/2 - 8!) \times 2$$

$$282968 := 8 + ((6! + 9!)/2 - 8!) \times 2$$

$$282969 := 9 + ((6! + 9!)/2 - 8!) \times 2$$

$$283680 := 0 + 8! + (6! + 3 \times 8!) \times 2$$

$$283681 := 1 + 8! + (6! + 3 \times 8!) \times 2$$

$$283682 := 2 + 8! + (6! + 3 \times 8!) \times 2$$

$$283683 := 3 + 8! + (6! + 3 \times 8!) \times 2$$

$$283684 := 4 + 8! + (6! + 3 \times 8!) \times 2$$

$$283685 := 5 + 8! + (6! + 3 \times 8!) \times 2$$

$$283686 := 6 + 8! + (6! + 3 \times 8!) \times 2$$

$$283687 := 7 + 8! + (6! + 3 \times 8!) \times 2$$

$$283688 := 8 + 8! + (6! + 3 \times 8!) \times 2$$

$$283689 := 9 + 8! + (6! + 3 \times 8!) \times 2$$

$$291600 := 0 + ((-0! + 61) \times 9)^2$$

$$291601 := 1 + ((-0! + 61) \times 9)^2$$

$$291602 := 2 + ((-0! + 61) \times 9)^2$$

$$291603 := 3 + ((-0! + 61) \times 9)^2$$

$$291604 := 4 + ((-0! + 61) \times 9)^2$$

$$291605 := 5 + ((-0! + 61) \times 9)^2$$

$$291606 := 6 + ((-0! + 61) \times 9)^2$$

$$291607 := 7 + ((-0! + 61) \times 9)^2$$

$$291608 := 8 + ((-0! + 61) \times 9)^2$$

$$291609 := 9 + ((-0! + 61) \times 9)^2$$

$$302400 := 0 + (0! + 4)!/2 \times (0! + 3)!$$

$$302401 := 1 + (0! + 4)!/2 \times (0! + 3)!$$

$$\begin{aligned} 302402 &:= 2 + (0! + 4)!/2 \times (0! + 3)! \\ 302403 &:= 3 + (0! + 4)!/2 \times (0! + 3)! \\ 302404 &:= 4 + (0! + 4)!/2 \times (0! + 3)! \\ 302405 &:= 5 + (0! + 4)!/2 \times (0! + 3)! \\ 302406 &:= 6 + (0! + 4)!/2 \times (0! + 3)! \\ 302407 &:= 7 + (0! + 4)!/2 \times (0! + 3)! \\ 302408 &:= 8 + (0! + 4)!/2 \times (0! + 3)! \\ 302409 &:= 9 + (0! + 4)!/2 \times (0! + 3)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 302760 &:= 0 + (6 + 7!) \times 20 \times 3 \\ 302761 &:= 1 + (6 + 7!) \times 20 \times 3 \\ 302762 &:= 2 + (6 + 7!) \times 20 \times 3 \\ 302763 &:= 3 + (6 + 7!) \times 20 \times 3 \\ 302764 &:= 4 + (6 + 7!) \times 20 \times 3 \\ 302765 &:= 5 + (6 + 7!) \times 20 \times 3 \\ 302766 &:= 6 + (6 + 7!) \times 20 \times 3 \\ 302767 &:= 7 + (6 + 7!) \times 20 \times 3 \\ 302768 &:= 8 + (6 + 7!) \times 20 \times 3 \\ 302769 &:= 9 + (6 + 7!) \times 20 \times 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 317540 &:= 0 + 4 \times 5^7 + (1 + 3)! \\ 317541 &:= 1 + 4 \times 5^7 + (1 + 3)! \\ 317542 &:= 2 + 4 \times 5^7 + (1 + 3)! \\ 317543 &:= 3 + 4 \times 5^7 + (1 + 3)! \\ 317544 &:= 4 + 4 \times 5^7 + (1 + 3)! \\ 317545 &:= 5 + 4 \times 5^7 + (1 + 3)! \\ 317546 &:= 6 + 4 \times 5^7 + (1 + 3)! \\ 317547 &:= 7 + 4 \times 5^7 + (1 + 3)! \\ 317548 &:= 8 + 4 \times 5^7 + (1 + 3)! \\ 317549 &:= 9 + 4 \times 5^7 + (1 + 3)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 322540 &:= 0 + 4 \times (-5 + 2 \times (2^3)!) \\ 322541 &:= 1 + 4 \times (-5 + 2 \times (2^3)!) \\ 322542 &:= 2 + 4 \times (-5 + 2 \times (2^3)!) \\ 322543 &:= 3 + 4 \times (-5 + 2 \times (2^3)!) \\ 322544 &:= 4 + 4 \times (-5 + 2 \times (2^3)!) \\ 322545 &:= 5 + 4 \times (-5 + 2 \times (2^3)!) \\ 322546 &:= 6 + 4 \times (-5 + 2 \times (2^3)!) \\ 322547 &:= 7 + 4 \times (-5 + 2 \times (2^3)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 322548 &:= 8 + 4 \times (-5 + 2 \times (2^3)!) \\ 322549 &:= 9 + 4 \times (-5 + 2 \times (2^3)!) \\ 322560 &:= 0 + (6 + 5 - 2)! - (2^3)! \\ 322561 &:= 1 + (6 + 5 - 2)! - (2^3)! \\ 322562 &:= 2 + (6 + 5 - 2)! - (2^3)! \\ 322563 &:= 3 + (6 + 5 - 2)! - (2^3)! \\ 322564 &:= 4 + (6 + 5 - 2)! - (2^3)! \\ 322565 &:= 5 + (6 + 5 - 2)! - (2^3)! \\ 322566 &:= 6 + (6 + 5 - 2)! - (2^3)! \\ 322567 &:= 7 + (6 + 5 - 2)! - (2^3)! \\ 322568 &:= 8 + (6 + 5 - 2)! - (2^3)! \\ 322569 &:= 9 + (6 + 5 - 2)! - (2^3)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 322680 &:= 0 + 8 \times (6 + 2)! + (2 + 3)! \\ 322681 &:= 1 + 8 \times (6 + 2)! + (2 + 3)! \\ 322682 &:= 2 + 8 \times (6 + 2)! + (2 + 3)! \\ 322683 &:= 3 + 8 \times (6 + 2)! + (2 + 3)! \\ 322684 &:= 4 + 8 \times (6 + 2)! + (2 + 3)! \\ 322685 &:= 5 + 8 \times (6 + 2)! + (2 + 3)! \\ 322686 &:= 6 + 8 \times (6 + 2)! + (2 + 3)! \\ 322687 &:= 7 + 8 \times (6 + 2)! + (2 + 3)! \\ 322688 &:= 8 + 8 \times (6 + 2)! + (2 + 3)! \\ 322689 &:= 9 + 8 \times (6 + 2)! + (2 + 3)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 323280 &:= 0 + 8 \times (2^3)! + (2 \times 3)! \\ 323281 &:= 1 + 8 \times (2^3)! + (2 \times 3)! \\ 323282 &:= 2 + 8 \times (2^3)! + (2 \times 3)! \\ 323283 &:= 3 + 8 \times (2^3)! + (2 \times 3)! \\ 323284 &:= 4 + 8 \times (2^3)! + (2 \times 3)! \\ 323285 &:= 5 + 8 \times (2^3)! + (2 \times 3)! \\ 323286 &:= 6 + 8 \times (2^3)! + (2 \times 3)! \\ 323287 &:= 7 + 8 \times (2^3)! + (2 \times 3)! \\ 323288 &:= 8 + 8 \times (2^3)! + (2 \times 3)! \\ 323289 &:= 9 + 8 \times (2^3)! + (2 \times 3)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 326880 &:= 0 + 8 \times 8! + 6! \times 2 \times 3 \\ 326881 &:= 1 + 8 \times 8! + 6! \times 2 \times 3 \\ 326882 &:= 2 + 8 \times 8! + 6! \times 2 \times 3 \\ 326883 &:= 3 + 8 \times 8! + 6! \times 2 \times 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 326884 &:= 4 + 8 \times 8! + 6! \times 2 \times 3 \\ 326885 &:= 5 + 8 \times 8! + 6! \times 2 \times 3 \\ 326886 &:= 6 + 8 \times 8! + 6! \times 2 \times 3 \\ 326887 &:= 7 + 8 \times 8! + 6! \times 2 \times 3 \\ 326888 &:= 8 + 8 \times 8! + 6! \times 2 \times 3 \\ 326889 &:= 9 + 8 \times 8! + 6! \times 2 \times 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 327600 &:= 0 + (0! + 6)! + 7! \times 2^{3!} \\ 327601 &:= 1 + (0! + 6)! + 7! \times 2^{3!} \\ 327602 &:= 2 + (0! + 6)! + 7! \times 2^{3!} \\ 327603 &:= 3 + (0! + 6)! + 7! \times 2^{3!} \\ 327604 &:= 4 + (0! + 6)! + 7! \times 2^{3!} \\ 327605 &:= 5 + (0! + 6)! + 7! \times 2^{3!} \\ 327606 &:= 6 + (0! + 6)! + 7! \times 2^{3!} \\ 327607 &:= 7 + (0! + 6)! + 7! \times 2^{3!} \\ 327608 &:= 8 + (0! + 6)! + 7! \times 2^{3!} \\ 327609 &:= 9 + (0! + 6)! + 7! \times 2^{3!} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 328320 &:= 0 + ((2 \times 3)! + 8!) \times 2^3 \\ 328321 &:= 1 + ((2 \times 3)! + 8!) \times 2^3 \\ 328322 &:= 2 + ((2 \times 3)! + 8!) \times 2^3 \\ 328323 &:= 3 + ((2 \times 3)! + 8!) \times 2^3 \\ 328324 &:= 4 + ((2 \times 3)! + 8!) \times 2^3 \\ 328325 &:= 5 + ((2 \times 3)! + 8!) \times 2^3 \\ 328326 &:= 6 + ((2 \times 3)! + 8!) \times 2^3 \\ 328327 &:= 7 + ((2 \times 3)! + 8!) \times 2^3 \\ 328328 &:= 8 + ((2 \times 3)! + 8!) \times 2^3 \\ 328329 &:= 9 + ((2 \times 3)! + 8!) \times 2^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 329280 &:= 0 + 8! \times (-2 + 9)^2 / 3! \\ 329281 &:= 1 + 8! \times (-2 + 9)^2 / 3! \\ 329282 &:= 2 + 8! \times (-2 + 9)^2 / 3! \\ 329283 &:= 3 + 8! \times (-2 + 9)^2 / 3! \\ 329284 &:= 4 + 8! \times (-2 + 9)^2 / 3! \\ 329285 &:= 5 + 8! \times (-2 + 9)^2 / 3! \\ 329286 &:= 6 + 8! \times (-2 + 9)^2 / 3! \\ 329287 &:= 7 + 8! \times (-2 + 9)^2 / 3! \\ 329288 &:= 8 + 8! \times (-2 + 9)^2 / 3! \end{aligned}$$

$$329289 := 9 + 8! \times (-2 + 9)^2 / 3!$$

$$\begin{aligned} 330480 &:= 0 + 8! + 403 \times 3!! \\ 330481 &:= 1 + 8! + 403 \times 3!! \\ 330482 &:= 2 + 8! + 403 \times 3!! \\ 330483 &:= 3 + 8! + 403 \times 3!! \\ 330484 &:= 4 + 8! + 403 \times 3!! \\ 330485 &:= 5 + 8! + 403 \times 3!! \\ 330486 &:= 6 + 8! + 403 \times 3!! \\ 330487 &:= 7 + 8! + 403 \times 3!! \\ 330488 &:= 8 + 8! + 403 \times 3!! \\ 330489 &:= 9 + 8! + 403 \times 3!! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 331920 &:= 0 + (2 + 9)! / (-1 + 3)! - 3!! \\ 331921 &:= 1 + (2 + 9)! / (-1 + 3)! - 3!! \\ 331922 &:= 2 + (2 + 9)! / (-1 + 3)! - 3!! \\ 331923 &:= 3 + (2 + 9)! / (-1 + 3)! - 3!! \\ 331924 &:= 4 + (2 + 9)! / (-1 + 3)! - 3!! \\ 331925 &:= 5 + (2 + 9)! / (-1 + 3)! - 3!! \\ 331926 &:= 6 + (2 + 9)! / (-1 + 3)! - 3!! \\ 331927 &:= 7 + (2 + 9)! / (-1 + 3)! - 3!! \\ 331928 &:= 8 + (2 + 9)! / (-1 + 3)! - 3!! \\ 331929 &:= 9 + (2 + 9)! / (-1 + 3)! - 3!! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 332640 &:= 0 + 462 \times (3 + 3)! \\ 332641 &:= 1 + 462 \times (3 + 3)! \\ 332642 &:= 2 + 462 \times (3 + 3)! \\ 332643 &:= 3 + 462 \times (3 + 3)! \\ 332644 &:= 4 + 462 \times (3 + 3)! \\ 332645 &:= 5 + 462 \times (3 + 3)! \\ 332646 &:= 6 + 462 \times (3 + 3)! \\ 332647 &:= 7 + 462 \times (3 + 3)! \\ 332648 &:= 8 + 462 \times (3 + 3)! \\ 332649 &:= 9 + 462 \times (3 + 3)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 333360 &:= 0 + (6 + 3)! / (3!! + 3!!) + 3!! \\ 333361 &:= 1 + (6 + 3)! / (3!! + 3!!) + 3!! \\ 333362 &:= 2 + (6 + 3)! / (3!! + 3!!) + 3!! \\ 333363 &:= 3 + (6 + 3)! / (3!! + 3!!) + 3!! \\ 333364 &:= 4 + (6 + 3)! / (3!! + 3!!) + 3!! \\ 333365 &:= 5 + (6 + 3)! / (3!! + 3!!) + 3!! \\ 333366 &:= 6 + (6 + 3)! / (3!! + 3!!) + 3!! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 333367 &:= 7 + (6 + 3!)/(3!! + 3!!) + 3!! \\ 333368 &:= 8 + (6 + 3!)/(3!! + 3!!) + 3!! \\ 333369 &:= 9 + (6 + 3!)/(3!! + 3!!) + 3!! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 334080 &:= 0 + 80 \times (-4! + 3!!) \times 3! \\ 334081 &:= 1 + 80 \times (-4! + 3!!) \times 3! \\ 334082 &:= 2 + 80 \times (-4! + 3!!) \times 3! \\ 334083 &:= 3 + 80 \times (-4! + 3!!) \times 3! \\ 334084 &:= 4 + 80 \times (-4! + 3!!) \times 3! \\ 334085 &:= 5 + 80 \times (-4! + 3!!) \times 3! \\ 334086 &:= 6 + 80 \times (-4! + 3!!) \times 3! \\ 334087 &:= 7 + 80 \times (-4! + 3!!) \times 3! \\ 334088 &:= 8 + 80 \times (-4! + 3!!) \times 3! \\ 334089 &:= 9 + 80 \times (-4! + 3!!) \times 3! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 335280 &:= 0 + 8! \times 25/3 - 3!! \\ 335281 &:= 1 + 8! \times 25/3 - 3!! \\ 335282 &:= 2 + 8! \times 25/3 - 3!! \\ 335283 &:= 3 + 8! \times 25/3 - 3!! \\ 335284 &:= 4 + 8! \times 25/3 - 3!! \\ 335285 &:= 5 + 8! \times 25/3 - 3!! \\ 335286 &:= 6 + 8! \times 25/3 - 3!! \\ 335287 &:= 7 + 8! \times 25/3 - 3!! \\ 335288 &:= 8 + 8! \times 25/3 - 3!! \\ 335289 &:= 9 + 8! \times 25/3 - 3!! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 337590 &:= 0 + 9! - 5 \times (7! + 3 \times 3!) \\ 337591 &:= 1 + 9! - 5 \times (7! + 3 \times 3!) \\ 337592 &:= 2 + 9! - 5 \times (7! + 3 \times 3!) \\ 337593 &:= 3 + 9! - 5 \times (7! + 3 \times 3!) \\ 337594 &:= 4 + 9! - 5 \times (7! + 3 \times 3!) \\ 337595 &:= 5 + 9! - 5 \times (7! + 3 \times 3!) \\ 337596 &:= 6 + 9! - 5 \times (7! + 3 \times 3!) \\ 337597 &:= 7 + 9! - 5 \times (7! + 3 \times 3!) \\ 337598 &:= 8 + 9! - 5 \times (7! + 3 \times 3!) \\ 337599 &:= 9 + 9! - 5 \times (7! + 3 \times 3!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 337650 &:= 0 - 5 \times (6 + 7!) + (3 \times 3)! \\ 337651 &:= 1 - 5 \times (6 + 7!) + (3 \times 3)! \\ 337652 &:= 2 - 5 \times (6 + 7!) + (3 \times 3)! \\ 337653 &:= 3 - 5 \times (6 + 7!) + (3 \times 3)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 337654 &:= 4 - 5 \times (6 + 7!) + (3 \times 3)! \\ 337655 &:= 5 - 5 \times (6 + 7!) + (3 \times 3)! \\ 337656 &:= 6 - 5 \times (6 + 7!) + (3 \times 3)! \\ 337657 &:= 7 - 5 \times (6 + 7!) + (3 \times 3)! \\ 337658 &:= 8 - 5 \times (6 + 7!) + (3 \times 3)! \\ 337659 &:= 9 - 5 \times (6 + 7!) + (3 \times 3)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 340560 &:= 0 + 6! \times ((5! - 0!) \times 4 - 3) \\ 340561 &:= 1 + 6! \times ((5! - 0!) \times 4 - 3) \\ 340562 &:= 2 + 6! \times ((5! - 0!) \times 4 - 3) \\ 340563 &:= 3 + 6! \times ((5! - 0!) \times 4 - 3) \\ 340564 &:= 4 + 6! \times ((5! - 0!) \times 4 - 3) \\ 340565 &:= 5 + 6! \times ((5! - 0!) \times 4 - 3) \\ 340566 &:= 6 + 6! \times ((5! - 0!) \times 4 - 3) \\ 340567 &:= 7 + 6! \times ((5! - 0!) \times 4 - 3) \\ 340568 &:= 8 + 6! \times ((5! - 0!) \times 4 - 3) \\ 340569 &:= 9 + 6! \times ((5! - 0!) \times 4 - 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 343000 &:= 0 + (-0! - 0! + 3 \times 4!)^3 \\ 343001 &:= 1 + (-0! - 0! + 3 \times 4!)^3 \\ 343002 &:= 2 + (-0! - 0! + 3 \times 4!)^3 \\ 343003 &:= 3 + (-0! - 0! + 3 \times 4!)^3 \\ 343004 &:= 4 + (-0! - 0! + 3 \times 4!)^3 \\ 343005 &:= 5 + (-0! - 0! + 3 \times 4!)^3 \\ 343006 &:= 6 + (-0! - 0! + 3 \times 4!)^3 \\ 343007 &:= 7 + (-0! - 0! + 3 \times 4!)^3 \\ 343008 &:= 8 + (-0! - 0! + 3 \times 4!)^3 \\ 343009 &:= 9 + (-0! - 0! + 3 \times 4!)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 345360 &:= 0 - 6!/3 + 5! \times 4 \times 3!! \\ 345361 &:= 1 - 6!/3 + 5! \times 4 \times 3!! \\ 345362 &:= 2 - 6!/3 + 5! \times 4 \times 3!! \\ 345363 &:= 3 - 6!/3 + 5! \times 4 \times 3!! \\ 345364 &:= 4 - 6!/3 + 5! \times 4 \times 3!! \\ 345365 &:= 5 - 6!/3 + 5! \times 4 \times 3!! \\ 345366 &:= 6 - 6!/3 + 5! \times 4 \times 3!! \\ 345367 &:= 7 - 6!/3 + 5! \times 4 \times 3!! \\ 345368 &:= 8 - 6!/3 + 5! \times 4 \times 3!! \\ 345369 &:= 9 - 6!/3 + 5! \times 4 \times 3!! \end{aligned}$$

$$345600 := 0 + 06! \times 5! \times 4!/3!$$

$$\begin{aligned} 345601 &:= 1 + 06! \times 5! \times 4!/3! \\ 345602 &:= 2 + 06! \times 5! \times 4!/3! \\ 345603 &:= 3 + 06! \times 5! \times 4!/3! \\ 345604 &:= 4 + 06! \times 5! \times 4!/3! \\ 345605 &:= 5 + 06! \times 5! \times 4!/3! \\ 345606 &:= 6 + 06! \times 5! \times 4!/3! \\ 345607 &:= 7 + 06! \times 5! \times 4!/3! \\ 345608 &:= 8 + 06! \times 5! \times 4!/3! \\ 345609 &:= 9 + 06! \times 5! \times 4!/3! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 345630 &:= 0 + (3! + 6! \times 5!) \times 4 + 3! \\ 345631 &:= 1 + (3! + 6! \times 5!) \times 4 + 3! \\ 345632 &:= 2 + (3! + 6! \times 5!) \times 4 + 3! \\ 345633 &:= 3 + (3! + 6! \times 5!) \times 4 + 3! \\ 345634 &:= 4 + (3! + 6! \times 5!) \times 4 + 3! \\ 345635 &:= 5 + (3! + 6! \times 5!) \times 4 + 3! \\ 345636 &:= 6 + (3! + 6! \times 5!) \times 4 + 3! \\ 345637 &:= 7 + (3! + 6! \times 5!) \times 4 + 3! \\ 345638 &:= 8 + (3! + 6! \times 5!) \times 4 + 3! \\ 345639 &:= 9 + (3! + 6! \times 5!) \times 4 + 3! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 345640 &:= 0 + 4 \times (6! \times 5! + 4 + 3!) \\ 345641 &:= 1 + 4 \times (6! \times 5! + 4 + 3!) \\ 345642 &:= 2 + 4 \times (6! \times 5! + 4 + 3!) \\ 345643 &:= 3 + 4 \times (6! \times 5! + 4 + 3!) \\ 345644 &:= 4 + 4 \times (6! \times 5! + 4 + 3!) \\ 345645 &:= 5 + 4 \times (6! \times 5! + 4 + 3!) \\ 345646 &:= 6 + 4 \times (6! \times 5! + 4 + 3!) \\ 345647 &:= 7 + 4 \times (6! \times 5! + 4 + 3!) \\ 345648 &:= 8 + 4 \times (6! \times 5! + 4 + 3!) \\ 345649 &:= 9 + 4 \times (6! \times 5! + 4 + 3!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 345720 &:= 0 + (-2 + 7)! + 5! \times 4 \times 3!! \\ 345721 &:= 1 + (-2 + 7)! + 5! \times 4 \times 3!! \\ 345722 &:= 2 + (-2 + 7)! + 5! \times 4 \times 3!! \\ 345723 &:= 3 + (-2 + 7)! + 5! \times 4 \times 3!! \\ 345724 &:= 4 + (-2 + 7)! + 5! \times 4 \times 3!! \\ 345725 &:= 5 + (-2 + 7)! + 5! \times 4 \times 3!! \\ 345726 &:= 6 + (-2 + 7)! + 5! \times 4 \times 3!! \\ 345727 &:= 7 + (-2 + 7)! + 5! \times 4 \times 3!! \\ 345728 &:= 8 + (-2 + 7)! + 5! \times 4 \times 3!! \end{aligned}$$

$$345729 := 9 + (-2 + 7)! + 5! \times 4 \times 3!!$$

$$\begin{aligned} 346320 &:= 0 + (2 + 3)! \times (6! \times 4 + 3!) \\ 346321 &:= 1 + (2 + 3)! \times (6! \times 4 + 3!) \\ 346322 &:= 2 + (2 + 3)! \times (6! \times 4 + 3!) \\ 346323 &:= 3 + (2 + 3)! \times (6! \times 4 + 3!) \\ 346324 &:= 4 + (2 + 3)! \times (6! \times 4 + 3!) \\ 346325 &:= 5 + (2 + 3)! \times (6! \times 4 + 3!) \\ 346326 &:= 6 + (2 + 3)! \times (6! \times 4 + 3!) \\ 346327 &:= 7 + (2 + 3)! \times (6! \times 4 + 3!) \\ 346328 &:= 8 + (2 + 3)! \times (6! \times 4 + 3!) \\ 346329 &:= 9 + (2 + 3)! \times (6! \times 4 + 3!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 346490 &:= 0 + 9! - 4^6 \times 4 - 3! \\ 346491 &:= 1 + 9! - 4^6 \times 4 - 3! \\ 346492 &:= 2 + 9! - 4^6 \times 4 - 3! \\ 346493 &:= 3 + 9! - 4^6 \times 4 - 3! \\ 346494 &:= 4 + 9! - 4^6 \times 4 - 3! \\ 346495 &:= 5 + 9! - 4^6 \times 4 - 3! \\ 346496 &:= 6 + 9! - 4^6 \times 4 - 3! \\ 346497 &:= 7 + 9! - 4^6 \times 4 - 3! \\ 346498 &:= 8 + 9! - 4^6 \times 4 - 3! \\ 346499 &:= 9 + 9! - 4^6 \times 4 - 3! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 347760 &:= 0 + (-6! \times 7 + 7! \times 4!) \times 3 \\ 347761 &:= 1 + (-6! \times 7 + 7! \times 4!) \times 3 \\ 347762 &:= 2 + (-6! \times 7 + 7! \times 4!) \times 3 \\ 347763 &:= 3 + (-6! \times 7 + 7! \times 4!) \times 3 \\ 347764 &:= 4 + (-6! \times 7 + 7! \times 4!) \times 3 \\ 347765 &:= 5 + (-6! \times 7 + 7! \times 4!) \times 3 \\ 347766 &:= 6 + (-6! \times 7 + 7! \times 4!) \times 3 \\ 347767 &:= 7 + (-6! \times 7 + 7! \times 4!) \times 3 \\ 347768 &:= 8 + (-6! \times 7 + 7! \times 4!) \times 3 \\ 347769 &:= 9 + (-6! \times 7 + 7! \times 4!) \times 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 354240 &:= 0 + 4 \times (2 + 4)! \times (5! + 3) \\ 354241 &:= 1 + 4 \times (2 + 4)! \times (5! + 3) \\ 354242 &:= 2 + 4 \times (2 + 4)! \times (5! + 3) \\ 354243 &:= 3 + 4 \times (2 + 4)! \times (5! + 3) \\ 354244 &:= 4 + 4 \times (2 + 4)! \times (5! + 3) \\ 354245 &:= 5 + 4 \times (2 + 4)! \times (5! + 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 354246 &:= 6 + 4 \times (2 + 4)! \times (5! + 3) \\ 354247 &:= 7 + 4 \times (2 + 4)! \times (5! + 3) \\ 354248 &:= 8 + 4 \times (2 + 4)! \times (5! + 3) \\ 354249 &:= 9 + 4 \times (2 + 4)! \times (5! + 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 354960 &:= 0 + 6! + 9! - 4! \times 5! \times 3 \\ 354961 &:= 1 + 6! + 9! - 4! \times 5! \times 3 \\ 354962 &:= 2 + 6! + 9! - 4! \times 5! \times 3 \\ 354963 &:= 3 + 6! + 9! - 4! \times 5! \times 3 \\ 354964 &:= 4 + 6! + 9! - 4! \times 5! \times 3 \\ 354965 &:= 5 + 6! + 9! - 4! \times 5! \times 3 \\ 354966 &:= 6 + 6! + 9! - 4! \times 5! \times 3 \\ 354967 &:= 7 + 6! + 9! - 4! \times 5! \times 3 \\ 354968 &:= 8 + 6! + 9! - 4! \times 5! \times 3 \\ 354969 &:= 9 + 6! + 9! - 4! \times 5! \times 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 355530 &:= 0 - 3!! + 5^5 \times (5! - 3!) \\ 355531 &:= 1 - 3!! + 5^5 \times (5! - 3!) \\ 355532 &:= 2 - 3!! + 5^5 \times (5! - 3!) \\ 355533 &:= 3 - 3!! + 5^5 \times (5! - 3!) \\ 355534 &:= 4 - 3!! + 5^5 \times (5! - 3!) \\ 355535 &:= 5 - 3!! + 5^5 \times (5! - 3!) \\ 355536 &:= 6 - 3!! + 5^5 \times (5! - 3!) \\ 355537 &:= 7 - 3!! + 5^5 \times (5! - 3!) \\ 355538 &:= 8 - 3!! + 5^5 \times (5! - 3!) \\ 355539 &:= 9 - 3!! + 5^5 \times (5! - 3!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 356880 &:= 0 + 8 \times (8! + (6! - 5) \times 3!) \\ 356881 &:= 1 + 8 \times (8! + (6! - 5) \times 3!) \\ 356882 &:= 2 + 8 \times (8! + (6! - 5) \times 3!) \\ 356883 &:= 3 + 8 \times (8! + (6! - 5) \times 3!) \\ 356884 &:= 4 + 8 \times (8! + (6! - 5) \times 3!) \\ 356885 &:= 5 + 8 \times (8! + (6! - 5) \times 3!) \\ 356886 &:= 6 + 8 \times (8! + (6! - 5) \times 3!) \\ 356887 &:= 7 + 8 \times (8! + (6! - 5) \times 3!) \\ 356888 &:= 8 + 8 \times (8! + (6! - 5) \times 3!) \\ 356889 &:= 9 + 8 \times (8! + (6! - 5) \times 3!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 357800 &:= 0 + (0! + 8)! - 7! - 5!/3 \\ 357801 &:= 1 + (0! + 8)! - 7! - 5!/3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 357802 &:= 2 + (0! + 8)! - 7! - 5!/3 \\ 357803 &:= 3 + (0! + 8)! - 7! - 5!/3 \\ 357804 &:= 4 + (0! + 8)! - 7! - 5!/3 \\ 357805 &:= 5 + (0! + 8)! - 7! - 5!/3 \\ 357806 &:= 6 + (0! + 8)! - 7! - 5!/3 \\ 357807 &:= 7 + (0! + 8)! - 7! - 5!/3 \\ 357808 &:= 8 + (0! + 8)! - 7! - 5!/3 \\ 357809 &:= 9 + (0! + 8)! - 7! - 5!/3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 357810 &:= 0 + (1 + 8)! - 7! - 5 \times 3! \\ 357811 &:= 1 + (1 + 8)! - 7! - 5 \times 3! \\ 357812 &:= 2 + (1 + 8)! - 7! - 5 \times 3! \\ 357813 &:= 3 + (1 + 8)! - 7! - 5 \times 3! \\ 357814 &:= 4 + (1 + 8)! - 7! - 5 \times 3! \\ 357815 &:= 5 + (1 + 8)! - 7! - 5 \times 3! \\ 357816 &:= 6 + (1 + 8)! - 7! - 5 \times 3! \\ 357817 &:= 7 + (1 + 8)! - 7! - 5 \times 3! \\ 357818 &:= 8 + (1 + 8)! - 7! - 5 \times 3! \\ 357819 &:= 9 + (1 + 8)! - 7! - 5 \times 3! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 358080 &:= 0 + (8 + 0!)! + 8 \times (5! - 3!) \\ 358081 &:= 1 + (8 + 0!)! + 8 \times (5! - 3!) \\ 358082 &:= 2 + (8 + 0!)! + 8 \times (5! - 3!) \\ 358083 &:= 3 + (8 + 0!)! + 8 \times (5! - 3!) \\ 358084 &:= 4 + (8 + 0!)! + 8 \times (5! - 3!) \\ 358085 &:= 5 + (8 + 0!)! + 8 \times (5! - 3!) \\ 358086 &:= 6 + (8 + 0!)! + 8 \times (5! - 3!) \\ 358087 &:= 7 + (8 + 0!)! + 8 \times (5! - 3!) \\ 358088 &:= 8 + (8 + 0!)! + 8 \times (5! - 3!) \\ 358089 &:= 9 + (8 + 0!)! + 8 \times (5! - 3!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 358590 &:= 0 + 9! + (5 - (8 - 5)!!) \times 3! \\ 358591 &:= 1 + 9! + (5 - (8 - 5)!!) \times 3! \\ 358592 &:= 2 + 9! + (5 - (8 - 5)!!) \times 3! \\ 358593 &:= 3 + 9! + (5 - (8 - 5)!!) \times 3! \\ 358594 &:= 4 + 9! + (5 - (8 - 5)!!) \times 3! \\ 358595 &:= 5 + 9! + (5 - (8 - 5)!!) \times 3! \\ 358596 &:= 6 + 9! + (5 - (8 - 5)!!) \times 3! \\ 358597 &:= 7 + 9! + (5 - (8 - 5)!!) \times 3! \\ 358598 &:= 8 + 9! + (5 - (8 - 5)!!) \times 3! \\ 358599 &:= 9 + 9! + (5 - (8 - 5)!!) \times 3! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 359160 &:= 0 - (6 - 1)! + 9! - 5 \times 3!! \\ 359161 &:= 1 - (6 - 1)! + 9! - 5 \times 3!! \\ 359162 &:= 2 - (6 - 1)! + 9! - 5 \times 3!! \\ 359163 &:= 3 - (6 - 1)! + 9! - 5 \times 3!! \\ 359164 &:= 4 - (6 - 1)! + 9! - 5 \times 3!! \\ 359165 &:= 5 - (6 - 1)! + 9! - 5 \times 3!! \\ 359166 &:= 6 - (6 - 1)! + 9! - 5 \times 3!! \\ 359167 &:= 7 - (6 - 1)! + 9! - 5 \times 3!! \\ 359168 &:= 8 - (6 - 1)! + 9! - 5 \times 3!! \\ 359169 &:= 9 - (6 - 1)! + 9! - 5 \times 3!! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 359280 &:= 0 + (-8 + 2^9 - 5) \times 3!! \\ 359281 &:= 1 + (-8 + 2^9 - 5) \times 3!! \\ 359282 &:= 2 + (-8 + 2^9 - 5) \times 3!! \\ 359283 &:= 3 + (-8 + 2^9 - 5) \times 3!! \\ 359284 &:= 4 + (-8 + 2^9 - 5) \times 3!! \\ 359285 &:= 5 + (-8 + 2^9 - 5) \times 3!! \\ 359286 &:= 6 + (-8 + 2^9 - 5) \times 3!! \\ 359287 &:= 7 + (-8 + 2^9 - 5) \times 3!! \\ 359288 &:= 8 + (-8 + 2^9 - 5) \times 3!! \\ 359289 &:= 9 + (-8 + 2^9 - 5) \times 3!! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 359370 &:= 0 + 7! + (3! + 9^5) \times 3! \\ 359371 &:= 1 + 7! + (3! + 9^5) \times 3! \\ 359372 &:= 2 + 7! + (3! + 9^5) \times 3! \\ 359373 &:= 3 + 7! + (3! + 9^5) \times 3! \\ 359374 &:= 4 + 7! + (3! + 9^5) \times 3! \\ 359375 &:= 5 + 7! + (3! + 9^5) \times 3! \\ 359376 &:= 6 + 7! + (3! + 9^5) \times 3! \\ 359377 &:= 7 + 7! + (3! + 9^5) \times 3! \\ 359378 &:= 8 + 7! + (3! + 9^5) \times 3! \\ 359379 &:= 9 + 7! + (3! + 9^5) \times 3! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 359400 &:= 0 + (0! + 4)! + 9! - 5 \times 3!! \\ 359401 &:= 1 + (0! + 4)! + 9! - 5 \times 3!! \\ 359402 &:= 2 + (0! + 4)! + 9! - 5 \times 3!! \\ 359403 &:= 3 + (0! + 4)! + 9! - 5 \times 3!! \\ 359404 &:= 4 + (0! + 4)! + 9! - 5 \times 3!! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 359405 &:= 5 + (0! + 4)! + 9! - 5 \times 3!! \\ 359406 &:= 6 + (0! + 4)! + 9! - 5 \times 3!! \\ 359407 &:= 7 + (0! + 4)! + 9! - 5 \times 3!! \\ 359408 &:= 8 + (0! + 4)! + 9! - 5 \times 3!! \\ 359409 &:= 9 + (0! + 4)! + 9! - 5 \times 3!! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 359460 &:= 0 + 6!/4 + 9! - 5 \times 3!! \\ 359461 &:= 1 + 6!/4 + 9! - 5 \times 3!! \\ 359462 &:= 2 + 6!/4 + 9! - 5 \times 3!! \\ 359463 &:= 3 + 6!/4 + 9! - 5 \times 3!! \\ 359464 &:= 4 + 6!/4 + 9! - 5 \times 3!! \\ 359465 &:= 5 + 6!/4 + 9! - 5 \times 3!! \\ 359466 &:= 6 + 6!/4 + 9! - 5 \times 3!! \\ 359467 &:= 7 + 6!/4 + 9! - 5 \times 3!! \\ 359468 &:= 8 + 6!/4 + 9! - 5 \times 3!! \\ 359469 &:= 9 + 6!/4 + 9! - 5 \times 3!! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 359640 &:= 0 - 4 \times 6! + 9! - 5! \times 3 \\ 359641 &:= 1 - 4 \times 6! + 9! - 5! \times 3 \\ 359642 &:= 2 - 4 \times 6! + 9! - 5! \times 3 \\ 359643 &:= 3 - 4 \times 6! + 9! - 5! \times 3 \\ 359644 &:= 4 - 4 \times 6! + 9! - 5! \times 3 \\ 359645 &:= 5 - 4 \times 6! + 9! - 5! \times 3 \\ 359646 &:= 6 - 4 \times 6! + 9! - 5! \times 3 \\ 359647 &:= 7 - 4 \times 6! + 9! - 5! \times 3 \\ 359648 &:= 8 - 4 \times 6! + 9! - 5! \times 3 \\ 359649 &:= 9 - 4 \times 6! + 9! - 5! \times 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 360720 &:= 0 + (2 + 7)! - 06! \times 3 \\ 360721 &:= 1 + (2 + 7)! - 06! \times 3 \\ 360722 &:= 2 + (2 + 7)! - 06! \times 3 \\ 360723 &:= 3 + (2 + 7)! - 06! \times 3 \\ 360724 &:= 4 + (2 + 7)! - 06! \times 3 \\ 360725 &:= 5 + (2 + 7)! - 06! \times 3 \\ 360726 &:= 6 + (2 + 7)! - 06! \times 3 \\ 360727 &:= 7 + (2 + 7)! - 06! \times 3 \\ 360728 &:= 8 + (2 + 7)! - 06! \times 3 \\ 360729 &:= 9 + (2 + 7)! - 06! \times 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 360790 &:= 0 + 9! + 70 - 6! \times 3 \\ 360791 &:= 1 + 9! + 70 - 6! \times 3 \\ 360792 &:= 2 + 9! + 70 - 6! \times 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 360793 &:= 3 + 9! + 70 - 6! \times 3 \\ 360794 &:= 4 + 9! + 70 - 6! \times 3 \\ 360795 &:= 5 + 9! + 70 - 6! \times 3 \\ 360796 &:= 6 + 9! + 70 - 6! \times 3 \\ 360797 &:= 7 + 9! + 70 - 6! \times 3 \\ 360798 &:= 8 + 9! + 70 - 6! \times 3 \\ 360799 &:= 9 + 9! + 70 - 6! \times 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 360990 &:= 0 + 9! + (90 - 6!) \times 3 \\ 360991 &:= 1 + 9! + (90 - 6!) \times 3 \\ 360992 &:= 2 + 9! + (90 - 6!) \times 3 \\ 360993 &:= 3 + 9! + (90 - 6!) \times 3 \\ 360994 &:= 4 + 9! + (90 - 6!) \times 3 \\ 360995 &:= 5 + 9! + (90 - 6!) \times 3 \\ 360996 &:= 6 + 9! + (90 - 6!) \times 3 \\ 360997 &:= 7 + 9! + (90 - 6!) \times 3 \\ 360998 &:= 8 + 9! + (90 - 6!) \times 3 \\ 360999 &:= 9 + 9! + (90 - 6!) \times 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 362160 &:= 0 - 6! + 1^2 \times (6 + 3)! \\ 362161 &:= 1 - 6! + 1^2 \times (6 + 3)! \\ 362162 &:= 2 - 6! + 1^2 \times (6 + 3)! \\ 362163 &:= 3 - 6! + 1^2 \times (6 + 3)! \\ 362164 &:= 4 - 6! + 1^2 \times (6 + 3)! \\ 362165 &:= 5 - 6! + 1^2 \times (6 + 3)! \\ 362166 &:= 6 - 6! + 1^2 \times (6 + 3)! \\ 362167 &:= 7 - 6! + 1^2 \times (6 + 3)! \\ 362168 &:= 8 - 6! + 1^2 \times (6 + 3)! \\ 362169 &:= 9 - 6! + 1^2 \times (6 + 3)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 362520 &:= 0 + (-2 + 5)!!/2 + (6 + 3)! \\ 362521 &:= 1 + (-2 + 5)!!/2 + (6 + 3)! \\ 362522 &:= 2 + (-2 + 5)!!/2 + (6 + 3)! \\ 362523 &:= 3 + (-2 + 5)!!/2 + (6 + 3)! \\ 362524 &:= 4 + (-2 + 5)!!/2 + (6 + 3)! \\ 362525 &:= 5 + (-2 + 5)!!/2 + (6 + 3)! \\ 362526 &:= 6 + (-2 + 5)!!/2 + (6 + 3)! \\ 362527 &:= 7 + (-2 + 5)!!/2 + (6 + 3)! \\ 362528 &:= 8 + (-2 + 5)!!/2 + (6 + 3)! \\ 362529 &:= 9 + (-2 + 5)!!/2 + (6 + 3)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 362640 &:= 0 + ((4! - 6)/2)! - 6!/3 \\ 362641 &:= 1 + ((4! - 6)/2)! - 6!/3 \\ 362642 &:= 2 + ((4! - 6)/2)! - 6!/3 \\ 362643 &:= 3 + ((4! - 6)/2)! - 6!/3 \\ 362644 &:= 4 + ((4! - 6)/2)! - 6!/3 \\ 362645 &:= 5 + ((4! - 6)/2)! - 6!/3 \\ 362646 &:= 6 + ((4! - 6)/2)! - 6!/3 \\ 362647 &:= 7 + ((4! - 6)/2)! - 6!/3 \\ 362648 &:= 8 + ((4! - 6)/2)! - 6!/3 \\ 362649 &:= 9 + ((4! - 6)/2)! - 6!/3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 362810 &:= 0 + (1 + 8)! - 2^6 - 3! \\ 362811 &:= 1 + (1 + 8)! - 2^6 - 3! \\ 362812 &:= 2 + (1 + 8)! - 2^6 - 3! \\ 362813 &:= 3 + (1 + 8)! - 2^6 - 3! \\ 362814 &:= 4 + (1 + 8)! - 2^6 - 3! \\ 362815 &:= 5 + (1 + 8)! - 2^6 - 3! \\ 362816 &:= 6 + (1 + 8)! - 2^6 - 3! \\ 362817 &:= 7 + (1 + 8)! - 2^6 - 3! \\ 362818 &:= 8 + (1 + 8)! - 2^6 - 3! \\ 362819 &:= 9 + (1 + 8)! - 2^6 - 3! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 362840 &:= 0 - 4 \times (8 + 2) + (6 + 3)! \\ 362841 &:= 1 - 4 \times (8 + 2) + (6 + 3)! \\ 362842 &:= 2 - 4 \times (8 + 2) + (6 + 3)! \\ 362843 &:= 3 - 4 \times (8 + 2) + (6 + 3)! \\ 362844 &:= 4 - 4 \times (8 + 2) + (6 + 3)! \\ 362845 &:= 5 - 4 \times (8 + 2) + (6 + 3)! \\ 362846 &:= 6 - 4 \times (8 + 2) + (6 + 3)! \\ 362847 &:= 7 - 4 \times (8 + 2) + (6 + 3)! \\ 362848 &:= 8 - 4 \times (8 + 2) + (6 + 3)! \\ 362849 &:= 9 - 4 \times (8 + 2) + (6 + 3)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 362880 &:= 0 + ((8 + 8 + 2)/6 \times 3)! \\ 362881 &:= 1 + ((8 + 8 + 2)/6 \times 3)! \\ 362882 &:= 2 + ((8 + 8 + 2)/6 \times 3)! \\ 362883 &:= 3 + ((8 + 8 + 2)/6 \times 3)! \\ 362884 &:= 4 + ((8 + 8 + 2)/6 \times 3)! \\ 362885 &:= 5 + ((8 + 8 + 2)/6 \times 3)! \\ 362886 &:= 6 + ((8 + 8 + 2)/6 \times 3)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 362887 &:= 7 + ((8 + 8 + 2)/6 \times 3)! \\ 362888 &:= 8 + ((8 + 8 + 2)/6 \times 3)! \\ 362889 &:= 9 + ((8 + 8 + 2)/6 \times 3)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 362890 &:= 0 + 9! - 8 + 2 \times (6 + 3) \\ 362891 &:= 1 + 9! - 8 + 2 \times (6 + 3) \\ 362892 &:= 2 + 9! - 8 + 2 \times (6 + 3) \\ 362893 &:= 3 + 9! - 8 + 2 \times (6 + 3) \\ 362894 &:= 4 + 9! - 8 + 2 \times (6 + 3) \\ 362895 &:= 5 + 9! - 8 + 2 \times (6 + 3) \\ 362896 &:= 6 + 9! - 8 + 2 \times (6 + 3) \\ 362897 &:= 7 + 9! - 8 + 2 \times (6 + 3) \\ 362898 &:= 8 + 9! - 8 + 2 \times (6 + 3) \\ 362899 &:= 9 + 9! - 8 + 2 \times (6 + 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 362900 &:= 0 + 09! + 2 + 6 \times 3 \\ 362901 &:= 1 + 09! + 2 + 6 \times 3 \\ 362902 &:= 2 + 09! + 2 + 6 \times 3 \\ 362903 &:= 3 + 09! + 2 + 6 \times 3 \\ 362904 &:= 4 + 09! + 2 + 6 \times 3 \\ 362905 &:= 5 + 09! + 2 + 6 \times 3 \\ 362906 &:= 6 + 09! + 2 + 6 \times 3 \\ 362907 &:= 7 + 09! + 2 + 6 \times 3 \\ 362908 &:= 8 + 09! + 2 + 6 \times 3 \\ 362909 &:= 9 + 09! + 2 + 6 \times 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 362990 &:= 0 + 9! + 92 + 6 \times 3 \\ 362991 &:= 1 + 9! + 92 + 6 \times 3 \\ 362992 &:= 2 + 9! + 92 + 6 \times 3 \\ 362993 &:= 3 + 9! + 92 + 6 \times 3 \\ 362994 &:= 4 + 9! + 92 + 6 \times 3 \\ 362995 &:= 5 + 9! + 92 + 6 \times 3 \\ 362996 &:= 6 + 9! + 92 + 6 \times 3 \\ 362997 &:= 7 + 9! + 92 + 6 \times 3 \\ 362998 &:= 8 + 9! + 92 + 6 \times 3 \\ 362999 &:= 9 + 9! + 92 + 6 \times 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 363060 &:= 0 + 60 \times 3 + (6 + 3)! \\ 363061 &:= 1 + 60 \times 3 + (6 + 3)! \\ 363062 &:= 2 + 60 \times 3 + (6 + 3)! \\ 363063 &:= 3 + 60 \times 3 + (6 + 3)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 363064 &:= 4 + 60 \times 3 + (6 + 3)! \\ 363065 &:= 5 + 60 \times 3 + (6 + 3)! \\ 363066 &:= 6 + 60 \times 3 + (6 + 3)! \\ 363067 &:= 7 + 60 \times 3 + (6 + 3)! \\ 363068 &:= 8 + 60 \times 3 + (6 + 3)! \\ 363069 &:= 9 + 60 \times 3 + (6 + 3)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 363090 &:= 0 + 9! - 03! + 6^3 \\ 363091 &:= 1 + 9! - 03! + 6^3 \\ 363092 &:= 2 + 9! - 03! + 6^3 \\ 363093 &:= 3 + 9! - 03! + 6^3 \\ 363094 &:= 4 + 9! - 03! + 6^3 \\ 363095 &:= 5 + 9! - 03! + 6^3 \\ 363096 &:= 6 + 9! - 03! + 6^3 \\ 363097 &:= 7 + 9! - 03! + 6^3 \\ 363098 &:= 8 + 9! - 03! + 6^3 \\ 363099 &:= 9 + 9! - 03! + 6^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 363120 &:= 0 + ((2 + 1) \times 3)! + 6!/3 \\ 363121 &:= 1 + ((2 + 1) \times 3)! + 6!/3 \\ 363122 &:= 2 + ((2 + 1) \times 3)! + 6!/3 \\ 363123 &:= 3 + ((2 + 1) \times 3)! + 6!/3 \\ 363124 &:= 4 + ((2 + 1) \times 3)! + 6!/3 \\ 363125 &:= 5 + ((2 + 1) \times 3)! + 6!/3 \\ 363126 &:= 6 + ((2 + 1) \times 3)! + 6!/3 \\ 363127 &:= 7 + ((2 + 1) \times 3)! + 6!/3 \\ 363128 &:= 8 + ((2 + 1) \times 3)! + 6!/3 \\ 363129 &:= 9 + ((2 + 1) \times 3)! + 6!/3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 363390 &:= 0 + 9! + (3 \times 3)!/6! + 3! \\ 363391 &:= 1 + 9! + (3 \times 3)!/6! + 3! \\ 363392 &:= 2 + 9! + (3 \times 3)!/6! + 3! \\ 363393 &:= 3 + 9! + (3 \times 3)!/6! + 3! \\ 363394 &:= 4 + 9! + (3 \times 3)!/6! + 3! \\ 363395 &:= 5 + 9! + (3 \times 3)!/6! + 3! \\ 363396 &:= 6 + 9! + (3 \times 3)!/6! + 3! \\ 363397 &:= 7 + 9! + (3 \times 3)!/6! + 3! \\ 363398 &:= 8 + 9! + (3 \times 3)!/6! + 3! \\ 363399 &:= 9 + 9! + (3 \times 3)!/6! + 3! \end{aligned}$$

$$363600 := 0 + 06! + (3^{6/3})!$$

$$363601 := 1 + 06! + (3^{6/3})!$$

$$363602 := 2 + 06! + (3^{6/3})!$$

$$363603 := 3 + 06! + (3^{6/3})!$$

$$363604 := 4 + 06! + (3^{6/3})!$$

$$363605 := 5 + 06! + (3^{6/3})!$$

$$363606 := 6 + 06! + (3^{6/3})!$$

$$363607 := 7 + 06! + (3^{6/3})!$$

$$363608 := 8 + 06! + (3^{6/3})!$$

$$363609 := 9 + 06! + (3^{6/3})!$$

$$363960 := 0 + 6! \times 9/3! + (6 + 3)!$$

$$363961 := 1 + 6! \times 9/3! + (6 + 3)!$$

$$363962 := 2 + 6! \times 9/3! + (6 + 3)!$$

$$363963 := 3 + 6! \times 9/3! + (6 + 3)!$$

$$363964 := 4 + 6! \times 9/3! + (6 + 3)!$$

$$363965 := 5 + 6! \times 9/3! + (6 + 3)!$$

$$363966 := 6 + 6! \times 9/3! + (6 + 3)!$$

$$363967 := 7 + 6! \times 9/3! + (6 + 3)!$$

$$363968 := 8 + 6! \times 9/3! + (6 + 3)!$$

$$363969 := 9 + 6! \times 9/3! + (6 + 3)!$$

$$365040 := 0 + (4 + 05)! + 6! \times 3$$

$$365041 := 1 + (4 + 05)! + 6! \times 3$$

$$365042 := 2 + (4 + 05)! + 6! \times 3$$

$$365043 := 3 + (4 + 05)! + 6! \times 3$$

$$365044 := 4 + (4 + 05)! + 6! \times 3$$

$$365045 := 5 + (4 + 05)! + 6! \times 3$$

$$365046 := 6 + (4 + 05)! + 6! \times 3$$

$$365047 := 7 + (4 + 05)! + 6! \times 3$$

$$365048 := 8 + (4 + 05)! + 6! \times 3$$

$$365049 := 9 + (4 + 05)! + 6! \times 3$$

$$365640 := 0 + 4 \times 6! - 5! + (6 + 3)!$$

$$365641 := 1 + 4 \times 6! - 5! + (6 + 3)!$$

$$365642 := 2 + 4 \times 6! - 5! + (6 + 3)!$$

$$365643 := 3 + 4 \times 6! - 5! + (6 + 3)!$$

$$365644 := 4 + 4 \times 6! - 5! + (6 + 3)!$$

$$365645 := 5 + 4 \times 6! - 5! + (6 + 3)!$$

$$365646 := 6 + 4 \times 6! - 5! + (6 + 3)!$$

$$365647 := 7 + 4 \times 6! - 5! + (6 + 3)!$$

$$365648 := 8 + 4 \times 6! - 5! + (6 + 3)!$$

$$365649 := 9 + 4 \times 6! - 5! + (6 + 3)!$$

$$367200 := 0 + (02 + 7)! + 6! \times 3!$$

$$367201 := 1 + (02 + 7)! + 6! \times 3!$$

$$367202 := 2 + (02 + 7)! + 6! \times 3!$$

$$367203 := 3 + (02 + 7)! + 6! \times 3!$$

$$367204 := 4 + (02 + 7)! + 6! \times 3!$$

$$367205 := 5 + (02 + 7)! + 6! \times 3!$$

$$367206 := 6 + (02 + 7)! + 6! \times 3!$$

$$367207 := 7 + (02 + 7)! + 6! \times 3!$$

$$367208 := 8 + (02 + 7)! + 6! \times 3!$$

$$367209 := 9 + (02 + 7)! + 6! \times 3!$$

$$367800 := 0 + (0! + 8)! + 7! - 6!/3!$$

$$367801 := 1 + (0! + 8)! + 7! - 6!/3!$$

$$367802 := 2 + (0! + 8)! + 7! - 6!/3!$$

$$367803 := 3 + (0! + 8)! + 7! - 6!/3!$$

$$367804 := 4 + (0! + 8)! + 7! - 6!/3!$$

$$367805 := 5 + (0! + 8)! + 7! - 6!/3!$$

$$367806 := 6 + (0! + 8)! + 7! - 6!/3!$$

$$367807 := 7 + (0! + 8)! + 7! - 6!/3!$$

$$367808 := 8 + (0! + 8)! + 7! - 6!/3!$$

$$367809 := 9 + (0! + 8)! + 7! - 6!/3!$$

$$367830 := 0 - 3!/8 + 7! + (6 + 3)!$$

$$367831 := 1 - 3!/8 + 7! + (6 + 3)!$$

$$367832 := 2 - 3!/8 + 7! + (6 + 3)!$$

$$367833 := 3 - 3!/8 + 7! + (6 + 3)!$$

$$367834 := 4 - 3!/8 + 7! + (6 + 3)!$$

$$367835 := 5 - 3!/8 + 7! + (6 + 3)!$$

$$367836 := 6 - 3!/8 + 7! + (6 + 3)!$$

$$367837 := 7 - 3!/8 + 7! + (6 + 3)!$$

$$367838 := 8 - 3!/8 + 7! + (6 + 3)!$$

$$367839 := 9 - 3!/8 + 7! + (6 + 3)!$$

$$367900 := 0 + 0! + 9! + 7 \times (6! - 3)$$

$$367901 := 1 + 0! + 9! + 7 \times (6! - 3)$$

$$367902 := 2 + 0! + 9! + 7 \times (6! - 3)$$

$$367903 := 3 + 0! + 9! + 7 \times (6! - 3)$$

$$367904 := 4 + 0! + 9! + 7 \times (6! - 3)$$

$$367905 := 5 + 0! + 9! + 7 \times (6! - 3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 367906 &:= 6 + 0! + 9! + 7 \times (6! - 3) \\ 367907 &:= 7 + 0! + 9! + 7 \times (6! - 3) \\ 367908 &:= 8 + 0! + 9! + 7 \times (6! - 3) \\ 367909 &:= 9 + 0! + 9! + 7 \times (6! - 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 369390 &:= 0 + 9! + 3 + 9 \times (6! + 3) \\ 369391 &:= 1 + 9! + 3 + 9 \times (6! + 3) \\ 369392 &:= 2 + 9! + 3 + 9 \times (6! + 3) \\ 369393 &:= 3 + 9! + 3 + 9 \times (6! + 3) \\ 369394 &:= 4 + 9! + 3 + 9 \times (6! + 3) \\ 369395 &:= 5 + 9! + 3 + 9 \times (6! + 3) \\ 369396 &:= 6 + 9! + 3 + 9 \times (6! + 3) \\ 369397 &:= 7 + 9! + 3 + 9 \times (6! + 3) \\ 369398 &:= 8 + 9! + 3 + 9 \times (6! + 3) \\ 369399 &:= 9 + 9! + 3 + 9 \times (6! + 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 369580 &:= 0 + (8! - 5! + 9! \times 6) / 3! \\ 369581 &:= 1 + (8! - 5! + 9! \times 6) / 3! \\ 369582 &:= 2 + (8! - 5! + 9! \times 6) / 3! \\ 369583 &:= 3 + (8! - 5! + 9! \times 6) / 3! \\ 369584 &:= 4 + (8! - 5! + 9! \times 6) / 3! \\ 369585 &:= 5 + (8! - 5! + 9! \times 6) / 3! \\ 369586 &:= 6 + (8! - 5! + 9! \times 6) / 3! \\ 369587 &:= 7 + (8! - 5! + 9! \times 6) / 3! \\ 369588 &:= 8 + (8! - 5! + 9! \times 6) / 3! \\ 369589 &:= 9 + (8! - 5! + 9! \times 6) / 3! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 372960 &:= 0 - 6 + 9! + 2 \times 7! + 3! \\ 372961 &:= 1 - 6 + 9! + 2 \times 7! + 3! \\ 372962 &:= 2 - 6 + 9! + 2 \times 7! + 3! \\ 372963 &:= 3 - 6 + 9! + 2 \times 7! + 3! \\ 372964 &:= 4 - 6 + 9! + 2 \times 7! + 3! \\ 372965 &:= 5 - 6 + 9! + 2 \times 7! + 3! \\ 372966 &:= 6 - 6 + 9! + 2 \times 7! + 3! \\ 372967 &:= 7 - 6 + 9! + 2 \times 7! + 3! \\ 372968 &:= 8 - 6 + 9! + 2 \times 7! + 3! \\ 372969 &:= 9 - 6 + 9! + 2 \times 7! + 3! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 372980 &:= 0 + 8 + 9! + 2 \times (7! + 3!) \\ 372981 &:= 1 + 8 + 9! + 2 \times (7! + 3!) \\ 372982 &:= 2 + 8 + 9! + 2 \times (7! + 3!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 372983 &:= 3 + 8 + 9! + 2 \times (7! + 3!) \\ 372984 &:= 4 + 8 + 9! + 2 \times (7! + 3!) \\ 372985 &:= 5 + 8 + 9! + 2 \times (7! + 3!) \\ 372986 &:= 6 + 8 + 9! + 2 \times (7! + 3!) \\ 372987 &:= 7 + 8 + 9! + 2 \times (7! + 3!) \\ 372988 &:= 8 + 8 + 9! + 2 \times (7! + 3!) \\ 372989 &:= 9 + 8 + 9! + 2 \times (7! + 3!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 373240 &:= 0 + 4 \times (-2 + 3!^7 / 3) \\ 373241 &:= 1 + 4 \times (-2 + 3!^7 / 3) \\ 373242 &:= 2 + 4 \times (-2 + 3!^7 / 3) \\ 373243 &:= 3 + 4 \times (-2 + 3!^7 / 3) \\ 373244 &:= 4 + 4 \times (-2 + 3!^7 / 3) \\ 373245 &:= 5 + 4 \times (-2 + 3!^7 / 3) \\ 373246 &:= 6 + 4 \times (-2 + 3!^7 / 3) \\ 373247 &:= 7 + 4 \times (-2 + 3!^7 / 3) \\ 373248 &:= 8 + 4 \times (-2 + 3!^7 / 3) \\ 373249 &:= 9 + 4 \times (-2 + 3!^7 / 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 373680 &:= 0 + (8^{6-3} + 7) \times 3!! \\ 373681 &:= 1 + (8^{6-3} + 7) \times 3!! \\ 373682 &:= 2 + (8^{6-3} + 7) \times 3!! \\ 373683 &:= 3 + (8^{6-3} + 7) \times 3!! \\ 373684 &:= 4 + (8^{6-3} + 7) \times 3!! \\ 373685 &:= 5 + (8^{6-3} + 7) \times 3!! \\ 373686 &:= 6 + (8^{6-3} + 7) \times 3!! \\ 373687 &:= 7 + (8^{6-3} + 7) \times 3!! \\ 373688 &:= 8 + (8^{6-3} + 7) \times 3!! \\ 373689 &:= 9 + (8^{6-3} + 7) \times 3!! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 375690 &:= 0 + 9! + 6^5 + 7! - 3! \\ 375691 &:= 1 + 9! + 6^5 + 7! - 3! \\ 375692 &:= 2 + 9! + 6^5 + 7! - 3! \\ 375693 &:= 3 + 9! + 6^5 + 7! - 3! \\ 375694 &:= 4 + 9! + 6^5 + 7! - 3! \\ 375695 &:= 5 + 9! + 6^5 + 7! - 3! \\ 375696 &:= 6 + 9! + 6^5 + 7! - 3! \\ 375697 &:= 7 + 9! + 6^5 + 7! - 3! \\ 375698 &:= 8 + 9! + 6^5 + 7! - 3! \end{aligned}$$

$$375699 := 9 + 9! + 6^5 + 7! - 3!$$

$$377280 := 0 + (82 - 7) \times 7! - 3!!$$

$$377281 := 1 + (82 - 7) \times 7! - 3!!$$

$$377282 := 2 + (82 - 7) \times 7! - 3!!$$

$$377283 := 3 + (82 - 7) \times 7! - 3!!$$

$$377284 := 4 + (82 - 7) \times 7! - 3!!$$

$$377285 := 5 + (82 - 7) \times 7! - 3!!$$

$$377286 := 6 + (82 - 7) \times 7! - 3!!$$

$$377287 := 7 + (82 - 7) \times 7! - 3!!$$

$$377288 := 8 + (82 - 7) \times 7! - 3!!$$

$$377289 := 9 + (82 - 7) \times 7! - 3!!$$

$$378000 := 0 + (0! + 08)! + 7! \times 3$$

$$378001 := 1 + (0! + 08)! + 7! \times 3$$

$$378002 := 2 + (0! + 08)! + 7! \times 3$$

$$378003 := 3 + (0! + 08)! + 7! \times 3$$

$$378004 := 4 + (0! + 08)! + 7! \times 3$$

$$378005 := 5 + (0! + 08)! + 7! \times 3$$

$$378006 := 6 + (0! + 08)! + 7! \times 3$$

$$378007 := 7 + (0! + 08)! + 7! \times 3$$

$$378008 := 8 + (0! + 08)! + 7! \times 3$$

$$378009 := 9 + (0! + 08)! + 7! \times 3$$

$$383760 := 0 + 6! \times (7 \times 3 + 8^3)$$

$$383761 := 1 + 6! \times (7 \times 3 + 8^3)$$

$$383762 := 2 + 6! \times (7 \times 3 + 8^3)$$

$$383763 := 3 + 6! \times (7 \times 3 + 8^3)$$

$$383764 := 4 + 6! \times (7 \times 3 + 8^3)$$

$$383765 := 5 + 6! \times (7 \times 3 + 8^3)$$

$$383766 := 6 + 6! \times (7 \times 3 + 8^3)$$

$$383767 := 7 + 6! \times (7 \times 3 + 8^3)$$

$$383768 := 8 + 6! \times (7 \times 3 + 8^3)$$

$$383769 := 9 + 6! \times (7 \times 3 + 8^3)$$

$$386640 := 0 + (-4 + 6!) \times 6!/8 \times 3!$$

$$386641 := 1 + (-4 + 6!) \times 6!/8 \times 3!$$

$$386642 := 2 + (-4 + 6!) \times 6!/8 \times 3!$$

$$386643 := 3 + (-4 + 6!) \times 6!/8 \times 3!$$

$$386644 := 4 + (-4 + 6!) \times 6!/8 \times 3!$$

$$386645 := 5 + (-4 + 6!) \times 6!/8 \times 3!$$

$$386646 := 6 + (-4 + 6!) \times 6!/8 \times 3!$$

$$386647 := 7 + (-4 + 6!) \times 6!/8 \times 3!$$

$$386648 := 8 + (-4 + 6!) \times 6!/8 \times 3!$$

$$386649 := 9 + (-4 + 6!) \times 6!/8 \times 3!$$

$$388080 := 0 + (-(8 - 0)!) + 8! \times (8 + 3)$$

$$388081 := 1 + (-(8 - 0)!) + 8! \times (8 + 3)$$

$$388082 := 2 + (-(8 - 0)!) + 8! \times (8 + 3)$$

$$388083 := 3 + (-(8 - 0)!) + 8! \times (8 + 3)$$

$$388084 := 4 + (-(8 - 0)!) + 8! \times (8 + 3)$$

$$388085 := 5 + (-(8 - 0)!) + 8! \times (8 + 3)$$

$$388086 := 6 + (-(8 - 0)!) + 8! \times (8 + 3)$$

$$388087 := 7 + (-(8 - 0)!) + 8! \times (8 + 3)$$

$$388088 := 8 + (-(8 - 0)!) + 8! \times (8 + 3)$$

$$388089 := 9 + (-(8 - 0)!) + 8! \times (8 + 3)$$

$$389760 := 0 + (67 - 9) \times 8!/3!$$

$$389761 := 1 + (67 - 9) \times 8!/3!$$

$$389762 := 2 + (67 - 9) \times 8!/3!$$

$$389763 := 3 + (67 - 9) \times 8!/3!$$

$$389764 := 4 + (67 - 9) \times 8!/3!$$

$$389765 := 5 + (67 - 9) \times 8!/3!$$

$$389766 := 6 + (67 - 9) \times 8!/3!$$

$$389767 := 7 + (67 - 9) \times 8!/3!$$

$$389768 := 8 + (67 - 9) \times 8!/3!$$

$$389769 := 9 + (67 - 9) \times 8!/3!$$

$$393540 := 0 + 4 \times 5 \times (3^9 - 3!)$$

$$393541 := 1 + 4 \times 5 \times (3^9 - 3!)$$

$$393542 := 2 + 4 \times 5 \times (3^9 - 3!)$$

$$393543 := 3 + 4 \times 5 \times (3^9 - 3!)$$

$$393544 := 4 + 4 \times 5 \times (3^9 - 3!)$$

$$393545 := 5 + 4 \times 5 \times (3^9 - 3!)$$

$$393546 := 6 + 4 \times 5 \times (3^9 - 3!)$$

$$393547 := 7 + 4 \times 5 \times (3^9 - 3!)$$

$$393548 := 8 + 4 \times 5 \times (3^9 - 3!)$$

$$393549 := 9 + 4 \times 5 \times (3^9 - 3!)$$

$$393660 := 0 + 6!/6 \times 3^9/3!$$

$$393661 := 1 + 6!/6 \times 3^9/3!$$

$$\begin{aligned} 393662 &:= 2 + 6!/6 \times 3^9/3! \\ 393663 &:= 3 + 6!/6 \times 3^9/3! \\ 393664 &:= 4 + 6!/6 \times 3^9/3! \\ 393665 &:= 5 + 6!/6 \times 3^9/3! \\ 393666 &:= 6 + 6!/6 \times 3^9/3! \\ 393667 &:= 7 + 6!/6 \times 3^9/3! \\ 393668 &:= 8 + 6!/6 \times 3^9/3! \\ 393669 &:= 9 + 6!/6 \times 3^9/3! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 398880 &:= 0 - 8!/8 + 8! + 9! + 3!! \\ 398881 &:= 1 - 8!/8 + 8! + 9! + 3!! \\ 398882 &:= 2 - 8!/8 + 8! + 9! + 3!! \\ 398883 &:= 3 - 8!/8 + 8! + 9! + 3!! \\ 398884 &:= 4 - 8!/8 + 8! + 9! + 3!! \\ 398885 &:= 5 - 8!/8 + 8! + 9! + 3!! \\ 398886 &:= 6 - 8!/8 + 8! + 9! + 3!! \\ 398887 &:= 7 - 8!/8 + 8! + 9! + 3!! \\ 398888 &:= 8 - 8!/8 + 8! + 9! + 3!! \\ 398889 &:= 9 - 8!/8 + 8! + 9! + 3!! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 413280 &:= 0 + 82 \times (3 \times 1 + 4)! \\ 413281 &:= 1 + 82 \times (3 \times 1 + 4)! \\ 413282 &:= 2 + 82 \times (3 \times 1 + 4)! \\ 413283 &:= 3 + 82 \times (3 \times 1 + 4)! \\ 413284 &:= 4 + 82 \times (3 \times 1 + 4)! \\ 413285 &:= 5 + 82 \times (3 \times 1 + 4)! \\ 413286 &:= 6 + 82 \times (3 \times 1 + 4)! \\ 413287 &:= 7 + 82 \times (3 \times 1 + 4)! \\ 413288 &:= 8 + 82 \times (3 \times 1 + 4)! \\ 413289 &:= 9 + 82 \times (3 \times 1 + 4)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 419760 &:= 0 + 6! \times (7!/9 - 1 + 4!) \\ 419761 &:= 1 + 6! \times (7!/9 - 1 + 4!) \\ 419762 &:= 2 + 6! \times (7!/9 - 1 + 4!) \\ 419763 &:= 3 + 6! \times (7!/9 - 1 + 4!) \\ 419764 &:= 4 + 6! \times (7!/9 - 1 + 4!) \\ 419765 &:= 5 + 6! \times (7!/9 - 1 + 4!) \\ 419766 &:= 6 + 6! \times (7!/9 - 1 + 4!) \\ 419767 &:= 7 + 6! \times (7!/9 - 1 + 4!) \\ 419768 &:= 8 + 6! \times (7!/9 - 1 + 4!) \end{aligned}$$

$$419769 := 9 + 6! \times (7!/9 - 1 + 4!)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 423360 &:= 0 + 6! \times (3!! + 3! \times (2 - 4!)) \\ 423361 &:= 1 + 6! \times (3!! + 3! \times (2 - 4!)) \\ 423362 &:= 2 + 6! \times (3!! + 3! \times (2 - 4!)) \\ 423363 &:= 3 + 6! \times (3!! + 3! \times (2 - 4!)) \\ 423364 &:= 4 + 6! \times (3!! + 3! \times (2 - 4!)) \\ 423365 &:= 5 + 6! \times (3!! + 3! \times (2 - 4!)) \\ 423366 &:= 6 + 6! \times (3!! + 3! \times (2 - 4!)) \\ 423367 &:= 7 + 6! \times (3!! + 3! \times (2 - 4!)) \\ 423368 &:= 8 + 6! \times (3!! + 3! \times (2 - 4!)) \\ 423369 &:= 9 + 6! \times (3!! + 3! \times (2 - 4!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 431400 &:= 0 + (0! + 4!) \times (-1 + 3!!) \times 4! \\ 431401 &:= 1 + (0! + 4!) \times (-1 + 3!!) \times 4! \\ 431402 &:= 2 + (0! + 4!) \times (-1 + 3!!) \times 4! \\ 431403 &:= 3 + (0! + 4!) \times (-1 + 3!!) \times 4! \\ 431404 &:= 4 + (0! + 4!) \times (-1 + 3!!) \times 4! \\ 431405 &:= 5 + (0! + 4!) \times (-1 + 3!!) \times 4! \\ 431406 &:= 6 + (0! + 4!) \times (-1 + 3!!) \times 4! \\ 431407 &:= 7 + (0! + 4!) \times (-1 + 3!!) \times 4! \\ 431408 &:= 8 + (0! + 4!) \times (-1 + 3!!) \times 4! \\ 431409 &:= 9 + (0! + 4!) \times (-1 + 3!!) \times 4! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 432000 &:= 0 + (-0! + (0! + 2)!)^3/4 \\ 432001 &:= 1 + (-0! + (0! + 2)!)^3/4 \\ 432002 &:= 2 + (-0! + (0! + 2)!)^3/4 \\ 432003 &:= 3 + (-0! + (0! + 2)!)^3/4 \\ 432004 &:= 4 + (-0! + (0! + 2)!)^3/4 \\ 432005 &:= 5 + (-0! + (0! + 2)!)^3/4 \\ 432006 &:= 6 + (-0! + (0! + 2)!)^3/4 \\ 432007 &:= 7 + (-0! + (0! + 2)!)^3/4 \\ 432008 &:= 8 + (-0! + (0! + 2)!)^3/4 \\ 432009 &:= 9 + (-0! + (0! + 2)!)^3/4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 434400 &:= 0 + (0! + 4!) \times (4 + 3!!) \times 4! \\ 434401 &:= 1 + (0! + 4!) \times (4 + 3!!) \times 4! \\ 434402 &:= 2 + (0! + 4!) \times (4 + 3!!) \times 4! \\ 434403 &:= 3 + (0! + 4!) \times (4 + 3!!) \times 4! \\ 434404 &:= 4 + (0! + 4!) \times (4 + 3!!) \times 4! \\ 434405 &:= 5 + (0! + 4!) \times (4 + 3!!) \times 4! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}434406 &:= 6 + (0! + 4!) \times (4 + 3!!) \times 4! \\434407 &:= 7 + (0! + 4!) \times (4 + 3!!) \times 4! \\434408 &:= 8 + (0! + 4!) \times (4 + 3!!) \times 4! \\434409 &:= 9 + (0! + 4!) \times (4 + 3!!) \times 4!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}446400 &:= 0 + (0! + 4!) \times (6! + 4!) \times 4! \\446401 &:= 1 + (0! + 4!) \times (6! + 4!) \times 4! \\446402 &:= 2 + (0! + 4!) \times (6! + 4!) \times 4! \\446403 &:= 3 + (0! + 4!) \times (6! + 4!) \times 4! \\446404 &:= 4 + (0! + 4!) \times (6! + 4!) \times 4! \\446405 &:= 5 + (0! + 4!) \times (6! + 4!) \times 4! \\446406 &:= 6 + (0! + 4!) \times (6! + 4!) \times 4! \\446407 &:= 7 + (0! + 4!) \times (6! + 4!) \times 4! \\446408 &:= 8 + (0! + 4!) \times (6! + 4!) \times 4! \\446409 &:= 9 + (0! + 4!) \times (6! + 4!) \times 4!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}447930 &:= 0 + (3!! - 9) \times 7! / (4 + 4) \\447931 &:= 1 + (3!! - 9) \times 7! / (4 + 4) \\447932 &:= 2 + (3!! - 9) \times 7! / (4 + 4) \\447933 &:= 3 + (3!! - 9) \times 7! / (4 + 4) \\447934 &:= 4 + (3!! - 9) \times 7! / (4 + 4) \\447935 &:= 5 + (3!! - 9) \times 7! / (4 + 4) \\447936 &:= 6 + (3!! - 9) \times 7! / (4 + 4) \\447937 &:= 7 + (3!! - 9) \times 7! / (4 + 4) \\447938 &:= 8 + (3!! - 9) \times 7! / (4 + 4) \\447939 &:= 9 + (3!! - 9) \times 7! / (4 + 4)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}450000 &:= 0 + (0! + 0! + 0!)!! \times 5^4 \\450001 &:= 1 + (0! + 0! + 0!)!! \times 5^4 \\450002 &:= 2 + (0! + 0! + 0!)!! \times 5^4 \\450003 &:= 3 + (0! + 0! + 0!)!! \times 5^4 \\450004 &:= 4 + (0! + 0! + 0!)!! \times 5^4 \\450005 &:= 5 + (0! + 0! + 0!)!! \times 5^4 \\450006 &:= 6 + (0! + 0! + 0!)!! \times 5^4 \\450007 &:= 7 + (0! + 0! + 0!)!! \times 5^4 \\450008 &:= 8 + (0! + 0! + 0!)!! \times 5^4 \\450009 &:= 9 + (0! + 0! + 0!)!! \times 5^4\end{aligned}$$

$$452160 := 0 + 6! \times (1 + 2 + 5^4)$$

$$\begin{aligned}452161 &:= 1 + 6! \times (1 + 2 + 5^4) \\452162 &:= 2 + 6! \times (1 + 2 + 5^4) \\452163 &:= 3 + 6! \times (1 + 2 + 5^4) \\452164 &:= 4 + 6! \times (1 + 2 + 5^4) \\452165 &:= 5 + 6! \times (1 + 2 + 5^4) \\452166 &:= 6 + 6! \times (1 + 2 + 5^4) \\452167 &:= 7 + 6! \times (1 + 2 + 5^4) \\452168 &:= 8 + 6! \times (1 + 2 + 5^4) \\452169 &:= 9 + 6! \times (1 + 2 + 5^4)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}453570 &:= 0 + (7! \times 5! \times 3 - 5!) / 4 \\453571 &:= 1 + (7! \times 5! \times 3 - 5!) / 4 \\453572 &:= 2 + (7! \times 5! \times 3 - 5!) / 4 \\453573 &:= 3 + (7! \times 5! \times 3 - 5!) / 4 \\453574 &:= 4 + (7! \times 5! \times 3 - 5!) / 4 \\453575 &:= 5 + (7! \times 5! \times 3 - 5!) / 4 \\453576 &:= 6 + (7! \times 5! \times 3 - 5!) / 4 \\453577 &:= 7 + (7! \times 5! \times 3 - 5!) / 4 \\453578 &:= 8 + (7! \times 5! \times 3 - 5!) / 4 \\453579 &:= 9 + (7! \times 5! \times 3 - 5!) / 4\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}453600 &:= 0 + (06 + 3)! \times 5/4 \\453601 &:= 1 + (06 + 3)! \times 5/4 \\453602 &:= 2 + (06 + 3)! \times 5/4 \\453603 &:= 3 + (06 + 3)! \times 5/4 \\453604 &:= 4 + (06 + 3)! \times 5/4 \\453605 &:= 5 + (06 + 3)! \times 5/4 \\453606 &:= 6 + (06 + 3)! \times 5/4 \\453607 &:= 7 + (06 + 3)! \times 5/4 \\453608 &:= 8 + (06 + 3)! \times 5/4 \\453609 &:= 9 + (06 + 3)! \times 5/4\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}453750 &:= 0 + (5 + 7! \times 3) \times 5! / 4 \\453751 &:= 1 + (5 + 7! \times 3) \times 5! / 4 \\453752 &:= 2 + (5 + 7! \times 3) \times 5! / 4 \\453753 &:= 3 + (5 + 7! \times 3) \times 5! / 4 \\453754 &:= 4 + (5 + 7! \times 3) \times 5! / 4 \\453755 &:= 5 + (5 + 7! \times 3) \times 5! / 4 \\453756 &:= 6 + (5 + 7! \times 3) \times 5! / 4 \\453757 &:= 7 + (5 + 7! \times 3) \times 5! / 4\end{aligned}$$

$$453758 := 8 + (5 + 7! \times 3) \times 5!/4$$

$$453759 := 9 + (5 + 7! \times 3) \times 5!/4$$

$$456250 := 0 + (5 \times 2 + 6!) \times 5^4$$

$$456251 := 1 + (5 \times 2 + 6!) \times 5^4$$

$$456252 := 2 + (5 \times 2 + 6!) \times 5^4$$

$$456253 := 3 + (5 \times 2 + 6!) \times 5^4$$

$$456254 := 4 + (5 \times 2 + 6!) \times 5^4$$

$$456255 := 5 + (5 \times 2 + 6!) \times 5^4$$

$$456256 := 6 + (5 \times 2 + 6!) \times 5^4$$

$$456257 := 7 + (5 \times 2 + 6!) \times 5^4$$

$$456258 := 8 + (5 \times 2 + 6!) \times 5^4$$

$$456259 := 9 + (5 \times 2 + 6!) \times 5^4$$

$$459650 := 0 + (5 + 6!) \times (9 + 5^4)$$

$$459651 := 1 + (5 + 6!) \times (9 + 5^4)$$

$$459652 := 2 + (5 + 6!) \times (9 + 5^4)$$

$$459653 := 3 + (5 + 6!) \times (9 + 5^4)$$

$$459654 := 4 + (5 + 6!) \times (9 + 5^4)$$

$$459655 := 5 + (5 + 6!) \times (9 + 5^4)$$

$$459656 := 6 + (5 + 6!) \times (9 + 5^4)$$

$$459657 := 7 + (5 + 6!) \times (9 + 5^4)$$

$$459658 := 8 + (5 + 6!) \times (9 + 5^4)$$

$$459659 := 9 + (5 + 6!) \times (9 + 5^4)$$

$$459750 := 0 + (-5! + 7! + 9!) \times 5/4$$

$$459751 := 1 + (-5! + 7! + 9!) \times 5/4$$

$$459752 := 2 + (-5! + 7! + 9!) \times 5/4$$

$$459753 := 3 + (-5! + 7! + 9!) \times 5/4$$

$$459754 := 4 + (-5! + 7! + 9!) \times 5/4$$

$$459755 := 5 + (-5! + 7! + 9!) \times 5/4$$

$$459756 := 6 + (-5! + 7! + 9!) \times 5/4$$

$$459757 := 7 + (-5! + 7! + 9!) \times 5/4$$

$$459758 := 8 + (-5! + 7! + 9!) \times 5/4$$

$$459759 := 9 + (-5! + 7! + 9!) \times 5/4$$

$$462960 := 0 + 6! \times (-9^2 + 6! + 4)$$

$$462961 := 1 + 6! \times (-9^2 + 6! + 4)$$

$$462962 := 2 + 6! \times (-9^2 + 6! + 4)$$

$$462963 := 3 + 6! \times (-9^2 + 6! + 4)$$

$$462964 := 4 + 6! \times (-9^2 + 6! + 4)$$

$$462965 := 5 + 6! \times (-9^2 + 6! + 4)$$

$$462966 := 6 + 6! \times (-9^2 + 6! + 4)$$

$$462967 := 7 + 6! \times (-9^2 + 6! + 4)$$

$$462968 := 8 + 6! \times (-9^2 + 6! + 4)$$

$$462969 := 9 + 6! \times (-9^2 + 6! + 4)$$

$$465360 := 0 + (6^{3!} - 5!) \times (6 + 4)$$

$$465361 := 1 + (6^{3!} - 5!) \times (6 + 4)$$

$$465362 := 2 + (6^{3!} - 5!) \times (6 + 4)$$

$$465363 := 3 + (6^{3!} - 5!) \times (6 + 4)$$

$$465364 := 4 + (6^{3!} - 5!) \times (6 + 4)$$

$$465365 := 5 + (6^{3!} - 5!) \times (6 + 4)$$

$$465366 := 6 + (6^{3!} - 5!) \times (6 + 4)$$

$$465367 := 7 + (6^{3!} - 5!) \times (6 + 4)$$

$$465368 := 8 + (6^{3!} - 5!) \times (6 + 4)$$

$$465369 := 9 + (6^{3!} - 5!) \times (6 + 4)$$

$$473580 := 0 + 8! + (5!^3 + 7!)/4$$

$$473581 := 1 + 8! + (5!^3 + 7!)/4$$

$$473582 := 2 + 8! + (5!^3 + 7!)/4$$

$$473583 := 3 + 8! + (5!^3 + 7!)/4$$

$$473584 := 4 + 8! + (5!^3 + 7!)/4$$

$$473585 := 5 + 8! + (5!^3 + 7!)/4$$

$$473586 := 6 + 8! + (5!^3 + 7!)/4$$

$$473587 := 7 + 8! + (5!^3 + 7!)/4$$

$$473588 := 8 + 8! + (5!^3 + 7!)/4$$

$$473589 := 9 + 8! + (5!^3 + 7!)/4$$

$$479520 := 0 + (-2 + 5)!! \times 9 \times 74$$

$$479521 := 1 + (-2 + 5)!! \times 9 \times 74$$

$$479522 := 2 + (-2 + 5)!! \times 9 \times 74$$

$$479523 := 3 + (-2 + 5)!! \times 9 \times 74$$

$$479524 := 4 + (-2 + 5)!! \times 9 \times 74$$

$$479525 := 5 + (-2 + 5)!! \times 9 \times 74$$

$$479526 := 6 + (-2 + 5)!! \times 9 \times 74$$

$$479527 := 7 + (-2 + 5)!! \times 9 \times 74$$

$$479528 := 8 + (-2 + 5)!! \times 9 \times 74$$
$$479529 := 9 + (-2 + 5)!! \times 9 \times 74$$

$$483120 := 0 - (2 + 1)!! + 3 \times 8! \times 4$$
$$483121 := 1 - (2 + 1)!! + 3 \times 8! \times 4$$
$$483122 := 2 - (2 + 1)!! + 3 \times 8! \times 4$$
$$483123 := 3 - (2 + 1)!! + 3 \times 8! \times 4$$
$$483124 := 4 - (2 + 1)!! + 3 \times 8! \times 4$$
$$483125 := 5 - (2 + 1)!! + 3 \times 8! \times 4$$
$$483126 := 6 - (2 + 1)!! + 3 \times 8! \times 4$$
$$483127 := 7 - (2 + 1)!! + 3 \times 8! \times 4$$
$$483128 := 8 - (2 + 1)!! + 3 \times 8! \times 4$$
$$483129 := 9 - (2 + 1)!! + 3 \times 8! \times 4$$

$$483361 := 0 + (-6!/3! + 3 \times 8!) \times 4$$
$$483361 := 1 + (-6!/3! + 3 \times 8!) \times 4$$
$$483362 := 2 + (-6!/3! + 3 \times 8!) \times 4$$
$$483363 := 3 + (-6!/3! + 3 \times 8!) \times 4$$
$$483364 := 4 + (-6!/3! + 3 \times 8!) \times 4$$
$$483365 := 5 + (-6!/3! + 3 \times 8!) \times 4$$
$$483366 := 6 + (-6!/3! + 3 \times 8!) \times 4$$
$$483367 := 7 + (-6!/3! + 3 \times 8!) \times 4$$
$$483368 := 8 + (-6!/3! + 3 \times 8!) \times 4$$
$$483369 := 9 + (-6!/3! + 3 \times 8!) \times 4$$

$$483480 := 0 + (8! - 4! - 3!) \times (8 + 4)$$
$$483481 := 1 + (8! - 4! - 3!) \times (8 + 4)$$
$$483482 := 2 + (8! - 4! - 3!) \times (8 + 4)$$
$$483483 := 3 + (8! - 4! - 3!) \times (8 + 4)$$
$$483484 := 4 + (8! - 4! - 3!) \times (8 + 4)$$
$$483485 := 5 + (8! - 4! - 3!) \times (8 + 4)$$
$$483486 := 6 + (8! - 4! - 3!) \times (8 + 4)$$
$$483487 := 7 + (8! - 4! - 3!) \times (8 + 4)$$
$$483488 := 8 + (8! - 4! - 3!) \times (8 + 4)$$
$$483489 := 9 + (8! - 4! - 3!) \times (8 + 4)$$

$$483720 := 0 - (-2 + 7)! + 3 \times 8! \times 4$$
$$483721 := 1 - (-2 + 7)! + 3 \times 8! \times 4$$
$$483722 := 2 - (-2 + 7)! + 3 \times 8! \times 4$$
$$483723 := 3 - (-2 + 7)! + 3 \times 8! \times 4$$
$$483724 := 4 - (-2 + 7)! + 3 \times 8! \times 4$$

$$483725 := 5 - (-2 + 7)! + 3 \times 8! \times 4$$
$$483726 := 6 - (-2 + 7)! + 3 \times 8! \times 4$$
$$483727 := 7 - (-2 + 7)! + 3 \times 8! \times 4$$
$$483728 := 8 - (-2 + 7)! + 3 \times 8! \times 4$$
$$483729 := 9 - (-2 + 7)! + 3 \times 8! \times 4$$
$$483780 := 0 + (-8 - 7 + 3 \times 8!) \times 4$$
$$483781 := 1 + (-8 - 7 + 3 \times 8!) \times 4$$
$$483782 := 2 + (-8 - 7 + 3 \times 8!) \times 4$$
$$483783 := 3 + (-8 - 7 + 3 \times 8!) \times 4$$
$$483784 := 4 + (-8 - 7 + 3 \times 8!) \times 4$$
$$483785 := 5 + (-8 - 7 + 3 \times 8!) \times 4$$
$$483786 := 6 + (-8 - 7 + 3 \times 8!) \times 4$$
$$483787 := 7 + (-8 - 7 + 3 \times 8!) \times 4$$
$$483788 := 8 + (-8 - 7 + 3 \times 8!) \times 4$$
$$483789 := 9 + (-8 - 7 + 3 \times 8!) \times 4$$

$$483840 := 0 + 4! \times 8! \times 3! / (8 + 4)$$
$$483841 := 1 + 4! \times 8! \times 3! / (8 + 4)$$
$$483842 := 2 + 4! \times 8! \times 3! / (8 + 4)$$
$$483843 := 3 + 4! \times 8! \times 3! / (8 + 4)$$
$$483844 := 4 + 4! \times 8! \times 3! / (8 + 4)$$
$$483845 := 5 + 4! \times 8! \times 3! / (8 + 4)$$
$$483846 := 6 + 4! \times 8! \times 3! / (8 + 4)$$
$$483847 := 7 + 4! \times 8! \times 3! / (8 + 4)$$
$$483848 := 8 + 4! \times 8! \times 3! / (8 + 4)$$
$$483849 := 9 + 4! \times 8! \times 3! / (8 + 4)$$

$$483880 := 0 + 8 + (8! \times 3 + 8) \times 4$$
$$483881 := 1 + 8 + (8! \times 3 + 8) \times 4$$
$$483882 := 2 + 8 + (8! \times 3 + 8) \times 4$$
$$483883 := 3 + 8 + (8! \times 3 + 8) \times 4$$
$$483884 := 4 + 8 + (8! \times 3 + 8) \times 4$$
$$483885 := 5 + 8 + (8! \times 3 + 8) \times 4$$
$$483886 := 6 + 8 + (8! \times 3 + 8) \times 4$$
$$483887 := 7 + 8 + (8! \times 3 + 8) \times 4$$
$$483888 := 8 + 8 + (8! \times 3 + 8) \times 4$$
$$483889 := 9 + 8 + (8! \times 3 + 8) \times 4$$

$$483980 := 0 + ((8! + 9) \times 3 + 8) \times 4$$
$$483981 := 1 + ((8! + 9) \times 3 + 8) \times 4$$
$$483982 := 2 + ((8! + 9) \times 3 + 8) \times 4$$

$$\begin{aligned}483983 &:= 3 + ((8! + 9) \times 3 + 8) \times 4 \\483984 &:= 4 + ((8! + 9) \times 3 + 8) \times 4 \\483985 &:= 5 + ((8! + 9) \times 3 + 8) \times 4 \\483986 &:= 6 + ((8! + 9) \times 3 + 8) \times 4 \\483987 &:= 7 + ((8! + 9) \times 3 + 8) \times 4 \\483988 &:= 8 + ((8! + 9) \times 3 + 8) \times 4 \\483989 &:= 9 + ((8! + 9) \times 3 + 8) \times 4\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}485760 &:= 0 - 6! - 7! + 5! \times 8^4 \\485761 &:= 1 - 6! - 7! + 5! \times 8^4 \\485762 &:= 2 - 6! - 7! + 5! \times 8^4 \\485763 &:= 3 - 6! - 7! + 5! \times 8^4 \\485764 &:= 4 - 6! - 7! + 5! \times 8^4 \\485765 &:= 5 - 6! - 7! + 5! \times 8^4 \\485766 &:= 6 - 6! - 7! + 5! \times 8^4 \\485767 &:= 7 - 6! - 7! + 5! \times 8^4 \\485768 &:= 8 - 6! - 7! + 5! \times 8^4 \\485769 &:= 9 - 6! - 7! + 5! \times 8^4\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}488880 &:= 0 + 8!/8 + 8! \times (8 + 4) \\488881 &:= 1 + 8!/8 + 8! \times (8 + 4) \\488882 &:= 2 + 8!/8 + 8! \times (8 + 4) \\488883 &:= 3 + 8!/8 + 8! \times (8 + 4) \\488884 &:= 4 + 8!/8 + 8! \times (8 + 4) \\488885 &:= 5 + 8!/8 + 8! \times (8 + 4) \\488886 &:= 6 + 8!/8 + 8! \times (8 + 4) \\488887 &:= 7 + 8!/8 + 8! \times (8 + 4) \\488888 &:= 8 + 8!/8 + 8! \times (8 + 4) \\488889 &:= 9 + 8!/8 + 8! \times (8 + 4)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}491400 &:= 0 + (0! + (4 - 1) \times 9)!/4!! \\491401 &:= 1 + (0! + (4 - 1) \times 9)!/4!! \\491402 &:= 2 + (0! + (4 - 1) \times 9)!/4!! \\491403 &:= 3 + (0! + (4 - 1) \times 9)!/4!! \\491404 &:= 4 + (0! + (4 - 1) \times 9)!/4!! \\491405 &:= 5 + (0! + (4 - 1) \times 9)!/4!! \\491406 &:= 7 + (0! + (4 - 1) \times 9)!/4!! \\491407 &:= 8 + (0! + (4 - 1) \times 9)!/4!! \\491408 &:= 9 + (0! + (4 - 1) \times 9)!/4!! \\491409 &:= 0 + (0! + (4 - 1) \times 9)!/4!!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}491640 &:= 0 + (4^6 + 1) \times (9 - 4)! \\491641 &:= 1 + (4^6 + 1) \times (9 - 4)! \\491642 &:= 2 + (4^6 + 1) \times (9 - 4)! \\491643 &:= 3 + (4^6 + 1) \times (9 - 4)! \\491644 &:= 4 + (4^6 + 1) \times (9 - 4)! \\491645 &:= 5 + (4^6 + 1) \times (9 - 4)! \\491646 &:= 6 + (4^6 + 1) \times (9 - 4)! \\491647 &:= 7 + (4^6 + 1) \times (9 - 4)! \\491648 &:= 8 + (4^6 + 1) \times (9 - 4)! \\491649 &:= 9 + (4^6 + 1) \times (9 - 4)!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}497280 &:= 0 + (8!/2 + 7!/9) \times 4! \\497281 &:= 1 + (8!/2 + 7!/9) \times 4! \\497282 &:= 2 + (8!/2 + 7!/9) \times 4! \\497283 &:= 3 + (8!/2 + 7!/9) \times 4! \\497284 &:= 4 + (8!/2 + 7!/9) \times 4! \\497285 &:= 5 + (8!/2 + 7!/9) \times 4! \\497286 &:= 6 + (8!/2 + 7!/9) \times 4! \\497287 &:= 7 + (8!/2 + 7!/9) \times 4! \\497288 &:= 8 + (8!/2 + 7!/9) \times 4! \\497289 &:= 9 + (8!/2 + 7!/9) \times 4!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}497660 &:= 0 + 6 \times (-6^7 + 9!) - 4 \\497661 &:= 1 + 6 \times (-6^7 + 9!) - 4 \\497662 &:= 2 + 6 \times (-6^7 + 9!) - 4 \\497663 &:= 3 + 6 \times (-6^7 + 9!) - 4 \\497664 &:= 4 + 6 \times (-6^7 + 9!) - 4 \\497665 &:= 5 + 6 \times (-6^7 + 9!) - 4 \\497666 &:= 6 + 6 \times (-6^7 + 9!) - 4 \\497667 &:= 7 + 6 \times (-6^7 + 9!) - 4 \\497668 &:= 8 + 6 \times (-6^7 + 9!) - 4 \\497669 &:= 9 + 6 \times (-6^7 + 9!) - 4\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}506880 &:= 0 + (-8 - 8 + 6!) \times (0! + 5)! \\506881 &:= 1 + (-8 - 8 + 6!) \times (0! + 5)! \\506882 &:= 2 + (-8 - 8 + 6!) \times (0! + 5)! \\506883 &:= 3 + (-8 - 8 + 6!) \times (0! + 5)! \\506884 &:= 4 + (-8 - 8 + 6!) \times (0! + 5)! \\506885 &:= 5 + (-8 - 8 + 6!) \times (0! + 5)!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}506886 &:= 6 + (-8 - 8 + 6!) \times (0! + 5)! \\506887 &:= 7 + (-8 - 8 + 6!) \times (0! + 5)! \\506888 &:= 8 + (-8 - 8 + 6!) \times (0! + 5)! \\506889 &:= 9 + (-8 - 8 + 6!) \times (0! + 5)!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}507600 &:= 0 + 06! \times 705 \\507601 &:= 1 + 06! \times 705 \\507602 &:= 2 + 06! \times 705 \\507603 &:= 3 + 06! \times 705 \\507604 &:= 4 + 06! \times 705 \\507605 &:= 5 + 06! \times 705 \\507606 &:= 6 + 06! \times 705 \\507607 &:= 7 + 06! \times 705 \\507608 &:= 8 + 06! \times 705 \\507609 &:= 9 + 06! \times 705\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}513360 &:= 0 + 6! \times 3!! - (3 - 1 + 5)! \\513361 &:= 1 + 6! \times 3!! - (3 - 1 + 5)! \\513362 &:= 2 + 6! \times 3!! - (3 - 1 + 5)! \\513363 &:= 3 + 6! \times 3!! - (3 - 1 + 5)! \\513364 &:= 4 + 6! \times 3!! - (3 - 1 + 5)! \\513365 &:= 5 + 6! \times 3!! - (3 - 1 + 5)! \\513366 &:= 6 + 6! \times 3!! - (3 - 1 + 5)! \\513367 &:= 7 + 6! \times 3!! - (3 - 1 + 5)! \\513368 &:= 8 + 6! \times 3!! - (3 - 1 + 5)! \\513369 &:= 9 + 6! \times 3!! - (3 - 1 + 5)!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}515640 &:= 0 + (-4 + 6!) \times (5 + 1)! + 5! \\515641 &:= 1 + (-4 + 6!) \times (5 + 1)! + 5! \\515642 &:= 2 + (-4 + 6!) \times (5 + 1)! + 5! \\515643 &:= 3 + (-4 + 6!) \times (5 + 1)! + 5! \\515644 &:= 4 + (-4 + 6!) \times (5 + 1)! + 5! \\515645 &:= 5 + (-4 + 6!) \times (5 + 1)! + 5! \\515646 &:= 6 + (-4 + 6!) \times (5 + 1)! + 5! \\515647 &:= 7 + (-4 + 6!) \times (5 + 1)! + 5! \\515648 &:= 8 + (-4 + 6!) \times (5 + 1)! + 5! \\515649 &:= 9 + (-4 + 6!) \times (5 + 1)! + 5!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}516230 &:= 0 + (3!! + 2) \times (6! - 1 \times 5) \\516231 &:= 1 + (3!! + 2) \times (6! - 1 \times 5) \\516232 &:= 2 + (3!! + 2) \times (6! - 1 \times 5)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}516233 &:= 3 + (3!! + 2) \times (6! - 1 \times 5) \\516234 &:= 4 + (3!! + 2) \times (6! - 1 \times 5) \\516235 &:= 5 + (3!! + 2) \times (6! - 1 \times 5) \\516236 &:= 6 + (3!! + 2) \times (6! - 1 \times 5) \\516237 &:= 7 + (3!! + 2) \times (6! - 1 \times 5) \\516238 &:= 8 + (3!! + 2) \times (6! - 1 \times 5) \\516239 &:= 9 + (3!! + 2) \times (6! - 1 \times 5)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}516360 &:= 0 + (6! - 3) \times 6! \times 1 + 5! \\516361 &:= 1 + (6! - 3) \times 6! \times 1 + 5! \\516362 &:= 2 + (6! - 3) \times 6! \times 1 + 5! \\516363 &:= 3 + (6! - 3) \times 6! \times 1 + 5! \\516364 &:= 4 + (6! - 3) \times 6! \times 1 + 5! \\516365 &:= 5 + (6! - 3) \times 6! \times 1 + 5! \\516366 &:= 6 + (6! - 3) \times 6! \times 1 + 5! \\516367 &:= 7 + (6! - 3) \times 6! \times 1 + 5! \\516368 &:= 8 + (6! - 3) \times 6! \times 1 + 5! \\516369 &:= 9 + (6! - 3) \times 6! \times 1 + 5!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}517680 &:= 0 + (-8 + 6! + 7) \times (1 + 5)! \\517681 &:= 1 + (-8 + 6! + 7) \times (1 + 5)! \\517682 &:= 2 + (-8 + 6! + 7) \times (1 + 5)! \\517683 &:= 3 + (-8 + 6! + 7) \times (1 + 5)! \\517684 &:= 4 + (-8 + 6! + 7) \times (1 + 5)! \\517685 &:= 5 + (-8 + 6! + 7) \times (1 + 5)! \\517686 &:= 6 + (-8 + 6! + 7) \times (1 + 5)! \\517687 &:= 7 + (-8 + 6! + 7) \times (1 + 5)! \\517688 &:= 8 + (-8 + 6! + 7) \times (1 + 5)! \\517689 &:= 9 + (-8 + 6! + 7) \times (1 + 5)!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}518280 &:= 0 + (8 + 2)! / (8 - 1) + 5! \\518281 &:= 1 + (8 + 2)! / (8 - 1) + 5! \\518282 &:= 2 + (8 + 2)! / (8 - 1) + 5! \\518283 &:= 3 + (8 + 2)! / (8 - 1) + 5! \\518284 &:= 4 + (8 + 2)! / (8 - 1) + 5! \\518285 &:= 5 + (8 + 2)! / (8 - 1) + 5! \\518286 &:= 6 + (8 + 2)! / (8 - 1) + 5! \\518287 &:= 7 + (8 + 2)! / (8 - 1) + 5! \\518288 &:= 8 + (8 + 2)! / (8 - 1) + 5! \\518289 &:= 9 + (8 + 2)! / (8 - 1) + 5!\end{aligned}$$

$$518360 := 0 + 6! \times 3!! - 8 \times 1 \times 5$$

$$\begin{aligned}518361 &:= 1 + 6! \times 3!! - 8 \times 1 \times 5 \\518362 &:= 2 + 6! \times 3!! - 8 \times 1 \times 5 \\518363 &:= 3 + 6! \times 3!! - 8 \times 1 \times 5 \\518364 &:= 4 + 6! \times 3!! - 8 \times 1 \times 5 \\518365 &:= 5 + 6! \times 3!! - 8 \times 1 \times 5 \\518366 &:= 6 + 6! \times 3!! - 8 \times 1 \times 5 \\518367 &:= 7 + 6! \times 3!! - 8 \times 1 \times 5 \\518368 &:= 8 + 6! \times 3!! - 8 \times 1 \times 5 \\518369 &:= 9 + 6! \times 3!! - 8 \times 1 \times 5\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}518400 &:= 0 + (04!/8)!! \times (1 + 5)! \\518401 &:= 1 + (04!/8)!! \times (1 + 5)! \\518402 &:= 2 + (04!/8)!! \times (1 + 5)! \\518403 &:= 3 + (04!/8)!! \times (1 + 5)! \\518404 &:= 4 + (04!/8)!! \times (1 + 5)! \\518405 &:= 5 + (04!/8)!! \times (1 + 5)! \\518406 &:= 6 + (04!/8)!! \times (1 + 5)! \\518407 &:= 7 + (04!/8)!! \times (1 + 5)! \\518408 &:= 8 + (04!/8)!! \times (1 + 5)! \\518409 &:= 9 + (04!/8)!! \times (1 + 5)!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}518520 &:= 0 + (2 \times 5)! / (8 - 1) + 5! \\518521 &:= 1 + (2 \times 5)! / (8 - 1) + 5! \\518522 &:= 2 + (2 \times 5)! / (8 - 1) + 5! \\518523 &:= 3 + (2 \times 5)! / (8 - 1) + 5! \\518524 &:= 4 + (2 \times 5)! / (8 - 1) + 5! \\518525 &:= 5 + (2 \times 5)! / (8 - 1) + 5! \\518526 &:= 6 + (2 \times 5)! / (8 - 1) + 5! \\518527 &:= 7 + (2 \times 5)! / (8 - 1) + 5! \\518528 &:= 8 + (2 \times 5)! / (8 - 1) + 5! \\518529 &:= 9 + (2 \times 5)! / (8 - 1) + 5!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}519360 &:= 0 + (6! \times 3! + 9 - 1) \times 5! \\519361 &:= 1 + (6! \times 3! + 9 - 1) \times 5! \\519362 &:= 2 + (6! \times 3! + 9 - 1) \times 5! \\519363 &:= 3 + (6! \times 3! + 9 - 1) \times 5! \\519364 &:= 4 + (6! \times 3! + 9 - 1) \times 5! \\519365 &:= 5 + (6! \times 3! + 9 - 1) \times 5! \\519366 &:= 6 + (6! \times 3! + 9 - 1) \times 5! \\519367 &:= 7 + (6! \times 3! + 9 - 1) \times 5! \\519368 &:= 8 + (6! \times 3! + 9 - 1) \times 5!\end{aligned}$$

$$519369 := 9 + (6! \times 3! + 9 - 1) \times 5!$$

$$\begin{aligned}520560 &:= 0 + 6! \times ((5 + 0)!) - 2 + 5 \\520561 &:= 1 + 6! \times ((5 + 0)!) - 2 + 5 \\520562 &:= 2 + 6! \times ((5 + 0)!) - 2 + 5 \\520563 &:= 3 + 6! \times ((5 + 0)!) - 2 + 5 \\520564 &:= 4 + 6! \times ((5 + 0)!) - 2 + 5 \\520565 &:= 5 + 6! \times ((5 + 0)!) - 2 + 5 \\520566 &:= 6 + 6! \times ((5 + 0)!) - 2 + 5 \\520567 &:= 7 + 6! \times ((5 + 0)!) - 2 + 5 \\520568 &:= 8 + 6! \times ((5 + 0)!) - 2 + 5 \\520569 &:= 9 + 6! \times ((5 + 0)!) - 2 + 5\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}523440 &:= 0 + (4!/4)! \times 3!! + (2 + 5)! \\523441 &:= 1 + (4!/4)! \times 3!! + (2 + 5)! \\523442 &:= 2 + (4!/4)! \times 3!! + (2 + 5)! \\523443 &:= 3 + (4!/4)! \times 3!! + (2 + 5)! \\523444 &:= 4 + (4!/4)! \times 3!! + (2 + 5)! \\523445 &:= 5 + (4!/4)! \times 3!! + (2 + 5)! \\523446 &:= 6 + (4!/4)! \times 3!! + (2 + 5)! \\523447 &:= 7 + (4!/4)! \times 3!! + (2 + 5)! \\523448 &:= 8 + (4!/4)! \times 3!! + (2 + 5)! \\523449 &:= 9 + (4!/4)! \times 3!! + (2 + 5)!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}523560 &:= 0 + 6! \times (5 + 3!! + 2) + 5! \\523561 &:= 1 + 6! \times (5 + 3!! + 2) + 5! \\523562 &:= 2 + 6! \times (5 + 3!! + 2) + 5! \\523563 &:= 3 + 6! \times (5 + 3!! + 2) + 5! \\523564 &:= 4 + 6! \times (5 + 3!! + 2) + 5! \\523565 &:= 5 + 6! \times (5 + 3!! + 2) + 5! \\523566 &:= 6 + 6! \times (5 + 3!! + 2) + 5! \\523567 &:= 7 + 6! \times (5 + 3!! + 2) + 5! \\523568 &:= 8 + 6! \times (5 + 3!! + 2) + 5! \\523569 &:= 9 + 6! \times (5 + 3!! + 2) + 5!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}524160 &:= 0 + (6 + 1)! \times (-4^2 + 5!) \\524161 &:= 1 + (6 + 1)! \times (-4^2 + 5!) \\524162 &:= 2 + (6 + 1)! \times (-4^2 + 5!) \\524163 &:= 3 + (6 + 1)! \times (-4^2 + 5!) \\524164 &:= 4 + (6 + 1)! \times (-4^2 + 5!) \\524165 &:= 5 + (6 + 1)! \times (-4^2 + 5!)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}524166 &:= 6 + (6 + 1)! \times (-4^2 + 5!) \\524167 &:= 7 + (6 + 1)! \times (-4^2 + 5!) \\524168 &:= 8 + (6 + 1)! \times (-4^2 + 5!) \\524169 &:= 9 + (6 + 1)! \times (-4^2 + 5!)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}526350 &:= 0 + (5 + 3!!) \times (6! + (-2 + 5)!) \\526351 &:= 1 + (5 + 3!!) \times (6! + (-2 + 5)!) \\526352 &:= 2 + (5 + 3!!) \times (6! + (-2 + 5)!) \\526353 &:= 3 + (5 + 3!!) \times (6! + (-2 + 5)!) \\526354 &:= 4 + (5 + 3!!) \times (6! + (-2 + 5)!) \\526355 &:= 5 + (5 + 3!!) \times (6! + (-2 + 5)!) \\526356 &:= 6 + (5 + 3!!) \times (6! + (-2 + 5)!) \\526357 &:= 7 + (5 + 3!!) \times (6! + (-2 + 5)!) \\526358 &:= 8 + (5 + 3!!) \times (6! + (-2 + 5)!) \\526359 &:= 9 + (5 + 3!!) \times (6! + (-2 + 5)!)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}527040 &:= 0 + (-(4 - 0)!! + 7!) \times (2 + 5!) \\527041 &:= 1 + (-(4 - 0)!! + 7!) \times (2 + 5!) \\527042 &:= 2 + (-(4 - 0)!! + 7!) \times (2 + 5!) \\527043 &:= 3 + (-(4 - 0)!! + 7!) \times (2 + 5!) \\527044 &:= 4 + (-(4 - 0)!! + 7!) \times (2 + 5!) \\527045 &:= 5 + (-(4 - 0)!! + 7!) \times (2 + 5!) \\527046 &:= 6 + (-(4 - 0)!! + 7!) \times (2 + 5!) \\527047 &:= 7 + (-(4 - 0)!! + 7!) \times (2 + 5!) \\527048 &:= 8 + (-(4 - 0)!! + 7!) \times (2 + 5!) \\527049 &:= 9 + (-(4 - 0)!! + 7!) \times (2 + 5!)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}527650 &:= 0 + (5 - 6! + 7!) \times (2 + 5!) \\527651 &:= 1 + (5 - 6! + 7!) \times (2 + 5!) \\527652 &:= 2 + (5 - 6! + 7!) \times (2 + 5!) \\527653 &:= 3 + (5 - 6! + 7!) \times (2 + 5!) \\527654 &:= 4 + (5 - 6! + 7!) \times (2 + 5!) \\527655 &:= 5 + (5 - 6! + 7!) \times (2 + 5!) \\527656 &:= 6 + (5 - 6! + 7!) \times (2 + 5!) \\527657 &:= 7 + (5 - 6! + 7!) \times (2 + 5!) \\527658 &:= 8 + (5 - 6! + 7!) \times (2 + 5!) \\527659 &:= 9 + (5 - 6! + 7!) \times (2 + 5!)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}531360 &:= 0 + 6! \times 3! \times (1 \times 3 + 5!) \\531361 &:= 1 + 6! \times 3! \times (1 \times 3 + 5!)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}531362 &:= 2 + 6! \times 3! \times (1 \times 3 + 5!) \\531363 &:= 3 + 6! \times 3! \times (1 \times 3 + 5!) \\531364 &:= 4 + 6! \times 3! \times (1 \times 3 + 5!) \\531365 &:= 5 + 6! \times 3! \times (1 \times 3 + 5!) \\531366 &:= 6 + 6! \times 3! \times (1 \times 3 + 5!) \\531367 &:= 7 + 6! \times 3! \times (1 \times 3 + 5!) \\531368 &:= 8 + 6! \times 3! \times (1 \times 3 + 5!) \\531369 &:= 9 + 6! \times 3! \times (1 \times 3 + 5!)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}533640 &:= 0 + (4! + 6! - 3) \times 3!! + 5! \\533641 &:= 1 + (4! + 6! - 3) \times 3!! + 5! \\533642 &:= 2 + (4! + 6! - 3) \times 3!! + 5! \\533643 &:= 3 + (4! + 6! - 3) \times 3!! + 5! \\533644 &:= 4 + (4! + 6! - 3) \times 3!! + 5! \\533645 &:= 5 + (4! + 6! - 3) \times 3!! + 5! \\533646 &:= 6 + (4! + 6! - 3) \times 3!! + 5! \\533647 &:= 7 + (4! + 6! - 3) \times 3!! + 5! \\533648 &:= 8 + (4! + 6! - 3) \times 3!! + 5! \\533649 &:= 9 + (4! + 6! - 3) \times 3!! + 5!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}535560 &:= 0 + (6! + 5!/5) \times 3!! - 5! \\535561 &:= 1 + (6! + 5!/5) \times 3!! - 5! \\535562 &:= 2 + (6! + 5!/5) \times 3!! - 5! \\535563 &:= 3 + (6! + 5!/5) \times 3!! - 5! \\535564 &:= 4 + (6! + 5!/5) \times 3!! - 5! \\535565 &:= 5 + (6! + 5!/5) \times 3!! - 5! \\535566 &:= 6 + (6! + 5!/5) \times 3!! - 5! \\535567 &:= 7 + (6! + 5!/5) \times 3!! - 5! \\535568 &:= 8 + (6! + 5!/5) \times 3!! - 5! \\535569 &:= 9 + (6! + 5!/5) \times 3!! - 5!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}536400 &:= 0 + (0! + 4! + 6!) \times 3! \times 5! \\536401 &:= 1 + (0! + 4! + 6!) \times 3! \times 5! \\536402 &:= 2 + (0! + 4! + 6!) \times 3! \times 5! \\536403 &:= 3 + (0! + 4! + 6!) \times 3! \times 5! \\536404 &:= 4 + (0! + 4! + 6!) \times 3! \times 5! \\536405 &:= 5 + (0! + 4! + 6!) \times 3! \times 5! \\536406 &:= 6 + (0! + 4! + 6!) \times 3! \times 5! \\536407 &:= 7 + (0! + 4! + 6!) \times 3! \times 5! \\536408 &:= 8 + (0! + 4! + 6!) \times 3! \times 5! \\536409 &:= 9 + (0! + 4! + 6!) \times 3! \times 5!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}536520 &:= 0 + (25 + 6!) \times 3!! + 5! \\536521 &:= 1 + (25 + 6!) \times 3!! + 5! \\536522 &:= 2 + (25 + 6!) \times 3!! + 5! \\536523 &:= 3 + (25 + 6!) \times 3!! + 5! \\536524 &:= 4 + (25 + 6!) \times 3!! + 5! \\536525 &:= 5 + (25 + 6!) \times 3!! + 5! \\536526 &:= 6 + (25 + 6!) \times 3!! + 5! \\536527 &:= 7 + (25 + 6!) \times 3!! + 5! \\536528 &:= 8 + (25 + 6!) \times 3!! + 5! \\536529 &:= 9 + (25 + 6!) \times 3!! + 5!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}537830 &:= 0 + 3! + (8!/7! + 3!)^5 \\537831 &:= 1 + 3! + (8!/7! + 3!)^5 \\537832 &:= 2 + 3! + (8!/7! + 3!)^5 \\537833 &:= 3 + 3! + (8!/7! + 3!)^5 \\537834 &:= 4 + 3! + (8!/7! + 3!)^5 \\537835 &:= 5 + 3! + (8!/7! + 3!)^5 \\537836 &:= 6 + 3! + (8!/7! + 3!)^5 \\537837 &:= 7 + 3! + (8!/7! + 3!)^5 \\537838 &:= 8 + 3! + (8!/7! + 3!)^5 \\537839 &:= 9 + 3! + (8!/7! + 3!)^5\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}543960 &:= 0 + 6 \times ((9! - 3!)/4 + 5!) \\543961 &:= 1 + 6 \times ((9! - 3!)/4 + 5!) \\543962 &:= 2 + 6 \times ((9! - 3!)/4 + 5!) \\543963 &:= 3 + 6 \times ((9! - 3!)/4 + 5!) \\543964 &:= 4 + 6 \times ((9! - 3!)/4 + 5!) \\543965 &:= 5 + 6 \times ((9! - 3!)/4 + 5!) \\543966 &:= 6 + 6 \times ((9! - 3!)/4 + 5!) \\543967 &:= 7 + 6 \times ((9! - 3!)/4 + 5!) \\543968 &:= 8 + 6 \times ((9! - 3!)/4 + 5!) \\543969 &:= 9 + 6 \times ((9! - 3!)/4 + 5!)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}549360 &:= 0 + 6 \times (3!! + 9!/4 + 5!) \\549361 &:= 1 + 6 \times (3!! + 9!/4 + 5!) \\549362 &:= 2 + 6 \times (3!! + 9!/4 + 5!)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}549363 &:= 3 + 6 \times (3!! + 9!/4 + 5!) \\549364 &:= 4 + 6 \times (3!! + 9!/4 + 5!) \\549365 &:= 5 + 6 \times (3!! + 9!/4 + 5!) \\549366 &:= 6 + 6 \times (3!! + 9!/4 + 5!) \\549367 &:= 7 + 6 \times (3!! + 9!/4 + 5!) \\549368 &:= 8 + 6 \times (3!! + 9!/4 + 5!) \\549369 &:= 9 + 6 \times (3!! + 9!/4 + 5!)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}563880 &:= 0 + 8! \times (8 + 3!) - 6! + 5! \\563881 &:= 1 + 8! \times (8 + 3!) - 6! + 5! \\563882 &:= 2 + 8! \times (8 + 3!) - 6! + 5! \\563883 &:= 3 + 8! \times (8 + 3!) - 6! + 5! \\563884 &:= 4 + 8! \times (8 + 3!) - 6! + 5! \\563885 &:= 5 + 8! \times (8 + 3!) - 6! + 5! \\563886 &:= 6 + 8! \times (8 + 3!) - 6! + 5! \\563887 &:= 7 + 8! \times (8 + 3!) - 6! + 5! \\563888 &:= 8 + 8! \times (8 + 3!) - 6! + 5! \\563889 &:= 9 + 8! \times (8 + 3!) - 6! + 5!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}564480 &:= 0 + 8! \times (4 + (-4 + 6) \times 5) \\564481 &:= 1 + 8! \times (4 + (-4 + 6) \times 5) \\564482 &:= 2 + 8! \times (4 + (-4 + 6) \times 5) \\564483 &:= 3 + 8! \times (4 + (-4 + 6) \times 5) \\564484 &:= 4 + 8! \times (4 + (-4 + 6) \times 5) \\564485 &:= 5 + 8! \times (4 + (-4 + 6) \times 5) \\564486 &:= 6 + 8! \times (4 + (-4 + 6) \times 5) \\564487 &:= 7 + 8! \times (4 + (-4 + 6) \times 5) \\564488 &:= 8 + 8! \times (4 + (-4 + 6) \times 5) \\564489 &:= 9 + 8! \times (4 + (-4 + 6) \times 5)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}566760 &:= 0 + (67 + 6!) \times 6! + 5! \\566761 &:= 1 + (67 + 6!) \times 6! + 5! \\566762 &:= 2 + (67 + 6!) \times 6! + 5! \\566763 &:= 3 + (67 + 6!) \times 6! + 5! \\566764 &:= 4 + (67 + 6!) \times 6! + 5! \\566765 &:= 5 + (67 + 6!) \times 6! + 5! \\566766 &:= 6 + (67 + 6!) \times 6! + 5! \\566767 &:= 7 + (67 + 6!) \times 6! + 5! \\566768 &:= 8 + (67 + 6!) \times 6! + 5!\end{aligned}$$

$$566769 := 9 + (67 + 6!) \times 6! + 5!$$

$$568080 := 0 + (8 + 0!)! + (8! + 6!) \times 5$$

$$568081 := 1 + (8 + 0!)! + (8! + 6!) \times 5$$

$$568082 := 2 + (8 + 0!)! + (8! + 6!) \times 5$$

$$568083 := 3 + (8 + 0!)! + (8! + 6!) \times 5$$

$$568084 := 4 + (8 + 0!)! + (8! + 6!) \times 5$$

$$568085 := 5 + (8 + 0!)! + (8! + 6!) \times 5$$

$$568086 := 6 + (8 + 0!)! + (8! + 6!) \times 5$$

$$568087 := 7 + (8 + 0!)! + (8! + 6!) \times 5$$

$$568088 := 8 + (8 + 0!)! + (8! + 6!) \times 5$$

$$568089 := 9 + (8 + 0!)! + (8! + 6!) \times 5$$

$$570240 := 0 + (4!/2)!/(07 \times 5!)$$

$$570241 := 1 + (4!/2)!/(07 \times 5!)$$

$$570242 := 2 + (4!/2)!/(07 \times 5!)$$

$$570243 := 3 + (4!/2)!/(07 \times 5!)$$

$$570244 := 4 + (4!/2)!/(07 \times 5!)$$

$$570245 := 5 + (4!/2)!/(07 \times 5!)$$

$$570246 := 6 + (4!/2)!/(07 \times 5!)$$

$$570247 := 7 + (4!/2)!/(07 \times 5!)$$

$$570248 := 8 + (4!/2)!/(07 \times 5!)$$

$$570249 := 9 + (4!/2)!/(07 \times 5!)$$

$$574530 := 0 + 3! \times ((-5 + 4!) \times 7! - 5)$$

$$574531 := 1 + 3! \times ((-5 + 4!) \times 7! - 5)$$

$$574532 := 2 + 3! \times ((-5 + 4!) \times 7! - 5)$$

$$574533 := 3 + 3! \times ((-5 + 4!) \times 7! - 5)$$

$$574534 := 4 + 3! \times ((-5 + 4!) \times 7! - 5)$$

$$574535 := 5 + 3! \times ((-5 + 4!) \times 7! - 5)$$

$$574536 := 6 + 3! \times ((-5 + 4!) \times 7! - 5)$$

$$574537 := 7 + 3! \times ((-5 + 4!) \times 7! - 5)$$

$$574538 := 8 + 3! \times ((-5 + 4!) \times 7! - 5)$$

$$574539 := 9 + 3! \times ((-5 + 4!) \times 7! - 5)$$

$$574560 := 0 + 6! \times (-5 + 4!) \times 7!/5!$$

$$574561 := 1 + 6! \times (-5 + 4!) \times 7!/5!$$

$$574562 := 2 + 6! \times (-5 + 4!) \times 7!/5!$$

$$574563 := 3 + 6! \times (-5 + 4!) \times 7!/5!$$

$$574564 := 4 + 6! \times (-5 + 4!) \times 7!/5!$$

$$574565 := 5 + 6! \times (-5 + 4!) \times 7!/5!$$

$$574566 := 6 + 6! \times (-5 + 4!) \times 7!/5!$$

$$574567 := 7 + 6! \times (-5 + 4!) \times 7!/5!$$

$$574568 := 8 + 6! \times (-5 + 4!) \times 7!/5!$$

$$574569 := 9 + 6! \times (-5 + 4!) \times 7!/5!$$

$$575125 := (((5! - ((2 + 1)))! \times (5 + 7!)) - 5)$$

$$575130 := 0 + (-3! + 1 \times 5!) \times (7! + 5)$$

$$575131 := 1 + (-3! + 1 \times 5!) \times (7! + 5)$$

$$575132 := 2 + (-3! + 1 \times 5!) \times (7! + 5)$$

$$575133 := 3 + (-3! + 1 \times 5!) \times (7! + 5)$$

$$575134 := 4 + (-3! + 1 \times 5!) \times (7! + 5)$$

$$575135 := 5 + (-3! + 1 \times 5!) \times (7! + 5)$$

$$575136 := 6 + (-3! + 1 \times 5!) \times (7! + 5)$$

$$575137 := 7 + (-3! + 1 \times 5!) \times (7! + 5)$$

$$575138 := 8 + (-3! + 1 \times 5!) \times (7! + 5)$$

$$575139 := 9 + (-3! + 1 \times 5!) \times (7! + 5)$$

$$584640 := 0 + (-4! + 6!) \times ((4!/8)!! + 5!)$$

$$584641 := 1 + (-4! + 6!) \times ((4!/8)!! + 5!)$$

$$584642 := 2 + (-4! + 6!) \times ((4!/8)!! + 5!)$$

$$584643 := 3 + (-4! + 6!) \times ((4!/8)!! + 5!)$$

$$584644 := 4 + (-4! + 6!) \times ((4!/8)!! + 5!)$$

$$584645 := 5 + (-4! + 6!) \times ((4!/8)!! + 5!)$$

$$584646 := 6 + (-4! + 6!) \times ((4!/8)!! + 5!)$$

$$584647 := 7 + (-4! + 6!) \times ((4!/8)!! + 5!)$$

$$584648 := 8 + (-4! + 6!) \times ((4!/8)!! + 5!)$$

$$584649 := 9 + (-4! + 6!) \times ((4!/8)!! + 5!)$$

$$588960 := 0 - 6! + 9!/8 \times (8 + 5)$$

$$588961 := 1 - 6! + 9!/8 \times (8 + 5)$$

$$588962 := 2 - 6! + 9!/8 \times (8 + 5)$$

$$588963 := 3 - 6! + 9!/8 \times (8 + 5)$$

$$588964 := 4 - 6! + 9!/8 \times (8 + 5)$$

$$588965 := 5 - 6! + 9!/8 \times (8 + 5)$$

$$588966 := 6 - 6! + 9!/8 \times (8 + 5)$$

$$588967 := 7 - 6! + 9!/8 \times (8 + 5)$$

$$588968 := 8 - 6! + 9!/8 \times (8 + 5)$$

$$588969 := 9 - 6! + 9!/8 \times (8 + 5)$$

$$590490 := 0 + (9 + (4 \times 0!)) \times 9^5$$

$$590491 := 1 + (9 + (4 \times 0!)) \times 9^5$$

$$590492 := 2 + (9 + (4 \times 0!)) \times 9^5$$

$$590493 := 3 + (9 + (4 \times 0!)) \times 9^5$$

$$590494 := 4 + (9 + (4 \times 0!)) \times 9^5$$

$$590495 := 5 + (9 + (4 \times 0!)) \times 9^5$$

$$590496 := 6 + (9 + (4 \times 0!)) \times 9^5$$

$$590497 := 7 + (9 + (4 \times 0!)) \times 9^5$$

$$590498 := 8 + (9 + (4 \times 0!)) \times 9^5$$

$$590499 := 9 + (9 + (4 \times 0!)) \times 9^5$$

$$596520 := 0 + ((2 + 5)! - 69) \times 5!$$

$$596521 := 1 + ((2 + 5)! - 69) \times 5!$$

$$596522 := 2 + ((2 + 5)! - 69) \times 5!$$

$$596523 := 3 + ((2 + 5)! - 69) \times 5!$$

$$596524 := 4 + ((2 + 5)! - 69) \times 5!$$

$$596525 := 5 + ((2 + 5)! - 69) \times 5!$$

$$596526 := 6 + ((2 + 5)! - 69) \times 5!$$

$$596527 := 7 + ((2 + 5)! - 69) \times 5!$$

$$596528 := 8 + ((2 + 5)! - 69) \times 5!$$

$$596529 := 9 + ((2 + 5)! - 69) \times 5!$$

$$599760 := 0 + 6! \times 7 \times (-9/9 + 5!)$$

$$599761 := 1 + 6! \times 7 \times (-9/9 + 5!)$$

$$599762 := 2 + 6! \times 7 \times (-9/9 + 5!)$$

$$599763 := 3 + 6! \times 7 \times (-9/9 + 5!)$$

$$599764 := 4 + 6! \times 7 \times (-9/9 + 5!)$$

$$599765 := 5 + 6! \times 7 \times (-9/9 + 5!)$$

$$599766 := 6 + 6! \times 7 \times (-9/9 + 5!)$$

$$599767 := 7 + 6! \times 7 \times (-9/9 + 5!)$$

$$599768 := 8 + 6! \times 7 \times (-9/9 + 5!)$$

$$599769 := 9 + 6! \times 7 \times (-9/9 + 5!)$$

$$604080 := 0 + (8 - 0!)! \times (4 + 0!)! - 6!$$

$$604081 := 1 + (8 - 0!)! \times (4 + 0!)! - 6!$$

$$604082 := 2 + (8 - 0!)! \times (4 + 0!)! - 6!$$

$$604083 := 3 + (8 - 0!)! \times (4 + 0!)! - 6!$$

$$604084 := 4 + (8 - 0!)! \times (4 + 0!)! - 6!$$

$$604085 := 5 + (8 - 0!)! \times (4 + 0!)! - 6!$$

$$604086 := 6 + (8 - 0!)! \times (4 + 0!)! - 6!$$

$$604087 := 7 + (8 - 0!)! \times (4 + 0!)! - 6!$$

$$604088 := 8 + (8 - 0!)! \times (4 + 0!)! - 6!$$

$$604089 := 9 + (8 - 0!)! \times (4 + 0!)! - 6!$$

$$604320 := 0 + (2 + 3)! \times (-4 + (0! + 6)!)$$

$$604321 := 1 + (2 + 3)! \times (-4 + (0! + 6)!)$$

$$604322 := 2 + (2 + 3)! \times (-4 + (0! + 6)!)$$

$$604323 := 3 + (2 + 3)! \times (-4 + (0! + 6)!)$$

$$604324 := 4 + (2 + 3)! \times (-4 + (0! + 6)!)$$

$$604325 := 5 + (2 + 3)! \times (-4 + (0! + 6)!)$$

$$604326 := 6 + (2 + 3)! \times (-4 + (0! + 6)!)$$

$$604327 := 7 + (2 + 3)! \times (-4 + (0! + 6)!)$$

$$604328 := 8 + (2 + 3)! \times (-4 + (0! + 6)!)$$

$$604329 := 9 + (2 + 3)! \times (-4 + (0! + 6)!)$$

$$604560 := 0 - 6! + 5! \times (4 + (0! + 6)!)$$

$$604561 := 1 - 6! + 5! \times (4 + (0! + 6)!)$$

$$604562 := 2 - 6! + 5! \times (4 + (0! + 6)!)$$

$$604563 := 3 - 6! + 5! \times (4 + (0! + 6)!)$$

$$604564 := 4 - 6! + 5! \times (4 + (0! + 6)!)$$

$$604565 := 5 - 6! + 5! \times (4 + (0! + 6)!)$$

$$604566 := 6 - 6! + 5! \times (4 + (0! + 6)!)$$

$$604567 := 7 - 6! + 5! \times (4 + (0! + 6)!)$$

$$604568 := 8 - 6! + 5! \times (4 + (0! + 6)!)$$

$$604569 := 9 - 6! + 5! \times (4 + (0! + 6)!)$$

$$604800 := 0 + 0840 \times 6!$$

$$604801 := 1 + 0840 \times 6!$$

$$604802 := 2 + 0840 \times 6!$$

$$604803 := 3 + 0840 \times 6!$$

$$604804 := 4 + 0840 \times 6!$$

$$\begin{aligned} 604805 &:= 5 + 0840 \times 6! \\ 604806 &:= 6 + 0840 \times 6! \\ 604807 &:= 7 + 0840 \times 6! \\ 604808 &:= 8 + 0840 \times 6! \\ 604809 &:= 9 + 0840 \times 6! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 604820 &:= 0 + ((2 + 8)! + (4 + 0!)!)/6 \\ 604821 &:= 1 + ((2 + 8)! + (4 + 0!)!)/6 \\ 604822 &:= 2 + ((2 + 8)! + (4 + 0!)!)/6 \\ 604823 &:= 3 + ((2 + 8)! + (4 + 0!)!)/6 \\ 604824 &:= 4 + ((2 + 8)! + (4 + 0!)!)/6 \\ 604825 &:= 5 + ((2 + 8)! + (4 + 0!)!)/6 \\ 604826 &:= 6 + ((2 + 8)! + (4 + 0!)!)/6 \\ 604827 &:= 7 + ((2 + 8)! + (4 + 0!)!)/6 \\ 604828 &:= 8 + ((2 + 8)! + (4 + 0!)!)/6 \\ 604829 &:= 9 + ((2 + 8)! + (4 + 0!)!)/6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 605400 &:= 0 + (0! + 4)! \times (5 + (0! + 6)!) \\ 605401 &:= 1 + (0! + 4)! \times (5 + (0! + 6)!) \\ 605402 &:= 2 + (0! + 4)! \times (5 + (0! + 6)!) \\ 605403 &:= 3 + (0! + 4)! \times (5 + (0! + 6)!) \\ 605404 &:= 4 + (0! + 4)! \times (5 + (0! + 6)!) \\ 605405 &:= 5 + (0! + 4)! \times (5 + (0! + 6)!) \\ 605406 &:= 6 + (0! + 4)! \times (5 + (0! + 6)!) \\ 605407 &:= 7 + (0! + 4)! \times (5 + (0! + 6)!) \\ 605408 &:= 8 + (0! + 4)! \times (5 + (0! + 6)!) \\ 605409 &:= 9 + (0! + 4)! \times (5 + (0! + 6)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 605520 &:= 0 + (2 + 5)! \times 5! + 06! \\ 605521 &:= 1 + (2 + 5)! \times 5! + 06! \\ 605522 &:= 2 + (2 + 5)! \times 5! + 06! \\ 605523 &:= 3 + (2 + 5)! \times 5! + 06! \\ 605524 &:= 4 + (2 + 5)! \times 5! + 06! \\ 605525 &:= 5 + (2 + 5)! \times 5! + 06! \\ 605526 &:= 6 + (2 + 5)! \times 5! + 06! \\ 605527 &:= 7 + (2 + 5)! \times 5! + 06! \\ 605528 &:= 8 + (2 + 5)! \times 5! + 06! \\ 605529 &:= 9 + (2 + 5)! \times 5! + 06! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 605570 &:= 0 + 7! \times 5! + 50 + 6! \\ 605571 &:= 1 + 7! \times 5! + 50 + 6! \\ 605572 &:= 2 + 7! \times 5! + 50 + 6! \\ 605573 &:= 3 + 7! \times 5! + 50 + 6! \\ 605574 &:= 4 + 7! \times 5! + 50 + 6! \\ 605575 &:= 5 + 7! \times 5! + 50 + 6! \\ 605576 &:= 6 + 7! \times 5! + 50 + 6! \\ 605577 &:= 7 + 7! \times 5! + 50 + 6! \\ 605578 &:= 8 + 7! \times 5! + 50 + 6! \\ 605579 &:= 9 + 7! \times 5! + 50 + 6! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 609840 &:= 0 + 4! \times 8! - 9! + (0! + 6)! \\ 609841 &:= 1 + 4! \times 8! - 9! + (0! + 6)! \\ 609842 &:= 2 + 4! \times 8! - 9! + (0! + 6)! \\ 609843 &:= 3 + 4! \times 8! - 9! + (0! + 6)! \\ 609844 &:= 4 + 4! \times 8! - 9! + (0! + 6)! \\ 609845 &:= 5 + 4! \times 8! - 9! + (0! + 6)! \\ 609846 &:= 6 + 4! \times 8! - 9! + (0! + 6)! \\ 609847 &:= 7 + 4! \times 8! - 9! + (0! + 6)! \\ 609848 &:= 8 + 4! \times 8! - 9! + (0! + 6)! \\ 609849 &:= 9 + 4! \times 8! - 9! + (0! + 6)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 610560 &:= 0 + 6! + (5! + 0!) \times (1 + 6)! \\ 610561 &:= 1 + 6! + (5! + 0!) \times (1 + 6)! \\ 610562 &:= 2 + 6! + (5! + 0!) \times (1 + 6)! \\ 610563 &:= 3 + 6! + (5! + 0!) \times (1 + 6)! \\ 610564 &:= 4 + 6! + (5! + 0!) \times (1 + 6)! \\ 610565 &:= 5 + 6! + (5! + 0!) \times (1 + 6)! \\ 610566 &:= 6 + 6! + (5! + 0!) \times (1 + 6)! \\ 610567 &:= 7 + 6! + (5! + 0!) \times (1 + 6)! \\ 610568 &:= 8 + 6! + (5! + 0!) \times (1 + 6)! \\ 610569 &:= 9 + 6! + (5! + 0!) \times (1 + 6)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 617760 &:= 0 + (6 + 7)! / (7! + (1 + 6)!) \\ 617761 &:= 1 + (6 + 7)! / (7! + (1 + 6)!) \\ 617762 &:= 2 + (6 + 7)! / (7! + (1 + 6)!) \\ 617763 &:= 3 + (6 + 7)! / (7! + (1 + 6)!) \\ 617764 &:= 4 + (6 + 7)! / (7! + (1 + 6)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}617765 &:= 5 + (6 + 7)! / (7! + (1 + 6)!) \\617766 &:= 6 + (6 + 7)! / (7! + (1 + 6)!) \\617767 &:= 7 + (6 + 7)! / (7! + (1 + 6)!) \\617768 &:= 8 + (6 + 7)! / (7! + (1 + 6)!) \\617769 &:= 9 + (6 + 7)! / (7! + (1 + 6)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}623700 &:= 0 + (0! + 7 + 3)! / 2^6 \\623701 &:= 1 + (0! + 7 + 3)! / 2^6 \\623702 &:= 2 + (0! + 7 + 3)! / 2^6 \\623703 &:= 3 + (0! + 7 + 3)! / 2^6 \\623704 &:= 4 + (0! + 7 + 3)! / 2^6 \\623705 &:= 5 + (0! + 7 + 3)! / 2^6 \\623706 &:= 6 + (0! + 7 + 3)! / 2^6 \\623707 &:= 7 + (0! + 7 + 3)! / 2^6 \\623708 &:= 8 + (0! + 7 + 3)! / 2^6 \\623709 &:= 9 + (0! + 7 + 3)! / 2^6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}632880 &:= 0 + (882 - 3) \times 6! \\632881 &:= 1 + (882 - 3) \times 6! \\632882 &:= 2 + (882 - 3) \times 6! \\632883 &:= 3 + (882 - 3) \times 6! \\632884 &:= 4 + (882 - 3) \times 6! \\632885 &:= 5 + (882 - 3) \times 6! \\632886 &:= 6 + (882 - 3) \times 6! \\632887 &:= 7 + (882 - 3) \times 6! \\632888 &:= 8 + (882 - 3) \times 6! \\632889 &:= 9 + (882 - 3) \times 6! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}635760 &:= 0 + 6! \times 7 \times (5! + 3!) + 6! \\635761 &:= 1 + 6! \times 7 \times (5! + 3!) + 6! \\635762 &:= 2 + 6! \times 7 \times (5! + 3!) + 6! \\635763 &:= 3 + 6! \times 7 \times (5! + 3!) + 6! \\635764 &:= 4 + 6! \times 7 \times (5! + 3!) + 6! \\635765 &:= 5 + 6! \times 7 \times (5! + 3!) + 6! \\635766 &:= 6 + 6! \times 7 \times (5! + 3!) + 6! \\635767 &:= 7 + 6! \times 7 \times (5! + 3!) + 6! \\635768 &:= 8 + 6! \times 7 \times (5! + 3!) + 6! \end{aligned}$$

$$635769 := 9 + 6! \times 7 \times (5! + 3!) + 6!$$

$$\begin{aligned}650880 &:= 0 - 8! + 8 \times 05! \times 6! \\650881 &:= 1 - 8! + 8 \times 05! \times 6! \\650882 &:= 2 - 8! + 8 \times 05! \times 6! \\650883 &:= 3 - 8! + 8 \times 05! \times 6! \\650884 &:= 4 - 8! + 8 \times 05! \times 6! \\650885 &:= 5 - 8! + 8 \times 05! \times 6! \\650886 &:= 6 - 8! + 8 \times 05! \times 6! \\650887 &:= 7 - 8! + 8 \times 05! \times 6! \\650888 &:= 8 - 8! + 8 \times 05! \times 6! \\650889 &:= 9 - 8! + 8 \times 05! \times 6! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}655840 &:= 0 + (4! + 8^5) \times 5! / 6 \\655841 &:= 1 + (4! + 8^5) \times 5! / 6 \\655842 &:= 2 + (4! + 8^5) \times 5! / 6 \\655843 &:= 3 + (4! + 8^5) \times 5! / 6 \\655844 &:= 4 + (4! + 8^5) \times 5! / 6 \\655845 &:= 5 + (4! + 8^5) \times 5! / 6 \\655846 &:= 6 + (4! + 8^5) \times 5! / 6 \\655847 &:= 7 + (4! + 8^5) \times 5! / 6 \\655848 &:= 8 + (4! + 8^5) \times 5! / 6 \\655849 &:= 9 + (4! + 8^5) \times 5! / 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}656640 &:= 0 + 4 \times (6! + 6!) \times (5! - 6) \\656641 &:= 1 + 4 \times (6! + 6!) \times (5! - 6) \\656642 &:= 2 + 4 \times (6! + 6!) \times (5! - 6) \\656643 &:= 3 + 4 \times (6! + 6!) \times (5! - 6) \\656644 &:= 4 + 4 \times (6! + 6!) \times (5! - 6) \\656645 &:= 5 + 4 \times (6! + 6!) \times (5! - 6) \\656646 &:= 6 + 4 \times (6! + 6!) \times (5! - 6) \\656647 &:= 7 + 4 \times (6! + 6!) \times (5! - 6) \\656648 &:= 8 + 4 \times (6! + 6!) \times (5! - 6) \\656649 &:= 9 + 4 \times (6! + 6!) \times (5! - 6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}657360 &:= 0 + 6! + (3!! + 7!) \times (5! - 6) \\657361 &:= 1 + 6! + (3!! + 7!) \times (5! - 6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}657362 &:= 2 + 6! + (3!! + 7!) \times (5! - 6) \\657363 &:= 3 + 6! + (3!! + 7!) \times (5! - 6) \\657364 &:= 4 + 6! + (3!! + 7!) \times (5! - 6) \\657365 &:= 5 + 6! + (3!! + 7!) \times (5! - 6) \\657366 &:= 6 + 6! + (3!! + 7!) \times (5! - 6) \\657367 &:= 7 + 6! + (3!! + 7!) \times (5! - 6) \\657368 &:= 8 + 6! + (3!! + 7!) \times (5! - 6) \\657369 &:= 9 + 6! + (3!! + 7!) \times (5! - 6)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}663840 &:= 0 + (4 + 8)!/3!! - 6! - 6! \\663841 &:= 1 + (4 + 8)!/3!! - 6! - 6! \\663842 &:= 2 + (4 + 8)!/3!! - 6! - 6! \\663843 &:= 3 + (4 + 8)!/3!! - 6! - 6! \\663844 &:= 4 + (4 + 8)!/3!! - 6! - 6! \\663845 &:= 5 + (4 + 8)!/3!! - 6! - 6! \\663846 &:= 6 + (4 + 8)!/3!! - 6! - 6! \\663847 &:= 7 + (4 + 8)!/3!! - 6! - 6! \\663848 &:= 8 + (4 + 8)!/3!! - 6! - 6! \\663849 &:= 9 + (4 + 8)!/3!! - 6! - 6!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}664560 &:= 0 - 6! + (5!/(4 + 6))/6! \\664561 &:= 1 - 6! + (5!/(4 + 6))/6! \\664562 &:= 2 - 6! + (5!/(4 + 6))/6! \\664563 &:= 3 - 6! + (5!/(4 + 6))/6! \\664564 &:= 4 - 6! + (5!/(4 + 6))/6! \\664565 &:= 5 - 6! + (5!/(4 + 6))/6! \\664566 &:= 6 - 6! + (5!/(4 + 6))/6! \\664567 &:= 7 - 6! + (5!/(4 + 6))/6! \\664568 &:= 8 - 6! + (5!/(4 + 6))/6! \\664569 &:= 9 - 6! + (5!/(4 + 6))/6!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}665280 &:= 0 + ((8 + 2)/5 \times 6)!/6! \\665281 &:= 1 + ((8 + 2)/5 \times 6)!/6! \\665282 &:= 2 + ((8 + 2)/5 \times 6)!/6! \\665283 &:= 3 + ((8 + 2)/5 \times 6)!/6! \\665284 &:= 4 + ((8 + 2)/5 \times 6)!/6! \\665285 &:= 5 + ((8 + 2)/5 \times 6)!/6! \\665286 &:= 6 + ((8 + 2)/5 \times 6)!/6! \\665287 &:= 7 + ((8 + 2)/5 \times 6)!/6! \\665288 &:= 8 + ((8 + 2)/5 \times 6)!/6!\end{aligned}$$

$$665289 := 9 + ((8 + 2)/5 \times 6)!/6!$$

$$\begin{aligned}665790 &:= 0 + (9! + (7 + 5)!)/6! + 6 \\665791 &:= 1 + (9! + (7 + 5)!)/6! + 6 \\665792 &:= 2 + (9! + (7 + 5)!)/6! + 6 \\665793 &:= 3 + (9! + (7 + 5)!)/6! + 6 \\665794 &:= 4 + (9! + (7 + 5)!)/6! + 6 \\665795 &:= 5 + (9! + (7 + 5)!)/6! + 6 \\665796 &:= 6 + (9! + (7 + 5)!)/6! + 6 \\665797 &:= 7 + (9! + (7 + 5)!)/6! + 6 \\665798 &:= 8 + (9! + (7 + 5)!)/6! + 6 \\665799 &:= 9 + (9! + (7 + 5)!)/6! + 6\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}666000 &:= 0 + ((0! + 0!) \times 6)!/6! + 6! \\666001 &:= 1 + ((0! + 0!) \times 6)!/6! + 6! \\666002 &:= 2 + ((0! + 0!) \times 6)!/6! + 6! \\666003 &:= 3 + ((0! + 0!) \times 6)!/6! + 6! \\666004 &:= 4 + ((0! + 0!) \times 6)!/6! + 6! \\666005 &:= 5 + ((0! + 0!) \times 6)!/6! + 6! \\666006 &:= 6 + ((0! + 0!) \times 6)!/6! + 6! \\666007 &:= 7 + ((0! + 0!) \times 6)!/6! + 6! \\666008 &:= 8 + ((0! + 0!) \times 6)!/6! + 6! \\666009 &:= 9 + ((0! + 0!) \times 6)!/6! + 6!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}666720 &:= 0 + 2 \times (7! \times 66 + 6!) \\666721 &:= 1 + 2 \times (7! \times 66 + 6!) \\666722 &:= 2 + 2 \times (7! \times 66 + 6!) \\666723 &:= 3 + 2 \times (7! \times 66 + 6!) \\666724 &:= 4 + 2 \times (7! \times 66 + 6!) \\666725 &:= 5 + 2 \times (7! \times 66 + 6!) \\666726 &:= 6 + 2 \times (7! \times 66 + 6!) \\666727 &:= 7 + 2 \times (7! \times 66 + 6!) \\666728 &:= 8 + 2 \times (7! \times 66 + 6!) \\666729 &:= 9 + 2 \times (7! \times 66 + 6!)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}673920 &:= 0 + 2 \times (9! - 3! \times (7! - 6!)) \\673921 &:= 1 + 2 \times (9! - 3! \times (7! - 6!)) \\673922 &:= 2 + 2 \times (9! - 3! \times (7! - 6!)) \\673923 &:= 3 + 2 \times (9! - 3! \times (7! - 6!)) \\673924 &:= 4 + 2 \times (9! - 3! \times (7! - 6!)) \\673925 &:= 5 + 2 \times (9! - 3! \times (7! - 6!))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}673926 &:= 6 + 2 \times (9! - 3! \times (7! - 6!)) \\673927 &:= 7 + 2 \times (9! - 3! \times (7! - 6!)) \\673928 &:= 8 + 2 \times (9! - 3! \times (7! - 6!)) \\673929 &:= 9 + 2 \times (9! - 3! \times (7! - 6!))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}683520 &:= 0 + (2 \times 5! + 3!!) \times (-8 + 6!) \\683521 &:= 1 + (2 \times 5! + 3!!) \times (-8 + 6!) \\683522 &:= 2 + (2 \times 5! + 3!!) \times (-8 + 6!) \\683523 &:= 3 + (2 \times 5! + 3!!) \times (-8 + 6!) \\683524 &:= 4 + (2 \times 5! + 3!!) \times (-8 + 6!) \\683525 &:= 5 + (2 \times 5! + 3!!) \times (-8 + 6!) \\683526 &:= 6 + (2 \times 5! + 3!!) \times (-8 + 6!) \\683527 &:= 7 + (2 \times 5! + 3!!) \times (-8 + 6!) \\683528 &:= 8 + (2 \times 5! + 3!!) \times (-8 + 6!) \\683529 &:= 9 + (2 \times 5! + 3!!) \times (-8 + 6!)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}685440 &:= 0 + (-4/4 + 5!) \times 8 \times 6! \\685441 &:= 1 + (-4/4 + 5!) \times 8 \times 6! \\685442 &:= 2 + (-4/4 + 5!) \times 8 \times 6! \\685443 &:= 3 + (-4/4 + 5!) \times 8 \times 6! \\685444 &:= 4 + (-4/4 + 5!) \times 8 \times 6! \\685445 &:= 5 + (-4/4 + 5!) \times 8 \times 6! \\685446 &:= 6 + (-4/4 + 5!) \times 8 \times 6! \\685447 &:= 7 + (-4/4 + 5!) \times 8 \times 6! \\685448 &:= 8 + (-4/4 + 5!) \times 8 \times 6! \\685449 &:= 9 + (-4/4 + 5!) \times 8 \times 6!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}685920 &:= 0 + 2 \times (9! - 5!) - 8! + 6! \\685921 &:= 1 + 2 \times (9! - 5!) - 8! + 6! \\685922 &:= 2 + 2 \times (9! - 5!) - 8! + 6! \\685923 &:= 3 + 2 \times (9! - 5!) - 8! + 6! \\685924 &:= 4 + 2 \times (9! - 5!) - 8! + 6! \\685925 &:= 5 + 2 \times (9! - 5!) - 8! + 6! \\685926 &:= 6 + 2 \times (9! - 5!) - 8! + 6! \\685927 &:= 7 + 2 \times (9! - 5!) - 8! + 6! \\685928 &:= 8 + 2 \times (9! - 5!) - 8! + 6! \\685929 &:= 9 + 2 \times (9! - 5!) - 8! + 6!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}693360 &:= 0 + (6! + 3^3 \times 9) \times 6! \\693361 &:= 1 + (6! + 3^3 \times 9) \times 6!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}693362 &:= 2 + (6! + 3^3 \times 9) \times 6! \\693363 &:= 3 + (6! + 3^3 \times 9) \times 6! \\693364 &:= 4 + (6! + 3^3 \times 9) \times 6! \\693365 &:= 5 + (6! + 3^3 \times 9) \times 6! \\693366 &:= 6 + (6! + 3^3 \times 9) \times 6! \\693367 &:= 7 + (6! + 3^3 \times 9) \times 6! \\693368 &:= 8 + (6! + 3^3 \times 9) \times 6! \\693369 &:= 9 + (6! + 3^3 \times 9) \times 6!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}695520 &:= 0 + 2 \times (-5! \times 5! + 9! - 6!) \\695521 &:= 1 + 2 \times (-5! \times 5! + 9! - 6!) \\695522 &:= 2 + 2 \times (-5! \times 5! + 9! - 6!) \\695523 &:= 3 + 2 \times (-5! \times 5! + 9! - 6!) \\695524 &:= 4 + 2 \times (-5! \times 5! + 9! - 6!) \\695525 &:= 5 + 2 \times (-5! \times 5! + 9! - 6!) \\695526 &:= 6 + 2 \times (-5! \times 5! + 9! - 6!) \\695527 &:= 7 + 2 \times (-5! \times 5! + 9! - 6!) \\695528 &:= 8 + 2 \times (-5! \times 5! + 9! - 6!) \\695529 &:= 9 + 2 \times (-5! \times 5! + 9! - 6!)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}696960 &:= 0 + 6! \times 969 - 6! \\696961 &:= 1 + 6! \times 969 - 6! \\696962 &:= 2 + 6! \times 969 - 6! \\696963 &:= 3 + 6! \times 969 - 6! \\696964 &:= 4 + 6! \times 969 - 6! \\696965 &:= 5 + 6! \times 969 - 6! \\696966 &:= 6 + 6! \times 969 - 6! \\696967 &:= 7 + 6! \times 969 - 6! \\696968 &:= 8 + 6! \times 969 - 6! \\696969 &:= 9 + 6! \times 969 - 6!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}697680 &:= 0 + (8!/(6 \times 7) + 9) \times 6! \\697681 &:= 1 + (8!/(6 \times 7) + 9) \times 6! \\697682 &:= 2 + (8!/(6 \times 7) + 9) \times 6! \\697683 &:= 3 + (8!/(6 \times 7) + 9) \times 6! \\697684 &:= 4 + (8!/(6 \times 7) + 9) \times 6! \\697685 &:= 5 + (8!/(6 \times 7) + 9) \times 6! \\697686 &:= 6 + (8!/(6 \times 7) + 9) \times 6! \\697687 &:= 7 + (8!/(6 \times 7) + 9) \times 6! \\697688 &:= 8 + (8!/(6 \times 7) + 9) \times 6! \\697689 &:= 9 + (8!/(6 \times 7) + 9) \times 6!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 699840 &:= 0 + (4 + 8) \times 9 \times 9 \times 6! \\ 699841 &:= 1 + (4 + 8) \times 9 \times 9 \times 6! \\ 699842 &:= 2 + (4 + 8) \times 9 \times 9 \times 6! \\ 699843 &:= 3 + (4 + 8) \times 9 \times 9 \times 6! \\ 699844 &:= 4 + (4 + 8) \times 9 \times 9 \times 6! \\ 699845 &:= 5 + (4 + 8) \times 9 \times 9 \times 6! \\ 699846 &:= 6 + (4 + 8) \times 9 \times 9 \times 6! \\ 699847 &:= 7 + (4 + 8) \times 9 \times 9 \times 6! \\ 699848 &:= 8 + (4 + 8) \times 9 \times 9 \times 6! \\ 699849 &:= 9 + (4 + 8) \times 9 \times 9 \times 6! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 700560 &:= 0 + (6! + 5!)^{0!+0!} - 7! \\ 700561 &:= 1 + (6! + 5!)^{0!+0!} - 7! \\ 700562 &:= 2 + (6! + 5!)^{0!+0!} - 7! \\ 700563 &:= 3 + (6! + 5!)^{0!+0!} - 7! \\ 700564 &:= 4 + (6! + 5!)^{0!+0!} - 7! \\ 700565 &:= 5 + (6! + 5!)^{0!+0!} - 7! \\ 700566 &:= 6 + (6! + 5!)^{0!+0!} - 7! \\ 700567 &:= 7 + (6! + 5!)^{0!+0!} - 7! \\ 700568 &:= 8 + (6! + 5!)^{0!+0!} - 7! \\ 700569 &:= 9 + (6! + 5!)^{0!+0!} - 7! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 705740 &:= 0 + 4 \times 7 \times 5 \times (0! + 7!) \\ 705741 &:= 1 + 4 \times 7 \times 5 \times (0! + 7!) \\ 705742 &:= 2 + 4 \times 7 \times 5 \times (0! + 7!) \\ 705743 &:= 3 + 4 \times 7 \times 5 \times (0! + 7!) \\ 705744 &:= 4 + 4 \times 7 \times 5 \times (0! + 7!) \\ 705745 &:= 5 + 4 \times 7 \times 5 \times (0! + 7!) \\ 705746 &:= 6 + 4 \times 7 \times 5 \times (0! + 7!) \\ 705747 &:= 7 + 4 \times 7 \times 5 \times (0! + 7!) \\ 705748 &:= 8 + 4 \times 7 \times 5 \times (0! + 7!) \\ 705749 &:= 9 + 4 \times 7 \times 5 \times (0! + 7!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 715920 &:= 0 + 2 \times (9! + 5! - 1 \times 7!) \\ 715921 &:= 1 + 2 \times (9! + 5! - 1 \times 7!) \\ 715922 &:= 2 + 2 \times (9! + 5! - 1 \times 7!) \\ 715923 &:= 3 + 2 \times (9! + 5! - 1 \times 7!) \\ 715924 &:= 4 + 2 \times (9! + 5! - 1 \times 7!) \\ 715925 &:= 5 + 2 \times (9! + 5! - 1 \times 7!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 715926 &:= 6 + 2 \times (9! + 5! - 1 \times 7!) \\ 715927 &:= 7 + 2 \times (9! + 5! - 1 \times 7!) \\ 715928 &:= 8 + 2 \times (9! + 5! - 1 \times 7!) \\ 715929 &:= 9 + 2 \times (9! + 5! - 1 \times 7!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 724320 &:= 0 + 2 \times (-3!! + (4^2 - 7)!) \\ 724321 &:= 1 + 2 \times (-3!! + (4^2 - 7)!) \\ 724322 &:= 2 + 2 \times (-3!! + (4^2 - 7)!) \\ 724323 &:= 3 + 2 \times (-3!! + (4^2 - 7)!) \\ 724324 &:= 4 + 2 \times (-3!! + (4^2 - 7)!) \\ 724325 &:= 5 + 2 \times (-3!! + (4^2 - 7)!) \\ 724326 &:= 6 + 2 \times (-3!! + (4^2 - 7)!) \\ 724327 &:= 7 + 2 \times (-3!! + (4^2 - 7)!) \\ 724328 &:= 8 + 2 \times (-3!! + (4^2 - 7)!) \\ 724329 &:= 9 + 2 \times (-3!! + (4^2 - 7)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 725480 &:= 0 + 8 + (4! + 5!) \times (-2 + 7!) \\ 725481 &:= 1 + 8 + (4! + 5!) \times (-2 + 7!) \\ 725482 &:= 2 + 8 + (4! + 5!) \times (-2 + 7!) \\ 725483 &:= 3 + 8 + (4! + 5!) \times (-2 + 7!) \\ 725484 &:= 4 + 8 + (4! + 5!) \times (-2 + 7!) \\ 725485 &:= 5 + 8 + (4! + 5!) \times (-2 + 7!) \\ 725486 &:= 6 + 8 + (4! + 5!) \times (-2 + 7!) \\ 725487 &:= 7 + 8 + (4! + 5!) \times (-2 + 7!) \\ 725488 &:= 8 + 8 + (4! + 5!) \times (-2 + 7!) \\ 725489 &:= 9 + 8 + (4! + 5!) \times (-2 + 7!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 725520 &:= 0 + 2 \times (-5! + (-5 + 2 \times 7)!) \\ 725521 &:= 1 + 2 \times (-5! + (-5 + 2 \times 7)!) \\ 725522 &:= 2 + 2 \times (-5! + (-5 + 2 \times 7)!) \\ 725523 &:= 3 + 2 \times (-5! + (-5 + 2 \times 7)!) \\ 725524 &:= 4 + 2 \times (-5! + (-5 + 2 \times 7)!) \\ 725525 &:= 5 + 2 \times (-5! + (-5 + 2 \times 7)!) \\ 725526 &:= 6 + 2 \times (-5! + (-5 + 2 \times 7)!) \\ 725527 &:= 7 + 2 \times (-5! + (-5 + 2 \times 7)!) \\ 725528 &:= 8 + 2 \times (-5! + (-5 + 2 \times 7)!) \\ 725529 &:= 9 + 2 \times (-5! + (-5 + 2 \times 7)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 725750 &:= 0 + (-5 + 7) \times (-5 + (2 + 7)!) \\ 725751 &:= 1 + (-5 + 7) \times (-5 + (2 + 7)!) \\ 725752 &:= 2 + (-5 + 7) \times (-5 + (2 + 7)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 725753 &:= 3 + (-5 + 7) \times (-5 + (2 + 7)!) \\ 725754 &:= 4 + (-5 + 7) \times (-5 + (2 + 7)!) \\ 725755 &:= 5 + (-5 + 7) \times (-5 + (2 + 7)!) \\ 725756 &:= 6 + (-5 + 7) \times (-5 + (2 + 7)!) \\ 725757 &:= 7 + (-5 + 7) \times (-5 + (2 + 7)!) \\ 725758 &:= 8 + (-5 + 7) \times (-5 + (2 + 7)!) \\ 725759 &:= 9 + (-5 + 7) \times (-5 + (2 + 7)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 725760 &:= 0 + 6! \times (7 + 5)^2 \times 7 \\ 725761 &:= 1 + 6! \times (7 + 5)^2 \times 7 \\ 725762 &:= 2 + 6! \times (7 + 5)^2 \times 7 \\ 725763 &:= 3 + 6! \times (7 + 5)^2 \times 7 \\ 725764 &:= 4 + 6! \times (7 + 5)^2 \times 7 \\ 725765 &:= 5 + 6! \times (7 + 5)^2 \times 7 \\ 725766 &:= 6 + 6! \times (7 + 5)^2 \times 7 \\ 725767 &:= 7 + 6! \times (7 + 5)^2 \times 7 \\ 725768 &:= 8 + 6! \times (7 + 5)^2 \times 7 \\ 725769 &:= 9 + 6! \times (7 + 5)^2 \times 7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 725850 &:= 0 + (5 + 8!) \times (5^2 - 7) \\ 725851 &:= 1 + (5 + 8!) \times (5^2 - 7) \\ 725852 &:= 2 + (5 + 8!) \times (5^2 - 7) \\ 725853 &:= 3 + (5 + 8!) \times (5^2 - 7) \\ 725854 &:= 4 + (5 + 8!) \times (5^2 - 7) \\ 725855 &:= 5 + (5 + 8!) \times (5^2 - 7) \\ 725856 &:= 6 + (5 + 8!) \times (5^2 - 7) \\ 725857 &:= 7 + (5 + 8!) \times (5^2 - 7) \\ 725858 &:= 8 + (5 + 8!) \times (5^2 - 7) \\ 725859 &:= 9 + (5 + 8!) \times (5^2 - 7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 730920 &:= 0 + 2 \times 9! + (-0! + 3!)! + 7! \\ 730921 &:= 1 + 2 \times 9! + (-0! + 3!)! + 7! \\ 730922 &:= 2 + 2 \times 9! + (-0! + 3!)! + 7! \\ 730923 &:= 3 + 2 \times 9! + (-0! + 3!)! + 7! \\ 730924 &:= 4 + 2 \times 9! + (-0! + 3!)! + 7! \\ 730925 &:= 5 + 2 \times 9! + (-0! + 3!)! + 7! \\ 730926 &:= 6 + 2 \times 9! + (-0! + 3!)! + 7! \\ 730927 &:= 7 + 2 \times 9! + (-0! + 3!)! + 7! \\ 730928 &:= 8 + 2 \times 9! + (-0! + 3!)! + 7! \end{aligned}$$

$$730929 := 9 + 2 \times 9! + (-0! + 3!)! + 7!$$

$$\begin{aligned} 732960 &:= 0 + (6! + 9!) \times 2 + 3!! + 7! \\ 732961 &:= 1 + (6! + 9!) \times 2 + 3!! + 7! \\ 732962 &:= 2 + (6! + 9!) \times 2 + 3!! + 7! \\ 732963 &:= 3 + (6! + 9!) \times 2 + 3!! + 7! \\ 732964 &:= 4 + (6! + 9!) \times 2 + 3!! + 7! \\ 732965 &:= 5 + (6! + 9!) \times 2 + 3!! + 7! \\ 732966 &:= 6 + (6! + 9!) \times 2 + 3!! + 7! \\ 732967 &:= 7 + (6! + 9!) \times 2 + 3!! + 7! \\ 732968 &:= 8 + (6! + 9!) \times 2 + 3!! + 7! \\ 732969 &:= 9 + (6! + 9!) \times 2 + 3!! + 7! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 733680 &:= 0 + (8! + 6!) \times 3 \times 3! - 7! \\ 733681 &:= 1 + (8! + 6!) \times 3 \times 3! - 7! \\ 733682 &:= 2 + (8! + 6!) \times 3 \times 3! - 7! \\ 733683 &:= 3 + (8! + 6!) \times 3 \times 3! - 7! \\ 733684 &:= 4 + (8! + 6!) \times 3 \times 3! - 7! \\ 733685 &:= 5 + (8! + 6!) \times 3 \times 3! - 7! \\ 733686 &:= 6 + (8! + 6!) \times 3 \times 3! - 7! \\ 733687 &:= 7 + (8! + 6!) \times 3 \times 3! - 7! \\ 733688 &:= 8 + (8! + 6!) \times 3 \times 3! - 7! \\ 733689 &:= 9 + (8! + 6!) \times 3 \times 3! - 7! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 735840 &:= 0 + (4 \times 8 + 5! - 3!) \times 7! \\ 735841 &:= 1 + (4 \times 8 + 5! - 3!) \times 7! \\ 735842 &:= 2 + (4 \times 8 + 5! - 3!) \times 7! \\ 735843 &:= 3 + (4 \times 8 + 5! - 3!) \times 7! \\ 735844 &:= 4 + (4 \times 8 + 5! - 3!) \times 7! \\ 735845 &:= 5 + (4 \times 8 + 5! - 3!) \times 7! \\ 735846 &:= 6 + (4 \times 8 + 5! - 3!) \times 7! \\ 735847 &:= 7 + (4 \times 8 + 5! - 3!) \times 7! \\ 735848 &:= 8 + (4 \times 8 + 5! - 3!) \times 7! \\ 735849 &:= 9 + (4 \times 8 + 5! - 3!) \times 7! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 735920 &:= 0 + 2 \times (9! + 5!/3 + 7!) \\ 735921 &:= 1 + 2 \times (9! + 5!/3 + 7!) \\ 735922 &:= 2 + 2 \times (9! + 5!/3 + 7!) \\ 735923 &:= 3 + 2 \times (9! + 5!/3 + 7!) \\ 735924 &:= 4 + 2 \times (9! + 5!/3 + 7!) \\ 735925 &:= 5 + 2 \times (9! + 5!/3 + 7!) \\ 735926 &:= 6 + 2 \times (9! + 5!/3 + 7!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}735927 &:= 7 + 2 \times (9! + 5!/3 + 7!) \\735928 &:= 8 + 2 \times (9! + 5!/3 + 7!) \\735929 &:= 9 + 2 \times (9! + 5!/3 + 7!)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}737280 &:= 0 + 8! \times 2^7 \times 3!/7! \\737281 &:= 1 + 8! \times 2^7 \times 3!/7! \\737282 &:= 2 + 8! \times 2^7 \times 3!/7! \\737283 &:= 3 + 8! \times 2^7 \times 3!/7! \\737284 &:= 4 + 8! \times 2^7 \times 3!/7! \\737285 &:= 5 + 8! \times 2^7 \times 3!/7! \\737286 &:= 6 + 8! \times 2^7 \times 3!/7! \\737287 &:= 7 + 8! \times 2^7 \times 3!/7! \\737288 &:= 8 + 8! \times 2^7 \times 3!/7! \\737289 &:= 9 + 8! \times 2^7 \times 3!/7!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}745920 &:= 0 + 2 \times 9! + 5! \times 4! \times 7 \\745921 &:= 1 + 2 \times 9! + 5! \times 4! \times 7 \\745922 &:= 2 + 2 \times 9! + 5! \times 4! \times 7 \\745923 &:= 3 + 2 \times 9! + 5! \times 4! \times 7 \\745924 &:= 4 + 2 \times 9! + 5! \times 4! \times 7 \\745925 &:= 5 + 2 \times 9! + 5! \times 4! \times 7 \\745926 &:= 6 + 2 \times 9! + 5! \times 4! \times 7 \\745927 &:= 7 + 2 \times 9! + 5! \times 4! \times 7 \\745928 &:= 8 + 2 \times 9! + 5! \times 4! \times 7 \\745929 &:= 9 + 2 \times 9! + 5! \times 4! \times 7\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}766080 &:= 0 + 8! \times (6 + 6 + 7) \\766081 &:= 1 + 8! \times (6 + 6 + 7) \\766082 &:= 2 + 8! \times (6 + 6 + 7) \\766083 &:= 3 + 8! \times (6 + 6 + 7) \\766084 &:= 4 + 8! \times (6 + 6 + 7) \\766085 &:= 5 + 8! \times (6 + 6 + 7) \\766086 &:= 6 + 8! \times (6 + 6 + 7) \\766087 &:= 7 + 8! \times (6 + 6 + 7) \\766088 &:= 8 + 8! \times (6 + 6 + 7) \\766089 &:= 9 + 8! \times (6 + 6 + 7)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}772560 &:= 0 + 6! \times 5! \times (2 + 7) - 7! \\772561 &:= 1 + 6! \times 5! \times (2 + 7) - 7! \\772562 &:= 2 + 6! \times 5! \times (2 + 7) - 7!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}772563 &:= 3 + 6! \times 5! \times (2 + 7) - 7! \\772564 &:= 4 + 6! \times 5! \times (2 + 7) - 7! \\772565 &:= 5 + 6! \times 5! \times (2 + 7) - 7! \\772566 &:= 6 + 6! \times 5! \times (2 + 7) - 7! \\772567 &:= 7 + 6! \times 5! \times (2 + 7) - 7! \\772568 &:= 8 + 6! \times 5! \times (2 + 7) - 7! \\772569 &:= 9 + 6! \times 5! \times (2 + 7) - 7!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}776160 &:= 0 + (6 + 16) \times 7! \times 7 \\776161 &:= 1 + (6 + 16) \times 7! \times 7 \\776162 &:= 2 + (6 + 16) \times 7! \times 7 \\776163 &:= 3 + (6 + 16) \times 7! \times 7 \\776164 &:= 4 + (6 + 16) \times 7! \times 7 \\776165 &:= 5 + (6 + 16) \times 7! \times 7 \\776166 &:= 6 + (6 + 16) \times 7! \times 7 \\776167 &:= 7 + (6 + 16) \times 7! \times 7 \\776168 &:= 8 + (6 + 16) \times 7! \times 7 \\776169 &:= 9 + (6 + 16) \times 7! \times 7\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}786240 &:= 0 + (-4! + 2 \times 6!/8) \times 7! \\786241 &:= 1 + (-4! + 2 \times 6!/8) \times 7! \\786242 &:= 2 + (-4! + 2 \times 6!/8) \times 7! \\786243 &:= 3 + (-4! + 2 \times 6!/8) \times 7! \\786244 &:= 4 + (-4! + 2 \times 6!/8) \times 7! \\786245 &:= 5 + (-4! + 2 \times 6!/8) \times 7! \\786246 &:= 6 + (-4! + 2 \times 6!/8) \times 7! \\786247 &:= 7 + (-4! + 2 \times 6!/8) \times 7! \\786248 &:= 8 + (-4! + 2 \times 6!/8) \times 7! \\786249 &:= 9 + (-4! + 2 \times 6!/8) \times 7!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}796320 &:= 0 + (-2 + (3!! + 6!)/9) \times 7! \\796321 &:= 1 + (-2 + (3!! + 6!)/9) \times 7! \\796322 &:= 2 + (-2 + (3!! + 6!)/9) \times 7! \\796323 &:= 3 + (-2 + (3!! + 6!)/9) \times 7! \\796324 &:= 4 + (-2 + (3!! + 6!)/9) \times 7! \\796325 &:= 5 + (-2 + (3!! + 6!)/9) \times 7! \\796326 &:= 6 + (-2 + (3!! + 6!)/9) \times 7! \\796327 &:= 7 + (-2 + (3!! + 6!)/9) \times 7! \\796328 &:= 8 + (-2 + (3!! + 6!)/9) \times 7! \\796329 &:= 9 + (-2 + (3!! + 6!)/9) \times 7!\end{aligned}$$

$$806380 := 0 + (8 + 3! + 6) \times (-0! + 8!)$$

$$\begin{aligned}806381 &:= 1 + (8 + 3! + 6) \times (-0! + 8!) \\806382 &:= 2 + (8 + 3! + 6) \times (-0! + 8!) \\806383 &:= 3 + (8 + 3! + 6) \times (-0! + 8!) \\806384 &:= 4 + (8 + 3! + 6) \times (-0! + 8!) \\806385 &:= 5 + (8 + 3! + 6) \times (-0! + 8!) \\806386 &:= 6 + (8 + 3! + 6) \times (-0! + 8!) \\806387 &:= 7 + (8 + 3! + 6) \times (-0! + 8!) \\806388 &:= 8 + (8 + 3! + 6) \times (-0! + 8!) \\806389 &:= 9 + (8 + 3! + 6) \times (-0! + 8!)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}806400 &:= 0 + (0! + 4! - 6 + 0!) \times 8! \\806401 &:= 1 + (0! + 4! - 6 + 0!) \times 8! \\806402 &:= 2 + (0! + 4! - 6 + 0!) \times 8! \\806403 &:= 3 + (0! + 4! - 6 + 0!) \times 8! \\806404 &:= 4 + (0! + 4! - 6 + 0!) \times 8! \\806405 &:= 5 + (0! + 4! - 6 + 0!) \times 8! \\806406 &:= 6 + (0! + 4! - 6 + 0!) \times 8! \\806407 &:= 7 + (0! + 4! - 6 + 0!) \times 8! \\806408 &:= 8 + (0! + 4! - 6 + 0!) \times 8! \\806409 &:= 9 + (0! + 4! - 6 + 0!) \times 8!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}806420 &:= 0 + 2 \times (4 + 6) \times (0! + 8!) \\806421 &:= 1 + 2 \times (4 + 6) \times (0! + 8!) \\806422 &:= 2 + 2 \times (4 + 6) \times (0! + 8!) \\806423 &:= 3 + 2 \times (4 + 6) \times (0! + 8!) \\806424 &:= 4 + 2 \times (4 + 6) \times (0! + 8!) \\806425 &:= 5 + 2 \times (4 + 6) \times (0! + 8!) \\806426 &:= 6 + 2 \times (4 + 6) \times (0! + 8!) \\806427 &:= 7 + 2 \times (4 + 6) \times (0! + 8!) \\806428 &:= 8 + 2 \times (4 + 6) \times (0! + 8!) \\806429 &:= 9 + 2 \times (4 + 6) \times (0! + 8!)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}806540 &:= 0 + 4 \times 5 \times (6 + 0! + 8!) \\806541 &:= 1 + 4 \times 5 \times (6 + 0! + 8!) \\806542 &:= 2 + 4 \times 5 \times (6 + 0! + 8!) \\806543 &:= 3 + 4 \times 5 \times (6 + 0! + 8!) \\806544 &:= 4 + 4 \times 5 \times (6 + 0! + 8!) \\806545 &:= 5 + 4 \times 5 \times (6 + 0! + 8!) \\806546 &:= 6 + 4 \times 5 \times (6 + 0! + 8!) \\806547 &:= 7 + 4 \times 5 \times (6 + 0! + 8!) \\806548 &:= 8 + 4 \times 5 \times (6 + 0! + 8!)\end{aligned}$$

$$806549 := 9 + 4 \times 5 \times (6 + 0! + 8!)$$

$$\begin{aligned}846720 &:= 0 + 2 \times 7 \times 6/4 \times 8! \\846721 &:= 1 + 2 \times 7 \times 6/4 \times 8! \\846722 &:= 2 + 2 \times 7 \times 6/4 \times 8! \\846723 &:= 3 + 2 \times 7 \times 6/4 \times 8! \\846724 &:= 4 + 2 \times 7 \times 6/4 \times 8! \\846725 &:= 5 + 2 \times 7 \times 6/4 \times 8! \\846726 &:= 6 + 2 \times 7 \times 6/4 \times 8! \\846727 &:= 7 + 2 \times 7 \times 6/4 \times 8! \\846728 &:= 8 + 2 \times 7 \times 6/4 \times 8! \\846729 &:= 9 + 2 \times 7 \times 6/4 \times 8!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}847230 &:= 0 + 3 \times (2 + 7 \times (4! + 8!)) \\847231 &:= 1 + 3 \times (2 + 7 \times (4! + 8!)) \\847232 &:= 2 + 3 \times (2 + 7 \times (4! + 8!)) \\847233 &:= 3 + 3 \times (2 + 7 \times (4! + 8!)) \\847234 &:= 4 + 3 \times (2 + 7 \times (4! + 8!)) \\847235 &:= 5 + 3 \times (2 + 7 \times (4! + 8!)) \\847236 &:= 6 + 3 \times (2 + 7 \times (4! + 8!)) \\847237 &:= 7 + 3 \times (2 + 7 \times (4! + 8!)) \\847238 &:= 8 + 3 \times (2 + 7 \times (4! + 8!)) \\847239 &:= 9 + 3 \times (2 + 7 \times (4! + 8!))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}855360 &:= 0 + (6 + 3!)/(5 \times (5! - 8)) \\855361 &:= 1 + (6 + 3!)/(5 \times (5! - 8)) \\855362 &:= 2 + (6 + 3!)/(5 \times (5! - 8)) \\855363 &:= 3 + (6 + 3!)/(5 \times (5! - 8)) \\855364 &:= 4 + (6 + 3!)/(5 \times (5! - 8)) \\855365 &:= 5 + (6 + 3!)/(5 \times (5! - 8)) \\855366 &:= 6 + (6 + 3!)/(5 \times (5! - 8)) \\855367 &:= 7 + (6 + 3!)/(5 \times (5! - 8)) \\855368 &:= 8 + (6 + 3!)/(5 \times (5! - 8)) \\855369 &:= 9 + (6 + 3!)/(5 \times (5! - 8))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}887040 &:= 0 + (4! - 0!) \times 7! \times 8 - 8! \\887041 &:= 1 + (4! - 0!) \times 7! \times 8 - 8! \\887042 &:= 2 + (4! - 0!) \times 7! \times 8 - 8! \\887043 &:= 3 + (4! - 0!) \times 7! \times 8 - 8! \\887044 &:= 4 + (4! - 0!) \times 7! \times 8 - 8! \\887045 &:= 5 + (4! - 0!) \times 7! \times 8 - 8! \\887046 &:= 6 + (4! - 0!) \times 7! \times 8 - 8!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}887047 &:= 7 + (4! - 0!) \times 7! \times 8 - 8! \\887048 &:= 8 + (4! - 0!) \times 7! \times 8 - 8! \\887049 &:= 9 + (4! - 0!) \times 7! \times 8 - 8!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}887760 &:= 0 + 6! + (7! + 7!) \times 88 \\887761 &:= 1 + 6! + (7! + 7!) \times 88 \\887762 &:= 2 + 6! + (7! + 7!) \times 88 \\887763 &:= 3 + 6! + (7! + 7!) \times 88 \\887764 &:= 4 + 6! + (7! + 7!) \times 88 \\887765 &:= 5 + 6! + (7! + 7!) \times 88 \\887766 &:= 6 + 6! + (7! + 7!) \times 88 \\887767 &:= 7 + 6! + (7! + 7!) \times 88 \\887768 &:= 8 + 6! + (7! + 7!) \times 88 \\887769 &:= 9 + 6! + (7! + 7!) \times 88\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}907020 &:= 0 + 20 \times (7! - 0!) \times 9 \\907021 &:= 1 + 20 \times (7! - 0!) \times 9 \\907022 &:= 2 + 20 \times (7! - 0!) \times 9 \\907023 &:= 3 + 20 \times (7! - 0!) \times 9 \\907024 &:= 4 + 20 \times (7! - 0!) \times 9 \\907025 &:= 5 + 20 \times (7! - 0!) \times 9 \\907026 &:= 6 + 20 \times (7! - 0!) \times 9 \\907027 &:= 7 + 20 \times (7! - 0!) \times 9 \\907028 &:= 8 + 20 \times (7! - 0!) \times 9 \\907029 &:= 9 + 20 \times (7! - 0!) \times 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}933120 &:= 0 + (2 + 1)! \times (3!! \times 3!! - 9!) \\933121 &:= 1 + (2 + 1)! \times (3!! \times 3!! - 9!) \\933122 &:= 2 + (2 + 1)! \times (3!! \times 3!! - 9!) \\933123 &:= 3 + (2 + 1)! \times (3!! \times 3!! - 9!) \\933124 &:= 4 + (2 + 1)! \times (3!! \times 3!! - 9!) \\933125 &:= 5 + (2 + 1)! \times (3!! \times 3!! - 9!) \\933126 &:= 6 + (2 + 1)! \times (3!! \times 3!! - 9!) \\933127 &:= 7 + (2 + 1)! \times (3!! \times 3!! - 9!) \\933128 &:= 8 + (2 + 1)! \times (3!! \times 3!! - 9!) \\933129 &:= 9 + (2 + 1)! \times (3!! \times 3!! - 9!)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}956880 &:= 0 + 886 \times 5! \times 9 \\956881 &:= 1 + 886 \times 5! \times 9 \\956882 &:= 2 + 886 \times 5! \times 9 \\956883 &:= 3 + 886 \times 5! \times 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}956884 &:= 4 + 886 \times 5! \times 9 \\956885 &:= 5 + 886 \times 5! \times 9 \\956886 &:= 6 + 886 \times 5! \times 9 \\956887 &:= 7 + 886 \times 5! \times 9 \\956888 &:= 8 + 886 \times 5! \times 9 \\956889 &:= 9 + 886 \times 5! \times 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}963840 &:= 0 + 4! \times (8! - (3!! + 6!)/9) \\963841 &:= 1 + 4! \times (8! - (3!! + 6!)/9) \\963842 &:= 2 + 4! \times (8! - (3!! + 6!)/9) \\963843 &:= 3 + 4! \times (8! - (3!! + 6!)/9) \\963844 &:= 4 + 4! \times (8! - (3!! + 6!)/9) \\963845 &:= 5 + 4! \times (8! - (3!! + 6!)/9) \\963846 &:= 6 + 4! \times (8! - (3!! + 6!)/9) \\963847 &:= 7 + 4! \times (8! - (3!! + 6!)/9) \\963848 &:= 8 + 4! \times (8! - (3!! + 6!)/9) \\963849 &:= 9 + 4! \times (8! - (3!! + 6!)/9)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}967680 &:= 0 + 8! \times 6 \times (7 + 6 - 9) \\967681 &:= 1 + 8! \times 6 \times (7 + 6 - 9) \\967682 &:= 2 + 8! \times 6 \times (7 + 6 - 9) \\967683 &:= 3 + 8! \times 6 \times (7 + 6 - 9) \\967684 &:= 4 + 8! \times 6 \times (7 + 6 - 9) \\967685 &:= 5 + 8! \times 6 \times (7 + 6 - 9) \\967686 &:= 6 + 8! \times 6 \times (7 + 6 - 9) \\967687 &:= 7 + 8! \times 6 \times (7 + 6 - 9) \\967688 &:= 8 + 8! \times 6 \times (7 + 6 - 9) \\967689 &:= 9 + 8! \times 6 \times (7 + 6 - 9)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}968040 &:= 0 + 4! \times (08! + 6 + 9) \\968041 &:= 1 + 4! \times (08! + 6 + 9) \\968042 &:= 2 + 4! \times (08! + 6 + 9) \\968043 &:= 3 + 4! \times (08! + 6 + 9) \\968044 &:= 4 + 4! \times (08! + 6 + 9) \\968045 &:= 5 + 4! \times (08! + 6 + 9) \\968046 &:= 6 + 4! \times (08! + 6 + 9) \\968047 &:= 7 + 4! \times (08! + 6 + 9) \\968048 &:= 8 + 4! \times (08! + 6 + 9) \\968049 &:= 9 + 4! \times (08! + 6 + 9)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}968400 &:= 0 + 04! \times 8! + (-6 + 9)!! \\968401 &:= 1 + 04! \times 8! + (-6 + 9)!!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 968402 &:= 2 + 04! \times 8! + (-6 + 9)!! \\ 968403 &:= 3 + 04! \times 8! + (-6 + 9)!! \\ 968404 &:= 4 + 04! \times 8! + (-6 + 9)!! \\ 968405 &:= 5 + 04! \times 8! + (-6 + 9)!! \\ 968406 &:= 6 + 04! \times 8! + (-6 + 9)!! \\ 968407 &:= 7 + 04! \times 8! + (-6 + 9)!! \\ 968408 &:= 8 + 04! \times 8! + (-6 + 9)!! \\ 968409 &:= 9 + 04! \times 8! + (-6 + 9)!! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 968410 &:= 0 + 1 + 4! \times 8! + 6! + 9 \\ 968411 &:= 1 + 1 + 4! \times 8! + 6! + 9 \\ 968412 &:= 2 + 1 + 4! \times 8! + 6! + 9 \\ 968413 &:= 3 + 1 + 4! \times 8! + 6! + 9 \\ 968414 &:= 4 + 1 + 4! \times 8! + 6! + 9 \\ 968415 &:= 5 + 1 + 4! \times 8! + 6! + 9 \\ 968416 &:= 6 + 1 + 4! \times 8! + 6! + 9 \\ 968417 &:= 7 + 1 + 4! \times 8! + 6! + 9 \\ 968418 &:= 8 + 1 + 4! \times 8! + 6! + 9 \\ 968419 &:= 9 + 1 + 4! \times 8! + 6! + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 973560 &:= 0 + (6! + 5!) \times (3!! + 7) + 9! \\ 973561 &:= 1 + (6! + 5!) \times (3!! + 7) + 9! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 973562 &:= 2 + (6! + 5!) \times (3!! + 7) + 9! \\ 973563 &:= 3 + (6! + 5!) \times (3!! + 7) + 9! \\ 973564 &:= 4 + (6! + 5!) \times (3!! + 7) + 9! \\ 973565 &:= 5 + (6! + 5!) \times (3!! + 7) + 9! \\ 973566 &:= 6 + (6! + 5!) \times (3!! + 7) + 9! \\ 973567 &:= 7 + (6! + 5!) \times (3!! + 7) + 9! \\ 973568 &:= 8 + (6! + 5!) \times (3!! + 7) + 9! \\ 973569 &:= 9 + (6! + 5!) \times (3!! + 7) + 9! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 997920 &:= 0 + (2 + 9) \times 7! \times (9 + 9) \\ 997921 &:= 1 + (2 + 9) \times 7! \times (9 + 9) \\ 997922 &:= 2 + (2 + 9) \times 7! \times (9 + 9) \\ 997923 &:= 3 + (2 + 9) \times 7! \times (9 + 9) \\ 997924 &:= 4 + (2 + 9) \times 7! \times (9 + 9) \\ 997925 &:= 5 + (2 + 9) \times 7! \times (9 + 9) \\ 997926 &:= 6 + (2 + 9) \times 7! \times (9 + 9) \\ 997927 &:= 7 + (2 + 9) \times 7! \times (9 + 9) \\ 997928 &:= 8 + (2 + 9) \times 7! \times (9 + 9) \\ 997929 &:= 9 + (2 + 9) \times 7! \times (9 + 9) \end{aligned}$$

2.2.2 Nonconsecutive

$$\begin{aligned} 00136 &:= 6 \times 3! + 100 \\ 00236 &:= 6 \times 3! + 200 \\ 00336 &:= 6 \times 3! + 300 \\ 00436 &:= 6 \times 3! + 400 \\ 00536 &:= 6 \times 3! + 500 \\ 00636 &:= 6 \times 3! + 600 \\ 00736 &:= 6 \times 3! + 700 \\ 00836 &:= 6 \times 3! + 800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 03509 &:= -90 + 5 \times 3!! - 0! \\ 03518 &:= -81 + 5 \times 3!! - 0! \\ 03527 &:= -72 + 5 \times 3!! - 0! \\ 03536 &:= -63 + 5 \times 3!! - 0! \\ 03545 &:= -54 + 5 \times 3!! - 0! \\ 03554 &:= -45 + 5 \times 3!! - 0! \\ 03563 &:= -36 + 5 \times 3!! - 0! \\ 03572 &:= -27 + 5 \times 3!! - 0! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 03581 &:= -18 + 5 \times 3!! - 0! \\ 03590 &:= -09 + 5 \times 3!! - 0! \\ 03600 &:= 00 + 6! \times (3! - 0!) \\ 03611 &:= 11 + 6! \times (3! - 0!) \\ 03622 &:= 22 + 6! \times (3! - 0!) \\ 03633 &:= 33 + 6! \times (3! - 0!) \\ 03644 &:= 44 + 6! \times (3! - 0!) \\ 03655 &:= 55 + 6! \times (3! - 0!) \\ 03666 &:= 66 + 6! \times (3! - 0!) \\ 03677 &:= 77 + 6! \times (3! - 0!) \\ 03688 &:= 88 + 6! \times (3! - 0!) \\ 03699 &:= 99 + 6! \times (3! - 0!) \\ 158400 &:= 00 + 4 \times (8! - (5 + 1)!) \\ 158411 &:= 11 + 4 \times (8! - (5 + 1)!) \\ 158422 &:= 22 + 4 \times (8! - (5 + 1)!) \\ 158433 &:= 33 + 4 \times (8! - (5 + 1)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}158444 &:= 44 + 4 \times (8! - (5 + 1)!) \\158455 &:= 55 + 4 \times (8! - (5 + 1)!) \\158466 &:= 66 + 4 \times (8! - (5 + 1)!) \\158477 &:= 77 + 4 \times (8! - (5 + 1)!) \\158488 &:= 88 + 4 \times (8! - (5 + 1)!) \\158499 &:= 99 + 4 \times (8! - (5 + 1)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}230400 &:= 00 + (4 \times (-0! + 3!))!^2 \\230411 &:= 11 + (4 \times (-0! + 3!))!^2 \\230422 &:= 22 + (4 \times (-0! + 3!))!^2 \\230433 &:= 33 + (4 \times (-0! + 3!))!^2 \\230444 &:= 44 + (4 \times (-0! + 3!))!^2 \\230455 &:= 55 + (4 \times (-0! + 3!))!^2 \\230466 &:= 66 + (4 \times (-0! + 3!))!^2 \\230477 &:= 77 + (4 \times (-0! + 3!))!^2 \\230488 &:= 88 + (4 \times (-0! + 3!))!^2 \\230499 &:= 99 + (4 \times (-0! + 3!))!^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}259200 &:= 00 + 2 \times 9 \times 5!^2 \\259211 &:= 11 + 2 \times 9 \times 5!^2 \\259222 &:= 22 + 2 \times 9 \times 5!^2 \\259233 &:= 33 + 2 \times 9 \times 5!^2 \\259244 &:= 44 + 2 \times 9 \times 5!^2 \\259255 &:= 55 + 2 \times 9 \times 5!^2 \\259266 &:= 66 + 2 \times 9 \times 5!^2 \\259277 &:= 77 + 2 \times 9 \times 5!^2 \\259288 &:= 88 + 2 \times 9 \times 5!^2 \\259299 &:= 99 + 2 \times 9 \times 5!^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}302400 &:= 00 + 420 \times 3!! \\302411 &:= 11 + 420 \times 3!! \\302422 &:= 22 + 420 \times 3!! \\302433 &:= 33 + 420 \times 3!! \\302444 &:= 44 + 420 \times 3!! \\302455 &:= 55 + 420 \times 3!! \\302466 &:= 66 + 420 \times 3!! \\302477 &:= 77 + 420 \times 3!! \\302488 &:= 88 + 420 \times 3!! \\302499 &:= 99 + 420 \times 3!! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}345600 &:= 00 + 6! * 5! * 4!/3! \\345611 &:= 11 + 6! * 5! * 4!/3! \\345622 &:= 22 + 6! * 5! * 4!/3! \\345633 &:= 33 + 6! * 5! * 4!/3! \\345644 &:= 44 + 6! * 5! * 4!/3! \\345655 &:= 55 + 6! * 5! * 4!/3! \\345666 &:= 66 + 6! * 5! * 4!/3! \\345677 &:= 77 + 6! * 5! * 4!/3! \\345688 &:= 88 + 6! * 5! * 4!/3! \\345699 &:= 99 + 6! * 5! * 4!/3! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}349005 &:= -50 - 0! + 9! - 4!^3 \\349014 &:= -41 - 0! + 9! - 4!^3 \\349023 &:= -32 - 0! + 9! - 4!^3 \\349032 &:= -23 - 0! + 9! - 4!^3 \\349041 &:= -14 - 0! + 9! - 4!^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}349105 &:= 50 - 1 + 9! - 4!^3 \\349116 &:= 61 - 1 + 9! - 4!^3 \\349127 &:= 72 - 1 + 9! - 4!^3 \\349138 &:= 83 - 1 + 9! - 4!^3 \\349149 &:= 94 - 1 + 9! - 4!^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}357905 &:= 50 + 9! - 7! + 5 \times 3 \\357916 &:= 61 + 9! - 7! + 5 \times 3 \\357927 &:= 72 + 9! - 7! + 5 \times 3 \\357938 &:= 83 + 9! - 7! + 5 \times 3 \\357949 &:= 94 + 9! - 7! + 5 \times 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}362950 &:= 05 + 9! + 2 + 63 \\362961 &:= 16 + 9! + 2 + 63 \\362972 &:= 27 + 9! + 2 + 63 \\362983 &:= 38 + 9! + 2 + 63 \\362994 &:= 49 + 9! + 2 + 63 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}362900 &:= 00 + 9! + 2 + 6 \times 3 \\362911 &:= 11 + 9! + 2 + 6 \times 3 \\362922 &:= 22 + 9! + 2 + 6 \times 3 \\362933 &:= 33 + 9! + 2 + 6 \times 3 \\362944 &:= 44 + 9! + 2 + 6 \times 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 362955 &:= 55 + 9! + 2 + 6 \times 3 \\ 362966 &:= 66 + 9! + 2 + 6 \times 3 \\ 362977 &:= 77 + 9! + 2 + 6 \times 3 \\ 362988 &:= 88 + 9! + 2 + 6 \times 3 \\ 362999 &:= 99 + 9! + 2 + 6 \times 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 362910 &:= 01 + 9! + 26 + 3 \\ 362921 &:= 12 + 9! + 26 + 3 \\ 362932 &:= 23 + 9! + 26 + 3 \\ 362943 &:= 34 + 9! + 26 + 3 \\ 362954 &:= 45 + 9! + 26 + 3 \\ 362965 &:= 56 + 9! + 26 + 3 \\ 362976 &:= 67 + 9! + 26 + 3 \\ 362987 &:= 78 + 9! + 26 + 3 \\ 362998 &:= 89 + 9! + 26 + 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 362901 &:= 10 + 9! + 2 + 6 + 3 \\ 362912 &:= 21 + 9! + 2 + 6 + 3 \\ 362923 &:= 32 + 9! + 2 + 6 + 3 \\ 362934 &:= 43 + 9! + 2 + 6 + 3 \\ 362945 &:= 54 + 9! + 2 + 6 + 3 \\ 362956 &:= 65 + 9! + 2 + 6 + 3 \\ 362967 &:= 76 + 9! + 2 + 6 + 3 \\ 362978 &:= 87 + 9! + 2 + 6 + 3 \\ 362989 &:= 98 + 9! + 2 + 6 + 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 362903 &:= 30 + 9! + 2 - 6 - 3 \\ 362914 &:= 41 + 9! + 2 - 6 - 3 \\ 362925 &:= 52 + 9! + 2 - 6 - 3 \\ 362936 &:= 63 + 9! + 2 - 6 - 3 \\ 362947 &:= 74 + 9! + 2 - 6 - 3 \\ 362958 &:= 85 + 9! + 2 - 6 - 3 \\ 362969 &:= 96 + 9! + 2 - 6 - 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 362904 &:= 40 + 9! + 2 - 6 \times 3 \\ 362915 &:= 51 + 9! + 2 - 6 \times 3 \\ 362926 &:= 62 + 9! + 2 - 6 \times 3 \\ 362937 &:= 73 + 9! + 2 - 6 \times 3 \\ 362948 &:= 84 + 9! + 2 - 6 \times 3 \\ 362959 &:= 95 + 9! + 2 - 6 \times 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 363000 &:= 00 + (-0! + 3!)! + (6 + 3)! \\ 363011 &:= 11 + (-0! + 3!)! + (6 + 3)! \\ 363022 &:= 22 + (-0! + 3!)! + (6 + 3)! \\ 363033 &:= 33 + (-0! + 3!)! + (6 + 3)! \\ 363044 &:= 44 + (-0! + 3!)! + (6 + 3)! \\ 363055 &:= 55 + (-0! + 3!)! + (6 + 3)! \\ 363066 &:= 66 + (-0! + 3!)! + (6 + 3)! \\ 363077 &:= 77 + (-0! + 3!)! + (6 + 3)! \\ 363088 &:= 88 + (-0! + 3!)! + (6 + 3)! \\ 363099 &:= 99 + (-0! + 3!)! + (6 + 3)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 363600 &:= 00 + 6! + (3^{6/3})! \\ 363611 &:= 11 + 6! + (3^{6/3})! \\ 363622 &:= 22 + 6! + (3^{6/3})! \\ 363633 &:= 33 + 6! + (3^{6/3})! \\ 363644 &:= 44 + 6! + (3^{6/3})! \\ 363655 &:= 55 + 6! + (3^{6/3})! \\ 363666 &:= 66 + 6! + (3^{6/3})! \\ 363677 &:= 77 + 6! + (3^{6/3})! \\ 363688 &:= 88 + 6! + (3^{6/3})! \\ 363699 &:= 99 + 6! + (3^{6/3})! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 367200 &:= 00 + (2 + 7)! + 6! \times 3! \\ 367211 &:= 11 + (2 + 7)! + 6! \times 3! \\ 367222 &:= 22 + (2 + 7)! + 6! \times 3! \\ 367233 &:= 33 + (2 + 7)! + 6! \times 3! \\ 367244 &:= 44 + (2 + 7)! + 6! \times 3! \\ 367255 &:= 55 + (2 + 7)! + 6! \times 3! \\ 367266 &:= 66 + (2 + 7)! + 6! \times 3! \\ 367277 &:= 77 + (2 + 7)! + 6! \times 3! \\ 367288 &:= 88 + (2 + 7)! + 6! \times 3! \\ 367299 &:= 99 + (2 + 7)! + 6! \times 3! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 378000 &:= 00 + (0! + 8)! + 7! \times 3 \\ 378011 &:= 11 + (0! + 8)! + 7! \times 3 \\ 378022 &:= 22 + (0! + 8)! + 7! \times 3 \\ 378033 &:= 33 + (0! + 8)! + 7! \times 3 \\ 378044 &:= 44 + (0! + 8)! + 7! \times 3 \\ 378055 &:= 55 + (0! + 8)! + 7! \times 3 \\ 378066 &:= 66 + (0! + 8)! + 7! \times 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}378077 &:= 77 + (0! + 8)! + 7! \times 3 \\378088 &:= 88 + (0! + 8)! + 7! \times 3 \\378099 &:= 99 + (0! + 8)! + 7! \times 3\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}453600 &:= 00 + (6 + 3)! \times 5/4 \\453611 &:= 11 + (6 + 3)! \times 5/4 \\453622 &:= 22 + (6 + 3)! \times 5/4 \\453633 &:= 33 + (6 + 3)! \times 5/4 \\453644 &:= 44 + (6 + 3)! \times 5/4 \\453655 &:= 55 + (6 + 3)! \times 5/4 \\453666 &:= 66 + (6 + 3)! \times 5/4 \\453677 &:= 77 + (6 + 3)! \times 5/4 \\453688 &:= 88 + (6 + 3)! \times 5/4 \\453699 &:= 99 + (6 + 3)! \times 5/4\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}507600 &:= 00 + 6! \times 705 \\507611 &:= 11 + 6! \times 705 \\507622 &:= 22 + 6! \times 705 \\507633 &:= 33 + 6! \times 705 \\507644 &:= 44 + 6! \times 705 \\507655 &:= 55 + 6! \times 705 \\507666 &:= 66 + 6! \times 705 \\507677 &:= 77 + 6! \times 705 \\507688 &:= 88 + 6! \times 705 \\507699 &:= 99 + 6! \times 705\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}507939 &:= -93 + 9! \times 7/05 \\507948 &:= -84 + 9! \times 7/05 \\507955 &:= -55 + 9! \times 7/05 \\507957 &:= -75 + 9! \times 7/05 \\507966 &:= -66 + 9! \times 7/05 \\507975 &:= -57 + 9! \times 7/05 \\507984 &:= -48 + 9! \times 7/05 \\507993 &:= -39 + 9! \times 7/05\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}518400 &:= 00 + (4!/8)!! \times (1 + 5)! \\518411 &:= 11 + (4!/8)!! \times (1 + 5)! \\518422 &:= 22 + (4!/8)!! \times (1 + 5)! \\518433 &:= 33 + (4!/8)!! \times (1 + 5)! \\518444 &:= 44 + (4!/8)!! \times (1 + 5)! \\518455 &:= 55 + (4!/8)!! \times (1 + 5)!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}518466 &:= 66 + (4!/8)!! \times (1 + 5)! \\518477 &:= 77 + (4!/8)!! \times (1 + 5)! \\518488 &:= 88 + (4!/8)!! \times (1 + 5)! \\518499 &:= 99 + (4!/8)!! \times (1 + 5)!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}604800 &:= 00 + 840 \times 6! \\604811 &:= 11 + 840 \times 6! \\604822 &:= 22 + 840 \times 6! \\604833 &:= 33 + 840 \times 6! \\604844 &:= 44 + 840 \times 6! \\604855 &:= 55 + 840 \times 6! \\604866 &:= 66 + 840 \times 6! \\604877 &:= 77 + 840 \times 6! \\604888 &:= 88 + 840 \times 6! \\604899 &:= 99 + 840 \times 6!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}806400 &:= 00 + 4 \times (6 - 0!) \times 8! \\806411 &:= 11 + 4 \times (6 - 0!) \times 8! \\806422 &:= 22 + 4 \times (6 - 0!) \times 8! \\806433 &:= 33 + 4 \times (6 - 0!) \times 8! \\806444 &:= 44 + 4 \times (6 - 0!) \times 8! \\806455 &:= 55 + 4 \times (6 - 0!) \times 8! \\806466 &:= 66 + 4 \times (6 - 0!) \times 8! \\806477 &:= 77 + 4 \times (6 - 0!) \times 8! \\806488 &:= 88 + 4 \times (6 - 0!) \times 8! \\806499 &:= 99 + 4 \times (6 - 0!) \times 8!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}937500 &:= 00 + 5^7 \times (3 + 9) \\937511 &:= 11 + 5^7 \times (3 + 9) \\937522 &:= 22 + 5^7 \times (3 + 9) \\937533 &:= 33 + 5^7 \times (3 + 9) \\937544 &:= 44 + 5^7 \times (3 + 9) \\937555 &:= 55 + 5^7 \times (3 + 9) \\937566 &:= 66 + 5^7 \times (3 + 9) \\937577 &:= 77 + 5^7 \times (3 + 9) \\937588 &:= 88 + 5^7 \times (3 + 9) \\937599 &:= 99 + 5^7 \times (3 + 9)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}968400 &:= 00 + 4! \times 8! + (-6 + 9)!! \\968411 &:= 11 + 4! \times 8! + (-6 + 9)!! \\968422 &:= 22 + 4! \times 8! + (-6 + 9)!!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 968433 &:= 33 + 4! \times 8! + (-6 + 9)!! \\
 968444 &:= 44 + 4! \times 8! + (-6 + 9)!! \\
 968455 &:= 55 + 4! \times 8! + (-6 + 9)!! \\
 968466 &:= 66 + 4! \times 8! + (-6 + 9)!! \\
 968477 &:= 77 + 4! \times 8! + (-6 + 9)!! \\
 968488 &:= 88 + 4! \times 8! + (-6 + 9)!! \\
 968499 &:= 99 + 4! \times 8! + (-6 + 9)!! \\
 \\
 968401 &:= 10 + 4! \times 8! + 6! - 9 \\
 968410 &:= 01 + 4! \times 8! + 6! + 9 \\
 968412 &:= 21 + 4! \times 8! + 6! - 9 \\
 968421 &:= 12 + 4! \times 8! + 6! + 9 \\
 968423 &:= 32 + 4! \times 8! + 6! - 9 \\
 968432 &:= 23 + 4! \times 8! + 6! + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 968434 &:= 43 + 4! \times 8! + 6! - 9 \\
 968443 &:= 34 + 4! \times 8! + 6! + 9 \\
 968445 &:= 54 + 4! \times 8! + 6! - 9 \\
 968454 &:= 45 + 4! \times 8! + 6! + 9 \\
 968456 &:= 65 + 4! \times 8! + 6! - 9 \\
 968465 &:= 56 + 4! \times 8! + 6! + 9 \\
 968467 &:= 76 + 4! \times 8! + 6! - 9 \\
 968476 &:= 67 + 4! \times 8! + 6! + 9 \\
 968478 &:= 87 + 4! \times 8! + 6! - 9 \\
 968487 &:= 78 + 4! \times 8! + 6! + 9 \\
 968489 &:= 98 + 4! \times 8! + 6! - 9 \\
 968498 &:= 89 + 4! \times 8! + 6! + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

2.2.3 Nonsymmetric

This section bring **selfie numbers** in reverse order of digits using **factorial** along with **basic operations**. Result appearing in above subsections are not included here. Due to high quantity of numbers, the results are limited up to 6 digits.

• Up To Five Digits Numbers

$$\begin{aligned}
 36 &:= 6 \times 3! & 0246 &:= 6 \times (42 - 0!) \\
 143 &:= 3! \times 4! - 1 & 0253 &:= (3! + 5!) \times 2 + 0! \\
 144 &:= 4! \times (4 - 1)! & 0255 &:= 5 \times (52 - 0!) \\
 337 &:= 7^3 - 3! & 0259 &:= (9 + 5!) \times 2 + 0! \\
 355 &:= -5 + 5! \times 3 & 0264 &:= 4! \times (6 \times 2 - 0!) \\
 456 &:= (-6 + 5!) \times 4 & 0294 &:= 49 \times (2 + 0!)! \\
 624 &:= 4! \times 26 & 0325 &:= 5 \times (2^{3!} + 0!) \\
 693 &:= -3 \times 9 + 6! & 0328 &:= 82 \times (3 + 0!) \\
 713 &:= 3!! - 1 \times 7 & 0359 &:= 9 \times 5! / 3 - 0! \\
 744 &:= 4! \times (4! + 7) & 0376 &:= 6! - 7^3 - 0! \\
 \\
 0132 &:= (2 \times 3!)! / 10! & 0378 &:= (8! + 7!) / (3! - 0!)! \\
 0134 &:= 4! \times 3! - 10 & 0379 &:= 9 \times 7 \times 3! + 0! \\
 0146 &:= 6 \times 4! + 1 + 0! & 0384 &:= 4! \times 8 \times (3 - 0!) \\
 0235 &:= (5! - 3) \times 2 + 0! & 0385 &:= (5! + 8) \times 3 + 0! \\
 0241 &:= (1 + 4)! \times 2 + 0! & 0392 &:= 2^9 - (3! - 0!)! \\
 0243 &:= 3^{4+(2 \times 0)!} & 0432 &:= 2 \times 3!^{4-0!} \\
 0245 &:= 5 \times (4! \times 2 + 0!) & 0433 &:= 3 \times 3! \times 4! + 0! \\
 & & 0497 &:= (-7! + 9!) / (4 - 0!)!! \\
 & & 0605 &:= (5! + 0!) \times (6 - 0!)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0679 &:= 97 \times (6 + 0!) \\ 0719 &:= (9 + 1)!/7! - 0! \\ 0732 &:= 2 \times 3! + (7 - 0)! \\ 0735 &:= 5 \times 3 + (7 - 0)! \\ 0743 &:= 3!! + 4! - (7 \times 0)! \\ 0752 &:= 2^5 + (7 - 0)! \\ 0756 &:= 6! + 5 \times 7 + 0! \\ 0763 &:= 3!! + 6 \times 7 + 0! \\ 0768 &:= 8 \times 6 + (7 - 0)! \\ 0785 &:= (5! - 8) \times 7 + 0! \\ 0793 &:= 3!! + 9!/7! + 0! \\ 0819 &:= 91 \times (8 + 0!) \\ 0955 &:= -5 + 5! \times (9 - 0!) \\ 1024 &:= 4^{(2+0)!-1} \\ 1345 &:= 5^4 + 3!! \times 1 \\ 1359 &:= 9 \times (5! + 31) \\ 1426 &:= 62 \times (4! - 1) \\ 1432 &:= 2 \times (3!! - 4 \times 1) \\ 1436 &:= 6! + 3!! - 4 \times 1 \\ 1442 &:= 2 \times ((4!/4)! + 1) \\ 1477 &:= 7 \times (7!/4! + 1) \\ 1573 &:= (3! + 7) \times (5! + 1) \\ 1704 &:= 4! \times 071 \\ 2304 &:= (4! \times (-0! + 3))^2 \\ 2403 &:= (3! + 0!)^4 + 2 \\ 2517 &:= (7! - 1 - 5)/2 \\ 2575 &:= -5 + (7! + 5!)/2 \\ 2736 &:= 6^3 + 7!/2 \\ 2864 &:= (-4 + 6!) \times 8/2 \\ 2876 &:= (6! + 7! - 8)/2 \\ 3072 &:= 2^7 \times (0! + 3)! \\ 3237 &:= (7! - 3!)/2 + 3!! \\ 3354 &:= 4 \times (5! + 3!!) - 3! \\ 3369 &:= (9 + 6)^3 - 3! \\ 3372 &:= 2 \times (7!/3 + 3!) \\ 3376 &:= -6! + (7 - 3)^{3!} \\ 3384 &:= 4! + 8!/(3! + 3!) \\ 3448 &:= -8 + 4! \times 4! \times 3! \\ 3453 &:= 3!!/5 \times 4! - 3 \\ 3455 &:= 5 \times (-(5 + 4!) + 3!!) \\ 3456 &:= 6!/5 \times 4 \times 3! \\ 3465 &:= 5 \times (6! - 4! - 3) \\ 3495 &:= 5! + (-9 + 4!)^3 \\ 3584 &:= -4! + 8 + 5 \times 3!! \\ 3585 &:= 5 \times (-8 + 5 + 3!!) \\ 3586 &:= -6 - 8 + 5 \times 3!! \\ 3591 &:= -1 \times 9 + 5 \times 3!! \\ 3599 &:= -9/9 + 5 \times 3!! \\ 3615 &:= 5 \times (1 \times 6! + 3) \\ 3625 &:= 5 \times (2 + 6! + 3) \\ 3636 &:= -6! + (3! + 6!) \times 3! \\ 3654 &:= 4! + 5 \times (6! + 3!) \\ 3655 &:= 5 \times (5 + 6! + 3!) \\ 3744 &:= -4! \times 4! + 7! - 3!! \\ 3755 &:= 5! + 5 \times (7 + 3!!) \\ 3957 &:= 7! - (5! \times 9 + 3) \\ 4093 &:= -3 + (9 - 0!)^4 \\ 4096 &:= (6!/90)^4 \\ 4176 &:= 6 \times ((7 - 1)! - 4!) \\ 4314 &:= 4! \times (-1 + 3!!)/4 \\ 4316 &:= 6! \times 1 \times 3! - 4 \\ 4324 &:= (4 + 2)! \times 3! + 4 \\ 4332 &:= (-2 + 3!!) \times 3! + 4! \\ 4337 &:= -7 + 3!! \times 3! + 4! \\ 4344 &:= 4!/4 \times 3!! + 4! \\ 4464 &:= (4! + 6!)/4 \times 4! \\ 4802 &:= 2 \times (-0! + 8)^4 \\ 4816 &:= 6! + 1 \times 8^4 \\ 5035 &:= -5 + (3! + (0 \times 5)!)! \\ 5037 &:= 7! - 3 - 0 \times 5 \\ 5064 &:= 4! + (6 + (0 \times 5)!)! \\ 5275 &:= -5 + 7! + 2 \times 5! \\ 5395 &:= -5 + 9 \times (3!! - 5!) \\ 5568 &:= 8 \times (6! - 5!/5) \\ 5765 &:= 5! \times 6 + 7! + 5 \\ 5836 &:= -6! + 3^8 - 5 \\ 6048 &:= 8!/40 \times 6 \\ 6399 &:= 9 \times (-9 + (-3 + 6)!!) \\ 6715 &:= -5 + (1 + 7)!/6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6748 &:= (8! + 4! \times 7)/6 \\ 6768 &:= 8 \times (6 + 7!/6) \\ 6835 &:= -5 + (3!! + 8!)/6 \\ 6864 &:= 4! + (6! + 8!)/6 \\ 6992 &:= 2^9 + 9 \times 6! \\ 7056 &:= 6^5 - (-0! + 7)! \\ 7193 &:= 3!! \times (9 + 1) - 7 \\ 7235 &:= 5 \times (3!! \times 2 + 7) \\ 7335 &:= 5 \times (-3!! + 3^7) \\ 7595 &:= (5! \times 9 + 5) \times 7 \\ 7992 &:= ((2 + 9)! + 9!)/7! \\ 8576 &:= 67 \times (5! + 8) \\ 8632 &:= 2 \times 3! \times 6! - 8 \\ 8648 &:= (8 + 4) \times 6! + 8 \\ \\ 00132 &:= 2 \times 3! \times (10 + 0!) \\ 00136 &:= 6 \times 3! + 100 \\ 00142 &:= -2 + 4! \times (1 + 0! + 0!)! \\ 00147 &:= 7 \times (4! - 1 - 0! - 0!) \\ 00149 &:= (-9 + 4!) \times 10 - 0! \\ 00156 &:= 6 \times (5 - 1)! + 0! + 0! \\ 00167 &:= 7 \times (-6 + 10)! - 0! \\ 00168 &:= 8!/6! \times (1 + 0! + 0!) \\ 00174 &:= 4! \times 7 + (1 + 0! + 0!)! \\ 00185 &:= 5! + 8^{1+0!} + 0! \\ 00194 &:= 4! \times (9 - 1) + 0! + 0! \\ 00195 &:= (5 + 9)^{1+0!} - 0! \\ 00196 &:= (6 + 9 - 1)^{0!+0!} \\ 00198 &:= (8 + 91) \times (0! + 0!) \\ 00215 &:= (5 + 1)^{2+0!} - 0! \\ 00217 &:= (7 - 1)^{2+0!} + 0! \\ 00238 &:= (8 - 3)! \times 2 - 0! - 0! \\ 00239 &:= (9 + 3) \times 20 - 0! \\ 00248 &:= -8 + 4^{2+0!+0!} \\ 00256 &:= (6 + 5 \times 2)^{0!+0!} \\ 00257 &:= (7! + 5!)/20 - 0! \\ 00258 &:= (8 + 5!) \times 2 + 0! + 0! \\ 00273 &:= (3! + 7) \times (20 + 0!) \\ 00279 &:= 9 \times (7 + (2 + 0! + 0!)!) \\ \\ 00285 &:= 5!/8 \times (20 - 0!) \\ 00287 &:= 7 \times 82/(0! + 0!) \\ 00295 &:= 59 \times ((2 + 0!)! - 0!) \\ 00314 &:= 4! \times 13 + 0! + 0! \\ 00324 &:= ((4 + 2) \times 3)^{0!+0!} \\ 00329 &:= (9 + 2) \times 30 - 0! \\ 00345 &:= (-5!/4 + 3!!)/(0! + 0!) \\ 00348 &:= (8 + 4) \times (30 - 0!) \\ 00349 &:= -9 + (-4 + 3!!)/(0! + 0!) \\ 00352 &:= (-2 + 5!) \times 3 - 0! - 0! \\ 00354 &:= -4 + (5! \times 3 - 0! - 0!) \\ 00356 &:= -6 + 5! \times 3 + 0! + 0! \\ 00357 &:= 7 \times (53 - 0! - 0!) \\ 00361 &:= (16 + 3)^{0!+0!} \\ 00362 &:= 2 \times (6 \times 30 + 0!) \\ 00374 &:= (4 \times 7 + 3!!)/(0! + 0!) \\ 00375 &:= 5 \times (73 + 0! + 0!) \\ 00382 &:= 2 \times (8 \times (3 + 0!)! - 0!) \\ 00384 &:= 4! \times (8 + 3! + 0! + 0!) \\ 00396 &:= 6! - 9 \times 3!^{0!+0!} \\ 00429 &:= (9 + 2) \times (40 - 0!) \\ 00436 &:= 6 \times 3! + 400 \\ 00437 &:= 73 \times (4 - 0!)! - 0! \\ 00453 &:= -3 - 5! + 4!^{0!+0!} \\ 00479 &:= -97 + 4!^{0!+0!} \\ 00486 &:= -6!/8 + 4!^{0!+0!} \\ 00489 &:= 98 \times (4 + 0!) - 0! \\ 00496 &:= 6! - 9 \times (4! + 0!) + 0! \\ 00497 &:= -79 + 4!^{0!+0!} \\ 00512 &:= 2^{-1+5 \times (0!+0!)} \\ 00529 &:= (9 \times 2 + 5)^{0!+0!} \\ 00534 &:= (4! + 3^5) \times (0! + 0!) \\ 00536 &:= 6 \times 3! + 500 \\ 00546 &:= -6 + 4! \times ((5 - 0!)! - 0!) \\ 00574 &:= 4!^{7-5} - 0! - 0! \\ 00576 &:= (6 - 7 + 5)!^{0!+0!} \\ 00587 &:= 7 \times (85 - 0!) - 0! \\ 00589 &:= 98 \times (5 + 0!) + 0! \\ 00594 &:= (-4 + 9) \times (5! - 0!) - 0! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 00628 &:= 8!/2^6 - 0! - 0! & 01329 &:= (9 + 2)^3 - 1 - 0! \\ 00635 &:= 5 \times (3! + (6 - 0!)! + 0!) & 01334 &:= 43 \times 31 + 0! \\ 00671 &:= (1 + 7)!/60 - 0! & 01344 &:= (4 + 4)!/(3 \times 10) \\ 00684 &:= (4!/8)!! - 6^{0!+0!} & 01368 &:= (8! + 6!)/(3 \times 10) \\ 00695 &:= (-(-5 + 9)! + 6!) \times 0! - 0! & 01372 &:= 2 \times 7^3 \times (1 + 0!) \\ 00718 &:= (8 - 1)!/7 - 0! - 0! & 01374 &:= 4 \times 7^3 + 1 + 0! \\ 00723 &:= -3! + 27^{0!+0!} & 01426 &:= 6! \times 2 - 4 - 10 \\ 00745 &:= (5! + 4) \times (7 - 0!) + 0! & 01429 &:= -9 + 2 \times ((4 - 1)!! - 0!) \\ 00746 &:= 6! + 4! + (7 \times 0)! + 0! & 01431 &:= -1 + (3!! - 4) \times (1 + 0!) \\ 00753 &:= 3!! + 5 \times 7 - 0! - 0! & 01432 &:= ((2 \times 3)! - 4) \times (1 + 0!) \\ 00759 &:= 95 \times (7 + 0!) - 0! & 01435 &:= -5 + 3! \times 4! \times 10 \\ 00763 &:= -3! + 6! + 7^{0!+0!} & 01436 &:= (6! - 3! + 4) \times (1 + 0!) \\ 00769 &:= 96 \times (7 + 0!) + 0! & 01438 &:= 8 \times 3!!/4 - 1 - 0! \\ 00784 &:= ((-4 + 8) \times 7)^{0!+0!} & 01439 &:= (9 + 3) \times (4 + 1)! - 0! \\ 00829 &:= 92 \times (8 + 0!) + 0! & 01462 &:= 2 \times 6! + 4! - 1 - 0! \\ 00836 &:= 6 \times 3! + 800 & 01464 &:= 4! + 6 \times 4! \times 10 \\ 00841 &:= (1 + 4)! \times (8 - 0!) + 0! & 01477 &:= 7 \times (7!/4! \times 1 + 0!) \\ 00845 &:= 5 \times (4! \times (8 - 0!) + 0!) & 01558 &:= (8 + 5) \times 5! - 1 - 0! \\ 00847 &:= 7 \times ((4 + (8 \times 0)!)! + 0!) & 01562 &:= 2 \times 6! + 5! + 1 + 0! \\ 00856 &:= 6! + 5! + 8 \times (0! + 0!) & 01675 &:= -5 + 7!/6 \times (1 + 0!) \\ 00864 &:= 4! \times 6 \times (8 - 0! - 0!) & 01703 &:= (3 + 0)! \times 71 - 0! \\ 00876 &:= 6! + 78 \times (0! + 0!) & 01705 &:= (5 - 0)! \times 71 + 0! \\ 00934 &:= 4! \times 39 - 0! - 0! & 01728 &:= (8/2)! \times (71 + 0!) \\ 00935 &:= (5! - 3) \times (9 - 0!) - 0! & 01762 &:= -2 + (6 \times 7)^{1+0!} \\ 00936 &:= 6 \times 3! + 900 & 01792 &:= 2^9 \times 7/(1 + 0!) \\ 00951 &:= (-1 + 5!) \times (9 - 0!) - 0! & 01874 &:= 4! \times 78 + 1 + 0! \\ 00953 &:= -3! + 5! \times (9 - 0!) - 0! & 01942 &:= -2 + 4! \times 9^{1+0!} \\ 00958 &:= 8 \times 5! - (9 \times 0)! - 0! & 02016 &:= (6 + 1 + 0!)!/20 \\ 00961 &:= (-1 + 6)! \times (9 - 0!) + 0! & 02136 &:= 6! \times 3 - (1 + 2 + 0)! \\ 00968 &:= 8 \times ((6 - (9 \times 0)!)! + 0!) & 02145 &:= (-5 + (4 - 1)!!) \times (2 + 0!) \\ 00976 &:= 6! + (7 + 9)^{0!+0!} & 02153 &:= 3 \times ((5 + 1)! - 2) - 0! \\ 01023 &:= 32^{0!+1} - 0! & 02155 &:= -5 + (5 + 1)! \times (2 + 0!) \\ 01034 &:= 4^{3!-0!} + 10 & 02159 &:= (9 \times 5! - 1) \times 2 + 0! \\ 01053 &:= (-3 + 5!) \times (-0! + 10) & 02161 &:= 1 \times 6! \times (1 + 2) + 0! \\ 01079 &:= 9 \times (7 - 0! - 1)! - 0! & 02166 &:= 6 \times (6!/(1 \times 2) + 0!) \\ 01152 &:= 2 \times (5 - 1)!^{1+0!} & 02175 &:= (5 + (7 - 1)!) \times (2 + 0!) \\ 01294 &:= (4 \times 9)^2 - 1 - 0! & 02183 &:= (3!! + 8) \times (1 + 2) - 0! \\ 01296 &:= 6! \times 9 \times 2/10 & 02233 &:= 3 \times (3!! + (2 + 2)!) + 0! \\ 01306 &:= 6^{0!+3} + 10 & 02334 &:= (4! + 3!^{3!})/20 \\ & & 02337 &:= 73 \times 32 + 0! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}02397 &:= (79 + 3!) \times (2 + 0!) \\02437 &:= 7 \times (3! - 4!)/2 + 0! \\02457 &:= (7! - 5! - 4)/2 - 0! \\02501 &:= (10 \times 5)^2 + 0! \\02507 &:= (7! - (-0! + 5!))/2 - 0! \\02535 &:= (5! + 3!! + 5) \times (2 + 0!) \\02544 &:= (4! + 4!) \times (52 + 0!) \\02573 &:= -3! + (7! + 5!)/2 - 0! \\02576 &:= (-6 + 7! + 5!)/2 - 0! \\02581 &:= ((-1 + 8)! + 5!)/2 + 0! \\02584 &:= 4! + (8 + 5!) \times 20 \\02591 &:= -1 + 9!/(5! + 20) \\02593 &:= 3!^{9-5} \times 2 + 0! \\02664 &:= 4 \times 6! - 6^{2+0!} \\02688 &:= 8 \times 8!/(6 \times 20) \\02737 &:= -7! + 3!^{7-2} + 0! \\02744 &:= (4 + 4) \times 7^{2+0!} \\02756 &:= 6^5 - 7! + 20 \\02844 &:= -4 + 4 \times (-8 + (2 + 0!)!!) \\02848 &:= (8 - 4) \times (-8 + (2 + 0!)!!) \\02856 &:= 6! + 5! + 8!/20 \\02863 &:= (3!! + 6! - 8) \times 2 - 0! \\02875 &:= 5 \times (7 \times 82 + 0!) \\02904 &:= 4! \times ((0! + 9)/2)! + 0! \\02915 &:= ((5 + 1) \times 9)^2 - 0! \\02917 &:= ((7 - 1) \times 9)^2 + 0! \\02934 &:= 4 \times 3!! + 9 \times (2 + 0!)! \\02946 &:= 6 \times (492 - 0!) \\02955 &:= 5 \times (592 - 0!) \\02968 &:= (-8! + 6 \times 9!)/(2 + 0!)!! \\02994 &:= 499 \times (2 + 0!)! \\03023 &:= (3^2)!/(-0! + 3!)! - 0! \\03024 &:= (4 \times 2 + 0!)!/(3! - 0!)! \\03025 &:= 5^2 \times (0! + (3! - 0!)!) \\03044 &:= 4 \times (40 + 3!! + 0!) \\03073 &:= 3! \times (7 + 0!)^3 + 0! \\03095 &:= (5! + 9) \times (0! + 3)! - 0! \\03144 &:= 4! + 4! \times 130 \\03175 &:= (5! + 7) \times ((1 + 3)! + 0!)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}03208 &:= 802 \times (3 + 0!) \\03249 &:= (9 + 4! \times 2)^{3-0!} \\03276 &:= -(6 \times 7)^2 + (3! + 0!)! \\03285 &:= 5 \times (-8^2 + 3!! + 0!) \\03344 &:= 4 \times (-4 + 3!! + (3! - 0!)!) \\03346 &:= -6! + 4^{3!} - 30 \\03348 &:= (8!/4! - 3!) \times (3 - 0!) \\03351 &:= 15^3 - (3 + 0!)! \\03352 &:= (-2 + 5! + 3!!) \times (3 + 0!) \\03355 &:= -5 + 5! \times (3^3 + 0!) \\03359 &:= 9!/(5! - 3! - 3!) - 0! \\03364 &:= 4 \times (6!/3! + 3!! + 0!) \\03367 &:= 7 \times ((6! + 3!!)/3 + 0!) \\03376 &:= (-6 + 7 \times 3)^3 + 0! \\03392 &:= 2^9 + 3!! \times (3 + 0!) \\03397 &:= (7!/9 + 3!) \times 3! + 0! \\03451 &:= (-1 + 5!) \times (4! + 3! - 0!) \\03454 &:= (4! + 5!) \times 4! - 3 + 0! \\03455 &:= 5!/5 \times 4! \times 3! - 0! \\03456 &:= 6!/5 \times (4 + 3 \times 0!) \\03457 &:= (7 + 5)^4/3! + 0! \\03485 &:= 5 \times (-(8 - 4)! + 3!! + 0!) \\03509 &:= -90 + 5 \times 3!! - 0! \\03518 &:= -81 + 5 \times 3!! - 0! \\03527 &:= -72 + 5 \times 3!! - 0! \\03529 &:= 9! \times (2 + 5)/3!! + 0! \\03545 &:= -54 + 5 \times 3!! - 0! \\03554 &:= -45 + 5 \times 3!! - 0! \\03555 &:= 5 \times (-5 - 5 + 3!! + 0!) \\03557 &:= (-7 + 5! \times 5) \times 3! - 0! \\03563 &:= (-3! + 6!) \times 5 - 3! - 0! \\03565 &:= 5 \times 6! - 5 - 30 \\03566 &:= (-6 + 6!) \times 5 - 3 - 0! \\03567 &:= (-7 + 6!) \times 5 + 3 - 0! \\03568 &:= -8 + 6! \times 5 - (3 + 0!)! \\03572 &:= -27 + 5 \times 3!! - 0! \\03574 &:= -4! - 7 + 5 \times (3!! + 0!) \\03579 &:= -9 - 7 + 5 \times (3!! - 0!) \\03581 &:= -18 + 5 \times 3!! - 0!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}03584 &:= 4 \times (8 + 5!) \times (3! + 0!) \\03585 &:= -5!/8 + 5! \times 30 \\03586 &:= -6 - 8 + 5! \times 30 \\03614 &:= (4 + 1) \times (6! + 3) - 0! \\03616 &:= (6 - 1) \times (6! + 3) + 0! \\03622 &:= 22 + 6! \times (3! - 0!) \\03624 &:= 4! - 2 \times 6! + (3! + 0!)! \\03644 &:= 4! + (4 + 6!) \times (3! - 0!) \\03645 &:= 5 \times (4 + 6!) - 3! + 0! \\03648 &:= 8 \times 4! \times (6 \times 3 + 0!) \\03654 &:= 4! + 5 \times 6! - 30 \\03665 &:= 5 \times (6 + 6! + 3!) - 0! \\03666 &:= 66 + 6! \times (3! - 0!) \\03671 &:= 17 \times 6^3 - 0! \\03677 &:= 77 + 6! \times (3! - 0!) \\03688 &:= 88 + 6! \times (3! - 0!) \\03689 &:= (9 + 8) \times (6^3 + 0!) \\03699 &:= 99 + 6! \times (3! - 0!) \\03725 &:= 5! + (-2 + 7) \times (3!! + 0!) \\03743 &:= -3!^4 + 7! + (3 \times 0!)! \\03745 &:= 5 \times (4 \times 7 + 3!! + 0!) \\03746 &:= -6^4 + 7! + 3 - 0! \\03751 &:= (1 + 5!) \times (7 + (3 + 0!)!) \\03756 &:= 6 \times (5^{7-3} + 0!) \\03774 &:= (4 + 7) \times 7^3 + 0! \\03775 &:= -5 + 7! - 7!/(3 + 0!) \\03853 &:= -3^5 + 8^{3+0!} \\03864 &:= 46 \times (83 + 0!) \\03875 &:= 5 \times (7 \times 8 + 3!! - 0!) \\03951 &:= -(1 + 5!) \times 9 + (3! + 0!)! \\03955 &:= -5 - 5! \times 9 + (3! + 0!)! \\03969 &:= (9 \times 6 + 9)^{3-0!} \\03975 &:= -5! + (7 + 9)^3 - 0! \\04095 &:= (-5 + 9)^{(-0!+4)!} - 0! \\04097 &:= (7 + (9 \times 0!)!)^4 + 0! \\04266 &:= 6 \times (6! - 2 \times 4 - 0!) \\04273 &:= -3!! + 7! + (-2 \times 4! + 0!) \\04293 &:= 3 \times (-9 + 2 \times (4 - 0!)!) \\04302 &:= (-2 - 0! + 3!!) \times (4 - 0!)!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}04303 &:= (3!! + 0!) \times 3! - 4! + 0! \\04307 &:= -7 + (-0! + 3!!) \times (4 - 0!)! \\04312 &:= -2 + (-1 + 3!!) \times (4 - 0!)! \\04313 &:= (3!! - 1) \times 3! - (4 \times 0!) \\04314 &:= (4 - 1)! \times 3!! - (4 - 0!)! \\04315 &:= (5 + 1)! \times 3! - 4 - 0! \\04317 &:= (7 - 1)! \times 3! - 4 + 0! \\04318 &:= -8 + (1 + 3!!) \times (4 - 0!)! \\04319 &:= 9 \times (-1 + 3!)! \times 4 - 0! \\04321 &:= (1 + 2)! \times 3!! + (4 \times 0!) \\04322 &:= 2 + 2 \times 3!! \times (4 - 0!) \\04323 &:= 3! \times (2 \times 3)! + 4 - 0! \\04325 &:= (5 - 2)! \times 3!! + 4 + 0! \\04326 &:= 6 \times ((2 \times 3)! + (4 \times 0!)! \\04328 &:= 8 + 2 \times 3!! \times (4 - 0!) \\04329 &:= 9 \times ((2 + 3)! \times 4 + 0!) \\04331 &:= (1 + 3!!) \times 3! + 4 + 0! \\04332 &:= (2 + 3!!) \times (3 + 4 - 0!) \\04333 &:= 3!! \times 3! + 3 \times 4 + 0! \\04335 &:= (5 + 3!! + 3!!) \times (4 - 0!) \\04373 &:= 3^7 \times (3! - 4) - 0! \\04374 &:= (-4 + 7)^{3!} \times (4 - 0!)! \\04386 &:= (6! + 8 + 3) \times (4 - 0!)! \\04398 &:= 8!/9 - 3^4 - 0! \\04408 &:= -8 \times ((0! - 4!) \times 4! + 0!) \\04436 &:= 6! \times 3! - 4 + (4 + 0!)! \\04437 &:= 7! - 3 - 4! \times (4! + 0!) \\04462 &:= -2 + (6! + 4!) \times (4 - 0!)! \\04463 &:= 3! \times (6! + 4!) - (4 \times 0!) \\04479 &:= 9!/(7 - 4)^4 - 0! \\04497 &:= 7! + 9 - 4! \times (4! - 0!) \\04498 &:= 8!/9 + 4! - (4 - 0!)! \\04527 &:= 7! - 2^{5+4} - 0! \\04536 &:= (6 + 3)!/(5! - 40) \\04537 &:= 7! - (3! + 5!) \times 4 + 0! \\04583 &:= 38 \times 5! + 4! - 0! \\04597 &:= 7! + (9 - 5!) \times 4 - 0! \\04656 &:= (6! + 56) \times (4 - 0!)! \\04697 &:= 7 \times (-9 + 6! - 40) \\04737 &:= -7^3 + 7! + 40\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 04763 &:= 3! \times (6! + 74) - 0! \\ 04797 &:= 7! - 9 \times (7 \times 4 - 0!) \\ 04805 &:= 5 \times (0! + 8 \times (4 + 0!)!) \\ 04815 &:= (5 + 1)! + 8^4 - 0! \\ 04817 &:= (7 - 1)! + 8^4 + 0! \\ 04825 &:= 5^2 \times (8 \times 4! + 0!) \\ 04837 &:= 7! - 3 + 8 \times (4! + 0!) \\ 04897 &:= 7! + 9 \times (8 - 4!) + 0! \\ 04937 &:= 7! - 3!!/9 - 4! + 0! \\ 04968 &:= 8 \times (6! - 9) - (4 - 0!)!! \\ 04975 &:= (5! + 79) \times (4! + 0!) \\ 04977 &:= 7! - 7 \times 9 - 4 \times 0 \\ 04978 &:= -8 + 7! - 9 \times (4 - 0!)! \\ 04987 &:= 7! - 8 - 9 \times (4 + 0!) \\ 04995 &:= (5! - 9) \times 9 \times (4 + 0!) \\ 05007 &:= 7! - (0! + 0!)^5 - 0! \\ 05024 &:= -4^2 + (0! + 5 + 0!)! \\ 05026 &:= (6! - 2) \times (0! + 5 + 0!) \\ 05027 &:= 7! - 2 \times (0! + 5) - 0! \\ 05032 &:= -2^3 + (0! + 5 + 0!)! \\ 05033 &:= -3! + (3! + 0!)! - (5 \times 0)! \\ 05035 &:= -5 + (3! + (0 \times 50)!)! \\ 05036 &:= 6! \times (3! + 0!) - 5 + 0! \\ 05037 &:= 7! - 3 - 0 \times 50 \\ 05064 &:= 4! + 6! \times (0! + 5 + 0!) \\ 05067 &:= 7 \times (6! - 0! + 5) - 0! \\ 05075 &:= 5 \times 7 + (0! + 5 + 0!)! \\ 05076 &:= 6 \times (7 \times (0! + 5!) - 0!) \\ 05087 &:= 7! + 8 \times (0! + 5) - 0! \\ 05117 &:= 7 \times (11 + (5 + 0!)!) \\ 05124 &:= 42 \times (1 + 5! + 0!) \\ 05234 &:= (4! \times 3)^2 + 50 \\ 05273 &:= -3! + 7! + 2 \times 5! - 0! \\ 05274 &:= -4 + 7! + 2 \times (5! - 0!) \\ 05276 &:= -6 + 7! + 2 \times (5! + 0!) \\ 05281 &:= (-1 + 8)! + 2 \times 5! + 0! \\ 05287 &:= 7! + 8 + 2 \times 5! - 0! \\ 05324 &:= (4! - 2) \times (3^5 - 0!) \\ 05327 &:= 7! + 2 \times 3!!/5 - 0! \\ 05337 &:= 7! - 3 + 3! \times 50 \\ 05377 &:= 7! + 7^3 - 5 - 0! \\ 05384 &:= 4! + 8 \times (3!! - 50) \\ 05385 &:= 5!/8 \times (3 \times 5! - 0!) \\ 05391 &:= 1 \times 9 \times (3!! - 5! - 0!) \\ 05393 &:= -3! + 9 \times (3!! - 5!) - 0! \\ 05395 &:= -5 + 9 \times (3!! - 5!) \times 0! \\ 05397 &:= 7! + 9/3 \times (5! - 0!) \\ 05399 &:= 9 \times ((9 - 3)! - 5!) - 0! \\ 05409 &:= 9 \times ((0! + 4) \times 5! + 0!) \\ 05535 &:= (5! + 3) \times (-5 + 50) \\ 05544 &:= 44 \times (5! + 5 + 0!) \\ 05568 &:= 8 \times (6! - 5 \times 5 + 0!) \\ 05639 &:= 9 \times 3!! - 6! - 5! - 0! \\ 05641 &:= (1 + 46) \times 5! + 0! \\ 05664 &:= (-4! + 6! + 6!) \times (5 - 0!) \\ 05688 &:= 8 \times (-8 + 6! - (5 \times 0)!) \\ 05694 &:= 4! + 9!/(65 - 0!) \\ 05697 &:= 7 \times (-9 + 6!) + (5 + 0!)! \\ 05732 &:= (2 \times 3!! - 7) \times (5 - 0!) \\ 05733 &:= -3^3 + 7! + (5 + 0!)! \\ 05736 &:= (6! - 3) \times (7 + (5 \times 0)!) \\ 05744 &:= -4 \times 4 + 7! + (5 + 0!)! \\ 05782 &:= -2 + 8!/7 + (5 - 0!)! \\ 05784 &:= 4! + 8!/7 + 5 \times 0 \\ 05824 &:= 4 \times 2 \times (8 + (5 + 0!)!) \\ 05825 &:= 52 \times (-8 + 5!) + 0! \\ 05826 &:= (6! + 2) \times 8 + 50 \\ 05831 &:= (1 + 3! \times 8) \times (5! - 0!) \\ 05833 &:= 3!^3/8 + (5 \times 0)! \\ 05834 &:= 4! + 3!! \times 8 - 50 \\ 05836 &:= 6^3/8 + 5 - 0! \\ 05841 &:= (-1 + 4)^8 - (5 + 0!)! \\ 05849 &:= 9^4 + 8 - (5 + 0!)! \\ 05875 &:= -5 + (-7! + 8!)/(5 + 0!) \\ 05888 &:= 8 \times (8 + 8 + (5 + 0!)!) \\ 05976 &:= 6! + 7! + 9 \times (5 - 0!)! \\ 05993 &:= 3! \times 9 \times (-9 + 5!) - 0! \\ 06047 &:= 7!/(4 + 0!) \times 6 - 0! \\ 06143 &:= 3! \times 4^{-1+6} - 0! \\ 06255 &:= 5^5 \times 2 + 6 - 0! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 06335 &:= -(5+3)! + 3!^6 - 0! \\ 06337 &:= 7! + 3!^3 \times 6 + 0! \\ 06338 &:= -8! + 3 + 3!^6 - 0! \\ 06355 &:= 5! \times 53 - 6 + 0! \\ 06384 &:= (4! \times 8 + 3!!) \times (6 + 0!) \\ 06399 &:= 9 \times (-9 + (3 + 6 \times 0)!!) \\ 06432 &:= 2 \times (3!! - 4!) + (6 + 0!)! \\ 06435 &:= (-5 + 3!!) \times (4 + 6 - 0!) \\ 06439 &:= 9 \times (3!! - 4) - 6 + 0! \\ 06445 &:= (5 + 4) \times (-4 + 6!) + 0! \\ 06475 &:= -5 + 7! + 4! \times 60 \\ 06479 &:= 9 \times (7 - 4)!! - (6 \times 0)! \\ 06483 &:= 3!! \times 8 + 4 + 6! - 0! \\ 06489 &:= 9 \times ((8 + 4 - 6)! + 0!) \\ 06549 &:= 9^4 - 5 - 6 - 0! \\ 06553 &:= (-3 + 5!) \times 56 + 0! \\ 06555 &:= (-5 + 5!) \times (56 + 0!) \\ 06579 &:= 9 \times (7 + 5 + 6! - 0!) \\ 06593 &:= 3!! \times 9 + 5! - 6 - 0! \\ 06609 &:= 9 \times (0! + 6!) + (6 - 0!)! \\ 06655 &:= 55 \times (6!/6 + 0!) \\ 06659 &:= 9 \times (5!/6 + 6!) - 0! \\ 06684 &:= 4! + 8!/6 - 60 \\ 06713 &:= -3! + (1 + 7)!/6 - 0! \\ 06718 &:= (8! + 1 - 7)/6 - 0! \\ 06719 &:= (9 - 1) \times 7!/6 - 0! \\ 06721 &:= (1^2 + 7)!/6 + 0! \\ 06724 &:= 4 \times (2 \times 7!/6 + 0!) \\ 06727 &:= -7! \times 2 + 7^{6-0!} \\ 06728 &:= 8 \times (2 + 7!/6 - 0!) \\ 06744 &:= 4! \times (47 \times 6 - 0!) \\ 06809 &:= 90 + 8!/6 - 0! \\ 06833 &:= -3! + (3!! + 8!)/6 - 0! \\ 06835 &:= 5! - 3! + 8!/6 + 0! \\ 06839 &:= ((9 - 3)! + 8!)/6 - 0! \\ 06841 &:= (1 + 4)! + 8!/6 + 0! \\ 06843 &:= (3!! + 4! + 8!)/6 - 0! \\ 06845 &:= 5! + (4! + 8!)/6 + 0! \\ 06939 &:= 9 \times (3!! - 9 + 60) \\ 07056 &:= 6^5 - (07 - 0!)! \\ 07057 &:= 7!/5 \times 07 + 0! \\ 07195 &:= -5 + (9 + 1) \times (7 - 0!)! \\ 07205 &:= 5 \times (0! + 2 \times (7 - 0!)!) \\ 07283 &:= 3^8 + 2 + (7 - 0!)! \\ 07356 &:= 6^5 - 3! \times 70 \\ 07392 &:= (2^9 + 3!!) \times (7 - 0!) \\ 07559 &:= 9!/(55 - 7) - 0! \\ 07569 &:= 9 \times (6! + 5! + (7 \times 0)!) \\ 07656 &:= 6^5 - 6!/(7 - 0!) \\ 07688 &:= 8 \times (8!/(6 \times 7) + 0!) \\ 07824 &:= 4! \times (2^8 + 70) \\ 07921 &:= (1 \times 2 + 9)!/7! + 0! \\ 07926 &:= 6! \times (2 + 9) + 7 - 0! \\ 08057 &:= (7!/5 - 0!) \times 8 + 0! \\ 08058 &:= 8!/5 + 0! - 8 + 0! \\ 08109 &:= 901 \times (8 + 0!) \\ 08165 &:= 5^{6-1} + (8 - 0!)! \\ 08593 &:= (-3! + 9 \times 5!) \times 8 + 0! \\ 08633 &:= (3! + 3!) \times 6! - 8 + 0! \\ 08639 &:= (9 + 3) \times 6! - (8 \times 0)! \\ 08643 &:= 3 \times (4 \times 6! + (8 \times 0)!) \\ 08644 &:= 4 \times (4! \times 6!/8 + 0!) \\ 08664 &:= 4! \times 6!/(-6 + 8) + 0! \\ 08675 &:= 5 \times (7 + 6!) + (8 - 0!)! \\ 08755 &:= -5 + 5! \times (-7 + 80) \\ 08911 &:= 11! \times 9/8! + 0! \\ 08919 &:= 91 \times 98 + 0! \\ 09234 &:= (4! - 3!) \times (2^9 + 0!) \\ 09247 &:= 7 \times ((4!/2)!/9! + 0!) \\ 09279 &:= 9 \times (7 + 2^{9+0!}) \\ 09373 &:= (3! + 7) \times (3!! + (9 \times 0)!) \\ 09547 &:= 74 \times (5! + 9) + 0! \\ 09729 &:= 9 \times ((-2 + 7)! \times 9 + 0!) \\ 09972 &:= 2 \times (7! - 9) - 90 \\ 10067 &:= (7! - 6) \times (0! + 0!) - 1 \\ 10073 &:= (-3 + 7!) \times (0! + 0!) - 1 \\ 10074 &:= (-4 + 7! + 0!) \times (0! + 1) \\ 10075 &:= -5 + 7! \times (0 + 0! + 1) \\ 10076 &:= -6 + (7! + 0!) \times (0! + 1) \\ 10097 &:= (7! + 9) \times (0! + 0!) - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 10344 &:= 4! \times (430 + 1) \\ 10369 &:= 9! / (6 \times 3! - 0!) + 1 \\ 10785 &:= 5! / 8 \times ((7 - 0!)! - 1) \\ 10935 &:= 5 \times 3^{9-0!-1} \\ 11339 &:= 9! / (33 - 1) - 1 \\ 11344 &:= 4 \times 4 \times (3!! - 11) \\ 11528 &:= 8 \times (2 \times (5 + 1)! + 1) \\ 11544 &:= 4! \times (4 \times 5! + 1) \times 1 \\ 11664 &:= ((4! - 6) \times 6)^{1+1} \\ 11957 &:= (7 + 5! \times 9) \times 11 \\ 12137 &:= -7 + (3 + 1)!! / 21! \\ 12142 &:= -2 + 4!! \times 1 / 21! \\ 12144 &:= 4!! / (4! - 1 \times 2 - 1)! \\ 12274 &:= (4! - 7) \times (2 + (2 + 1)!!) \\ 12504 &:= 4! \times (0 + 521) \\ 12544 &:= (-4 - 4 + 5!)^2 \times 1 \\ 12605 &:= 5 \times ((0! + 6)! / 2 + 1) \\ 12759 &:= -9 + (5! - 7)^2 - 1 \\ 12923 &:= (3!! - 2) \times (9 \times 2) - 1 \\ 12933 &:= (3! \times 3!! - 9) \times (2 + 1) \\ 12959 &:= 9! / (5! - 92) - 1 \\ 13239 &:= 9 \times (3!! \times 2 + 31) \\ 13248 &:= (8! - 4!^2) / 3 \times 1 \\ 13368 &:= (8! - 6^3) / 3 \times 1 \\ 13392 &:= 2 \times 9 \times (3!! + (3 + 1)!) \\ 13432 &:= ((2^3)! - 4!) / 3 \times 1 \\ 13438 &:= 8! / 3 - 4 + 3 - 1 \\ 13439 &:= 9! / (3^4 / 3) - 1 \\ 13453 &:= -3 + (5! - 4)^{3-1} \\ 13458 &:= (8! + 54) / 3 \times 1 \\ 13488 &:= 8 \times (8! / 4! + 3!) \times 1 \\ 13536 &:= 6! + 3!^5 + (3! + 1)! \\ 13537 &:= 7! + 3!^5 + 3!! + 1 \\ 13555 &:= -5 + 5! \times (5! - 3! - 1) \\ 13557 &:= (-7 + 5!) \times 5! - 3 \times 1 \\ 13566 &:= (-6 + 6!) \times (-5 + (3 + 1)!) \\ 13661 &:= (-1 + 6!) \times (6 \times 3 + 1) \\ 13834 &:= 4!^3 + 8 + 3 - 1 \\ 13945 &:= 5! + 4!^{9/3} + 1 \\ 14255 &:= -5! + 5!^2 - 4! - 1 \\ 14325 &:= 5!^2 - 3 \times (4! + 1) \\ 14335 &:= 5 \times ((3!! - 3) \times 4 - 1) \\ 14352 &:= (-2 - 5! + 3!!) \times 4! \times 1 \\ 14365 &:= 5 \times (-6 + 3!! \times 4 - 1) \\ 14373 &:= -3^7 + 3!! \times (4! - 1) \\ 14375 &:= 5^{7-3} \times (4! - 1) \\ 14376 &:= -6! + 7! \times 3 - 4! \times 1 \\ 14395 &:= 5 \times ((9 - 3)! \times 4 - 1) \\ 14425 &:= 5!^{-2+4} + 4! + 1 \\ 14515 &:= 5! \times (1 + 5!) - 4 - 1 \\ 14525 &:= 5!^2 + 5^{4-1} \\ 14564 &:= 4 \times (6! \times 5 + 41) \\ 14567 &:= (7 + 6! - 5!) \times 4! - 1 \\ 14637 &:= 7 \times 3 \times (6! - 4! + 1) \\ 14755 &:= -5 + (-5! + 7!) \times (4 - 1) \\ 14973 &:= 3 \times (7! - 9) - (4 + 1)! \\ 15093 &:= -3 \times (9 - (0! + 5 + 1)!) \\ 15117 &:= (7! - 1) \times (-1 + 5 - 1) \\ 15232 &:= 2^{3!} \times 2 \times (5! - 1) \\ 15237 &:= 7! \times 3 - 2 + 5! - 1 \\ 15239 &:= 9! / (3! - 2)! + 5! - 1 \\ 15367 &:= (7 + 6! / 3!) \times (5! + 1) \\ 15425 &:= 5!^2 + 4^5 + 1 \\ 15488 &:= 8 \times (-8 + 4!) \times (5! + 1) \\ 15505 &:= 5^{0!+5} - 5! \times 1 \\ 15609 &:= (9 + (-0! + 6)!) \times (5! + 1) \\ 15631 &:= (-1 + 3!)^6 + 5 + 1 \\ 15635 &:= 5^{3!} + 6 + 5 - 1 \\ 15649 &:= (9 - 4)^6 + (5 - 1)! \\ 15654 &:= 4! + 5^6 + 5 \times 1 \\ 15745 &:= 5^{(-4+7)!} + 5! \times 1 \\ 15864 &:= 4! \times (6! - 8 - 51) \\ 16128 &:= 8! \times 2 \times 1 / (6 - 1) \\ 16345 &:= (5! / 4!)^{3!} + 6! \times 1 \\ 16464 &:= 4! \times (6! - 4) - 6! \times 1 \\ 16495 &:= 5! - 9 + 4^{6+1} \\ 16537 &:= (-7 + 3! \times 5) \times (6! - 1) \\ 16564 &:= 4! \times 6! + 5 - 6! - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 16585 &:= 5! \times 8 + 5^6 \times 1 \\ 16742 &:= (-2 + 4!) \times 761 \\ 16813 &:= 3! + (-1 + 8)^{6-1} \\ 16944 &:= 4! \times (-4 - 9 + 6! - 1) \\ 16945 &:= -((5! + (4! \times (9 - 6!)))) + 1 \\ 17064 &:= 4! \times (6! - 0! - 7 - 1) \\ 17232 &:= (-2 + 3!)! \times (-2 + (7 - 1)!) \\ 17253 &:= (3 + 5! \times 2) \times 71 \\ 17264 &:= 4! \times 6! - 2 \times (7 + 1) \\ 17279 &:= 9! / (7 + 2 \times 7) - 1 \\ 17303 &:= (3!! + 0!) \times (-3 + 7)! - 1 \\ 17304 &:= 4! \times ((0 \times 3)! + (7 - 1)!) \\ 17346 &:= -6 + 4! \times (3 + (7 - 1)!) \\ 17351 &:= (-1 + 5)! \times 3!! + 71 \\ 17424 &:= 4! \times (2 + 4 + (7 - 1)!) \\ 17496 &:= (6! + 9) \times 4 \times (7 - 1) \\ 18729 &:= 9^{-2+7} - 8! \times 1 \\ 18742 &:= -2 + 4! \times 781 \\ 18963 &:= -3!! + (-6 + 9)^{8+1} \\ 19323 &:= -3!!/2 + 3^9 \times 1 \\ 19368 &:= (-8 + 6! \times 3) \times 9 \times 1 \\ 19443 &:= 3 \times ((4!/4)! \times 9 + 1) \\ 19464 &:= 4! \times 6! + 4! \times 91 \\ 19474 &:= (4 + 7!/4!) \times 91 \\ 19684 &:= (-4!/8 + 6)^9 + 1 \\ 19747 &:= 7 \times (4! + 7) \times 91 \\ 20144 &:= 4 \times (-4 + (1 + (0! + 2)!)!) \\ 20148 &:= (8! - 4!) \times 1/02 \\ 20157 &:= 7! \times (5 - 1) - 0! - 2 \\ 20158 &:= 8! \times 5/10 - 2 \\ 20184 &:= 4! + 8! / (1 \times 0 + 2) \\ 20268 &:= (8! + 6^{2+0!})/2 \\ 20448 &:= (8! + 4! \times 4!) / 02 \\ 20449 &:= (9 \times 4 \times 4 - 0!)^2 \\ 20455 &:= 5 \times (-5 + 4^{(0!+2)!}) \\ 20485 &:= 5 \times (8^4 + (0/2)!) \\ 20665 &:= 5^6 + (6 + (0/2)!)! \\ 20736 &:= (6 \times 3 \times (7 + 0!))^2 \\ 20873 &:= (3!! - 7) + 8! / (0 + 2) \\ 20876 &:= 6! + (-7 + 8! - 0!) / 2 \\ 21456 &:= (6! \times 5 - 4!) \times (1 + 2)! \\ 21575 &:= 5 \times (7! - 5 - (1 + 2)!!) \\ 21603 &:= 30 \times 6! + 1 + 2 \\ 21605 &:= 5 \times (0! + 6 \times (1 + 2)!!) \\ 22398 &:= 8! / 9 \times (3 + 2) - 2 \\ 22472 &:= (2 + 7!/4!)^2 / 2 \\ 22599 &:= -9 \times (9 - (5 + 2)! / 2) \\ 22675 &:= -5 + (7! + (6 + 2)!) / 2 \\ 22678 &:= (8! + 7 \times 6!) / 2 - 2 \\ 22679 &:= (9 \times 7! - 6) / 2 + 2 \\ 23024 &:= 4^2 \times (-0! + 3!! \times 2) \\ 23035 &:= -5 + 3!! \times (0 + 32) \\ 23038 &:= 8 \times (3 + 0!) \times 3!! - 2 \\ 23064 &:= 4! + 6! \times (0 + 32) \\ 23066 &:= -6 + (6! + 0!) \times 32 \\ 23136 &:= (6! + 3) \times 1 \times 32 \\ 23304 &:= -4! - 0 + 3!^{3!} / 2 \\ 23319 &:= -9 + 1 \times 3!^{3!} / 2 \\ 23323 &:= -3 - 2 + 3!^{3!} / 2 \\ 23324 &:= -4 + (2 \times 3)^{3!} / 2 \\ 23325 &:= -5 + 2 + 3!^{3!} / 2 \\ 23331 &:= 1 \times 3 + 3!^{3!} / 2 \\ 23332 &:= (2^3 + 3!^{3!}) / 2 \\ 23334 &:= (4 \times 3 + 3!^{3!}) / 2 \\ 23364 &:= 4 \times (-6! + 3^{3!+2}) \\ 23377 &:= 7 \times 7 + 3!^{3!} / 2 \\ 23409 &:= (9 + (0 + 4)! \times 3!)^2 \\ 23424 &:= 4^2 \times (4! + 3!! \times 2) \\ 23436 &:= 63 \times (4! + 3!) / 2 \\ 23513 &:= -(3! + 1)^5 + (3! + 2)! \\ 23664 &:= (-4! + 6!) \times (6 \times 3! - 2) \\ 23694 &:= (4! + 9) \times ((6 - 3)!! - 2) \\ 23755 &:= -5 + 5 \times 7! - 3!! \times 2 \\ 23758 &:= (8 \times 5 - 7) \times 3!! - 2 \\ 23762 &:= (26 + 7) \times 3!! + 2 \\ 23856 &:= 6 \times (-5! + 8^{3! - 2}) \\ 24191 &:= -1 + 9! / (-1 + 4^2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24276 &:= 6 \times 7 \times (2 + 4!)^2 \\ 24346 &:= (6! - 4) \times 34 + 2 \\ 24384 &:= 4! \times (8^3 - 4) \times 2 \\ 24576 &:= 6 \times (7 - 5)^{4!/2} \\ 24579 &:= (-9 + 7!) \times 5 - 4!^2 \\ 24624 &:= 4! \times (2^{6+4} + 2) \\ 24649 &:= (9 + 4 + 6 \times 4!)^2 \\ 24695 &:= -5^{(9-6)!} + (4 \times 2)! \\ 24964 &:= ((4! - 6) \times 9 - 4)^2 \\ 24975 &:= 5 \times 7! - (-9 + 4!)^2 \\ 25075 &:= 5 \times (7! + 0 - 5^2) \\ 25088 &:= 8 \times (8! / (0! + 5)!)^2 \\ 25165 &:= 5 \times (6! - 1) \times (5 + 2) \\ 25167 &:= (7! - 6 - 1) \times 5 + 2 \\ 25173 &:= (-3! + 7! + 1) \times 5 - 2 \\ 25174 &:= -4! + 7! \times 1 \times 5 - 2 \\ 25175 &:= 5 \times 7! - 1 \times 5^2 \\ 25183 &:= (-3 + (8 - 1)!) \times 5 - 2 \\ 25185 &:= 5 \times ((8 - 1)! - 5 + 2) \\ 25189 &:= -9 + (8 - 1)! \times 5 - 2 \\ 25198 &:= 8! / (9 - 1) \times 5 - 2 \\ 25205 &:= 5 \times (-0! + 2 + (5 + 2)!) \\ 25207 &:= (7! + (0 \times 2)!) \times 5 + 2 \\ 25208 &:= ((8 - 0)!) + 2 \times 5 - 2 \\ 25215 &:= 5 \times (1 + 2 + (5 + 2)!) \\ 25217 &:= (7! + 1 + 2) \times 5 + 2 \\ 25335 &:= 5 \times (3^3 + (5 + 2)!) \\ 25337 &:= (7! + 3^3) \times 5 + 2 \\ 25575 &:= 5 \times (75 + (5 + 2)!) \\ 25577 &:= (7! + 75) \times 5 + 2 \\ 25758 &:= (-8 + 5! + 7!) \times 5 - 2 \\ 25775 &:= 5 \times (7! - 7 + 5! + 2) \\ 25893 &:= -3 \times 9 + 8! - 5!^2 \\ 25915 &:= -5 + (-1 + 9)! - 5!^2 \\ 25918 &:= (8 + 1)! / (9 + 5) - 2 \\ 25922 &:= (2^2)! \times 9 \times 5! + 2 \\ 25944 &:= 4! + 4 \times 9 \times (5 - 2)!! \\ 25945 &:= 5! \times 4! \times 9 + 5^2 \\ 26064 &:= (4 + 6!) \times (0 + 6^2) \\ 26136 &:= (6 + 3!!) \times 1 \times 6^2 \\ 26208 &:= (8 + (0! + 2)!!) \times 6^2 \\ 26279 &:= (9! / 7 - 2 + 6!) / 2 \\ 26352 &:= (2 + 5!) \times 3! \times 6^2 \\ 26488 &:= 8! - 8 - 4!^{6/2} \\ 26496 &:= 69 \times (4! + 6! / 2) \\ 26635 &:= -5 + 3!! + 6! \times 6^2 \\ 26664 &:= 4! + 6! + 6! \times 6^2 \\ 26848 &:= 8 \times (-4 + 8! / (6 \times 2)) \\ 26864 &:= 4 \times (-6 + 8! / 6 + 2) \\ 26868 &:= 8! - (6 + 8! / 6) \times 2 \\ 26898 &:= 8! + (9 - 8! / 6) \times 2 \\ 26937 &:= 73 \times (9 + 6! / 2) \\ 27456 &:= (6 + 5) \times (-4! + 7! / 2) \\ 27534 &:= (4!^3 - 57) \times 2 \\ 27634 &:= (4!^{-3+6} - 7) \times 2 \\ 27648 &:= 8 \times 4! \times 6! / (7 - 2) \\ 27715 &:= 5 \times (-1 + 7!) + 7! / 2 \\ 27735 &:= 5 \times (3 + 7!) + 7! / 2 \\ 27744 &:= 4! + (4 + 7) \times 7! / 2 \\ 28438 &:= 8! - (3 \times 4)! / 8! - 2 \\ 28575 &:= (5! + 7) \times (5! / 8)^2 \\ 28656 &:= 6^5 + 6! + 8! / 2 \\ 28735 &:= 5^3! \times 7 - 8! \times 2 \\ 28795 &:= -5 - 9! / 7 + 8! \times 2 \\ 28798 &:= 8! - 9! / 7 + 8! - 2 \\ 28805 &:= 5 \times (0! + 8 \times (8 - 2)!) \\ 28944 &:= (4!^4 + 9!) / (8 / 2)! \\ 28974 &:= -4^7 + 9! / 8 - 2 \\ 29376 &:= 6 \times (7! - (3 + 9)^2) \\ 29576 &:= 6 \times (7! - 5! + 9) + 2 \\ 29736 &:= 6 \times (-3 + 7! - 9^2) \\ 29946 &:= 6 \times (-49 + (9 - 2)!) \\ 30137 &:= 7! \times 3! - 103 \\ 30175 &:= -5 + (7! - 10) \times 3! \\ 30176 &:= 6 \times 7! - (1 + 0!)^3! \\ 30186 &:= -6 \times (8 + 1 - (0! + 3)!) \\ 30228 &:= (8 - 2) \times (-2 + (0! + 3)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 30234 &:= ((4 + 3)! - (2 \times 0)!) \times 3! \\
 30235 &:= -5 + 3 \times 2 \times (0! + 3)! \\
 30237 &:= 7! \times 3 \times 2 - 0 - 3 \\
 30239 &:= 9! / (3! \times 2) - (0/3)! \\
 30252 &:= (2 + (5 + 2)!) \times (0 + 3)! \\
 30264 &:= (4 + (6 + (2 \times 0)!)!) \times 3! \\
 30267 &:= 7! \times 6 + (2 + 0!)^3 \\
 30273 &:= ((3! + 7!) \times 2 - 0!) \times 3 \\
 30276 &:= (6 + 7!) \times 2 \times (0 + 3) \\
 30288 &:= (8 + (8 - (2 \times 0)!)!) \times 3! \\
 30297 &:= ((7! + 9) \times 2 + 0!) \times 3 \\
 30324 &:= 42 \times (3 - 0! + 3!!) \\
 30354 &:= (4! - 5 + (3! + 0)!) \times 3! \\
 30355 &:= 5! - 5 + 3! \times (0! + 3)! \\
 30366 &:= 6 \times (6! + 3) \times (0! + 3!) \\
 30372 &:= (-2 + 7! + (3 + 0)!) \times 3! \\
 30377 &:= -7 + (7! + (3 + 0)!) \times 3! \\
 30384 &:= (4! + (8 - (3 \times 0)!)!) \times 3! \\
 30475 &:= -5 + (7! + 40) \times 3! \\
 30576 &:= (6 + 7! + 50) \times 3! \\
 30738 &:= (83 + 7!) \times (0 + 3)! \\
 30786 &:= (6! / 8 + 7! + 0!) \times 3! \\
 31668 &:= 8! - (6 + 6) \times (1 + 3!!) \\
 31782 &:= (2^8 + 7! + 1) \times 3! \\
 31995 &:= -5 \times 9 \times (9 - 1 \times 3!!) \\
 32048 &:= 8^{4+0!} - (2 \times 3)! \\
 32128 &:= 8! - 2^{1+2 \times 3!} \\
 32256 &:= (6 + 5!) \times 2^{2^3} \\
 32258 &:= -8! / 5 + 2 + (2^3)! \\
 32394 &:= ((4! - 9) \times 3!! - 2) \times 3 \\
 32395 &:= 5 \times 9 \times 3!! - 2 - 3 \\
 32403 &:= (3!! / (0 + 4))^2 + 3 \\
 32406 &:= (6! / (0 + 4))^2 + 3! \\
 32448 &:= (8 + 4 \times 4!)^2 \times 3 \\
 32537 &:= -7 - 3!^5 + (2^3)! \\
 32538 &:= 8! - 3!^5 - 2 \times 3 \\
 32544 &:= 4! \times 452 \times 3 \\
 32568 &:= 8! - 6^5 + (-2 + 3)! \\
 32648 &:= 8 \times 4^6 - (2 + 3)!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 32744 &:= 4 \times (4^7 / 2 - 3!) \\
 32748 &:= 8! - (4 + 7! / 2) \times 3 \\
 32762 &:= (2 + 6)^{7-2} - 3! \\
 32784 &:= 4! + 8! - 7! / 2 \times 3 \\
 32805 &:= 5 \times (0! + 8)^{-2+3!} \\
 32832 &:= 2^{3!} + 8^{2+3} \\
 33144 &:= 4! + (4! - 1) \times (3!! + 3!!) \\
 33408 &:= 8 \times (0 - 4! + 3!!) \times 3! \\
 33458 &:= 8! + (5 - 4!)^3 - 3 \\
 33484 &:= -4 + (8 \times 4)^3 + 3!! \\
 33488 &:= 8 \times 8^4 + (3 + 3)! \\
 33489 &:= (9 - 8 \times 4!)^{3!/3} \\
 33495 &:= 5 \times (9 \times (4! + 3!!) + 3) \\
 33558 &:= (-8 + 55) \times (-3! + 3!!) \\
 33585 &:= 5 \times (8 \times (5! + 3!!) - 3) \\
 33587 &:= -7 + 8! \times 5 / 3! - 3! \\
 33599 &:= (9! / 9 \times 5 - 3!) / 3! \\
 33648 &:= 8 \times (-4 + 6!) \times 3! - 3!! \\
 33768 &:= -8! + (6 \times 7)^{-3+3!} \\
 33769 &:= (9! \times 67 + 3!!) / 3!! \\
 33835 &:= -5 + 3!! \times 8 \times 3! - 3!! \\
 33837 &:= (7! - 3!!) \times 8 - 3!! - 3 \\
 33839 &:= -9 \times 3!! + 8! - 3 / 3 \\
 33852 &:= (2 - 5! + 8 \times 3!!) \times 3! \\
 33864 &:= (4 + 6! \times 8) \times 3! - 3!! \\
 33984 &:= -48 \times (9 + 3 - 3!!) \\
 34047 &:= (7! / 4 + 0!) \times (4! + 3) \\
 34224 &:= (4! + 22) \times (4! + 3!!) \\
 34248 &:= 8! - 4!! / (2 \times (4! - 3)!) \\
 34266 &:= (6! - 6) \times 2 \times 4! - 3! \\
 34368 &:= 8 \times ((6 - 3)!! - 4) \times 3! \\
 34377 &:= 7 \times (7! - 3 \times 43) \\
 34386 &:= 6 \times (8 \times (3!! - 4) + 3) \\
 34416 &:= 61 \times 4! \times 4! - 3!! \\
 34432 &:= 2 \times (3!! \times 4! - 4^3) \\
 34435 &:= -5^3 + (4! + 4!) \times 3!! \\
 34452 &:= 2 \times (-54 + 4! \times 3!!) \\
 34464 &:= (-4 + 6!) \times 4! + 4! \times 3!! \\
 34497 &:= -7 \times 9 + (4! + 4!) \times 3!!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34512 &:= 2 \times (-(-1 + 5)! + 4! \times 3!!) \\ 34524 &:= 4!/2 \times (5! \times 4! - 3) \\ 34528 &:= 8 \times ((2 + 5)! - 4 - 3!!) \\ 34536 &:= (6! \times (3 + 5) - 4) \times 3! \\ 34542 &:= 2 \times (-4 - 5 + 4! \times 3!!) \\ 34544 &:= 4 \times (-4 + 5! \times 4! \times 3) \\ 34545 &:= (-5 + 4 \times 5! \times 4!) \times 3 \\ 34555 &:= -5 + 5! \times (5! - 4!) \times 3 \\ 34557 &:= (7 + 5) \times 5! \times 4! - 3 \\ 34575 &:= 5 \times (7! + 5^4 \times 3) \\ 34584 &:= (48 \times 5! + 4) \times 3! \\ 34602 &:= 2 \times ((0! + 6!) \times 4! - 3) \\ 34624 &:= 4! \times 2 \times 6! + 4^3 \\ 34632 &:= 2 \times (36 + 4! \times 3!!) \\ 34648 &:= -8 + 4! \times (6! + 4 + 3!!) \\ 34668 &:= (8 \times 6! - 6 + 4!) \times 3! \\ 34686 &:= 6 \times (8 \times 6! + 4! - 3) \\ 34688 &:= -8 \times (8 - 6 \times (4 + 3!!)) \\ 34704 &:= ((4 - 0)!! + 7! + 4!) \times 3! \\ 34773 &:= -3 + 7 \times (7! - 4! \times 3) \\ 34777 &:= 7 \times (7! + 7 + 4!) - 3!! \\ 34968 &:= (8 \times (6! + 9) - 4) \times 3! \\ 34992 &:= 2 \times (9 + 9)^4/3! \\ 35077 &:= 7 \times (7! + 0! - 5 \times 3!) \\ 35268 &:= (8 \times 6! - 2 + 5!) \times 3! \\ 35272 &:= (-2 + 7!) \times (2 + 5) + 3! \\ 35275 &:= -5 + 7 \times (2 \times 5 - 3!) \\ 35277 &:= 7 \times (7! - 2) + 5 + 3! \\ 35394 &:= 49 \times 3!! + 5! - 3! \\ 35424 &:= 4!/2 \times 4! \times (5! + 3) \\ 35477 &:= 7 \times (7! + 4! + 5) - 3! \\ 35488 &:= 8! + 8 \times (-4 + 5! - 3!!) \\ 35557 &:= 7^5 + 5^5 \times 3! \\ 35648 &:= 8 \times (4^6 + 5! \times 3) \\ 35792 &:= 2^9 - 7! + (5 + 3)! \\ 35793 &:= 3 \times 97 \times (5! + 3) \\ 35864 &:= -4^6 + 8! - 5! \times 3 \\ 35937 &:= (-7 - 3!!/9 + 5!)^3 \\ 35943 &:= 3!!/5! + (9 + 4!)^3 \\ 36007 &:= 7 \times (0! + (0! + 6)!) + 3!! \\ 36015 &:= 5 \times (10 \times 6! + 3) \\ 36025 &:= 5^2 \times (0! + 6! + 3!!) \\ 36153 &:= -3!! + 51 \times (6! + 3) \\ 36224 &:= (4 \times 2)! - (-2 + 6)^{3!} \\ 36248 &:= 8! + 4! - (-2 + 6)^{3!} \\ 36288 &:= 8! - 8^2 \times 63 \\ 36289 &:= 9!/(8 + 2) + 6/3! \\ 36477 &:= 7 \times (7 \times (4! + 6!) + 3) \\ 36481 &:= (-1 + 8 \times 4!)^{6/3} \\ 36585 &:= -5! + 8! - 5 \times (6! + 3) \\ 36678 &:= 8! - (7 + 6!) \times 6 + 3!! \\ 36715 &:= -5 + 17 \times 6! \times 3 \\ 36744 &:= 4! + (4! - 7) \times 6! \times 3 \\ 36748 &:= 8! - 4 \times (-7 + 6!) - 3!! \\ 36757 &:= -7 \times (5 - 7! - 6^3) \\ 36758 &:= 8! - 5 \times (-7 + 6!) + 3 \\ 36792 &:= (-2 + 9) \times (7! + 6^3) \\ 36798 &:= 8! - 9! \times 7/6! + 3! \\ 37044 &:= 4 \times ((4 - 0!) \times 7)^3 \\ 37173 &:= 3^7 \times 17 - 3! \\ 37248 &:= 8! - 4 \times 2^7 \times 3! \\ 37344 &:= 4 \times (-4! + 3!! \times (7 + 3!!)) \\ 37434 &:= 4! \times 3!! + 4 \times 7! - 3! \\ 37435 &:= -5 + 3!! \times 4 \times (7 + 3!) \\ 37488 &:= 8! + (8^4 - 7!) \times 3 \\ 37584 &:= (4! \times 8)^{-5+7} + 3!! \\ 37748 &:= 8! + 4 \times (77 - 3!!) \\ 37795 &:= -5 + 9 \times (7! - 7!/3!) \\ 37805 &:= 5 \times (0! + (8! + 7!)/3!) \\ 37938 &:= 8! - 397 \times 3! \\ 38248 &:= 8! - 4! - 2^{8+3} \\ 38278 &:= 8 \times (7! - 2^8) + 3! \\ 38328 &:= 8! - (-2 + 3!)! \times 83 \\ 38368 &:= 8! - 6! - 3!! - 8^3 \\ 38448 &:= 8! - 4! \times 48 - 3!! \\ 38472 &:= (2 \times 7)^4 + 8!/3!! \\ 38523 &:= -3!!/2 \times 5 + 8! + 3 \\ 38525 &:= 5^{2+5} - 8! + 3!! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 38526 &:= -6!/2 \times 5 + 8! + 3! \\ 38528 &:= 8! - 2^5 \times 8!/3!! \\ 38584 &:= (48 + 5) \times (8 + 3!!) \\ 38592 &:= -(-2 + 9)!/5 + 8! - 3!! \\ 38637 &:= -7!/3 - 6 + 8! + 3 \\ 38664 &:= (-4 + 6!) \times (6 \times 8 + 3!) \\ 38688 &:= 8! - 8 \times 68 \times 3 \\ 38736 &:= 6! + 3!^7 - 8! \times 3! \\ 38755 &:= -5 - 5! \times 7 + 8! - 3!! \\ 38767 &:= -7!/6 + 7 + 8! - 3!! \\ 38799 &:= -9 + 9 \times (7! - 8 - 3!!) \\ 38832 &:= -2 \times 3!! + 8! - 8 \times 3! \\ 38863 &:= -3^6 - 8 + 8! - 3!! \\ 38889 &:= 9 \times ((8 + 8!)/8 - 3!!) \\ 38928 &:= 8! - 29 \times 8 \times 3! \\ 38936 &:= 6! \times 3! \times 9 + 8!/3!! \\ 38955 &:= -5 \times (5! + 9) + 8! - 3!! \\ 38963 &:= 3!! \times 6 \times 9 + 83 \\ 39024 &:= (4! + (2 + 0!)!! \times 9) \times 3! \\ 39048 &:= 8! + 4! \times (0! - 9 \times 3!) \\ 39339 &:= (3! \times 9^3 - 3) \times 9 \\ 39339 &:= -9 \times (3 - 3! \times 9^3) \\ 39363 &:= 3^6 \times 3! \times 9 - 3 \\ 39392 &:= 2^9 + 3!! \times 9 \times 3! \\ 39438 &:= 8! - 3! \times 49 \times 3 \\ 39456 &:= 6 \times (5! - 4! + 9 \times 3!!) \\ 39528 &:= 8 \times ((2 + 5)! - 9) - 3!! \\ 39568 &:= 8! - 6! - 5 - 9 \times 3 \\ 39583 &:= -3 + 8! - 5 - 9^3 \\ 39588 &:= 8! - 8 + 5 - 9^3 \\ 39728 &:= 8! + 2^7 - (9 - 3)! \\ 39744 &:= 4! \times 4! \times (7 \times 9 + 3!) \\ 39754 &:= ((4 + 5)! - 7!)/9 - 3! \\ 39758 &:= 8! - 5 - 7!/9 + 3 \\ 39763 &:= ((3 + 6)! - 7!)/9 + 3 \\ 39768 &:= 8 \times (-6 + 7 \times (-9 + 3!!)) \\ 39808 &:= 8! + 0 - 8^{9/3} \\ 39813 &:= -3 + 1 \times 8! - 9!/3!! \\ 39816 &:= (6 + 1) \times 8 \times (-9 + 3!!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39824 &:= 4 \times 2 + 8! - 9!/3!! \\ 39834 &:= 4! - 3! + 8! - 9!/3!! \\ 39837 &:= 7 \times (3 + 8 \times (-9 + 3!!)) \\ 39858 &:= 8! - (5 + 8 \times 9) \times 3! \\ 39879 &:= 9 \times 7 + 8! - 9!/3!! \\ 39884 &:= -4 + 8! - 8 \times 9 \times 3! \\ 39888 &:= 8! - (8 + 8) \times 9 \times 3 \\ 39896 &:= 6!/9 + 8! - 9!/3!! \\ 39936 &:= 6^3! - 9!/(9 \times 3!) \\ 39948 &:= 8! - 4 \times (99 - 3!) \\ 40128 &:= 8! + (2 - 10) \times 4! \\ 40199 &:= 9!/9 - 1 - (0! + 4!) \\ 40228 &:= 8! - (22 + 0!) \times 4 \\ 40248 &:= (8!/4! - 2 - 0!) \times 4! \\ 40268 &:= 8! - (6 \times 2 + 0!) \times 4 \\ 40284 &:= -4 + 8! - 2^{0!+4} \\ 40295 &:= ((-5 + 9) \times 2)! - 0! - 4! \\ 40332 &:= (2^3)! + 3 \times (0 + 4) \\ 40335 &:= (5 + 3)! + 3 \times (0! + 4) \\ 40337 &:= -7 + (3 \times 3 - 0!)! + 4! \\ 40338 &:= 8! + 3! + 3 \times 04 \\ 40342 &:= (2 \times 4)! - 3 + 0! + 4! \\ 40343 &:= ((3! - 4)^3)! - 0! + 4! \\ 40344 &:= (4 + 4)! + 3! \times (0 + 4) \\ 40345 &:= (5!/4! + 3)! + 0! + 4! \\ 40352 &:= 2^5 + (3 + 0! + 4)! \\ 40358 &:= 8! + 5 \times 3 - 0! + 4! \\ 40368 &:= 8 \times (6 + (3 + 0 + 4)!) \\ 40372 &:= (2 \times (7! + 3!) + 0!) \times 4 \\ 40383 &:= -3! + 8! + 3 \times (-0! + 4!) \\ 40386 &:= -6 + 8! + 3 \times 04! \\ 40388 &:= 8! + 8^{3-0!} + 4 \\ 40392 &:= 2 \times (9 + (3! + 0!)!) \times 4 \\ 40398 &:= 8! + 9 \times 3! + 04! \\ 40408 &:= 8! + (-0! + 4! - 0!) \times 4 \\ 40428 &:= 8! + (2 + 4! + 0!) \times 4 \\ 40464 &:= 4! \times 6 + (4 - 0 + 4)! \\ 40468 &:= 8! + 6 \times 4! + 0 + 4 \\ 40528 &:= 8! + (2 + 50) \times 4 \\ 40536 &:= 6^3 + (5 - 0! + 4)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 40538 &:= 8! + 3^5 - 0! - 4! \\
 40828 &:= 8! + 2^{8+0!} - 4 \\
 40832 &:= (2^3)! + 8^{-0!+4} \\
 40838 &:= 8! + 3! + 8^{-0!+4} \\
 40945 &:= 5^4 + (9 - (0/4)!)! \\
 40964 &:= 4^6 \times (9 + 0!) + 4 \\
 40978 &:= 8! + 7 \times (90 + 4) \\
 41035 &:= -5 + 3!! + ((0! + 1) \times 4)! \\
 41064 &:= 4! + 6! + ((0! + 1) \times 4)! \\
 41348 &:= 8! + 4^{3!-1} + 4 \\
 41448 &:= 8! + 4! \times (4! - 1 + 4!) \\
 41538 &:= 8! - 3! + 51 \times 4! \\
 41544 &:= (4 + 4)! + 51 \times 4! \\
 41548 &:= 8! + 4! \times 51 + 4 \\
 41616 &:= -(6 + 1)! + 6^{(-1+4)!} \\
 41617 &:= -7! + 1 + 6^{(-1+4)!} \\
 41688 &:= 8! + (8!/6! + 1) \times 4! \\
 41736 &:= 6^{3!} - 7! + (1 + 4)! \\
 41756 &:= 6! \times (57 + 1) - 4 \\
 42048 &:= 8! + 4! \times (0! + 2) \times 4! \\
 42288 &:= 8! + 82 \times 24 \\
 42336 &:= 63 \times (3!! - 2 \times 4!) \\
 42368 &:= 4 \times 2^{3+6} + 8! \\
 42378 &:= 8! + 7^3 \times (2 + 4) \\
 42736 &:= 6 \times 3!! + (7 \times 2)^4 \\
 42768 &:= 8! + 6! + 72 \times 4! \\
 42848 &:= (8! + 4^8 \times 2)/4 \\
 43185 &:= 5!/8 \times (-1 + 3!! \times 4) \\
 43188 &:= 8! - 8 + (-1 + 3!!) \times 4 \\
 43195 &:= -5 + (9 - 1)! + 3!! \times 4 \\
 43196 &:= 6 \times (9 + 1) \times 3!! - 4 \\
 43199 &:= 9!/9 - 1 + 3!! \times 4 \\
 43204 &:= (4 + 0!)!^2 \times 3 + 4 \\
 43208 &:= 8! + (0 + 2 + 3!!) \times 4 \\
 43248 &:= 8! + 4! \times 2 + 3!! \times 4 \\
 43388 &:= 8! + 8^3 \times 3! - 4 \\
 43584 &:= 4! + 8! + 5! \times (3 + 4!) \\
 43676 &:= (67 - 6) \times (3!! - 4) \\
 43684 &:= (4! - 8)! / (6 + 3!)! + 4 \\
 43688 &:= (8 + 8^6) / 3! - 4 \\
 43728 &:= 8! + 2 \times (7! / 3 + 4!) \\
 43824 &:= (4! - 2) \times 83 \times 4! \\
 43896 &:= (69 - 8) \times 3!! - 4! \\
 43916 &:= 61 \times (9 - 3)! - 4 \\
 43959 &:= 9^5 - (9! - 3!!) / 4! \\
 44176 &:= 6! + 7! + 14^4 \\
 44544 &:= 4! \times (-4 + 5!) \times 4 \times 4 \\
 44628 &:= 8! + (-2 + 6!) \times 4! / 4 \\
 44635 &:= -5 + 3! \times 6! + (4 + 4)! \\
 44664 &:= (4 + 6!) \times 6 + (4 + 4)! \\
 44668 &:= 8! + 6 \times (6! + 4) + 4 \\
 44688 &:= 8! + (8 + 6!) \times 4! / 4 \\
 44782 &:= -2 + 8! + 7! - 4! \times 4! \\
 44784 &:= 4! \times ((8! + 7!) / 4! - 4!) \\
 44896 &:= -6! + 9! / 8 + 4^4 \\
 44928 &:= 8! + 2 \times 9 \times 4^4 \\
 45189 &:= 9 \times ((8 - 1)! + 5 - 4!) \\
 45279 &:= 9 \times 7! - (-2 + 5)^4 \\
 45297 &:= (7! - 9 + 2) \times (5 + 4) \\
 45306 &:= ((6 + 0!)! - 3!) \times (5 + 4) \\
 45315 &:= (-5 + (1 + 3!)!) \times (5 + 4) \\
 45319 &:= 9 \times ((1 + 3!)! - 5) + 4 \\
 45336 &:= 63 \times 3! \times 5! - 4! \\
 45342 &:= (-2 + (4 + 3!)!) \times (5 + 4) \\
 45355 &:= -5 + (5! + 3!!) \times 54 \\
 45356 &:= (6 + 5!) \times 3 \times 5! - 4 \\
 45359 &:= 9! / (5 + 3) - 5 + 4 \\
 45378 &:= (8 + 7! - 3!) \times (5 + 4) \\
 45379 &:= 9 \times 7! + 3 \times 5 + 4 \\
 45387 &:= 7! + 8! + 3 \times (5 + 4) \\
 45592 &:= (-2 + 95 \times 5!) \times 4 \\
 45595 &:= -5 + 95 \times 5! \times 4 \\
 45679 &:= 9 \times 7 \times (6! + 5) + 4 \\
 45732 &:= (4! + (5! + 7) \times 3!!) / 2 \\
 45783 &:= 3^8 \times 7 - 5! - 4! \\
 45837 &:= 7! - 3 + 8! + 5! \times 4 \\
 45888 &:= (-8 + (8 + 8) \times 5!) \times 4! \\
 45936 &:= -6! + 3!^{(9-5)!/4} \\
 46016 &:= (6! - 1) \times (0 + 64)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}46056 &:= (65 - 0!) \times 6! - 4! \\46072 &:= 2 \times (7! - 0! + 6!) \times 4 \\46075 &:= -5 + (7 - 0!)! \times 64 \\46076 &:= 6! \times (70 - 6) - 4 \\46082 &:= 2 \times (8! + 0! - 6! \times 4!) \\46137 &:= -7 + (3!! + 1) \times 64 \\46144 &:= 4 \times 4 \times (1 + 6!) \times 4 \\46232 &:= (2 + 3!!) \times 2^6 + 4! \\46288 &:= 8! + 8 \times (2 + 6! + 4!) \\46328 &:= -8 + 2^{3!} \times (6! + 4) \\46336 &:= (6/3)^{3!} \times (6! + 4) \\46337 &:= -7^3 + 3!^6 + 4! \\46368 &:= 8 \times (6! + 3^6) \times 4 \\46476 &:= 6^{(7-4)!} - 6!/4 \\46536 &:= 6^{3!} - 5 \times 6 \times 4 \\46564 &:= 4! + 65 \times (6! - 4) \\46566 &:= 6^6 + 5 \times (6 - 4!) \\46584 &:= 4! - 8! + 5! \times (6! + 4) \\46623 &:= -3^2 + 6^6 - 4! \\46624 &:= -4 \times 2 + 6^6 - 4! \\46625 &:= -5 - 2 + 6^6 - 4! \\46626 &:= (6/2)!^6 - 6 - 4! \\46627 &:= -7 + 2 + 6^6 - 4! \\46628 &:= -(8/2)! + 6^6 - 4 \\46633 &:= 3/3 + 6^6 - 4! \\46634 &:= -4 + 3! + 6^6 - 4! \\46638 &:= -8 - 3! + 6^6 - 4 \\46652 &:= (2 - 5 + 6)!^6 - 4 \\46653 &:= 3! - 5 + 6^6 - 4 \\46655 &:= -5 \times 5 + 6^6 + 4! \\46658 &:= (8 - 5)! + 6^6 - 4 \\46664 &:= 4!/6 + 6^6 + 4 \\46667 &:= 7!/6! + 6^6 + 4 \\46674 &:= (-4 + 7)!^6 - 6 + 4! \\46681 &:= 1^8 + 6^6 + 4! \\46689 &:= 9!/8! + 6^6 + 4! \\46704 &:= 4! + (-0! + 7)^6 + 4!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}46736 &:= 6^{3!} + 76 + 4 \\46796 &:= 6! + 9 \times 7! + 6! - 4 \\46871 &:= -1 + 7 \times (8!/6 - 4!) \\46883 &:= 3^8 + 8! + 6 - 4 \\46936 &:= 6^{3!} + 9!/6^4 \\47368 &:= -8 + 6! + 3!^{(7-4)!} \\47376 &:= 6^7/3! + (7 - 4)!! \\47476 &:= (-6! + 7! - 4) \times (7 + 4) \\47488 &:= 8! + 8^4 \times 7/4 \\47538 &:= 8! + 3 \times (5 + 7^4) \\47664 &:= 4! \times (6! + 6 + 7!/4) \\47868 &:= 8! - 6 \times (8 - 7!)/4 \\48333 &:= 3!^{3!} - 3 + 8!/4! \\48336 &:= 6^{3+3} + 8!/4! \\48344 &:= (4! - 4)^3 + 8! + 4! \\48366 &:= 6^6 + (3!! + 8!)/4! \\48384 &:= 4! \times 8 \times 3 \times 84 \\48388 &:= 8!/(8 - 3) + 8! + 4 \\48408 &:= 8!/(0! + 4) + 8! + 4! \\48596 &:= 69 \times 5! + 8! - 4 \\48664 &:= (-4 + 6!) \times 68 - 4! \\48936 &:= 6! \times (3 + 9) + 8! - 4! \\48955 &:= -5 + 5! \times (9 + 8) \times 4! \\48956 &:= 6! \times 5 + 9!/8 - 4 \\49374 &:= (4! + 7!) \times 39/4 \\49556 &:= (6! + 5!) \times 59 - 4 \\49656 &:= 6 \times 5! \times 69 - 4 \\49668 &:= -8 + 6! \times 69 - 4 \\49824 &:= -4!^2 - 8! + 9!/4 \\50275 &:= 5 \times (7! \times 2 - 0!) - 5! \\50375 &:= 5 \times (7! \times (3 - 0!)) - 5) \\50395 &:= ((5 + 9) \times 3!! - 0!) \times 5 \\50625 &:= (5!/(2 + 6))^{-0!+5} \\50688 &:= 8 \times (-8! + 6^{0!+5}) \\50769 &:= 9 \times (6! + 7! + 0! - 5!) \\50967 &:= 7 \times (6! + 9^{-0!+5}) \\51373 &:= 37^3 + (1 + 5)! \\51719 &:= 9!/(1 \times 7) - 1 - 5! \\51737 &:= (7 + 3!!) \times 71 + 5!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 51839 &:= 9 \times 3!! \times 8 - 1^5 \\ 51845 &:= (5 + 4)! / (8 - 1) + 5 \\ 51879 &:= 9! / 7 - 81 + 5! \\ 51968 &:= 8 \times (6! \times 9 + 1) + 5! \\ 52079 &:= 9! / 7 - 0! + 2 \times 5! \\ 53337 &:= 73 \times 3^{3!} + 5! \\ 53424 &:= 424 \times (3! + 5!) \\ 53557 &:= -7 \times (5! + 5 - 3!^5) \\ 53592 &:= (-2 + 9) \times (-5! + 3!^5) \\ 53658 &:= 8! + (5! - 6) \times (-3 + 5!) \\ 53688 &:= 8 \times (8! / 6 + 3!) - 5! \\ 53712 &:= -(2 + 1)!! + 7 \times 3!^5 \\ 53713 &:= -3!! + 1 + 7 \times 3!^5 \\ 53808 &:= 8 \times (0! + 8! / 3! + 5) \\ 53824 &:= (4! - 2^8)^{-3+5} \\ 53848 &:= 8 \times (-4 + 8! / 3!) + 5! \\ 53856 &:= 6! \times 5! - 8! + 3!^5 \\ 53946 &:= (6 + 4! \times 9) \times 3^5 \\ 54396 &:= (-6! + 9! \times 3) / (4 \times 5) \\ 54549 &:= (-9 + 4! \times 5!) \times (4! - 5) \\ 54576 &:= (6! + 7! \times 54) / 5 \\ 54644 &:= (-4 + 4 \times 6!) \times (4! - 5) \\ 54688 &:= 8 \times (8! / 6 - 4 + 5!) \\ 54742 &:= -2 + 4! \times (7^4 - 5!) \\ 54869 &:= (-9! + 6^8) / 4! + 5 \\ 55375 &:= (5 + 7!) \times (3! + 5) - 5! \\ 55939 &:= 9! / 3!! \times (-9 + 5!) - 5 \\ 56087 &:= 78 \times (-0! + 6!) + 5 \\ 56448 &:= 8! \times (4/4 + 6) / 5 \\ 56485 &:= (-5 + 84) \times (6! - 5) \\ 56544 &:= 4 \times (4 + 5!) \times (-6 + 5!) \\ 56568 &:= 8 \times (6^5 - 6!) + 5! \\ 56755 &:= -5 + (5! + 7!) \times (6 + 5) \\ 56957 &:= (-7 + 5!) \times 9! / 6! + 5 \\ 57126 &:= (6 + 2)! - 1 + 7^5 \\ 57127 &:= (7 + 2 - 1)! + 7^5 \\ 57128 &:= 8! + 2 - 1 + 7^5 \\ 57465 &:= 5^6 \times 4 - 7! + 5 \\ 57602 &:= 2 \times (0! + (6! + 7!) \times 5) \\ 57624 &:= 4! + 2 \times (6! + 7!) \times 5 \\ 57625 &:= (5 + 2 \times (6! + 7!)) \times 5 \\ 57648 &:= 8! + 4! \times (6! + 7 - 5) \\ 57843 &:= 3!! - 4 + 8! + 7^5 \\ 57847 &:= (7 - 4)!! + 8! + 7^5 \\ 58325 &:= 5^2 \times 3!! + 8! + 5 \\ 58329 &:= 9^{2+3} - (8 - 5)!! \\ 58368 &:= 8 \times (6! + 3^8) + 5! \\ 58459 &:= 9! / (5 \times 4) + 8! - 5 \\ 58464 &:= (-4! + 6!) / 4 \times 8! / 5! \\ 58688 &:= 8 \times (-8 - 6! + 8! / 5) \\ 58935 &:= -5! + 3! + (9! / 8!)^5 \\ 59013 &:= -3!^{1+0!} + 9^5 \\ 59023 &:= -3! - 20 + 9^5 \\ 59024 &:= -4! - 2 + 0! + 9^5 \\ 59025 &:= -5^2 + 0! + 9^5 \\ 59026 &:= -(6 - 2)! + 0! + 9^5 \\ 59035 &:= -5 \times 3 + 0! + 9^5 \\ 59036 &:= -6 - 3! - 0! + 9^5 \\ 59037 &:= -7 + 3^{0!+9} - 5 \\ 59039 &:= -9 - (3 \times 0)! + 9^5 \\ 59042 &:= -2 - 4 - 0! + 9^5 \\ 59043 &:= -3 - 4 + 0! + 9^5 \\ 59044 &:= -4 - (4 \times 0)! + 9^5 \\ 59045 &:= -5 + (4 \times 0)! + 9^5 \\ 59046 &:= -6 + 4 - 0! + 9^5 \\ 59047 &:= -7 + 4 + 0! + 9^5 \\ 59048 &:= -(84 \times 0)! + 9^5 \\ 59062 &:= 2 \times 6 + 0! + 9^5 \\ 59073 &:= 3 \times (7 + 0!) + 9^5 \\ 59074 &:= 4! + (7 \times 0)! + 9^5 \\ 59095 &:= 5 \times 9 + 0! + 9^5 \\ 59144 &:= 4 \times 4! - 1 + 9^5 \\ 59145 &:= 5! - 4! + 1 \times 9^5 \\ 59159 &:= 9^5 - 1 - 9 + 5! \\ 59163 &:= -3! + (6 - 1)! + 9^5 \\ 59169 &:= 9^6 \times 1 / 9 + 5! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 59175 &:= 5! + 7 - 1 + 9^5 \\ 59275 &:= (5! - 7) \times 2 + 9^5 \\ 59319 &:= 9 \times ((-1 + 3!) \times 9 + 5!) \\ 59385 &:= (5! - 8) \times 3 + 9^5 \\ 59395 &:= -5 + 9!/3! - 9 \times 5! \\ 59481 &:= 18 \times 4! + 9^5 \\ 59645 &:= -5! - 4 + 6! + 9^5 \\ 59649 &:= -(9 - 4)! + 6! + 9^5 \\ 59655 &:= 5 \times 5! + 6 + 9^5 \\ 59683 &:= 3!! - 86 + 9^5 \\ 59755 &:= 5! \times 5! + 7! \times 9 - 5 \\ 59761 &:= -1 + 6! - 7 + 9^5 \\ 59768 &:= -8 + 6! + 7 + 9^5 \\ 59874 &:= 4! + 7!/8 \times 95 \\ 60359 &:= (9! - 5 - 3!! - 0!)/6 \\ 60432 &:= 2 \times 3! \times (-4 + (0! + 6)!) \\ 60459 &:= (9! - 5! - (4 - 0!)!)/6 \\ 60469 &:= 9!/6 - 4 - 0! - 6 \\ 60473 &:= 3 \times 7! \times 4 - 0! - 6 \\ 60474 &:= 4 \times 7! \times (4 - 0!) - 6 \\ 60475 &:= -5 + 7! \times ((4 - 0!)! + 6) \\ 60479 &:= (9! - (7 - 4)!)/(0 + 6) \\ 60495 &:= -5 + (9! + (4 + 0!)!)/6 \\ 60595 &:= -5 + (9! + (5 + 0!)!)/6 \\ 60596 &:= (6! + 9! - (5 - 0!)!)/6 \\ 60624 &:= (4! + 2 \times (6 + 0!)!) \times 6 \\ 60992 &:= 2^9 + 9!/(0 + 6) \\ 61834 &:= (-4 + 3!!/8) \times (-1 + 6!) \\ 62784 &:= (4! \times 8 + 7!) \times 2 \times 6 \\ 63468 &:= 86 \times (4! - 3! + 6!) \\ 63624 &:= (4! + 2^6) \times (3 + 6!) \\ 63884 &:= -4 + 88 \times (3! + 6!) \\ 64518 &:= 8!/15 \times 4! + 6 \\ 64696 &:= (6! + 9!)/6 + 4^6 \\ 64776 &:= (6! + 7! + 7! - 4) \times 6 \\ 64792 &:= 2^{9+7} - 4! - 6! \\ 64806 &:= (6! + 0! + 8!/4) \times 6 \\ 64836 &:= (6! + 3! + 8!/4) \times 6 \\ 64846 &:= 6 + 4^8 + 4! - 6! \\ 64888 &:= 8! - 8 + 8^4 \times 6 \\ 65284 &:= 4^8 - 2 \times (5! + 6) \\ 65422 &:= 2^{2^4} - 5! + 6 \\ 65544 &:= 4! + (-4! - 5 + 5!) \times 6! \\ 65664 &:= (-4! \times 6 + 6!) \times (5! - 6) \\ 65735 &:= -5^{3!} + (-7 + 5!) \times 6! \\ 66144 &:= 4 \times (4! \times (-1 + 6!) - 6!) \\ 66248 &:= -8 + 4^{2+6} + 6! \\ 66396 &:= -6 + 93 \times (6! - 6) \\ 66738 &:= 8! + 37 \times (6! - 6) \\ 66784 &:= 4 \times (-8 + 7!) + 6^6 \\ 67195 &:= -5 + (9! + (1 + 7!)!)/6 \\ 67536 &:= (6 + 3)!/5 - 7 \times 6! \\ 68352 &:= 2^5 \times 3 \times (-8 + 6!) \\ 68544 &:= 4 \times 4! \times ((-5 + 8)!! - 6) \\ 68579 &:= 97 \times (-5 - 8 + 6!) \\ 69024 &:= ((4 + 2)! - 0!) \times 96 \\ 69144 &:= 4! + (4 - 1)!! \times 96 \\ 69216 &:= (6! + 1^2) \times 96 \\ 69255 &:= (5! - 5^2) \times (9 + 6!) \\ 69312 &:= (2 + 1 \times 3!!) \times 96 \\ 69336 &:= 6^3 + 3!! \times 96 \\ 69504 &:= (4 + (0! + 5)!) \times 96 \\ 69696 &:= (6! + (9 - 6)!) \times 96 \\ 69777 &:= 7 \times (7! + 7! - 9) - 6! \\ 69786 &:= -6! + 8! + (7! - 9) \times 6 \\ 69847 &:= 7! + 4^8 - 9 - 6! \\ 69864 &:= -4! + (6! + 8) \times 96 \\ 69966 &:= (6! - 6) \times 99 - 6! \\ 69984 &:= (4! + 8 \times 9) \times (9 + 6!) \\ 70546 &:= (-6 + 4 \times 5) \times (-0! + 7!) \\ 70584 &:= 4! + (8 + 5 + 0!) \times 7! \\ 71199 &:= 9 \times (-9 + 11!/7!) \\ 71273 &:= 3!! + (7! \times 2 - 1) \times 7 \\ 71993 &:= 3!! \times (9 + 91) - 7 \\ 72035 &:= 5 \times ((3! - 0!)!^2 + 7) \\ 72549 &:= 9! \times 4!/5! - 27 \\ 72559 &:= 9!/5 - 5 \times 2 - 7 \\ 72581 &:= (1 + 8)!/5 - 2 + 7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}72585 &:= (5 + 8!)/5 \times (2 + 7) \\73085 &:= 5^{8-(0/3)!} - 7! \\73088 &:= 8 \times (8^{0!+3} + 7!) \\73236 &:= (6 - 3!!) \times (2 - 3!!)/7 \\73296 &:= 6! + 9! \times 2/(3 + 7) \\73389 &:= -(9 + 8) \times (3!! + 3 - 7!) \\73433 &:= 3!! \times 34 \times 3 - 7 \\73435 &:= -5 + 3! \times (4! \times 3!! - 7!) \\73464 &:= 4! + 6 \times (4! \times 3!! - 7!) \\73597 &:= (7! + 9!)/5 + 3! + 7 \\73645 &:= (-5 + (-4 + 6!) \times 3!!)/7 \\73805 &:= 5^{-0!+8} + 3!! - 7! \\74064 &:= 4 \times (6! - 0!) \times 4! + 7! \\74164 &:= (4! \times 6! + 1) \times 4 + 7! \\74304 &:= -(4 - 0!)^{3!} + 4! \times 7! \\74348 &:= 8! + (4 + 3!!) \times 47 \\74385 &:= -5!/8 \times (3^4 - 7!) \\74431 &:= (1 + 3!)^4 \times (4! + 7) \\74688 &:= 8! - 8 \times (6! + 4! - 7!) \\74879 &:= (9! - 7 + 8! \times 4)/7 \\75243 &:= -3!! \times 4 - 2 + 5^7 \\75245 &:= -5 \times 4!^2 + 5^7 \\75344 &:= -4^4 + 3 \times 5 \times 7! \\75473 &:= (3 \times 7! - 4!) \times 5 - 7 \\75525 &:= 5 \times (-2 + 5) \times (-5 + 7!) \\75543 &:= 3 \times (-4! + 5 + 5 \times 7!) \\75565 &:= 5 \times ((6 + 5!) \times 5! - 7) \\75585 &:= (5 - 8) \times (5 - 5 \times 7!) \\75595 &:= -5 + (-9 + 5!/5) \times 7! \\75603 &:= 3 \times (0! + 6! \times 5 \times 7) \\75635 &:= (5 \times 3 \times 6! + 5) \times 7 \\75637 &:= (7! \times 3 + 6) \times 5 + 7 \\76356 &:= (-6 + 5!) \times (-3! + 6!) - 7! \\77378 &:= -8! + 7^{3!} + 7 \times 7 \\77559 &:= 9!/5 - 57 + 7! \\77609 &:= 9!/(-0! + 6) + 7! - 7 \\77634 &:= (4! - 3!) \times (-6! - 7 + 7!) \\78352 &:= (-2 + 5!) \times (3!! - 8 \times 7) \\78489 &:= (9 + 8)^4 + 8 - 7!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}79335 &:= 5 \times (3!! + 3 \times (9 + 7!)) \\79823 &:= -3!! + 2 \times 8! - 97 \\79947 &:= (7!/4 + 9) \times 9 \times 7 \\80352 &:= 2 \times (-5! - (3 + 0!)! + 8!) \\80402 &:= 2 \times (0! - (4 + 0!)! + 8!) \\80424 &:= 4! + 2 \times (-(4 + 0!)! + 8!) \\80448 &:= (8!/4 - 4!) \times (0 + 8) \\80479 &:= 9! - 7 \times (4! - 0! + 8!) \\80528 &:= 8 + 0 - 5! + 2 \times 8! \\80572 &:= 2 \times (-7 \times 5 + 0! + 8!) \\80582 &:= 2 \times 8! - 50 - 8 \\80592 &:= 2 \times (-(9 - 5)! + (0 + 8)!) \\80622 &:= 2 \times ((2 + 6)! - 0! - 8) \\80623 &:= -3 + 2 \times (-6 - 0! + 8!) \\80624 &:= -4 + 2 \times (-6 + 0 + 8!) \\80625 &:= -5 + 2 \times (-6 + 0! + 8!) \\80628 &:= 8! + 0 - 6 \times 2 + 8! \\80629 &:= -9 + 2 \times (-(6 \times 0)! + 8!) \\80632 &:= 2 \times (3 + 6 - 0!)! - 8 \\80634 &:= (4!/3)! - 6 + 08! \\80638 &:= 8! + 0 - 6/3 + 8! \\80639 &:= 9!/(3 + 6) - 0! + 8! \\80652 &:= 2 \times (5 + (6 \times 0)! + 8!) \\80662 &:= 2 \times (6 + 6 - 0! + 8!) \\80664 &:= 4! + (6/6 + 0!) \times 8! \\80682 &:= 2 \times 8! + 6 \times (-0! + 8) \\80688 &:= 8! + 8 \times 6 + 0 + 8! \\80752 &:= 2 \times (57 - 0! + 8!) \\80784 &:= (4! - 8) \times (7! + 0! + 8) \\80792 &:= (2 \times (9 + 7!) + 0!) \times 8 \\80802 &:= 2 \times (0! + 80 + 8!) \\80824 &:= 4! + 2 \times (80 + 8!) \\81355 &:= -5 + 5! \times 3!! - (-1 + 8)! \\81384 &:= 4! + 8! + 3!! + 1 \times 8! \\81542 &:= 2 \times (451 + 8!) \\82082 &:= 2 \times (8! + 0! + (-2 + 8)!) \\82086 &:= (6! + (8! - 0!)) \times 2 + 8 \\82368 &:= 8 \times 6^3 + 2 \times 8! \\82944 &:= 4^4 \times 9 + 2 \times 8! \\83157 &:= 7! + 5^{1+3!} - 8\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 83232 &:= 2 \times (3!^{-2+3!} + 8!) \\ 83304 &:= ((4+0!)! - 3) \times (3!! - 8) \\ 83349 &:= 9! \times (4! - 3)^3 / 8! \\ 83488 &:= 8! + 8! + 4 \times (3!! - 8) \\ 83523 &:= 3!! / 2 \times 5! + 3 + 8! \\ 83526 &:= 6! / 2 \times 5! + 3! + 8! \\ 83528 &:= (-8/2 + 5!) \times 3!! + 8 \\ 83534 &:= (-4! + 3!!) \times 5! + 3! + 8 \\ 84075 &:= 5 \times (7^{0!+4} + 8) \\ 84968 &:= -8 \times 6! + 9! / 4 + 8 \\ 85305 &:= (5! + 0!) \times (3!! - 5! / 8) \\ 85448 &:= (-8 + (4! / 4)!) \times 5! + 8 \\ 85568 &:= (-8 + 6!) \times 5! + 5! + 8 \\ 85573 &:= (3!! - 7) \times 5! + 5 + 8 \\ 85663 &:= -3^6 + 6! \times 5! - 8 \\ 85664 &:= -4! + (6! - 6) \times 5! + 8 \\ 85665 &:= 5! \times (6! - 6) - 5! / 8 \\ 85666 &:= -6 + (6! - 6) \times 5! - 8 \\ 85675 &:= -5 + 7! + 6! \times (5! - 8) \\ 85679 &:= 9 \times 7! - 6 + 5 + 8! \\ 85698 &:= 8! + (9! + 6! / 5) / 8 \\ 85705 &:= 5 \times (0! + 7!) \times 5 - 8! \\ 85739 &:= 9 \times (3! + 7!) + 5 + 8! \\ 85795 &:= 5! + 9 \times 7! - 5 + 8! \\ 86151 &:= -1 + (5! + 1) \times (6! - 8) \\ 86152 &:= (2 + 5! - 1) \times (6! - 8) \\ 86256 &:= 6^{(5-2)!} - 6! + 8! \\ 86332 &:= (2 + 3)! \times 3!! - 68 \\ 86335 &:= 5! \times 3!! + 3 - 68 \\ 86351 &:= -1 + 5! \times 3!! - 6 \times 8 \\ 86356 &:= 6! \times 5! - 36 - 8 \\ 86384 &:= -4! + (8 - 3)! \times 6! + 8 \\ 86386 &:= 6! \times (8 - 3)! - 6 - 8 \\ 86392 &:= (2 + 9/3)! \times 6! - 8 \\ 86395 &:= -5 + (9 + 3!) \times 6! \times 8 \\ 86397 &:= 7! \times 9 + (-3 + 6!) + 8! \\ 86402 &:= 2 \times (0! + 4 \times 6! + 8!) \\ 86404 &:= -4 + (0! + 4)! \times 6! + 8 \\ 86408 &:= ((8 \times 0)! + 4)! \times 6! + 8 \\ 86424 &:= 4! + 2 \times (4 \times 6! + 8!) \\ 86448 &:= ((8! + 4!) / 4 + 6!) \times 8 \\ 86456 &:= 6! \times 5! + 4 \times (6 + 8) \\ 86475 &:= 5 \times (7 + 4! \times 6! + 8) \\ 86506 &:= (6! + 0!) \times 5! - 6 - 8 \\ 86584 &:= 4! \times (8 + 5 \times 6!) - 8 \\ 86632 &:= (2 + 3!!) \times 6! / 6 - 8 \\ 86968 &:= -8 + 6^{(9-6)!} + 8! \\ 86976 &:= 6^7 / (9 - 6)! + 8! \\ 87368 &:= 8! / 6 \times (3! + 7) + 8 \\ 87384 &:= 4! + 8! / 3! \times 7 + 8! \\ 87976 &:= -6^7 + 9! + 7! - 8 \\ 88416 &:= 6^{1+4} + 8! + 8! \\ 89253 &:= (-3 + 5!^2) \times 9 - 8! \\ 90675 &:= (-5 + 7! + (6 + 0!)!) \times 9 \\ 90702 &:= 2 \times ((0 + 7)! - 0!) \times 9 \\ 90711 &:= ((1 + 1) \times 7! - 0!) \times 9 \\ 90732 &:= 2 \times (3! + 7! \times (-0 + 9)) \\ 90738 &:= (8 - 3!) \times (7! + 0!) \times 9 \\ 90747 &:= (7! + 4 + 7! - 0!) \times 9 \\ 91449 &:= 9! / 4 + (4 - 1)!! + 9 \\ 92364 &:= (-4 + 6!) \times ((3 + 2)! + 9) \\ 92525 &:= 5!^2 + 5^{-2+9} \\ 92672 &:= 2^7 \times 6! + 2^9 \\ 93303 &:= (3 - 0!) \times 3!^{3!} - 9 \\ 93312 &:= 2 \times 1 \times 3!^{-3+9} \\ 93321 &:= 1 \times 2 \times 3!^{3!} + 9 \\ 93325 &:= -5 + 2 \times (3!^{3!} + 9) \\ 93342 &:= 2 \times (4! + 3!^{3!} - 9) \\ 93366 &:= 6 \times (6^{3!} / 3 + 9) \\ 93591 &:= (1 + 9 + 5!) \times 3!! - 9 \\ 94976 &:= -6! - 7! + 9! - 4^9 \\ 95237 &:= (7 + 3!!) \times (2 + 5! + 9) \\ 95265 &:= (5^6 - (2 + 5)!) \times 9 \\ 95872 &:= 2 \times 7 \times 8^5 - 9! \\ 96336 &:= 6^{3!} + 3!! \times 69 \\ 96576 &:= 6 \times (7^5 - 6! + 9) \\ 96984 &:= 4! \times (8 \times 9! / 6! + 9) \\ 97792 &:= -2 \times 9! + 7^7 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 98425 &:= 5 \times (2 + (4!/8)^9) \\ 98503 &:= (3!! - 0!) \times (5! + 8 + 9) \\ 99369 &:= (9^{(6-3)!} + 9!)/9 \end{aligned}$$

• **Six Digits Numbers**

This subsection brings **factorial-type selfie numbers** in reverse order of digits. The numbers are with excess of brackets "(.)". These can be easily simplified.

$$\begin{aligned} 100785 &:= ((5 \times ((8! - 7) + 0!))/(0! + 1)) \\ 100798 &:= (8! - ((9!/(-7 + 0!)) + (0! + 1))) \\ 100802 &:= ((20 \times ((8 - 0!))!) + (0! + 1)) \\ 100805 &:= ((5 \times ((0! + 8!) + 0!))/(0! + 1)) \\ 100835 &:= (5 \times (3! + ((8!/(0! + 0!)) + 1))) \\ 102241 &:= ((142 \times (((2 + 0!))!)) + 1) \\ 102425 &:= ((5^2) \times ((4^{(2+0!)}) + 1)) \\ 102815 &:= (((51 \times 8!)/20) - 1) \\ 103344 &:= ((4! \times (4^{3!})) + ((3! + 01)!)) \\ 103392 &:= (((-(2 - 9)))! + (3^{3!})) \times (0! + 1)) \\ 103533 &:= (-3 + ((3!/(-5)) \times ((3! \times (-0!)) + 1))) \\ 103535 &:= (((5! \times 3!)/5) \times (3!! - 0!)) - 1) \\ 103536 &:= (((((6 - 3)!)/5) \times (3!! - 0!)) \\ 103537 &:= (((7!/35) \times (3!! - 0!)) + 1) \\ 103543 &:= (3! + (((4! + 5!) \times (3!! - 0!)) + 1)) \\ 103632 &:= ((-2 + (3! \times 6!)) \times ((3 + 01)!)) \\ 103643 &:= ((3! \times ((4! \times 6!) - 3!)) - 01) \\ 103646 &:= (((((6! \times 4!) - 6) \times 3!) + 0!) + 1) \\ 103648 &:= (-8 - (4! \times (((6! \times 3!) - 0!) \times (-1)))) \\ 103655 &:= (((5!/5) \times ((6! \times 3!) - 0!)) - 1) \\ 103656 &:= (((6!/5) \times 6!) - ((3 + 01)!)) \\ 103667 &:= (-7 + (-6 \times ((-6!) \times ((3 + 0!))!)) + 1)) \\ 103673 &:= ((3! \times (((7! + 6!) \times 3) - 0!)) - 1) \\ 103674 &:= ((4! \times (7! - 6!)) - ((3 \times 01)!)) \\ 103675 &:= (-5 + ((7! - 6!) \times ((3 + 01)!)) \\ 103678 &:= (((8!/7) \times (6 \times 3)) - 0!) - 1) \\ 103679 &:= (((9!/(-7)) \times (-6/3)) - 01) \\ 103681 &:= ((((-(1 - 8)))! - 6!) \times ((3 + 0!))! + 1) \\ 103683 &:= (3 \times (((8 \times 6!) \times 3!) + 01)) \\ 103686 &:= (-6 \times (((8 \times 6!) \times (-3)) - 01)) \\ 103689 &:= (9 \times (((8 \times 6!) \times (3 - 0!)) + 1)) \\ 103703 &:= (((3 + 0!))! \times ((7! - 3!!) + 0!)) - 1) \\ 103704 &:= (4! \times ((0! + 7!) - (((3 \times 01)!))!)) \\ 103705 &:= (((5 - 0!))! \times ((7! - 3!!) + 0!)) + 1) \\ 103728 &:= (((8/2)! \times ((7! - 3!!) + (0! + 1))) \\ 103799 &:= (((9! + 9!)/7) + ((3! - 0!))! - 1) \\ 103824 &:= ((4! \times (-2 - 8)) \times (3!! + 01)) \\ 103873 &:= -((((3!! - (7! + 8)) \times ((3 + 0!))! - 1)) \\ 103874 &:= ((4! \times ((7! + 8) - 3!!)) + (0! + 1)) \\ 104255 &:= ((5! + (5^2)) \times (((4 - 0!))! - 1)) \\ 104335 &:= (((5^{3!}) - 3!!) \times (((4 - 0!))! + 1)) \\ 104545 &:= (((5 + 4!) \times 5) \times (((4 - 0!))! + 1)) \\ 104664 &:= (4! \times ((6! \times 6) + (40 + 1))) \\ 104676 &:= (-6 \times (((-7 - 6!) \times 4!) + 0! + 1)) \\ 104831 &:= (((13 \times 8!)/(4 + 0!)) - 1) \\ 104833 &:= ((-3!) \times ((3!! + 8) \times (-4!)) + 01) \\ 104944 &:= ((4 \times 4) \times ((9^4) - 0!) - 1)) \\ 104976 &:= (((6^7) \times 9)/(4 \times 01)!)) \\ 104984 &:= ((4 + (8 \times 9^4)) \times (0! + 1)) \\ 105497 &:= (7 \times ((9!/4!) - ((50 - 1)))) \\ 105625 &:= ((5 + ((2^6) \times 5))^{0!+1}) \\ 105734 &:= (((4! - 3) \times (7! - 5)) - 01) \\ 105737 &:= (((7 \times 3) \times (7! + 5)) + (0! + 1)) \\ 105835 &:= (-5 + (3 \times (8! - (((5 + 0!) + 1)!))) \\ 105837 &:= (7! - ((3! - (8! \times 5))/(0! + 1))) \\ 105848 &:= (8! + (-(4 - (8^5))) \times (0! + 1)) \\ 105868 &:= (8! + ((6 + (8^5)) \times (0! + 1))) \\ 107163 &:= ((3^{6+1}) \times (7^{0!+1})) \\ 108535 &:= (((5^{3!}) - 5!) \times (8 - 01)) \\ 108656 &:= -((6! + (((5^6) \times (-8 + 0!)) - 1))) \\ 108936 &:= ((6! + (3 \times 9!))/(8 + 0!) + 1)) \\ 109357 &:= ((7 \times (5^{3!})) - (9 \times (0! + 1))) \\ 109438 &:= ((((-8!) - 3!!) \times (-4!))/9) - (0! + 1)) \\ 110592 &:= ((2 \times ((9 - 5))!^{0!+1+1}) \\ 110825 &:= ((-5 + (2 \times ((8 - 0!))!)) \times 11) \\ 110875 &:= (-5 - ((7! + ((8 - 0!))!)) \times (-11)) \\ 110878 &:= (8! - (((7! - 8!) + 0!) \times (1 + 1))) \end{aligned}$$

- 111744 := -(((4!^4) - (((7 + 1)!) × 11)))
112847 := (-((7^4)) × ((-8 × ((2 + 1)!) + 1))
113039 := (((9!/3) - 0!) - (3! × 11))
113542 := ((-2 + 4!) × ((5! + ((3! + 1)!) + 1))
113568 := ((-8 - 6!) × (-((5 × 31) + 1)))
114048 := (8 × (((4 - 0!)!^4) × 11))
114359 := ((953 × ((4 + 1)!) - 1)
114479 := (((-9 + (7 × 4!)) × (((4 - 1)!)!) - 1)
114725 := (((-52) + 7!) × (4! - 1)) + 1)
114794 := (((-49) + 7!) × (4! - 1)) + 1)
114827 := (((7! - (2^8)) × 4!) + 11)
114975 := (-5 × ((7! + 9!)/(-4¹⁺¹)))
115184 := -((4! + (8 × (-1 - (5!¹⁺¹))))
115186 := (-6 + (8 × (-1 + (5!¹⁺¹))))
115195 := (-5 + ((9 - 1) × (5!¹⁺¹)))
115202 := (2 × (0! + ((2 × 5!)¹⁺¹)))
115204 := (4 × (0! + (2 × (5!¹⁺¹))))
115208 := (8 × (((0 × 2)!) + (5!¹⁺¹)))
115224 := (4! + (2 × ((2 × 5!)¹⁺¹)))
115247 := (((7^4) × 2) × ((5 - 1)!) - 1)
115248 := (8 × ((4 + 2) + (5!¹⁺¹)))
115437 := (((7! + 3) - 4!) × (((5 - 1)!) - 1))
115584 := ((4! × 8) × ((5! × 5) + (1 + 1)))
115782 := (((2 - 8) + 7!) × (((5 - 1)!) - 1))
115805 := ((5 - (-((0! - 8)!)!) × (-(((5 - 1)!) - 1)))
115893 := ((3 × (-9 + 8!)) - (((5 + 1) + 1)!)
115897 := ((7! - (9 - 8)) × (((5 - 1)!) - 1))
115995 := ((5! - 9) × (95 × 11))
116343 := ((3 + 4!) × ((3! × 6!) - 11))
116469 := (9 × (((-6 + 4!) × (6! - 1)) - 1))
116629 := (((9^2) × (6! + 6!)) - 11)
116638 := ((8! × 3) - ((6! × 6) + (1 + 1)))
116639 := (((-((9 × 3)) × 6!) × (-6)) - (1 × 1))
116647 := ((7! × 4!) - ((6 × (6! - 1)) - 1))
116649 := (9 × (((4! - 6) × 6!) + (1 × 1)))
116739 := (9 × ((3 × (7! - 6!)) + 11))
116864 := (-((4^6)) - (8! × (-6/(1 + 1))))
116937 := (((7^3!) + 9) - 6!) - (1 × 1))
116964 := (((4! - 6) × 9) × (6! + (1 + 1)))
117537 := (((7^3!) - 5!) + ((7 + 1) × 1))
117625 := (((5 + 2)^6) - (-((7 - 11)!)!)
117631 := (((1 + 3!)^6) - (7 + 11))
117637 := ((7^3!) - (((6 + 7) - 1) × 1))
117647 := ((7⁴⁺⁶⁻⁷)! - (1 + 1))
117667 := (((7!/6!)^6) + (7 + 11))
117673 := (3! + (((7^6) + 7) + 11))
117674 := ((4! + ((7^6))) + ((7 × (1 - 1)!)!)
117737 := ((7^3!) + (77 + 11))
117744 := ((4! × 4) + (((7⁷⁻¹) - 1)))
117745 := ((5! - 4!) + ((7^{7×1-1})))
117759 := ((-9 + 5!) + (((7⁷⁻¹) - 1)))
117775 := (5! + (7 + ((7⁷⁻¹) - 1)))
118162 := (((-2 × 6!) - 1) × (-81 + 1))
118326 := (((6! × (-2)) - 3) × (-81 + 1))
118373 := (3!! + (((7^3!) + (8/(1 + 1))))
118376 := (6! - (((7^3!) + 8) × (-1) + 1))
118464 := (((4^6) × 4!) + (8!/(1 + 1)))
118773 := (-((3^7)) + (7! × ((8/(1 + 1)!)!)
118803 := (3 × ((0! + 8!) - (((8 - 1) - 1)!)!)
119379 := (((9! - 7!)/3) + ((9 × 11)))
120238 := (((8! × 3) - 2) - (((02 + 1)!)!)
120239 := (((9!/3) - ((2 × 0)!) - (((2 + 1)!)!)
120243 := ((3 × (((4 × 2)!) + 0!)) - (((2 + 1)!)!)
120383 := ((3 × 8!) - (((3 + 0!)!^2) + 1))
120384 := (4! × (-((8 × 3) + ((0! + ((2 + 1)!)!)!)
120504 := (4! × 05021)
120578 := (8! - 7 - 5!) × (0! + 2) - 1
120583 := -((((3! - 8!) + 5!) × (0! + 2)) - 1))
120585 := (((5 - 8!) + 5!) × ((0 - 2) - 1))
120599 := (((9!/9) - 5!) × (0! + 2)) - 1
120624 := ((4! × (-2 + 6!)) × (0! + ((2 + 1)!)!)
120679 := (((9! + (7!/(-6)))/(0! + 2)) - 1)
120719 := ((((-9!) + (-((1 - 7)!)!)/(-((0! + 2)))) - 1)
120744 := (4! × (((-4 + 7!) + 0!) - ((2 + 1)!)!)
120768 := ((8! + ((6 - 70))) × (2 + 1))
120774 := ((4! × ((7! - 7) - 0!)) + ((2 + 1)!)
120792 := (((2 - 9) + 7!) × ((0! + (2 + 1)!)!)
120798 := ((8! + (9 × (-7 + 0!))) × (2 + 1))
120813 := (((3!! - 1) × 8) + 0!) × 21
120816 := ((-6 + (-((1 - 8)!)!) × ((0! + (2 + 1)!)!)
120834 := (((43 - 8!) - 0!) × (-2 + 1))
120835 := (-((5^3)) - (8! × ((0 - 2) - 1)))

$$\begin{aligned} 120837 &:= (((7 \times 3!) - 8!) - 0!) \times (-2 + 1)) \\ 120839 &:= (((9!/3) - ((8 - 0!) - 2)!) - 1) \\ 120841 &:= -((((1 + 4)!) - ((8! \times (0! + 2)) + 1))) \\ 120845 &:= -(((5! - 4) - ((8! \times (0! + 2)) + 1))) \\ 120849 &:= (((9 \times 4) - 8!) + 0!) \times (-2 + 1)) \\ 120855 &:= (5! - ((5 + 8!) \times (0! + 2))) \times (-1) \\ 120864 &:= (4! \times ((-6 + ((8 - 0!)!) + (2 \times 1))) \\ 120873 &:= (3 \times (((-7 + 8!) - 0!) - (21))) \\ 120874 &:= (((4! \times 7!) - (80)) - ((2 + 1)!)) \\ 120883 &:= ((3 \times 8!) - ((80 - 2) - 1)) \\ 120889 &:= -((9 \times 8) + ((8! \times (0! + 2)) + 1)) \\ 120897 &:= -((7 \times 9) - (8! \times ((0 - 2) - 1))) \\ 120923 &:= -(((3!^2) - ((9!/(0! + 2)) - 1))) \\ 120924 &:= (((4!/2) - ((9 - 0!)!) \times (-2 + 1)) \\ 120928 &:= (((8! - (2 + 9)) \times (0! + 2)) + 1) \\ 120929 &:= (((-92) + 9!) - 0!)/(2 + 1) \\ 120932 &:= (((((2^3)!) - 9) \times (0! + 2)) - 1) \\ 120933 &:= -((3^3) - (9!/(0 - 2) - 1)) \\ 120934 &:= ((4! + ((3! - 9!)/(0! + 2))) \times (-1)) \\ 120936 &:= (-6 - ((-3!) + ((9 - 0!)!) \times (-2 + 1))) \\ 120937 &:= -((((7 - 3)!) - ((9!/(0! + 2)) + 1)) \\ 120938 &:= 8! \times 3 - (9 \times 0!) - 21 \\ 120939 &:= ((9!/3) - ((9 \times 0) + 21)) \\ 120942 &:= (((2 + 4) - ((9 - 0!)!) \times (-2 + 1)) \\ 120943 &:= ((3! - 4!) + ((9!/(0! + 2)) + 1)) \\ 120944 &:= (((4! + 4!) - 9!)/(0 - 2) - 1) \\ 120945 &:= (((5!/4!) - ((9 - 0!)!) \times (-2 + 1)) \\ 120946 &:= (-6 - ((4! - 9!)/(0 + 2))) \\ 120947 &:= 7! \times 4! + 9 - 0! - 21 \\ 120948 &:= (8! - 4) \times (9 \times 0 + 2 + 1) \\ 120949 &:= (((-9 - 4!) + 9!)/(0 + 2)) \\ 120952 &:= (((-(25) + 9!) + 0!)/(2 + 1)) \\ 120953 &:= -((3 + 5) + ((9!/(0! + 2)) + 1)) \\ 120954 &:= (((4! - 5) - 9!) - 0!)/(-2 + 1)) \\ 120955 &:= (-5 + (((5 - 9)!) \times ((0! + ((2 + 1)!)!))) \\ 120956 &:= (((-(6 + 5) + 9!) - 0!)/(2 + 1)) \\ 120957 &:= (((-(7 + 5) + 9!)/(0! + 2)) + 1) \\ 120958 &:= (((8 - 5)!) - 9!)/((0 - 2) - 1) \\ 120959 &:= (((9! + ((5 - 9))) + 0!)/(2 + 1)) \\ 120972 &:= (2 \times (7 - ((-9!)/((0! + 2)!) + 1))) \\ 120973 &:= ((3! + 7) - (9!/(0 - 2) - 1)) \\ 120974 &:= (((4! \times 7!) + 9) - 0!) + ((2 + 1)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 120975 &:= ((5 - (7! \times (-9 + 0!))) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 120978 &:= (((8! + 7) - ((9 \times 0)!) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 120981 &:= (((1 - 8!) - 9) + 0!) \times (-2 + 1)) \\ 120982 &:= (-2 - (((8! + 9) - 0!) \times (-2 + 1))) \\ 120983 &:= ((3 \times (8! + 9)) - (0! + (2 + 1))) \\ 120984 &:= (4! - (8! \times (((9 \times 0) - 2) - 1))) \\ 120985 &:= (-5 - (((8! + 9) + 0!) \times (-2 + 1))) \\ 120986 &:= (((-6 \times (8! + 9))/(0 - 2)) - 1) \\ 120987 &:= (((7! \times (-8)) - 9) \times ((0 - 2) - 1)) \\ 121068 &:= ((8! + (6^{0!+1})) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 121083 &:= ((3 \times (8! + 0!)) + ((-1 + ((2 + 1)!)!)) \\ 121086 &:= (6 \times ((8!/(0! + 1)) + (21))) \\ 121128 &:= (8 \times (((((2 + 1)!)! + 1) \times 21)) \\ 121323 &:= (3 \times (((2^3)!) + (121))) \\ 121338 &:= (((-(8! + 3!)) - ((3! - 1)!) \times (-2 + 1)) \\ 121383 &:= (3 \times ((8! + ((3! - 1)!) + (21))) \\ 121487 &:= (((7! - 8) \times 4!) - 1) + (((2 + 1)!)!) \\ 121674 &:= (((4! \times 7!) + 6!) - (((1 \times 2) + 1)!) \\ 121683 &:= (((3 \times 8!) + 6!) + ((1 \times 2) + 1)) \\ 121704 &:= ((4! \times (0! + 7!)) + (((1 \times 2) + 1)!) \\ 121728 &:= ((8! + (2^{7+1})) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 121799 &:= (((9! + 9!) + 7!)/((1 + 2)!) - 1) \\ 122286 &:= (-6 \times ((8!/(0 - 2)) - (221))) \\ 122385 &:= (((5 - 8!) \times (-3)) + (2 \times (((2 + 1)!)!)) \\ 122395 &:= ((-5 - (9!/(0 - 3))) + (2 \times (((2 + 1)!)!)) \\ 122396 &:= ((6! + ((9!/(3!)) - 2)) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 122677 &:= ((7! + ((7^6))) - (2 \times ((2 + 1)!) \\ 122968 &:= ((-8 - (6! \times (-9))) \times (-2 - 21)) \\ 123048 &:= (((8! - 4!) + ((03)!)!) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 123117 &:= (((-(7 + 1)!) - 1) - 3!) \times (-2 + 1)) \\ 123123 &:= (((((3! + 2)!) + 1) + 3!) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 123137 &:= -((7^3) \times (((-1 \times 3!) / 2) + 1)) \\ 123138 &:= (((8! + 3!) - 1) \times 3) + (21) \\ 123183 &:= (3 \times ((8! + ((1 \times 3)!)!) + (21))) \\ 123264 &:= ((4! - (6!/(0 - 2))) \times 321) \\ 123392 &:= ((2^9) \times ((-3 - 3!)/(-2 + 1))) \\ 123487 &:= (-7 \times (((8! - ((4 + 3)!) / (-2)) - 1)) \\ 123648 &:= 8! \times 46 / (-3! + 21) \\ 123668 &:= (-86) \times ((-6!) - 3!) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 123744 &:= (4! \times ((-4 + 7!) + (((3 + 2) \times 1)!) \\ 123745 &:= (((5! - 4) + 7!) \times ((3! - 2)!) + 1) \\ 123833 &:= (3! - ((3 \times ((-8!) - 3!) + 2)) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

- 123834** := $((4 \times 3!) + ((8! \times 3) - ((2 + 1)!))$
123835 := $(-5 - (((3! + 8!) \times (-3)) - (((2 + 1)!)!))$
123837 := $(7! - (-3 \times ((8! - ((3 \times 2)!)) - 1))$
123839 := $((9!/3) + (((8 \times 3!)/2) - 1))$
123843 := $((3! \times 4) + ((8! \times 3) + (2 + 1)))$
123846 := $((6! \times 4) + ((8! \times 3) + ((2 + 1)!))$
123848 := $(- (8!) + (-4 \times ((- (8!) - 3!) - (2 \times 1))))$
123858 := $((((8 \times 5!) + 8!) + 3!) \times (2 + 1))$
123864 := $((4! - ((6! + 8!) \times (-3))) + (((2 + 1)!)!)$
123983 := $((3 \times 8!) + ((9! / ((3 + 2)!)) - 1))$
124344 := $(4! \times (-4 + (((3 \times 4!)^2) + 1)))$
124368 := $((8 \times 6) \times (((3!^4) \times 2) - 1))$
124373 := $((3! \times (-7 + ((3! \times 4!)^2))) - 1)$
124383 := $(3 \times ((8! + 3!) + (421)))$
124389 := $((9!/8!) \times (-3 + (4!^{2+1}))$
124437 := $((7! + (3! \times 4!)) \times 4!) + (21)$
124464 := $(4! \times (((6^4) \times 4) + 2) \times 1)$
124469 := $((9 \times (6 + (4! \times (4!^2)))) - 1)$
124479 := $(9 \times (7 + (4!^{4-2+1})))$
124489 := $((9 \times (8 + (4! \times (4!^2)))) + 1)$
124535 := $(5! - (((3!^5) \times (-4^2))) + 1)$
124848 := $((8! + (((4!/8)!^4)) \times (2 + 1))$
125008 := $(8 \times (0! + (05^{(2+1)!}))$
125048 := $(8 \times (((4 - 0!)! + ((5^{(2+1)!}))))$
125275 := $((-5 - (7! \times (-25))) - (((2 + 1)!)!)$
125315 := $((-((5 + 1)) - (-3 \times 5!))^2) - 1)$
125316 := $((-6 - (-((1 \times 3)) \times 5!))^{2 \times 1})$
125317 := $((-((7 - 1)) - (-3 \times 5!))^2) + 1)$
125425 := $(-((5^2)) \times ((4! - ((5 + 2)!)) - 1))$
125688 := $(8 \times (86 + (5^{(2+1)!})))$
125725 := $((5^2) \times (7! - ((5 \times 2) + 1)))$
125744 := $(-((4^4)) - (7! \times (-((5^2) \times 1))))$
125755 := $((5! - ((-5 + 7!) \times (5^2))) \times (-1))$
125785 := $(-5 \times (((-8 + 7!) \times (-5)) + (2 + 1)))$
125825 := $(-((5^2)) \times ((8 - ((5 + 2)!)) - 1))$
125875 := $((-5 + 7!) \times (((8 + 5) \times 2) - 1))$
125957 := $((((7! \times 5) - 9) \times 5) + (2 \times 1))$
125975 := $((5^{-7+9}) \times (((5 + 2)! - 1))$
125997 := $(7! - ((9 - 9!) / ((5 - 2) \times 1)))$
126025 := $((5^2) \times (0! + (((6 + 2) - 1)!))$
126026 := $(((((6!/2) + 0!) - 6)^2) + 1)$
126035 := $((5 \times 3!) + 0!) \times ((6^2) - 1)$
126047 := $(7! + ((4! \times (((0! + 6)! + 2)) - 1))$
126055 := $(-5 \times ((-5 \times (((0! + 6)! + 2)) - 1))$
126147 := $(7 \times (((4! + 1) \times 6!) + (21)))$
126358 := $(8! - ((5! \times (3 - 6!)) + (2 \times 1)))$
126359 := $(((-9 - (5! \times (-3))) \times (6!/2)) - 1)$
126475 := $(((-5 + 7!) + 4!) \times (((6 - 2)! + 1))$
126658 := $8! + 5! \times 6! - 62 \times 1$
126714 := $((((4! + 1) \times 7!) + 6!) - ((2 + 1)!)$
126715 := $(-5 - (- (176) \times (((2 + 1)!)!))$
126722 := $((22 \times (7! + 6!)) + (2 \times 1))$
126742 := $((-2 + 4!) \times ((7! + 6!) + (2 - 1)))$
126744 := $(4! + (4! \times (7! - (6! / (- (2 + 1))))))$
126808 := $((80 + 8) \times ((6! \times 2) + 1))$
127029 := $((9! / (-20)) \times (-7)) + (21)$
127439 := $((9 \times 3!) + ((4! \times 7!) - (2 - 1)))$
127449 := $((9^4) + (4! \times (7! - (2 + 1))))$
127584 := $((4! + 8!) - (5! \times (-7 - (((2 + 1)!)!)))$
127675 := $(-5 - ((76 \times 7!) / (- (2 + 1))))$
127723 := $(-(((3! + (-2 \times 7!)) - (7^{(2+1)!})))$
127727 := $((7! - 2) + 7!) + (7^{(2+1)!})$
127729 := $((((9 - 2)! + 7!) + (7^{(2+1)!})))$
127737 := $((7^3!) + 7) + ((7! \times 2) + 1)$
127795 := $(-5 \times (((9! - 7!) / (- (7 \times 2))) + 1))$
127824 := $((4! \times ((2^8) + 7!)) + (((2 + 1)!)!)$
127953 := $((((3 - 5!) \times 9) - 7!) \times (-21))$
128163 := $((((3! \times 61) - 8)^2) - 1)$
128485 := $((5^8) + 4) - (8^{(2+1)!})$
129024 := $(4! \times ((2^{-0!+9}) \times 21))$
129258 := $(8! - ((5! + 2) \times (- (9^{2+1}))))$
129546 := $(((((6!/4) \times 5!) - 9) \times ((2 + 1)!))$
129555 := $((5! \times 5!) - 5) \times (9 \times (2 - 1))$
129564 := $((4! - (6! \times 5!)) \times (-9)) / ((2 + 1)!)$
129594 := $((-((4 - 9)))! \times (5! \times 9)) - ((2 + 1)!)$
129595 := $(-5 \times ((9! / (- (5 + 9))) + (2 - 1)))$
129599 := $((9 \times (((9 \times 5) / 9)!^2)) - 1)$
129602 := $(((-20) \times 6!) \times (-9)) + (2 \times 1)$
129606 := $(6 \times (0! - (6! \times (- (9 + 21))))$
129609 := $(9 \times (((- (0!)) + (- ((6 - 9)!))!^2) + 1))$
129636 := $(6 \times (3! - (6! \times (- (9 + 21))))$

- 129645 := $(-5 \times ((-4 \times ((6! \times 9) + 2)) - 1))$
129655 := $((((5! \times 5!) + 6) \times 9) + (2 - 1))$
130321 := $((((1 + 2) \times 3!) + 0!)^{3+1})$
130322 := $((22 - 3)^{0!+3} + 1)$
130345 := $(((-5 + 4!)^{3+0!}) + ((3 + 1)!))$
130355 := $(-5 \times (((-5!) - 3!!) - 0!) \times 31)$
130442 := $((2 + 4!) \times (-((4! - 0!)) + ((3! + 1)!))$
130599 := $(9 \times (-9 + ((5! + 0!) \times ((3! - 1)!)))$
131014 := $((4! + 1) + 0!) \times (-1 + ((3! + 1)!))$
131027 := $((7! \times (-2)) + 0!) \times (-13 \times 1))$
131039 := $((9 \times 3 - 0!) \times ((1 + 3!)!) - 1)$
131068 := $((8^6)/(0! + 1)) - (3 + 1)$
131074 := $((4^{7+0!}) + 1) \times (3 - 1)$
131762 := $((26 \times 7!) + 1) + 3!! + 1)$
131792 := $(2^{9+7+1}) + (((3 \times 1)!))!$
132293 := $(-3 + (92 \times 2) \times (3!! - 1))$
132336 := $((6^{3!}) + (3!! \times ((2 + 3)! - 1)))$
132481 := $(184 \times ((2 \times 3)!)) + 1)$
132488 := $(8! - (8 \times ((-((4^2)) \times 3!!) - 1)))$
132608 := $(8! + ((0! + 6!) \times (2^{3!+1})))$
132664 := $((46 \times (6 - 2)) \times (3!! + 1))$
132848 := $((8 \times 4!) - 8) \times (2 + (((3 \times 1)!))!)$
133055 := $(5! \times ((5 + 0!)!) + ((3!^{3!}) - 1))$
133056 := $6! \times 5! + 03!^{3!} \times 1$
133057 := $((-(((7 + 5)!/(0! - 3!)))/3!! + 1)$
133176 := $((6! - 7!) + ((1 + 3!)!) \times (-31))$
133236 := $(-6!) + (((3!!/2) + (3!))^{3-1})$
133248 := $((-((8^4)) - ((2^3)!)) \times (-3 \times 1))$
133269 := $(9 - ((6! - 2) \times 3!)) \times (-31)$
133331 := $((-1 + ((3 - 3!!) \times (-3!))) \times 31)$
133344 := $(-((4! \times 4!)) + (3!! \times (3! \times 31)))$
133362 := $((-2 \times 6!) + 3!) \times (-3 \times 31))$
133476 := $(-6 \times (74 - (3!! \times 31)))$
133536 := $((6^{3!}) - (5! \times ((-3 - 3!!) - 1)))$
133559 := $((9 \times 5!) \times (5! + 3)) + 3!! - 1)$
133628 := $(8! - (-2 \times ((6^{3!}) - (3 - 1))))$
133632 := $((2^3)! + ((6^{3!}) \times (3 - 1)))$
133638 := $(8! + (((3!^6) + 3) \times (3 - 1)))$
133655 := $(5! \times (5 + 6!)) + ((3!^{3!}) - 1)$
133672 := $((2 - 7!) + 6!) + 3! \times (-31)$
133703 := $((3!! + (0! - 7!) + 3!)) \times (-31)$
133732 := $(-2 + ((-((3! - 7!)) - 3!!) \times 31))$
133734 := $((4 \times 3!) + 7) \times 3! \times (3!! - 1)$
133765 := $((5 - (6! \times 7)) + 3!!) \times (-31)$
133776 := $(-6 \times (-7!) - ((7 - 3)! \times (3!! - 1)))$
133827 := $((7! - (-((2 - 8)!)) - 3) \times 31)$
133836 := $(-6 \times ((3! + 8) - (3!! \times 31)))$
133839 := $(9 \times 3) \times (-83 + ((3! + 1)!))$
133847 := $((7! - 4!) + 8!) - 3!! \times 3 - 1)$
133866 := $(-6 + (-6 \times (8 - (3!! \times 31))))$
133893 := $(3 \times ((9!/8) - (3^{(3 \times 1)!})))$
133896 := $((6! - (9!/8)) \times (-3)) - ((3 + 1)!)$
133897 := $((7! \times 9 - 8) - 3!!) \times 3 + 1)$
133919 := $((9!/(-1 - 9)) - 3!!) \times 3 - 1)$
133921 := $((1 \times 2) \times 93) \times 3!! + 1)$
133932 := $(2 \times ((3!! \times 93) + ((3 \times 1)!))$
133956 := $((6! - (59 \times 3!))^{3-1})$
133967 := $(-7 + (-6 \times (-9 - (3!! \times 31))))$
133974 := $((-((4 - 7)!)) \times (9 + (3!! \times 31)))$
134075 := $((5 + 7!) - ((-((0! - 4)!))!) \times 31)$
134106 := $((6! + 0!) \times (-((1 - 4)!)) \times 31)$
134137 := $((-7 - (3!! \times (-((1 - 4)!))) \times (-31))$
134168 := $((-8 - (6! \times (-((1 - 4)!))) \times (-31))$
134376 := $((6! \times 7!)/(3 + 4!)) - ((3 + 1)!)$
134385 := $(-5 \times (((8!/3!) \times (-4)) + (3 \times 1)))$
134389 := $((9! + 8!)/3) - ((4 \times 3) - 1)$
134395 := $(-5 \times ((9!/(-3^4)) \times 3!) + 1)$
134398 := $((8! + 9!)/3) - ((4 - 3) + 1)$
134399 := $((9! + ((9 + 3) - 4)!)/3) - 1)$
134485 := $(-5 \times (((8! + 4!) \times (-4))/3) - 1)$
134575 := $(5! + (((-((7^5)) \times 4!)/(-3)) - 1))$
134634 := $((-4!) - (3!! \times (-6!)))/4 + ((3! + 1)!)$
134635 := $(-5 + (3!! \times ((6!/4) + 3!) + 1))$
134637 := $(7! - (3!! \times (6!/(-4))) + (3 \times 1))$
134638 := $((-8 - (3!! \times (-6!)))/4 + ((3! + 1)!)$
134641 := $((1 - ((4! + 6!)/(-4))) \times 3!! + 1)$
134662 := $(-2 + (((6! \times (-6)) - 4!) \times (-31)))$
134664 := $((-4 - 6!) \times ((6!/(-4)) - ((3 \times 1)!))$
134665 := $((5! + 66) \times (4 + 3!!)) + 1)$
134726 := $((6! - 2) - 7!) - 4! \times (-31)$
134783 := $((3 \times 8) \times 7!) + ((4!^3) - 1)$
134784 := $((48 - 7!) \times (4 - 31))$
134827 := $((-((7 - 2)) - (-8 \times 4!)) \times (3!! + 1))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 134847 &:= (((7 \times 4) \times ((8^4) + 3!!)) - 1) \\
 134937 &:= (((7^3!) + 9) - ((-4!) \times 3!!) + 1) \\
 134995 &:= (-5 + (9 \times ((9!/4!) - ((3! - 1)!!))) \\
 135036 &:= ((6 \times 3!) \times ((0! + 5!) \times 31)) \\
 135168 &:= (((8 \times (6! - 1)) - 5!) \times ((3 + 1)!) \\
 135243 &:= ((3 + 4!) \times (((2 + 5)!) - (31))) \\
 135348 &:= (8! - 4) \times 3 + 5^{3-1} \\
 135359 &:= (((9! + ((5! \times 3) \times 5!))/3) - 1) \\
 135364 &:= (-4 \times ((6! \times (3! - (53))) - 1)) \\
 135384 &:= ((4! - (8! \times (-3))) + (5^{3-1})) \\
 135576 &:= (((6 \times 7!) \times 5) - ((5^3!) - 1)) \\
 135718 &:= (((((8! - 1) + 7!) - 5!) \times 3) + 1) \\
 135719 &:= (((9!/(1 + 7)) - 5!) \times 3) - 1) \\
 135738 &:= (((8! + 3!) + 7!) - 5!) \times (3 \times 1) \\
 135879 &:= ((9 \times (7! - 8)) + 5) \times (3 \times 1) \\
 135955 &:= (-5 + (5! \times ((9 \times (5! + 3!)) - 1))) \\
 135963 &:= (3 \times (6 + (9 \times (-5 + ((3! + 1)!!)))) \\
 135966 &:= (((-6 \times (6! - 9)) - 5!) \times (-31)) \\
 135972 &:= (27 \times (-((9 - 5) + ((3! + 1)!!))) \\
 135975 &:= ((5! + (((7! \times (-9)) - 5) \times 3)) \times (-1)) \\
 135995 &:= (59 \times (((9!/5!) - 3!!) + 1)) \\
 135999 &:= (9 \times (-9 + ((9!/5!) \times (3! - 1)))) \\
 136078 &:= (((8! + 7!) - 0!) \times (6 - 3)) + 1) \\
 136095 &:= ((5 + (9 \times ((0! + 6)!!)) \times (3 \times 1)) \\
 136097 &:= (((7! \times 9) - (0 - 6)) \times 3) - 1) \\
 136099 &:= (((9!/(9 - 0!)) + 6) \times 3) + 1) \\
 136112 &:= ((2^{1+16}) + ((3! + 1)!) \\
 136134 &:= ((4! + 3) \times (((1 + 6)!) + (3 - 1))) \\
 136269 &:= ((9 + (6!/(-2 - 6))) \times (3!! + 1)) \\
 136365 &:= ((-5 \times 6!) + (3 \times ((6^3!) - 1))) \\
 136464 &:= (4! \times (646 + ((3! + 1)!!)) \\
 136565 &:= ((5 - 6!) \times (-5 + (6 \times 31))) \\
 136583 &:= ((3 \times 8!) + (((5^6) - 3) + 1)) \\
 136655 &:= (((5! + 5) \times 6!) + ((6^3!) - 1)) \\
 136783 &:= (3!! + (((8! + 7!) - 6) \times 3) + 1) \\
 136793 &:= (((((3 \times 9) \times 7!) + 6!) - 3!) - 1) \\
 136799 &:= (((9!/(9 + 7)) \times 6) + 3!!) - 1) \\
 136801 &:= ((10 \times ((8! + 6!)/3)) + 1) \\
 136835 &:= (-5 \times (((-38) \times 6!) - 3!) - 1) \\
 136857 &:= (((7^5) \times (8! + 6!))/((3! + 1)!) \\
 137159 &:= ((9 \times (5! + ((-1 \times 7!) \times (-3)))) - 1) \\
 137169 &:= (9 \times (((6 - 1)!) - ((7! \times (-3)) - 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 137257 &:= (((7^{5+2}) - 7)/3!) + 1) \\
 137333 &:= (((3^3)^3) + ((7^3!) + 1)) \\
 137344 &:= ((4^{4+3}) + (7! \times ((3 + 1)!!)) \\
 137377 &:= (((((7^7) + 3!!) - 7)/3!) + 1) \\
 137385 &:= (-5 \times (8! - ((3^7) \times 31))) \\
 137493 &:= (((3^9) - 4!) \times 7) - ((3! - 1)!) \\
 137496 &:= -((((-(6 - 9))!)! + (4! \times ((-7!) - 3!!) + 1))) \\
 137542 &:= (-2 + (4! \times 5731)) \\
 137544 &:= (4! \times (-((4! + 5) - 7!)) + (((3 \times 1)!)!)) \\
 137648 &:= 8 \times (4! \times 6! - 73 - 1) \\
 137664 &:= (((-((4 \times 6)) + 6!) + 7!) \times ((3 + 1)!) \\
 137736 &:= (((6! - ((3 \times 7))) + 7!) \times ((3 + 1)!) \\
 137744 &:= (-4 \times (4 - (-7 \times (-7!) + ((3! - 1)!!))) \\
 137752 &:= ((-2 + ((5! - 7!) \times (-7))) \times (3 + 1)) \\
 137754 &:= ((-4 \times ((5! - 7!) \times 7)) - ((3 \times 1)!) \\
 137755 &:= (-5 + ((5! - 7!) \times (-7 \times (3 + 1)))) \\
 137759 &:= (((9! + (5 \times (7! + 7!)))/3) - 1) \\
 137767 &:= (((7^6)/7) + (7! \times ((3 + 1)!!)) \\
 137774 &:= (((4! \times 7!) + 7) + (7^{3-1})) \\
 137780 &:= (-1 + (((3^7) \times 7!)/80)) \\
 137793 &:= (((((3^9) \times 7) + 7) + 3!) - 1) \\
 137952 &:= ((2^5) \times ((-9 + 7!) - (((3 \times 1)!)!)) \\
 137979 &:= (9 \times (((7! + 9!)/(7 - 3)!) + 1)) \\
 137984 &:= ((4 \times 8) \times (((-9 + 7!) - 3!!) + 1)) \\
 137994 &:= (4! + (9 \times ((9! + 7!)/((3 + 1)!!))) \\
 137996 &:= (((6! - (9 \times (9 - 7!))) \times 3) - 1) \\
 138024 &:= (4! \times ((-2 + 0!) + (8 \times (3!! - 1)))) \\
 138039 &:= (-9 + ((3!! - 0!) \times (8 \times ((3 + 1)!!))) \\
 138044 &:= (-4 - ((4! \times (0 - 8)) \times (3!! - 1))) \\
 138048 &:= ((-8 \times 4!) \times (0! - (((8 - 3) + 1)!!)) \\
 138144 &:= (4! \times (-4 + (((1 \times 8)!) / (3! + 1)))) \\
 138145 &:= (-5!) + ((4! \times (1 + (8 \times 3!))) + 1) \\
 138216 &:= (((6 \times 1) - 2)! \times ((8 \times 3!!) - 1)) \\
 138233 &:= (((3!! \times ((3! - 2)!) \times 8) - (3! + 1)) \\
 138234 &:= (((4!^3) \times (2 + 8)) - ((3 \times 1)!) \\
 138235 &:= (-5 + (((3 \times 2)!) \times 8) \times ((3 + 1)!!)) \\
 138236 &:= (((-6!) \times ((3! - 2)!) \times (-8)) - (3 + 1)) \\
 138239 &:= (((((9 + 3) \times 2) \times 8) \times 3!!) - 1) \\
 138262 &:= (-2 + (((6 - 2)!) \times ((8 \times 3!!) + 1))) \\
 138264 &:= (4! \times ((6! + (((2 + 8) - 3)!) + 1)) \\
 138312 &:= (((-((2 + 1)) - (3!! \times 8)) \times (-((3 + 1)!!)) \\
 138313 &:= (((3 + 1)!) \times ((3!! \times 8) + 3)) + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

- 138336** := (((6! × 3!) + 3) × (8 × (3 + 1)))
138354 := ((4! × (5 + (3!! × 8))) - ((3 × 1)!))
138355 := ((5! - 5) - (3!! × (-8 × ((3 + 1)!)))
138364 := (-4 × (((6! × 3!) × (-8)) - (31)))
138383 := (((3!! × (-8)) - (3!)) × (-8 × 3)) - 1)
138384 := ((-((4 - 8)))! × (3! + (8!/(3! + 1))))
138423 := (-((3²)) + ((4! × 8) × (3!! + 1)))
138424 := (-((4 × 2)) + ((4! × 8) × (3!! + 1)))
138425 := (-((5 + 2)) + ((4! × 8) × (3!! + 1)))
138426 := (-6 + ((24 × 8) × (3!! + 1)))
138427 := (-((7 - 2)) + ((4! × 8) × (3!! + 1)))
138428 := (-((8/2)) + ((4! × 8) × (3!! + 1)))
138431 := (((-1 - 3!!) × (-((4 × 8)) × 3!)) - 1)
138432 := (((2 × 3!!) × 4) + 8) × ((3 + 1)!)
138433 := ((3/3) + ((4! × 8) × (3!! + 1)))
138434 := ((((-4!) × 3!!) - 4!) × (-8)) + (3 - 1))
138448 := ((-8 + 4!) + ((4! × 8) × (3!! + 1)))
138546 := (-6 + (4! × (5 + (8 × (3!! + 1))))))
138607 := (7 × (0! - ((6! - 8!)/(3 - 1)))
138622 := (-2 + (((2 + 6!) × 8) × ((3 + 1)!))
138624 := (((4 - 2) + 6!) × 8) × ((3 + 1)!)
138959 := (((95 + 98) × 3!!) - 1)
138973 := ((3 - ((7!/9) × (-8))) × 31)
139048 := (((8 × 4!) - 0!) × ((9³) - 1))
139097 := ((-7 + (((9 - 0!)!)/(-9))) × (-31))
139536 := ((6^{3!}) + ((5! + 9) × (((3 × 1)!)!))
139624 := ((4! - (((2 + 6)!)/(-9))) × 31)
139635 := ((5! - ((3!⁶) + 9)) × (-3 × 1))
139679 := ((97 × (6! + ((9 - 3)!)) - 1)
139824 := (4! × (2 + (8 × ((9³) - 1))))
139942 := (-2 + (4! × (((9 + 9)³) - 1)))
139944 := (4! × ((4! × ((9 × 9) × 3)) - 1))
139968 := (8 × ((6! + 9) × (((9/3) + 1)!))
140168 := (8 × (((6! + 10) × 4!) + 1))
140287 := (-7 × (((8!)/(-2)) - 0!) + ((4 + 1)!))
140447 := (((7! - 4!) × (4! - (0 - 4))) - 1)
140477 := ((-7 × (((7! - 4!) + 0!) × (-4))) + 1)
140659 := ((9 × ((5⁶) + 0!)) + (4! + 1))
140759 := ((((-9 × 5!) - 7!) × (0! - 4!)) - 1)
141127 := (-7 × ((((((2 + 1)! + 1)! × (-4)) - 1))
141177 := ((-7 × ((7! + (1 + 1)) × (-4))) + 1)
141287 := ((-7 × ((8!)/(-2)) - ((1 × 4)!)) - 1)
142297 := (((((79 - 2)²) × 4!) + 1)
142569 := (9 × (((-6 × 5!) × (2 - 4!)) + 1))
142577 := ((-7 × ((7! + (52)) × (-4))) + 1)
142659 := (9 × (((5! + 6)²) - 4!) - 1))
142672 := ((-((2⁷)) + 6!) × 241)
142693 := (((3! - (-9 × 6!)) × (-2 + 4!)) + 1)
142757 := ((7⁵) + ((7! - 2) × (4! + 1)))
142848 := (8 × ((4! + ((8 - 2)!)) × ((4 × 1)!))
142859 := (((((9!/5!)/8)²) - 4!) - 1)
143048 := (8 × ((((-((4! + 0!)) - 3!)) × (-4!)) + 1))
143087 := (7! + ((8 × ((0! - 3!)) × (-4!))) - 1))
143345 := (((5! + (4^{3!})) × 34) + 1)
143448 := ((8! × 4) - (4! × (3!! + (4! - 1))))
143475 := (-5 × ((-7 × (4^{3!})) - (4! - 1)))
143568 := (((8! + (6⁵)) × 3) - (((4 - 1)!))
143592 := ((2 × ((9!/5) - 3!)) - (((4 + 1)!))
143744 := (-((4⁴)) - ((7! + 3!)) × (-4! + 1)))
143755 := (-5!) + (((5 - 7!) - 3!)) × (-4! + 1)))
143825 := (((5 + 2) - (8 × 3!)) × (-4! + 1))
143837 := (-7!) + ((-3 - (-8!)/3!))⁴⁻¹)
143856 := (((6! - 5!) - 8) × (3⁴⁺¹))
143857 := (((7! - ((5! × (-8)) + 3!)) × 4!) + 1)
143872 := (-((2⁷)) - ((8 × 3!)) × (-4! + 1)))
143895 := (5! + ((9 - (8 × 3!)) × (-4! + 1)))
143934 := (((4! - 3!)) × (-9)) - (3!)) × (4! - 1))
144008 := (8 × (0! - (-((0! + 4!)) × (((4 - 1)!)))))
144342 := ((2 - 4!) × (-3^{4+4×1}))
144384 := (4! × ((8 × 3!)) + ((4⁴) × 1))
144457 := (((7! + 5!) × (4! + 4)) - (4! - 1))
144475 := (((5! + 7!) × (4! + 4)) - (4 + 1))
144507 := (((7! + 0!) + 5!) × (4! + 4)) - 1)
144576 := (((6 × 7!) - 5!) × 4!)/(4 + 1))
144577 := (((7 × (7! + 5!)) + 4!) × 4) + 1)
144768 := (((8 × 6) - 7!) × ((-4 - 4!) - 1))
144883 := ((((-3 + 8!) - (8⁴)) × 4) - 1)
144884 := (4 × (8! - ((8⁴) + 4) - 1))
144888 := (-8 - ((8! - (8⁴)) × (-4 × 1)))
144935 := (-5 × ((3!! - (9 + 4)) × (-41)))
145129 := (((9! × 2)/(1 × 5)) - 4!) + 1)
145146 := (-6 + (((4 + 1) + 5)!/(4! + 1)))
145152 := (((2 × 5)!)/(((1 + 5) × 4) + 1))

- 145176 := (((6! × (7! + 1)) - 5!)/(4! + 1))
145193 := (((3! × 9!)/15) + 41)
145272 := (((2 × ((7 + 2)!)/5) + ((4 + 1)!))
145293 := (((3!! + (9! × 2))/5) - (4 - 1))
145295 := (5! + (((9! × 2)/5) + 4!) - 1)
145296 := ((6! + (9! × 2))/(5!/((4 × 1)!))
145347 := ((-7 × ((4 - 3!!) × (5 + 4!))) - 1)
145392 := (2 × (((9! + 3!)/5) - ((4 × 1)!))
145464 := ((4! - 6!) × (-4 + (5 × 41)))
145472 := ((2^{-7+4!}) + (5! × ((4 + 1)!))
145475 := ((5 - (7!/(-4))) × (5! - (4 + 1)))
145584 := ((4! + (8!/5)) × ((-5 + 4!) - 1))
145637 := (7! - 3 × 6) × (5 + 4!) - 1
145799 := (((9 × 9) × 75) × 4!) - 1
145928 := ((8 - ((2 - 9)!)) × (-5 - ((4 × 1)!))
146045 := (((5 + 4!) × ((0! + 6)! - 4)) + 1)
146073 := ((-3 + 7!) × ((06 + 4!) - 1))
146131 := ((1 - ((3! + 1)!)) × ((-6 - 4!) + 1))
146154 := (((4! + 5) × ((1 + 6)!)) - ((4 - 1)!))
146184 := (4! + (((8 - 1)! × ((6!/4!) - 1)))
146218 := (((8 - 1)! + 2) × ((6!/4!) - 1))
146276 := (((-6 - 7!) + 2) × ((-6 - 4!) + 1))
146305 := ((-5 - ((0! + 3)!)) × ((-6 - 4!) + 1))
146308 := ((8! - ((0! + (3!^6)) × 4)) × (-1))
146334 := (((4 + 3)! + 3!) × ((6!/4!) - 1))
146339 := (((93 + 3!!) × (6!/4)) - 1)
146432 := ((2^{3!+4}) × ((6 × 4!) - 1))
146534 := (((4 - 3!!) × (-5)) - 6) × 41
146561 := ((-((1 + 6) + 5!) × ((6⁴) + 1))
146575 := (((5! - 7!) × (-5 + 6!))/(4! × (-1)))
146592 := (2 × ((9!/5) + (6 × ((4 + 1)!))
146593 := (((3!! - (9!/(-5))) × (6 - 4)) + 1)
146657 := ((7 + (-5 × (6 - 6!))) × 41)
146743 := ((34 × ((7! - 6!) - 4)) - 1)
146855 := -(((5! × 5!) + (((8! - 6) × (-4)) + 1)))
146856 := (((6! × (-5)) + 8!) - 6) × (4 × 1))
146865 := ((5 + (-68) × 6!) × (-4 - 1))
146875 := ((-5 + ((7! - 8!)/(-6))) × (4! + 1))
146883 := (3 × (8! + (8641)))
146955 := (-5 × ((5! + 9) + (6! × (-41))))
147175 := (((5! × (-7)) - 1) × (-7)) × (4! + 1))
147239 := ((9 × (((3! - 2)⁷) - 4!)) - 1)
147303 := (((3! - 0!)! - 3) × ((7!/4) - 1))
147313 := (((3!! × (-1 + 3!)) - 7) × 41)
147355 := (-((5⁵)) + (3!! × ((7!/4!) - 1)))
147383 := (((3!! - 8) × (-3 + (7!/4!))) - 1)
147384 := (4! × ((83 × 74) - 1))
147433 := (((3 × 3) × (4⁷)) - 4!) + 1)
147436 := (((-6!) - 3!!) + (-4 + 7!)) × 41)
147439 := ((-9 × (3! - ((4⁷) + 4))) + 1)
147456 := ((6!/5) × (4^{(7-4)!-1}))
147481 := (((1 + 8) × (4⁷)) + 4!) + 1)
147488 := (-88) × (4 - (7!/(4 - 1)))
147591 := (-(((1 × 9)⁵)) - (7! × (-41)))
147605 := (5 × ((0! - 6!) + (7! × ((4 - 1)!)))
147624 := (4! - (((-2 × 6!) + 7!) × (-41)))
147755 := ((-55 - 7!) × (-((7 × 4) + 1)))
147763 := -(((3! - 6!) + 7) × ((7!/4!) - 1))
147783 := (((3!! + 8) × (-7 + (7!/4!))) - 1)
147829 := ((9 + 2) × ((8!/(7 - 4)) - 1))
147938 := (((8!/3) + 9) × (7 + 4)) - 1)
148256 := (((6! × 5) + ((2 × 8))) × 41)
148585 := (((5⁸) - 5!) - (8! × ((4 - 1)!))
148705 := ((5^{0!+7}) - (8! × ((4 - 1)!))
149035 := (-5 - (3!! × ((0 - 9) × (4! - 1))))
149039 := (((-9 × 3!!) × (((0 × 9)! - 4!)) - 1)
149064 := (4! + ((6! × 09) × (4! - 1)))
149136 := ((6! - 3) × (1 + (9 × (4! - 1))))
149155 := ((5 + (((5 + 1)! × 9)) × (4! - 1))
149184 := (-4 × ((8! × (-1)) + (9!/((4 + 1)!))))
149248 := ((8⁴) + ((-2 × 9!)/(-4 + 1)))
149293 := (((3!! × (-9)) - (2 + 9)) × (-4! - 1))
149385 := (((5!/8) - (3!! × (-9))) × (4! - 1))
149445 := (-5 × (((4!/4)! + 9) × (-41)))
149473 := (((3!! - (7 × 4)) × (9 × 4!)) + 1)
149568 := (8 × ((6! + 59) × ((4 × 1)!))
149786 := (((6! - 8) × (7! + 9))/4!) - 1)
149832 := (-((2³)) × (8! - (9⁴⁺¹)))
149968 := ((-8 - 6!) × (9 - ((9 × 4!) - 1))
150336 := (-((6³)) × (((3 + 0!)! - (((5 + 1)!)))
150367 := (-7 × (((6! × (-30)) + 5!) - 1))
150475 := (-5 + (((7!/4!) - 0!) × ((5 + 1)!))
150476 := ((6! × ((7!/4!) - 0!)) - (5 - 1))

- 150903** := $((3^{-0!+9}) \times (-(0! - ((5 - 1)!)))$
150904 := $((4! - 0!) \times (9^{-0!+5})) + 1$
150944 := $(-((4^4)) - (((9 + 0)!)/(-(5 - 1)!)))$
151172 := $(2 \times (((7! - 1) \times 15) + 1))$
151175 := $(-5 \times (((7! - 1) \times (-(1 + 5))) - 1))$
151176 := $(-6 \times (((7! - 1) \times (-(1 \times 5))) - 1))$
151193 := $(-(3!) - (((-((9 + 1)!)/(-(1 - 5)))! + 1))$
151195 := $((5! - (9 + 1)! \times (-1))/(5 - 1)!)$
151199 := $((9! \times (9 + 1))/(-(1 - 5)!)) - 1$
151201 := $((10!)/(-(2 - 1 - 5)!)) + 1$
151206 := $(-6 \times (((0! + ((2 + 1)!))! \times (-5)) - 1))$
151275 := $(5 + (7! \times 2)) \times (15 \times 1)$
151284 := $(4 \times (8! - (21 \times (5! - 1))))$
151319 := $(((((9 + 1)!)/((3 + 1)!)) + 5!) - 1)$
151343 := $((-3!) \times (-(4!) - (((3! + 1)! \times 5))) - 1)$
151356 := $(-6 \times (((5 + ((3! + 1)!)) \times (-5)) - 1))$
151375 := $(-5 \times (((7! + 3!) \times (-(1 + 5))) + 1))$
151376 := $(((((6 - 7!) \times 3!) + 1) \times (-5)) + 1)$
151479 := $(9 \times ((7^{4+1}) + ((5 - 1)!))$
151765 := $(-5 \times ((-6 \times (7! - 1)) - (5! - 1)))$
152279 := $((9 + (7!/(2 + 2))) \times 5!) - 1$
152357 := $(((-7 + 5!) - 3!) \times (-251))$
152497 := $(7! + ((9 \times (4^{2+5})) + 1))$
152544 := $(4! \times (-4 + (5! \times (2 + 51))))$
152664 := $(-4 \times (-6 + (6! \times (-(2 + 51))))))$
153046 := $((-((6^4)) - 0!) \times ((3 - 5!) - 1))$
153255 := $((5^5) - ((2 + 3)! \times 51)$
153336 := $((6! \times ((3!^3) - 3)) - ((5 - 1)!)$
153344 := $((4^4) \times (((3 + 3)! - 5!) - 1))$
153459 := $((9 + 5!) - (-4 \times 3!)) \times 51$
153472 := $((2^7) \times (((4 + 3!) \times 5!) - 1))$
153485 := $((5 - 8!) \times (-4)) - ((3!^5) - 1))$
153549 := $(9 \times ((4! + 5!) - 3)) \times (5! + 1)$
153696 := $((6! - 9) \times (6^3)) + ((5 \times 1)!)$
153729 := $((9^2) - 7!) \times ((3! \times (-5)) - 1))$
153793 := $((3 + 9) \times (7! + (3!^5))) + 1$
153865 := $((5^6) - ((8 \times 3!) \times (-(5 - 1)!)))$
153937 := $((7^3!) + (9!/(3! + (5 - 1))))$
154217 := $(-7 + (((1 + 2)!^4) \times (5! - 1)))$
154224 := $((4 \times 2) - 2^4) \times (5! - 1)$
154319 := $((-(9 + 1)) + (3!^4)) \times 5! - 1$
154343 := $((3!^4) - ((3 - 4)) \times (5! - 1))$
154384 := $((4 \times ((8 + 3!)^4)) + ((5 + 1)!)$
154439 := $(((-9 + (3!^4)) \times (4! \times 5)) - 1)$
154449 := $(9 \times ((4! \times ((4!/4)!)) - ((5! - 1))))$
154462 := $(-((2 + (6^4))) \times ((4! \times (-5)) + 1))$
154496 := $((6! \times 9) \times 4!) - ((4^5) \times 1)$
154629 := $(9 \times (((-2 + 6!) \times 4!) - (51)))$
154656 := $((6^5) + (6! \times (4 \times 51)))$
154673 := $(-(3! - (((7 - (6^4))) \times 5!) - 1)))$
154675 := $((5! \times (-(7 - (6^4)))) - (5 \times 1))$
154681 := $((((1 - 8) + (6^4)) \times 5!) + 1)$
154752 := $((2^5) \times (7! - ((4 \times 51))))$
154896 := $((6! \times (-9)) - ((8! + 4!) \times (-(5 - 1))))$
154937 := $(-7 + (((3! \times (-9)) + 4!) \times (-(5 - 1)!)))$
154944 := $(-(((4! \times 4!) + ((-9 \times 4!) \times ((5 + 1)!)))$
155304 := $(4! \times ((0! - 3!) \times (-(5 + 5) - 1)))$
155349 := $((9 \times 4!) \times 3!) - (5! + (51))$
155394 := $((4! \times 9) \times 3!) - (5! + (5 + 1))$
155395 := $(-5 + (((-9 \times 3!) + 5) \times (-(5 - 1)!)))$
155439 := $(9 \times ((3! \times 4!) - ((5 + 5) - 1))$
155463 := $(-(3! + (((6^4)) \times 5!) + (51)))$
155465 := $((5! \times (6^4)) - (55 \times 1))$
155466 := $((-6 + (6! \times 4!)) \times ((5 + 5) - 1))$
155469 := $(((((9 - 6)!^4) \times 5!) - (51))$
155488 := $(8! - (8 \times (4 - (5! \times ((5 \times 1)!))))$
155493 := $((3 \times 9) \times ((4! \times (5! + 5!) - 1))$
155496 := $((6! \times 9) \times 4!) - ((5 \times 5) - 1)$
155516 := $((6^{-1+5}) \times 5!) - (5 - 1)$
155519 := $((9 \times ((1 + 5)!)/5) \times 5!) - 1$
155524 := $(-4 \times (((-((2 - 5)))!^5) \times (-5)) - 1))$
155528 := $(8 \times (((2 + 5)! + ((5! \times 5!) + 1)))$
155529 := $(9 \times (((-((2 - 5)))! \times (5!/5)) + 1))$
155538 := $((8! + 3) - (5! \times 5!)) \times (5 + 1)$
155543 := $((3!^4) \times 5!) + ((5!/5) - 1)$
155544 := $(4! - ((4! \times 5!) \times (-(55 - 1))))$
155546 := $((6^4) \times 5!) + ((5 \times 5) + 1)$
155636 := $((6^3) \times 6!) + 5! - (5 - 1)$
155639 := $(-9! - (((3! \times 6!) \times 5!) + 5!) - 1))$
155664 := $(4! \times (6 + (6! \times ((5 + 5) - 1))))$
155736 := $(-((6^3)) \times (((-7 \times 5!) + 5!) - 1))$
156085 := $((-5 + ((8 - 0)!))! \times ((6 \times 5) + 1))$

- 156128 := ((82 × 16) × (5! - 1))
156144 := (((4!⁴⁺¹) + 6!)/51)
156147 := ((7! - (4 - 1)) × ((6 × 5) + 1))
156237 := -(((7! + 3) + (((2 + 6)!) × (-5 - 1))))
156238 := (((8! × 3!) - 2) - (6! × (5! - 1)))
156239 := (((93 × 2) × (6! + 5!)) - 1)
156271 := ((1 + 7!) × ((26 + 5) × 1))
156302 := ((-2 - ((0! + 3!)!) × (-((6 × 5) + 1)))
156361 := (((1 + (6³) × 6!) + 5!) + 1)
156384 := (((4! + 8!) × 3!) - (6! × (5! - 1)))
156484 := (4 × (8! + ((-((4 + 6) × 5!) + 1)))
156549 := (((-9 × 4!) × (-5 - 6!)) - (51))
156594 := (((4! × (-9)) × (-5 - 6!)) - (5 + 1))
156595 := (-5 - (9 × ((-5 - 6!) × ((5 - 1)!)))
156599 := (9 × (((9 - 5)!) × 6!) + 5!) - 1)
156636 := ((6 × 3!) × ((6 × (6! + 5)) + 1))
156774 := (((4! + 7) × (7! - 6)) + ((5 + 1)!))
157184 := ((4 × 8!) - ((1 + 7)⁵⁻¹)
157244 := (4 × (((4 × 2)!) + ((7! / (-5)) - 1)))
157343 := ((((-3 × 4!) × (-3⁷)) - 5!) - 1)
157408 := ((8 × 04) × ((7! - 5!) - 1))
157432 := ((2³) × ((4 × (7! - 5!)) - 1))
157437 := ((-7 × ((3 + 4!) × (-7))) × (5! - 1))
157439 := (((9 + ((3!⁴) + 7)) × 5!) - 1)
157442 := (2 × (((4 × 4) × (7! - 5!)) + 1))
157444 := (-4 × ((-((4 + 4) × (7! - 5!)) - 1))
157448 := (8 × (((-4 + (4! × 7)) × 5!) + 1))
157461 := ((1 - 6!) × ((4! × (-7)) - (51)))
157464 := (4! × (((6 - 4) + 7)⁵⁻¹)
157472 := (((2⁷) / 4) × ((7! - 5!) + 1))
157679 := ((9 × ((-7 + 6!) + (7⁵))) - 1)
157845 := -((((5! + 4) - 8!) - (7⁵⁺¹)))
157849 := -((((9 - 4)!) - 8!) - (7⁵⁺¹)))
157884 := (-4 × ((8 - 8!) - ((-7 × 5!) - 1)))
157897 := (((7! - 9) × 8) + (7⁵⁺¹))
157978 := ((8 × 7!) + ((9 + (7⁵⁺¹))))
157984 := ((4! + 8!) - (9 - (7⁵⁺¹)))
158155 := (-((5⁵)) - (((1 × 8)!) × (-5 - 1)))
158255 := (-((55²)) - (8! × (-5 - 1)))
158304 := (((4! + ((03)!)!) - 8!) × (-5 - 1))
158343 := (-3!) + ((-4 × (3!! - 8!)) - (51))
158352 := (((2 + 5!) × 3!) - 8!) × (-5 - 1))
158356 := (((6! + 5) + 3!) - 8!) × (-5 - 1))
158364 := (-4 × (((6 + 3) - 8!) + ((5 + 1)!))
158368 := (-8 - (((6! + 3!) - 8!) × (5 - 1))
158371 := (-1 + (((-7 - 3!!) + 8!) × (5 - 1))
158373 := ((-((3⁷)) - 3!!) - (8! × (-5 - 1)))
158384 := (((-4 + 8!) - 3!!) × ((8 - 5) + 1))
158385 := ((5! / (-8)) + ((3!! - 8!) × (-5 - 1)))
158386 := (-((6 + 8) + ((3!! - 8!) × (-5 - 1)))
158391 := (-((1 × 9) + ((3!! - 8!) × (-5 - 1)))
158392 := (((2 + ((9 - 3)!) - 8!) × (-5 - 1))
158394 := ((-4 × (((9 - 3)!) - 8!)) - (5 + 1))
158395 := (-5 + (((9 - 3)!) - 8!) × (-5 - 1))
158399 := (-((9/9) + ((3!! - 8!) × (-5 - 1)))
158416 := (((6! - (1 × 4) - 8!) × (-5 - 1))
158424 := (4! - (((2 + 4)!) - 8!) × (5 - 1))
158425 := ((5²) - (-4 × (8! - ((5 + 1)!)))
158436 := ((6 × 3!) - (-4 × (8! - ((5 + 1)!)))
158486 := (((6! - 8!) × (-4) + ((85 + 1)))
158496 := (((-((6 - 9)!)!) - (4! + 8!)) × (-5 - 1))
158592 := (2 × ((9! / 5) - (8! / (-5 + 1))))
158604 := (-4 × (((06)!) - 8!) - (51))
158656 := ((656 - 8!) × (-5 - 1))
158664 := (-4 × ((-66) - 8!) + ((5 + 1)!))
158748 := ((8! - ((4! + 7!) / 8)) × (5 - 1))
158784 := (4! - ((8! + (7! / (-8))) × (-5 - 1)))
158847 := (-((7⁴)) - ((8 - 8!) × (5 - 1))
158879 := (((9! × 7) / (8 + 8)) + 5!) - 1)
158976 := ((6⁷) + (9! / (-((8 - 5) × 1)))
159232 := (((2³)!) - (2⁹)) × (5 - 1))
159248 := ((8! + (4 - (2⁹))) × (5 - 1))
159264 := (4 × (((6 + 2)!) - (9! / ((5 + 1)!)))
159275 := (((5⁷) × 2) + ((9! / 5!) + 1))
159335 := ((5! × (3!! + 3)) - ((9! / (-5)) + 1))
159444 := (4 × (((4 + 4)!) - (9 × 51)))
159456 := (((6! × 5) + 4!) × ((9 × 5) - 1))
159562 := ((2 + 6!) × (5 + (9 × ((5 - 1)!)))
159586 := ((6 + 8) × ((5! × 95) - 1))
159684 := (4 × (8! + (((6! / (-9)) × 5) + 1))
159744 := -((4! + (4! × (-7 × 951))))
159768 := (8! - 6 × 7 × 9) × (5 - 1)
159822 := (2 × (((2 × 8!) - 9) - ((5 + 1)!))

- 159841 := (((148 × 9) × 5!) + 1)
159842 := (2 × (((((4!/8)!)! × (-9 + 5!)) + 1))
159984 := (4 × (8! - (((9 × 9) × (5 - 1))))))
160024 := (4! + (20^{-0!+6-1}))
160337 := ((-7 - (3!³)) × (0! - ((6 × 1)!))
160583 := (((3! + 8!) × (5 - 0!)) - (6! + 1))
160584 := ((4 × ((8! + 5) + 0!)) - ((6 × 1)!))
160587 := (((7 + 8!) × (5 - 0!)) - (6! + 1))
160804 := (-4 × (((0 - 8!) - 0!) + ((6 - 1)!))
161051 := ((1 + (5 × (0! + 1)))⁶⁻¹)
161052 := (((2 × 5) + 0!)⁻¹⁺⁶) + 1)
161165 := (5! - (6 - (11⁶⁻¹)))
161184 := ((4! - 8!) × (((1 × 1) - 6) + 1))
161239 := (-9 - (32 × (1 - ((6 + 1)!)))
161248 := ((8! × 4) - ((2 × 16) × 1))
161264 := ((4 - ((6 + 2)!)) × ((1 - 6) + 1))
161268 := ((8! - (6/2)) × -((1 - 6) + 1))
161273 := -((3! - ((7! × (2 × 16)) - 1))
161274 := ((4 × (((7 + 2) - 1)!)) - (6 × 1))
161275 := (-5 - (7! × -((2 × 16) × 1)))
161279 := (((9 + 7) × 2) × ((1 + 6)!)) - 1)
161304 := (4! + ((0! + 3) × (((1 + 6) + 1)!))
161308 := (((8! + 0!) + 3!) × -((1 - 6) + 1))
161312 := ((2^{-1+3!}) × (1 + ((6 + 1)!))
161327 := (((7! × (-2)) - 3) × (-16)) - 1)
161328 := (((8!/2) + 3!) × ((1 + 6) + 1))
161344 := (-4 × (((4!/3)!) + (16)) × (-1))
161348 := (((8! × 4) + 3!) + (1 + 61))
161373 := (((3 + 7!) × 31) + ((6 + 1)!))
161377 := (((7! + 7!) + 3!) × 16) + 1)
161384 := (((4 - 8!) × -(3 + 1)) + ((6 - 1)!))
161448 := ((8! × 4) + (4! × ((1 × 6) + 1))
161497 := (7! - (((-9 × 4!) - 1) × (6! + 1))
161524 := (4 × (((2 + 5) + 1)! + (61)))
161744 := (-4 × ((4 - ((7 + 1)!)) - ((6 - 1)!))
161754 := ((4 × (5! + ((7 + 1)!)) - (6 × 1))
161784 := (4 × ((8! + (7 - 1)) + ((6 - 1)!))
161792 := ((2⁹) × ((7!/16) + 1))
161856 := (((6!/5) + 8!) × -((1 - 6) + 1))
162324 := (4 × (((2³)!) + 261))
162607 := (-7 + (-0! + 6!)) × (2 × 6! - 1)
162729 := -((9! - ((27²) × (6! + 1))))
163438 := (((-8!) - 3!) × (-4)) - ((3 + 6!) - 1))
163456 := -(((6! × 5!) + ((4^{3!}) × (-61))))
163475 := (((57 × 4) × (-3 + 6!)) - 1)
163584 := (4! × ((-8 × 5!) + (3!⁶⁻¹)))
163667 := ((-((7 + 6)) - (6!/(-3))) × (6! + 1))
163684 := (4 × (8! - (((6!/3!) - 6!) - 1))
163872 := (2 × (((7! - 8!) - (3!⁶)) × (-1))
163875 := 5 × (7 + 8^{(-3+6)!-1})
163884 := (-4 × (((8 - 8!) - 3!) + (61)))
164162 := (2 × (((-6 + ((1 + 4)!)) × 6!) + 1))
164164 := (-4 × ((-((61 - 4) × 6!) - 1))
164184 := (4 × (((8! + (1 + 4)) + 6!) + 1))
164275 := ((57 × (2 - (-4 × 6!))) + 1)
164439 := (9 × (((3 + 4!)!/(4!)! + (6! + 1)))
164585 := (((5 × (8⁵)) + 4!) + 6!) + 1)
164859 := (9! - ((5 × ((8! + 4) - 6!)) + 1))
164864 := ((((-4 + 6!) + 8!) × 4) + ((6 × 1)!))
164946 := ((6 - (4! × (-9))) × ((4! + 6!) - 1))
165152 := ((2⁵) × ((1 + 5!) + ((6 + 1)!))
165328 := (8! + ((2³) × ((5⁶) + 1))
165377 := (7! - ((-((7³)) + 5!) × (6! - 1))
165432 := (((2 × (3!⁴)) + 5!) × 61)
165435 := ((5! + 3) × ((4! × 56) + 1))
165582 := (2 × (-8 - (((5 - 5!) × 6!) + 1))
165595 := (-5 × (((9 - 55) × 6!) + 1))
165602 := (2 × (((0! - 6) + 5!) × 6!) + 1))
165624 := (4! + ((2 × 6!) × (5! - (6 - 1))))
165643 := (-3 + (46 × ((5 × 6!) + 1))
165864 := (4! × (((6! × 8)/(-5)) × (-6)) - 1))
166259 := (((-9 + (5! × 2)) × 6!) - (61))
166288 := (((8 - 8!) × (2 - 6)) + ((6 + 1)!))
166323 := (3 × (((((2 + 3) + 6)!/6!) + 1))
166344 := (4! + ((4! + (3 + 6)) × ((6 + 1)!))
166345 := -((((5! - 4) × ((3! - 6!) - 6!)) - 1))
166375 := ((5 - (7! × (-3))) × ((6 + 6) - 1))
166494 := -((4! - ((-9 - 4!) × (-6 - ((6 + 1)!))))
166584 := (-4 × (8! - ((5! - 6) × (6! - 1))))
166595 := ((5 + (9!/5!)) × -(6 - 61))
166749 := ((-9 - 4!) × -((7 + 6)) - ((6 + 1)!))
166848 := 8! + 4! × 8 × (6! - 61)
166924 := ((4 × 29) × ((6! + 6!) - 1))
167039 := (((9 + ((3 + 0!)!) × 7!) + ((6! - 1)))

- 167048** := $(8 \times (((4 \times (07)!) + 6!) + 1))$
167489 := $((((9 - 8!) + (4^7)) \times (- (6 + 1)))$
167527 := $((7 - 2)! + 5! - 7) \times (6! - 1)$
167555 := $((5! + 5!) - 5) \times (-7 + ((6 \times 1)!))$
167936 := $((((6!/3) - 9) \times (7 + 6!)) - 1)$
168025 := $(-((5^2)) \times (((08)! / (-6)) - 1))$
168145 := $(5! - ((4! + 1) \times ((8! / (-6)) - 1)))$
168246 := $((-6 + (4! \times (2 + 8))) \times (6! - 1))$
168336 := $((6^{3!}) + ((3 \times 8!) + ((6 \times 1)!))$
168476 := $(-(((6! - 7!) - (4 \times ((8! + 6!) - 1))))$
168525 := $(-((5^2)) \times (((5! + 8!) / (-6)) - 1))$
168714 := $((4 - 1) \times 78) \times (6! + 1)$
168793 := $((39 \times ((7! + 8) - 6!)) + 1)$
168832 := $((2 + 3) \times 8!) - (8^{6-1})$
169195 := $(5 \times (((9 - 1)!) + ((-9 \times 6!) - 1)))$
169236 := $((((6! + 3!)^2) - 9!) + ((6 + 1)!))$
169245 := $(5 \times (((4 \times 2)!) + (-9 \times (6! - 1))))$
169337 := $(-7 \times (((3 \times 3)! / (-9 + 6)) + 1))$
169338 := $((8! \times 3!) - 3!) + (9! / (-6 - 1))$
169344 := $((((4 + 4)!) \times 3!) + (9! / (-6 - 1)))$
169398 := $((8! + 9) \times 3!) + (9! / (-6 - 1))$
170471 := $((1 \times 7^4) \times 071)$
170543 := $((-34) \times (((5 - 0!)! - 7!)) - 1)$
170755 := $((5^5) - ((7 - 0!)!) \times 71)$
171275 := $((5 - (7! \times 2)) \times (- (17 \times 1)))$
171326 := $((6/2) + 31) \times (7! - 1)$
171327 := $(7! + ((2 + 31) \times (7! - 1)))$
171359 := $((9 + (5^{3-1})) \times 7!) - 1)$
171361 := $((-1 + ((6 \times 3!) - 1)) \times 7!) + 1)$
171362 := $(2 \times (((6 \times 3) - 1) \times 7!) + 1)$
171367 := $(-7 \times (6! - ((3! - 1) \times 7!) + 1))$
171394 := $((4 \times 9) - 3) + 1) \times (7! + 1)$
171396 := $((69 \times 3!)^{17+1})$
171427 := $((7! + 2) \times (41 - 7)) - 1)$
171428 := $((8 + 2) + 4!) \times ((1 + 7!) + 1)$
172322 := $(2 \times (((-2 + 3!) \times (-((2 - 7)!)) + 1))$
172544 := $(-((4^4)) - ((5! \times (-2)) \times ((7 - 1)!))$
172553 := $((3! \times 5!) - 5!) \times 2) - (7 \times 1)$
172561 := $((1 - 6!) \times (-5!) - (-((2 - 7)!)) + 1)$
172562 := $(2 \times (((6! \times 5!) - (-((2 - 7)!)) + 1))$
172735 := $(-5 \times (3! - (((7! - 2) \times 7) + 1)))$
172765 := $(-5 \times (6! - (-7 \times ((2 - 7!) - 1))))$
173033 := $((3! / 3) \times (0! + 3!)) - (7 \times 1)$
173052 := $(2 \times ((5! \times (0! + 3!)) + (7 - 1)))$
173064 := $(4! \times (((6! + 0!) \times (3 + 7)) + 1))$
173447 := $((7! \times 4!) - ((4! \times (-3^7)) + 1))$
173502 := $(2 \times ((0! - 5!) \times (-3^{7-1})))$
173532 := $(2 \times (3! - (5! \times (-3 - ((7 - 1)!))))$
173586 := $(6! + (((8! - (5^3)) \times 7) + 1))$
173641 := $((-(((1 + 4)!) \times ((-6!) - 3!) - 7)) + 1)$
173645 := $(-5 \times ((4! \times ((-6!) - 3!) - 7)) - 1)$
173652 := $(2 \times ((5! \times 6!) - (3! \times (-71))))$
173663 := $((36 \times (-((6^3)) + 7!)) - 1)$
173761 := $((1 + 6!) \times ((7! / (3 \times 7)) + 1))$
173879 := $((9! - 7!) / (8 - 3!)) - (7! + 1)$
174768 := $(8 \times (((6! + (7^4)) \times 7) - 1))$
174824 := $((4! + 2) \times ((8! + 4!) / (7 - 1)))$
174933 := $((3^3) \times ((9 \times (-((4 - 7)!))!)) - 1)$
174959 := $((9 \times ((5! \times ((9 - 4)!) + 7!)) - 1)$
174996 := $((6! \times (-9)) + ((9 \times 4) \times (7! + 1)))$
175275 := $(-5 \times (((7! - (2^5)) \times (-7)) + 1))$
175357 := $(-7 \times ((-5 \times ((3! \times (-5)) + 7!)) - 1))$
175386 := $(-6 \times (((8! \times (-3)) / 5) - 7!) + 1)$
175393 := $((3! \times ((9! / (3 \times 5)) + 7!)) + 1)$
175433 := $(-((3! - ((34 \times (5! + 7!)) - 1)))$
175435 := $(-5 + (34 \times (5! + ((7 \times 1)!)))$
175525 := $(-((5 + 2) \times (5! - (5 \times (7! - 1))))$
175561 := $(((((1 + 6)!) \times 5) - 5!) \times 7) + 1)$
175567 := $(-7 \times (6! + ((-5 \times (5! + 7!)) - 1)))$
175573 := $(3! + (-7 \times (5! - ((5 \times 7!) + 1))))$
175643 := $((34 \times ((6 + 5!) + 7!)) - 1)$
175673 := $(-((3! - (-7 \times ((6! \times (-5 \times 7)) + 1))))$
175685 := $(5 \times (8! - (((6! / 5) + 7!) - 1))$
175715 := $(-(((5 + 1)!) - ((7 \times 5) \times (7! + 1))))$
175716 := $(-((6! + (((1 + 7!) \times (-5 \times 7)) - 1)))$
175765 := $((5! - 6!) + ((7 \times 5) \times (7! - 1)))$
175805 := $(-5 \times (((0! + 8!) - 5!) - 7!) \times (-1))$
175835 := $(5 \times (((3! + 8!) - 5!) - 7!) + 1)$
175875 := $((5 \times 7) \times ((8! - 5!) / (7 + 1)))$
175897 := $((-7 \times ((9 \times 8) + (-5 \times 7!)) + 1)$
176185 := $(-5 \times (((8 - 1)!) - 6) \times (-7) + 1)$
176285 := $(-5 \times ((-8!) + (-((2 - 6)!)) + ((7! - 1))))$
176315 := $(-((5! - (-((1 - 36)) \times (7! + 1))))$
176327 := $((7! - 2) \times 36) - 7! - 1)$

- 176357 := (((7! × 5) - ((3 - 6)))! × 7) - 1
176365 := (((5 - 6) + 36) × (7! - 1))
176375 := (5 × (((7! × 3!) - 6) + 7!) + 1)
176384 := (-((4⁸)) - ((-(3 - 6)))! × (-((7 + 1)))!)
176385 := (-5 × (((8! + ((3 - 6))) - 7!) × (-1)))
176393 := (((((3 × 9!)/3!) - 6) - 7!) - 1)
176395 := (-5 + (((9! × 3)/6) - ((7 × 1)))!)
176396 := (((((6 - 9!) × (-3))/6) - 7!) - 1)
176397 := -((7! + ((9! - 3!)/((6 - 7) - 1))))
176399 := ((-((9/9) - 36)) × 7!) - 1
176401 := (((((10!)/4!)/6) × 7) + 1)
176405 := (5 × (((((0 × 4)!) + 6) × 7!) + 1))
176407 := (-7 × (((0! + 4) × 6!) × (-7)) - 1)
176425 := (5 × (((((2 × 4)!) + 6) - 7!) - 1))
176429 := (((((9!/2) + 4!) + 6) - 7!) - 1)
176435 := ((5 × (3 + 4)) × ((6! × 7) + 1))
176459 := (((9! + 5!)/(-4 - 6)) - 7!) - 1
176475 := (-5 × (((7! - ((4 - 6))) × (-7)) - 1))
176485 := (5 × (((8! + 4!) - 6) - 7!) - 1)
176547 := (-7 × (4 + (-5 × ((6 + 7!) - 1))))
176555 := (5! + ((5 + (5 × 6)) × (7! + 1)))
176567 := (((((7! + 6) × 5) - 6) × 7) - 1)
176575 := (-5 × ((-7 × (5 - 6!)) - ((7 + 1)))!)
176605 := (-5 × (((0! + 6) × (-6 - 7!)) + 1))
176615 := (-5 × (((((1 + 6)!) + 6) × (-7)) - 1))
176617 := (-7 × (((1 - 6) × (6 + 7!)) - 1))
176645 := (((5 + 4!) + 6) × ((6 + 7!) + 1))
176657 := ((7 + 5!) × (6! + 671))
176687 := (((7! + 8) × (6 × 6)) - 7!) - 1
176745 := (-5 × ((((-4 - 7!) - 6) × 7) + 1))
176755 := (5 × (5! + (-7 × ((6 - 7!) + 1))))
176785 := (5 × ((8! - 7!) + ((6 + 71))))
176796 := (-6 × (((-9 + 7!) × (-6)) + ((7 - 1)))!)
176825 := (((5! × 2) + 8) × (6! - 7)) + 1
177035 := (5 × (((3! - 0!))! - (-7 × (7! + 1))))
177144 := (4! + (41 × (7! - ((7 - 1)))!))
177156 := (-6 × (((5! - 1) - 7!) × (7 - 1)))
177235 := (-5 × (((((3! - 2)!) + 7!) × (-7)) + 1))
177336 := (6 × ((3! × (3! + 7!)) - ((7 - 1)))!)
177345 := (-5 × (((4! + 3) + 7!) × (-7 × 1)))
177366 := ((-6 + (6!/(-3))) × ((7!/(-7)) - 1))
177455 := (-5 × (((5!/(-4)) - 7!) × 7) - 1)
177525 := (-5 × (((-(2⁵)) - 7!) × 7) - 1)
177665 := (-5 × (((-(6 × 6)) - 7!) × 7) - 1))
177949 := (((9 × 4) × (-97) + 7!) + 1)
178313 := ((31 × (3!! + (-8 + 7!))) + 1)
178374 := ((4! + 7) × ((3! - (8!/7)) × (-1)))
178464 := (-4 × (((6! + 4!) - 8!) - ((7 × 1)))!)
178553 := ((3!! × ((5! + 5!) + 8)) - (7 × 1))
178555 := (-5 + (((5! + 5!) + 8) × ((7 - 1)))!)
178561 := (((1 + (6 × 5)) × 8!)/7) + 1
178564 := (-4 × (((6 × 5!) - 8!) - 7!) - 1)
179253 := (3 × ((5!²) + (9 × (7! - 1))))
179465 := ((5 - 6!) × (-((4 × 9) × 7) - 1))
180729 := (((9!/2) - ((7 - 0!))!) + (8 + 1))
181279 := (((-9 + (7! × 2)) × 18) + 1)
181329 := (((9!/2) - ((3! - 1)))! + (8 + 1))
181333 := (((3! × 3!) × (-3 + (-((1 - 8)))!)) + 1)
181344 := (-4 × ((4! - ((3! + 1)))! - ((8 × 1)))!)
181349 := (((9! × 4) - 3!)/(1 × 8)) - 1
181359 := ((9!/(5 - 3)) - ((1 × 81)))
181377 := ((7 - (7! × (3 + 1))) × (-8 + 1))
181386 := ((-6 + (8!/(3 - 1))) × (8 + 1))
181399 := (((9! × 9) - 3!)/18) - 1
181404 := ((40 - 4) × (-1 + ((8 - 1)))!)
181429 := ((9!/2) - (((4 - 1) + 8) × 1))
181431 := (((((1 + 3!))! × (-4) + 1) × (-8 + 1))
181435 := (-5 + ((3! × ((4 - 1)!) × ((8 - 1)))!))
181439 := (((9! - 3!) + 4)/(1⁸) + 1)
181444 := (-4 × (((((4 + 4) + 1)!)/(-8)) - 1))
181446 := (-6 × (((4!/(-4)) × (-((1 - 8)))! - 1))
181449 := ((9!/(4/4) + 1)) + (8 + 1))
181464 := (4! + ((6 × ((4 - 1)!) × ((8 - 1)))!))
181476 := ((6 × ((7 - 4)!) × (1 + ((8 - 1)))!))
181529 := ((9!/2) + ((5 × 18) - 1))
181684 := (4 × ((8! + (61)) + ((8 - 1)))!)
181763 := ((36 × (7! + (1 + 8))) - 1)
182325 := ((-5 + ((2 × 3)!) × ((2⁸) - 1))
182413 := ((3!! + 1) × (-4 - ((2⁸) + 1)))
182439 := (9 × (((3!! + 4) × 28) - 1))
182527 := (((-7 + ((-(2 - 5)))!)) × (2⁸)) - 1
182665 := -((5! + (((6 - 6!) × (2⁸)) - 1))
182736 := ((6^{3!}) + (7! × (28 - 1)))
182835 := (((5 + 3!) - 8) × ((2⁸) - 1))

- 182959 := (((9!/5!) + 9!)/2) + (8 - 1)
183384 := ((4! + ((8!/3)/3!)) × 81)
183457 := (((7!/(5 × 4)) × (3!! + 8)) + 1)
183489 := -((((9! + (8⁴))/3! - 8) - 1))
183557 := ((-(7⁵)) + 5!) × (-(3 + 8) × 1))
183565 := (-5 × (((6! × 5) + 3!) - 8!) + 1))
183605 := (-5 × ((-(0! - 6) × 3!) - ((8! + 1))))
183627 := ((7 + 2) × (6! + ((3⁸⁺¹))))
183864 := -((4! × (6! - 8381)))
183879 := (((9! + 7!)/(8 - 3!)) - (81))
183947 := -((((7! - 4!) + 9!)/(3! - 8) + 1))
183964 := (-4 × (-(6!) - ((9! - 3!)/8) + 1))
184313 := ((3!! × ((1 + 3)⁴)) - (8 - 1))
184319 := (((-(9 - 1)) × 3!!) × (-(4 × 8))) - 1)
184321 := (((((1 + 2)!)! × ((3! - 4)⁸)) + 1))
184324 := (-4 × (((2 × 3!!) × (-4)) - ((8! + 1))))
184328 := (8 × (((2 × 3)!) × (4 × 8)) + 1)
184329 := ((9!/2) + ((3!! × 4) + (8 + 1)))
184344 := (((4⁴) × 3!!) + (-(4 - 8) × 1))!
184352 := (((-(2⁵)) × 3!!) - 4) × (-(8 × 1))
184368 := ((-(8! + 6)) + (3!! × 4!)) × (-(8 × 1))
184377 := (((-7 - ((7! + 3!) × 4)) × (-8)) + 1)
184644 := (((4⁴) × 6!) + ((4 × 81)))
184689 := (9 × (((8! + 6!) × (-4))/(-8)) + 1)
184761 := (((-(1 - 6))!) - ((7⁴))) × (-81)
184832 := ((-2 - 3!!) × (-(8 × 4) × 8 × 1))
184855 := (55 × ((8!/(4 + 8)) + 1))
185329 := (((9! × 2) - 3!!)/5) + ((8! + 1))
185342 := (2 × (((-4 - 3!!) × (-(5! + 8))) - 1))
185343 := (3!! + 4) × (-3 + 5)⁸ - 1
185344 := ((4⁴) × (3!! - ((5 - 8) - 1)))
185395 := (-5 × (((9 × 3) × 5!) - 8!) + 1)
185473 := (((((3! × 7!) × 4!)/5) + 8!) + 1)
185592 := ((((-2 × 9!)/(-5)) + 5!) + ((8 × 1))!)
185631 := (((1 - 3!!) - 6!) × (-(5! + (8 + 1))))
185664 := ((4 × (6⁶)) + (5! × (-(8 × 1))))
185742 := ((2 - (4 × (7! + 5!))) × (-(8 + 1)))
185744 := (-4 × (4 + ((7! + 5!) × (-(8 + 1))))
185763 := (3 × (((6! - 7!) × (-5)) + 8!) + 1))
185766 := (-6 × ((6! × (-(7 × 5) + 8))) - 1))
185848 := (8 × ((4! × ((8 × 5!) + 8)) - 1))
185965 := (-((5⁶) + 9)) - ((-5 × 8!) + 1))
186304 := (4 × (0! + ((3!⁶) - (81))))
186354 := ((4! + 5) × ((3! - 6!) × (-(8 + 1))))
186432 := ((2^{3!}) × ((4 × (6! + 8)) + 1))
186457 := ((7! × 5) - ((-4 × (-6 + 8!)) - 1))
186475 := (-5 - (7! × (-(46 - 8) - 1)))
186492 := ((2 × ((9!/4) + 6)) + ((8 - 1))!)
186517 := ((7! + 1) × (((5 × 6) + 8) - 1))
186534 := ((4! × (3!⁵)) - (6!/(8 × 1)))
186631 := (((1 + 3) × (6⁶)) + (8 - 1))
186632 := (((-2 + 3!) × (6⁶)) + (8 × 1))
186714 := (41 × (7! - ((6 × 81))))
187345 := (-5 × ((4 × (3!! - 7)) - ((8! + 1))))
187353 := (((3! + 5!) + (3⁷)) × 81)
187559 := ((9 × (5! - (-5 × 7!))) - (8! + 1))
188384 := (-4 × (((8!/3!) + 8) × (-(8 - 1))))
188385 := (5 × (8! - (3 × 881)))
190344 := (((-4!) - (4! × 3!!)) × (-(0! + (9 + 1))))
191482 := ((2 - (8!/4)) × (-(19 × 1)))
191488 := (8 × (8! - (4⁻¹⁺⁹⁻¹)))
191522 := (2 × (((2 + 5)!) × 19) + 1)
191664 := (4! × ((-6 - 6!) × (-(1 + 9) + 1)))
191737 := (-((7³)) × ((7!/(-1 × 9)) + 1))
192146 := (((((6! + 4!) + 1)²) - 9!) + 1)
192335 := ((5 - 3!!) × ((3!)/(-2) + (91)))
192768 := 8 × 6 × (7! - 2⁹⁺¹)
193235 := (-5 × (3!! - ((2 × (3⁹)) + 1)))
193375 := (((-(5 × 7)) - (3!! × (-3))) × 91)
193536 := (((((6 + 3)!) / (-5 × 3)) × (-(9 - 1)))
193548 := (((8! × 4!)/5) + ((3 + 9) × 1))
193584 := (4! × (((8!/5) - 3!) + (9 - 1)))
193648 := (((8 × 4) - (6! × 3)) × (-91))
193968 := (((8! - 6!) - 9!) × 3!)/(-(9 + 1))
194048 := ((8^{4+0!}) - (-4 × ((9 - 1))!))
194269 := (-((9⁶)) + (-2 × ((4! - 9!) + 1)))
194337 := ((7 + (3!! × (-3! + 4!))) × (-(9 × 1)))
194355 := ((5 + ((5! × 3!)/(-4))) × (-(9 × 1)))
194364 := ((4 - (6! × (3! + 4!))) × (-(9 × 1)))
194365 := ((((-5 × 6!) × 3!) + 4) × (-9)) + 1)
194368 := (-8 - ((6! × 3) - 4!) × (-91))
194399 := (((9 + 9) × 3!!) × (4! - 9)) - 1

$$\begin{aligned} 194435 &:= (((((5! \times 3!)/(-4)) - 4) \times (-9)) - 1) \\ 194436 &:= (((6! \times (3! + 4!)) + 4) \times (9 \times 1)) \\ 194453 &:= (((((3!! \times 5!) + 4!)/(-4)) \times (-9)) - 1) \\ 195039 &:= -(((9^{3+0!}) + (-5 \times ((9-1)!))) \\ 195648 &:= (-(((8^4) \times 6) + 5!) \times (-9-1)) \\ 195662 &:= ((2+6!) \times (((6 \times 5) \times 9) + 1)) \\ 195685 &:= ((5 \times 8!) - ((65 \times 91))) \\ 195768 &:= (8 \times ((6! - ((7! \times 5) - 9)) \times (-1))) \\ 195833 &:= -((3!! - ((3! \times ((8^5) - 9)) - 1))) \\ 195835 &:= (-5 + ((3!! \times (-8)) - (-5 \times ((9-1)!))) \\ 195836 &:= ((6! \times 3!!) + (((8! - 5) - 9!) + 1)) \\ 195864 &:= ((4! - (6! \times 8)) - (-5 \times ((9-1)!)) \\ 196248 &:= (8! - (4! \times (((2+6!) \times (-9)) + 1))) \\ 196273 &:= (((((3!^7) \times 2) - 6!) - 9!) + 1) \\ 196559 &:= (((9!/5!) \times (56+9)) - 1) \\ 196561 &:= (((1+6)! \times ((5 \times 6) + 9)) + 1) \\ 196563 &:= (3 \times ((6-5) + (6! \times 91))) \\ 196567 &:= (-7 \times ((6! \times (-((5 \times 6) + 9))) - 1)) \\ 196584 &:= (4! - (((8-5) \times 6!) \times (-91))) \\ 196585 &:= (((5+8!) \times 5) - (((-((6-9)))! + 1)!)) \\ 196624 &:= (((4 \times 2)^6) - (6! \times 91)) \\ 196742 &:= ((2 + (-((4-7) \times 6!)) \times 91) \\ 196793 &:= ((39 \times (7! + (-((6-9)!)) - 1) \\ 196833 &:= (3 \times (((3!!/8) \times (6! + 9)) + 1)) \\ 196835 &:= (-5 \times (((-((3^8)) \times (-((6-9)!)) - 1)) \\ 197337 &:= ((7!/(-3)) + (((3^7) \times 91))) \\ 197379 &:= ((-9 + ((7! \times (-3))/7)) \times (-91)) \\ 197568 &:= (((8! \times 6)/5!) \times (7+91)) \\ 197665 &:= (-5 \times ((6! + 67) - ((9-1)!)) \\ 197685 &:= (-5 \times (((8! - 6!) - ((7 \times 9)) \times (-1))) \\ 197965 &:= (-5 \times (((-((6-9)!))! + (7 - ((9-1)!))) \\ 198035 &:= (-5 \times (3!! + ((0! - 8!) - (9-1))) \\ 198045 &:= (-5 \times (((4-0!)! + ((8! + 9) \times (-1)))) \\ 198395 &:= (-5 \times (((-9!) + (3!! \times 8))/9 + 1)) \\ 198435 &:= (-5 \times (3!! + ((4-8!) - (91))) \\ 198555 &:= (-5 \times (((5! \times 5) - 8!) + (9 \times 1))) \\ 198647 &:= (((7+4!) \times ((6! - 8) \times 9)) - 1) \\ 198653 &:= (((3 \times (5+6!)) + 8) \times 91) \\ 198744 &:= ((4! + 4) \times (78 \times 91)) \\ 198795 &:= (5 \times (((9! - 7!) \times 8!)/9! - 1)) \\ 199055 &:= (-5 \times (509 - ((9-1)!)) \\ 199583 &:= (((3! \times 8!)/5!) \times 99) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 199764 &:= ((4-6!) \times ((7!/(-9+9))) + 1)) \\ 200385 &:= (-5 \times (-8!) + (3^{-0!+(0!+2)!})) \\ 200855 &:= ((-5 \times (5-8!)) - (((0!+02)!))! \\ 200856 &:= (-((6! - (5 \times 8!))) - (((0!+0!) + 2)!)) \\ 200873 &:= -(((3!! + 7) + (8! \times (0! - ((0!+2)!)))) \\ 200875 &:= ((-5 \times ((7! \times (-8)) + 0!)) - (((0!+2)!))! \\ 200885 &:= ((5 \times (8! + ((8 \times 0)!)) - (((0!+2)!))! \\ 200886 &:= (-((6! + 8!)) + ((8! + 0!) \times ((0!+2)!)) \\ 201085 &:= (5 \times ((8! - 0!) - (102))) \\ 201285 &:= (5 \times (8! - (21 \times (0! + 2)))) \\ 201358 &:= ((8! \times 5) - (((3! - 1)! + 0!) \times 2)) \\ 201455 &:= (-5 \times ((5+4!) - ((10-2)!)) \\ 201498 &:= 8! \times (9-4) - 102 \\ 201568 &:= (8! - 6) \times 5 - 1 \times 02 \\ 201572 &:= ((2 \times 7) \times ((5!^{1+0!}) - 2)) \\ 201591 &:= (-((1 \times 9)) - (-5 \times ((10-2)!)) \\ 201597 &:= (((7!/9) \times 5!) - 1) \times (0! + 2)) \\ 201598 &:= ((8! \times ((9-5) + 1)) - 02) \\ 201599 &:= (((9!/9) \times 5) - (1^02)) \\ 201602 &:= (((20 \times ((6+1)!)) + 0!) \times 2) \\ 201615 &:= (5 \times (((((1+6) + 1)! + 0!) + 2)) \\ 201624 &:= (4! - (((2+6)! \times (-10/2))) \\ 201625 &:= ((-5 - ((2+6)!)) \times (-10/2)) \\ 201648 &:= -((8! + (4! \times (((6+1)! + 0!) \times (-2)))) \\ 201654 &:= (4! - (-5 \times (6 + ((10-2)!)) \\ 201655 &:= (-5 \times (-((5+6)) - ((10-2)!)) \\ 201658 &:= ((8! \times 5) + ((6 \times 10) - 2)) \\ 201755 &:= (5! - (-5 \times (7 + ((10-2)!))) \\ 201895 &:= (((-59) - 8!) \times (-10/2)) \\ 202315 &:= ((-5 \times (1 - ((3! + 2)!)) + (((0! + 2)!))! \\ 202318 &:= (((8! \times (-1 + 3!)) - 2) + (((0! + 2)!))! \\ 202335 &:= ((-5 \times (-3 - ((3! + 2)!)) + (((0! + 2)!))! \\ 202585 &:= (5 \times (8! - ((5-202))) \\ 203038 &:= ((8! \times (3! - 0!)) - ((3!! - 0!) \times (-2))) \\ 203385 &:= (-5 \times (-8!) - ((3! - 3!)/(0-2))) \\ 203734 &:= (43 \times (7! - 302)) \\ 203742 &:= ((-2 + 4!) \times ((7 \times 3)^{0!+2})) \\ 204245 &:= (5 \times (((4 \times 2)! + ((4! - 0!)^2))) \\ 204304 &:= ((-4 \times ((0! + 3!) - ((4+0!)!))!^2) \\ 204482 &:= ((284 \times (((4-0!)!))! + 2) \\ 204485 &:= (5 \times (8! + ((4! \times 4!) + ((0 \times 2)!))!)) \\ 204687 &:= (7 \times ((-8 + ((6!/4) - 0!)^2)) \end{aligned}$$

- 204802 := $(2 \times (0! + ((8 \times 40)^2)))$
204824 := $(4! + ((2 \times ((8 \times 40)^2)))$
204845 := $(5 \times ((4! + 8!) + ((4! + 0!)^2)))$
205175 := $(-5 \times (-(((7 + 1)! - 5)) - (((0! + 2)!)))$
205185 := $(5 \times (((8! + ((1 + 5)!)) - 0!) - 2))$
205335 := $((5 \times 3) \times ((-3 + 5!)^{02}))$
205379 := $((9 + ((7 + 3) \times 5))^{01+2})$
205395 := $((59^3) + ((5 - 0!)^2))$
205396 := $(-(6!) + (((9!/3!) - (50)^2))$
205448 := $((8!/4!) + 4) \times (5! + 02)$
205584 := $(4! \times ((8!/5) + (502)))$
205768 := $((-8 + 6!) \times ((-7 + ((5 - 0!)!)^2))$
205785 := $(5 \times (8! + (((7 \times 5!) - 0!) - 2)))$
205805 := $(-5 \times (-(((0! + 8!) + 5!)) - (((0! + 2)!)))$
206724 := $(42 \times ((7! - ((6 - 0!)!) + 2))$
206758 := $((((8! \times 5) + 7!) + ((6 - 0!)!) - 2)$
206784 := $(-((4 - 8)) \times (7! + (6^{(0!+2)!}))$
207264 := $(4! \times (((6! + 2) - 7!) \times (0 - 2)))$
207276 := $(-((6! + ((7! - 2) \times (-7)))) \times ((0! + 2)!)$
207314 := $((4! \times ((1 + 3!) - 7!)) - 0!) \times (-2)$
207326 := $((6^2) \times (3! + ((7! - 0!))) + 2)$
207336 := $(-6 \times ((-3!) \times (3! + ((7! - 0!)))) - 2)$
207344 := $(-4 \times (4 + (3! \times (-70 + 2))))$
207346 := $((6! \times 4!) \times 3! - 7) \times 02$
207349 := $(-9 - (((4! \times (3! - 7!)) + 0!) \times 2))$
207354 := $((4! \times ((5 \times 3!) + 7!)) - ((0! + 2)!)$
207358 := $((8! \times 5!) \times 3) / 70 - 2$
207359 := $((9! / (-5)) + ((3!^7) - ((0 \times 2)!))$
207362 := $((2 \times ((6 + 3)!)) / (-7) - 0!) \times (-2)$
207374 := $((4! \times (-7!) + 3!) - 7) \times (0 - 2)$
207384 := $((4 + ((8! \times 3!) / 7)) \times ((0! + 2)!)$
207394 := $((4 \times 9) \times (3! + (7! + 0!))) - 2$
207515 := $((5! + 1) \times 5) \times (7^{0!+2})$
207649 := $((9!/4) - 6!) + (7^{(0!+2)!})$
208384 := $((4 \times 8!) / (-3)) + (8^{(0!+2)!})$
208765 := $(-5 \times (-(((6! - 7) + 8!)) - (((0! + 2)!)))$
208849 := $((9 + 48) \times 8 + 0!)^2$
209185 := $(5^8) - (((1 \times 9)! / 02)$
209664 := $((4! \times 6) \times ((6! + 9) - 0!) \times 2)$
211675 := $(-5 - ((7! \times (-6 + 1))) \times ((1 + 2)!)$
211676 := $((-6 \times ((7! \times (-6 + 1))) + 1)) + 2$
211677 := $((7! \times (7 \times 6)) - ((1 \times 1) + 2))$
211678 := $((8! - 7!) \times 6 - ((1 - 1) + 2))$
211679 := $((9! \times 7) / (-6) + (1 + 1)) / (-2)$
211694 := $((4! + 9!) \times (6 + 1)) / 12$
211724 := $((42 \times (7! + 1)) + (1 \times 2))$
211757 := $(-7 \times (-5 - ((7! + 1) \times ((1 + 2)!)))$
211776 := $(-6 \times ((-7 \times (7! + (1 + 1))) - 2))$
213698 := $(-((8! - ((9!/6!)^{3-1}) + 2))$
214369 := $((9! / (((6 - 3)!)) - 41)^2$
214848 := $(-8 \times (4! - ((8! \times 4) / ((1 + 2)!)))$
215635 := $(-5 - ((3! \times (-((6! - 5!) - 1))) / 2))$
215664 := $(4! - ((6! \times ((6! - 5!) - 1)) / (-2)))$
216003 := $((300 \times 6!) + (1 + 2))$
216025 := $((5^2) \times (0! - (6! \times (-12))))$
216634 := $(43 \times ((6! \times (6 + 1)) - 2))$
216717 := $((7! \times (1 + (7 \times 6))) - (1 + 2))$
216718 := $((8 - 1)! \times ((7 \times 6) + 1)) - 2$
216734 := $((43 \times 7!) + ((6 + 1) \times 2))$
217296 := $((6! - 9!) / (2 - 7)) \times (1 + 2)$
217346 := $(-6 \times ((4^3!) - ((7 + 1)!)) + 2)$
217728 := $((8! \times (-27)) / (7 - 12))$
218385 := $(5 \times ((8! - 3) - (8! / (-12))))$
218405 := $(-5 \times (-0! - (((4! - 8)! / (12)!)))$
219576 := $((6^7) + 5!) - (9! / ((1 + 2)!))$
219744 := $((4 \times ((4 + 7)! - 9!)) / (((1 + 2)!))$
219961 := $((1 + 6)! / 9 - (91)^2)$
221398 := $(8! - ((9! - 3!) / (-1 \times 2))) + 2)$
221698 := $(8! - ((9! - ((6 - 1)!)) / (-2)) + 2)$
221729 := $(-9 + (((-2 \times 7!) + 1) \times (-22)))$
221738 := $((8! / (3 - 7)) + 1) \times (-22)$
221748 := $(8! + ((4! - ((7 \times 1) + 2)!)) / (-2))$
221756 := $((6 + 5) \times 7! - 1) \times (2 + 2)$
221758 := $((8! \times ((5 + 7) - 1)) / 2) - 2$
221776 := $(-6 + ((7! + 7!) + 1) \times 22)$
221784 := $((4! + 8!) - (((7 \times 1) + 2)! / (-2))$
221824 := $(-(((4 \times 2)! - (8^{(1+2) \times 2})))$
221826 := $(-(((6 + 2)! - (8^{(1+2)!} + 2)))$
221828 := $(-((8! - 2) - ((8^{(1+2)!} + 2)))$
221838 := $((8^3!) - 8!) + (12 + 2)$
221848 := $(-((8! - 4!) - (8^{(1+2) \times 2})))$
222048 := $((-8!) + ((-4!) + (((0! + 2)!)) / 2)) / 2$

$$\begin{aligned}
 222312 &:= (((21^3) + 2) \times ((2 + 2)!)) \\
 222476 &:= (6! - (((7! \times (4! - 2)) - 2) \times (-2))) \\
 222784 &:= ((4! - 8) \times (((7 - 2)! - 2)^2)) \\
 223218 &:= (-8! - (((((1 + 2)! + 3!!)^2) / (-2))) \\
 223488 &:= -(((8! + 8!) + ((4^3) \times (-22)))) \\
 223729 &:= (((9 + 2) \times (7 + (3!^2)))^2) \\
 223776 &:= (((6! + 7!) - (7^3)) \times (-2)) - 2 \\
 223778 &:= (((8! / (-7)) + ((7^3)^2)) \times 2) \\
 223872 &:= (2 \times ((7! + (8 \times 3!)) \times 22)) \\
 223998 &:= (((8! + 9!) / (-9)) \times (-3 + 2)) - 2 \\
 224384 &:= (((4^8) + (3!^{4+2})) \times 2) \\
 224635 &:= (-5 - ((3! \times 6!) \times ((4! + 2) \times (-2)))) \\
 224642 &:= (((((2 + 4!) \times 6!) \times 4!) / 2) + 2) \\
 224664 &:= (4! + ((6! \times (-6)) \times ((4! + 2) \times (-2)))) \\
 224676 &:= ((-6 + (((7! + 6!) / 4!) \times 2))^2) \\
 224715 &:= (-5 \times (1 - (((7! / 4!) + 2)^2)) \\
 224735 &:= (-5 \times (-3 - (((7! / 4!) + 2)^2)) \\
 224736 &:= (((6! \times 3!) + 7!) + 4) \times ((2 + 2)!)) \\
 224796 &:= ((-69 - 7!) \times (-42 + 2)) \\
 224982 &:= ((2 \times 8!) + ((9^4) \times 22)) \\
 225266 &:= ((-6 \times ((6! + 2) \times (-52))) + 2) \\
 225504 &:= (((4 - 0!)!^5) \times (5 + ((2 + 2)!)) \\
 225562 &:= ((2 + (6^5)) \times (5 + ((2 + 2)!)) \\
 225784 &:= ((4 + (((8! \times (-7)) / 5) \times 2)) \times (-2)) \\
 225786 &:= (-6 - (((8! \times (-7)) / 5) \times (2 + 2))) \\
 225788 &:= (((((8! + 8!) \times 7) / (-5)) + 2) \times (-2)) \\
 225804 &:= (((4 - 0!)! + ((8! / 5!)^2)) \times 2) \\
 225806 &:= (((-6 - 0!) - ((8! / 5!)^2)) \times (-2)) \\
 225808 &:= ((8 + (((08)! / 5!)^2)) \times 2) \\
 225814 &:= (4! - ((1 - ((8! / 5!)^2)) \times 2)) \\
 225824 &:= (((4^2) + ((8! / 5!)^2)) \times 2) \\
 225834 &:= (((4! - 3) + ((8! / 5!)^2)) \times 2) \\
 225876 &:= ((-((6 \times 7)) - ((8! / 5!)^2)) \times (-2)) \\
 226086 &:= ((6 \times (8! + 0!)) + (6! \times (-22))) \\
 226574 &:= (((-4 \times ((7 - 5!) - 6))^2) - 2) \\
 226575 &:= ((-5 + 7!) \times (5 \times ((6/2)^2))) \\
 226576 &:= (((6 - 7) + 5!) \times (6 - 2)^2) \\
 226755 &:= ((-5 - (-5 \times 7!)) \times ((6/2)^2)) \\
 226775 &:= (-5 \times (((7 - 7!) - ((6 + 2)!)) - 2)) \\
 226785 &:= ((5! / 8) \times (((7! \times 6) - 2) / 2)) \\
 226795 &:= (((5 \times 9) \times 7!) - ((6/2) + 2)) \\
 226799 &:= (9! + (((9 \times 7!) \times 6) + 2) / (-2)) \\
 226801 &:= (((((10)! / 8) + 6) / 2) - 2) \\
 226805 &:= (5 \times ((0! + 8!) + ((6 + (2/2))!)) \\
 226824 &:= (4! + (((2 + 8)! / ((6 - 2)^2))) \\
 226937 &:= (((7! + 3) \times (9 + (6^2))) + 2) \\
 227664 &:= ((4! + 6!) \times (6 \times ((7^2) + 2))) \\
 228472 &:= (2 \times ((7! \times 4!) - ((82^2)))) \\
 228508 &:= (((8 - 0!)^5 + 8!) \times (2 + 2)) \\
 228656 &:= -((6! - ((56 \times ((8^2)^2)))) \\
 229441 &:= ((-1 + ((4! - (4! \times (-9))) \times 2))^2) \\
 229538 &:= ((8! + (3!^5)) + ((9! / 2) + 2)) \\
 229755 &:= (5! + (((5 \times 7) \times ((9^2)^2))) \\
 230395 &:= (-5 + (((9! / 3!) - ((0! + 3)!))^2)) \\
 230396 &:= (((6! / 9) \times 3!) - 0!) \times (3! - 2)) \\
 230424 &:= (4! + ((2 \times 40) \times 3!^2)) \\
 230425 &:= ((5^2) + ((4 \times (-((0! - 3)!))^2)) \\
 230436 &:= ((6 \times 3!) + ((4 \times (-((0! - 3)!))^2)) \\
 230444 &:= (44 + ((4 \times (-((0! - 3)!))^2)) \\
 230448 &:= (8 \times (4 - ((-40) \times 3!) - 2)) \\
 230496 &:= (6 \times (((9 + 4) + 0!)^{3! - 2})) \\
 230499 &:= (99 + ((4 \times (-((0! - 3)!))^2)) \\
 230528 &:= (-((8^2)) \times ((-5 \times ((03)!)) - 2)) \\
 230976 &:= (((6! - 7) \times 9) - 0!) \times (3!^2) \\
 231336 &:= ((6! - 3!) \times ((3 \times ((1 \times 3)!))^2)) \\
 231361 &:= ((1 + ((6! / (-3)) \times (1 - 3)))^2) \\
 231478 &:= ((((-8 + 7!) \times (4! - 1)) + 3) \times 2) \\
 231725 &:= ((-5 - (-2 \times 7!)) \times (-1 + ((3! - 2)!)) \\
 231799 &:= ((9! - 9) - (((7 + 1)^{3!}) / 2)) \\
 231808 &:= (((8 + 0!)! - ((8^{1 \times 3!}) / 2)) \\
 231809 &:= ((9! + 0!) - ((8^{1 \times 3!}) / 2)) \\
 231834 &:= (((4 + 3)! + ((8! - 1) \times (-3))) \times (-2)) \\
 231835 &:= (-5 - (((-3 \times 8!) + ((1 + 3)!)) \times 2)) \\
 231838 &:= ((8! \times 3!) + ((8! / (-1 + 3))) - 2)) \\
 231839 &:= (((9! \times 3!) / 8) - 1) - ((3! + 2)!)) \\
 231842 &:= ((-((2 - 48)) \times ((1 + 3)!)) + 2) \\
 231848 &:= ((8! / (-4)) + (((8! + 1) \times 3!) + 2)) \\
 231864 &:= ((46 \times ((8 - 1)!)) + ((3! - 2)!)) \\
 231876 &:= ((6! - 7!) + ((81 \times 3!)^2)) \\
 232322 &:= (-2 + ((2 + ((3! \times (-2)) / (-3)))^2))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 232464 &:= (-((4! - 6!)) \times (-((4! + 2)) - (3!!/(-2)))) \\ 232559 &:= (9! - ((-5 - ((5! + 2) \times (-3)))^2)) \\ 232631 &:= (-1 - (-(((3 \times 6)^2)) \times (3!! - 2))) \\ 232632 &:= ((2 - 3!!) \times (-((6^2) \times (3^2)))) \\ 232947 &:= (((7! + 4!) \times (-92)) - 3!)/(-2) \\ 233118 &:= (-81) \times (((1 - 3!!) - 3!!) \times 2) \\ 233135 &:= (-5 \times (31 - ((3!^{3!}) + 2))) \\ 233145 &:= (-5 \times ((4! + 1) - ((3!^{3!}) - 2))) \\ 233155 &:= -((5! - (-5 \times (1 - (3!^{3 \times 2})))))) \\ 233184 &:= (-4 \times ((-81) \times 3!!) + ((3! - 2)!)) \\ 233199 &:= (9 \times (-9 + ((-1 \times 3!!) \times (-3!^2)))) \\ 233235 &:= (5 \times ((3!^{2 \times 3}) - (3^2))) \\ 233254 &:= -((4! + ((-5 \times ((2 \times 3)^{3!}) + 2))) \\ 233259 &:= (-9 - ((-5 \times (-2 + (3!^{3!}))) + 2)) \\ 233265 &:= (-5 \times ((6/2) - (3!^{3 \times 2}))) \\ 233268 &:= (((8! - (6! \times 2)) \times 3!) - (3! \times 2)) \\ 233292 &:= (((2 \times 9)^2) \times 3!!) + (3! \times 2) \\ 233294 &:= ((-4 \times ((-(9^2)) \times 3!!) - 3) + 2) \\ 233304 &:= (4! + (((03)!^{3!}) \times (3 + 2))) \\ 233305 &:= (5 \times (((03)!^{3!}) + ((3 + 2)))) \\ 233314 &:= (4! + ((-1 + 3!) \times ((3!^{3!}) + 2))) \\ 233315 &:= (-5 \times (1 - (((3!^{3!}) + 3!) + 2))) \\ 233316 &:= (((6 - 1) \times (3!^{3!})) + (3!^2)) \\ 233325 &:= (5 \times (((2 \times 3)^{3!}) + (3^2))) \\ 233334 &:= (4! + (((3!^{3!}) + 3!) \times (3 + 2))) \\ 233335 &:= (5 \times ((3!^{3!}) + ((3 \times 3) + 2))) \\ 233345 &:= (-5 \times (-4 - ((3!^{3!}) + (3^2)))) \\ 233355 &:= (5! - (-5 \times ((3!^{3!}) - (3^2)))) \\ 233367 &:= ((-7 - 6!) \times (3 - ((3 \times 3!)^2))) \\ 233375 &:= (-5 \times (-((7 \times 3)) - ((3!^{3!}) - 2))) \\ 233395 &:= (-5 \times (9 - ((3!^{3!}) + 32))) \\ 233405 &:= (-5 \times ((0! - 4!) - ((3!^{3!}) + 2))) \\ 233415 &:= (-5 \times ((-1 - 4!) - ((3!^{3!}) + 2))) \\ 233472 &:= (-((2^{7+4})) \times (3! - ((3 + 2)!)) \\ 233475 &:= ((57 \times (4^3)) + (3!/2)) \\ 233493 &:= (-3 + (9 \times (4! - (3!! \times (-3!^2)))))) \\ 233496 &:= ((6 \times 9) \times (4 + (3! \times ((3 \times 2)!)))) \\ 233555 &:= (-5 \times (-55 - (3!^{3 \times 2}))) \\ 233602 &:= (-2 + ((0! + 6!) \times ((3 \times 3!)^2))) \\ 233604 &:= (-4 \times ((0! + 6!) \times (-((3 \times 3)^2)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 233655 &:= ((5 \times ((5^6) \times 3)) - ((3 \times 2)!)) \\ 233675 &:= (((((5^7) + 6) \times 3) - 3!!) + 2) \\ 233735 &:= (-((5! + 3)) + ((-((7^3!)) + 3!!) \times (-2))) \\ 233738 &:= (-(((8 - 3)!)) + ((-((7^3!)) + 3!!) \times (-2))) \\ 233755 &:= ((-((5^5)) - 7!) + (3! \times ((3! + 2)!)) \\ 233835 &:= ((5! + (3^8)) \times (3 + 32)) \\ 233858 &:= ((8!/(-5)) - ((8! \times (-3 + 3))) - 2) \\ 233926 &:= (((((6! + 2) \times 9) \times 3!) \times 3!) - 2) \\ 233928 &:= (8 \times (((29 \times 3!) - 3)^2)) \\ 233953 &:= (3!! - ((-5 \times (-9 + (3!^{3!}))) + 2)) \\ 233985 &:= (-5 \times (-8!) + ((-9 \times 3!!) + (3!/2))) \\ 234232 &:= (((-2 + ((3! - 2)!))^4) - ((3! - 2)!)) \\ 234242 &:= ((-2 + ((4! - 2)^4)) - (3! \times 2)) \\ 234244 &:= (-4 + (((4! - 2)^4) - 3!) - 2) \\ 234245 &:= (-5 + (((4! - 2)^4) - (3 \times 2))) \\ 234246 &:= (-6 + (((4! - 2)^4) - 3!) + 2) \\ 234248 &:= ((((((8 - 4)! - 2)^4) - 3!) - 2) \\ 234249 &:= (-9 + (((4! - 2)^{4!/3!}) + 2)) \\ 234251 &:= (-((1 \times 5)) + ((-2 + 4!)^{3! - 2})) \\ 234253 &:= (-3 + 5^2)^4 - 3!/2 \\ 234254 &:= (((4 \times 5) + 2)^{4!/3!}) - 2 \\ 234255 &:= (((5!/5) - 2)^4) - (3 - 2) \\ 234259 &:= (((((9 - 5)! - 2)^4) + (3!/2)) \\ 234261 &:= (-((1 - 6)) + ((-2 + 4!)^{3! - 2})) \\ 234262 &:= (((-2 + ((6 - 2)!))^4) + (3 \times 2)) \\ 234264 &:= (((((4 \times 6) - 2)^4) + 3!) + 2) \\ 234292 &:= (((2 + 9) \times 2)^4) + (3!^2) \\ 234305 &:= (((5^{0!+3!}) - 4!) \times 3) + 2 \\ 234357 &:= (((7! \times ((5! - 3) - 4!)) - 3!)/2) \\ 234435 &:= (((5^3!) + 4) \times (4! - (3^2))) \\ 234576 &:= ((6^7) - (((5 + 4)!)/(3! + 2))) \\ 234616 &:= (((6 + 16)^4) - (3!!/(-2))) \\ 234639 &:= (-93) \times ((-6 - ((4 + 3)!)/2) \\ 234874 &:= (((4! - 7) \times (-8 + (4!^3))) + 2) \\ 234974 &:= (((4! + ((7 - 9)))^4) + 3!!) - 2 \\ 234976 &:= (((6 + 7) + 9)^4) + ((3 \times 2)!)) \\ 234984 &:= -((4! + (-((8 + 9)) \times (4!^{3!/2})))) \\ 235198 &:= -((((8! + (9! \times (1 - 5)))/3!) + 2)) \\ 235224 &:= 4! \times (-2 + 2)! + 5! + 3^2 \\ 235225 &:= ((5 + (((2 + 2)! \times 5!)/3!))^2 \end{aligned}$$

- 235226** := $((6^2) - ((2 + 5)^{3!})) \times (-2)$
235234 := $(-(4^3) - (((2 + 5)^{3!}) \times (-2)))$
235245 := $(-5 + ((4! - ((2 + 5)^{3!})) \times (-2)))$
235258 := $(-((8 \times 5)) - (((2 + 5)^{3!}) \times (-2)))$
235267 := $((((7^6) \times 2) + 5) - (3!^2))$
235274 := $(-(4! - (((7 \times (2 + 5))^3 \times 2)))$
235277 := $(-7 + ((-7 + ((2 + 5)^{3!})) \times 2))$
235278 := $-8 + (7^{(-2+5)!} - 3!) \times 2$
235281 := $(-1 + ((-8 + ((2 + 5)^{3!})) \times 2))$
235285 := $(-((5 + 8)) - (((2 + 5)^{3!}) \times (-2)))$
235289 := $(-((9!/8!) + (((2 + 5)^{3!}) \times (-2))))$
235292 := $((-2 + 9)^{(-2+5)!} - 3) \times 2$
235299 := $((9/9) - (((2 + 5)^{3!}) \times (-2)))$
235302 := $2 \times ((-0! + 3 + 5)^{3!} + 2)$
235369 := $(-((9! - 6!)) + ((3!! + 53)^2))$
235372 := $(2 \times ((7^{3!}) + (5 + 32)))$
235374 := $(-4 - (((7^{3!}) + (5!/3)) \times (-2)))$
235386 := $(6 \times (8! - (((3! \times 5) + 3)^2)))$
235437 := $((7! - 3) + (((4! \times 5!)/3!)^2))$
235438 := $((((83 \times 4) - 5) \times 3!) - 2)$
235468 := $((-8 - 6!) + (((4 \times 5!) + 3!)^2))$
235594 := $((((4 \times (9^5)) + 5!) - 3!) - 2)$
235836 := $(6 \times ((-((3! - (8 \times 5)))^3) + 2))$
235874 := $((4! \times 78) \times (5! + 3!)) + 2$
235879 := $((9! + 7) + (-8 \times ((5! + 3!)^2)))$
235924 := $((4! + 2) \times (((9!/5!) \times 3) + 2))$
235953 := $(-((3^5)) - (-((9^5)) \times (3! - 2)))$
235954 := $((4 \times (5! + (9^5))) - 3!) - 2$
236016 := $(6! - ((-1 + ((0! + 6)^{3!})) \times (-2)))$
236148 := $((8 \times 41) \times 6!) - (3! \times 2)$
236154 := $((4! \times (5! - ((1 + 6)!)) + 3) \times (-2))$
236158 := $((-8 \times ((5! - ((1 + 6)!)) \times 3!)) - 2)$
236168 := $((8! \times 6) + ((1 - 6!) \times (3! + 2)))$
236184 := $((4! - (8! \times (1 + 6))) + (3!!^2))$
236188 := $(-8 + ((81 \times ((6 - 3)!)^2))$
236193 := $(-3 + ((9^{-1+6}) \times (3! - 2)))$
236194 := $((4! \times (9^{-1+6}))/3!) - 2$
236288 := $(-(8! + (-((8^2)) \times ((6! \times 3!) + 2))))$
236384 := $((4 \times 83) \times ((6! - 3!) - 2))$
236535 := $(((((5^{3!}) \times (-5)) - 6!) \times 3!)/(-2))$
236714 := $(-4!) + ((-(((1 \times 7)^6)) - 3!) \times (-2)))$
236726 := $((6! \times 2) - ((-((7^6)) + 3!) \times 2))$
236727 := $(-7 - ((-((2 - (7^6))) + 3!) \times (-2)))$
236728 := $(-((8 + 2)) - ((-((7^6)) - 3!) \times 2))$
236729 := $(-9 + (2 \times ((7^6) + ((3 \times 2)!)))$
236731 := $(-1 - ((3!! + ((7^6) - 3)) \times (-2)))$
236732 := $((((2 \times 3)! + ((7^6) - 3)) \times 2)$
236734 := $((4 + 3!!) + ((7^6) - 3!) \times 2)$
236736 := $((((6/3!) - ((7^6))) - 3!) \times (-2))$
236737 := $(-7 - ((-((3 + (7^6))) - 3!) \times 2))$
236738 := $((8 - 3!) \times ((7^6) + ((3 \times 2)!))$
236741 := $(-((1 - 4)) - ((-((7^6)) - 3!) \times 2))$
236742 := $((((2 - 4) - (7^6)) - 3!) \times (-2))$
236743 := $(-3 - ((-((4 + (7^6))) - 3!) \times 2))$
236744 := $((((4!/4)! + ((7^6) + 3)) \times 2)$
236746 := $((6! + 4) + (7^{(6-3)!})) \times 2$
236753 := $((3 \times 5) - ((-((7^6)) - 3!) \times 2))$
236755 := $(((-5 - 5!) - 7!) - (-6 \times ((3! + 2)!))$
236758 := $((8! + ((5! + 7!)/(-6))) \times 3! - 2)$
236762 := $(2 \times ((6! + ((7^6))) + (3! \times 2)))$
236786 := $((6 \times 8) - ((-((7^6)) - 3!) \times 2))$
236799 := $((-((9 \times 9)) - 7!) - (-6 \times ((3! + 2)!))$
236847 := $(-(7! - (((4 - 8!) \times (-6)) - (3^2))))$
236854 := $((((-4 - 5!) + 8!) - 6!) \times 3! - 2)$
236856 := $(-6 \times (((5! - 8!) + 6!) + 3!) - 2)$
236869 := $((-9 - 6!) + (((8! - 6!) \times 3!) - 2))$
236875 := $(-5! \times 7 + 8!) \times 6 - 3 - 2$
236892 := $(-(((2 - 9)))! + ((8! \times (-6)) - (3! \times 2)))$
236897 := $(-(((7! - 9) + (((8! \times (-6)) - 3!) - 2)))$
236928 := $(8! + (((2^{9+6}) \times (3 \times 2))))$
236935 := $(5 \times (3!! - (-9 - ((6^{3!}) + 2))))$
236974 := $(47 \times (((9 - (6/3)))! + 2))$
237068 := $((8 \times 6) - 0!) \times ((7! + 3!) - 2)$
237164 := $((46 + 1) \times (7! + 3!)) + 2$
237238 := $((8! \times 3!) - 2) - 7! - (3! / (-2))$
237276 := $((6 + (((7 + 2)!/7!))^3) / 2)$
237384 := $((4! + 8!) \times 3! - 7!) - (3! / (-2))$
237398 := $((8! / (-9)) + (-3!) \times (7 - ((3! + 2)!)))$
237466 := $(6! - (((6! + 4) + (7^{3!})) \times (-2)))$
237475 := $((5 + 7!) \times 47) - (3! / (-2))$
237486 := $(-6 \times ((-((8! - 4!) + 7)) + 3!) + 2)$

- 237556 := (((6! × 55) - 7) × 3!) - 2
237576 := ((6⁷) - (5! × (-7 - (3! / (-2))))
237586 := -((((6! - 8!) - ((5 - 7))) × 3!) + 2))
237595 := ((-5 - 9!) + (5! × (7! - (3!²))))
237598 := (((8! - ((-(((9 - 5) - 7))))!) × 3!) - 2)
237606 := (6 × ((0! - 6!) + (((7 + 3) - 2)!))
237608 := (((((8! + 0!) × 6) - 7!) + 3!) + 2)
237628 := (((((8! - 2) - 6!) + 7) × 3!) - 2)
237636 := (6 × ((3! - 6!) + (((7 + 3) - 2)!))
237638 := (((((8! + 3!) × 6) - 7!) + 3!) + 2)
237642 := (((((2 × 4)!) - 6!) + 7) × (3 × 2))
237644 := ((((((4 + 4)!) - 6!) + 7) × 3!) + 2)
237655 := (-55) × ((6! - 7!) - (3 - 2))
237688 := (((((8 + 8!) - 6!) + 7) × 3!) - 2)
237696 := (-6 × (((-9 + 6!) - 7) - ((3! + 2)!))
237698 := (((((8! + 9) - 6!) + 7) × 3!) + 2)
237735 := (-5 × (-((3⁷)) + (7! × (-3²))))
237743 := (3! - ((-47) × (7! + 3)) - 2)
237744 := (4! × ((4! × (-7)) - ((7! - 3) × (-2))))
237804 := (((4 - 0)!) × (8! - ((7³) × 2))
237864 := (-((4⁶)) + (((8! + 7) × 3!) - 2)
237886 := ((6 × 8!) - ((8! / (7 + 3)) + 2))
237951 := (((1 - 5!) × (-9 - 7!)) - ((3²)!))
238136 := (((-631) + 8!) × 3!) + 2)
238137 := -7 + (-3 + 1)! + 8³²
238138 := (((8! - (((3! + 1)! / 8)) × 3!) - 2)
238142 := (-2 + (((4! × (-1)) + (8³)²))
238144 := (((-4 × ((4 - 1)!) + (8³)²))
238176 := (((6⁷) - ((1 × 8)!) + (3! × (-2)))
238315 := ((-5 × (1 + 3!)) + (8! × (3 × 2)))
238316 := (6! - (((-1 - 3!) + 8!) × (-3!)) - 2))
238318 := (8! + (((-1 + 3!) × (8! - 3!)) - 2))
238323 := (((3! - 2) × 3!) - ((8! - 3!)) / 2)
238328 := (((8/2)!) + 38)^{3! / 2}
238331 := ((-1 + 3!) - (-3!) × ((8! - 3!) + 2))
238332 := (((2 × 3)!) - (-3!) × ((8! - 3!) + 2))
238335 := ((-5 × (3! - 3)) + (8! × (3 × 2)))
238336 := (6! + (((3 - 3!) + 8!) × 3!) - 2))
238346 := (6! + (((4 - 3!) + 8!) × 3!) + 2))
238356 := (((6! - 5!) - 3!) - 8!) × (-3 × 2))
238446 := (-6 × (((4! × 4!) - 8!) + (3! / 2))
238448 := ((8 + (((4! × 4!) - 8!) × 3)) × (-2))
238457 := (((7 - (5! × 4!)) × (-83)) - 2)
238462 := (((((-((2 - 6)))! × 4!) - 8!) × (-3!)) - 2)
238464 := ((4! × 6!) + ((48³) × 2))
238466 := (((6! - (6⁴)) + 8!) × 3!) + 2)
238476 := (-((((6⁷) - 4) - 8)) + (3!²))
238533 := (3 × ((3! × 5!) - (83²)))
238536 := (-6 × (3! - (((5! + 8!) + (3!²))))
238555 := (-((5⁵)) - ((5! + (8! × (-3))) × 2))
238558 := (((((8 - 5!) × 5) + 8!) × 3!) - 2)
238576 := (((-((6⁷)) + 5!) - 8) + (3!²))
238584 := (4! - (-((8! / 5!)) × ((-8 + 3!) - 2)))
238607 := ((7⁰6) - ((8! × (-3)) + 2))
238675 := (-((5⁷)) - ((6! - 8!) × (3! + 2)))
238678 := (((8! - ((7! - 6!) / 8)) × 3!) - 2)
238734 := ((43 × (7! + (8³))) - 2)
238755 := (-((5⁵)) + (((-7 + 8!) × 3!) + 2))
238784 := ((48 × 7!) - ((8! / 3!)²))
238786 := (((-((6 × 87)) + 8!) × 3!) - 2)
238833 := (-3 + (3! × (8! - ((8³) + 2))))
238836 := (((6 - 3)!) × (8! - ((8³) + 2)))
238838 := (-8 + ((3! × (8! - (8³))) - 2))
238839 := (-9 - (3 × ((8! - (8³)) × (-2))))
238846 := (((-((64 × 8)) + 8!) × 3!) - 2)
238848 := (((8⁴) / 8) - 8!) × (-3 × 2))
238896 := ((6! - (9! / 8!)) × (8! / ((3 + 2)!))
238984 := (((-489) + 8!) × 3!) - 2)
238986 := ((6 × (8! - 9)) - ((8 × 3!) / 2))
239034 := ((-4 × (3! + ((0! - (9! / 3!)))) - 2)
239036 := (((6 × (3! + 0!)) - 9!) / 3) × (-2))
239094 := (((4 × 9) + 0!) × 9) × (3! - 2))
239397 := ((7! - (((9! / 3) + 9!) - 3!)) / (-2))
239518 := ((((((8 + 1) + 5)!) / 9!) - 3!) - 2)
239522 := (((((2 × (2 + 5)))! / 9!) - 3!) + 2)
239573 := ((37 × (-5 - (-9 × 3!))) - 2)
239586 := (6 × (8! - (((5! + 9) × 3) + 2))
239616 := ((6¹⁺⁶) - ((9 - 3) + 2)!)
239648 := ((8! + ((-4 - (6! / (-9)))³)) / 2)
239668 := -((8! + ((-(((6⁶) + 9)) × 3!) + 2))
239679 := (9! - (((7 + 6) × 9) × 3²))
239706 := (6 × (((0! + 7)!) - 9) + (3! / (-2)))
239733 := -(((((-3 + 3!)⁷) - (9! / (-3)) × (-2)))

$$\begin{aligned} 239734 &:= (-4!) - ((-(37 \times 9)) \times 3!) + 2) \\ 239736 &:= ((6! \times (37 \times 9)) - ((3! - 2)!) \\ 239754 &:= (((-4 + 5!) + 7!) \times (-93)) / (-2) \\ 239797 &:= (((7 - (9! / (-7))) - (9^3)) / (-2) \\ 239805 &:= (5 \times (((0! + (8 \times 9)) \times 3)^2)) \\ 239814 &:= (((4 - 1))! \times ((8! + 9) + (3! / (-2)))) \\ 239826 &:= (-6 \times (((-2 - 8!) - 9) - (3! / (-2)))) \\ 239872 &:= (((2^7) \times 8) + (9! / (-3))) \times (-2) \\ 239976 &:= (((6^7) - (9! / 9)) - (3! / (-2))) \\ 240144 &:= (4! \times (4 + ((10^4) + 2))) \\ 240336 &:= (6! + ((3!^{3+0!}) - ((4 \times 2)!) \\ 240384 &:= (((4 \times 8) - ((3! + 0!)!) \times (4! \times (-2))) \\ 240386 &:= ((6 \times (8! - ((3 + 0!)^4))) + 2) \\ 240475 &:= (-5 - (((-((7! \times 4!)) + ((-((0! - 4)))!)!) \times 2)) \\ 240496 &:= ((6! + ((9! + 4!) / (0! - 4))) \times (-2) \\ 240742 &:= ((((-2 \times (4! - 7!)) - 0!) \times 4!) - 2) \\ 240744 &:= (4! + (((4! - 7!) + 0!) \times 4!) \times (-2)) \\ 240768 &:= 8 \times 6 \times (7! - ((-0! + 4!) - 2)!) \\ 240786 &:= (6 \times (8! - (7 \times ((0! + 4!) + 2)))) \\ 240846 &:= (((6! / 4) - 8!) - 0!) \times (-4 + 2)) \\ 240959 &:= (((((9 + 5))! / 9!) - 0!) + ((4 + 2)!) \\ 241206 &:= (-6!) - (((0! + 2))! \times (-1 - ((4 \times 2)!)!) \\ 241236 &:= -((6! - (3! \times (((2 + 1))! + ((4 \times 2)!)!))) \\ 241248 &:= ((8 \times 42) \times (((-((1 - 4)))!) - 2)) \\ 241283 &:= ((3! \times (8! - 2)) - ((1 + 4!)^2)) \\ 241338 &:= (((8! \times 3!) - 3!) - (((1 \times 4)!)^2)) \\ 241343 &:= ((3! \times ((4! / 3)!) - (1 + (4!)^2)) \\ 241344 &:= (((4 + 4))! \times 3!) - (((1 \times 4)!)^2)) \\ 241368 &:= (((8! \times 6) + ((3 + 1)!) - (4!)^2) \\ 241386 &:= ((6 \times ((8! + 3!) + 1)) - (4!)^2) \\ 241387 &:= (((7 + 8!) \times 3!) + 1) - (4!)^2) \\ 241391 &:= (((-((1 - 9)))! \times 3!) - ((-1 + 4!)^2)) \\ 241392 &:= (((2 + 9) - ((3! + 1)!) \times (4! \times (-2))) \\ 241398 &:= (((8! + 9) \times 3!) - (((1 \times 4)!)^2)) \\ 241428 &:= (8! - 2 \times 41) \times (4 + 2) \\ 241438 &:= ((8! \times 3!) - ((4 \times ((1 + 4))!) + 2)) \\ 241476 &:= (-6 \times (74 - (((1 \times 4) \times 2)!) \\ 241478 &:= (((8! - 74) \times (-((1 - 4)))!) + 2) \\ 241486 &:= ((6 \times (8! - (4! \times (-1 - 4)))) - 2) \\ 241582 &:= (-2 + ((8! / 5!) \times (-1 + ((4 + 2)!) \\ 241596 &:= (-6 \times ((9 \times (5 + 1)) - ((4 \times 2)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 241626 &:= (6 \times (((2 + 6))! - 1) - (4! \times 2)) \\ 241631 &:= (-1 + (((3! - ((6 + 1))!) \times 4!) \times (-2))) \\ 241632 &:= (((-((2 \times 3)) + ((6 + 1))!) \times 4!) \times 2) \\ 241638 &:= ((8! \times 3!) - (-6 \times (1 - (4! \times 2)))) \\ 241668 &:= ((8! \times 6) - ((6 \times 1) \times 42)) \\ 241675 &:= (-5 + (((7! - (6 - 1)) \times 4!) \times 2)) \\ 241686 &:= 6 \times (8! - 61 + 4! - 2) \\ 241704 &:= (4! \times (0! - ((7! - (1 + 4)) \times (-2)))) \\ 241724 &:= (((4! \times 2) \times 7!) - ((14^2))) \\ 241726 &:= (((-6 - (-2 \times (7! - 1))) \times 4!) - 2) \\ 241728 &:= (((-((8 / 2)) + 7!) \times ((1 \times 4)!) \times 2) \\ 241732 &:= (2 \times ((((-3 + 7!) - 1) \times 4!) + 2)) \\ 241738 &:= ((8! \times 3!) - (((7 - 1))! / 4) + 2) \\ 241746 &:= (-6 \times (((4 \times 7) + 1) - ((4 \times 2)!) \\ 241751 &:= ((-1 - 5!) - (((7! - 1) \times 4!) \times (-2))) \\ 241762 &:= (-2 + (6 \times (((7 + 1))! - 4!) - 2)) \\ 241764 &:= -((4! - (6 \times (((7 + 1))! - 4!) + 2))) \\ 241767 &:= (-7 + ((6 \times (((7 + 1))! - 4!)) - 2)) \\ 241769 &:= (-9 + ((6 \times (((7 + 1))! - 4!)) + 2)) \\ 241774 &:= (((-((4 - 7)))! \times ((7 + 1))! - 4!) - 2) \\ 241776 &:= (((-6 + 7!) + 7!) \times (((-((1 - 4)))! - 2)!) \\ 241784 &:= (((4! - 8!) \times (-7 - 1)) + (4 \times 2)) \\ 241786 &:= ((6 \times 8!) - ((71 - 4) \times 2)) \\ 241802 &:= (((2 + 0!)! \times 8!) - (((1 + 4))! - 2)) \\ 241805 &:= -(((5! + 0!) - ((8! + 1) \times (4 + 2))) \\ 241806 &:= ((6 \times (0! + 8!)) - (-(((1 - 4) - 2)!) \\ 241818 &:= ((8! - (18 - 1)) \times (4 + 2)) \\ 241822 &:= (-2 - (((-2 + ((8 - 1))!) \times 4!) \times (-2))) \\ 241824 &:= (((-((4^2)) + 8!) \times ((1 \times 4) + 2)) \\ 241826 &:= ((-6 \times ((2 - 8!) + 14)) + 2) \\ 241828 &:= ((8! + (2 \times ((8! + 1) - 4!))) \times 2) \\ 241842 &:= ((2 + 4) \times ((8! - 1) - (4! / 2))) \\ 241846 &:= ((-6 \times (4 - 8!)) - ((-1 - 4!) \times (-2))) \\ 241848 &:= (((8! - 4!) + 8!) \times ((1^4) + 2)) \\ 241856 &:= (((-((6 + 5)) + 8!) \times (-((1 - 4)))!) + 2) \\ 241871 &:= (-1 - (((7 - 8!) + 1) \times (4 + 2))) \\ 241872 &:= (((2 + 7) - 8!) - 1) \times (-4 + 2)) \\ 241873 &:= ((3! \times (-7 + 8!)) + (((1 - 4) - 2)) \\ 241874 &:= (((-((4 - 7)) \times 8!) + 1) - 4!) \times 2) \\ 241875 &:= (-5 + (((-7 + 8!) \times (-((1 - 4)))!) + 2)) \\ 241876 &:= ((-6 \times (7 - 8!)) - ((1^4) \times 2)) \\ 241877 &:= (-7 + (((7 - 8!) - 1) \times (-4 + 2))) \end{aligned}$$

- 241878** := $(8! - 7) \times (8 - 1 - 4) \times 2$
241882 := $((((2 + 8!) - 8) \times -((1 - 4)))!) - 2$
241883 := $((3! \times (-8 + 8!)) - 1) + (4!/2)$
241884 := $((4!/8)!) \times (8! - ((1 \times 4) + 2))$
241885 := $((5 - 8!) \times -(8 - 1)) - ((4 \times 2)!)$
241886 := $((6 \times 8!) - ((8 \times 1) \times 4) + 2)$
241888 := $((8 + 8) \times (((8 + 1)!/4!) - 2))$
241893 := $((((-((3 - 9)) \times 8!) - 1) - 4!) - 2)$
241894 := $((-((4 + 9)) - (8! \times (1 - 4))) \times 2)$
241896 := $((-((6 - 9)) - 8!) + 1) \times -(4 + 2))$
241902 := $((2 + 0!) - ((9 - 1)!) \times -(4 + 2))$
241903 := $((3! \times -((0! - 9)))!) - (1 + 4^2)$
241904 := $((4! - (09)!) / -(1 - 4)) \times (-2)$
241906 := $((-6 \times (0! - ((9 - 1)!) - (4 \times 2)))$
241907 := $(-7 - ((0! - ((9 - 1)!) \times (4 + 2)))$
241908 := $((8! - ((0 \times 9)!) - 1) \times (4 + 2))$
241909 := $(-9 - ((0! + (9!/(1 - 4))) \times 2))$
241912 := $((2 + 1)! \times ((9 - 1)!) - (4 \times 2))$
241913 := $-(((3! + 1) - (((9 - 1)!) \times (4 + 2))))$
241914 := $((4 - 1)! \times ((9 - 1)!) - (4 + 2))$
241915 := $(-5 + (((1 + 9)! / -(1 - 4^2))))$
241916 := $((6 - ((1 \times 9)!) / -(1 - 4)) \times (-2))$
241918 := $((8! \times ((1 - 9) + 14)) - 2)$
241919 := $((9! + 1) - ((9! / -(1 - 4)) + 2))$
241920 := $0 + 2 \times 9! / (1^4 + 2)$
241921 := $(1 - ((-2 \times 9!) / ((1^4) + 2)))$
241921 := $1 + 2 \times 9! / (1^4 + 2)$
241922 := $(((((2 + 2)!) \times ((9 - 1)!) / 4) + 2)$
241922 := $2 + 2 \times 9! / (1^4 + 2)$
241923 := $(3 - ((-2 \times 9!) / ((1^4) + 2)))$
241923 := $3 + 2 \times 9! / (1^4 + 2)$
241924 := $((-((4 + 2)) - 9!) / -(1 - 4)) \times (-2)$
241924 := $4 + 2 \times 9! / (1^4 + 2)$
241925 := $(5 - ((-2 \times 9!) / ((1^4) + 2)))$
241925 := $5 + 2 \times 9! / (1^4 + 2)$
241926 := $((((6/2)!) \times ((9 - 1)!) + (4 + 2))$
241926 := $6 + 2 \times 9! / (1^4 + 2)$
241927 := $(7 - ((-2 \times 9!) / ((1^4) + 2)))$
241927 := $7 + 2 \times 9! / (1^4 + 2)$
241928 := $((8! \times -((2 - 9) + 1))) + (4 \times 2)$
241928 := $8 + 2 \times 9! / (1^4 + 2)$
241929 := $(9 - ((-2 \times 9!) / ((1^4) + 2)))$
241929 := $9 + 2 \times 9! / (1^4 + 2)$
241931 := $((-1 + (3! \times ((9 - 1)!) + (4!/2)))$
241932 := $((((-2 \times 3!) \times ((9 - 1)!) - 4!) / (-2))$
241933 := $(-3 + ((3! \times ((9 - 1)!) + (4^2))))$
241934 := $((4! - 3) + 9!) / (1 - 4) \times (-2)$
241935 := $((5 \times 3) + ((9 - 1)! \times (4 + 2)))$
241936 := $((6 - 3)! \times ((9 - 1)!) + (4^2))$
241937 := $(-7 + (3 \times (((9 - 1)!) + 4) \times 2))$
241938 := $((8! + 3) \times ((9 - 1) - 4) + 2)$
241942 := $((2 + 4) \times ((9 - 1)!) + 4!) - 2$
241944 := $(4! \times ((4 - ((9 - 1)!) / (-4)) + 2))$
241946 := $((-6 \times (-4 - ((9 - 1)!) + (4 - 2)))$
241947 := $-((((7! \times 4!) - 9!) - 1) - 4!) - 2$
241948 := $((8! \times 4!) - ((9! - 14) \times 2))$
241961 := $(-1 + ((6 \times ((9 - 1)!) + 42)))$
241964 := $((-4 - (-6 \times ((9 - 1)!) + (4! \times 2)))$
241967 := $(-7 - (-6 \times (9 + (((1 \times 4) \times 2)!)))$
241968 := $((8! \times 6) + ((9 - 1) \times (4 + 2)))$
241969 := $((9! \times (-6)) / (-9) + 1) + (4! \times 2)$
241974 := $((4! \times 7!) - ((9 \times (1 - 4))) \times 2)$
241978 := $(((-87) - 9!) / -(1 - 4)) \times (-2)$
241996 := $((-6 \times (-9 - ((9 - 1)!) + (4! - 2)))$
242016 := $((6 + 1)! + 02) \times 4! \times 2$
242028 := $((8! + (20 - 2)) \times (4 + 2))$
242038 := $((8! \times 3!) + (((0 \times 2)!) + 4)!) - 2$
242046 := $(6 \times (((4! - 0!) - 2) + ((4 \times 2)!))$
242048 := $((8! + 4!) \times ((0! + 2)!) - (4^2))$
242057 := $(-7 + (((5! + 0!) + 2) \times 4^2))$
242064 := $((4! + ((6 + 02)!) \times (4 + 2))$
242066 := $((6 \times (((6 + 02)!) + 4!)) + 2)$
242076 := $((-6 - (((7! + 0!) + 2) \times 4!)) \times (-2))$
242136 := $(-6 \times -((3 \times 12)) - ((4 \times 2)!))$
242168 := $((8! \times 6) + (124 \times 2))$
242176 := $((6 \times ((7 + 1)!) + ((2^4)^2))$
242193 := $(3 \times (91 - (-2 \times ((4 \times 2)!)))$
242196 := $(6 \times (((9 - 1)!) + ((2 \times 4!) - 2)))$
242234 := $(((-4!) + 3!!)^2 / 2) + (4! + 2)$
242304 := $(4! \times (((0! + 3)!) \times 2) + (4^2))$
242352 := $((2 + 5)! + (3^2)) \times 4! \times 2$
242368 := $(8! - 6) \times 3! + (-2 + 4!)^2$
242386 := $((6 \times (8! - 3)) + ((-2 + 4!)^2))$

$$\begin{aligned} 242396 &:= (((6! + 9!)/(-3)) + 2) \times (-4 - 2)) \\ 242398 &:= ((8 \times ((9! + 3!) \times 2)/4!) - 2) \\ 242448 &:= ((8! + (44 \times 2)) \times (4 + 2)) \\ 242488 &:= ((-8 - (8! \times (-4 + 2)))) + (4!^2)) \\ 242496 &:= (-6 \times (-((94 + 2)) - ((4 \times 2)!)) \\ 242545 &:= ((5^4) + (((5 - 2)! \times ((4 \times 2)!)) \\ 242568 &:= ((8! \times 6) + (((5 - 2)!^4)/2)) \\ 242586 &:= ((6 \times ((8! + 5!) - 2)) - 42) \\ 242598 &:= (((8! - 9) + 5!) + 2) \times (4 + 2)) \\ 242626 &:= ((6! - 2) - (-6 \times (-2 + ((4 \times 2)!))) \\ 242628 &:= (((8! - 2) \times 6) + ((2 \times 4) - 2)!) \\ 242634 &:= ((-4 + 3!) - ((-6 \times ((2 \times 4)! + 2)) \\ 242635 &:= (-5 + ((3! \times ((6 + 2)! + ((4 + 2)!)) \\ 242636 &:= ((6! - 3!) + ((6 \times ((2 \times 4)! + 2)) \\ 242638 &:= (((((8! \times 3!) + 6!) \times (-2)) + 4)/(-2)) \\ 242642 &:= (((((2 \times 4)! \times 6) + 2) + ((4 + 2)!)) \\ 242646 &:= ((6! + 4) + ((6 \times ((2 \times 4)! + 2)) \\ 242652 &:= (((-2 - 5!) - ((6 + 2)! \times (-4 + 2))) \\ 242656 &:= ((6 \times (5! + ((6 + 2)!)) + ((4^2))) \\ 242658 &:= (((8! + 5!) \times 6) + ((2^4) + 2)) \\ 242664 &:= (4! + ((6 \times ((6 + 2)! + ((4 + 2)!)) \\ 242666 &:= (6! + (((6 \times ((6 + 2)! + 4!) + 2)) \\ 242668 &:= (((((8! \times 6) + 6!) + 2) + 4!) + 2) \\ 242686 &:= (((6 \times 8!) + 6!) + ((2 \times 4!) - 2)) \\ 242688 &:= (((8 + 8!) \times 6) + ((2 \times 4) - 2)!) \\ 242733 &:= (3! + (-3 - (((7! + 2) \times 4!) \times (-2)))) \\ 242736 &:= (6! - (3 \times ((7! + 2) \times (-4^2)))) \\ 242758 &:= (((8! + 5!) \times 7) - 2) - ((4 \times 2)!) \\ 242784 &:= (((4! + 8!) + ((7 - 2)!) \times (4 + 2)) \\ 242786 &:= ((6 \times ((8! + ((7 - 2)!) + 4!) + 2) \\ 242856 &:= (6 \times ((5! + 8!) + ((2 + 4)^2)) \\ 242976 &:= (6! + (((-7 - ((9 - 2)!) \times 4!) \times (-2))) \\ 242988 &:= ((8! + (89 \times 2)) \times (4 + 2)) \\ 243024 &:= (4! \times (-2 + (((0! + 3!)! + 4!) \times 2)) \\ 243049 &:= ((9 - ((-4 \times (-((0! - 3)!))! - 4))^2) \\ 243071 &:= (-1 - (((-7!) - ((0! + 3)!) \times (4! \times 2))) \\ 243072 &:= ((2 - (-70 \times 3!)) \times (4!^2)) \\ 243074 &:= -(((4! + 7!) \times ((0! - 3) \times 4!) - 2)) \\ 243076 &:= ((6 \times ((7 + 0)!)! + (34^2)) \\ 243168 &:= ((8 \times 6) \times (((1 + 3)!)! + (4! + 2))) \\ 243216 &:= (6 \times (((1 + 2)!)^3 + ((4 \times 2)!) \\ 243218 &:= ((8! \times ((1 + 2)!) + ((3!^4) + 2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 243248 &:= (8 \times ((42 \times (3! + 4)) - 2)) \\ 243264 &:= ((-4 - 6!) \times (-((2^3) \times 42))) \\ 243318 &:= (((((8! + 1) \times (-3)) - 3!) + 4!) \times (-2)) \\ 243338 &:= (((8! \times 3!) + 3!) + 3!) - (4! - 2)) \\ 243358 &:= (((8! + 5!) \times 3!) + 3!) - (4 - 2)) \\ 243374 &:= (((4! \times 7!) + 3!) + (3 + 4)) \times 2) \\ 243382 &:= ((2 \times ((8! \times 3) + 3!)) + (4! - 2)) \\ 243384 &:= (((4 + 8!) \times (-3)) - 3!) \times (-4 - 2)) \\ 243386 &:= ((6 \times 8!) - (((3^3) + 4) \times (-2))) \\ 243392 &:= (2 \times (((9!/3) + 3!) + (4^2))) \\ 243396 &:= ((6! - (((9!/(-3)) + 3!) - 4!)) \times 2) \\ 243399 &:= (-9 + (((9!/(-3)) - 3!) - 4!) \times (-2)) \\ 243408 &:= (8! \times (-0! + 4) + 3! + 4!) \times 2) \\ 243432 &:= ((23 \times 4!) \times ((-3 + 4!)^2)) \\ 243448 &:= (((8! + (4^4)) \times 3!) - (4 \times 2)) \\ 243468 &:= ((8! + (6 \times 43)) \times (4 + 2)) \\ 243558 &:= (((-8!/5!)) \times (-5 - 3!)) - 42) \\ 243572 &:= ((2 \times 7) \times (((-5 - 3!) \times (-4!)) - 2)) \\ 243648 &:= (((846 \times 3!) \times 4!) \times 2) \\ 243672 &:= (((-2 \times (7! + 6)) + 3!) \times (-4! + 2)) \\ 243744 &:= ((((-44) - 7!) + 3!) \times 4!) \times (-2)) \\ 243838 &:= ((8! \times 3!) + ((8!/(-3 + 4!)) - 2)) \\ 243862 &:= (-2 - (-6 \times (8! + (-((3! - 4!)^2)))) \\ 243937 &:= -((((7^3) - 9!) + ((3!^4) - 2)) \\ 243938 &:= ((8! \times 3!) + (((-9!/3!) \times (-4)) + 2)) \\ 243978 &:= ((8! + ((7^9/3))) \times (4 + 2)) \\ 244036 &:= ((6! + (30 - (4^4)))^2) \\ 244086 &:= (-6 \times (-8!) - (-((0! + 4) - 4!)^2)) \\ 244656 &:= (6! + ((5! + 6) \times (44^2))) \\ 244679 &:= (((9! - ((7^6))) + 4!) - (4!^2)) \\ 244806 &:= ((6 \times (0! + 8!)) - (-4 \times ((4 + 2)!)) \\ 244836 &:= ((6 \times (3! + 8!)) - (-4 \times ((4 + 2)!)) \\ 244864 &:= -(((4! \times 6!) - ((8^{4+4-2}))) \\ 244986 &:= ((6! + ((8 - (9^4)))) \times (-42)) \\ 245025 &:= ((-5 \times (((-2 - 0!) - 5!) + 4!)^2) \\ 245229 &:= (9! - ((2 + ((2 + 5)^{4+2}))) \\ 245279 &:= (9! - ((7^{(-2+5)!}) - (4! \times 2))) \\ 245338 &:= -(((8^3) - 3) \times ((5! \times (-4)) - 2)) \\ 245346 &:= (6 \times (((4!/3)!) + (-5 + (4!^2))) \\ 245368 &:= (-8 - (-6 \times (((3 + 5)!) + (4!^2))) \\ 245374 &:= (((4! + (7!/3)) \times (5! + 4!)) - 2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 245376 &:= ((6^7) + (((3! \times 5!) \times 4!) \times (-2))) & 246976 &:= ((6! \times (7^{9-6})) + ((4^2))) \\ 245448 &:= (84 \times ((4! \times 5!) + 42)) & 247007 &:= ((7! - 0!) + (((0! + 7!) \times 4!) \times 2)) \\ 245538 &:= (((8! + 3) - (5! \times (-5))) \times (4 + 2)) & 247008 &:= (((8 - 0!)!) + (((0! + 7!) \times 4!) \times 2)) \\ 245642 &:= ((-2 + 4^6) \times 5! + 4)/2 & 247077 &:= ((-7 \times ((7! - 0!) \times (-7)) - 4!) - 2) \\ 245668 &:= ((8! \times 6) + (((6 \times (5^4)) - 2))) & 247254 &:= (((4! + 5)^2) \times (7 \times 42)) \\ 245745 &:= (((5! \times (4^7)) - 5!)/(4 \times 2)) & 247357 &:= ((7 - 5!) \times (-((3^7) + 4) - 2)) \\ 245762 &:= (((-(2^{6+7})) \times 5!)/(-4)) + 2 & 247388 &:= (-8 + ((8! \times 3!) + ((74^2)))) \\ 245856 &:= ((6 + ((5! + 8) \times 5!)) \times (4^2)) & 247408 &:= ((8 - 0!) \times ((47 \times 4)^2)) \\ 245886 &:= (6 \times ((8! + (85)) + (4!^2))) & 247416 &:= (61 \times (4! + (7 \times (4!^2)))) \\ 245888 &:= (-((8 \times 8)) \times ((8 \times 5!) \times (-4)) - 2) & 247518 &:= ((81 - ((5! + 7!) \times 4!)) \times (-2)) \\ 246186 &:= (-6 \times (((8 + 1) - 6!) - ((4 \times 2)!)) & 247532 &:= (2 \times ((((-3 + 5!) + 7!) \times 4!) - 2)) \\ 246218 &:= (((-8!) - (((1 + 2)!))!) \times (-6)) - (4! - 2) & 247533 &:= (-3 - (((3 - 5!) - 7!) \times 4!) \times 2) \\ 246228 &:= ((8 - 2) \times ((-2 + 6!) + ((4 \times 2)!)) & 247536 &:= (((((6 - 3) - 5!) - 7!) \times 4!) \times (-2)) \\ 246235 &:= (-5 - (-((3 \times 2)) \times (6! + ((4 \times 2)!))) & 247555 &:= ((-5 - 5!) + ((5! + 7!) \times 4!) \times 2) \\ 246238 &:= (((8! + ((3 \times 2)!)) \times 6) - (4 - 2)) & 247566 &:= ((-6 - 6!) \times (-5 + ((7 \times 4!) \times (-2)))) \\ 246252 &:= (((-(2 - 5))!) \times ((2 + 6!) + ((4 \times 2)!)) & 247568 &:= (((8!/6!) - ((5! + 7!) \times 4!)) \times (-2)) \\ 246258 &:= (((8! + (5 - 2)) + 6!) \times (4 + 2)) & 247584 &:= ((4! - 8!) + (5! \times ((7^4) - 2))) \\ 246264 &:= (((4 + 6!) + ((2 + 6)!)) \times (4 + 2)) & 247599 &:= (-((9 \times 9)) + (((5! + 7!) \times 4!) \times 2)) \\ 246266 &:= (((6! + ((6 + 2)!)) \times 6) + 4!) + 2 & 247638 &:= (((8! \times 3!) + 6!) + 7!) - 42 \\ 246268 &:= (((8! + 6!) + 2) \times 6) + ((4^2)) & 247648 &:= ((8 \times (-4 + 6!)) + ((7! \times 4!) \times 2)) \\ 246276 &:= (-6 \times (-726 - ((4 \times 2)!)) & 247658 &:= (((((8! + 5!) \times 6) + 7!) - 4!) + 2) \\ 246288 &:= (((8! + ((8 - 2)!)) \times 6) + (4! \times 2)) & 247668 &:= (((8! \times 6) + 6!) + 7!) - (4!/2) \\ 246318 &:= (((8! + 13) + 6!) \times (4 + 2)) & 247675 &:= (((-5 + 7!) + 6!) + ((7! \times 4!) \times 2)) \\ 246348 &:= (((8! + 4!) - 3!) + 6!) \times (4 + 2)) & 247678 &:= (((8!/7) \times (67 - 4!)) - 2) \\ 246355 &:= ((5! - 5) + (3! \times (6! + ((4 \times 2)!))) & 247698 &:= (8! - (9 \times ((6! + 7!) \times (-4)) - 2)) \\ 246368 &:= (((8! + 6!) \times 3!) + (64 \times 2)) & 247736 &:= ((6! + ((3! \times 7!) + 7)) \times (4 \times 2)) \\ 246377 &:= ((-7 + ((7^3) \times 6!)) - (4!^2)) & 247744 &:= (((-((4 \times 4)) - 7!) \times (-7 + 42)) \\ 246384 &:= (((4! + 8!) \times 3!) + (6! \times (4 + 2))) & 247758 &:= (((8! + 5!) - 7!) \times 7) - 42 \\ 246386 &:= (((6! + 8!) \times 3!) + ((6 \times 4!) + 2)) & 247808 &:= (8 \times ((08 + (7 \times 4!))^2)) \\ 246528 &:= (((8! \times 2)/(-5)) + 6!) \times (-4^2)) & 247959 &:= (9! - (((5 \times 9) \times 7) + 4!^2)) \\ 246595 &:= ((-5 + 9!) - (((5!/6)!)/(4^2)!)) & 247968 &:= (((((8 + 6) \times 9) + 7!) \times 4!) \times 2) \\ 246636 &:= (6 \times (3!! - (-66 - ((4 \times 2)!))) & 247977 &:= ((-7 \times ((7! + 9) \times (-7))) + (4!^2)) \\ 246679 &:= ((9! - ((7^6))) - ((6! + 4) \times (-2))) & 248004 &:= (((4 - 0!)!) \times (-0! - (84)))^2 \\ 246714 &:= ((41 \times (7! - 6)) + ((4 \times 2)!)) & 248064 &:= (((4^{6-0!}) + 8!) \times (4 + 2)) \\ 246734 &:= (43 \times (((7! + 6!) - 4!) + 2)) & 248344 &:= (4! - ((4!^3) - (8^{4+2}))) \\ 246778 &:= (((8! - 7!) \times 7) - ((6!/4) + 2)) & 248349 &:= ((9^4) + (3! \times ((8! - 4!) + 2))) \\ 246816 &:= (((6! + ((1 \times 8)!)) \times 6) + (4!^2)) & 248395 &:= (-5 - ((-9 \times 3!!) + (8! \times (-4 + 2)))) \\ 246897 &:= ((-7 \times ((9 - 8!) - 6!)) - ((4 \times 2)!)) & 248448 &:= ((8 \times 4!) \times (((4!/8)!^4) - 2)) \\ 246947 &:= ((7! - (4 + 9)) - (-6 \times ((4 \times 2)!)) & 248481 &:= (((1 + 8)^4) - (8! \times (-4 + 2))) \\ 246957 &:= 7! - 5 + 9!/6 \times 4 + 2 & 248483 &:= ((3^8) + (((4! \times 8!)/4) + 2)) \\ 246958 &:= (((8!/5!) \times ((-9 + 6!) + 4!)) - 2 & 248628 &:= (((8! - 2) \times 6) + (8!/(4 + 2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 248638 &:= ((8!/3!) - ((-6 \times 8!) + (4 - 2))) \\ 248648 &:= (8! + (4! - 6 + 8^4)/2) \\ 248688 &:= (((8 + 8!) \times 6) + (8!/(4 + 2))) \\ 248832 &:= ((2 \times 3!)^{(8+8/4)/2}) \\ 248973 &:= (37 \times (9 + (8!/(4 + 2)))) \\ 249336 &:= (((63^3) + 9) - ((4 + 2)!)) \\ 249468 &:= ((8! \times 6) - ((4! - (9!/4!))/2)) \\ 249475 &:= (-5 - (((7 + 4) \times 9!)/(-4^2))) \\ 249535 &:= ((5 + 3!) \times (5 + (9!/(4^2)))) \\ 249543 &:= (((3 \times 4)^5 - 9) + ((4 + 2)!)) \\ 249576 &:= (((6^7) - 5!) - ((9!/4!) \times 2)) \\ 249652 &:= ((2 + ((5! \times 6!)/9)) \times (4! + 2)) \\ 250965 &:= ((5 - 6!) \times (9 + (((0! + 5)!)/(-2)))) \\ 251875 &:= (((5 - 7!) - ((8 - 1)!)) \times (-5^2)) \\ 251974 &:= -((4! + ((7! \times (-((9 + 1) \times 5))) + 2))) \\ 251975 &:= (((-5 \times 7!) \times (-9 + 1)) - ((5^2))) \\ 251998 &:= (((8! + 9!)/(-9 - 1)) \times (-5)) - 2 \\ 252025 &:= ((5^2) \times (0! - (-2 \times ((5 + 2)!))) \\ 252027 &:= (((7! \times (-2)) - 0!) \times (-25)) + 2 \\ 252074 &:= (4! - ((7! + 0!) \times (2 - 52))) \\ 252075 &:= ((-5 + ((7! - 0!) \times (-2))) \times (-5^2)) \\ 252175 &:= ((-5 + ((7! + 1) \times (-2))) \times (-5^2)) \\ 252464 &:= ((-((4^6) + 4!) \times (-2 + (5!/(-2)))) \\ 252639 &:= (9 \times (-((3^6) + (2 \times (5!^2)))) \\ 252697 &:= ((-7 + (((-9 + 6!)^2) - 5!))/2) \\ 253064 &:= -((4! + ((6! - 0!) \times (-352))) \\ 253296 &:= -((6! - (((9!/(2 \times 3))/5!^2))) \\ 253344 &:= ((4! \times (-4)) + (3!! \times 352)) \\ 253368 &:= ((-((8! - (6 \times 3!))) - (3!! \times 5!)) \times (-2)) \\ 253395 &:= (-((5 \times 9)) + (3!! \times 352)) \\ 253428 &:= (((8! - (2 + 4)) + (3!! \times 5!)) \times 2) \\ 253432 &:= (((((2^3)!) - 4) + (3!! \times 5!)) \times 2) \\ 253438 &:= (((8 \times 3!!) \times (4 \times (3! + 5))) - 2) \\ 253458 &:= ((-((8! + (5 + 4))) - (3!! \times 5!)) \times (-2)) \\ 253462 &:= (-2 - (((6! - 4) \times (-3)) \times (5! - 2))) \\ 253464 &:= ((4 - 6!) \times (4 + ((-3 \times 5!) + 2))) \\ 253484 &:= (-4 - (((-((8! + 4!)) - (3!! \times 5!)) \times 2)) \\ 253488 &:= (((8! + ((8 - 4)!)) + (3!! \times 5!)) \times 2) \\ 253664 &:= (-((4^6) + (6! \times ((3 \times 5!) - 2))) \\ 253768 &:= ((((-8 + 6!) \times (7 - 3!)) + 5!)/(-2)) \\ 253798 &:= -((8! + ((9 + ((7^3) \times (-5))))/2))) \\ 253888 &:= (-((8 + 8) \times (8 - ((3! + 5!)^2))) \\ 253959 &:= ((9!/5) + (((9! + 3!) - 5!)/2)) \\ 253968 &:= (-((8 \times 6) + (((9!/3!)/5!^2))) \\ 254016 &:= (((6 \times 104) - 5!)^2) \\ 254043 &:= ((3 + 4!) \times (((0! - 4!) + 5!)^2)) \\ 254304 &:= (((4!)/(((0! - 3!) \times (-4)!)) - (((5 - 2)!))! \\ 254306 &:= (-6!) - (((((0! + 3)!)/(-((4 \times 5)!)) - 2)) \\ 254368 &:= ((8^6) - ((3!^4) \times ((5 - 2)!)) \\ 254545 &:= ((5! \times (-4)) + (((5^4) - 5!)^2)) \\ 254592 &:= (((-((2 - 9)))! - (5! + 4!)) \times 52) \\ 254734 &:= (((4!^3) - 7!) \times (4! + 5)) - 2 \\ 254736 &:= (6! + (((3 \times 7!) \times 4)/5!^2)) \\ 254784 &:= (((4!)/(-((8 - (7 \times 4))))!) + (5! \times (-2))) \\ 254866 &:= ((6! - (6 + 8)) \times ((4! - 5^2)) \\ 254964 &:= (((4!)/((6!/(9 \times 4)))! - (5!/2)) \\ 254998 &:= (((8 + 9) \times ((9!/4!) - 5!)) - 2) \\ 255022 &:= (2 + 2)!!/((-0! + 5) \times 5) - 2 \\ 255024 &:= (((4 + 20)!)/(((5 + 5) \times 2)!)) \\ 255026 &:= (((((6 - 2)!)/(((0! - 5) \times (-5)!))! + 2) \\ 255034 &:= (((4!)/(((3 + 0!) \times 5)! + (5 \times 2)) \\ 255234 &:= -(((4! - ((3^2+5))) \times (5! - 2))) \\ 255264 &:= (((4!)/(((6 - 2) \times 5)! - (5! \times (-2))) \\ 255346 &:= (((6! - 4!) \times 3) + 5) \times (5! + 2)) \\ 255575 &:= (-5 - (((7! - 5) - 5!) \times (-52))) \\ 255728 &:= (-8 - (((2 - 7!) + 5!) \times 52)) \\ 255736 &:= (((6/3) - 7!) + 5!) \times (-52) \\ 255744 &:= ((4! \times (-4)) + ((7! - 5!) \times 52)) \\ 255788 &:= (((8/8) - 7!) + 5!) \times (-52) \\ 255795 &:= (-((5 \times 9) + ((7! - 5!) \times 52)) \\ 255894 &:= ((4^{9!/8!}) - ((5^5) \times 2)) \\ 255904 &:= ((4^09) - (5! \times 52)) \\ 255915 &:= (((5! + 1) \times 9) \times (-5 + (5! \times 2))) \\ 256248 &:= (((8! - (4!/2)) \times 6) + (5!^2)) \\ 256266 &:= (((6 - 6!) \times (-2 + 6!)) + 5!)/(-2) \\ 256268 &:= (-8 + 6!)/2 \times 6! - 52 \\ 256284 &:= (((4 - 8!) + 2) \times (-6)) + (5!^2) \\ 256308 &:= (8! - 0!) \times 3! - 6 + 5!^2 \\ 256338 &:= (((8! \times 3!) + ((3 \times 6))) + (5!^2)) \\ 256344 &:= (((-4 - ((4!/3)!)) \times (-6)) + (5!^2)) \\ 256345 &:= -(((5! \times (4! + (-3 \times 6!))) - ((5^2)))) \\ 256356 &:= (((-6 - ((5 + 3)!)) \times (-6)) + (5!^2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 256454 &:= (((4!)! / ((5 \times 4)!) - ((6! - 5) \times (-2))) \\ 256498 &:= (-89) \times ((-(4 \times 6) \times 5!) - 2) \\ 256579 &:= (((-9 + 7!) \times (56 - 5)) - 2) \\ 256625 &:= ((5! + ((2 - 6!) \times (6! - 5))) / (-2)) \\ 256673 &:= -((3!! + (7 - ((6! \times (6! - 5)) / 2)))) \\ 256675 &:= (-5 - (((7 - 6!) \times 6) \times 5!) / 2) \\ 256735 &:= (-5 - (((3!! \times (-7 + 6!)) + 5!) / (-2))) \\ 256764 &:= (4! - (((6! - 7) \times 6!) + 5!) / (-2)) \\ 256977 &:= -((7! - (-7 \times (9 - (6! \times 52)))) \\ 256986 &:= ((6! + ((8! - 9) \times 6)) + (5!^2)) \\ 257015 &:= ((51 \times (07)!) - (5^2)) \\ 257035 &:= ((-5 - ((3! + 0!)!) - (7! \times (-52))) \\ 257037 &:= -(((7! + 3) + ((0 - 7!) \times 52))) \\ 257038 &:= ((8! \times (3! + 0!)) - ((7! \times 5) + 2)) \\ 257064 &:= ((4! - ((6 + 0!)!)) - (7! \times (-52))) \\ 257092 &:= -(((-(2 - 9)!) + ((0! + 7!) \times (-52))) \\ 257094 &:= (((4^9) - (07)!) - (5 \times 2)) \\ 257104 &:= ((4^{0!+1+7}) - ((5 + 2)!) \\ 257154 &:= (-4 - (((-51) \times 7!) - 5!) + 2) \\ 257156 &:= (-6 - (((-51) \times 7!) - 5!) - 2) \\ 257293 &:= (-3 - ((92 - 7!) \times 52)) \\ 257295 &:= (((5! - ((9 \times 2))) \times (7! + 5)) / 2) \\ 257315 &:= ((-51) \times (-3 - 7!)) + (5! + 2) \\ 257334 &:= -((4! + ((3! - (3^7)) \times (5! - 2)))) \\ 257338 &:= (((8^3!) - 3!) - 7!) + (5! \times 2) \\ 257344 &:= (((4 + 4)^{3!}) - 7!) + (5! \times 2) \\ 257352 &:= -(((2 + 5)!) - ((3! + 7!) \times 52)) \\ 257357 &:= -(((7! + 5) - ((3! + 7!) \times 52)) \\ 257358 &:= -((((8 - 5)!) - (3^7)) \times (5! - 2)) \\ 257374 &:= -(((4! + 7!) - ((3^7) \times 5!) - 2)) \\ 257384 &:= ((-4 - (8 \times (3!! - (7^5)))) \times 2) \\ 257386 &:= (-6 - (8 \times ((3!! - (7^5)) \times 2))) \\ 257497 &:= -(((7! + 9) \times (4! - 75)) + 2) \\ 257499 &:= 99 \times (-4! + 75)^2 \\ 257608 &:= ((-(80 + 6) + 7!) \times 52) \\ 257638 &:= (8 + 3 \times (6! - 7)) \times 5! - 2 \\ 257946 &:= (((6! + (4^9)) - 7!) + 5!) + 2) \\ 257971 &:= (-1 - ((79 - 7!) \times 52)) \\ 258048 &:= (((8 - 4!) \times (08)!) / (-5)) \times 2) \\ 258064 &:= ((-4 \times ((-6 - ((0 \times 8)!) - 5!))^2) \\ 258238 &:= (((-8 + (3 \times ((2 - 8)!)!)) \times 5!) - 2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 258256 &:= (-((6^5) / 2)) + (8^{(5-2)!}) \\ 258304 &:= ((4^{0!+3!}) + (8! \times ((5 - 2)!)!) \\ 258336 &:= ((6 \times 3) \times ((3! \times (-8)) + (5!^2))) \\ 258537 &:= (-7 + ((3!! \times (-5)) + (8^{(5-2)!}))) \\ 258544 &:= (((4! / 4)!) \times (-5)) + (8^{(5-2)!}) \\ 258564 &:= (((4 - 6!) \times 5) + (8^{(5-2)!})) \\ 258624 &:= (-((4!^2) - ((-6!) \times (((8 - 5)!)!)) / 2) \\ 258727 &:= ((7^{-2+7}) + (8! \times ((5 - 2)!)!) \\ 258836 &:= (((6! \times 3!!) - 8) - (((8 - 5)!)!)) / 2) \\ 258838 &:= ((((-8!) \times 3!!) + 8!) / (8 - 5!)) - 2) \\ 258955 &:= ((-(5^5) + 9!) - ((8! \times 5) / 2)) \\ 259072 &:= (-((2^7) \times (0! - ((9 \times 5)^2))) \\ 259081 &:= (((-(1 - 8)!) / (0! + 9)) + 5)^2) \\ 259136 &:= (((-6!) \times 3!!) - ((1 - 9) - 5!)) / (-2) \\ 259165 &:= (-5 \times ((6 + 1) + (9! / (-5 + 2)))) \\ 259194 &:= (-4 - (((9 + 1)!) / (-9 + 5))) + 2) \\ 259195 &:= (-5 - (-((9 \times 1) + 9) \times (5!^2))) \\ 259196 &:= (-6 - (((9 + 1)!) / (-9 + 5))) - 2) \\ 259212 &:= (2 \times (((1 + 2)!) - (-9 \times (5!^2)))) \\ 259215 &:= (-5 \times (-((1 + 2)) + (9! / (-5 + 2)))) \\ 259225 &:= (((5!^2) \times (2 \times 9)) + (5^2)) \\ 259226 &:= (((6!^2) / 2) + ((9 - 5)!) + 2) \\ 259236 &:= ((6 \times 3!) + ((2 \times 9) \times (5!^2))) \\ 259263 &:= ((3 - (((6!^2) + 9) + 5!)) / (-2)) \\ 259264 &:= (-4 \times (6! - (2^{(9-5)^2})) \\ 259269 &:= ((-9 - (((6!^2) + 9) + 5!)) / (-2)) \\ 259335 &:= (-5 \times (-((3^3) + (9! / (-5 + 2)))) \\ 259337 &:= (((-(7! + 3) - 3!) \times (-9 \times 5)) + 2) \\ 259353 &:= (3 \times ((5! \times 3!!) + (-9 - (5! / (-2)))) \\ 259361 &:= (-1 - ((6 \times 3) \times (-9 - (5!^2)))) \\ 259362 &:= ((2 \times (6 + 3)) \times (9 + (5!^2))) \\ 259425 &:= ((5!^2) + ((495^2))) \\ 259434 &:= ((4! - 3!) \times ((4 + 9) + (5!^2))) \\ 259533 &:= ((-3!) \times ((3!! \times 5!) - (9 - 5!)) / (-2) \\ 259575 &:= (-5 \times (-75) + (9! / (-5 + 2))) \\ 259584 &:= (4! \times (((8 + 5!) - ((9 - 5)!)^2)) \\ 259631 &:= -((((1 + 3!)^6) - 9!) - (5!^2)) \\ 259637 &:= -7^3! + 6 + 9! + 5!^2 \\ 259735 &:= (-5 - ((3!! - (7! + 9)) \times (5! / 2))) \\ 259764 &:= (4! - (((6! - 7!) - 9) \times 5!) / 2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 259776 &:= ((6! + 7!) + ((-7 \times 9!)/(-5 \times 2))) \\ 259839 &:= (((9! \times 3!)/8) - ((-9 + 5!)^2)) \\ 259848 &:= ((8! \times 4) + (8 \times ((-9 + 5!)^2))) \\ 259984 &:= (((-((4 - 8))^9) - (9 \times 5!) \times 2)) \\ 260124 &:= (4! + ((-210) + 6!)^2)) \\ 260281 &:= ((1 + ((8 - 2))!) \times (0! - (6!/(-2)))) \\ 260632 &:= (-2 - ((3! + 6!) \times (0! + (6!/(-2)))))) \\ 260635 &:= (-5 - (((3 + 6!) + 0!) \times 6!/(-2))) \\ 260664 &:= (4! - (6! \times (-((60 \times 6) + 2)))) \\ 260694 &:= ((4^9) + (((-6 + 0!) - 6!) \times 2)) \\ 260704 &:= 4^{0!+7+0!} - 6! \times 2 \\ 261248 &:= (((-((8^4)) + (((2 + 1))!)! \times (-6!)))/(-2)) \\ 261256 &:= -((6! - (52 \times (((1 + 6))! - 2)))) \\ 261355 &:= (-5 + (((5 + 3!!) + 1) \times (6!/2))) \\ 261362 &:= (2 - (((6! + 3!) \times ((1 \times 6))!)/(-2))) \\ 261424 &:= -((((4 + 2))! - ((4^{1+6+2}))) \\ 261426 &:= (((((6 + 2)^{(4-1)!}) - 6!) + 2) \\ 261486 &:= -((6! - ((8^{(4-1)!}) + (62)))) \\ 261576 &:= ((6^7) + ((-51) \times 6!/2)) \\ 261716 &:= ((6! - 1) \times (((7 + 1) + 6!/2)) \\ 261723 &:= (((((3!!^2) + 7!) \times (-1)) - 6)/(-2)) \\ 261782 &:= (-((2 - (8^{7-1}))) + (6!/(-2))) \\ 261784 &:= (((((4^8) \times (7 + 1)) - 6!)/2) \\ 261904 &:= ((4^09) - (((-1) - 6))! \times 2)) \\ 261974 &:= ((4! \times (-7)) + (((9 - 1)^6) - 2)) \\ 262067 &:= (-((7 + 6)) \times (0! - (((2 + 6))!)/2)) \\ 262075 &:= (-5 - (7! \times ((0 - 26) \times 2))) \\ 262078 &:= ((8^{7-0!}) - ((2^6) + 2)) \\ 262080 &:= 0 + 8! \times (0! + 2 \times 6)/2 \\ 262081 &:= (1 - ((8! \times (0! + (2 \times 6)))/(-2))) \\ 262081 &:= 1 + 8! \times (0! + 2 \times 6)/2 \\ 262082 &:= ((2^{(8+0!) \times 2}) - 62) \\ 262082 &:= 2 + 8! \times (0! + 2 \times 6)/2 \\ 262083 &:= (3 - ((8! \times (0! + (2 \times 6)))/(-2))) \\ 262083 &:= 3 + 8! \times (0! + 2 \times 6)/2 \\ 262084 &:= ((4^{8+0!}) + ((2 - 62))) \\ 262084 &:= 4 + 8! \times (0! + 2 \times 6)/2 \\ 262085 &:= (5 - ((8! \times (0! + (2 \times 6)))/(-2))) \\ 262085 &:= 5 + 8! \times (0! + 2 \times 6)/2 \\ 262086 &:= ((6 \times (8! + 0!)) + (((2 + 6))!)/2)) \\ 262086 &:= 6 + 8! \times (0! + 2 \times 6)/2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 262087 &:= ((7 \times (8! + 0!)) - (((2 + 6))!)/2)) \\ 262087 &:= 7 + 8! \times (0! + 2 \times 6)/2 \\ 262088 &:= (8 - ((8! \times (0! + (2 \times 6)))/(-2))) \\ 262088 &:= 8 + 8! \times (0! + 2 \times 6)/2 \\ 262089 &:= (9 - ((8! \times (0! + (2 \times 6)))/(-2))) \\ 262089 &:= 9 + 8! \times (0! + 2 \times 6)/2 \\ 262094 &:= ((4^9) - (((0! - (26)) \times (-2))) \\ 262108 &:= 8^{(0!+2)!} - 6^2 \\ 262128 &:= 8^{(2+1)!} - (2 + 6) \times 2 \\ 262132 &:= (((2^3)^{(1+2)!}) - (6 \times 2)) \\ 262137 &:= (-7 + (((3 + 1) \times 2)^{(6/2)!})) \\ 262208 &:= ((8^{(0!+2)!}) + (2 + 62)) \\ 262334 &:= (((((4^3!) + 3) \times (2^6)) - 2) \\ 262338 &:= ((8^{3!}) + ((32 \times 6) + 2)) \\ 262385 &:= -(((5! - (8^{3!})) + ((2 + 6!)/(-2)))) \\ 262392 &:= (((-((2 - 9))! + (3!)) \times (26 \times 2)) \\ 262394 &:= (((4^9) - 3!) + ((2^{6+2})) \\ 262435 &:= (-5 + (((3^{4+2}) \times 6!)/2)) \\ 262439 &:= (-9 + (((3!! + 4)^2) + 6!)/2)) \\ 262447 &:= ((7 + ((4!/4))!) \times ((2 + 6!)/2)) \\ 262468 &:= ((8^6) + (((4!/2) + 6)^2)) \\ 262504 &:= ((4^{-0!+5 \times 2}) - (6!/(-2))) \\ 262656 &:= ((6 - 5!) \times (-(((6 + 2) \times 6)^2))) \\ 262794 &:= (((4^9) - 72) + 6!) + 2) \\ 262838 &:= (((8^{3!}) - ((8/2))!) + 6!) - 2) \\ 262862 &:= ((-2 + 6!) + ((8^{2+6-2})) \\ 262864 &:= (((4^6)/8)^2) + (((6/2))!)) \\ 262868 &:= (((8^6) + ((8 - 2))!) + (6 - 2)) \\ 262926 &:= (6! + (((2^9)^2) + 62)) \\ 263166 &:= -(((6! - ((6! + 1) \times (3! - (6!/(-2)))))) \\ 263175 &:= ((5 + ((7 - 1))!) \times ((3! + 6!)/2)) \\ 263368 &:= (((8^6) - (3!^3)) + (6! \times 2)) \\ 263376 &:= -(((6! + ((7 - 3))!) \times (3! + (6!/(-2)))))) \\ 263466 &:= ((6 - 6!) \times (((4! - 3!) + 6!)/(-2))) \\ 263506 &:= (((6 + 0!) - (5! \times (-3))) \times (6! - 2)) \\ 263515 &:= (-5 + (((1 + 5))! \times (3! - (6!/(-2)))))) \\ 263518 &:= (((8! + ((1 \times 5) \times 3!!)) \times 6) - 2) \\ 263536 &:= ((6! + (3 + 5)) \times 362) \\ 263538 &:= ((8! - ((3! \times (-5)) - 3)) \times ((6/2)!)) \\ 263554 &:= (4! + ((5 - (5! \times (-3))) \times (6! + 2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 263568 &:= ((8^6) + ((-(5+3)) + 6!) \times 2)) \\ 263584 &:= (((4^8) \times (5-3)) - 6!) \times (-2)) \\ 263594 &:= ((4^9) + ((5 + ((-(3-6))!))! \times 2)) \\ 263664 &:= ((4! \times 6) + (6! \times (3! - (6!/(-2)))))) \\ 263846 &:= (((6! - 4) \times (8 + (3^6)))/2) \\ 263848 &:= ((8!/4!) + ((8^3!) + ((6-2)!)) \\ 263886 &:= ((6! + (8/8)) \times (3! - (6!/(-2)))) \\ 264237 &:= ((7! - 3) - (((2+4)! \times 6!)/(-2))) \\ 264264 &:= ((-4 + (6!/(-2))) \times ((-4 - 6!) - 2)) \\ 264384 &:= (-4 \times (-8!) - ((3!! - 4) \times (6^2))) \\ 264505 &:= (5 \times (0! + (((5 \times 46)^2))) \\ 264597 &:= (((((-7 \times 9!) \times 5)/4!) + 6)/(-2)) \\ 264598 &:= (((8! + (9!/(5! - 4!))) \times 6) - 2) \\ 264608 &:= (8 \times (((0! - 6!) \times (-46)) + 2)) \\ 264636 &:= -((6! - ((3^6) \times (-4 + (6!/(-2)))))) \\ 264686 &:= (((6! \times 8) - 6) \times 46) + 2) \\ 264862 &:= (-2 + ((6! - 8) \times ((4! + 6!)/2))) \\ 264864 &:= (4! \times (((6! - 8)/4) \times 62)) \\ 264868 &:= ((8 + ((6! - 8) \times (4! + 6!)))/2) \\ 264897 &:= ((-7 \times (9 - 8!)) - (4! \times (((6/2)!)!)) \\ 264984 &:= (((4! \times 8) - 9) \times ((-4 - 6!) \times (-2))) \\ 265236 &:= (-6 \times ((3!! - (2 + 5)) \times (-62))) \\ 265352 &:= ((((-2 - 5!) \times 3) \times (-5 - 6!)) + 2) \\ 265355 &:= ((5 - (5! \times (-3))) \times ((5 + 6!) + 2)) \\ 265363 &:= (((((3 + 6)^3!) + 5) - 6!)/2) \\ 265572 &:= (((2 - 7!) + 5!) \times (-56 - 2)) \\ 265574 &:= ((4! - 7) \times (-5 - ((5^6) + 2))) \\ 265625 &:= ((5 + (2 \times 6)) \times (5^{(6/2)!})) \\ 265627 &:= (((-7 + (-((2 - 6))!)) \times (5^6)) + 2) \\ 265632 &:= (2 \times ((3!^6) + (5! \times (6! - 2)))) \\ 265739 &:= (((9^3!) + (7 + (5 \times 6)))/2) \\ 265745 &:= (5! + ((4! - 7) \times (5^{(6/2)!})) \\ 265965 &:= -((5! - ((6! + 9) \times (5 - (6!/(-2)))))) \\ 265967 &:= ((-7 + (6! \times (-9))) \times (-5 + (6^2))) \\ 266037 &:= (7! - ((3!! - 0!) \times ((-6 - 6!)/2))) \\ 266081 &:= ((-1 - (((8 + 0!)^6) + 6!))/(-2)) \\ 266238 &:= ((8^3!) + ((2^{6+6}) - 2)) \\ 266256 &:= ((6^5) + (((2 - 6!) \times 6!)/(-2))) \\ 266346 &:= (-6 + ((4! - (3! \times 6!)) \times (-62))) \\ 266352 &:= ((-2 - (5! \times (-3))) \times (6! + ((6 - 2)!)) \\ 266364 &:= (((4! + 6!) \times (-3 + 6!)) - 6!)/2) \\ 266438 &:= ((8^3!) - (((4 - 6!) \times 6) + 2)) \\ 266448 &:= ((8 + ((4!/4)!)) \times (6 - (6!/(-2)))) \\ 266468 &:= (((8^6) + 4) + (6! \times ((6/2)!)) \\ 266482 &:= ((((-2 + 8!) + (4^6)) \times 6) - 2) \\ 266487 &:= (-7 + (((8! + (4^6)) \times 6) - 2)) \\ 266488 &:= (((8! + (8^4)) \times 6) - (6 + 2)) \\ 266489 &:= (-9 - (((8! + (4^6)) \times (-6)) - 2)) \\ 266496 &:= (((-((6 - 9))!) \times ((4^6) + ((6 + 2)!)) \\ 266856 &:= ((6! - 5!) + ((86 \times 6)^2)) \\ 266976 &:= ((6^7) + (9 \times (-6!) - (((6/2)!)!)) \\ 267096 &:= (((6 \times 9) - 0!) \times 7!) - ((6 - 2)! \\ 267148 &:= 8^{(4-1)!} + 7! - 6^2 \\ 267176 &:= ((-6 + 7!) + (((1 + 7)^6) - 2)) \\ 267177 &:= ((7! - 7) + ((1 + 7)^{(6/2)!})) \\ 267178 &:= ((-8 + 7!) + (((1 + 7)^6) + 2)) \\ 267184 &:= ((4^{8+1}) + (7 \times (((6/2)!)!)) \\ 267187 &:= (7! + ((8^{-1+7}) + (6/2))) \\ 267208 &:= ((8^{(0!+2)!}) + (7! + ((6 - 2)!)) \\ 267264 &:= ((4! - 6!) \times (-((2^7) \times 6)/2)) \\ 267335 &:= (((-((5^3!)) + 3!!) - (-7 \times ((6 + 2)!)) \\ 267344 &:= (((-((4 + 4)) - 3!!) + 7!) \times 62) \\ 267406 &:= ((((-6!) \times (-((0! - 4)!))! + 7) \times (-62)) \\ 267543 &:= ((3!! + (4 + 5)) \times (7 - (6!/(-2)))) \\ 267544 &:= (((4! + 4!) + 5) \times (7! + (6 + 2))) \\ 267597 &:= ((7! + 9) \times ((57 - 6) + 2)) \\ 267648 &:= ((-8 \times 4!) - ((6! - 7!) \times 62)) \\ 267786 &:= (6 \times (((8! + 7!) - 7) - 6!) - 2) \\ 267796 &:= ((-6 \times (((-9 \times 7!) + 7) + 6!)) - 2) \\ 267826 &:= (((((6! + 2) - 8!) - 7!) \times (-6)) - 2) \\ 267828 &:= ((8 - 2) \times (((8! + 7!) - 6!) - 2)) \\ 267834 &:= (-4 + ((3! \times ((8! + 7!) - 6!)) - 2)) \\ 267835 &:= (-5 + (3 \times (((8! + 7!) - 6!) \times 2)) \\ 267836 &:= (-6 + ((3! \times ((8! + 7!) - 6!)) + 2)) \\ 267852 &:= (((-((2 - 5))!) \times (((8! + 7!) - 6!) + 2)) \\ 267864 &:= (((4 - 6!) + 8!) + 7!) \times ((6/2)! \\ 267868 &:= ((8^6) - ((8!/(-7)) + ((6^2))) \\ 267886 &:= (((((6! - 8) - 8!) - 7!) \times (-6)) - 2) \\ 267894 &:= (((((4^9) - 8) + 7!) + 6!) - 2) \\ 267896 &:= (((((6! - 9) - 8!) - 7!) \times (-6)) + 2) \\ 267904 &:= (((4^09) + 7!) + (((6/2)!)! \\ 267944 &:= (4! + ((4^9) + (76^2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 267985 &:= ((5^8) + ((9! + 7!)/(-6/2))) \\ 268272 &:= ((27^2) \times (8 - (6!/(-2)))) \\ 268322 &:= (-2 + (((2^{3!}) \times 8) + 6^2)) \\ 268333 &:= (-3 + (((3!! \times 3!) + 8) \times 62)) \\ 268336 &:= (((6! \times (-3 + 3)) - 8) \times (-62)) \\ 268353 &:= (((3! + 5!)^3)/(-8)) + (6!^2) \\ 268379 &:= (((9! - 7!) \times 3!) - 8)/(6 + 2) \\ 268562 &:= (2 + (6! \times ((5 + 8) - (6!/(-2)))))) \\ 268583 &:= (((3^8) - 5!) + (((8^6) - 2))) \\ 268584 &:= ((4 \times (85 + 8)) \times (6! + 2)) \\ 268703 &:= ((3^{0!+7}) + (((8^6) - 2))) \\ 268738 &:= -8!/3 + 7 \times 8! - 62 \\ 268795 &:= ((-5 + 9!) - ((-7 \times 8!)/(-6/2))) \\ 268798 &:= (((8!/9) + (7! \times 8)) \times 6) - 2 \\ 268802 &:= ((-20) \times ((8! + 8!)/(-6))) + 2 \\ 268804 &:= (4 \times (0! + ((8! - (8!/6)) \times 2))) \\ 268805 &:= (-5 \times (0! + (((8 \times 8!)/(-6)) - 2))) \\ 268807 &:= ((7 \times (0! + 8!)) - (8!/(6/2))) \\ 268808 &:= (8 \times ((0! + 8!) - (8!/((6/2)!))) \\ 268815 &:= (-5 \times (-1 + (((8 \times 8!)/(-6)) - 2))) \\ 268848 &:= (8 \times ((4 + 8!) - ((8!/6) - 2))) \\ 268855 &:= (-5 \times (5 - (8 \times ((8!/6) + 2)))) \\ 268944 &:= (4! \times ((4 + 9) \times 862)) \\ 269137 &:= (((7! \times 3) + 1) + ((9!/6!)^2)) \\ 269184 &:= ((4! \times 8) \times ((-19) + 6!) \times 2) \\ 269278 &:= ((8! \times 7) - (((2 \times 9) \times 6!) + 2)) \\ 269568 &:= (((8 - 6!) - 5!) \times (-9 \times (6^2))) \\ 269635 &:= (((5^{3!}) - 6) + ((9!/6!)^2)) \\ 269641 &:= (((1 + 4)^6) + ((9!/6!)^2)) \\ 269667 &:= (7! + (((-6 - 6!) \times (9 + 6!))/(-2))) \\ 269676 &:= (-6 \times (((7! - 6) \times (-9)) - (6!/(-2)))) \\ 269973 &:= (-((3^7)) + ((9! \times 9)/(6 \times 2))) \\ 270478 &:= (((8! - (7!/(4 - 0!))) \times 7) - 2) \\ 270576 &:= (((6^7) + ((5 + 0!))!) + (7! \times (-2))) \\ 270848 &:= 8 \times (4! \times 8 - 0! - 7)^2 \\ 271773 &:= (((3! \times (7 - 7!)) + 1) \times (-7 + 2)) \\ 271795 &:= (-5 \times (((9!)/(-7)) + 1) - (7!/2)) \\ 271836 &:= (-6 \times ((3! - ((8 - 1)!)) \times (7 + 2))) \\ 271978 &:= ((8! \times 7) - ((91 + 7!) \times 2)) \\ 272052 &:= (((2 + 50) + 2) \times (7! - 2)) \\ 272054 &:= (((4 + 50) \times (-2 + 7!)) + 2) \\ 272079 &:= (9 \times ((7! \times ((0! + 2))!) - (7 + 2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 272106 &:= (((6 + 0!))! - 1) \times (27 \times 2) \\ 272133 &:= ((3^3) \times (1 - ((-2 \times 7!) + 2))) \\ 272155 &:= (-5 + (((5! - 12) \times 7!)/2)) \\ 272158 &:= (((8!)/(-5 - 1)) \times (-27)) - 2 \\ 272178 &:= ((8! + ((7! - 1) \times (-2))) \times (7 + 2)) \\ 272184 &:= (4! + (((8 - 1)! \times (27 \times 2))) \\ 272193 &:= (3 \times ((9 \times (1 - (-2 \times 7!))) + 2)) \\ 272214 &:= ((4! + (1 + 2)) \times ((2 \times 7!) + 2)) \\ 272259 &:= (-9 + ((52 + 2) \times (7! + 2))) \\ 272268 &:= ((8^6) - ((-22) - 7!) \times 2) \\ 272272 &:= (2 \times (((7! + 2) \times 27) + 2)) \\ 272322 &:= (2 \times ((2 + ((3!!/2) + 7))^2)) \\ 272373 &:= ((3!^7) + (3 \times ((2 + 7!)/(-2)))) \\ 272374 &:= (((4 + 7!) \times 3!) \times (2 + 7)) - 2 \\ 272376 &:= (-6 \times (((7! + 3!) - 2) \times (-7 + 2))) \\ 272496 &:= (-6 \times ((9 \times (-((4 + 2) - 7!)) - 2)) \\ 272544 &:= -(((4!^4) + (5! \times ((2 - 7!) + 2))) \\ 272856 &:= (6 \times (((5! + 8!) - 2) + 7!) - 2) \\ 272866 &:= (6! + ((6 \times ((8! - 2) + 7!)) - 2)) \\ 272876 &:= ((6! - (-7 \times 8!)) + ((2 + 7!) \times (-2))) \\ 272946 &:= ((6! + (4^9)) + ((2 \times 7!) + 2)) \\ 273218 &:= -(((8!)/((1 + 2)!)) - ((3!^7) + 2)) \\ 273338 &:= (((-8!) + 3!)/3!) + (((3!^7) + 2)) \\ 273352 &:= (((2^5) + 3!) \times (3! + 7))/2) \\ 273373 &:= ((3!^7) - ((3 \times (3^7)) + 2)) \\ 273383 &:= ((-((3^8)) + 3!) + ((3!^7) + 2)) \\ 273456 &:= ((-(((6^5) \times 4) + 3!)) \times (-7 + 2)) \\ 273486 &:= ((68 \times (4^{3!})) - (7! + 2)) \\ 273529 &:= (((((9^2) + 5) \times 3!) + 7)^2) \\ 273576 &:= ((6^7) + (-53) \times ((7 - 2)!)) \\ 273595 &:= (-5 \times (((-9 - (5^{3!})) \times (-7))/(-2))) \\ 273744 &:= -(((4!^4) - ((7! + 3!) \times ((7 - 2)!))) \\ 273755 &:= (((-5 - 5!) \times (-7 + 3!)) + ((7 + 2)!)) \\ 273794 &:= (((4! \times (9 + 7)) \times (3! - 7)) + 2) \\ 273838 &:= ((8!)/(-3)) + (((-8!) - 3!) \times (-7) - 2) \\ 273856 &:= -((6! - (((5 + ((8^3) + 7))^2))) \\ 273856 &:= -6! + (5 + 8^3 + 7)^2 \\ 273948 &:= ((8!/4!) + ((9 \times 3!) \times (7! + 2))) \\ 274178 &:= ((8!)/(-7)) + (((-((1 - 4)!))^7) + 2) \\ 274246 &:= (((((6! + 4!)^2) - 4) - 7!)/2) \\ 274568 &:= (((8! \times 6) - 5!) + ((4^7) \times 2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 274576 &:= (((6! + 7) - ((5 + 4!) \times 7))^2) \\ 274658 &:= (8! - 5) \times 6 + 4^7 \times 2 \\ 274678 &:= (((8! + 7!) \times 6) - ((-4 + 7!)/(-2))) \\ 274684 &:= (-4 - ((8! \times (-6)) - ((4^7) \times 2))) \\ 274695 &:= (((5! - (9! \times (-6)))/4) + 7!)/2 \\ 274776 &:= (((6^7) - 7!) - (4! \times (7 - 2))) \\ 275088 &:= (88 \times (0! + (5^{7-2}))) \\ 275338 &:= (((8 - (3!! \times (-3))) \times (5! + 7)) + 2) \\ 275384 &:= (-4!) + ((-8!)/3!!) \times ((5! - 7!) + 2))) \\ 275395 &:= (((5! \times (-9^3)) - 5) + ((7 + 2)!)) \\ 275408 &:= ((-80) + 4!) \times ((5! - 7!) + 2) \\ 275456 &:= -((((6! \times 5!) + (4^5)) - ((7 + 2)!)) \\ 275488 &:= 8 \times (8! - 4 - 5! \times 7^2) \\ 275518 &:= -((((8!/(1 + 5))!) \times (5! - 7!)) + 2) \\ 275618 &:= (8! + (((((1 + 6)^5) \times 7) \times 2))) \\ 275632 &:= -((((2^3)!) / 6!) \times ((5! - 7!) - 2))) \\ 275744 &:= (-4 \times (((-4 - 7!) + 5!) \times (7 \times 2))) \\ 275745 &:= ((5 \times 4!) + (((75 \times 7)^2))) \\ 276334 &:= (((-4 \times 3!!) - 3!!) + (((6^7) - 2))) \\ 276335 &:= ((-5 \times 3!!) - ((3 - ((6^7) + 2)))) \\ 276336 &:= (6 \times (((3!^3!) - 6!) + ((7 - 2)!)) \\ 276338 &:= (((8 \times 3!) \times ((-3 + 6!) + 7!)) + 2) \\ 276344 &:= ((4 + (4! \times ((-3 + 6!) + 7!))) \times 2) \\ 276346 &:= (-6 - ((4^3) \times ((6! - 7!) + 2))) \\ 276358 &:= (((8! - 5!) - ((-((3 - 6))!)) \times 7) - 2) \\ 276382 &:= (-2 + ((8 \times 3!) \times ((6! + 7!) - 2))) \\ 276384 &:= (4! \times (((8 - 3!) - 6!) - 7!) \times (-2))) \\ 276424 &:= (-4 \times (((2 \times 4!) \times 6!) - 7) \times (-2))) \\ 276432 &:= ((((-2 + 3!))! - ((4! \times (6! + 7!)))) \times (-2)) \\ 276444 &:= (-4 \times (((4! \times (-4)) \times 6!) + (7 + 2))) \\ 276448 &:= (-((8 \times 4) - (4! \times ((6! + 7!) \times (-2)))) \\ 276452 &:= (2 \times (((5! - 4!) \times 6!) - 7) \times 2) \\ 276454 &:= ((4 \times (((5! - 4!) \times 6!) - 7)) + 2) \\ 276455 &:= (-((5 \times 5) - (4! \times ((6! + 7!) \times (-2)))) \\ 276456 &:= -((((6! \times 5!) + ((4 \times 6))) - ((7 + 2)!)) \\ 276464 &:= (-4 + ((6 - (4! \times (6! + 7!))) \times (-2))) \\ 276466 &:= ((6! \times (64 \times 6)) - (7 \times 2)) \\ 276467 &:= (-((7 + 6) - (4! \times ((6! + 7!) \times (-2)))) \\ 276469 &:= (-9 - ((64 \times (6! - 7!)) + 2)) \\ 276474 &:= (((4 - 7) + (4! \times (6! + 7!))) \times 2) \\ 276478 &:= (((8!/7) \times 4!) + ((6 - 7)) \times 2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 276494 &:= (((((4! \times 9) - 4!) \times 6!) + 7) \times 2) \\ 276497 &:= ((((-7 + 9!) + 4!) - (6! \times ((7 - 2)!)) \\ 276504 &:= (4! - (((05!) \times 6!) - ((7 + 2)!)) \\ 276574 &:= ((-((4 \times 7)) \times 5!) + (((6^7) - 2))) \\ 276578 &:= ((8! / (-7 + 5)) + ((6^7) + 2)) \\ 276595 &:= ((5! + 9!) - ((5! \times 6!) + (7 - 2))) \\ 276624 &:= (4! \times (((2 \times 6!) + 6) + (7! \times 2))) \\ 276684 &:= (((((4! \times 8!) + 6!) - 6) / 7) \times 2) \\ 276744 &:= (4! \times ((4 + 7) - ((6! + 7!) \times (-2)))) \\ 276768 &:= (((8! - 6!) \times 7) - (6 \times 72)) \\ 276784 &:= (4! + ((-8 + 7!) \times (6 + (7^2)))) \\ 276848 &:= ((-8 + (4! \times ((8 + 6!) + 7!))) \times 2) \\ 276864 &:= (4! \times (6! + (((8 \times (6 + 7))^2))) \\ 276925 &:= ((5 - (-((2 - 9)))!) \times (-6 + (7^2))) \\ 276928 &:= (-((8^2)) \times (((-9 + 6!) - 7!) + 2)) \\ 276992 &:= (((2^9) + 9!) - (6! \times ((7 - 2)!)) \\ 277034 &:= (((4! + 3!!) - ((0! + 7!))!) \times (-7)) + 2) \\ 277054 &:= (-((4! \times 5!)) + ((-((0! - 7))^7) - 2)) \\ 277085 &:= -((5! - (((8! + 0!) \times 7) - 7!) - 2)) \\ 277087 &:= ((7 \times (8! + 0!)) - (7! + ((7 - 2)!)) \\ 277128 &:= (8! - (2 + 1)!) \times 7 - 72 \\ 277137 &:= -7 \times (3!! - (1 + 7)! + 7 + 2) \\ 277139 &:= (((9^3) - ((1 + 7)!)) \times (-7)) + 2) \\ 277174 &:= (((4 - ((7 + 1))!) \times (-7)) - 7!) + 2) \\ 277186 &:= (((6! - 8!) \times (-1 \times 7)) - (7 \times 2)) \\ 277187 &:= (((7 \times 8!) + 1) - 7!) - (7 \times 2) \\ 277189 &:= (-9 + ((8! \times (1 \times 7)) - 7!) - 2) \\ 277191 &:= (((1 - ((9 - 1))!) \times (-7)) - 7!) - 2) \\ 277194 &:= (-4 - (((9 - 1)! \times (-7)) + 7!) + 2) \\ 277196 &:= (-6 + (((9 - 1)! \times 7) - 7!) + 2) \\ 277198 &:= (((8 \times 9) - 17) \times 7!) - 2) \\ 277202 &:= (((2^{0!+2})!) \times 7) - (7! - 2) \\ 277247 &:= ((((-7 - ((4 \times 2))!) \times (-7)) - 7!) - 2) \\ 277248 &:= (((8! - 4!) \times (-2)) - 7!) + ((7 + 2)!)) \\ 277255 &:= (55 \times (((-2 - 7!) - 7!) / (-2))) \\ 277286 &:= (((6! - 8!) - 2) \times (-7)) + 72) \\ 277319 &:= ((9! - 1) - ((3!! - 7) \times ((7 - 2)!)) \\ 277344 &:= (((4! \times 4!) + (3! \times 7!)) \times (7 + 2)) \\ 277348 &:= (((8! + 4) - 3!!) \times 7) + (((7 - 2)!)) \\ 277352 &:= (((-2 - (5 \times 3!)) \times (-77)) - 2) \\ 277365 &:= ((5 + 6) \times ((3 + 7!) \times (7 - 2))) \\ 277368 &:= (((-8 - 6!) \times (-3)) \times (7 + ((7 - 2)!)) \end{aligned}$$

- 277384 := $((-(4 \times 8)) + (3!^7)) - (7!/2)$
277408 := $-8 + (-0! + 4)!^7 - 7!/2$
277413 := $(-3 + (((-(1 - 4))!)^7) + (7!/(-2)))$
277416 := $((6^{4 \times 7}) - (7!/2))$
277475 := $((5 + 7!) \times (4 + ((7 \times 7) + 2)))$
277583 := $((((3 + 8) \times 5) \times (7! + 7)) - 2)$
277697 := $((7! + 9) \times (6 + (7 \times 7))) + 2$
277776 := $((6^7) - (((7!/(-7)) + 7!)/2))$
277873 := $(3!! + (((7 - 8!) \times (-7)) - 7!) + 2)$
277938 := $((-(8!) + 3!!) - (9 \times ((7! \times (-7)) - 2)))$
278035 := $((((-5!) + 3!!) + (0! - 8!)) \times (-7)) + 2$
278136 := $((6! + (3!^{-1+8})) - (7!/2))$
278224 := $(((((4!^2) - 2) - 8!) \times (-7)) + 2)$
278245 := $((5 - ((4!^2) - 8!)) \times 7) + 2$
278306 := $-(((6! + 0!) \times (3! - (8 \times (7^2))))))$
278374 := $(((((4! \times 7) - 3!!) + 8!) \times 7) - 2)$
278593 := $((3!! + 9) \times (-5)) + ((8! \times 7) - 2)$
278598 := $((8!/(-9)) - (((5! + 8!) \times (-7)) + 2))$
278638 := $((-(8 - 3) \times 6!) + ((8! \times 7) - 2))$
278648 := $((8^4) \times 68) + ((7 - 2)!)$
278676 := $((6^7) - ((6!/(-8)) \times (-7 \times 2)))$
278693 := $((3 + ((9!/6!) - 8!)) \times (-7)) + 2$
278784 := $((4! + ((8 \times ((7 \times 8) + 7))))^2)$
278945 := $(((((5! \times 4) - 9) - 8!) \times (-7)) + 2)$
279166 := $((6! + 6!) - 1) \times (97 \times 2)$
279334 := $((-4 \times (3! + (3!! \times (-97)))) - 2)$
279344 := $((-4!) + (-4 \times ((3!! \times (-97)) - 2)))$
279346 := $((-6 + (-4 \times ((3!! \times (-97)) + 2)))$
279348 := $((-(8! - 4!)) - (3!!^{9-7}))/(-2)$
279349 := $((-9 + (((-4 \times 3!!) \times (-97)) - 2))$
279358 := $((8 \times 5!) \times (3 \times 97)) - 2$
279366 := $6 \times (6^{3!} - 97 + 2)$
279384 := $(4! + (((8 \times 3!!) \times 97)/2))$
279394 := $((-4 \times (-9 + (3!! \times (-97)))) - 2)$
279464 := $((-4 - 6!) \times (-((4 \times 97) - 2)))$
279576 := $((6^7) - (((((5 - 9) + 7))!)!/2))$
279648 := $(8! - (4! \times ((-(6 \times 9)) + 7!) \times (-2)))$
279682 := $((2^8) + (((-(6 - 9))!)^7) + 2)$
279687 := $((7 \times (8! - 6)) + 9) - (7!/2)$
279713 := $(((((3! - 1)^7) - 9!) + 7!) + 2)$
279718 := $((((8! + 1) \times 7) - 9) - (7!/2))$
279735 := $-((5! - ((3!^7) - ((9 + 72))))))$
279736 := $((-6 + ((3!^7) - ((97 \times 2))))$
279753 := $((3 \times (5^7)) - (-9 \times (7! + 2)))$
279776 := $((6^7) - ((7!/(-9 \times 7)) \times (-2)))$
279778 := $((((8! + 7) \times 7) + 9) - (7!/2))$
279816 := $((6^{-1+8}) - (-((9 - (7 \times 2))))!)$
279841 := $(-1 + 4!)^{8-9+7-2}$
279873 := $((3!^7) - (((8 \times 9) - 7) - 2))$
279927 := $((-7 + (((2 + (9/9)))!^7) - 2))$
279929 := $((-9 + (((2 + (9/9)))!^7) + 2))$
279932 := $((-2 + ((3!^{9-9+7}) - 2))$
279933 := $((-3 - ((3! \times (-9)) \times ((9!/7!)^2)))$
279973 := $((3!^7) + (((9 \times 9) - 7)/2))$
280176 := $((6^7) - (-10 \times ((8/2)!))$
280448 := $((8! - (4^4)) \times (0! + (8 - 2)))$
280537 := $((-7 \times ((3^5) - (08!)) - 2)$
280558 := $-((((8! - 5!) - 5!) \times (0! - 8)) + 2)$
280634 := $((-(4!) + 3!!) + ((6^{-0!+8}) + 2))$
280653 := $((3!! - 5) + ((6^{-0!+8}) + 2))$
280656 := $(6 \times (5! + ((6^{08-2})))$
280658 := $((((8 - 5)!))! + ((6^{-0!+8}) + 2))$
280663 := $((3^6) + ((6^{-0!+8}) - 2))$
280666 := $(6! + ((6^{6+0!}) + (8 + 2)))$
280673 := $((((3!^7) + 6!) + 0!) + ((8 \times 2)))$
280776 := $((6^7) + (7!/(08 - 2)))$
280795 := $((-5 + 9!) + (((7 - 0!))! + 8!) \times (-2)))$
280943 := $-((((3!^4) - 9!) + 0!) + (8! \times 2)))$
280946 := $((-(6^4) + 9!) - ((0! - 8!) \times (-2)))$
281356 := $(((-6 - (5^{3!})) \times (-18)) - 2)$
281358 := $((8! - 5!) - 3!) \times ((1 + 8) - 2)$
281374 := $((-4!) + ((-7 \times (((3! - 1)! - 8!)) - 2))$
281376 := $((6^7) - (-((3 - 1) \times ((8 - 2)!))!)$
281378 := $-8 + 7 \times (-3! - 1)! + 8! - 2$
281407 := $((-7 \times (((0! + ((4 + 1)!)) - 8!) - 2))$
281476 := $-((6! + ((7 \times (((4 - 1)! - 8!)) + 2)))$
281496 := $((((6! - 9!) + 4!) \times (-1)) - (8! \times 2))$
281506 := $-((6! - ((0! + (5 + 1)) \times (8! - 2)))$
281519 := $((9! - 1) - ((5 + 1)!)) - (8! \times 2)$
281538 := $(8! - (3! \times (((5! - 1) - 8!) - 2)))$
281547 := $(7 \times (((4! - 5!) - 1) + 8!) - 2)$

$$\begin{aligned} 281576 &:= -((6! + (-7 \times ((5 + 1) + 8!) + 2))) \\ 281647 &:= ((-7 \times ((4! + (61)) - 8!)) + 2) \\ 281727 &:= ((-7 \times ((2 + 71) - 8!)) - 2) \\ 281729 &:= ((9 - 2) \times ((-71) + 8!) - 2) \\ 281736 &:= (-((6! - (3!^7))) - ((-((1 - 8)!)/(-2))) \\ 281738 &:= (((-8!)/3!!) \times (-7! - (1 + 8))) + 2) \\ 281748 &:= (8! - 4!) \times 7 - 18^2 \\ 281757 &:= (-7 \times ((5 - ((7 + 1)!)) + (8^2))) \\ 281792 &:= (-((2 - 9)) \times (((7 + 1)! - (8^2))) \\ 281797 &:= ((-7 \times ((9 \times 7) - ((1 \times 8)!)) - 2) \\ 281855 &:= ((55 - 8!) \times (-((1 + 8) - 2))) \\ 282037 &:= (-7 \times ((3^{0!+2}) - (8! - 2))) \\ 282067 &:= ((-7 \times (((6 - 0!)^2) - 8!)) + 2) \\ 282072 &:= (((2 - 7!) + 0!) \times (-28 \times 2)) \\ 282119 &:= ((9! - ((11^2))) - (8! \times 2)) \\ 282137 &:= ((-7 \times ((3 + 12) - 8!)) + 2) \\ 282158 &:= 8! \times (5 \times 1 + 2) - 82 \\ 282207 &:= ((-7 \times ((0! + (2 + 2)) - 8!)) + 2) \\ 282212 &:= ((2 + 12) \times (-2 + (8!/2))) \\ 282217 &:= ((-7 \times (((1^2) + 2) - 8!)) - 2) \\ 282218 &:= (8 + 1)! - 22 - 8! \times 2 \\ 282219 &:= ((9! + ((1 - 22))) - (8! \times 2)) \\ 282226 &:= (((6 \times 2) + 2) \times ((2 - 8!)/(-2))) \\ 282228 &:= (((8! - 2) \times (-((2/2) - 8))) + 2) \\ 282229 &:= ((9! - (22/2)) - (8! \times 2)) \\ 282231 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times (-((2/2) + 8!)) - 2) \\ 282233 &:= ((-3 + ((3^2)!)) + ((2 + 8!) \times (-2))) \\ 282234 &:= (-4 - (((-((3 + 2) + 2)) \times 8!) + 2)) \\ 282235 &:= (-5 - (((3! \times 2) + 2) \times 8!)/(-2)) \\ 282236 &:= ((((((6 + 3)!/2) - 2) - 8!) \times 2) \\ 282237 &:= ((-7 + ((3^2)!)) + ((2 - 8!) \times 2)) \\ 282238 &:= (((8! \times 3!) - 2) + (((2 \times 8)/2)!)) \\ 282239 &:= ((9! - 3) - (((2/2) - 8!) \times (-2))) \\ 282242 &:= (((2 \times 4)! \times (-((2/2) - 8))) + 2) \\ 282251 &:= (-1 + (((5 + 2) \times (2 + 8!)) - 2)) \\ 282253 &:= (-3 - (((5 + 2) \times (-2 - 8!)) - 2)) \\ 282254 &:= ((4 + (5 \times 2)) \times ((2 + 8!)/2)) \\ 282258 &:= ((8! \times (5 + 2)) + ((2 \times 8) + 2)) \\ 282259 &:= (((9! - 5) + ((2 + 2)!)) - (8! \times 2)) \\ 282261 &:= ((1 + 6) \times (((2/2) + 8!) + 2)) \\ 282264 &:= (4! - ((6!)/(-2)) \times (28^2)) \\ 282268 &:= ((8 + 6) \times (-((2 + 2) - 8!)/(-2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 282287 &:= (((7 + 8!) \times (-((2/2) - 8))) - 2) \\ 282288 &:= -((8! + (8 \times (-((2 + 2)) - 8!) - 2))) \\ 282304 &:= ((4^{03^2}) + (8!/2)) \\ 282317 &:= (-7 \times (-((1 \times 3)^2)) - 8! - 2) \\ 282338 &:= ((8 + 3!) \times (3! + ((2 + 8!)/2))) \\ 282347 &:= ((-7 \times (((4! + 3!)/(-2)) - 8!)) + 2) \\ 282352 &:= ((2 + 5) \times (((3! + 2)! + (8 \times 2))) \\ 282355 &:= (((5! - 5) + ((3^2)!)) - (8! \times 2)) \\ 282357 &:= ((-7 \times (-((5 \times 3) + 2)) - 8!)) - 2) \\ 282358 &:= ((8! + 5!) + (((3 \times 2) \times 8!) - 2)) \\ 282359 &:= (((9! + 5!) - 3) + ((-2 \times 8!) + 2)) \\ 282368 &:= (((8^6) - ((3!/2) \times 8!)) \times 2) \\ 282384 &:= (((4! + 8!) \times 3!) + (((2 \times 8)/2)!)) \\ 282386 &:= ((-6 \times (-8!) - ((3! - 2)!)) + (8! + 2)) \\ 282387 &:= (7 \times (8! + (3 + ((2 \times 8) + 2)))) \\ 282408 &:= ((8 - 0!) \times (4! + (((2 \times 8)/2)!)) \\ 282417 &:= ((-7 \times (-((1 + 4)^2)) - 8!)) + 2) \\ 282448 &:= -((8! + (-4 \times (((4! + 2) + 8!) \times 2)))) \\ 282476 &:= ((6 + ((7! + 4) \times 28)) \times 2) \\ 282478 &:= ((8! \times 7) + ((4! \times (2 + 8)) - 2)) \\ 282576 &:= ((6 + 7!) \times (52 + (8/2))) \\ 282597 &:= (-7 \times (9 + ((5! + (2 \times 8!))/(-2)))) \\ 282671 &:= (-1 - ((-7 \times (62 + 8!)) + 2)) \\ 282673 &:= (-3 - ((-7 \times (62 + 8!)) - 2)) \\ 282678 &:= (((8! \times 7) + 6!) - 282) \\ 282679 &:= (-9 + (-7 \times (-62 - 8!) - 2)) \\ 282737 &:= (-7 \times (((3 - 72) - 8!) - 2)) \\ 282807 &:= (7 \times ((0! + 8!) - (2 - 82))) \\ 282816 &:= (((6 + 1) \times (82 + 8!)) + 2) \\ 282837 &:= ((-7 \times (-((3 + 82)) - 8!)) + 2) \\ 282876 &:= (6! - ((-7 \times 8!) + ((2 + 82)))) \\ 282877 &:= (-7 \times ((-7 - 8!) - ((2 + 82)))) \\ 282878 &:= 8! \times 7 - 82 + (8 - 2)! \\ 282896 &:= ((6! + 9!) - ((8! \times 2) + (8^2))) \\ 282897 &:= ((-7 \times (9 - 8!)) + ((2 + (8/2)!)) \\ 282934 &:= (((-4!) + 3!!) + (((9 - 2) \times 8!) - 2)) \\ 282938 &:= ((-8 + 3!!) + ((9 - 2) \times (8! - 2))) \\ 282946 &:= (6! - (((4 - 9) - 2) \times (8! - 2))) \\ 282953 &:= (3!! + (-5 + (((9 - 2) \times 8!) - 2)) \\ 282956 &:= (((6 \times 5!) + 9!) + ((2 + 8!) \times (-2))) \\ 282958 &:= (((8 - 5)! + ((9 - 2) \times 8!) - 2)) \\ 282974 &:= (((-((4 - 7)))! + ((9 - 2) \times (8! + 2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 282978 &:= ((8! \times 7) + ((92 \times 8) + 2)) \\ 282984 &:= (4! - ((8! \times (-9 - 2))) - ((8 - 2)!)) \\ 282996 &:= ((6! + 9!) + (((9 \times 2) - 8!) \times 2)) \\ 283057 &:= ((7 \times ((5! - 03) + 8!)) - 2) \\ 283074 &:= (-4 + ((7 \times (((0! - 3!)))! + 8!)) - 2)) \\ 283076 &:= (-6 + ((7 \times (((0! - 3!)))! + 8!)) + 2)) \\ 283087 &:= (7 \times (8! + ((03 + 8)^2)) \\ 283157 &:= (7 \times (((5! + 13) + 8!) - 2)) \\ 283335 &:= ((((-5 - 3!)) \times (3!! + (3!))) - 8!)/(-2)) \\ 283349 &:= ((9! - (43^3)) - ((8/2)!)) \\ 283507 &:= (-7 \times (-0!) + (-5 \times ((3!!/8)^2))) \\ 283536 &:= ((-(((6^3) - 5!)) - 3!!) \times (-8 - 2)) \\ 283668 &:= (8! - (-6 \times (((6!/3) + 8!) - 2))) \\ 283678 &:= ((8! \times 7) - (6 - (38^2))) \\ 283679 &:= ((9! - 7) - (((6! + 3) - 8!) \times (-2))) \\ 283691 &:= ((-1 + 9!) + (((6! + 3!) - 8!) \times 2)) \\ 283698 &:= (8! - (((-9 - 6!) + (-3 \times 8!)) \times 2)) \\ 283736 &:= ((6! + 3!!) + (7 \times ((3! + 8!) + 2))) \\ 283738 &:= (((8! + 3!) \times 7) - ((3!! + 8) \times (-2))) \\ 283765 &:= (((5^6) \times (7 + 3!)) + (8! \times 2)) \\ 283968 &:= (8 \times (-6!) + ((9! - 3!)/(8 + 2))) \\ 284757 &:= ((((-7 + 5!) \times 7!) - ((4!/8)!)/2) \\ 284758 &:= 8! \times (5! - 7)/(4! - 8) - 2 \\ 284759 &:= ((9! - (5^7)) + (4!/(8 - 2))) \\ 284976 &:= ((6^7) + (((9 + 4) - 8) + 2)!)) \\ 285144 &:= (4! \times (((-((4 - 1)) + 5!) - 8^2)) \\ 285147 &:= ((-7 \times (-415) - 8!)) + 2) \\ 285355 &:= (-5 + (((-5 \times 3!) + 5!) \times (-82))) \\ 285475 &:= ((-((5^7)) + ((4 + 5)!)) + ((8 - 2)!)) \\ 285598 &:= (((((8 + 9)! \times 5)/(5 + 8)!)) - 2) \\ 285605 &:= 5 \times (-0! + 6 \times 5 \times 8)^2 \\ 285744 &:= (4! \times (4! + (((7 + 5)!/8!) + 2))) \\ 285745 &:= (5 \times ((4! + (7^5)) + 8!) - 2) \\ 285835 &:= (-5 + (((3!! + 8!) \times 5) + (8! \times 2))) \\ 285838 &:= 5! + (3!! + 8!) \times 5 + 8! - 2 \\ 285864 &:= ((4! + ((6! + 8!) \times 5)) + (8! \times 2)) \\ 285865 &:= ((((-5 - 6!) - 8!) \times (-5)) + (8! \times 2)) \\ 286225 &:= (((5^2)^2) + (6!/(-8)))^2 \\ 286344 &:= (((4! \times 4!) + 3!) \times (6 \times 82)) \\ 286348 &:= ((8! + (4^3)) - (-6 \times (8! + 2))) \\ 286464 &:= ((((-4 + 6!) \times 4!) + 6!) \times (8 \times 2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 286844 &:= (((4!^4) + ((8! \times 6) - 8))/2) \\ 287157 &:= (((7! - 5!) - 1) - ((-7 \times 8!) + 2)) \\ 287159 &:= (((9! - 5!) - 1) + 7!) - (8! \times 2)) \\ 287175 &:= -((((5! - 7!) - 1) - (7 \times (8! + 2)))) \\ 287217 &:= (7 \times (((1 + 2)!))! + ((-7 + 8!) - 2)) \\ 287254 &:= -(((4! - ((5 + 2)!)) + ((-7 \times 8!) + 2))) \\ 287256 &:= (((6 - 5!)/(-2)) \times 7!) - ((8/2)!)) \\ 287257 &:= 7! - 5^2 + 7 \times 8! + 2 \\ 287258 &:= ((-8 + ((5 + 2)!)) + (7 \times (8! - 2))) \\ 287273 &:= (((-3 + 7!) - 2) - ((-7 \times 8!) + 2)) \\ 287274 &:= (-4 - (((-((7^2)) \times 7!) - 8!) + 2)) \\ 287275 &:= ((-5 + 7!) - (((2 \times 7) \times 8!)/(-2))) \\ 287276 &:= (((6 - ((7 - 2)!)) \times 7!) + 8)/(-2)) \\ 287277 &:= ((7! - (7 - 2)) + ((7 \times 8!) + 2)) \\ 287278 &:= (((8! \times 7) + 2) + 7!) - (8/2)) \\ 287292 &:= ((-2 + ((9 - 2)!)) + (7 \times (8! + 2))) \\ 287294 &:= (((4 - 9) - 2)! + (7 \times (8! + 2))) \\ 287304 &:= (4! - (((0! + 3!))! \times (7 - (8^2)))) \\ 287327 &:= ((7 \times (((2 \times 3)! + 7) + 8!)) - 2) \\ 287331 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times (3!! + (7 + 8!))) + 2) \\ 287337 &:= ((7! + (3/3)) \times (-7 - (8^2))) \\ 287338 &:= (((8^3) - 3!) + 7!) + (8!/2) \\ 287343 &:= ((3 + 4) \times (3!! - ((-7 - 8!) - 2))) \\ 287344 &:= (((4 + 4)^3) + 7!) + (8!/2) \\ 287358 &:= (((8^5) \times (3 + 7)) - 8!) - 2) \\ 287362 &:= (((-(((2 + 6)!)) - 3!!) \times (-7)) + (82)) \\ 287383 &:= (((3!! + (8! + 3)) \times 7) + (82)) \\ 287384 &:= (((4! + 8!) + 3!!) \times 7) - ((8^2)) \\ 287386 &:= (((6! + 8!) + 3!) \times 7) + (8^2) \\ 287387 &:= ((-7 \times ((-8!) - 3!) - (7 + 8))) + 2) \\ 287438 &:= (((8! + 3!) + 4!) \times 7) - (8 + 2) \\ 287494 &:= (((4! + 9)^{-4+7}) \times 8) - 2) \\ 287519 &:= ((9! - 1) - (5! \times ((7!/8) - 2))) \\ 287527 &:= (((7^2) \times (-5 - 7!)) + (8! + 2)) \\ 287537 &:= ((7! + ((3^5))) + (7 \times (8! + 2))) \\ 287544 &:= -((4! \times (4! - ((5 \times (7^{8/2})))))) \\ 287575 &:= (((5 + 7!) \times 57) + (8 + 2)) \\ 287664 &:= (((4! \times ((6! \times 6) - 7)) + 8!) \times 2) \\ 287734 &:= (((4^3) - 7) \times (7! + 8)) - 2) \\ 287849 &:= (((-((9^4)) - 8!) \times (-7)) - 8!) + 2) \\ 287937 &:= (((-73) \times (-9 - 7!)) - (8! \times 2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 287972 &:= (((2 \times (-7 - (9!/(-7)))) + 8!) \times 2) \\ 287986 &:= (((6! \times 8) + 9!) + ((7 + 8!) \times (-2))) \\ 287995 &:= (-5 - (((9! + 9!)/(-7)) - 8!) \times 2) \\ 288368 &:= (8 \times ((-6 \times (3!! - 8)) + ((8! - 2))) \\ 288386 &:= (((((6! - 8) \times 3!) - 8!) \times (-8)) + 2) \\ 288566 &:= ((-6 \times (-((6^5) - 8!)) - (8 + 2)) \\ 288568 &:= (-8 - ((-((6^5) - 8!) \times (8 - 2))) \\ 288576 &:= ((6^7) + (5! \times (8 + (8^2)))) \\ 288636 &:= ((6^3!) + (-6 \times ((-8 - 8!) - 2))) \\ 288897 &:= ((-7 \times (9 - 8!)) + (8!/(8 - 2))) \\ 288968 &:= (((8!/6) + 9!) + 8) - (8! \times 2) \\ 289584 &:= (((4 \times 8!)/(-5)) \times (-9)) - ((8 - 2)!) \\ 289737 &:= (73 \times (((7 \times 9!)/8!)^2)) \\ 289768 &:= (8 \times (-(67) + (9!/(8 + 2)))) \\ 289792 &:= ((2^9) \times ((7!/9) + (8 - 2))) \\ 290405 &:= (5 \times ((0! + (4! \times (0! + 9)))^2)) \\ 291447 &:= (((-7 + (4!^4)) - (-((1 - 9)))!) - 2) \\ 291448 &:= (-8 + ((4!^4) - (((1 + 9) - 2)!)) \\ 291449 &:= (((-9 + (4!^4)) - (-((1 - 9)))!) + 2) \\ 291454 &:= (((4!^5)/4!) - (-((1 - 9)))!) - 2) \\ 291548 &:= -((8! - ((4!^{5-1}) + (92)))) \\ 291593 &:= (((3!! \times (-9 \times 5)) + 1) \times (-9)) + 2) \\ 291688 &:= ((-88) - 6!) \times (-19^2)) \\ 291699 &:= (9! - (9 \times ((6! - 1) \times (9 + 2)))) \\ 291848 &:= (8 \times (((4! \times 8) - (1^9))^2)) \\ 292005 &:= (-5 \times ((-0!) - (((0! + 2)!)!) \times (9^2))) \\ 292315 &:= (-5 - (((1 + 3)!)! \times (-29 \times 2))) \\ 292318 &:= (((8!)/(-1 + 3)) \times (-29)) - 2) \\ 292344 &:= (4! - (((4 + 3)!) \times (-29 \times 2))) \\ 292348 &:= ((-((8! + 4)) + (3!! \times (-2))) \times (-9 - 2)) \\ 292372 &:= (((-2 + 7!) \times 3!) + ((2^9)^2)) \\ 292375 &:= (-5 \times (7 - ((3!! + 2) \times (9^2)))) \\ 292377 &:= (-7 + ((7! \times 3!) + ((2^9)^2))) \\ 292653 &:= ((3 + (5 \times (6! + 2))) \times (9^2)) \\ 292774 &:= ((4! - ((7! + 7) \times (-29))) \times 2) \\ 292782 &:= (-2 - ((-8 - 7!) \times (29 \times 2))) \\ 292784 &:= (-4 \times (((-8 - 7!) \times 29)/2)) \\ 292794 &:= ((4! + ((9 + 7!) \times (-29))) \times (-2)) \\ 293166 &:= ((6 \times 61) \times (3!! + ((9^2)))) \\ 293384 &:= (((4! + 8!)/3) + (3!^{9-2})) \\ 293544 &:= (((4! + (4! \times 5!)) + 3!!) \times (9^2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 293585 &:= (-5 \times (8 - ((-5 - 3!!) \times (-9^2)))) \\ 293625 &:= (-5 \times (((2 + 6!) + 3) \times (-9^2))) \\ 293758 &:= ((-((8 \times (5 + 7))) \times 3!!) + ((9! - 2))) \\ 293762 &:= ((-2 \times ((6! + 7!) \times 3!)) + (9! + 2)) \\ 293764 &:= (((((4! - 6!) \times 7) - 3!)/(-9))^2) \\ 293778 &:= ((8! \times 7) + (((-7!) - 3!!) - 9) \times (-2))) \\ 293888 &:= 8 \times (8! - 8^3 \times (9 - 2)) \\ 294168 &:= (8 \times ((6! + 1) \times (49 + 2))) \\ 294334 &:= ((4! \times ((3! - 3!!) \times 4)) + ((9! - 2))) \\ 294336 &:= (((6^3!) \times 3!) + ((-((4 - 9)))!^2)) \\ 294546 &:= ((6! \times 45) + ((4^9) + 2)) \\ 294576 &:= ((6^7) - (-5!) \times ((-((4 - 9)))! + 2))) \\ 294624 &:= ((4! - 2) \times ((6! + 4!) \times (9 \times 2))) \\ 294768 &:= (-8! + 6^7/4 \times 9)/2 \\ 294788 &:= ((((-8 + 8!) + 7!) \times (-4 + 9))/(-2)) \\ 294804 &:= (((-((4^08)) + 4!) \times (-9))/2) \\ 294827 &:= (((7! - 2) + 8!) \times (-4 + 9))/(-2)) \\ 294849 &:= (((-((9 - (4 \times 8))) \times 4!) - 9)^2) \\ 295245 &:= (5 \times (((4! - ((2 - 5))) \times 9)^2)) \\ 295464 &:= (4! \times (-((6 + 4)) + ((5! - 9)^2))) \\ 295486 &:= (((((6! + 8!) \times (-4))/(-5)) \times 9) - 2) \\ 295584 &:= ((-((4 - 8)))! \times (-5 + ((5! - 9)^2))) \\ 295678 &:= -((8! - (((7! \times (6! - 5!))/9) - 2))) \\ 295704 &:= (4! \times (((((0 \times 7) + 5)!) - 9)^2)) \\ 295846 &:= (6! - (((4! + (8^5)) \times (-9)) + 2)) \\ 295944 &:= (4! + (4! \times (9 + ((5! - 9)^2)))) \\ 296358 &:= (((8! - (5^3!)) \times 6) + 9) \times 2) \\ 296359 &:= ((9! - 5) - ((-3 - 6!) \times (-92))) \\ 296398 &:= -((((((8! + 9!)/3!) - 6!) - 9!) + 2)) \\ 296436 &:= (-6 \times (((3!! - 4) \times (-69)) - 2)) \\ 296448 &:= (8! - (-4 \times ((4! - 6!) \times (-92)))) \\ 296519 &:= (((9! - 1) - 5!) - (6! \times 92)) \\ 296635 &:= ((-5 + ((3 + 6)!) - (6! \times 92)) \\ 296638 &:= -((8! - (((-36) \times 6!) + 9!) - 2)) \\ 296639 &:= ((9! - (3!/6)) - (6! \times 92)) \\ 296642 &:= (((-((2 \times 46)) \times 6!) + 9!) + 2) \\ 296664 &:= (4! + (6! \times ((6 \times 69) - 2))) \\ 296676 &:= ((67 \times 6) \times (6! + ((9 \times 2))) \\ 296688 &:= (8 \times ((8! + 6) - ((6! \times (-9))/(-2)))) \\ 296984 &:= (-((4^8)) + (((9! - 6!) + 9!)/2)) \\ 297025 &:= (((5 - 20) + (7!/9))^2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 297342 &:= -2^{4 \times (-3+7)} + 9! - 2 \\ 297348 &:= (8! - 4) \times 3 - 7! + 9!/2 \\ 297353 &:= (((3! + (53)) \times 7!) - (9 - 2)) \\ 297358 &:= (((((8 + 5!) + 3) \times 7!) - 9!) - 2) \\ 297362 &:= (((2 \times 6)!/3!) - ((7! + 9!) - 2)) \\ 297371 &:= (((1 - 7!) \times (3! + 7)) + (9! - 2)) \\ 297378 &:= (((8 \times 7) + 3) \times 7!) + ((9 \times 2)) \\ 297384 &:= (-((4^8)) + (((3! \times 7) + 9!) - 2)) \\ 297387 &:= (7 \times 8!) + ((3! \times (7! + 9))/2) \\ 297395 &:= (5 \times ((9!/3!) + 7)) - ((9 - 2)!) \\ 297417 &:= (((7! + 1) \times (-4 - (7 \times 9)))) - 2) \\ 297537 &:= (7! + 3) \times (5! - ((7 \times 9) - 2)) \\ 297558 &:= (8 \times (-((5^5)) - 7!)) + (9! - 2) \\ 297674 &:= (((4! - 7!) \times (6 + 7)) + 9!) + 2 \\ 297865 &:= (5^6) + ((-8 \times 7!) \times (-9 - 2))) \\ 298373 &:= -((3!! - ((7^3) + ((8 + 9!)/2)))) \\ 298558 &:= (((((8! - 5!)/5) \times (-8)) + 9!) - 2) \\ 299047 &:= (((7^4) + (-((0! - 9))))!) \times (9 - 2)) \\ 299376 &:= (((6^7) - 3!!) + (9!/(9 \times 2))) \\ 299648 &:= -((8! - ((4^6) \times ((9 \times 9) + 2)))) \\ 300237 &:= (((7! + 3!)/2) \times (-0!) + (-((0! - 3!))))!) \\ 301675 &:= ((-5 - (7! \times (-6 \times 10)))) - 3!!) \\ 302275 &:= (-5 - ((7! - 2) \times (-20 \times 3))) \\ 302337 &:= (((7! \times (-3)) + 3) \times (-20)) - 3) \\ 302375 &:= (-5 \times (((7! \times 3!) \times (-2)) - 0!) + 3!)) \\ 302376 &:= (((6! \times 7!)/3!)/2) - ((0! + 3)!) \\ 302384 &:= (-((4^8)) + ((3^2)!) + ((0! + 3)!)!) \\ 302385 &:= (-5 \times (((8! \times (-3))/2) + 03)) \\ 302425 &:= (5^2) + (420 \times 3!!) \\ 302436 &:= ((6 \times 3!) + (420 \times 3!!)) \\ 302468 &:= (((8^6) + 4) + ((2^03)!) \\ 302527 &:= (((((7! + 2) \times 5!)/2) + 0!) + 3!) \\ 302547 &:= (7 \times (4! + (((5!^2) - 0!) \times 3))) \\ 302573 &:= (((((-3 - 7!) \times 5!)/(-2)) - 0!) - 3!) \\ 302579 &:= (((((-9 + 7!) \times 5!)/2) - 0!) + 3!!) \\ 302753 &:= (((3!! + (5! \times 7!))/2) - (0! + 3!)) \\ 302755 &:= (-5 + (5! \times ((7!/2) + 03))) \\ 302756 &:= (((6! + (5! \times 7!))/2) - (0! + 3)) \\ 302875 &:= (-5 + ((7! + 8) \times (20 \times 3))) \\ 303124 &:= ((421 \times 3!!) + (0! + 3)) \\ 303786 &:= (6 \times (((8 + 7)^{3+0!}) + 3!)) \\ 303839 &:= (9! - (((3!! \times 83) + 0!) - 3!)) \\ 304134 &:= (((4!^3) \times ((-1 + 4!) - 0!)) + 3!) \\ 304225 &:= (-((5^2)) \times (-2 - ((4! - 0!)^3))) \\ 304325 &:= ((5^2) \times (3! + ((4! - 0!)^3))) \\ 304359 &:= ((9! - 5!) - (-((3^4)) \times (-0! - 3!))) \\ 304479 &:= (9! - (((7 - 4)^4) \times (0! + 3!))) \\ 304559 &:= ((9! + (((5! \times 5!) \times (-4)) - 0!)) - 3!!) \\ 304584 &:= ((4! - 8!) + (((5! \times 4) - 0!) \times 3!)) \\ 304585 &:= ((5^8) + (5! \times ((4 - 0!) - 3!))) \\ 304704 &:= (((4! - ((0 \times 7))!) \times 4!)^{-0!+3}) \\ 304856 &:= ((((-6 + 5!) - 8) \times 4) \times (-0! + 3!)) \\ 305136 &:= ((6^{3!+1}) + (5 \times ((0! + 3!)))!) \\ 305274 &:= (((4! + (7!/2)) \times 5!) - (03)!) \\ 305395 &:= (-5 \times (-(((9!/3!) - 5!) - 0!)) - 3!)) \\ 305575 &:= (((5! - (7 \times 5)) \times 5) \times (-0! + 3!)) \\ 305647 &:= ((-((7^4)) \times ((-6 - 5!) - 0!)) + 3!!) \\ 305844 &:= ((4! + 4) \times (((8^5) + 0!)/3)) \\ 306294 &:= (((4! \times (9 \times 2)) - 6) \times (-0! + 3!)) \\ 306385 &:= ((5^8) - ((-3 + ((6 - 0!)))!) \times 3!)) \\ 306424 &:= ((424 \times (6! + 0!)) + 3!!) \\ 306597 &:= (((7! + 9!) \times (-5))/(-6)) - 03) \\ 306716 &:= (((61 \times 7!) - 6!) - 0!) - 3) \\ 306717 &:= ((71 \times (7! - 6!)) - 03) \\ 306916 &:= (((((6 + 1)!/9) - 6)^{-0!+3}) \\ 306935 &:= -((((5 + 3)! - 9!) + ((6 - 0!)^{3!})) \\ 306938 &:= -((((8! - 3) - 9!) + ((6 - 0!)^{3!})) \\ 307328 &:= ((8 + ((2 + 3)!) \times (7^{0!+3})) \\ 307376 &:= (((67 - 3!) \times (7! - 0!)) - 3) \\ 307385 &:= (((58 + 3) \times (7! - 0!)) + 3!) \\ 307439 &:= (9! - ((3!! + ((4 + 7)!)/(03)!))!) \\ 307584 &:= (((((4!/8)!^5) + 7!) \times ((0! + 3!))) \\ 307623 &:= (-((3 - 2^6)) \times (7! + 03)) \\ 307745 &:= ((54 + 7) \times ((7! - 0!) + 3!)) \\ 307867 &:= (-((7 - 68)) \times ((7! + 0!) + 3!)) \\ 308374 &:= (((47 \times 3^8) + 0!) + 3!) \\ 308416 &:= (-61) \times (-((4! - 8)) - ((0! + 3!)))!)) \\ 308736 &:= ((-((6^3)) + 7!) \times (8^{-0!+3})) \\ 308877 &:= (((((7 + 7)!/8!)/(8 - 0!)) - 3) \\ 308883 &:= (((3! + 8)!/(8! \times (8 - 0!))) + 3) \\ 308886 &:= (((((6 + 8)!/8!)/(8 - 0!)) + 3!) \\ 309144 &:= (4! + (((-((4! - 1)) \times ((9 - 0!)))!)/(-3))) \\ 309645 &:= (-5 \times ((-4 \times 6!) - (9^{-0!+3!}))) \end{aligned}$$

- 309985 := ((5⁸) - ((9!/(-9)) × (0! - 3)))
310176 := ((6⁷) - (-((10)!/((-1 + 3)!)))
310344 := (4! + ((430 + 1) × 3!))
310848 := (8 × (-((4! - 8!)) - ((0! + 1) × 3!)))
310896 := (-6 × ((9!/(-8 + 0!)) + ((1 + 3)!))
310944 := (4! × (-4 + ((9 × (0! + 1)) × 3!)))
311327 := (((72 × 3!) + 1) × (-1 + 3!))
311364 := (((4! - 6) × 31)⁻¹⁺³)
311542 := ((-2 + 4!) × ((5! - 1)⁻¹⁺³)
312267 := (7! × 62) - 213
312336 := (((-6!) - 3!) - (3!)) × (-(((2 + 1)!)³))
312356 := ((65 - 3) × (-2 + ((1 + 3)!))
312467 := (7! × (64 - 2)) - 13
312475 := (-5 + (((7 + 4!) × 2) × ((1 + 3)!))
312477 := (7! × ((7 + 4!) × 2)) - (1 × 3)
312487 := (((7! - (8! × 4)) × (-2)) + (1 + 3!))
312498 := (8! - (((9!/(-4)) - ((2 + 1)!)) × 3))
312504 := (4 × (0! + ((5^{21/3})))
312673 := (((3 + 7!) × 62) + 1) + 3!
313479 := (9 × (7! + (((4! + 3!) + 1)³))
313597 := (((7!/9)⁵⁻³) - (1 × 3))
313632 := ((2 × (3! + 6!)) × (3!^{1×3}))
313728 := ((8 × 2) × (((7^{3!}) - 1)/3!))
313749 := (9! - (((4⁷) - 3!) - 1) × 3)
313769 := (9! - (67 × (3!! + 13)))
313938 := -((8! + ((3! - (9^{3!-1})) × 3!))
313968 := -(((8! + 6) - ((9^{3!-1}) × 3!))
314297 := (((((7!/9)²) - 4!) + 1) + 3!))
314356 := (((6!/5) × 3) + 4) × (1 + 3!))
314429 := (((92 - 4!)⁴⁻¹) - 3)
314431 := (-1 + (((3 × 4!) - 4)^{1×3}))
314438 := ((8 × (34⁴⁻¹)) + 3!)
314496 := (-6 × (9! - ((4! × 4!) × (1 + 3!)))
314516 := (-61) × (-((5! - 4) - ((1 + 3)!))
314545 := ((-5 + 4!) × (-5 + ((4! - 1) × 3!))
314686 := ((((-6 - 8!) - 6!) × (4! - 1))/(-3))
314752 := (((2 + 5!) - 7!) × (-((4 × 1)³))
314832 := (((2 - (3⁸)) × 4!) × (1 - 3))
314888 := (8 × ((8! - ((8!/4!) - 1)) + 3!))
314904 := -((4! × (0! + ((9⁴) × (1 - 3))))
314934 := ((4 × ((3⁹) × 4)) + ((1 × 3)!))
314942 := (2 × (((4! × (9⁴)) + 1) + 3!))
314968 := (8 × (((6 × (9⁴)) - 1) + 3!))
315372 := ((2 - (-73) × ((5 + 1)!)) × 3!)
315525 := (525 × (-((5! - 1) + 3!))
315744 := (4! × ((-4 + (7!/(-5))) × (-13)))
315784 := ((4! × (8! + (-7 × (5! + 1))))/3)
315832 := ((2³) × (((8! - 5!) - 1) - 3!))
315838 := ((-8 × (3!! - (8! - 5!))) + ((1 - 3)))
316085 := ((-5 × (8! - 0!)) + ((6! - 1) × 3!))
316088 := ((8 × ((8! + 0!) - 6!)) - (((1 × 3)!))
316219 := (9! - (((((1 + 2)!)⁶) - 1) + 3!))
316288 := (8 × ((8! - (2⁶)) - (((1 × 3)!))
316488 := ((8 × ((8! - 4!) - 6!)) - ((-1 + 3)!))
316787 := (((7! + 8!) × 7) - 6!) - 13
316789 := (9! - ((8 × ((7! + 6!) + 1)) + 3))
316795 := ((-5 + ((9 × 7!) × (6 + 1))) - 3!))
316797 := (((7! × (9 × 7)) - 6!) - (1 × 3))
316799 := (9! - (((9 × 7!) + 6!) + (1³)))
316802 := (2 × (0! + ((8! - 6!) × (1 + 3)))
316804 := (4 × (0! - ((8! - 6!) × (1 - 3)))
316805 := ((5 × (0! - 8!)) + (6!⁻¹⁺³))
316807 := (((7 + 0!) × (8! - 6!)) + (1 + 3!))
316808 := (8 × ((0! + 8!) - ((6 × (1³)))!))
316809 := ((9 × ((0! + 8!) - ((6 + 1)!)) - 3!))
316824 := (4! × (((2 + 8!) - 6!) + 1)/3))
316832 := ((2³) × ((8! - 6!) + (1 + 3)))
316838 := ((8 × (((3 + 8!) - 6!) + 1)) + 3!)
316848 := 8 × (4 + 8! - 6! - 1 + 3)
316855 := (55 × ((8 × 6!) + (1³)))
316888 := (8 × (((8 + 8!) - 6!) + (1 × 3)))
316893 := (((3!! - 9!)/(-8)) × (6 + 1)) + 3)
316896 := (((6! - 9!)/(-8)) × (6 + 1)) + 3!
316937 := ((-7 + 3!!) + ((9! - (6^{1×3!})))
316944 := (((4!/4)!) + ((9! - (6^{1×3!})))
317079 := ((9 × 7) × (((0! - 7!) × (-1)) - 3!))
317268 := (8! - 6² + 7!) × (1 + 3!)
317328 := (((-((8²)) × (3 - 7!)) - ((1 + 3)!))
317334 := (((4! - 3) × (-3 + 7!)) + 1) × 3)
317336 := ((63 × (-3 + 7!)) + (-1 + 3!))
317373 := ((3 × 7) × ((3 × 7!) - 1) - 3!))
317379 := ((((-9 × 7!) + 3) × (-7)) - ((-1 + 3)!))

$$\begin{aligned} 317387 &:= (7 \times (((8! - 3!) + 7!) - 13)) \\ 317397 &:= (((7 \times 9) \times ((-3 + 7!) + 1)) + 3) \\ 317439 &:= (9! - (3 \times (4! - ((7! + 1) \times (-3)))))) \\ 317457 &:= ((7 \times (5 + 4)) \times (7! - (1^3))) \\ 317478 &:= (((8! - ((7 - 4)!) + 7!) \times (1 + 3!)) \\ 317479 &:= (((9 \times 7!) - 4) \times 7) - 13) \\ 317486 &:= (-6 - (((8! - 4) + 7!) \times (-1 - 3!))) \\ 317487 &:= (((((7! + 8!) - 4) \times 7) + 1) - 3!) \\ 317488 &:= 8 \times (8! - 4) - 7! \times 1^3 \\ 317489 &:= (((9! / (-8)) + 4) \times (-7)) - (1 \times 3)) \\ 317497 &:= (((((7! \times (-9)) + 4) \times (-7)) - 1) + 3!) \\ 317499 &:= (9! - (((9! / 4!) + 7) \times (1 \times 3))) \\ 317523 &:= (((3 \times (2 + 5)) \times 7!) + 1) \times 3) \\ 317529 &:= (9 \times (((2 + 5) \times 7!) + (1^3))) \\ 317537 &:= 7! - 3 + 5^7 \times (1 + 3) \\ 317564 &:= ((4 \times (6 + (5^7))) + ((1 + 3!)!)) \\ 317579 &:= ((((-9 \times 7!) - 5) \times (-7)) + ((1 + 3!)!)) \\ 317583 &:= ((-3 - 8!) - ((5 - (71^3)))) \\ 317586 &:= (((68 - 5) \times (7! + 1)) + 3) \\ 317588 &:= ((-8 - 8!) + (5 + (71^3))) \\ 317589 &:= ((9 \times ((8! + 5) - 7!)) + ((1 + 3!)!)) \\ 317595 &:= (5! + (9 \times (-5 + (7! \times (1 + 3!)))))) \\ 317649 &:= (((((9! / 4!) + 6) \times 7) + 1) \times 3) \\ 317664 &:= (((4! + 6!) \times (6 \times 71)) + 3!!) \\ 317688 &:= (((8 \times (8! + 6)) - 7!) + ((-1 + 3!)!)) \\ 317709 &:= ((9 \times 07) \times (7! + (1 \times 3))) \\ 317736 &:= ((63 \times 7!) + (((7 - 1)^3)) \\ 317749 &:= ((9 \times (4! - (7! \times (-7)))) + 13) \\ 317772 &:= (((2 + 7) \times 7) \times (7! + (1 + 3))) \\ 317799 &:= (9! - (9 \times ((7! - 7) - ((1 + 3!)!))) \\ 317958 &:= (((((8! / (-5)) - 9!) / (-7)) + 1) \times 3!) \\ 317961 &:= (((1 + 6) \times 9) \times ((7! + 1) + 3!)) \\ 318177 &:= ((-7 \times ((7! - 1) \times (-8 + 1))) + 3!!) \\ 318239 &:= ((9! + (((3^2)!) / (-8)) - 1) + 3!!) \\ 318464 &:= (-((4^6)) - ((4! \times 8!) / (-1 \times 3))) \\ 318488 &:= (((8 \times 8!) + 4!) - (8^{1+3})) \\ 318595 &:= (-5 + (9 \times ((5! + 8!) - ((1 + 3!)!))) \\ 318775 &:= (-((5^7)) + ((7! / 8)^{-1+3})) \\ 318856 &:= ((6! \times (-5)) + (8 \times (8! - 13))) \\ 318953 &:= ((3!! \times (-5)) + (((9! - 8!) - 1) - 3!)) \\ 318956 &:= (((6! \times (-5)) + 9!) - 8!) - (1 + 3) \\ 318965 &:= (((((-5 \times 6!) + 9!) - 8!) - 1) + 3!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 319441 &:= ((((-1 + 4!)^4) + ((9 - 1)!) - 3!!) \\ 319488 &:= (8 \times (8! - (4! \times ((9 + 1) + 3!)))) \\ 320252 &:= (((-2 + 5!)^2) \times 023) \\ 320256 &:= ((6^{5+2}) + ((02^3)!) \\ 320268 &:= (8! - (((6^{(2+0)!) + 2) \times (-3!))) \\ 320276 &:= (((6^7) + 20) + ((2^3)!) \\ 320373 &:= (-((3^7)) + (((3! + 0!)!) \times (2^3))) \\ 320376 &:= (((6^7) + ((3! - 0!)!) + ((2^3)!) \\ 320398 &:= (-((8! - 9!)) - (((3!! + 0!) \times 2) + 3!)) \\ 320688 &:= (8 \times (8! - ((6! / (0! + 2)) - 3!)) \\ 320832 &:= ((2^3) \times (8! - (((0! + 2)!)^3))) \\ 320976 &:= (((6^7) + ((9 - 0!)!) + (((2 \times 3)!)!)) \\ 321024 &:= ((-4!) + (((2 + 0!)!) + 1)!) \times (2^3!) \\ 321216 &:= (((6 + 1)!) - (21)) \times (2^3!) \\ 321288 &:= ((8 \times 8!) + (-212) \times 3!) \\ 321408 &:= (((8 + 0!)!) - (4! \times (12^3))) \\ 321409 &:= ((9! + 0!) - (4! \times (12^3))) \\ 321584 &:= (-4 \times (((8! - 5!) + 1) \times (-2)) + 3!) \\ 321586 &:= (-6 - (((8! - 5!) - 1) \times (-2^3))) \\ 321588 &:= ((8 \times (8! - 5!)) - ((1 \times 2) \times 3!)) \\ 321598 &:= (-(((8! - 9!) + ((5! + 1) \times 2))) - 3!!) \\ 321608 &:= (((8! + 0!) - ((6 - 1)!) \times (2^3)) \\ 321648 &:= (((8! - 4!) \times ((6 \times 1) + 2)) - 3!!) \\ 321728 &:= ((8^2) \times ((7! - 1) - (2 \times 3!)) \\ 321744 &:= ((-4 \times (4! + (((7 + 1)!) \times (-2)))) - 3!!) \\ 321768 &:= ((-8 - 6!) + ((7! - 1) \times (2^3))) \\ 321769 &:= (((9! - 6!) - 71) - ((2^3)!) \\ 321784 &:= ((-4 \times ((8! - 7) \times (-1 \times 2))) - 3!!) \\ 321792 &:= (((-((2 + 9) + 7!) - 1) \times (2^3!)) \\ 321798 &:= (-(((8! - 9!) + (7 \times ((1 + 2)!)!)) - 3!!) \\ 321808 &:= ((-8 \times ((0! - 8!) + (1 + 2))) - 3!!) \\ 321824 &:= ((-4 \times ((2 - 8!) \times (1 \times 2))) - 3!!) \\ 321829 &:= (((9! - 2) - 8!) - ((1 + 2)^3!)) \\ 321831 &:= ((-1 - 3!!) + ((8! - 1) \times (2^3))) \\ 321832 &:= (((2^3) \times (8! - 1)) - ((2 \times 3)!) \\ 321834 &:= (((4! / 3) \times 8!) - (((1 + 2)!)! - (3!)) \\ 321835 &:= ((-5 - 3!!) + (8 \times (((1 \times 2)^3)!) \\ 321838 &:= (((((8! \times (-3)) - 8!) + 1) \times (-2)) - 3!!) \\ 321839 &:= (-((9^3)) - ((8! + 1) \times (-2^3))) \\ 321841 &:= ((1 - ((4! \times 8!) / (-1 + 2))) - 3!!) \end{aligned}$$

- 321842** := $((2 \times ((4 \times 8!) + 1)) - ((2 \times 3)!)$
321844 := $((4 - ((4! \times 8!)/(-1 + 2))) - 3!)$
321845 := $((5 - ((4! \times 8!)/(-1 + 2))) - 3!)$
321846 := $-((6! - (((4! \times 8!)/(1 + 2)) + 3!))$
321847 := $((7 - ((4! \times 8!)/(-1 + 2))) - 3!)$
321848 := $(-8 \times (((4! - 8!) + 1) + (2^{3!}))$
321849 := $((9 - ((4! \times 8!)/(-1 + 2))) - 3!)$
321853 := $-((3! + (-5 + ((8! + 1) \times (-2^3))))$
321856 := $((-((6 + 5)) + ((8 - 1)!) \times (2^{3!}))$
321864 := $((4! - 6!) - 8!) + (((1 + 2) \times 3)!)$
321884 := $((((4 + 8!) \times 8) + 12) - 3!)$
321886 := $((((6 + 8!) \times 8) - (1 \times 2)) - 3!)$
321887 := $((7 + 8!) \times 8) - ((1 + 2)^{3!})$
321888 := $(8 \times (8! - (((8 + 1)^2) + 3))$
321889 := $((9! - 8!) + ((8 - 1)^2)) - 3!)$
321958 := $(((((8! - 5!) - 9!) \times (-1)) - 2) - 3!)$
321977 := $(-7 - (((7! - 9) \times (-1)) \times (2^{3!}))$
322048 := $(8 \times (((4 \times 02)!) - (2^{3!})))$
322102 := $(2 \times (-((0! - 12))^{2+3}))$
322168 := $((8! - ((6 + 1)^2)) \times (2^3))$
322173 := $(-3 + ((7! - ((1 + 2)!) \times (2^{3!})))$
322176 := $((6 - 7!) \times (-(((1 \times 2) + 2)^3))$
322235 := $((-5 + (3! \times (-2))) \times (-223))$
322288 := $(8 \times (8! - (2 + (2^{2+3}))))$
322304 := $((4 - ((0! + 3)!) \times (-((2 + 2)^3))$
322344 := $(-4 \times (((4! - ((3! + 2)!) \times 2) + (3!)))$
322368 := $((8! - (((6/3) + 2)!) \times (2^3))$
322384 := $((4! \times ((8! - ((3! - 2)!) + 2))/3)$
322398 := $-(((8! - 9!) + ((3 + ((2 + 2)!) \times 3!)))$
322428 := $((8 \times ((2 \times 4)!) - (22 \times 3!))$
322431 := $(-1 + (((3 + 4)!) - 2) \times (2^{3!}))$
322432 := $((2 - ((3 + 4)!) \times (-((2 + 2)^3))$
322435 := $(-((5^3)) - (((4 \times 2)!) \times (-2^3)))$
322438 := $((((8!/3) \times 4!) - 2) - ((2 + 3)!)$
322448 := $((((8! \times 4) + 4) \times 2) - ((2 + 3)!)$
322464 := $(-4 \times ((6 \times 4) + (-2 \times ((2^3)!))))$
322484 := $(-4 \times (((8 - ((4 \times 2)!) \times 2) + 3))$
322488 := $((8 - 8!) \times (-4 \times 2)) - (2^3)$
322489 := $((9 - 8!) \times (-4 \times 2)) - ((2 - 3))$
322493 := $(((-3 + 9!) - ((4 \times 2)!) - (2^{3!}))$
322494 := $((-4 \times ((9 - ((4 \times 2)!) \times 2)) + 3!)$
322497 := $(-((7 \times 9) - (((4 \times 2)!) \times (-2^3)))$
322498 := $(((((8! - 9) \times (-4)) - 2) \times (-2)) + 3!)$
322508 := $((8 + 0!)! + (-52 - ((2^3)!))$
322509 := $((9! + 0!) - 52) - ((2^3)!)$
322528 := $((8! + 2) - ((5 - 2)!) \times (2^3))$
322536 := $((6 + (((3 + 5)!) \times (-2))) \times (2 - 3!))$
322537 := $7! \times (3 + 5)^2 - 23$
322538 := $((8 \times (((3 + 5)!) - 2)) - (2 \times 3))$
322554 := $((((4 + 5)!) - ((5 - 2)!) - ((2^3)!)$
322555 := $(-5 + (((5 + 5) - 2) \times ((2^3)!)$
322557 := $((7! \times (((5 + 5) - 2)^2) - 3)$
322558 := $((8 + (5/5))!) - 2 - ((2^3)!)$
322559 := $((9! - (5/5)) - ((2 + (2 \times 3)!)$
322573 := $((3! + 7) + (((5 + 2)!) \times (2^{3!})))$
322576 := $(((((6 + 7) - 5)!) + 2) \times (2^3))$
322582 := $((2 + 8!) \times ((5 \times 2) - 2)) + 3!$
322584 := $((4! - 8!) + (((5 - 2) \times 2) + 3)!)$
322588 := $((8 \times (8! + 5)) - ((2 + 2) \times 3))$
322594 := $((4! + 9!) + (5 \times 2)) - ((2^3)!)$
322608 := $((8! - (0 - 6)) \times (2 + (2 \times 3)))$
322609 := $(9! + (((0! + 6)^2) - ((2^3)!))$
322616 := $((-((6 + 1)) - ((6 + 2)!) \times (-2^3))$
322624 := $((-((4 \times 2)) - ((6 + 2)!) \times (-2^3))$
322644 := $(4 \times (4! + (((6 + 2)!) \times 2) - 3))$
322648 := $(8! - 4) \times (6 + 2) + (2 + 3)!$
322672 := $((2 \times 7) + ((6 + 2)!) \times (2^3))$
322679 := $(-9 - (((-7 \times 6!) - 2) \times (2^{3!})))$
322698 := $-8! + 9! + (6 \times 2)^2 - 3!$
322751 := $(-1 - (((-5 - 7!) + 2) \times (2^{3!})))$
322752 := $((2 - 5) - 7!) \times (-((2 + 2)^3))$
322768 := $((8! + ((6 + 7) \times 2)) \times (2^3))$
322776 := $((6^7) + ((7!/2) + ((2^3)!))$
322784 := $((4 \times 8) \times (((7! + 2) \times 2) + 3))$
322808 := $((8! - 0!) \times 8) + (2^3)$
322816 := $((6 + 1)!) + (8/2) \times (2^{3!})$
322824 := $(4! \times ((2 \times (82^2)) + 3))$
322844 := $(-4 \times (((4! + 8!) \times (-2)) - (23)))$
322848 := $((8! + 4) \times 8) + (2^3)$
322857 := $(7! + 5) \times 8^2 - 23$
322864 := $(-4 \times (((6 + 8!) \times (-2)) - (2^{3!})))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 322875 &:= (((5 + 7!) \times (8^2)) - (2 + 3)) \\
 322884 &:= (((4! + 8!) \times 8) + (22 \times 3!)) \\
 322888 &:= (8 \times (8! + ((8^2) - 23))) \\
 322928 &:= (8! \times 2 + 92) \times (-2 + 3!) \\
 322937 &:= (-7 + ((3! + ((9 - 2))!) \times (2^{3!}))) \\
 322944 &:= (4 \times (((4! + (92))^2) \times 3!)) \\
 323008 &:= (((8 - 0)!) + (0! + 3!)) \times (2^{3!}) \\
 323072 &:= (((2 + 7!) + (03)!) \times (2^{3!})) \\
 323088 &:= (8 \times (((8! - 0!) + 3) + (2^{3!}))) \\
 323136 &:= ((-((6 + 3)) - ((1 + 3!)!)) \times (-2^{3!})) \\
 323159 &:= (((9! - 5!) - 1) + 3!!) - ((2^3)!) \\
 323197 &:= (-7 \times (-91) + (3!! \times (-2^{3!}))) \\
 323248 &:= (8! - 4) \times 2^3 + (2 \times 3!) \\
 323268 &:= (((8 \times ((6 + 2)!) + 3!!) - (2 \times 3!)) \\
 323273 &:= (3!! - (7 + (((2^3)!) \times (-2^3)))) \\
 323274 &:= ((-4 + ((7! \times (2^3)) - 2)) + 3!!) \\
 323275 &:= (-5 + ((7! \times (2^3)) + ((2 \times 3)!) \\
 323276 &:= (6! + ((7! \times (2^3)) - (-2 + 3!))) \\
 323278 &:= (((8! \times 7) - 2) + 3!!) + ((2^3)!) \\
 323298 &:= (-(((8! - 9!) - (2 \times (3^2)))) + 3!!) \\
 323328 &:= (8 \times (((2^3)!) + ((32 \times 3))) \\
 323388 &:= ((8 \times 8!) + ((3! \times 3!) \times 23)) \\
 323398 &:= (-((8! - 9!)) + (((3!!/3!) - 2) + 3!!)) \\
 323433 &:= ((3 \times 3) \times ((4! + (3^2))^3)) \\
 323484 &:= (((((4! + 8!) \times (-4)) - 3!) \times (-2)) + 3!!) \\
 323485 &:= (((5! + 8!) - 4) \times (3! + 2)) - 3) \\
 323488 &:= (8 \times (8! + (4 \times (32 - 3)))) \\
 323517 &:= (((((7 + 1)!) + 5!) \times (3! + 2)) - 3) \\
 323518 &:= (((8! - 1) + 5!) \times (3! + 2)) + 3! \\
 323523 &:= (((((3! + 2)!) + 5!) \times (3! + 2)) + 3) \\
 323526 &:= (((((6 + 2)!) + 5!) \times (3! + 2)) + 3!) \\
 323528 &:= (((8! - 2) + 5!) + 3) \times (2^3) \\
 323538 &:= (((8! + 3) + 5!) \times (3! + 2)) - 3! \\
 323544 &:= (((((4 + 4)!) + 5!) + 3) \times (2^3)) \\
 323545 &:= (5 \times (((4! + 5)^3) + ((2^3)!)) \\
 323568 &:= (((8! + 6) + 5!) \times ((3 + 2) + 3)) \\
 323584 &:= (4! - ((8! + ((5^3))) \times (-2^3))) \\
 323589 &:= (((9 + 8!) + 5!) \times (3! + 2)) - 3) \\
 323598 &:= (((8! + 9) + 5!) \times (3! + 2)) + 3! \\
 323617 &:= 7 \times ((1 - 6^3)^2 + 3!) \\
 323648 &:= (((8! + 46) \times (3! + 2)) + 3!!)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 323688 &:= (8 \times (8! + ((6!/(3 + 2)) - 3))) \\
 323712 &:= (((21 + 7!) - 3) \times (2^{3!})) \\
 323728 &:= ((8! + (2 \times 73)) \times (2^3)) \\
 323764 &:= (((((4! \times (-6)) - 7) + 3!!)^2) + 3) \\
 323776 &:= (((6 + 7) + 7!) + 3!) \times (2^{3!}) \\
 323888 &:= ((8 \times (8! + (8 \times 32))) - 3!!) \\
 323891 &:= (-1 + (9 \times (8! - ((3!! + 2) \times 3!)))) \\
 323925 &:= ((5^2) \times (((-9 \times 3!!) \times (-2)) - 3)) \\
 323979 &:= (9! + ((-7 + ((-9 \times 3!!) \times 2)) \times 3)) \\
 323987 &:= (((-7 - 8!) + 9!) - ((3!! \times (-2)) + (3!))) \\
 323988 &:= ((8 \times 8!) + (((9 - 3!!) \times (-2)) + (3!))) \\
 323994 &:= (((((4 \times 9!)/(-9)) - 3!!) \times (-2)) - (3!)) \\
 323995 &:= ((-5 + 9!) + ((-9 \times 3!) \times ((2 \times 3)!) \\
 324009 &:= (9 \times (0! + ((0! + 4!) \times 2) \times 3!)) \\
 324036 &:= (-6 \times ((3!! \times (0! + 4!)) + 2) \times (-3)) \\
 324088 &:= (8 \times ((8! - 0!) + (4! \times (2^3)))) \\
 324096 &:= (((6 + ((9 \times 0)!)!) + 4!) \times (2^{3!})) \\
 324176 &:= (6! + ((7! + 14) \times (2^{3!}))) \\
 324288 &:= ((8 \times 8!) + ((24/2)^3)) \\
 324352 &:= ((2 + 5) \times ((3!! + 4) \times (2^{3!}))) \\
 324385 &:= ((5^8) - (3!! \times (4 \times 23))) \\
 324405 &:= 5 \times (-0! + 4^4)^2 - 3!! \\
 324481 &:= (((1 - 8) + (4! \times 4!))^2) + 3!! \\
 324488 &:= ((8 \times (8! + (4^4))) - ((2 + 3)!) \\
 324528 &:= (8 \times (((2 \times 5!) + ((4 \times 2)!) + 3!)) \\
 324576 &:= ((6^7) + (((5! + 4)/2) \times 3!)) \\
 324608 &:= (((-8 - ((0! + 6)!) - 4!) \times (-2^{3!})) \\
 324723 &:= (((3!!/2) - (7 + 4!))^2) \times 3) \\
 324816 &:= (6! + (((-((1 - 8))!) + 4!) \times (2^{3!}))) \\
 324864 &:= ((4 - (6!/(-8))) \times ((4!^2) \times 3!)) \\
 324906 &:= (((6 \times (0! + (94)))^2) + 3!) \\
 325155 &:= (-5 \times (-((51 \times 5)^2)) - 3!) \\
 325248 &:= (8 \times (((4 \times 2)!) / 5!) + ((2^3)!)) \\
 325288 &:= (8 \times (8! - (2 - ((5 + 2)^3)))) \\
 325344 &:= (-4 \times ((4! + (((3 + 5)!) \times (-2))) - 3!)) \\
 325389 &:= ((9! - 8!) + ((-3 - 5!) \times (-23))) \\
 325424 &:= (-((4^2)) - (-452 \times 3!)) \\
 325429 &:= (-((9 + 2)) - (-452 \times 3!)) \\
 325432 &:= (-2 + ((3!! \times 452) - (3!))) \\
 325436 &:= (((6 + 3)!) - 4) + (-52 \times 3!))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 325438 &:= (-8 + ((3!! \times 452) + (3!))) \\ 325439 &:= ((9! + ((3 - 4))) + (-(52) \times 3!!)) \\ 325441 &:= ((1^4) - (-(452) \times 3!!)) \\ 325442 &:= (-((2 - 4)) - (-(452) \times 3!!)) \\ 325445 &:= ((5!/4!) - (-(452) \times 3!!)) \\ 325452 &:= ((2 - (5! \times (-(452)))) \times 3!) \\ 325459 &:= (((9! - 5) + 4!) + (-(52) \times 3!!)) \\ 325464 &:= ((4 \times 6) - (-(452) \times 3!!)) \\ 325475 &:= ((5 \times 7) - (-(452) \times 3!!)) \\ 325488 &:= (8 \times (8! + (((4 + 5!) - 2) \times 3))) \\ 325587 &:= ((7! - (((8! + 5!)/5!)^2)) \times (-3)) \\ 325588 &:= ((8 \times 8!) + (((55^2) + 3))) \\ 325698 &:= -8! + 9! + 6 \times 523 \\ 326044 &:= (((((4! \times 4!) + 0!) - 6)^2) + 3) \\ 326159 &:= (9! - ((51 \times 6!) - ((2 - 3))) \\ 326337 &:= 7 \times (3!^{3!} - 6^2) - 3 \\ 326339 &:= ((9!/3) + (-((3 - 62)^3)) \\ 326417 &:= (-7 \times ((1 + 4!) - ((6^2)^3)) \\ 326448 &:= ((8 \times ((4! \times 4!) + ((6 + 2)!)) - 3!!) \\ 326464 &:= (((-(4 - (6^4))) - 6!)^2) - 3!!) \\ 326557 &:= (-7 \times (5 - (((5 - 6) - 2)!^{3!})) \\ 326587 &:= ((7 \times (((8 - 5)!^6)) - (2 + 3)) \\ 326589 &:= (((9!/(-8 \times 5)) \times (-(6^2))) - 3) \\ 326591 &:= (-1 - ((9!/5!) \times (-(6^2) \times 3))) \\ 326592 &:= (((-2 \times 9!) + ((5 + 6)!)/((2 + 3)!)) \\ 326603 &:= (((3! + 0!) \times ((6^6) + 2)) - 3) \\ 326606 &:= (((6 + 0!)! \times ((6^6) + 2))/3!!) \\ 326607 &:= ((7 \times (0! + (6^6))) + (2^3)) \\ 326613 &:= ((3! + 1) \times ((6^{(6/2)!}) + 3)) \\ 326616 &:= (((6 + 1) \times (6^6)) + ((-2 + 3)!)) \\ 326627 &:= (-7 \times (-2 - ((6^{(6/2)!}) + 3))) \\ 326637 &:= ((7 \times ((3!^6) + ((6/2)!)) + 3) \\ 326673 &:= (-3 + (-7 \times (-(6^6)) - (2 \times 3!))) \\ 326688 &:= ((8! + (86 \times 6)) \times (2^3)) \\ 326736 &:= (((6^3!) \times 7) + (6!/(2 + 3))) \\ 326744 &:= ((4!^4) + ((-7 \times 6!) + (2^3))) \\ 326784 &:= ((4! \times 8) + (7 \times ((6^2)^3)) \\ 326848 &:= (8 \times ((4! + 8!) + ((6 + 2)^3)) \\ 326868 &:= (((((8!/6) \times 8) + 6!) - 2) \times 3!) \\ 326875 &:= (((-5 + 7!) - (-8 \times ((6 + 2)!)) - 3!!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 326878 &:= ((8! + ((7 \times (8! + 6!)) - 2)) - 3!!) \\ 326891 &:= (((-1 + 9!) - 8!) + ((6! + 2) \times 3!)) \\ 326949 &:= (9! - (((4! + 9)^{6/2}) - 3!)) \\ 326976 &:= ((6 - (-7 \times (9 + 6!))) \times (2^{3!})) \\ 326977 &:= (((7! \times (-7)) + 9!) - 623) \\ 327312 &:= (((((2 + 1)!^{3!}) \times 7) + ((2 \times 3)!)) \\ 327314 &:= ((((((4 - 1)!^{3!}) \times 7) + 2) + 3!!) \\ 327333 &:= (((3!^{3!}) + 3) \times 7) + ((2 \times 3)! \\ 327334 &:= ((4! + (((3!^{3!}) \times 7) - 2)) + 3!!) \\ 327336 &:= ((6! - ((3!^{3!}) \times (-7))) + ((-2 + 3)!)) \\ 327368 &:= (((-8 - (6^3!)) \times (-7)) + ((2 \times 3)!)) \\ 327384 &:= (((4! - (8!/3!)) \times (-7^2)) - 3!!) \\ 327439 &:= (9! - ((3 + 4) \times (7! + (23)))) \\ 327444 &:= ((4!^4) - (((4 - 7)! \times (2 + 3!))) \\ 327447 &:= ((-7 + (((4!^4) - 7!) - 2)) + 3!!) \\ 327448 &:= (-8 + (((4!^4) - 7!) + ((2 \times 3)!)) \\ 327449 &:= ((-9 + (((4!^4) - 7!) + 2)) + 3!!) \\ 327454 &:= (((((4!^5)/4!) - 7!) - 2) + 3!!) \\ 327564 &:= -(((4! - (65 \times 7!)) + (2 \times 3!)) \\ 327568 &:= ((-8 + (65 \times 7!)) - ((-2 + 3)!)) \\ 327575 &:= (5 \times ((7! - 5) + (((7 + 2)!/3!)) \\ 327576 &:= (((6 + 7) \times 5) \times 7!) - ((-2 + 3)!)) \\ 327579 &:= (9! - (-7 \times ((5 - 7!) - (2^3))) \\ 327587 &:= ((7! - (8 + 5)) + (7! \times (2^3))) \\ 327588 &:= ((8 \times 8!) - (((5! \times (-7)) + 2) \times 3!)) \\ 327589 &:= (((9! - 8!) - 5) + 7!) - (2 \times 3) \\ 327592 &:= (((((2 + 9)!/5!) - 7!) - (2^3)) \\ 327594 &:= (((4 + 9) \times 5) \times 7!) - (2 \times 3) \\ 327595 &:= ((-5 + 9!) - ((5! \times (7^2)) \times 3!)) \\ 327597 &:= (((7! - ((-9 - 5!) \times 7!))/2) - 3) \\ 327671 &:= (((1 + 7!) \times (67 - 2)) + 3!) \\ 327674 &:= (((4^7) \times (6 + (7 \times 2))) - 3!) \\ 327719 &:= ((9! - 1) - ((7! \times 7) - ((2 + 3)!)) \\ 327727 &:= (((7! + 2) \times (-7 - 72)) - 3) \\ 327744 &:= (((4!^4) - 7!) - (7!/(-2 + 3))) \\ 327765 &:= (((5^6) \times 7) - ((7 - 2)! \times 3) \\ 327774 &:= (((4! - 7!) \times 7) + ((7 + 2)! + 3!) \\ 327879 &:= (((-9 - 7!) - 8!) + (72^3)) \\ 327888 &:= (((8!/(-8)) - 8!) + (72^3)) \\ 327889 &:= (((9! - 8)/(-8)) + (72^3)) \end{aligned}$$

- 327897** := -(((7! - 9) + 8!) - (7²)))
327936 := (((6! + (3 + 9)) × 7) × (2³!))
327969 := (9 × (((6! + 9) × (7²)) + 3!))
328125 := ((5⁽²⁺¹⁾!) × (((8/2)!) - 3))
328128 := (8 × (((((2 + 1)!)! + 8!) - ((-2 + 3!)!))!))
328179 := (((9 + 7!) × (1 + (8²))) - 3!)
328256 := ((6 × ((5!²) + 8!)) - (2³!))
328284 := (-4 + (8 × (((-2 + 8!) - 2) + 3!)))
328288 := (8 × (((-((8/2)) + 8!) + ((2 × 3)!)!))
328304 := (-4 × (((((0! + 3!) + 8!) × (-2)) + (3!)))
328306 := (-6 + ((((-0!) + 3!) + 8!) × (2³)))
328307 := (((7 + 0!) × (3!! + ((8! - 2)))) + 3)
328308 := (((((8! - 0!) + 3!) × 8) - (-2 + 3!))
328309 := ((9! + 0!) - (((3!! × (-8)) - 2) × (-3!)))
328311 := (-1 - ((((-1 + 3!) + 8!) × (-2³)))
328312 := (((-((2 - 1)) + 3!) + 8!) × (2³))
328313 := (-((3! + 1)) - ((3!! + 8!) × (-2³)))
328314 := (-(((4 - 1)!) - ((3!! + 8!) × (-2³)))
328315 := (-5 + ((((-1 × 3!) - 8!) × (-2³)))
328318 := (((((8! - 1) + 3!) × 8) + (2 × 3))
328319 := ((9! - 1) - ((3! × 8) × ((2 × 3)!)!))
328332 := (((((2 + 3)!) × 3!) + ((8! + 2) × 3!))
328335 := ((5! × 3!) - (-3 - ((8! + 2) × 3!))
328336 := ((6! - ((3! / (-3)) - 8!)) × (2³))
328337 := (-7 - ((3!! + (3 + 8!)) × (-2³)))
328338 := (((((8! + 3) + 3!) × 8) - (2 × 3))
328342 := ((-2 + 4!) - ((3!! + 8!) × (-2³)))
328344 := ((4 + 4) × ((3 + 8!) + ((2 × 3)!)!))
328346 := (-6 - (((4 + 3!) + 8!) × (-2³)))
328348 := (((((8! + 4) + 3!) × 8) - (-2 + 3!))
328352 := ((2⁵) - ((3!! + 8!) × (-2³)))
328354 := ((-4 × (((5 + 3!) + 8!) × (-2))) - (3!))
328355 := (-5 - (((5 + 3!) + 8!) × (-2³)))
328356 := ((6! × 5!) - ((3! + 8!) × (-2 × 3)))
328364 := (-4 - (((6! + 3!) + 8!) × (-2³)))
328368 := (((8! + 6!) + 3!) × (-8 × (2 - 3)))
328373 := (-3 - (((7 + 3!) + 8!) × (-2³)))
328376 := ((6! - (((-7!) / 3!) - 8!)) × (2³))
328382 := (-2 + (((8 + 3!) + 8!) × (2³)))
328384 := ((4! × (((8 + 3!) + 8!) × 2)) / 3!)
328388 := (((((8 + 8!) + 3!) × 8) + (-2 + 3!))
328391 := (-1 + (((9³) + 8!) × (2³)))
328392 := (((2 × 9)³) - (-8 × ((2³)!))
328398 := (((8! + ((9³))) × 8) + (2 × 3))
328405 := ((5 × (0! + (4⁸))) + ((2 × 3)!)
328415 := ((5 × (1 + ((4⁸) + 2))) + 3!))
328448 := (8 × (((4 × 4) + 8!) + ((2 × 3)!)!))
328464 := ((-4 × (-((6⁴)) - (8! × 2))) + 3!))
328488 := (8 × (((8! + 4!) + ((8 - 2)!) - 3))
328504 := ((-4 - 0!) + ((5 + (8²))³))
328505 := ((-5 + 0!) + ((5 + (8²))³))
328508 := -((((8 × 0)!) - ((5 + (8²))³)))
328536 := (((((6 × 3) × (5 + 8))²) × 3!)
328688 := (8 × ((8! + ((6 × 8) - 2)) + 3!))
328768 := (((8! + 6!) + ((7 × 8))) × (2³))
328832 := ((2³) × ((8! + (8²)) + 3!))
328838 := ((8 × (3!! + (8! + (8²)))) + (3!))
328846 := (((((6! - 4!) + 8!) × 8) - 2) + 3!))
328848 := ((-8 × ((4! - 8!) - ((8 - 2)!)!)) + 3!))
328896 := (((6! + (9 × 8)) + 8!) × (2³))
328968 := (((((8! + 6!) - 9) × 8) + ((2 × 3)!)
329038 := ((((-8!) - 3!) × (0! - 9)) - 2) + 3!))
329039 := ((9 × 3!) - ((0! - 9!) + ((2³)!))
329345 := (-5 × (((4 - 3!) × 92) + 3))
329392 := -(((2⁹⁺³) - (9! - ((2 × 3)!)!))
329616 := (((((6 - 1) + 6)!) - 9!) / ((2 + 3)!)
329688 := ((8 × ((8! + 6!) + ((9²)))) + 3!))
329841 := ((-((1 + 4)) × 8!) + (((9²))³))
330456 := (-(((6! - 5!) - (4!⁰¹⁺³))) - 3!))
330588 := (8! + (((8! / 5) - 0!) × 3!) × 3!))
330985 := ((5⁸) - (((-9!) + ((0! + 3!)!) / (-3!)))
331044 := (((4!⁴) + 0!) - 13) - 3!))
331048 := ((-8 + (4!⁰¹⁺³)) - 3!))
331053 := (-3 + (((5 - 0!)!¹⁺³) - 3!))
331054 := (((4!⁵⁻⁰) + 1) - 3!) - 3)
331056 := (((-6 × (-5 + 0!)!¹⁺³) - 3!))
331344 := (4! × (((4!³) - ((1 + 3)!) + 3!))
331544 := ((4!⁴) - (((5 - 1)!) - 3!) / (-3))
331584 := (4! × (-8 + (((5 - (1³)))!³)))
331625 := ((5 + 2) × ((6! - 1) + (3!³)))
331632 := ((((-2 + 3!)!) × (-6 + (((1 + 3)!)³)))

$$\begin{aligned} 331644 &:= (((4!^4) - ((6-1)!) - 3!) - 3!) \\ 331667 &:= (-7 \times (((-6-6!) + 1) - (3!^{3!})) \\ 331734 &:= ((4!^{-3+7}) - ((1+3!) \times 3!)) \\ 331744 &:= ((4!^4) + ((7 - (13 \times 3))) \\ 331824 &:= (4! \times (2 + (((8 \times 1) \times 3^3))) \\ 331944 &:= ((4!^4) + ((-9!)/(((1 \times 3)!)!)/(-3)) \\ 332178 &:= (((8-7!) - 1) \times (-2 \times 33)) \\ 332277 &:= ((7 + ((7! - 2) \times (-2))) \times (-33)) \\ 332298 &:= -((((8! - ((9+2)!) / ((2+3)!) + 3!)) \\ 332328 &:= (8! + (((23 \times 2)^3) \times 3)) \\ 332359 &:= ((9! - ((5^3!) \times 2) + (3^3!)) \\ 332432 &:= (-(((2^3!) - (4!^{-2+3!})) + 3!)) \\ 332448 &:= ((-8 \times 4!) + (((4!/2)!) / (3!! + 3!))) \\ 332473 &:= ((((-((3-7)))!^4) - 23) + 3!)) \\ 332475 &:= ((-5 - (7! \times (-4-2))) \times 33) \\ 332484 &:= (((4!^{8-4}) - (2 \times 3!)) + 3!)) \\ 332488 &:= ((-8 + (((8-4)!^{-2+3!})) + 3!)) \\ 332493 &:= (3!! - (9 - ((4!^{-2+3!}) + 3!)) \\ 332495 &:= (((((-((5-9)))!^4) + 2) + 3!!) - 3) \\ 332496 &:= (6! + (9 \times (((4! \times 2)^3) / 3)) \\ 332504 &:= (((4!^{-0!+5}) + (2^3)) + 3!)) \\ 332544 &:= ((4!^4) + ((5! + (2^3)) \times 3!)) \\ 332571 &:= (((1-7!) \times ((5!/(-2)) - 3!)) - 3) \\ 332574 &:= (((((4+7)!) / 5!) - ((2 \times 33))) \\ 332578 &:= (-8! + (7+5)! / 2) / 3!! - 3! \\ 332586 &:= (6 \times (8! - (((5+2)!) - 3) \times (-3))) \\ 332589 &:= (9! + (((-8 - ((5+2)!) \times 3!) - 3)) \\ 332592 &:= (((2+9)!) / 5!) - ((2^3) \times 3!) \\ 332597 &:= ((-7+9!) - (((5+2)!) + 3!) \times 3!)) \\ 332624 &:= (-((4^2)) - (-(((6 \times 2)!) / (3!! + 3!))) \\ 332627 &:= (-7! + (2 \times 6!) / 2) / 3!! - 3! \\ 332629 &:= (-((9+2)) - (-(((6 \times 2)!) / (3!! + 3!))) \\ 332632 &:= (-2 - (((((3!+6)!) / (-2)) / 3!!) + (3!))) \\ 332634 &:= (((((4 \times 3)!) / 6!) / 2) - (3+3)) \\ 332635 &:= (-5 + (((3!+6)!) / (2 \times ((3+3)!))) \\ 332636 &:= (((-6!) - ((3!+6)!) / (-2)) / 3!! - 3) \\ 332637 &:= (((7! \times 3!) \times ((6+2)+3)) - 3) \\ 332638 &:= -8 + (3!+6)! / (2 \times 3!!) + 3! \\ 332639 &:= (((((9+3)!) / 6!) / 2) - (3/3)) \\ 332652 &:= ((2 + (((5+6)!) / ((2 \times 3)!) \times 3!)) \\ 332655 &:= ((-5 - (((5+6)!) \times 2) / 3!)) \times (-3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 332664 &:= (4! - (((6+6)!) / (-2)) / ((3+3)!) \\ 332667 &:= (((7! \times 66) + ((-2+3)!) + 3) \\ 332668 &:= (((8! + ((6+6)!) / 2) / ((3+3)!) \\ 332673 &:= ((3 + (7! \times 6)) \times ((2^3) + 3)) \\ 332675 &:= ((5 \times 7) - (-(((6 \times 2)!) / (3!! + 3!))) \\ 332676 &:= (((6-7!) \times 6) + (((2 \times 3) + 3)!) \\ 332679 &:= (9! + (((7! - 6) \times (-2 \times 3)) + 3)) \\ 332688 &:= ((8 \times ((8!/6!) + 2)) \times (3!! - 3)) \\ 332699 &:= (9! + (((9! - 6!) / (-2) - 3!) / 3!)) \\ 332703 &:= (-3 - ((0! + 7!) \times (-2 \times 33))) \\ 332706 &:= (((6 \times 0)!) + 7!) \times (2 \times 33) \\ 332707 &:= -((7! - ((0! + 7!) \times ((2^3!) + 3))) \\ 332733 &:= ((33 \times ((7! \times 2) + 3)) - 3!) \\ 332739 &:= ((9 + (3! \times 7!)) \times ((2^3) + 3)) \\ 332742 &:= (2 \times (-4 + (((7^2) + 3!)^3)) \\ 332748 &:= ((8! - (((-4-7!) - 2) \times 3)) \times 3!)) \\ 332755 &:= ((5! - 5) - (7! \times (-2 \times 33))) \\ 332762 &:= (2 \times (((6 + (7^2))^3) + 3!)) \\ 332766 &:= (((66 \times 7!) + ((2+3)!) + 3!) \\ 332772 &:= ((2+7!) \times ((72-3) - 3)) \\ 332784 &:= (((4! + 8!) - ((7!/(-2)) \times 3!)) \times 3!)) \\ 332805 &:= ((5 + ((-((0! - 8)!) \times 2)) \times 33) \\ 332928 &:= -((8! - (((-((2 \times 9)) \times (2-3!))^3))) \\ 333095 &:= (((-5 - ((9+0!)^{3!}) + 3!) / (-3)) \\ 333276 &:= -((((6! - (((7-2)!) + 3!)^3) / 3!)) \\ 333334 &:= (((((4+3!)^{3!}) + (3!/3)) / 3) \\ 333348 &:= ((-8 + (((4! - 3)^3) \times 3!)) \times 3!)) \\ 333355 &:= (-5 - (((((5+3)!) / 3!!) \times (-3!)) - 3!)) \\ 333356 &:= (((6+5!)^3 - (3!!/3)) / 3!) \\ 333357 &:= -((((7! - 5!) \times 3!) + 3) - ((3 \times 3)!) \\ 333359 &:= (9! - (((-((5!+3)) \times 3!!) - 3) / (-3)) \\ 333372 &:= (((2-7!) \times 3!) + 3!!) + (((3 \times 3)!) \\ 333378 &:= (((8! - ((7! \times (-3)) - 3)) \times 3!) + 3!)) \\ 333384 &:= (4! + (((((8+3)!) \times 3!) / 3!!) + 3!)) \\ 333388 &:= (-8 + (((((8-3)!) + 3!)^3) / 3!)) \\ 333395 &:= (((5! + (9-3))^3 - 3!) / 3!) \\ 333396 &:= (((-((6 - (9 \times 3))) \times 3!)^3) / 3!) \\ 333455 &:= (5! - ((5 + ((4+3!)^{3!})) / (-3)) \\ 333479 &:= (9! - ((7 \times (4^3!)) + (3^3!)) \\ 333497 &:= ((-7+9!) + ((4! \times 3!!) - (3!^{3!})) \\ 333504 &:= ((4!^{-0!+5}) + ((3! + 3!)^3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 333515 &:= ((5! - 1) + (((5! + 3!)^3)/3!)) \\ 333516 &:= ((6! + (((1 + (5^3))^3)))/3!) \\ 333648 &:= (-((8! - ((4 \times 6) \times 3)^3)) + 3!!) \\ 333756 &:= (((6 + 5) \times ((7! + 3!) \times 3!)) + 3!!) \\ 333864 &:= (((4! - 6!) - ((8 \times 3!)^3)) \times (-3)) \\ 333888 &:= -((8! - (8 \times (((8 - 3)!) + (3!^3)))))) \\ 333936 &:= ((6! + (((3! \times 9) - 3!)^3)) \times 3) \\ 333954 &:= ((4!^{-5+9}) + ((-3!) - 3!!) \times (-3)) \\ 333984 &:= ((-(4^8)) + ((9! + 3!)/3)) \times 3! \\ 334035 &:= ((5! - 3) \times (-0!) + (-4 \times (3! - 3!!))) \\ 334138 &:= (((8 \times 3!) + 1) \times ((4^3) - 3!)) \\ 334152 &:= ((((-2 + 5!) - 1) \times 4) \times (3!! - (3!))) \\ 334224 &:= ((-422) \times 4!) \times (-33) \\ 334254 &:= ((4! + 5) \times (((2^4) \times 3!) + (3!))) \\ 334288 &:= (8 \times (8! + (2 \times (4 + (3!^3)))))) \\ 334319 &:= (9! - (((13^4) \times 3)/3)) \\ 334364 &:= (-4 + (((6^3!) \times 43)/3!)) \\ 334368 &:= (((-86) \times 3!) \times 4!) \times (-3^3)) \\ 334534 &:= (((4 + (3!^5)) \times 43) - 3!) \\ 334544 &:= ((-4 \times (4 - 5!)) \times ((4 - 3) + 3!!)) \\ 334554 &:= ((-4 \times (-5!) + (-((5! - 4) \times 3!))) - (3!)) \\ 334584 &:= ((4! + (-8 \times (5! + (4!^3)))) \times (-3)) \\ 334611 &:= ((1 + 16) \times ((4! + 3!)^3)) \\ 334644 &:= ((4!^4) + (((6! \times 4) - 3!) - 3!)) \\ 334648 &:= (-8 - (-4 \times (6! + ((4!^3) \times 3!))) \\ 334656 &:= (((-((6^5)) + 6!) \times 4) + ((3 \times 3)!) \\ 334752 &:= ((-(2^5)) - 7!) \times ((4! \times (-3)) + 3!)) \\ 334776 &:= (((6^7) + ((7^4) \times 3!))/3!) \\ 334794 &:= (((((4! - 9) \times (7 + 4!)) \times 3!!) - (3!)) \\ 334797 &:= (((((7 \times 9) \times 7) + 4!) \times 3!) - 3) \\ 334848 &:= ((8! + (4! \times (8! - (4! \times 3!))))/3) \\ 334854 &:= ((4! \times ((5! + 8) + (4!^3))) + 3!) \\ 334944 &:= -(((4! \times (4! - 9!))/(4! + (3!/3))) \\ 335185 &:= ((5^8) + ((-1 \times ((5 + 3)!)!)/3!)) \\ 335238 &:= ((((-8!) - (3!^2))/5) \times (-3)) + (3!) \\ 335373 &:= ((3!^7) + (((3! + 5)!)!)/3!) - 3) \\ 335375 &:= ((5^7) + ((35^3) \times 3!)) \\ 335376 &:= (((6^7) \times 3!) + ((5 + 3)!)!)/3! \\ 335472 &:= (2 \times (((7! \times 4!) + 5!) + (3!^3))) \\ 335478 &:= (8 \times (7! - 4) + 5^3!) \times 3! \\ 335544 &:= (4! + (((-4 \times (5 - 5!)) + 3!) \times 3!)) \\ 335559 &:= (((9^5) \times 5) + ((5 + 3)!) - 3!) \\ 335575 &:= ((5! + (7 \times 5)) \times (5 - (3!! \times (-3)))) \\ 335598 &:= (8! + (((9^5) \times 5) + 33)) \\ 335616 &:= (-6!) + (((16)!/5!)/3!)/3! \\ 335634 &:= (((4!/3)!) + (-6 + (5^3!)) \times 3! \\ 335658 &:= ((8! + (((5^6) - 5) + 3)) \times 3! \\ 335659 &:= ((9! - 5) + ((-6 - 5!) \times (3!^3))) \\ 335667 &:= ((-(7^6)) + (6! \times (5 + 3))) \times (-3) \\ 335682 &:= (((2 + 8!) \times 6) + ((5^3!) \times 3!)) \\ 335706 &:= (((6 + ((0! + 7)!)! + (5^3!)) \times 3! \\ 335718 &:= (((8 + ((1 + 7)!)! + (5^3!)) \times 3! \\ 335814 &:= (((4! + ((1 \times 8)!)! + (5^3!)) \times 3! \\ 335872 &:= (((2 + 7)!) - 8) - ((5 \times 3!)^3) \\ 335874 &:= (((((4^7) + 8!) - 5) - 3!) \times 3! \\ 335879 &:= ((9! + ((7 - 8))) - ((5 \times 3!)^3) \\ 335895 &:= (-5 \times (((9 - 8!) \times 5)/3) + 3!) \\ 335898 &:= ((8! - (9 \times (-((8^5)) + 3!))) + 3!!) \\ 335904 &:= ((4! + (09)!) - ((5 \times 3!)^3)) \\ 335925 &:= (-((5^2)) \times ((9 - ((5 + 3)!)!)/3)) \\ 335957 &:= (((((7^5) - 9) \times 5!)/3!) - 3) \\ 335985 &:= (-5 \times (((8!/9) \times (-5 \times 3)) + 3)) \\ 335987 &:= (-7 + (((8! + 9!) \times 5)/3!) - 3!) \\ 335995 &:= (-5 \times (((9!/9) \times (-5)) + 3)/3) \\ 335999 &:= (((((9!/(-9)) - 9!) \times (-5)) - 3!)/3!) \\ 336382 &:= (-2 + ((8^3) \times (-63) + 3!)) \\ 336384 &:= ((-4 \times 8!) + (((3! + 6)^3!)/3!)) \\ 336528 &:= 82 \times (5! - 6) \times 3! \times 3! \\ 336585 &:= (5 \times (8! + (((5 \times 6)^3) - 3))) \\ 336595 &:= ((-5 + 9!) - (5! \times ((6^3) + 3))) \\ 336636 &:= (-((6 \times ((3^6) \times 6))) + ((3 \times 3)!) \\ 336639 &:= (9! + ((-((3^6) \times 6)) \times 3!) + 3) \\ 336671 &:= (-1 + (7 \times ((6! + 6!) + (3!^3))) \\ 336708 &:= (((8 + 0)!)! - ((7 + 6!) \times 3!) \times 3!) \\ 336709 &:= ((9! + 0!) - ((7 + 6!) \times 3!) \times 3!) \\ 336744 &:= (((4!^4) + 7!) - (((6^3)/3)) \\ 336774 &:= -((4! + (-((77 \times 6)) \times (3!^3))) \\ 336816 &:= (((6 + 1)!) + (((8 \times 6)^3) \times 3)) \\ 336817 &:= (7! + (1 + (((8 \times 6)^3) \times 3))) \\ 336858 &:= (((8 \times 58) \times (6! + 3!)) - 3!)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 336864 &:= -(((4-6)^8) - 6!) \times (3!! + (3!)) \\ 336879 &:= (-9 \times ((7! - 8!) - ((6! - 3) \times 3)) \\ 336933 &:= (-((3^3)) + 9!) - ((6! \times 3!) \times 3!) \\ 336944 &:= (-((4 \times 4) + 9!) - ((6! \times 3!) \times 3!)) \\ 336948 &:= (-((8 + 4) + 9!) - ((6! \times 3!) \times 3!)) \\ 336954 &:= (((4! \times 5!) \times (-9)) - 6) + ((3 \times 3)!) \\ 336957 &:= (((7! \times (-5)) + 9!) - 6!) - 3! + 3 \\ 336961 &:= (((1^6) + 9!) - ((6! \times 3!) \times 3!)) \\ 336962 &:= (2 + (6! \times ((9!/6!) - (3! \times 3!))) \\ 336963 &:= (-((3 - 6) + 9!) - ((6! \times 3!) \times 3!)) \\ 336964 &:= (((4!/6) + 9!) - ((6! \times 3!) \times 3!)) \\ 336965 &:= (5 + (6! \times ((9!/6!) - (3! \times 3!))) \\ 336966 &:= ((6! \times 6!) - ((9!/(6/3)) - 3!)) \\ 336967 &:= (((7!/6!) + 9!) - ((6! \times 3!) \times 3!)) \\ 336968 &:= (8 + (6! \times ((9!/6!) - (3! \times 3!))) \\ 336969 &:= (9 + (6! \times ((9!/6!) - (3! \times 3!))) \\ 336972 &:= (((2 - 7!) + (9!/6)) + 3!!) \times 3! \\ 336973 &:= (((3! + 7) + 9!) - ((6! \times 3!) \times 3!)) \\ 336978 &:= (((87 - 9) \times 6!) + 3) \times 3! \\ 336984 &:= ((4! - (8! \times (-9))) - ((6! \times 3!) \times 3!)) \\ 336996 &:= (((69 + 9) \times 6!) + 3!) \times 3! \\ 337275 &:= (-((5 - 72)) \times (7! - 3!)) - 3 \\ 337278 &:= (((8 - 7!) - 2) \times (-73 + 3!)) \\ 337345 &:= ((5 - ((4 + 3)!) \times (-73 + 3!)) \\ 337356 &:= ((6! - ((-5 - 3!) \times (7! + 3!))) \times 3! \\ 337362 &:= (((2^6) + 3) \times (7! + 3!)) - 3!! \\ 337365 &:= ((-5 \times (63 + 7!)) + ((3 \times 3)!) \\ 337428 &:= ((82 - 4) \times ((7! + 3!) - 3!)) \\ 337479 &:= (((9 \times 7) + 4) \times ((7! - 3!) + 3)) \\ 337488 &:= ((8 \times (8! - 4!)) - (7! \times (3 - 3!))) \\ 337539 &:= ((9! - 3!) + (-5 \times (7! + ((3^3)))) \\ 337544 &:= (((4!^4) + 5) + 7!) + 3 + 3!! \\ 337545 &:= (((5 + 4)!) + (-5 \times (7! + ((3^3)))) \\ 337549 &:= ((9! + 4) + (-5 \times (7! + ((3^3)))) \\ 337555 &:= ((-5 - 5!) + ((-5 \times 7!) + ((3 \times 3)!) \\ 337559 &:= ((9! - 5!) - ((5 \times 7!) + (3/3))) \\ 337569 &:= ((9! - 6) + ((5 \times 7) \times (-3 - 3!))) \\ 337607 &:= (((7! - 0!) \times 67) - (3 + 3)) \\ 337635 &:= ((-5 \times ((3 + 6) + 7!)) + ((3 \times 3)!) \\ 337641 &:= ((1 \times 467) \times (3!! + 3)) \\ 337671 &:= (((-1 \times 7!) \times (-67)) - (3 \times 3)) \\ 337672 &:= (-2 + ((7! \times 67) - (3 + 3))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 337673 &:= -((3! - ((7! \times 67) - (3/3))) \\ 337674 &:= ((((-4 \times 7!) - 6) - 7!) + ((3 \times 3)!) \\ 337675 &:= (-5 + (7! \times ((67 - 3) + 3))) \\ 337676 &:= ((-6 - (7! \times (-67))) + (3!/3)) \\ 337677 &:= ((7! \times (7 + (6 \times (7 + 3)))) - 3) \\ 337678 &:= (-8 - ((7! \times (-67)) - (3 + 3))) \\ 337679 &:= ((-((9 - 76)) \times 7!) - (3/3)) \\ 337681 &:= (((-((1 - 8)))! \times 67) + (3/3)) \\ 337689 &:= ((9! - 8!) - (((-6 - 7!) + 3) \times 3)) \\ 337692 &:= (((-((2 - 9)))! \times 67) + (3! + 3!)) \\ 337695 &:= ((-5 \times (-((9 - 6) + 7!)) + ((3 \times 3)!) \\ 337698 &:= -(((8! - 9!) + (((6! \times 7) + 3!) \times (-3))) \\ 337704 &:= (4! + ((0 - 7!) \times (-73 + 3!))) \\ 337715 &:= ((-5 \times (((1 \times 7)!) - 7)) + ((3 \times 3)!) \\ 337716 &:= ((61 \times 7!) + ((7! + 3!) \times 3!)) \\ 337725 &:= ((-5 \times ((-2 + 7!) - 7)) + ((3 \times 3)!) \\ 337747 &:= ((74 - 7) \times (7! + (3/3))) \\ 337752 &:= (((-25) - 7!) + (7^3!)) \times 3 \\ 337755 &:= (((5!/5) + 7!) - (7^3!)) \times (-3) \\ 337757 &:= (((7! \times (-5)) + 77) + ((3 \times 3)!) \\ 337759 &:= (9! + (((-5 \times 7!) + 73) + 3!)) \\ 337779 &:= (((9 + 7) + 7!) - (7^3!)) \times (-3) \\ 337792 &:= (-(((2^9) \times 7) \times 7)) + ((3 \times 3)!) \\ 337794 &:= -(((4! + 9) - ((7! - (7^3!)) \times (-3))) \\ 337795 &:= (-5 - ((9 + 7!) - (7^3!)) \times 3) \\ 337803 &:= (((3! + 0!)! - (-8 + (7^3!))) \times (-3)) \\ 337827 &:= (((7^{-2+8}) - 7!) \times (-3 + 3!)) \\ 337962 &:= (((-2 \times (6! - 9)) \times (7 - 3!))/3) \\ 337972 &:= (((-2 - 7!) - 9!) + ((7^3! \times 3!)) \\ 337977 &:= (7! + (((7! + 9) + 7!) \times 33)) \\ 338076 &:= ((67 \times ((-((0! - 8)))! + 3!)) - 3! \\ 338256 &:= ((6 \times (5 + (2^8))) \times (3!^3)) \\ 338297 &:= ((-7 + 9!) - (((2 \times 8)^3) \times 3!)) \\ 338349 &:= (9! - (((4^3!) - 8) \times 3!) + 3) \\ 338364 &:= ((4 \times (6! + 3)) \times (((8 - 3)!) - 3)) \\ 338384 &:= ((-((4^8)) + 3!!) + (8! + ((3 \times 3)!) \\ 338385 &:= (-5 \times (-8!) + ((-38) \times 3!!) + 3)) \\ 338397 &:= (((7!/9) - (3!!/8)) \times 3!!) - 3 \\ 338436 &:= (((6! - 3!) \times (-4 - 83)) \times 3! \\ 338455 &:= (-5 \times ((5 - (4^8)) + (3!! \times (-3)))) \\ 338472 &:= (2 \times (7! + (4 \times (8! + (3^3!)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 338491 &:= (((1 \times 9))! - (((4 \times 8) - 3)^3)) \\ 338495 &:= (((-(5 - 9)))!^4) + ((8! - 3!)/3!) \\ 338688 &:= (((8! \times (8 + 6))/(8 - 3)) \times 3) \\ 338724 &:= (((4! \times (-2)) - (7!/(-8)))^{3/3}) \\ 338785 &:= ((5^8) + ((-78) + 3!) \times 3!) \\ 338976 &:= ((((-6 \times 7!) + 9!) - 8!) + (3!^{3!})) \\ 339278 &:= (-8! + 7) \times 2 + 9 \times 3!^{3!} \\ 339336 &:= (((6! \times (-33)) + 9!) + (3!^3)) \\ 339552 &:= ((((-(2 - 5)))!^5) + (9!/(-3))) \times (-3) \\ 339564 &:= (((-(4 - 6^5))) + (9!/(-3))) \times (-3) \\ 339576 &:= (((6^7) - 5!) + (9!/3!)) - 3!! \\ 339585 &:= (-5 \times (((8! \times (-5)) + 9)/3) - 3!!) \\ 339744 &:= (((-(4^4)) - (-79) \times 3!!) \times 3!) \\ 339795 &:= (((-5 \times (9 + 7!)) + 9!) - (3!! \times (-3))) \\ 339834 &:= ((4! \times 3!!) - (((8! - 9!) + (3 + 3)))) \\ 339843 &:= (3!! \times 4!) - (((8! - 9!) + 3) - 3!!) \\ 339864 &:= (4! \times (6! - ((8! + (9/3))/(-3)))) \\ 339984 &:= (4! \times (((8! + ((9 + 9))/3) + 3!)) \\ 340332 &:= ((2 - 3!!) \times (((3! - 0!))! \times (-4)) + (3!)) \\ 340557 &:= -((7! - ((5! \times 5!) \times (04!) - 3)) \\ 340992 &:= ((2^9) \times ((-9 + ((0! + 4!)! \times 3!)) \\ 341256 &:= -(((6! - ((5!^2) - 1) \times 4) \times 3!)) \\ 341309 &:= ((9! - 0!) + ((3!! - 1) \times (-4! + 3!))) \\ 341776 &:= ((67 \times 7!) + ((1 \times 4)^{3!})) \\ 341997 &:= ((7! + 9!) + ((9!/(-14)) - 3)) \\ 342089 &:= -((9! - ((8 + ((0! + 2)^4))^3)) \\ 342144 &:= (44 \times (((1 + 2))!^4) \times 3!) \\ 342249 &:= (((9 + (4!^2))^2) + (4 \times 3!)) \\ 342395 &:= ((-5 + 9!) - ((3 + 2) \times (4^{3!}))) \\ 342544 &:= (((4!^4) + 5!) + ((-2 + 4!)^3)) \\ 342656 &:= (((6! + 5!) \times 6!) - ((2 \times 4)^{3!})) \\ 342689 &:= (9! + ((8! + (62))/(4 - 3!)) \\ 342709 &:= (9! + (((07)! + 2) \times (-4)) - 3) \\ 342715 &:= (-5 - (((-1 + ((7 - 2))!) \times (-4)) \times 3!)) \\ 342717 &:= ((7! \times (((1 + 7)^2) + 4)) - 3) \\ 342718 &:= (((8! \times 17)/2) + 4) - 3! \\ 342719 &:= (9! + (((1 + 7))!/(-2)) - (4 - 3)) \\ 342728 &:= (((((8! \times 2) + 7!) + 2) \times 4!)/3!) \\ 342729 &:= ((9! - 2) - (((7! - 2) \times 4) - 3)) \\ 342739 &:= (9! + (((3! - 7!) - 2) \times 4) + 3) \\ 342744 &:= (4! + ((-4 \times 7!) + (((2 + 4) + 3)!)) \\ 342747 &:= (((7! \times (-4 - 72))) + 4!) + 3) \\ 342749 &:= (9! + ((((-4 \times 7!) + 2) + 4!) + 3)) \\ 342768 &:= (((8! + 6) + (7!/2)) \times (4!/3)) \\ 342779 &:= (9! + (((7! - (7 \times 2)) \times (-4)) + 3)) \\ 342784 &:= (((4! - 8) \times 7!) + ((2 \times 4)^{3!})) \\ 342786 &:= ((68 \times 7!) + (2 + (4^3))) \\ 342798 &:= (((8! - (-9 \times (7! + 2))) \times 4) + 3!) \\ 342859 &:= (((9! - 5) - (8!/2)) + (4! \times 3!)) \\ 342867 &:= (((-(7^6)) - ((8! \times (-2))/4!)) \times (-3)) \\ 342935 &:= -((((5^{3!}) - 9!) + (((2 + 4))! \times 3!)) \\ 342958 &:= (((8 + 5!) - 9) \times (2 - (-4 \times 3!))) \\ 342986 &:= ((68 \times (((9 - 2))! + 4)) - 3!) \\ 343024 &:= (4! + ((2 \times (0! + 34))^3)) \\ 343071 &:= (((1 - (70^3))) - (4! \times (-3))) \\ 343097 &:= (-79) \times (0! - ((3!! + 4) \times 3!)) \\ 343159 &:= ((9! - (5^{1 \times 3!})) - (4^{3!})) \\ 343189 &:= ((9! - 8) - (((1 \times 3) + 4!)^3)) \\ 343193 &:= (((-3 + 9!) - 1) - ((3 + 4!)^3)) \\ 343194 &:= (((-4 + 9!) + 1) - ((3 + 4!)^3)) \\ 343198 &:= (((8! \times 9) + 1) - ((3 + 4!)^3)) \\ 343245 &:= (((-(5^{4+2})) - 3!) \times (-4! - 3)) \\ 343344 &:= (((4!^4) - 3!) - (-3 \times (4^{3!}))) \\ 343359 &:= (9! - (((5! \times 3!) + 3) \times (4! + 3))) \\ 343368 &:= (((8! - (6! \times 3)) \times 3) - 4!) \times 3) \\ 343386 &:= -(((6! - ((8! - 3!)/3)) \times (4! + 3)) \\ 343435 &:= (((((5^3) - 4!)^3) + 4)/3) \\ 343436 &:= (((6 + 3))! - 4) - (3!! \times (4! + 3)) \\ 343439 &:= (9! - ((3!! \times (4! + 3)) + (4 - 3))) \\ 343456 &:= ((((-(6! \times 5!) + 4) + 3!!) \times (-4)) + 3!!) \\ 343459 &:= (((9! - 5) + 4!) - (3!! \times (4! + 3))) \\ 343555 &:= (-5 - (5! \times (((5 - 3!!) \times 4) - 3)) \\ 343569 &:= (9! - (((6! - 5) \times (3 + 4!)) + 3!)) \\ 343695 &:= (-5 \times ((-96) \times (3!! - 4)) - 3) \\ 343749 &:= (((-(9 - (4^7))) - 3!) \times (4! - 3)) \\ 343836 &:= (((6^{3!}) - ((8! - 3) \times 4)) \times (-3)) \\ 343896 &:= (-69) \times ((8 - 3!!) \times (4 + 3)) \\ 343899 &:= (9! - (((-9 + 8)) + 3!!) \times (4! + 3)) \\ 343916 &:= (((6! - 1) + 9!) - ((3 + 4!)^3)) \\ 343917 &:= (((7 - 1))! + 9!) - ((3 + 4!)^3) \\ 343938 &:= ((8 + 3!) \times (-9 + (3! \times (4^{3!}))) \\ 344062 &:= (-2 - (((-60) - 4!) \times (4^{3!}))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 344064 &:= ((4! + (60)) \times ((4 \times 4)^3)) \\ 344163 &:= ((((-3 + 6!) \times ((1 + 4)!) \times 4) + 3) \\ 344256 &:= (-((6! - ((5!^2) + 4) \times 4!)) - 3!!) \\ 344259 &:= ((9! - 5) + ((2 + 4!) \times (4 - 3!!))) \\ 344359 &:= ((9! - (5^3)) - (-4 \times (-4 - 3!!))) \\ 344396 &:= (((6! + 9!)/3!! - 4!) \times (-4 + 3!!)) \\ 344397 &:= -((((7! - 9!) + 3) + (((4 + 4)!/3))) \\ 344439 &:= (9! + (3 \times ((4! \times (-4^4)) - 3))) \\ 344488 &:= (((8 \times 8!) - 4!) + ((4! + 4)^3)) \\ 344496 &:= (-((6! - 9!)) - (4! \times ((4 \times 4) + 3!!))) \\ 344505 &:= (((5! - 0!) \times 5) \times ((4! \times 4!) + 3)) \\ 344544 &:= (-((4! \times 4!)) + (5! \times (-4 - (-4 \times 3!!)))) \\ 344564 &:= (4 \times ((6! \times 5!) - ((4^4) + 3))) \\ 344569 &:= ((((-9 + 6!) - 5!) - 4)^{-4+3!}) \\ 344605 &:= (5 \times ((0! + ((6 + 4) \times 4)^3)) \\ 344625 &:= (-5 \times (((2 - 6!) \times 4!) \times 4) + 3) \\ 344688 &:= ((8 \times 8! - ((6! \times (-4)) + 4!)) - 3!!) \\ 344733 &:= ((-3 \times (3!! - 7!)) + (((4!^4) - 3))) \\ 344736 &:= (63 \times (7! + (4! \times (4! - 3!)))) \\ 344756 &:= (((((6! \times 5!) - 7) - 4!) \times 4) - 3!!) \\ 344784 &:= ((4! \times ((8 \times 7) \times (4^4))) + 3!!) \\ 344832 &:= ((2^3) \times (8! + (-4 \times (4! - 3!)))) \\ 344835 &:= ((((-5 \times 3!!) + 8) \times (4! \times (-4))) + 3) \\ 344856 &:= (((6! \times 5!) \times (8 - 4)) - 4!) - 3!!) \\ 344896 &:= (-((((6! - 9!) + 8) - 4!)) - (4! \times 3!!)) \\ 344903 &:= -(((3!! + ((0! - 9!) - 4!)) + (4! \times 3!!)) \\ 344904 &:= (4! - ((0! + (((9 - 4)!) \times (-4))) \times 3!!)) \\ 344905 &:= (-(((5! - 0!) - 9!)) + (4! \times (-4! - 3!!))) \\ 344955 &:= (-5 \times ((5! + 9) + ((4! \times (-4)) \times 3!!)) \\ 344964 &:= (((-((4^6)) + 9!) + 4) - (4!^3)) \\ 344968 &:= (((-8 - 6!) + 9!) - (4! \times (-4 + 3!!))) \\ 344976 &:= (-((((6! + 7!) - 9!)) - ((4!)/((4! - 3)!)) \\ 344992 &:= (-((2^9) + 9!) - (4! \times (4 + 3!!))) \\ 345024 &:= (4! \times (((20 \times 5!) - 4) \times 3!)) \\ 345114 &:= ((((((4 - 1)!)! - 1) \times (5! \times 4)) - (3!)) \\ 345117 &:= ((((((7 - 1)!)! - 1) \times 5!) \times 4) - 3) \\ 345123 &:= ((((((3 \times 2)!)! - 1) \times 5!) \times 4) + 3) \\ 345126 &:= (((6! - (2 - 1)) \times 5!) \times 4) + 3! \\ 345135 &:= (-5 \times (((3!! - 1) \times (-5! - 4!)) - 3)) \\ 345144 &:= (4! \times (((4! - 1) \times (5^4)) + 3!)) \\ 345235 &:= (-5 + (((3 + 2)!) \times ((5! \times 4!) - 3))) \\ 345257 &:= (-((7^5-2)) - ((5! \times (-4)) \times 3!!)) \\ 345264 &:= ((4 \times (((6! - 2) \times 5!) - 4!)) + 3!!) \\ 345325 &:= (-((5^2)) \times ((3! + 5) - (4!^3))) \\ 345328 &:= (((-8 - ((2 - 3!!) \times 5!)) \times 4) + 3!!) \\ 345339 &:= (9! - (((3!! + (3! + 5))) \times 4!) - 3) \\ 345342 &:= (((-2 - (-4 \times 3!!)) \times 5!) - (4! - 3!)) \\ 345344 &:= (-4 \times (((4! \times 3!!) \times (-5)) + ((4^3)))) \\ 345345 &:= (((-((5!/4!)) + 3!!) \times ((5! \times 4) + 3)) \\ 345348 &:= ((84 - 3!!) \times (-543)) \\ 345349 &:= ((9! - (((4 + 3)^5 + 4))) - 3!!) \\ 345352 &:= (((2 - ((5! \times 3!!) + 5!)) \times (-4)) - 3!!) \\ 345355 &:= (-5 - (((5! \times 3!!) + 5!) \times (-4) + 3!!)) \\ 345375 &:= (((-57) + (3!! \times 5!)) \times 4) + 3 \\ 345377 &:= (-7 + (((7! - (3^5))) \times 4!) \times 3) \\ 345384 &:= -((((4!/8)!^3) + ((5! \times (-4)) \times 3!!)) \\ 345392 &:= ((2^9) - ((3!! \times (5! \times (-4))) + 3!!)) \\ 345408 &:= ((-8 \times (04)!) - ((5! \times (-4)) \times 3!!)) \\ 345432 &:= (((-2 - (3!! \times (-4))) \times 5!) - (4! \times (-3))) \\ 345448 &:= ((-8 + (4!^4)) - ((5 - 4!) \times 3!!)) \\ 345453 &:= (-3 - (((5! \times (-4)) \times 5!) + 4!) \times 3!!) \\ 345455 &:= (-5 \times ((5 + 4!) - (5 \times (4!^3)))) \\ 345456 &:= (((6! \times (-5)) + ((4 + 5)!) - (4!^3)) \\ 345465 &:= (-5 \times ((6! \times (4! - 5!)) + (4! + 3))) \\ 345472 &:= (-((2^7)) + (4! \times (5!^{-4+3!}))) \\ 345475 &:= (-((5^7-4)) - ((5! \times (-4)) \times 3!!)) \\ 345479 &:= ((-97) - 4!) - ((5! \times (-4)) \times 3!!) \\ 345486 &:= (((6!/(-8)) - 4!) - ((5! \times (-4)) \times 3!!)) \\ 345488 &:= ((-88) - 4!) - ((5! \times (-4)) \times 3!!) \\ 345495 &:= (-(((5! + 9) - 4!)) - ((5! \times (-4)) \times 3!!)) \\ 345496 &:= (((6!/(-9)) - 4!) - ((5! \times (-4)) \times 3!!)) \\ 345497 &:= ((-79) - 4!) - ((5! \times (-4)) \times 3!!) \\ 345498 &:= (-((8 + 94)) - ((5! \times (-4)) \times 3!!)) \\ 345504 &:= (-4 \times (((0 - 5!) \times 5!) + 4) \times 3!) \\ 345525 &:= (((-((5 - 2)) + (5! \times 5!)) \times 4!) - 3) \\ 345528 &:= (((8/2)!) \times (((5! \times 5) \times 4!) - 3)) \\ 345531 &:= (((-((1 \times 3)) + (5! \times 5!)) \times 4!) + 3) \\ 345532 &:= (-2 - (((3 - (5! \times 5!)) \times 4!) - 3!)) \\ 345534 &:= ((4! \times (-3)) + (((5! \times 5!) \times 4!) + 3!)) \\ 345535 &:= (((5!^3) - 5)/5) - (4^3) \\ 345536 &:= ((6! \times ((3 \times 5!) + 5!)) - (4^3)) \\ 345538 &:= (((-8!)/3!!) + (((5! \times 5!) \times 4!) - 3!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 345539 &:= (((9! - 3!) - (55)) - (4! \times 3!)) \\ 345542 &:= ((-2 \times (4! + 5)) - ((5! \times (-4)) \times 3!)) \\ 345543 &:= ((3! \times (4 \times 5!)) - (54 + 3)) \\ 345545 &:= (((5 + 4)! - (55)) - (4! \times 3!)) \\ 345546 &:= ((6 + (-4 \times 5!)) \times (-((5 + 4)^3)) \\ 345549 &:= ((9! + ((4 - 55))) - (4! \times 3!)) \\ 345552 &:= (2 \times (((5! + 5!) \times 5!) - 4) \times 3!) \\ 345557 &:= (-(((7! + 5!)/5!)) - ((5! \times (-4)) \times 3!)) \\ 345562 &:= (-2 - (-6 \times (((5! \times 5!) \times 4) - 3!)) \\ 345564 &:= (((4 \times 6!) \times 5!) - ((5!/4) + 3!)) \\ 345565 &:= (-(((5 \times 6) + 5)) - ((5! \times (-4)) \times 3!)) \\ 345567 &:= (-7 - (((6! \times 5!) - 5) \times (-4)) + 3!) \\ 345568 &:= ((-8 + (6! \times 5!)) \times ((5 - 4) + 3)) \\ 345569 &:= ((9! - (6 + (5 \times 5))) - (4! \times 3!)) \\ 345573 &:= (-((3 \times 7)) + ((5! \times 5!) \times 4!) - 3!) \\ 345574 &:= (-((4! + (7 - 5))) - ((5! \times (-4)) \times 3!)) \\ 345575 &:= (-((5^7 - 5)) - ((5! \times (-4)) \times 3!)) \\ 345576 &:= (((6! \times (75 + 5)) - 4) \times 3!) \\ 345577 &:= (((((7!/(-7)) \times 5!) + 5) \times (-4)) - 3) \\ 345579 &:= (9! + ((-7 - ((5! + 5!) \times 4!)) \times 3)) \\ 345582 &:= (-((2 - 8)) \times (((5! \times 5!) \times 4) - 3)) \\ 345583 &:= (-((3 + 8)) + (((5! \times 5!) \times 4!) - 3!)) \\ 345584 &:= (-4 - (((8 \times 5!) \times 5!) - 4) \times (-3)) \\ 345585 &:= ((5!/(-8)) - (((5! \times 5!) \times (-4)) \times 3!)) \\ 345586 &:= (-((6 + 8)) - (((5! \times 5!) \times (-4)) \times 3!)) \\ 345587 &:= (-7 - (((((8 - 5)!))! \times (5! \times (-4))) + (3!))) \\ 345588 &:= ((8 - (((8 \times 5!) \times 5!) + 4)) \times (-3)) \\ 345589 &:= (-((9 + 8)) + (((5! \times 5!) \times 4!) + 3!)) \\ 345591 &:= (-((1 \times 9)) - (((5! \times 5!) \times (-4)) \times 3!)) \\ 345592 &:= (-((2 + 9)) + (((5! \times 5!) \times 4!) + 3)) \\ 345593 &:= ((3! \times ((9 - 5) \times 5!)) - (4 + 3)) \\ 345594 &:= ((4! + 9!) - ((5 + (5! \times 4!)) \times 3!)) \\ 345595 &:= (-5 - ((9 \times 5!) \times (-5 \times (4^3)))) \\ 345596 &:= (((6! \times ((9 - 5)!)) \times 5!) - 4!)/3! \\ 345597 &:= ((((((7 - 9) + 5)!))! \times (5! \times 4)) - 3) \\ 345598 &:= (((8!/(9 + 5)) \times 5!) + 4) - 3! \\ 345599 &:= (-((9/9)) - (((5! \times 5!) \times (-4)) \times 3!)) \\ 345621 &:= (((((1 + 2)! + (6! \times 5!)) \times 4) - 3) \\ 345623 &:= ((((((3 + 2)! \times 6!) + 5) \times 4) + 3) \\ 345624 &:= ((((-((4^2)) \times 6!) \times (-5)) + 4) \times 3!) \\ 345625 &:= ((5^2) + (((6! \times 5!) \times 4!)/3!)) \\ 345626 &:= (((((6!^2)/(-6)) - 5) \times (-4)) + 3!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 345628 &:= ((8/2) \times ((6! \times 5!) + (4 + 3))) \\ 345629 &:= (((9! + (-((2 - 6)!)) + 5) - (4! \times 3!)) \\ 345653 &:= (-((3 - 56)) - ((5! \times (-4)) \times 3!)) \\ 345654 &:= (((4 \times 5!) \times 6!) + ((5 + 4) \times 3!)) \\ 345658 &:= (((-8 - ((5! \times 6!) + 5)) \times (-4)) + 3!) \\ 345659 &:= (((-9 - ((5! \times 6!) + 5)) \times (-4)) + 3) \\ 345661 &:= (((16 + (6! \times 5!)) \times 4) - 3) \\ 345663 &:= (-((3 - 66)) - ((5! \times (-4)) \times 3!)) \\ 345664 &:= (((4!/6) \times 6!) \times 5! + (4^3)) \\ 345671 &:= ((((-17) - (6! \times 5!)) \times (-4)) + 3) \\ 345673 &:= (-((3 - 76)) - ((5! \times (-4)) \times 3!)) \\ 345674 &:= (((4! - 7) + (6! \times 5!)) \times 4) + 3! \\ 345683 &:= (-((3 - 86)) - ((5! \times (-4)) \times 3!)) \\ 345684 &:= (-((4 - 8)) \times (((6! \times 5!) + 4!) - 3)) \\ 345685 &:= (5! - (((-8 + (6! \times 5!)) \times (-4)) + 3)) \\ 345693 &:= (-((3 - 96)) - ((5! \times (-4)) \times 3!)) \\ 345699 &:= 9! + (9 - 6! - 5) \times 4! + 3 \\ 345703 &:= (((3! + 0!)/7) - ((5! \times (-4)) \times 3!)) \\ 345713 &:= (((3! - 1)! - 7) - ((5! \times (-4)) \times 3!)) \\ 345719 &:= (((9! - (1^7)) + 5!) - (4! \times 3!)) \\ 345734 &:= (((4! \times 3!) + 7) \times (5 \times 4)) - (3!)) \\ 345735 &:= ((5! - 3) \times (75 - (-4 \times 3!))) \\ 345737 &:= (((-((7^3)) \times 7!)/(-5)) - (4 + 3)) \\ 345743 &:= (((3! \times 4!) + 7) \times (5 \times 4)) + 3) \\ 345744 &:= (((4! \times 4!) + (7 + 5))^{-4+3!}) \\ 345746 &:= (((6! \times 4!) + 7) \times (5 \times 4)) + 3! \\ 345747 &:= (((-((7^4) - (7^5))) \times 4!) + 3) \\ 345755 &:= (5! - (-5 \times (7 + (5 \times (4^3)))))) \\ 345765 &:= (((5^6) + (7 \times 5!)) \times (4! - 3)) \\ 345768 &:= -((8! + (((6! - (7^5)) \times 4) \times 3!)) \\ 345795 &:= (((5! + 9!) + 75) - (4! \times 3!)) \\ 345825 &:= ((5 + (-((2 - 8)!))! \times ((5! \times 4) - 3)) \\ 345864 &:= (((((4 \times 6!) + 8) \times 5!) + 4!) - 3!)) \\ 345929 &:= ((9! - (-((2 - 9)^5)) - (4! \times 3!)) \\ 345936 &:= (((6^3) + 9!) + 5!) - (4! \times 3!)) \\ 345939 &:= (9! - (((3! - (9 + 5)) \times 4!) - 3)) \\ 345955 &:= (-5 - (5! \times (-9 - ((5! \times 4!) - 3!)))) \\ 345957 &:= (((-((7^5)) + 9!) - 5!) + (4!/3!)) \\ 345964 &:= (((((4 \times 6!) + 9) \times 5!) + 4) - 3!)) \\ 345992 &:= (((2^9) + 9!) - 5!) - (4! \times 3!)) \\ 346053 &:= (((3! - (5! \times (0! + 6!))) \times (-4)) - 3) \\ 346056 &:= ((-6 + (5! \times (0! + 6!))) \times (4!/3!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 346064 &:= (4 \times (((6! + 0!) \times 6!) - 4!)/3!) \\ 346079 &:= 9! - 7^{(0 \times 6)!+4} + 3! \\ 346083 &:= (((-(3 - 8)))! \times ((0! + 6!) \times 4)) + 3) \\ 346104 &:= ((4! - 0!) \times (((1 + 6)!) - 4!) \times 3) \\ 346149 &:= (9! + (((4! - 1) - 6!) \times 4!) - 3) \\ 346248 &:= (-84) \times (-26) - (4^3) \\ 346269 &:= ((9! + 6!) - ((2 + 6!) \times 4!) + 3) \\ 346272 &:= (((2 + 7)!) + ((-2 - 6!) \times 4!)) + 3!! \\ 346279 &:= (((9! + 7) + ((-2 - 6!) \times 4!)) + 3!!) \\ 346294 &:= (-(((4! - 9!) + 2) + (6! \times 4!))) + 3!! \\ 346296 &:= (((6! + 9!) - ((2 - 6)!)!) - (4! \times 3!!)) \\ 346304 &:= ((4 \times (((-(0! - 3!)))! \times 6!) - 4) + (3!!)) \\ 346312 &:= (((2 + (((-1 + 3!))! \times (-6!))) \times (-4)) + 3!!) \\ 346314 &:= (((4 + 1)!) \times (3! - (6! \times (-4)))) - 3! \\ 346315 &:= (-5 - (((-1 + 3!))! \times ((6! \times (-4)) - 3!))) \\ 346319 &:= (((9! - 1) + 3!!) - ((6! \times 4) \times 3!)) \\ 346352 &:= (((-2 - ((5! \times 3!!) + 6)) \times (-4)) + 3!!) \\ 346356 &:= (((6! \times 5!) + (3 + 6)) \times 4) + 3!! \\ 346391 &:= (((-1 + 9!) + ((3 - 6!) \times 4!)) + 3!!) \\ 346409 &:= (9! + (((0! - 4!) \times (6! - 4)) - 3)) \\ 346464 &:= ((((-4 + 6!) + (4^6)) \times 4!) \times 3) \\ 346469 &:= (9! - (((6 + (4^6)) \times 4) + 3)) \\ 346472 &:= (((2 + 7)!) - (-4 \times (-6 - (4^3)))) \\ 346479 &:= ((9! + 7) - (-4 \times (-6 - (4^3)))) \\ 346518 &:= (((8 + 1)^5 - (6^4)) \times 3!) \\ 346529 &:= ((9! - ((2 + ((5^6) + 4)))) - 3!!) \\ 346536 &:= ((6^3) - (5! \times ((6! \times (-4)) - 3!))) \\ 346539 &:= ((9! - 3!!) - ((5^6) - (4!/3!))) \\ 346544 &:= (((4! + (4! \times 5!)) \times (6! - 4))/3!) \\ 346555 &:= (-5 - (5! \times (-5 + ((6! \times (-4)) - 3)))) \\ 346596 &:= (((69 + (5! \times 6!)) \times 4) + 3!!) \\ 346608 &:= ((8! + (((0! + 6) + 6!) \times 4!)) \times 3!) \\ 346752 &:= (((-(2^{5+7}) - 6!) \times 4!) \times (-3)) \\ 346779 &:= (9! - (((-(7 \times 7) + 6!) \times 4!) - 3)) \\ 346793 &:= (3!! + ((9! - (7^{6-4+3}))) \\ 346896 &:= ((6! + 9!) - (8 \times ((6! - 4!) \times 3))) \\ 346932 &:= (23 \times (((9! - 6!)/4!) - 3!!) \\ 346945 &:= (((5^4) + 9!) - (6! \times 4!)) + 3!! \\ 346959 &:= ((9! - ((5! + 9)^{6-4})) + 3!!) \\ 346968 &:= (8 \times ((6! - 9) \times (64 - 3))) \\ 347039 &:= ((9! - ((-3 \times (0! - 7!)) + 4)) - 3!!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 347064 &:= (4! - (-(60) \times ((7! + 4!) + 3!))) \\ 347072 &:= (-((2 - 70)) \times (7! + (4^3))) \\ 347238 &:= (((8! + 3) - ((27)!) / (4!)!) \times 3!) \\ 347255 &:= -(((5^{5-2})! - ((7 - 4) \times 3)!) \\ 347265 &:= (((-(5^6) + ((2 + 7)!) + 4) + 3!) \\ 347277 &:= ((7! - 7) \times ((27 - 4) \times 3)) \\ 347293 &:= (((-3^9) + ((2 + 7)!) + (4^3)) \\ 347304 &:= (4! \times ((-0!) - 3!!) + ((7! + 4!) \times 3)) \\ 347328 &:= (((-((8 - 2)^3) + 7!) \times 4!) \times 3) \\ 347331 &:= ((-1 + (((3^3) - 7!) \times 4!)) \times (-3)) \\ 347334 &:= (((-4!) \times (3!! - (3 \times (7! + 4!)))) + (3!)) \\ 347337 &:= (((7! - 3) + ((3! - 7!) \times 4!)) \times (-3)) \\ 347444 &:= (((4!^4) + (4^7) + 4) - 3!!) \\ 347457 &:= (((7! + 5) - ((-4 + 7!) \times 4!)) \times (-3)) \\ 347471 &:= (-1 - ((7! - ((-4 + 7!) \times 4!)) \times 3)) \\ 347496 &:= (((-69) \times (4 - 7!)) + (4 \times 3)) \\ 347519 &:= ((9! - (((1 - 5) - 7!)^4)) - 3!!) \\ 347633 &:= (((-3!) - 3!!) / (-6)) \times (-7 - (-4 \times 3!)) \\ 347692 &:= (((-2 + 9!) + 6) - ((7! + 4!) \times 3)) \\ 347694 &:= ((4! + 9!) + (((-6 - 7!) - 4!) \times 3)) \\ 347696 &:= (((69 \times 6!) \times 7) - (4^3)) \\ 347697 &:= (-7 \times ((9 + 6!) - (7! \times (4 + 3!)))) \\ 347698 &:= ((-8 + 9!) + (((6 - 7!) - 4!) \times 3)) \\ 347709 &:= (9! + (((07 - 7!) - 4!) \times 3)) \\ 347724 &:= (((4!/2) + 7!) - (7! \times 4!)) \times (-3) \\ 347727 &:= (7 + 2)! - (7 + 7! + 4) \times 3 \\ 347729 &:= ((9! + 2) + (((-7 - 7!) - 4) \times 3)) \\ 347733 &:= (((3 \times 3) + 7!) - (7! \times 4!)) \times (-3) \\ 347736 &:= ((63 \times 7!) + ((7! - 4) \times 3!)) \\ 347739 &:= (9! - (((3! + 7!) \times (7 - 4)) + 3)) \\ 347742 &:= ((2 - (((4! \times 7!) - 7!) - 4)) \times (-3)) \\ 347744 &:= (-4 - (((4! \times 7!) - 7!) - 4) \times (-3)) \\ 347745 &:= (((5!/4!) + 7!) - (7! \times 4!)) \times (-3) \\ 347748 &:= ((-8 + 4! + 7) \times 7! - 4) \times 3 \\ 347754 &:= (((4 + 5)!) + ((7! \times (-7 - 4)) - 3!)) \\ 347755 &:= ((-5 - (-5 \times 7!)) - (7! \times (-4^3))) \\ 347757 &:= ((7! \times (-5)) - ((7! \times (-74)) + 3)) \\ 347759 &:= ((9! + 5) + ((7! \times (-7 - 4)) - 3!)) \\ 347773 &:= ((3! + 7) + ((7! - (7! \times 4!)) \times (-3)) \\ 347775 &:= (((-5 - (7! \times (-((7/7) + 4!)))) \times (-3)) \\ 347778 &:= (((-((8 - 77)) \times 7!) + 4!) - 3!) \\ 347781 &:= (((-((1 - 8)) - 7!) + (7! \times 4!)) \times 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 347782 &:= (-2 - (((-8 + 7!) - (7! \times 4!)) \times 3)) \\ 347784 &:= (4! - ((8 - 77) \times ((4 + 3)!)) \\ 347787 &:= (((7! \times (-8 - 77)) + 4!) + 3) \\ 347793 &:= (3! - (((-9 + 7!) - (7! \times 4!)) \times 3)) \\ 347796 &:= ((69 \times 7!) - ((7 - 43))) \\ 347808 &:= (((8 + 0!)! - (((-8 - 7!) + 4!) \times (-3))) \\ 347809 &:= ((9! + 0!) - (((-8 - 7!) + 4!) \times (-3))) \\ 347831 &:= (-1 - (((3 \times 8!) - 7!) + 4!) \times (-3)) \\ 347832 &:= ((-(((2 - 3) - 8)))! - ((7! - 4!) \times 3)) \\ 347904 &:= (4 \times ((-(0! - 9)))! + (((7 - 4)!^{3!})) \\ 347925 &:= (((5!^2) + 97) \times 4!) - 3) \\ 347928 &:= (((8!/(-2)) + 9!) + (-7 \times (-4!) - 3!)) \\ 347944 &:= (((4^4) + 9!) - ((7! + 4!) \times 3)) \\ 347949 &:= ((9! - 4!) - (((9! - 7!)/4!) - 3)) \\ 347951 &:= (((-1 + 5!) + 9!) - ((7! - 4!) \times 3)) \\ 347959 &:= (9! - (((5! + 9!) - 7!)/4!) + 3!) \\ 347967 &:= ((7! \times 69) + ((7!/4!) - 3)) \\ 347969 &:= (9! - ((6 - ((9! - 7!)/(-4)))/3!)) \\ 347973 &:= (((-3 \times 7!) + 9!) + ((7!/4!) + 3)) \\ 347976 &:= ((6^7) + (((9 \times 7!)/4) \times 3!)) \\ 347979 &:= (9! - (((7! - 97) + 4!) \times 3)) \\ 347994 &:= ((4! + 9!) + (((9! - 7!)/(-4))/3!)) \\ 348048 &:= -(((8! - (4! \times (0! + (8^4)))) \times 3!)) \\ 348239 &:= (9! - (((3!/2) + 8)^{4!/3!})) \\ 348336 &:= -(((6! - ((3 \times 3)!)) + (((8 - 4)!^3))) \\ 348339 &:= ((9! - 3!) - (-3 + (((8 - 4)!^3))) \\ 348344 &:= (((4!^4) - 3!) + 8) + (4! \times 3!) \\ 348359 &:= ((9! + 5!) - ((3 + 8)^{4!/3!})) \\ 348448 &:= (-((8 \times 4)) - (-484) \times 3!) \\ 348455 &:= (-((5 \times 5)) - (-484) \times 3!) \\ 348467 &:= (-7 - ((6! \times (-484)) + 3!)) \\ 348474 &:= -(((-(4 - 7)))! + (-484) \times 3!)) \\ 348477 &:= (((7!/(-7)) \times (-484)) - 3) \\ 348479 &:= (((9! - 7!) + ((4 + 8!)/(-4))) + 3!) \\ 348481 &:= ((1^8) - (-484) \times 3!) \\ 348484 &:= (-((4 - 8)) - (-484) \times 3!) \\ 348489 &:= ((9 \times 8! + ((4! - 8!)/4!)) + 3!) \\ 348504 &:= (4! + (((0! + 5!) \times (8 - 4)) \times 3!)) \\ 348506 &:= (((6! \times (0! + 5!)) + 8) \times 4) - 3! \\ 348519 &:= ((9! - 1) - (-5 \times (8 + (-4 \times 3!)))) \\ 348576 &:= (((6! \times 75) + (8^4)) \times 3!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 348579 &:= ((9! - 7!) - (((5 - 8) + 4!)^3)) \\ 348624 &:= (((-(((4 + 2)^6)) - 8!) \times (-4)) + 3!) \\ 348632 &:= (((-2 - ((3!^6) + 8!)) \times (-4)) + 3!) \\ 348707 &:= 70 \times 7! - 8^4 + 3 \\ 348784 &:= ((4^8) + (7 \times (8! + (4! \times 3!)))) \\ 348864 &:= (4! \times ((6! - 8) + (((8 - 4)!^3))) \\ 348935 &:= -((((5^3!) - 9!) - ((8!/4)/3!)) \\ 348936 &:= -((((6!/3!) - 9!) + (((8 - 4)!^3))) \\ 348955 &:= (((-((5^5) + 9!) - (8!/4)) - 3!) \\ 348959 &:= (9! - ((5 + ((9 + 8)^4))/3!)) \\ 349007 &:= -((((7^{0!+0!}) - 9!) + (4!^3)) \\ 349028 &:= (((-((8 + 20)) + 9!) - (4!^3)) \\ 349029 &:= ((9! - ((2 + 0!) \times 9)) - (4!^3)) \\ 349031 &:= -((((((1 + 3)! + 0!) - 9!) + (4!^3))) \\ 349034 &:= -((((((4!^3) + 0!) - 9!) + 4!) - 3)) \\ 349035 &:= -((((5!/3!) + 0!) - 9!) + (4!^3)) \\ 349038 &:= (((8! - 3) + 0!) \times 9) - (4!^3) \\ 349043 &:= (((-((3 \times 4)) - 0!) + 9!) - (4!^3)) \\ 349044 &:= (((-4 \times (4 - 0!)) + 9!) - (4!^3)) \\ 349045 &:= ((-5 - ((4 - 0!)!)) + (9! - (4!^3))) \\ 349046 &:= (((-((6 + 4)) + (09)!) - (4!^3)) \\ 349048 &:= (((-8 + (((4 \times 0) + 9)!)) - (4!^3)) \\ 349051 &:= (((-((1 \times 5)) + (09)!) - (4!^3)) \\ 349052 &:= (((2 - 5) - 0!) + 9!) - (4!^3) \\ 349053 &:= (((-3 + ((5 \times 0) + 9)!)) - (4!^3)) \\ 349054 &:= (((4 - 5) - 0!) + 9!) - (4!^3) \\ 349055 &:= (((-((5/5)) + (09)!) - (4!^3)) \\ 349056 &:= (((6 - 5) \times 09)! - (4!^3)) \\ 349057 &:= (((((7 \times 5) \times 0)! + 9!) - (4!^3)) \\ 349058 &:= (((8 - 5) - 0!) + 9!) - (4!^3) \\ 349059 &:= (((9 - 5) - 0!) + 9!) - (4!^3) \\ 349061 &:= (((-((1 - 6)) + (09)!) - (4!^3)) \\ 349062 &:= (((2 + ((6 \times 0)!))! + (9! - (4!^3))) \\ 349063 &:= (((3! + ((6 \times 0)!)) + 9!) - (4!^3)) \\ 349072 &:= (((2 \times (7 + 0!)) + 9!) - (4!^3)) \\ 349074 &:= (((4! - 7) + 0!) + 9!) - (4!^3) \\ 349083 &:= (((3 + 8!) \times 09) - (4!^3)) \\ 349084 &:= (((-4 \times (-8 + 0!)) + 9!) - (4!^3)) \\ 349104 &:= (((4! \times (0! + 1)) + 9!) - (4!^3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 349168 &:= (((-8 + ((6 - 1)!) + 9!) - (4!^3)) \\
 349176 &:= (((6!/(7 - 1)) + 9!) - (4!^3)) \\
 349185 &:= (((5! + (8 + 1)) + 9!) - (4!^3)) \\
 349195 &:= (((5! + 9!) + (19)) - (4!^3)) \\
 349204 &:= -((((((4 + 0!)!)^2) - (9! + 4)) - 3!)) \\
 349218 &:= (((81 \times 2) + 9!) - (4!^3)) \\
 349236 &:= (((6!/(3! - 2)) + 9!) - (4!^3)) \\
 349299 &:= (9! - (-((9 - (2^9))) \times (4! + 3))) \\
 349344 &:= (((4! \times (4 \times 3)) + 9!) - (4!^3)) \\
 349362 &:= (- (26) \times (3 - (9!/(4! + 3)))) \\
 349368 &:= (((8!/(-(6 - 3))) + 9!) + (4! \times (-3))) \\
 349377 &:= -((7! - (7 \times (((3! + 9)^4) + 3!))) \\
 349384 &:= (((4! - 8!)/3) + 9!) - (4!^3) \\
 349392 &:= ((-2 + (9!/(-(3 - 9)!))!) \times (-4! + 3!)) \\
 349405 &:= -((5! - ((0! - ((4^9) \times 4))/(-3))) \\
 349428 &:= (((8! \times (-2 - 4!))/9) + 4) \times (-3) \\
 349429 &:= (9! - (((((2 \times 4)!) + 9) + 4!)/3)) \\
 349436 &:= (((6 + 3)!) - 4) - (9!/(4! + 3)) \\
 349438 &:= (((((8!/(-3)) + 4) + 9!) + 4) + 3!) \\
 349438 &:= -8!/3 - 4 + 9! - 4 + 3! \\
 349439 &:= ((9!/(-3 - 4!)) + (9! - (4 - 3))) \\
 349459 &:= (((9! - 5) + 4!) - (9!/(4! + 3))) \\
 349524 &:= (4^{(2 \times 5)!/9!} - 4)/3 \\
 \\
 349528 &:= ((8 + (2^{5-9+4!}))/3) \\
 349533 &:= (3!! - (((3^5) - 9!) + (4!^3))) \\
 349559 &:= (((9 - 5!) \times 5!) + 9!) - (4 - 3) \\
 349585 &:= (((5^8) - (-(((5 - 9) - 4)!)) - 3!)) \\
 349648 &:= (((8! + 4!)/6) \times (9 + 43)) \\
 349653 &:= ((((-3 - 5!) + 6!) + 9!) - (4!^3)) \\
 349656 &:= (((6! \times (-5))/(-6)) + 9!) - (4!^3) \\
 349657 &:= (-7 \times (5 + (-69) \times (4 + 3!))) \\
 349659 &:= (9 \times (-5 - (((6! \times (-9)) + 4) \times 3!))) \\
 349679 &:= (((-97) + 6!) + 9!) - (4!^3) \\
 349686 &:= (((6!/(-8)) + 6!) + 9!) - (4!^3) \\
 349688 &:= (((-88) + 6!) + 9!) - (4!^3) \\
 349692 &:= ((-2 + (9 \times ((6! \times 9) - 4))) \times 3!) \\
 349694 &:= ((-4 + 9!) - (6 \times ((9 + 4)^3))) \\
 349696 &:= (((6!/(-9)) + 6!) + 9!) - (4!^3) \\
 349697 &:= (((-79) + 6!) + 9!) - (4!^3) \\
 \\
 349698 &:= ((8! \times 9) - (6 \times ((9 + 4)^3))) \\
 349758 &:= (((((8!/(-5)) - 7!) + 9!) - 4!) + 3!) \\
 349763 &:= -((((3! - 6!) + 7) - 9!) + (4!^3)) \\
 349769 &:= (((9 - 6)!)! - ((7 - 9!) + (4!^3))) \\
 349773 &:= ((-3 - ((7!/(-7)) - 9!)) - (4!^3)) \\
 349776 &:= ((6! + (((7 - 7) + 9))!) - (4!^3)) \\
 349777 &:= ((7^7) + ((7! \times (-94)) - 3!)) \\
 349839 &:= (9! - (((3! \times 8) + (9^4)) + 3!)) \\
 349866 &:= ((6! - ((6!/(-8)) - 9!)) - (4!^3)) \\
 349896 &:= (((6! \times ((9 \times 8) + 9)) - 4) \times 3!) \\
 349916 &:= (((6! \times (-19)) + 9!) - 4) + 3! \\
 349923 &:= (((((3!^2) - 9!) \times 9)/4) + 3) \\
 349926 &:= (((((6!^2) - 9!) \times 9)/4) + 3!) \\
 349932 &:= (((2 \times 3!) \times (-9)) + (9! + (4 \times 3))) \\
 349937 &:= -7 + (3!! \times 9 \times 9 + 4) \times 3! \\
 349944 &:= (((((4!/4)!) \times (9 \times 9)) + 4) \times 3!) \\
 349959 &:= (9! + (59 \times ((-9 \times 4!) - 3))) \\
 349962 &:= (((-2 - 6!) + (9 \times (9^4))) \times 3!) \\
 349963 &:= (((3! \times 6!) \times (9 \times 9)) + 43) \\
 349967 &:= (-7 - ((6! - (9 \times (9^4))) \times 3!)) \\
 349974 &:= ((-((4 - 7)!)) \times ((9 \times (9^4)) - 3!)) \\
 349991 &:= ((-1 + 9!) - ((9 + 9) \times (-4 + 3!))) \\
 349993 &:= -((3!! - (9! - (-((9/9) + 4!)^3))) \\
 350279 &:= (9! + (((7!/(-2)) + 0!) \times 5) - 3!) \\
 350285 &:= (((5^8) - 20) - ((5 + 3)!)) \\
 350305 &:= ((5^{0!+3!+0!}) - ((5 + 3)!)) \\
 350394 &:= ((-4 \times ((-(9^3)) - 0!) \times 5!) - 3!) \\
 350406 &:= ((6! + 0!) \times ((4 \times (05)!) + 3!)) \\
 350658 &:= (((8 \times 5!) + 6) \times ((0! + 5!) \times 3)) \\
 350664 &:= (((-4 \times (-6 - 6!)) \times (0! + 5!)) - 3!)) \\
 350886 &:= ((68 \times (((8 - 0)!) + 5!)) + (3!)) \\
 351232 &:= (2 \times ((32 + (-((1 - 5)!^3))) \\
 351279 &:= ((9! - 7!) - (((2 + 1)^{5+3}))) \\
 351344 &:= (-4 \times (4 + (3!! \times ((1 - 5!) - 3)))) \\
 351354 &:= ((4! \times ((5! + (3 - 1)) \times 5!)) - 3!) \\
 351364 &:= (-4 \times (((-6!) - 3!) - 1) - (5! \times 3!)) \\
 351379 &:= (9! - ((7 \times 31) \times 53)) \\
 351384 &:= (4! \times ((8 + 3)^{1^5+3})) \\
 351459 &:= (9! - (((5! - 4!) \times (-1 + 5!)) - 3)) \\
 351504 &:= (4! \times (((0! + 5!) + 1) \times 5!) + 3!) \\
 351585 &:= (585 \times ((1 - 5!) + 3!))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 351834 &:= (((-4 - 3!) \times 81) + 5) \times (-3!) \\ 351939 &:= (9! - (((3! + 9) \times 15) + (3!))) \\ 351954 &:= (((4 + 5))! - ((91 \times 5!) + 3!)) \\ 351955 &:= (((-5 - 5!) + 9!) - (15 \times 3!)) \\ 351959 &:= (9! + (((5 - ((9 - 1)^5))/3))) \\ 351963 &:= (((3 + 6))! - ((91 \times 5!) - 3)) \\ 351969 &:= ((9! + 6) - ((91 \times 5!) - 3)) \\ 351999 &:= ((9! - ((9 \times 9))) - (15 \times 3!)) \\ 352075 &:= ((-5 - (-70) \times ((2 + 5)!)) - 3!) \\ 352077 &:= (((7! \times 70) + ((2 - 5))) - 3!) \\ 352089 &:= (9 \times ((8! + 0!) + (2 \times (5! - 3!)))) \\ 352229 &:= (9! - ((22^{-2+5}) + 3)) \\ 352297 &:= ((7! + 9!) + ((2 - (25^3)))) \\ 352324 &:= (-4 \times (((-2 - 3!) \times (2 + 5!)) + 3)) \\ 352377 &:= ((-7 \times ((7! - 3!) \times (-2 \times 5))) - 3) \\ 352384 &:= (-4 \times (((-8 - 3!) \times (2 + 5!)) + 3!)) \\ 352394 &:= ((4^9) + ((3! + 2) \times (5^3))) \\ 352439 &:= ((9! + ((3 \times 4!)^2)) - (5^3!)) \\ 352587 &:= ((-((7^{(8-5) \times 2})) + 5!) \times (-3)) \\ 352675 &:= (-((5^7)) + (-((6! - 2) \times (5! - 3!))) \\ 352727 &:= ((-7 \times (((-2 \times 7!) + 2) \times 5)) - 3) \\ 352737 &:= (7^{3!} - 7 \times 2 \times 5) \times 3 \\ 352764 &:= (((4! - 6!) - 7!)/(-2)) \times (5! + 3) \\ 352773 &:= (((-3 - (7! \times (-7))) \times (2 \times 5)) + 3) \\ 352774 &:= (((4 + (7! \times (-7 \times 2))) \times (-5)) - 3!) \\ 352776 &:= (((6 + (7! \times (-7 \times 2))) \times (-5)) + 3!) \\ 352779 &:= (((9! - 7!) - 7!) - ((2 + 5) \times 3)) \\ 352785 &:= ((-5 \times ((8! - 7!) \times (-2))) - (5 \times 3)) \\ 352787 &:= (-7 - (((8! - 7!) \times (-2 \times 5))) + 3!) \\ 352791 &:= ((-1 + 9!) - ((7! \times 2) + (5 + 3))) \\ 352793 &:= ((-3 + 9!) - ((7! + 2) \times (5 - 3))) \\ 352794 &:= ((-4 + 9!) - ((7! \times 2) + (5 - 3))) \\ 352795 &:= (((-5 + 9!) - 7!) - (((2 \times 5) - 3)!)) \\ 352796 &:= ((-6 + 9!) - ((7! \times 2) - (5 - 3))) \\ 352797 &:= ((7! \times ((9 + 7) - 2) \times 5) - 3) \\ 352799 &:= ((9! - 9) - ((7! \times 2) - (5 + 3))) \\ 352803 &:= (((((3! + 0!))! - 8!) \times (-2 \times 5)) + 3) \\ 352805 &:= (5 \times ((0! + 8!) + (((2 + 5)! \times 3!))) \\ 352806 &:= (((((6 + 0!))! - 8!) \times (-2 \times 5)) + (3!)) \\ 352807 &:= (((7! - 0!) - 8!) \times (-2 \times 5)) - 3) \\ 352808 &:= (((8! + 0!) \times 8) + (((2 + 5)! \times 3!)) \\ 352833 &:= (3 \times (-38) + ((2 + 5)^{3!})) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 352836 &:= ((6! + 3!) \times (((8/2) \times 5!) + 3!)) \\ 352875 &:= (-5 \times (((7! - 8!) \times 2) - (5 \times 3))) \\ 352877 &:= (((7! \times (-7)) - 8) \times (-2 \times 5)) - 3) \\ 352927 &:= (((7! \times (-2)) + 9!) + ((2 + (5^3)))) \\ 352967 &:= (((((7^6) \times 9) \times 2) + 5!)/3!) \\ 352974 &:= (-((4 - 7) \times (9 + ((2 + 5)^{3!}))) \\ 353028 &:= (((-82) \times (0! - 3!)) - 5!) \times 3! \\ 353034 &:= ((4! + (((3! + 0!)^{3!}) + 5)) \times 3) \\ 353037 &:= (((7^{3!}) + ((03!) \times 5)) \times 3) \\ 353067 &:= ((((-((7^6)) + 0!) \times (-3)) + 5!) + 3) \\ 353073 &:= ((3 \times 7) \times (((0! + 3!)^5) + 3!)) \\ 353248 &:= (-8 + (-4 \times ((2 - 3!) \times (5! + 3)))) \\ 353289 &:= (9! - ((-82) \times (3 - 5!)) - 3) \\ 353307 &:= (((7^{03+3}) + 5!) \times 3) \\ 353316 &:= (((((6 + 1)^{3!}) + 3) + 5!) \times 3) \\ 353325 &:= (((((5 + 2)^{3!}) + 3!) + 5!) \times 3) \\ 353344 &:= (-4 \times (-((4^{3!})) - (3! \times (5! - 3)))) \\ 353349 &:= (9! - ((4! + 3) \times 353)) \\ 353373 &:= (-3!) + (((-((7^{3!})) + (3!)/(-5))) \times (-3)) \\ 353376 &:= ((6^7) + (((-3 \times 3!) + 5!) \times 3!)) \\ 353379 &:= ((9 \times ((7^{3!}) - (3!)/(-5)))/3) \\ 353397 &:= (-((7! - 9!)) - ((3! \times 3!) + ((5! + 3)))) \\ 353439 &:= (9! - ((3! \times 4) + ((3^{5+3}))) \\ 353488 &:= -(8 + 8!) \times 4 + (3! - 5) \times 3! \\ 353519 &:= ((9! - 1) - (((5 + 3) + 5) \times 3!)) \\ 353544 &:= ((4! - ((4! \times 5!) \times (-3 - 5!))) - 3!) \\ 353556 &:= (6! + (((5! \times 5) - 3!)^{5-3})) \\ 353559 &:= (((9^5) - 5!) \times 3! - (5 \times 3)) \\ 353577 &:= (-7 \times (((7^5) + (3! \times 5)) \times (-3))) \\ 353591 &:= (-1 - (((9^5) + 3) + 5!) \times 3!) \\ 353592 &:= (2 \times (((9^5) + 3) - 5!) \times 3) \\ 353619 &:= (9! - (((1 \times 6) + (3 \times 5)^3)) \\ 353625 &:= ((-5 - ((2 - 6) \times 3!)) \times (5! + 3)) \\ 353658 &:= (((8! + (5!^{6-3}))/5) - 3!) \\ 353659 &:= (((9! - 5) - 6!) - (3!^5)) - 3! \\ 353667 &:= (((7^6) \times (6 - 3)) + (5! \times 3!)) \\ 353671 &:= (-((1 - (((7^6) \times 3) + 5))) + 3!) \\ 353674 &:= (((4 + (7^6)) \times 3) - 5) + 3! \\ 353691 &:= ((-1 + ((9!/6!) \times 3!)) \times (5! - 3)) \\ 353694 &:= (((4 \times (9^6))/3!) + 5!) - 3! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 353696 &:= (((6 + 96)^3) - 5!)/3 \\ 353737 &:= ((-7 \times (-((37^3)) + 5!)) + 3!) \\ 353755 &:= (-((5! + (5^7))) + ((3!! - 5!) \times 3!!)) \\ 353792 &:= ((2^9) \times (7 - ((3! - 5!) \times 3!)) \\ 353799 &:= ((9! - 9) - (((7! \times (-3))/5) \times (-3))) \\ 353808 &:= (((8 + 0!))/((8 - 3)!)) \times (5! - 3) \\ 353875 &:= (-((5^7)) - (((8 - 3)! \times (-5)) \times 3!!)) \\ 353895 &:= (((5! \times (-983)) - 5) \times (-3)) \\ 353925 &:= ((-((5^2) \times 9)) + 3!!) \times (-5 + 3!!)) \\ 353931 &:= ((1 - (((3^9) \times 3!) - 5!)) \times (-3)) \\ 353932 &:= (-2 - (((3^9) \times 3!) - 5!) \times (-3)) \\ 353964 &:= (-4 \times (69 - (3!! \times (5! + 3)))) \\ 353973 &:= ((-((3^7)) + 9!) - (((3 + 5)!/3!)) \\ 354144 &:= (4! \times (-4 + (((1 + 4)! \times (5! + 3)))) \\ 354159 &:= (((9!/5!) - ((1 - 4))) \times (5! - 3)) \\ 354234 &:= (((4! \times 3!)/(-2)) + (((4 + 5)! - 3!)) \\ 354235 &:= ((-5 + ((3^2)!)) + ((4! \times 5!) \times (-3))) \\ 354237 &:= (((-7!) + 3!!) \times 2) + (((4 + 5)! - 3)) \\ 354239 &:= ((9! - (3 - 2)) + ((4! \times 5!) \times (-3))) \\ 354255 &:= (((5! - ((5 + 2)!)) \times 4!) - 5) \times (-3)) \\ 354264 &:= ((4! - 6!) \times (-((2^{4+5}) - 3))) \\ 354292 &:= (-2 + (((9!/(2 \times 4)!)^5) \times 3!)) \\ 354294 &:= (((4! - ((9 + 2) + 4)^5) \times 3!) \\ 354311 &:= (((11^{3!}) + 4!)/5) - 3! \\ 354339 &:= (9! - ((-33) + (4! \times 5!)) \times 3) \\ 354342 &:= (2 \times (4! + (3^{-4+5 \times 3}))) \\ 354355 &:= ((5! - 5) - (3!! \times (-4 \times (5! + 3)))) \\ 354357 &:= (((((7! - 5!) \times 3) \times 4!) + 5!) - 3) \\ 354363 &:= (((3!/6) - (3!! \times (-4))) \times (5! + 3)) \\ 354384 &:= (4! \times (((8 + 3)^4) + (5^3))) \\ 354544 &:= (-4 \times (4! + (-((5! + 4)) \times (-5 + 3!)))) \\ 354579 &:= (9! - ((7 + ((5! \times 4!) - 5!)) \times 3)) \\ 354595 &:= ((-5 + 9!) - (((5! \times 4!) - 5!) \times 3)) \\ 354599 &:= (9! - ((95 - 4)^{5-3})) \\ 354639 &:= (9! - ((3 + 64) \times (5! + 3))) \\ 354657 &:= ((7! - 5! + 6) \times 4! - 5) \times 3 \\ 354693 &:= ((-3 + 9!) - ((6! + 4!) \times (5 + 3!))) \\ 354719 &:= (((9! - 1) - (74 \times 5!)) + 3!!) \\ 354744 &:= ((-4 \times (4! + 7!)) + (4! \times (5^{3!}))) \\ 354759 &:= (9! - (((5! - 7) \times 4!) - 5) \times 3) \\ 354789 &:= (9! - (-87) \times ((4! - 5!) + 3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 354809 &:= (9! - (((0! + 8!) + 4)/5) + 3!)) \\ 354819 &:= (9! - (((1 + 8)!/45) - 3)) \\ 354855 &:= ((5 + (5! \times ((8 - 4)!)) \times (5! + 3)) \\ 354872 &:= (((2 + 7)! - ((8 + ((4 \times 5)^3)))) \\ 354879 &:= (9! + ((7 - 8) - ((4 \times 5)^3))) \\ 354904 &:= ((4! + (09!)) - (((4 \times 5)^3)) \\ 354936 &:= (-((((6! \times 3!) - 9!) + 4!)) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 354937 &:= (-(((7! + 3) - 9!)) - (-4 \times (-5 - 3!))) \\ 354959 &:= (9! - (-((5 - 94)^{5-3})) \\ 354975 &:= (((-5 - 7!) + 9!) - (-4 \times (5 - 3!))) \\ 354984 &:= (4! - ((-((8 + 9)) \times (4! + 5)) \times 3!)) \\ 354996 &:= (-6 \times ((-((9 \times 9^4))) - 5!) + 3)) \\ 355094 &:= ((-4 + 9!) - (((0! + 5)^5) + 3!)) \\ 355098 &:= ((8! \times 9) - (((0! + 5)^5) + 3!)) \\ 355109 &:= (((9! - 0!) - (((1 + 5)^5))) + 3! \\ 355224 &:= (4 \times ((2 + ((-((2 - 5)))!)) \times (5! + 3))) \\ 355248 &:= (8! + (((4! - (-((2 - 5)!))^5)/3!)) \\ 355557 &:= -((7! - (((5^5) - 5!) \times 5!) - 3)) \\ 355563 &:= (-3 - ((6 - 5!) \times ((5^5) - 3!)) \\ 355599 &:= ((9! - ((9^{5-5/5}))) - 3!!) \\ 355669 &:= (9! - (((6! + 6!) \times 5) + 5) + 3!)) \\ 355679 &:= ((9! - 7) + ((6! \times (-5 + 5))) + 3!)) \\ 355689 &:= (9! - (((-8 - 6!) + ((5^5))) \times 3)) \\ 355697 &:= ((((-7 + 9!) - (6^5)) - 5!) + 3!!) \\ 355768 &:= ((8!/6!) \times (-7 + (5! \times 53))) \\ 355793 &:= -((3!! - (((9! - 7) - (5! \times 53)))) \\ 355829 &:= ((9! - ((-((2 - 8)^5) - 5)) + 3!!) \\ 355839 &:= (((9! - (3^8)) - 5!) + (5! \times (-3))) \\ 355894 &:= ((4^9) + (((8 - 5)! \times (5^{3!}))) \\ 355896 &:= (((6! + 9!) - (8!/5)) - (5! \times (-3))) \\ 355944 &:= -((((4! \times 4!) - 9!) + (5! \times 53)) \\ 356179 &:= (9! - (((((7 + 1)! + 6) - 5!)/3!)) \\ 356184 &:= (4! - ((8!/(1 \times 6)) \times (-53))) \\ 356259 &:= (9! - ((5!^2) - (((6^5) + 3)))) \\ 356299 &:= ((9! - (9^{-2+6})) - (5!/3!)) \\ 356319 &:= (9! - (((1 \times 3)^{6+5-3}))) \\ 356349 &:= ((-((9^4)) + ((3 + 6)!)) + (5 \times 3!)) \\ 356379 &:= (9! - ((7 + ((3 \times 6) \times 5!)) \times 3)) \\ 356382 &:= (((-2 + 8!) - 3!!) \times (-6 - (5 \times 3))) \\ 356389 &:= (9! - ((8 \times 3!)) + ((6! + 5) + 3!)) \\ 356394 &:= (((((4! + 9) \times 3) \times 6!) \times 5) - 3!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 356395 &:= ((-5 + 9!) + (((3 \times 6) \times 5!) \times (-3))) \\ 356397 &:= -(((7! - 9!) + (((3! + 6) \times 5!) + 3))) \\ 356399 &:= (9! - ((9 \times (3! + 6!)) - 53)) \\ 356404 &:= ((4 \times (0! + ((4! + 6!) \times 5!))) - 3!!) \\ 356409 &:= (9 \times (((0 \times 4)! - 6!) + ((5 + 3)!)) \\ 356425 &:= ((-5 - (((2 \times 4)! / 6)) \times (-53)) \\ 356436 &:= ((6 + 3) \times ((4 - 6!) + ((5 + 3)!)) \\ 356454 &:= (((4! \times 5!) + 4!) - 6) \times (5! + 3) \\ 356478 &:= (((8! / ((7 - 4)!)) + 6) \times 53) \\ 356489 &:= ((9 \times ((8! + 4) - 6!)) + 53) \\ 356499 &:= ((9! - (9^4)) + ((6 \times 5) \times 3!)) \\ 356539 &:= ((9! - (((3!^5) - 6!) + 5)) + 3!!) \\ 356544 &:= ((4! \times (-4)) \times (((-5 \times 6!) - 5!) + 3!)) \\ 356694 &:= ((-4 \times (-((9^6) + (6! \times (-5)))) / 3!) \\ 356785 &:= ((5^8) - (((7! + 6!) - 5!) \times 3!)) \\ 356829 &:= (9! - (((2 + 8)! / (6! - 5!)) + 3)) \\ 356848 &:= 8 \times (-4 + 8! + (6! - 5) \times 3!) \\ 356849 &:= ((-9 - ((4! + 8!) / 6)) \times (-53)) \\ 356869 &:= ((9! + 6!) + (((8! / (-6)) - 5) - 3!)) \\ 356873 &:= (3!! - (7 - ((8! / 6) \times 53))) \\ 356973 &:= (((-3 - 7!) + 9!) + ((6! / (-5)) \times 3!)) \\ 356976 &:= (((6! \times (-7)) + 9!) + ((6! / (-5)) \times 3!)) \\ 356979 &:= (9! - (-7 \times (((-9 - 6!) - 5!) + 3!)) \\ 356987 &:= -((((7! + 8) - 9!) + 6!) + ((5^3))) \\ 356992 &:= (-2 - (99 \times ((6! \times (-5)) - 3!)) \\ 356995 &:= (((-5 + 9!) - ((9 \times 6!) + 5!)) + 3!!) \\ 357039 &:= (9! - ((3^{0!+7}) - (5! \times 3!)) \\ 357079 &:= (((9! - 7!) + 0!) - ((7 + 5!) \times 3!)) \\ 357088 &:= 8 \times (8! + 0! + 7! - 5 - 3!!) \\ 357119 &:= ((9! - 1) - (((1 + 7) \times 5!) \times 3!)) \\ 357125 &:= ((((((5 \times 2) - 1)! - 7!) + 5) - 3!!) \\ 357139 &:= ((9! - 3!!) + ((-1 - 7!) + (5! / 3!)) \\ 357144 &:= (4! \times (((-4!) - ((1 - 7)!)) + (5^3))) \\ 357149 &:= (((9! + 4!) - ((1 \times 7)!)) + 5) - 3!!) \\ 357173 &:= -((3!! + (((-71) \times 7!) - (53)))) \\ 357235 &:= ((((-5 + ((3^2)!)) - 7!) + 5!) - 3!!) \\ 357249 &:= (9! - (((4!^2) + 7!) + (5 \times 3))) \\ 357329 &:= (9! - ((2 \times (3 - 7!)) + (5^3))) \\ 357475 &:= ((-5 - 7!) - (((4! \times 7!) - 5!) \times (-3))) \\ 357497 &:= ((((-7 + 9!) + 4!) - 7!) + (5! \times (-3))) \\ 357499 &:= (9! - (((9 \times 4!) + 7!) + (5^3))) \\ 357579 &:= (((9! - 7!) + 5!) + ((-7 - 5!) \times 3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 357595 &:= (((5! + 9!) - 5) - 7!) + (5! \times (-3)) \\ 357597 &:= -(((7! - 9!) + ((5! \times (7 - 5)) + 3))) \\ 357609 &:= (9! - ((0! + 6) \times 753)) \\ 357659 &:= (((9! - (56)) - 7!) - ((5^3))) \\ 357679 &:= (9! - (7 \times ((6! - 7) + (5 \times 3!))) \\ 357684 &:= (((-((4 - 8)) \times (6! + 7)) \times (5! + 3)) \\ 357693 &:= ((-3 + 9!) + (((6! - 7!) / 5) \times 3!)) \\ 357696 &:= (-69) \times (((6! - 7!) / 5) \times 3!) \\ 357697 &:= -(((7! - 9!) + ((6 + 7) \times (5 + 3!))) \\ 357708 &:= (8 + 0!)! - 7 - 7! - 5^3 \\ 357709 &:= (((9! + 0!) - 7!) - (7 + (5^3))) \\ 357729 &:= (((9! + ((2 \times 7))) - 7!) - ((5^3))) \\ 357733 &:= ((((((3 \times 3)! + 7) - 7!) - 5!) + 3!) \\ 357744 &:= (((4! \times (-4)) - 7!) + (((7 + 5) - 3)!)) \\ 357759 &:= (((9! - 5!) - 7!) + ((7! / 5!) - 3)) \\ 357763 &:= (((3 + 6)! - 7!) - (-7 \times (-5 - 3!)) \\ 357769 &:= (((9! + 6) - 7!) - (-7 \times (-5 - 3!)) \\ 357787 &:= (((78 - 7) \times 7!) - (53)) \\ 357789 &:= ((9 \times (8! + 7)) - ((7! + 5!) - 3!)) \\ 357791 &:= (((1 \times 9)! - 7!) - (7^{5-3})) \\ 357793 &:= (((3 \times ((9! - 7!) - 7)) - 5!) / 3) \\ 357794 &:= ((-4 + 9!) + ((-7 - (7 \times 5!)) \times 3!)) \\ 357795 &:= (((-5 \times 9) - 7!) + (((7 + 5) - 3)!)) \\ 357796 &:= (((-6 + 9!) - 7!) - ((7 \times 5) + 3)) \\ 357797 &:= (((-7 + 9!) - 7!) - ((7 + 5) \times 3)) \\ 357798 &:= 8! + 9 \times (7! \times 7 - 5) + 3 \\ 357799 &:= (((9! - 9) - 7!) - ((7 \times 5) - 3)) \\ 357833 &:= ((((((3 \times 3)! + 8) - 7!) - (5 \times 3)) \\ 357837 &:= (7! - (((3! + 8) \times 7!) \times (-5)) + 3)) \\ 357839 &:= (((9! + 3!) + 8) - 7!) - (5 \times 3) \\ 357841 &:= ((((((1^4) + 8)! - 7!) - 5) + 3!) \\ 357845 &:= (((5 + 4)! + ((8! / (-7)) + 5)) + 3!!) \\ 357849 &:= ((9! - ((4! / 8)!)) - (7! - (5 \times 3))) \\ 357851 &:= ((((((1^5) + 8)! - 7!) + 5) + 3!) \\ 357855 &:= (((((5 / 5) + 8)! - 7!) + (5 \times 3)) \\ 357863 &:= (((((3 + 6)! + 8) - 7!) + (5 \times 3)) \\ 357869 &:= (((9! + (6 + 8)) - 7!) + (5 \times 3)) \\ 357872 &:= (((((2 + 7)! - 8) - 7!) + (5! / 3)) \\ 357875 &:= ((((-5 - 7!) - 8!) \times (-7)) + ((5 + 3)!)) \\ 357878 &:= (8! + ((7 \times ((8! + 7!) + 5)) + 3)) \\ 357889 &:= (((9! + ((8 \times 8))) - 7!) - (5 \times 3)) \\ 357893 &:= (3!! + ((9! + ((8! / (-7)) + (53)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 357894 &:= ((4! - ((-9 \times 8!) + 7!)) + (5 \times 3!)) \\ 357896 &:= ((6! + 9!) - (8 \times (-7 + (5! \times 3!)))) \\ 357897 &:= -(((7! - 9!) - (8 + (7^{5-3})))) \\ 357903 &:= -((((3! + 0!)! - (9 \times (7 + ((5 + 3)!)))))) \\ 357904 &:= (((4! + (09)!) - 7!) + (5!/3)) \\ 357911 &:= (((((1 + 1) - 9) \times 7) + 5!)^3) \\ 357917 &:= ((71^{-9+7+5}) + 3!) \\ 357929 &:= (((9^2) + 9!) - 7!) + (5 + 3) \\ 357934 &:= (((4^3) + 9!) - 7!) + (5 \times 3!) \\ 357935 &:= ((((-5 \times 3!) + 9!) - 7!) + ((5^3))) \\ 357936 &:= ((((-((6 \times 3)) + 9!) - 7!) + 5!) - 3!) \\ 357938 &:= (((8! - 3) \times 9) - 7!) + ((5^3)) \\ 357939 &:= (((9! - ((3 \times 9))) - 7!) + 5!) + 3! \\ 357941 &:= ((((-1 \times 4!) + 9!) - 7!) + ((5^3))) \\ 357944 &:= (((4! \times 4) + 9!) - 7!) + (5 + 3) \\ 357945 &:= (((-(5 \times 4)) + 9!) - 7!) + ((5^3)) \\ 357955 &:= (((-(5 + 5)) + 9!) - 7!) + ((5^3)) \\ 357982 &:= (((((2 \times 8) + 9!) - 7!) + 5!) + 3!) \\ 357983 &:= ((3!/8) + (((9! - 7!) + (53)))) \\ 357984 &:= (((4! - 8!) \times (-9)) - 7!) - (5! \times (-3)) \\ 357993 &:= (((((3 \times 9) + 9!) - 7!) + 5!) + 3!) \\ 358064 &:= (((4^6) + ((0! + 8))! - ((5! \times 3!))) \\ 358079 &:= (((9! - 7!) - 0!) - ((8 \times 5) \times 3!)) \\ 358179 &:= ((9! - 7!) + (((1 - 8) + 5!) \times 3)) \\ 358195 &:= (((-5 + 9!) - ((1 - 8)))! - (5! \times (-3))) \\ 358197 &:= -(((7! - 9!) - ((-(1^8)) + 5!) \times 3)) \\ 358269 &:= (9! - (((6^2) \times (8 + 5!)) + 3)) \\ 358319 &:= ((9! - 1) + ((3!! + (8 \times 5)) \times (-3!))) \\ 358323 &:= (((3^2))! + ((-38) \times 5!) + 3) \\ 358344 &:= ((-4 + (4 \times (3!! - 8))) \times (5! + 3!)) \\ 358348 &:= (8! + ((4 \times ((38 + 5)^3)))) \\ 358389 &:= ((9 \times (-((8^3)) + 8!)) + (5! - 3)) \\ 358395 &:= (-5 - ((-9!) \times 3!)/((8 - 5)^{3!})) \\ 358549 &:= ((9 \times ((-4 \times 5!) + 8!)) - (5 + 3!)) \\ 358559 &:= ((9! - (5/5)) - (((8 - 5)! \times 3!)) \\ 358608 &:= (((8 + 0!)! - (-6 \times (8 - (5! \times 3!)))) \\ 358609 &:= ((9! + 0!) - (-6 \times (8 - (5! \times 3!)))) \\ 358638 &:= (((83 \times 6!) + (8 + 5)) \times 3!) \\ 358639 &:= (9! - (((3! \times 6!) - (85)) + 3!)) \\ 358669 &:= (9! - (((6! \times 6) + 8) - 5!) + 3) \\ 358675 &:= (-((5^7)) + (-((6! + 8)) \times (5! - 3!))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 358736 &:= (((6 + 3)!) + (-7 \times ((-8 - 5!) + 3!))) \\ 358739 &:= (9! - ((37 \times (-8 + 5!)) - 3)) \\ 358789 &:= (((9! - 8) - 7!) + ((8 \times 5!) - 3)) \\ 358792 &:= (((-2 + 9!) - 7!) - ((-8 \times 5!) + 3!)) \\ 358793 &:= ((3!! + ((9! - 7))) - (8 \times (-5!) + 3!)) \\ 358798 &:= (((-8 + 9!) - 7!) - ((-8 \times 5!) - 3!)) \\ 358848 &:= ((8! + (-4 \times (8! - (8!/5!)))) \times (-3)) \\ 358917 &:= ((7! \times (-1)) + ((9 \times (8! + 5!)) - 3)) \\ 358919 &:= (((9! - 1) - (9!/(-8 + 5!))) - 3!) \\ 358937 &:= (((-7^3) - (-9 \times 8!)) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 358939 &:= ((9! - (((3^9) - 8)/5)) - 3!) \\ 358947 &:= -(((7! - 4!) - ((9 \times (8! + 5!)) + 3))) \\ 358964 &:= (-((4^6) + (9 \times (8! + (5!/3!)))) \\ 358972 &:= ((-2 - 7!) + (9 \times ((8! + 5!) + 3!))) \\ 359035 &:= -((((5^{3! - 0!}) - 9!) + (5! \times 3!)) \\ 359136 &:= (((((6!/3!) - 1) \times 9!)/5!) - 3!) \\ 359139 &:= ((9! - 3!) - (((1 \times 9)!/5!) - 3)) \\ 359144 &:= -((((4^{4-1!}) - 9!) + (5! \times (-3))) \\ 359153 &:= ((3!! \times (-5)) + (((-1 + 9!) - 5!) - 3!)) \\ 359155 &:= (((-5 \times ((5 + 1)!)) + 9!) - ((5^3))) \\ 359156 &:= (((6! \times (-5) + 1) + 9!) - ((5^3))) \\ 359159 &:= (((9! - 5!) - (1^9)) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359199 &:= ((9! - (((9 \times 1) \times 9))) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359214 &:= ((4! - 1) \times ((2 - 9) + (5^{3!}))) \\ 359231 &:= -((((1 + 3!)^2 - 9!) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359232 &:= (((-2 \times ((3! - 2)!)) + 9!) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359235 &:= ((((-5!) + 3!)^2 - (9 \times 5)) - 3!) \\ 359237 &:= ((-7 - ((3!^2) - 9!)) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359239 &:= -((((9 \times 3!)^2 - 9!) + 5) - 3!) \\ 359244 &:= (((4 - ((4 \times 2)!)) \times (-9)) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359247 &:= ((((-7 - 4!) - 2) + 9!) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359248 &:= ((((-8 + 4!) \times (-2)) + 9!) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359249 &:= (((9! - 4!) + ((2 - 9))) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359253 &:= (((-3^{5-2}) + 9!) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359255 &:= -((5! + (-((5 + (2 \times 9))) \times (5^3)))) \\ 359256 &:= (((6! - 5!)^2 - ((9 - 5)!)) - 3!) \\ 359262 &:= (((2 - ((6 + 2)!)) \times (-9)) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359263 &:= -((((3! \times (6! + 2)) - (9! - 5))) + 3!) \\ 359264 &:= (((-4 \times (6 - 2)) + 9!) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359265 &:= (((-5 \times ((6/2)!)) + 9!) - (5 \times 3)) \\ 359266 &:= (((-((6 + 6) + 2)) + 9!) - (5 \times 3!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 359267 &:= (((-7 - ((6/2))!) + 9!) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359268 &:= ((-(((8 + 6) - 2)) + 9!) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359271 &:= (((((1 \times 7) + 2))! - 9) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359274 &:= (((((4 - 7) \times 2) + 9!) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359275 &:= (-5 \times (((7 - 2) - 9!)/5) + 3!)) \\ 359277 &:= ((-(((7/7) + 2)) + 9!) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359278 &:= ((-(((8 - 7) \times 2)) + 9!) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359279 &:= (9! - ((7 + 2)/9)) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359291 &:= (((1 \times 9))! + (2 + 9)) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359293 &:= (((3! + 9!) - ((2 - 9))) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359294 &:= (((-4 + 9!) + ((2 \times 9))) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359298 &:= (((8! \times 9) + ((2 \times 9))) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359302 &:= (((-2 + ((0! + 3))!) + 9!) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359304 &:= ((4! + (((0 \times 3) + 9))!) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359305 &:= (-5 \times ((0! + 3!) - ((9!/5) + 3!)) \\ 359307 &:= (((((7 + 0!))! + 3) \times 9) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359312 &:= (((2^{-1+3!}) + 9!) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359315 &:= (-5 \times ((-1 + 3!) - ((9!/5) + 3!)) \\ 359316 &:= (((6 + 1))! + (3! \times ((9^5) - 3))) \\ 359317 &:= ((7! + 1) + (3! \times ((9^5) - 3))) \\ 359319 &:= (9! - ((((((1 \times 3))!)! - 9) \times 5) + (3!))) \\ 359325 &:= (((-5 - ((2^3))!) \times (-9)) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359328 &:= (((((8 \times 2) \times 3) + 9!) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359329 &:= (9! - ((((-2 + 3!) - 9) \times 5) + (3!))) \\ 359331 &:= (((1 + 3!))! + ((3! \times (9^5)) - 3)) \\ 359332 &:= ((-2 + 3!) - ((3! + (9^5)) \times (-3!)) \\ 359333 &:= (((3! \times (-3!)) + 3!) + (9! + (53))) \\ 359334 &:= (((((4 + 3))! / 3!) + (9^5)) \times 3!) \\ 359335 &:= ((-5 \times (3! - 3)) + (9! + (5! / 3))) \\ 359337 &:= (7! + (((3 + 3) \times (9^5)) + 3)) \\ 359339 &:= (((9 - 3!) \times 3!) + (9! + 5)) + 3! \\ 359342 &:= ((-((2 - (4^3))) + 9!) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359343 &:= ((((-3 + 4!) \times 3) + 9!) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359346 &:= ((-6 - ((4! \times (-3)) - 9!)) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359349 &:= (9! - ((4! \times ((3 \times 9) + 5!)) + 3)) \\ 359352 &:= (((2 + 5))! + (3! \times ((9^5) + 3))) \\ 359355 &:= (-5 \times ((-((5 \times 3)) + (9! / (-5))) + 3!)) \\ 359357 &:= ((7! + 5) + (3! \times ((9^5) + 3))) \\ 359358 &:= (((8 + 5) \times 3!) + 9!) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359367 &:= (7! - ((-6 \times (3! + (9^5))) + 3)) \\ 359384 &:= (-((((-(4 - 8))^{3!}) - 9!) + 5!)) + 3! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 359394 &:= (((4 - 9) \times 3!) + ((9! + 5!) - 3!)) \\ 359397 &:= ((((((7! / (-9)) \times 3!) + 9!) - 5!) - 3) \\ 359422 &:= (-2 - ((-2 - 4!) \times (((9 - 5))!^3))) \\ 359424 &:= ((4! - ((2 - 4))) \times (((9 - 5))!^3)) \\ 359439 &:= (9! - (((3! - (4! + 9)) \times 5) + (3!))) \\ 359448 &:= (((8 \times 4!) - 4!) + 9!) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359454 &:= -((((4! + 5!) \times 4!) - 9!) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359467 &:= -7! / 6 \times 4 + 9! - 53 \\ 359474 &:= ((-4 + 7!) + ((4! + (9^5)) \times 3!)) \\ 359488 &:= ((-8 + ((8! + 4!) \times 9)) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359493 &:= (((-3 + 9!) - (4! \times (-9 + 5!))) - 3!)) \\ 359496 &:= ((6! + 9!) + (-((4 \times 9)) \times (5! - 3!))) \\ 359504 &:= -((((4^{0!+5}) - 9!) - (5! \times 3!)) \\ 359519 &:= (((9! - 1) - 5!) - (9 \times 5!) \times 3) \\ 359532 &:= (((2 \times (3! + 5!)) + 9!) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359544 &:= (((4! \times (-4 - 5!)) + 9!) + (5! \times (-3))) \\ 359555 &:= (-5 \times ((-55) + (9! / (-5))) + 3!)) \\ 359569 &:= (9! - (((6! - (59)) \times 5) + 3!)) \\ 359582 &:= ((28 - 5) \times (9 + (5^3))) \\ 359619 &:= (9! - (((1 + 6) + (9 \times 5!)) \times 3)) \\ 359634 &:= ((-4 \times 3!) - ((6 - 9!) - (5! \times (-3)))) \\ 359635 &:= ((-5 + ((3 + 6))!) - ((9 \times 5!) \times 3)) \\ 359639 &:= ((9! - (3! / 6)) - ((9 \times 5!) \times 3)) \\ 359664 &:= (((-4 \times (6! - 6)) + 9!) + (5! \times (-3))) \\ 359675 &:= (((-5 \times (-7 + 6!)) + 9!) - (5! \times (-3))) \\ 359679 &:= (9! - ((-((7 + 6)) + (9 \times 5!)) \times 3)) \\ 359719 &:= ((9! - 1) - ((79 \times 5!) / 3)) \\ 359725 &:= -((((5^{-2+7}) - 9!) + (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359728 &:= (((8^2) \times 7) + 9!) - (5 \times 3!)) \\ 359747 &:= (((-(((7^4) + 7)) + 9!) + 5) - 3!)) \\ 359749 &:= (9! - ((4! + 7) \times (95 + 3!))) \\ 359755 &:= (-((5^5)) + (((7 - 9) + 5) \times 3!)) \\ 359779 &:= (9! - (-7 \times (((7! / (-9)) + 5!) - 3))) \\ 359799 &:= ((9! - 9) - (((7! + 9!) / 5!) + 3!)) \\ 359839 &:= (((9! - 3!) - 8) - ((9! / 5!) + 3)) \\ 359845 &:= (((5 + 4))! - 8) - ((9! / 5!) + 3) \\ 359849 &:= ((9! - 4) - (((8! \times 9) / 5!) + 3)) \\ 359854 &:= (((4 + 5))! - 8) - ((9! / 5!) - 3!)) \\ 359856 &:= ((6! - (-((5 - 8)))!) \times ((9! / 5!) / 3!)) \\ 359858 &:= (((8! / 5!) - 8!) \times (-9)) + (5 - 3) \\ 359859 &:= (((((-9 + 5!) + 8) \times 9!) / 5!) + 3) \\ 359894 &:= (((4! + 9!) + 8) - ((9! / 5!) - 3!)) \end{aligned}$$

- 359909 := ((9! - 0!) - ((99 × 5) × 3!))
359934 := (((4! × 3) + 9!) - ((9!/5!) - 3!))
359937 := (((73 × 9) + 9!) - (5 × 3!))
359939 := (9! - ((3!)/(-9)) + ((9!/5!) - 3))
359943 := (((3⁴) + 9!) - ((9!/5!) - 3!))
359957 := (((((7! × 5)/(-9)) + 9!) - 5!) - 3)
359964 := ((-4 × (6! + 9)) - (-9 × ((5 + 3)!))
359973 := ((-(3⁷)) + 9!) - (-((9 - (5 × 3)))!))
359975 := 5! - 7 + 9! - 9!/5! + 3!
359982 := (((2 - 8!) × (-9)) - (9!/(5! + 3!)))
359983 := ((3! - ((8 + 9) - 9!)) - (5 × 3!))
359984 := -((((4! - 8) - 9!) + (9!/(5! + 3!)))
359985 := (((5!/(-8)) + 9!) - (9!/(5! + 3!)))
359986 := ((-((6 + 8)) + 9!) - (9!/(5! + 3!)))
359991 := (((1 × 9)! - 9) - (9!/(5! + 3!)))
359995 := ((-5 + 9!) - (9!/(9 + 5! - 3)))
359997 := -(((7! - 9!) - ((9 + 9) × 5!) - 3))
359999 := ((9! - (9/9)) - (9!/(5! + 3!)))
360015 := (-5 × ((-100) × 6! - 3))
360355 := (-5 - (-(((5 × 3)!)/(0! + (6 + 3)!)))
360359 := ((9! + ((5! × (-3)) - 0!)) - (6! × 3))
360369 := (9! - (((6! - 3) + (-((0! - 6)!)) × 3))
360385 := ((5⁸) - (((3! + 0!) × 6!) × 3!))
360442 := (((-2 + 4!) × (4^{0!+6})) - 3!)
360448 := ((8⁴) × ((4! + 0!) + (63)))
360474 := ((-((4 + (7⁴))) - 0!) + ((6 + 3)!))
360475 := ((-((5 + (7⁴))) + 0!) + ((6 + 3)!))
360479 := (9! - ((7⁴) + (0 × 63)))
360573 := ((-((3⁷)) - 5!) + ((06 + 3)!))
360589 := (((9! - 8) - 5!) - ((0! + 6!) × 3))
360593 := -((((3! - 9!) + 5!) + 0!) + (6! × 3))
360594 := ((4! + 9!) - ((50 + 6!) × 3))
360595 := (((-5 + 9!) - 5!) + ((0 - 6!) × 3))
360679 := (((9! - (7 × 6)) + 0!) - (6! × 3))
360693 := ((3 × (-9 - 6!)) - (0 - ((6 + 3)!))
360696 := ((-6 + 9!) - ((-6 - (06!)) × (-3)))
360699 := (9! - (((((9 - 6)! + 0!) + 6!) × 3))
360709 := (((9! - 0!) - 7) - ((0! + 6!) × 3))
360715 := ((-5 + (((1 + 7) + 0)!)) - (6! × 3))
360719 := ((9! - 1) - (((7 × 0) + 6)! × 3))
360735 := ((-5 + ((-3 × ((7 + 0)!)) + 6!)) × (-3))
360738 := (((((8! × (-3)) + 7) + 0!) + 6!) × (-3))
360738 := (8! × 3 + 7 - 0! - 6!) × 3
360744 := (4! + (((4! × (-7)) + 0!) × 6!) × (-3))
360749 := (((9! + ((4 × 7))) + 0!) - (6! × 3))
360759 := (9! - (((-(5 + 7)) - 0!) + 6!) × 3))
360783 := (((-3 × (8! + 7)) - (0 - 6!)) × (-3))
360832 := (-((2³⁺⁸)) + ((06 + 3)!))
360839 := ((9! + (-((3 - 8)!)) - (0! + (6! × 3)))
360859 := ((9! - 5) - ((-8!)/(-((0! - 6)!)) × (-3!))
360864 := ((4 - 6!) × (8 × (0 - 63)))
360927 := (((7 + 2)! + (-9 × (0! + ((6³))))
360929 := ((9! + 2) + (-9 × (0! + ((6³))))
360933 := (((3!³) + 9!) - ((0! + 6!) × 3))
360936 := (((6 + 3)! + (9 × (0 - (6³))))
360939 := (9! + (3 - (9 × (06³))))
360944 := ((-((4⁴)) + 9!) - (((0! + 6)!/3))
360945 := (((5 + 4)! + (9 × (0! - ((6³))))
360949 := ((9! + 4) + (9 × (0! - ((6³))))
360984 := (((4! - 8!) × (-9)) - (((0! + 6)!/3))
361089 := ((9 × ((8! + 0!) - (-((1 - 6)!)) - 3!))
361193 := -((((3! - 9!) + 1) + (((1 + 6)!/3))
361195 := ((-5 + 9!) + (((1 × 1) + 6)!/(-3))
361319 := (((9! - 1) - 3!) - (((1 + 6)!/3!))
361344 := ((4! × (-4³)) + (((1 × 6) + 3)!))
361359 := (9! - ((5! - 3) × (16 - 3)))
361367 := (-(((7 × (6³)) + 1)) + ((6 + 3)!))
361368 := (((-8 × 6!) + ((3 + 1)!)) × (-63))
361369 := (((9!/6!) × (-3)) + 1) + ((6 + 3)!))
361389 := (9! - (((8 × 31) × 6) + 3))
361416 := ((-61) × 4!) + (((1 × 6) + 3)!))
361429 := ((9! - 2) + ((4! - 1) × (-63)))
361432 := ((-2 × (3! + 4)) - (-1 × ((6 + 3)!))
361436 := (((-6!) - 3!) + (-4 + (((1 × 6) + 3)!))
361439 := (9! - ((3 + (((4 - 1)! × 6!)/3))
361459 := (((9! - 5) + 4!) - ((1 × 6)! - 3!))
361465 := -(((5! + ((6⁴) - 1)) - ((6 + 3)!))
361499 := (9! - (9 + (4 × ((1 + 6)³))))
361549 := (9! - (-((4! - (5 × (1 + 6))))³))
361559 := (9! - ((5 × (5! - 1)) + (6! + 3!))
361584 := (((4! - 8!) + 5!) × (-((1 × 6) + 3))
361585 := ((5⁸) - (((5! + 1) × 6!)/3))
361593 := (3! + ((9! + ((-51) + 6!) × (-3))))

$$\begin{aligned} 361659 &:= (9! - ((5! \times 61) + 6)/3!) \\ 361704 &:= -((4! \times (0! + ((7! - (16)) \times (-3)))) \\ 361728 &:= ((8! - (2^7)) \times ((1 \times 6) + 3)) \\ 361729 &:= (-(((9 \times (2^7)) - 1) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 361734 &:= (((4! \times 3) \times (7! - (16))) + 3!) \\ 361744 &:= (-(((4 \times 4) \times 71)) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 361746 &:= ((-6 - (4! \times (7! - (16)))) \times (-3)) \\ 361755 &:= (((5! + 5) - ((7 + 1))!) \times (-6 + 3)) \\ 361793 &:= -(((3!! - ((9! - 7)) - ((-((1 - 6)))! \times (-3)))) \\ 361795 &:= (-5 + (9 \times (((7 + 1))! - (6!/3!))) \\ 361799 &:= (9! + (((-9 \times ((7 - 1))! - 6)/3!)) \\ 361803 &:= (3 \times (0! - ((-8!) + (-((1 - 6)))! \times 3))) \\ 361809 &:= (9 \times ((0! + 8!) - (((1 \times 6))!/3!)) \\ 361827 &:= ((7 + 2) \times ((8! - (-((1 - 6)))! + 3)) \\ 361839 &:= ((9! - 3!!) - (81 - (6!/(-3)))) \\ 361845 &:= (((5! - 4) - 8!) - 1) \times (-6 + 3)) \\ 361854 &:= ((-((4^5)) + ((8 + 1))!) - (6/3)) \\ 361871 &:= (-1 - (-7 \times (((8 - 1))! + (6^3)))) \\ 361872 &:= (((2 + 7))! + ((-8!)/(-((1 - 6)))! \times 3)) \\ 361879 &:= ((9! + 7) + ((-8!)/(-((1 - 6)))! \times 3)) \\ 361919 &:= ((9! - 1) - (((9 - 1) \times 6!/3!)) \\ 361921 &:= -((((1 + 2))!)! - ((9! + 1) + (6!/(-3)))) \\ 361923 &:= -((3!! - (((2 + 9!) + 1) + (6!/(-3)))) \\ 361925 &:= (((((5! \times (-2)) + 9!) - 1) - 6!) + 3!) \\ 361936 &:= (((6!/(-3)) + 9!) + (16)) - 3!! \\ 361937 &:= -7 - 3!! + 9! - 1 \times 6^3 \\ 361943 &:= -((3!! + (((4! \times 9) + 1) - ((6 + 3))!)) \\ 361944 &:= (4! \times (((4 + 9) - ((1 + 6))!) \times (-3)) \\ 361947 &:= (((((7!/4!) - 9!) \times (-1)) - 6!) - 3) \\ 361948 &:= (((((8! - 4!) \times 9) + 1) - 6!) + 3) \\ 361949 &:= (9! - (49 \times (16 + 3))) \\ 361984 &:= (((4! \times (-8)) + 9!) + (16)) - 3!! \\ 361986 &:= (((6 - 8!) \times (-9)) - (((1 + 6))!/3!)) \\ 361989 &:= (9! - (((8 + 91) \times (6 + 3))) \\ 361995 &:= ((-((5 \times 9) + 9!) - (((1 + 6))!/3!)) \\ 361998 &:= (8! - 99 + 1) \times (6 + 3) \\ 362035 &:= ((-((5^3)) + ((0! + (2 + 6))!) - 3!!) \\ 362037 &:= -((((7!/3!) + 0!) + 2) - ((6 + 3))!) \\ 362088 &:= (((-8 + 8!) \times (0! + (2 + 6))) - 3!!) \\ 362089 &:= (((9! - 8) + 0!) - (2^6)) - 3!! \\ 362093 &:= (((3!! - 9!) \times (-0!)) - ((2^6) + 3)) \\ 362096 &:= -(((6! - 9!) + (((0 - 2) + 6)^3))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 362097 &:= ((-((7 \times 9)) + ((0! + (2 + 6))!) - 3!!) \\ 362099 &:= (9! - (((9 - 0!)^2) + 6!) - 3)) \\ 362133 &:= ((-((3^3)) - (((1 + 2))!)! + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 362134 &:= (((4! \times (-31)) - 2) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 362136 &:= -(((6! + ((3 + 1))!) - (((2 \times 6) - 3))!) \\ 362139 &:= (-(((9^3) + 12)) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 362144 &:= ((-((4 \times 4)) - (((1 + 2))!)! + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 362147 &:= (((-7 + (((4 - 1)^2))!) - 6!) - 3!) \\ 362149 &:= (-(((9^4 - 1) + 2)) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 362152 &:= ((((((2 \times 5) - 1))! - 2) - 6!) - 3!) \\ 362153 &:= (-(((3^5 + 1) - 2)) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 362154 &:= (((4 + 5))! - (((1 + 2)^6) - 3)) \\ 362155 &:= ((-5 - ((5 + 1))!) + (((2 \times 6) - 3))!) \\ 362158 &:= (((((8 - 5))!)! \times (-1)) - (2 - ((6 + 3))!)) \\ 362159 &:= (9! + ((5 - (((1 + 2)^6) - 3))) \\ 362163 &:= ((3 - 6!) + (((1^2) \times 6) + 3))! \\ 362176 &:= -(((6! - ((7 + 1) \times 2)) - ((6 + 3))!) \\ 362184 &:= ((4! + ((8 + 1))!) - ((2 \times (6 - 3))!) \\ 362193 &:= (((-3 + 9!) - (((1 + 2))!)! + (6 \times 3!)) \\ 362196 &:= (((6! - 9!) \times (-1)) + ((2 \times 6) \times 3)) \\ 362204 &:= -((((4! + 02)^2) - ((6 + 3))!) \\ 362208 &:= (((8 + 0!))! - ((-2 \times (-((2 - 6))!) + 3!!)) \\ 362209 &:= ((9! + 0!) - ((-2 \times (-((2 - 6))!) + 3!!)) \\ 362255 &:= (-(((5 \times 5)^2) + (((2 \times 6) - 3))!) \\ 362256 &:= -(((6 \times 52) \times 2)) + ((6 + 3))! \\ 362259 &:= (9! - (((52 \times 2) \times 6) - 3)) \\ 362289 &:= ((9 \times (8! - ((2 + (2^6)))) + 3) \\ 362291 &:= (((-1 + 9!) + (22 \times 6)) - 3!!) \\ 362297 &:= ((-7 + 9!) - (((2 + 2))!^{6/3})) \\ 362302 &:= (-2 - (((0! + 3))!^2) - ((6 + 3))!) \\ 362304 &:= -(((4!^{0 \times 3 + 2}) - ((6 + 3))!) \\ 362343 &:= ((3!!/4) + (((3^2))! - 6!) + 3) \\ 362346 &:= (((6!/4) + ((3^2))!) - 6!) + 3! \\ 362349 &:= ((9! - 4!) - (((3^2))!/6!) + 3) \\ 362359 &:= (9! - (((5! + 3) + (2 \times 6!))/3)) \\ 362364 &:= ((-4 + ((6 + 3))!) - ((2 + 6)^3)) \\ 362368 &:= ((8! \times (6 + 3)) - ((2 + 6)^3)) \\ 362369 &:= (9! - ((-6/3!) + ((2 + 6)^3))) \\ 362374 &:= (((4! \times (-7 \times 3)) - 2) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 362376 &:= (((6! + 7!) - 3!) - 2) \times 63 \\ 362379 &:= (9! - (((-7 \times 3!) \times (-2 \times 6)) - 3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 362389 &:= (9! + (((8 \times (3 - (2^6))) - 3))) \\ 362392 &:= ((-2 + 9!) - ((3^{-2+6}) \times 3!)) \\ 362393 &:= -(((3! - 9!) + ((-3 - (2 \times 6!))/(-3)))) \\ 362394 &:= ((4! + 9!) - (((3^2)!/6!) + 3!)) \\ 362395 &:= ((-5 + 9!) - (((3! - 2) \times 6!)/3!)) \\ 362396 &:= ((-6 + 9!) - ((3! - (2 \times 6!))/(-3))) \\ 362398 &:= (((-8 + 9!) + 3!) + ((2 \times 6!)/(-3))) \\ 362399 &:= (9! - (((9/3) + (2 \times 6!))/3)) \\ 362402 &:= (((-20) \times 4!) + 2) + ((6 + 3)!) \\ 362404 &:= (((4! + 0!) \times 4!) + 2)^{6/3} \\ 362408 &:= (((8 + 0!)!) + ((4! - (2 \times 6!))/3)) \\ 362409 &:= (9! - ((0! - ((4! + 2) \times (-6))) \times 3)) \\ 362433 &:= -((3! + (((-3 + 4!)^2) - ((6 + 3)!))) \\ 362436 &:= ((-6 \times ((3 \times 4!) + 2)) + ((6 + 3)!) \\ 362439 &:= (9! - (((3 + 4)^2) \times (6 + 3))) \\ 362446 &:= (((6 - 4!) \times 4!) - 2) + ((6 + 3)!) \\ 362448 &:= (((8! - 4!) - 4!) \times ((2 \times 6) - 3)) \\ 362449 &:= (9! + (((4/4) - (2 \times (6^3)))) \\ 362458 &:= -(((8!/(5! - 4!)) + (2 - ((6 + 3)!))) \\ 362469 &:= (9! - ((6 \times (4 + (2^6))) + 3)) \\ 362472 &:= (((2 + 7)!) + 4!) - (2 \times (6^3)) \\ 362474 &:= ((4! \times (7 - 4!)) - (-2 - ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 362479 &:= (((9! + 7) + 4!) - (2 \times (6^3))) \\ 362484 &:= (((-4 - 8!) + (4! \times 2)) \times -(6 + 3)) \\ 362488 &:= (-8 + (((-8 \times 4!) \times 2) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 362491 &:= (((-1 + 9!) - 4) + (-((2^6) \times 3!)) \\ 362493 &:= ((-3 + 9!) - (4! \times (-2 - (6 \times 3)))) \\ 362495 &:= (((-5 + 9!) + 4) + (-((2^6) \times 3!)) \\ 362496 &:= ((-6 + 9!) - ((4 + 2) \times 63)) \\ 362499 &:= (9! - (((9 \times 42) + 6) - 3)) \\ 362508 &:= (8 + 0!)! - (5! - 2 + 6) \times 3 \\ 362509 &:= ((9! + 0!) - ((5! - ((2 - 6))) \times 3)) \\ 362514 &:= ((-(4 - 1)) \times (5! + 2)) + ((6 + 3)!) \\ 362515 &:= (-5 + (((1 + 5)!)/(-2)) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 362516 &:= -(((6 + 1) \times 52)) + ((6 + 3)!) \\ 362518 &:= (((((8 + 1)!) - 5!) - 2) + (6!/(-3))) \\ 362519 &:= (9! - (((1 + 5)!) + 2)/(6/3)) \\ 362535 &:= -(((5! + (((3 \times 5)^2))) - ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 362537 &:= (-((7^3)) + ((5 + ((2 \times 6)/3))!) \\ 362538 &:= (((-8!) - 3!)/5!) + (((2 \times 6) - 3)!) \\ 362539 &:= ((9! - 3!) - (5 \times ((2^6) + 3))) \\ 362542 &:= -((((((2 \times 4)!/5!) + 2) - ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 362544 &:= ((4! \times (-4 + (5 \times 2))) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 362545 &:= (((5 + 4)!) - (5 \times ((2^6) + 3))) \\ 362549 &:= (9! + ((4 - (5 \times ((2^6) + 3)))) \\ 362554 &:= (((4 + 5)!) - ((5 \times (2^6)))) - 3! \\ 362555 &:= ((-5 \times (5 - (5!/(-2)))) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 362556 &:= -(((((-6 + (5!/5))^2) - ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 362559 &:= (9! - (((55 - 2) \times 6) + 3)) \\ 362562 &:= -((((2^6) \times 5) - 2) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 362563 &:= (((3 + 6)!) - ((5 \times (2^6)) - 3)) \\ 362564 &:= -((4 + (6 \times 52)) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 362565 &:= (((-5 + 6!) + ((5 + 2)!) \times 63) \\ 362569 &:= (9! - (6 - (5 \times (2 - 63)))) \\ 362579 &:= (9! - ((7 \times 52) - 63)) \\ 362589 &:= (9! - ((85 + (2 \times 6)) \times 3)) \\ 362594 &:= -4 + 9! - (5! - 26) \times 3 \\ 362598 &:= 8! \times 9 - (5! - 26) \times 3 \\ 362604 &:= (((4! - 0!) \times (-6 \times 2)) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 362609 &:= ((9! - 0!) - ((6!/(2 + 6)) \times 3)) \\ 362617 &:= -((7 + (16^2))) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 362619 &:= (9! - (((-1 + 6!) + (2^6))/3)) \\ 362622 &:= -(((2^{2+6}) + 2) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 362623 &:= (((3^2)!) + ((6 - 263))) \\ 362624 &:= -((4 \times (2^6))) + (((2 \times 6) - 3)!) \\ 362628 &:= ((8! - (26 + 2)) \times (6 + 3)) \\ 362629 &:= (9! + ((2 \times 6) - 263)) \\ 362632 &:= (((-2 + 3!) \times (-62)) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 362634 &:= (((-4 + ((3 + 6)!) - 2) + (6!/(-3))) \\ 362635 &:= ((-5 + ((3 + 6)!) - ((2 \times 6!)/3!)) \\ 362636 &:= (((6!/(-3)) - (6 - 2)) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 362638 &:= (((8! \times (3 + 6)) - 2) + (6!/(-3))) \\ 362639 &:= (((9! \times 3) - (6/2)) - 6!)/3 \\ 362651 &:= (-1 + (((5! - 6) \times (-2)) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 362652 &:= (((-2 \times 5!) + (6 \times 2)) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 362654 &:= -(((4 \times 56) + 2)) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 362655 &:= (((5 \times 5) - ((6 + 2)!) \times -(6 + 3)) \\ 362657 &:= -7 + (5 + 6 - 2)! - 6^3 \\ 362659 &:= (9! - (5 + (((6 \times 2) - 6^3))) \\ 362662 &:= ((-2 + ((6 + (6/2)))! - ((6^3))) \\ 362664 &:= (((4 \times 6) - ((6 + 2)!) \times -(6 + 3)) \\ 362666 &:= -((((6 \times 6) \times 6) - 2)) + ((6 + 3)!)) \end{aligned}$$

- 362671** := $(1 - ((7! / ((6 - 2)!) - ((6 + 3)!)!))$
362672 := $((2 + 7)!) + (((6 + 2) - (6^3)))$
362673 := $(-(3 \times (7 + 62))) + ((6 + 3)!)$
362674 := $(4 - ((7! / ((6 - 2)!) - ((6 + 3)!)!))$
362675 := $((5! - 7!) / ((6 - 2)!) + ((6 + 3)!)$
362676 := $(6 - ((7! / ((6 - 2)!) - ((6 + 3)!)!))$
362677 := $((7 \times (7 - (6^2))) + ((6 + 3)!)$
362678 := $(8 - ((7! / ((6 - 2)!) - ((6 + 3)!)!))$
362679 := $(9! + (((7 + 6) + 2) - (6^3)))$
362682 := $((-2 - 8!) + ((6 - 2)!) \times -(6 + 3))$
362684 := $((4! \times (-8)) - (6 - 2)) + ((6 + 3)!)$
362688 := $(-(((8 + 8) \times 6) \times 2)) + ((6 + 3)!)$
362689 := $((9! - 8) - ((6! / (-2 - 6))) + 3)$
362691 := $((1 \times 9)!) - ((6/2) \times 63)$
362692 := $((-2 + 9!) - (62 \times (6 - 3)))$
362694 := $((4! + 9!) - ((6 + (2^6)) \times 3))$
362695 := $((-5 + 9!) + (((6^2) - (6^3))))$
362696 := $((-6 + 9!) + (62)) + (6! / (-3))$
362698 := $((-8 + 9!) - (6 \times (26 + 3)))$
362704 := $((40 + ((7 + 2)!) - ((6^3)))$
362705 := $(-(((50 \times 7) / 2)) + ((6 + 3)!)$
362709 := $(9! - (((0 - 7) + (2^6)) \times 3))$
362714 := $((4! \times (-1 \times 7)) + 2) + ((6 + 3)!)$
362715 := $((51 + ((7 + 2)!) - ((6^3)))$
362718 := $((8 + 1)!) - (((7 + 2) \times 6) \times 3)$
362719 := $(9! - ((1 \times 7) \times (26 - 3)))$
362722 := $((-2 + ((2 + 7)!) - (26 \times 3)!)$
362724 := $((4! - 2) \times (-7) - 2) + ((6 + 3)!)$
362726 := $((62 + ((7 + 2)!) - ((6^3)))$
362727 := $((7! - 2) \times 72) - (6 + 3)$
362728 := $8^2 + (7 + 2)! - 6^3$
362729 := $(9! - (((2^7) + 26) - 3))$
362732 := $(-(((2 \times 37) \times 2)) + ((6 + 3)!)$
362733 := $((3 \times 3)!) - ((7^2) \times (6 - 3))$
362734 := $(-(((4 \times 37) - 2)) + ((6 + 3)!)$
362735 := $((-5 - 3!) / (7 - 2)) + ((6 + 3)!)$
362736 := $((6 + 3)!) - ((72 \times 6) / 3)$
362737 := $73 + (7 + 2)! - 6^3$
362739 := $(9! - (((3 \times 7) + 26) \times 3))$
362742 := $((-2 - (4! \times (7! - 2))) \times -(6 - 3))$
362743 := $(-(((3! \times 4!) - 7) - (((2 \times 6) - 3)!)$
362744 := $((-((4 \times 4) - ((7 - 2)!) + ((6 + 3)!)$
362747 := $((-7 \times (4! - (7 - 2))) + ((6 + 3)!)$
362748 := $84 + (7 + 2)! - 6^3$
362751 := $(((-1 \times 5!) + ((7 + 2)!) - (6 + 3))$
362753 := $(-(((3! + 5!) - ((7 + 2)!) + (6/3)!)$
362754 := $((4 + 5)!) - ((7 \times 2) \times (6 + 3))$
362756 := $(((-6 - 5!) + ((7 + 2)!) + (6/3))$
362757 := $(((-7 \times 5!) + ((7 + 2)!) + 6!) - 3$
362759 := $(9! + ((5 - ((7 \times 2) \times (6 + 3))))$
362761 := $((1^6) - ((7 - 2)!) + ((6 + 3)!)$
362762 := $(2 + (((6 \times ((7 + 2)!) - 6!) / 3)!)$
362764 := $((4! / 6) - ((7 - 2)!) + ((6 + 3)!)$
362765 := $(5 + (((6 \times ((7 + 2)!) - 6!) / 3)!)$
362766 := $((6! / (-6)) + ((7 + 2)!) + ((6 - 3)!)$
362767 := $((7! / 6!) - ((7 - 2)!) + ((6 + 3)!)$
362768 := $(8 + (((6 \times ((7 + 2)!) - 6!) / 3)!)$
362769 := $(9! - (6 + (7 \times ((2 \times 6) + 3))))$
362774 := $(-(((4 + (7 \times 7)) \times 2)) + ((6 + 3)!)$
362775 := $(-((5 \times (7 + (7 \times 2)))) + ((6 + 3)!)$
362776 := $(-((6 + ((7 \times 7) \times 2))) + ((6 + 3)!)$
362777 := $((7! + 7) / (-7^2)) + ((6 + 3)!)$
362779 := $(9! - (((7 \times 7) \times 2) + 6) - 3)$
362781 := $((1 + 8)!) - ((7 + 26) \times 3)$
362782 := $(-(((28 \times 7) / 2)) + ((6 + 3)!)$
362783 := $((3! \times (-8)) - (7^2)) + ((6 + 3)!)$
362784 := $((4! \times 8!) / 7! / (-2)) + ((6 + 3)!)$
362787 := $((7! / 8) + ((7 + 2)!) - 6!) - 3$
362789 := $(9! - (((8 \times 7) / 2) + 63))$
362801 := $((-1 + ((0! + 8)!) - (26 \times 3))$
362802 := $(((-2 - 0!) \times 8!) + (26)) \times (-3)$
362805 := $((5 \times (0! - ((8 \times 2)))) + ((6 + 3)!)$
362808 := $((8 - (08)!) \times -(2 \times 6 - 3))$
362809 := $((9! + 0!) - (((8/2) \times 6) \times 3))$
362822 := $(-(((2 \times 28) + 2)) + ((6 + 3)!)$
362823 := $((3^2)!) - (((8 + 2) \times 6) - 3)$
362824 := $((4! \times (-2)) - 8) + (((2 \times 6) - 3)!)$
362825 := $((5! - (2 + 8)) / (-2)) + ((6 + 3)!)$
362826 := $((6/2)!) - 8! \times -(2 \times 6 - 3))$
362829 := $(9! - (((2 - 8) \times 2) + 63))$
362831 := $(-((1 + ((3 \times 8) \times 2))) + ((6 + 3)!)$
362832 := $(-(((2 \times 3) \times 8)) + (((2 \times 6) - 3)!)$
362833 := $((3 \times 3)!) + (((8 \times 2) - 63))$

- 362834** := $(-((4 \times (3 + 8)) + 2)) + ((6 + 3)!)!$
362835 := $(-((53 - 8)) + (((2 \times 6) - 3)!)!$
362836 := $((6 + 3)!) - (8 + ((2 \times 6) \times 3))$
362837 := $((7 \times 3) - (8^2)) + ((6 + 3)!)!$
362838 := $((8 \times (3 - 8)) - 2) + ((6 + 3)!)!$
362839 := $9! + (((3 \times 8) - 2) - 63))$
362851 := $((1^5 + 8)!) - (26 + 3)$
362852 := $((2 - 58)/2) + ((6 + 3)!)!$
362853 := $(-((35 - 8)) + (((2 \times 6) - 3)!)!$
362854 := $((4 + 5)!) - (8 + (2 \times (6 + 3)))$
362855 := $(-((5 \times 5)) + (((8 - 2) + 6) - 3)!)!$
362856 := $((6 - 5) + 8)!) - ((2 + 6) \times 3)$
362857 := $((7 \times (5 - 8)) - 2) + ((6 + 3)!)!$
362858 := $((8 \times (5 - 8)) + 2) + ((6 + 3)!)!$
362859 := $9! - (((5 \times 8) + 2)/6) \times 3)$
362871 := $((1^7) - 8!) \times (-((2 \times 6) - 3))$
362872 := $((2 + 7)!) - ((8/2) \times 6/3)$
362874 := $((4 - 7) \times 8!) + 2) \times (-6 - 3))$
362875 := $-5 + (((78/26) \times 3)!)!$
362876 := $((6 - 7) \times 8)/2) + ((6 + 3)!)!$
362877 := $((7 - ((7 - 8) \times 2))!) - (6 - 3)$
362878 := $((8 \times 7)/8) + 2)!) - (6/3)$
362879 := $9! - ((7 - 8) + 2)^6 3)$
362913 := $((3 + 1)!) + 9) + ((2 \times 6) - 3)!)!$
362914 := $((4! + (1 + 9)) + ((2 \times 6) - 3)!)!$
362919 := $9! + (((1 \times 9) - 2) + 6) \times 3)$
362924 := $(4 \times (2 + 9)) + ((2 \times 6) - 3)!)!$
362925 := $((5^2) + 9!) + (2 + (6 \times 3))$
362926 := $(62 + 9!) + ((2 - (6 \times 3)))$
362927 := $(-((7 \times 2) + 9!) - (2 - 63))$
362928 := $((8^2) + 9!) + ((2 - (6 \times 3)))$
362929 := $9! + (((2 - 9) \times 2) + 63)$
362931 := $((-1 - 3!) + 9!) + (2^6) - 3!$
362934 := $((4! \times (-3)) + 9!) + ((2 \times 63))$
362935 := $((5!/3) + 9!) + ((2 \times 6) + 3)$
362937 := $(-((7 \times 3) + 9!) + ((26 \times 3)))$
362938 := $((8! + 3!) \times 9) + ((2 \times 6)/3)$
362941 := $((1^4 \times 9)!) - (2 - 63)$
362942 := $(-((2^4) + 9!) + ((26 \times 3)))$
362943 := $((3 + 4) \times 9) + (((2 \times 6) - 3)!)!$
362944 := $4! + 4! + 9! - 2 + 6 \times 3$
362945 := $(5 \times (4 + 9)) + (((2 \times 6) - 3)!)!$
362946 := $((6 \times 4!) + 9!) - ((26 \times 3))$
362948 := $((84 + 9!) + ((2 - (6 \times 3)))$
362949 := $9! + ((49 - 26) \times 3)$
362951 := $((-1 - 5!) + 9!) + ((2^6) \times 3)$
362962 := $(-((2 - 6)) + 9!) + ((26 \times 3))$
362964 := $(4 + ((6!/9) + (((2 \times 6) - 3)!)!$
362965 := $((5!/6) + 9!) + (2 + 63)$
362968 := $((8!/6!) + 9!) + (26) + 3!$
362971 := $(-((1^7) - 92)) + ((6 + 3)!)!$
362972 := $((2^7) + 9!) - ((2 \times 6) \times 3)$
362973 := $((3 \times 7) + 9!) + ((2 \times 6) \times 3!)$
362974 := $((-47) - 9!) \times (-2) - ((6 + 3)!)!$
362975 := $((5! - 7) + 9!) - (2 \times (6 + 3))$
362976 := $(6 \times (7 + 9)) + (((2 \times 6) - 3)!)!$
362979 := $9! + ((7 \times 9) + ((2 \times 6) \times 3))$
362982 := $((2 - 8!) \times (-9)) + (((2 + 6) - 3)!)!$
363001 := $((10 - 0)!) + ((3! + 6!)/3!)$
363005 := $5^{003} + (6 + 3)!$
363009 := $9! + ((0! - ((0! + 3!) \times (-6))) \times 3)$
363012 := $((21 + 0!) \times 3!) + ((6 + 3)!)!$
363018 := $(8 + 1)! + (0! + 3!) \times 6 - 3!$
363019 := $(9! + 103) + (6 \times 3!)$
363024 := $((4! \times (2 \times 03)) + ((6 + 3)!)!$
363025 := $((5^2) + (-((0! - 3!)))!) + ((6 + 3)!)!$
363027 := $((7^2) \times 03) + ((6 + 3)!)!$
363029 := $(9! + 2) + (((0! + 3)!) \times 6) + 3)$
363036 := $((6 + 3)!) + (-((0! - 3!)))!) + (6 \times 3!)$
363039 := $9! + ((3^0 3) \times 6) - 3)$
363041 := $((-1 + 4!) \times (0! + 3!)) + ((6 + 3)!)!$
363042 := $((2 + 4!) + 0!) \times 3!) + ((6 + 3)!)!$
363045 := $((54 + 0!) \times 3) + ((6 + 3)!)!$
363047 := $((7 \times 4!) - 0!) + ((3^{6/3})!)!$
363048 := $((8!/40)/3!) + ((6 + 3)!)!$
363049 := $9! + ((4! \times (0! + 3!)) + (6/3!))$
363054 := $((4! + (50 \times 3)) + ((6 + 3)!)!$
363072 := $((2^{7-0!}) \times 3) + ((6 + 3)!)!$
363075 := $(-((5 - 70) \times 3)) + ((6 + 3)!)!$
363079 := $((9! + 7) - ((0! + 3)!)!) + ((6^3))$
363084 := $((4! + 8!) - 0!) \times (3 + 6) - 3$
363085 := $(-5 + ((8 + 0)!)!) - ((3! - ((6^3))))$
363089 := $((9! - 8) + ((0 \times 3)!)!) + ((6^3))$
363117 := $711/3 + (6 + 3)!$

$$\begin{aligned} 363118 &:= (((8 + 1))! + (((-1 \times 3!) + 6!)/3)) \\ 363119 &:= (((9! - 1) + ((1 + 3))!) + ((6^3)) \\ 363132 &:= ((2 \times (3! + ((-1 + 3!)!)) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 363133 &:= (((3 \times 3)! + 13) - (6!/(-3))) \\ 363139 &:= (((9! + 3!) + 13) - (6!/(-3))) \\ 363144 &:= ((44 \times ((1 \times 3))!) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 363149 &:= (((9! + 4!) - 1) + 3!) - (6!/(-3))) \\ 363155 &:= ((55 \times (-1 + 3!)) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 363159 &:= (9! + (((5 + 1)^3) + 63)) \\ 363168 &:= (((8 \times 6) \times ((1 \times 3))!) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 363189 &:= ((9 \times (8! - ((1 - 36)))) - 3!) \\ 363195 &:= (((5 \times 9) \times (1 + 3!)) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 363205 &:= ((5 \times (0! + (2^{3!}))) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 363217 &:= (((7^{1+2}) - 3!) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 363219 &:= (9! + (123 + (6^3))) \\ 363223 &:= (((3 + 2) + 2)^3 + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 363229 &:= (9! + ((-22) + 3!)/(6/3)) \\ 363232 &:= (-2 - ((3!)/(-2)) - (((3 + 6))! - 3!)) \\ 363234 &:= -(((4! - ((3^2))!) + (3! \times (-63))) \\ 363235 &:= (((5! \times 3) - (2 + 3)) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 363238 &:= (((-8 - 3!)/(-2)) + (((3 + 6))! - 3!)) \\ 363246 &:= (((6!/(4 - 2)) + 3!) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 363248 &:= (((-8 + 4!) \times 23) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 363252 &:= (((2 + 5!) + 2) \times 3) + ((6 + 3))! \\ 363255 &:= ((5 \times ((5^2) \times 3)) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 363257 &:= (((-7^{5-2}) + 3!) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 363258 &:= (((8!)/(-5 + 2)) - 3!) \times (-63) \\ 363259 &:= ((9! - 5) + ((2^{3!}) \times ((6 - 3))!)) \\ 363262 &:= (-2 - ((-6 \times (2^{3!})) - ((6 + 3))!)) \\ 363264 &:= (((4^{6/2}) \times 3!) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 363271 &:= ((17 \times 23) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 363276 &:= (((-6 - 72) \times 3!) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 363278 &:= (((8 \times (7^2)) + 3!) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 363279 &:= (9! - ((7 \times ((2 \times 3) - 63))) \\ 363292 &:= ((-2 + 9!) + ((23 \times 6) \times 3)) \\ 363294 &:= ((4! + 9!) - (((2^{3!}) \times (-6)) - 3!)) \\ 363295 &:= ((-5 + 9!) + (((2^{3!}) + 6) \times 3!)) \\ 363296 &:= (((6! + 9!) - (2^{3!})) + (6!/(-3))) \\ 363298 &:= -8 + 9! + 2 \times (-3 + 6^3) \\ 363309 &:= (9! + (((0! + 3))! \times (3 \times 6)) - 3) \\ 363312 &:= ((2 \times (((1 \times 3))!^3)) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 363328 &:= (((8 \times ((2^3))!)/3!) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 363329 &:= (9! + (((2^3)^3) - 63)) \\ 363336 &:= (((6!/3) + ((3 \times 3))!) + ((6^3)) \\ 363339 &:= (9! + ((3!^3) + (((3^6)/3))) \\ 363344 &:= (((-4^4) + ((3 + 3))!) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 363348 &:= (((84 - 3!) \times 3!) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 363349 &:= ((9! + 433) + (6 \times 3!)) \\ 363354 &:= (((4 \times 5!) - 3!) + ((3^{6/3}))! \\ 363355 &:= (((-5! + ((5^3))) + 3!) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 363359 &:= (9! + (((5! \times 3!) - 3) + 6!)/3) \\ 363381 &:= (((1 + 8))! + (((3 \times 3))!/6! - 3)) \\ 363383 &:= (((-3 - (8^3)) - 3!) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 363384 &:= ((4! \times ((8 \times 3) - 3)) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 363386 &:= (((-6 - (8^3)) + ((3^{6/3}))! \\ 363399 &:= 9! + 9^3 + 3! - 6^3 \\ 363408 &:= (8 + 0!)! + 4! + 3! - 6^3 \\ 363409 &:= (((9! + 0!) + 4!) + 3!) - ((6^3)) \\ 363419 &:= ((9! - 1) + ((4! + 3!) \times (6 \times 3))) \\ 363429 &:= (9 \times ((-2 + ((4!/3))!) + 63)) \\ 363432 &:= ((23 \times 4!) + ((3^{6/3}))! \\ 363435 &:= (((-5 - (3!/4)) \times (-3)) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 363438 &:= (((8! + 3!) - 4!) \times (3 + 6)) + 3! \\ 363439 &:= (9! + (343 + (6^3))) \\ 363444 &:= (((4! \times 4!) - (4 \times 3)) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 363445 &:= (-5 + (((4! \times 4!) - 3!) + ((6 + 3))!)) \\ 363448 &:= (((8!/4!) + 4!)/3) + ((6 + 3))! \\ 363449 &:= ((9! - 4) - (((4! \times 3!) - 6!) + 3)) \\ 363453 &:= (-3 + (((5! - 4!) \times 3!) + ((6 + 3))!)) \\ 363455 &:= (((-5 \times (5 + 4!)) + 3!) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 363456 &:= (((6!/5) \times 4) + ((3^{6/3}))! \\ 363459 &:= (((9 - 5))! \times 4!) + 3) + ((6 + 3))! \\ 363462 &:= (((-2 - 6))! \times 4!) + ((3! + ((6 + 3))!)) \\ 363474 &:= (((4! \times (7! + (4!/3))) + 6) \times 3) \\ 363475 &:= (((-5^{7-4}) + 3!) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 363478 &:= (((8 \times 74) + 3!) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 363479 &:= ((9! + (((7 - 4))!)) - ((3! + 6!)/3!)) \\ 363483 &:= (((3 + 8!) + (4^3)) \times (6 + 3)) \\ 363486 &:= (((6!/(-8)) - 4!) + 3!) + ((6 + 3))! \\ 363489 &:= ((9 \times (8! - (4 \times 3))) + (6! - 3)) \\ 363491 &:= (((-1 + 9!) - ((4! - 3!) \times 6)) + 3!) \\ 363495 &:= ((5 \times (((9 - 4))! + 3)) + ((6 + 3))!)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 363496 &:= ((6! + 9!) + ((4 - (36 \times 3))) \\
 363497 &:= (((-7 + 9!) - 4!) + (3 \times (6^3))) \\
 363505 &:= ((5 \times (05^3)) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363509 &:= ((9! - 0!) + (5 \times (3! + (6!/3!)))) \\
 363515 &:= ((-5 \times ((-1 - 5!) - 3!)) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363519 &:= ((9! - 1) + (((5 + 3)!/63)) \\
 363523 &:= (((3^2)! - ((5 - (3 \times (6^3)))) \\
 363528 &:= (((8/2) + 5)! + (3 \times (6^3))) \\
 363533 &:= (((3 \times 3)! + (5 + (3 \times (6^3)))) \\
 363535 &:= ((5 \times (3! + ((5^3)))) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363536 &:= (6! - ((-((3 - 5)^3!) - ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363537 &:= ((-73) - ((5 + 3)!) \times (-6 + 3)) \\
 363539 &:= ((9! + 3!) + (5 + (3 \times (6^3)))) \\
 363542 &:= (((-2 \times (4! + 5)) + 3!!) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363545 &:= ((5^4) + ((5!/3) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363546 &:= ((6! + ((4 + 5)!) - ((3 \times 6) \times 3)) \\
 363549 &:= (9! + (453 + (6^3))) \\
 363552 &:= (((2 \times 5!)/(-5) + 3!!) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363554 &:= (((4 + 5)!) + (((5!/(-3)) + 6!) - 3!)) \\
 363555 &:= ((5 \times (5! + (5 \times 3))) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363557 &:= ((-((7! + 5!)/5!)) + 3!!) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363559 &:= ((9! + 5) + (((5!/(-3)) + 6!) - 3!)) \\
 363573 &:= (3!! - (7 + ((5!/3!) - ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363575 &:= ((-((5^{7-5})) + 3!!) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363576 &:= ((6! - (((7 + 5)/3)!) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363579 &:= (((9! - (((7 + 5)/3)!) + 6!) + 3) \\
 363581 &:= (((1 + 8)! - ((5! - 3!)/6) + 3!!) \\
 363582 &:= ((-((2 - 8) \times (5! - 3)) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363584 &:= -(((4! - 8) - ((5! \times 3!) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363585 &:= ((5!/(-8)) + ((5! \times 3!) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363586 &:= (((6! - 8) + (((5 \times 3) - 6)!) - 3! \\
 363587 &:= (((-7 + (((8 - 5) \times 3)!) + 6!) - 3! \\
 363589 &:= (((9 \times 8!) - (5 + 3)) + 6!) - 3) \\
 363591 &:= (((1 \times 9)!) - (5 \times 3)) + 6! + 3! \\
 363592 &:= (-2 + (((9 \times ((5 + 3)!) + 6!) - 3!)) \\
 363594 &:= (((4! + (95)) \times 3!) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363595 &:= ((-5 + 9!) + (((5 + 3) - 6) \times 3)!) \\
 363596 &:= ((6! + 9!) - ((5 - 3) \times 6/3)) \\
 363597 &:= ((-7 + 9!) - ((5 - ((3 + 6)^3))) \\
 363598 &:= (((8! \times 9) - (5 + 3)) + 6!) + 3! \\
 363612 &:= (((2 + 1) + 6)! + ((3^6) + 3)) \\
 363616 &:= ((6! + (16)) + ((3^{6/3})!) \\
 363618 &:= (((8 + 1)! + (6 + ((3^6) + 3))) \\
 363619 &:= (9! + ((1 + 6) + ((3^6) + 3))) \\
 363624 &:= ((4! + ((2 \times (6 - 3)))!) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363625 &:= (((5^2) + 6!) + ((3^{6/3})!) \\
 363626 &:= ((6! + (26)) + ((3^{6/3})!) \\
 363627 &:= (((7 + 2)! + 6!) + ((3 + 6) \times 3)) \\
 363628 &:= (((8!/2)/6! + 3!!) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363629 &:= (((9! + 2) + 6!) + ((3 + 6) \times 3)) \\
 363636 &:= ((6! + 36) + ((3^{6/3})!) \\
 363642 &:= (((2 \times 4!) + 6!) - 3!) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363646 &:= ((6! + 46) + ((3^{6/3})!) \\
 363648 &:= ((-8 \times (4! - (6!/3!))) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363654 &:= (((4 + 5)!) + 6!) + ((3 \times 6) \times 3)) \\
 363656 &:= ((6! + (56)) + ((3^{6/3})!) \\
 363657 &:= 7 \times 5! - 63 + (6 + 3)! \\
 363659 &:= (9! + (563 + (6^3))) \\
 363664 &:= (((-((4 - 6))^6) + 3!!) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363672 &:= (((2 + 7)! + 6!) + ((3! + 6) \times 3!)) \\
 363676 &:= ((6! + 76) + ((3^{6/3})!) \\
 363686 &:= ((6! + (86)) + ((3^{6/3})!) \\
 363696 &:= ((6! + 96) + ((3^{6/3})!) \\
 363703 &:= (((3!! + 0!)/7) + 3!!) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363708 &:= (8 + 0!)! + 7!/3! - 6 - 3! \\
 363709 &:= ((9! + 0!) + (((7!/3!) - 6) - 3!)) \\
 363713 &:= -(((3! + 1) - ((7!/3!) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363714 &:= (((4 + 1)!) \times 7) - 3!) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363715 &:= (-5 + (((1 \times 7)!) / 3!) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363717 &:= (((7!/(-1 - 7)) - 3) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363718 &:= (((8 + 1)!) + ((7!/3!) - (6/3)) \\
 363719 &:= (9! + (((1 \times 7)!) - 3!)/((6 - 3)!) \\
 363721 &:= (((1 + 2)!) + 7!)/3! + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363723 &:= (((3 + 2)!) \times 7) + 3) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363724 &:= ((-((4 - (2^7))) + 3!!) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363726 &:= (((6^2) + 7!)/3!) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363727 &:= (((7 + 2)!) + (((7! + 3!)/6) + 3!)) \\
 363728 &:= (((8 + ((2 + 7)!) + 3!!) + ((6!/3)!) \\
 363729 &:= ((9! + 2) + (((7! + 3!)/6) + 3!)) \\
 363732 &:= ((2 \times 3!) + ((7!/3!) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363735 &:= (((5! + 3) \times 7) - 3!) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363739 &:= (9! + (((3! + 7!)/3!) + ((6 \times 3)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 363741 &:= ((-1 + (4! \times ((7! + 3!) + 6))) \times 3) \\ 363742 &:= ((-2 + 4!) + ((7!/3!) + ((6 + 3)!))!) \\ 363744 &:= (4! \times (((4! - 7!) - 36) \times (-3))) \\ 363745 &:= (((5! + 4) \times 7) - 3) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 363747 &:= (((7! + 4!) + 7!) \times 36) + 3) \\ 363749 &:= ((9! + 4!) + (((7! - 3!)/6) + 3!)) \\ 363752 &:= (2^5) + ((7!/3!) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 363754 &:= ((((-4 - 5!) \times (-7)) + 3!) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 363755 &:= (((-5 - 5!) \times (-7)) + ((3^{6/3})!)) \\ 363756 &:= ((((-6 - 5!) \times (-7)) - 3!) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 363759 &:= (9! + ((5! \times 7) + ((36 + 3)))) \\ 363762 &:= (((2 + 6!) \times 7) + 3!!) \times 63) \\ 363765 &:= (((5! + 6) \times 7) + 3) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 363768 &:= ((8 \times 6) + ((7!/3!) + ((6 + 3)!))!) \\ 363769 &:= (9! + (673 + (6^3))) \\ 363774 &:= ((4! \times (7 - (7! \times (-3)))) + (6! + 3!)) \\ 363775 &:= (((5! + 7) \times 7) + 3!) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 363789 &:= (9! + (((8 \times ((7 - 3)!)) + 6!) - 3)) \\ 363793 &:= (3!! + (((9! + 73) + (6!/3!)))) \\ 363796 &:= ((6! + 9!) + (7 + (3 \times 63))) \\ 363808 &:= (((-8 + ((0! + 8)!)) + 3!!) + ((6^3))) \\ 363809 &:= (((9! + 0!) - 8) + 3!!) + ((6^3)) \\ 363813 &:= (3!! + (((1 + 8)! - (3 - (6^3)))) \\ 363816 &:= ((6! + ((1 + 8)!)) + (3!^{6-3})) \\ 363825 &:= (((-(5^2) - 8!) \times (-3 + 6)) + 3!!) \\ 363835 &:= (-5 - (((3!! \times 8)/(-3!)) - ((6 + 3)!))!) \\ 363836 &:= (((6! - 3) \times 8)/3!) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 363839 &:= ((9! + 3) + ((8 \times (-3 + 6!))/3!)) \\ 363843 &:= (3!! - (((4! + 8!) + 3) \times (-6 + 3))) \\ 363848 &:= (((8!/4!) + 8) - 3!!) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 363849 &:= ((9 \times ((4! + 8!) + 3)) + (6! + 3!)) \\ 363851 &:= ((((-1 - 5!) \times (-8)) + 3) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 363858 &:= ((8 \times 5!) + (((8! \times 3) + 6) \times 3)) \\ 363859 &:= ((9! - 5) + (8 \times (3 + (6!/3!)))) \\ 363864 &:= (4! + (((6! \times 8)/3!) + ((6 + 3)!))!) \\ 363876 &:= (((-6 \times 7!) - (83)) \times (-6 - 3!)) \\ 363879 &:= (9! + (783 + (6^3))) \\ 363885 &:= (((5! - 8) + 8!) \times (3 + 6)) - 3) \\ 363888 &:= (((-8 + 8!) + ((8 - 3)!)) \times (6 + 3)) \\ 363896 &:= ((6! + 9!) + (((8^3) - (6^3)))) \\ 363897 &:= ((-7 + 9!) + (((8^3) \times 6)/3)) \\ 363898 &:= (-8 - (-9 \times ((8! - 3!) + (6!/3!)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 363899 &:= ((9! + 983) + (6 \times 3!)) \\ 363904 &:= (4! + (((0! + 9)^3) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 363933 &:= (((3 \times 3)! + (9 \times (-3 + (6!/3!)))) \\ 363935 &:= ((5 - 3!!) \times (((9! - 3!)/(-6!)) - (3!))) \\ 363936 &:= (((6!/(-3)) + 9!) - (3! \times (-6^3))) \\ 363937 &:= (((((7^3) + 9!) - 3) + 6!) - 3) \\ 363939 &:= ((9! + 3!) + (9 \times (-3 + (6!/3!)))) \\ 363945 &:= ((-5 \times ((4! \times (-9)) + 3)) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 363951 &:= (((1 - 5!) \times (-9)) + ((3^{6/3})!)) \\ 363952 &:= (-2 + (((5! \times 9) - 3!) + ((6 + 3)!))!) \\ 363954 &:= (((4! \times (5 \times 9)) - 3!) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 363955 &:= (-5 + ((5! \times 9) + ((3^{6/3})!)) \\ 363957 &:= (((7!/5) + 9!) + 3!) + (63) \\ 363958 &:= ((8! + 5!) \times 9 \times 3 - 6)/3 \\ 363959 &:= (((9 \times 5!) + 9!) - (3 - (6/3))) \\ 363984 &:= (((4! \times (-8)) + 9!) - (3! \times (-6^3))) \\ 363986 &:= (((6! + 8) + 9!) - (3! \times (-63))) \\ 363989 &:= (9! + (893 + (6^3))) \\ 363992 &:= (((2^9) + 9!) + 3!!) - ((6!/3!)) \\ 363993 &:= ((-3 + 9!) + (-93) \times (-6 - 3!)) \\ 363996 &:= (((6! + 9!) - ((9 \times 36))) + 3!!) \\ 363999 &:= (9! + (((9!/9)/3!) - 6)/3!) \\ 364032 &:= (((2 \times ((3 + 0!)!) \times 4!) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 364134 &:= (((4! - ((3! + 1)!)/(-4)) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 364135 &:= (-5 - (((3! + 1)!)/(-4)) - ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 364138 &:= (((8 - ((3! + 1)!)/(-4)) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 364139 &:= (9! + (((3! + 1)!/4) - (6/3!)) \\ 364149 &:= (9! + (((4! - 1) \times 4!) + 6!) - 3) \\ 364152 &:= (((2 + 51) \times 4!) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 364164 &:= (4! + (((6 + 1)!/4) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 364168 &:= (-((8 - ((6 \times 1)^4))) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 364169 &:= (((9!/6!) - 1) \times (4 + 6!)) - 3) \\ 364173 &:= (-((3 - ((7 - 1)^4))) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 364176 &:= ((6^{7+1-4}) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\ 364179 &:= (9! + (((7 - 1)^4) + 6) - 3) \\ 364185 &:= (((5! + 8!) + 1) + 4!) \times (6 + 3)) \\ 364239 &:= (9! + ((3 \times 2)^4) + 63) \\ 364269 &:= (9! + ((6/2) \times 463)) \\ 364272 &:= (((2 + 7)! + ((-2 \times 4!) + 6!)) + 3!!) \\ 364279 &:= (((9! + 7) + ((-2 \times 4!) + 6!)) + 3!!) \\ 364288 &:= ((88 \times (2^4)) + ((6 + 3)!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 364294 &:= -(((4! - 9!) - (2 \times ((-4 + 6!) + 3)))) \\ 364295 &:= ((-5 + 9!) + (2 \times ((-4 + 6!) - 3!)) \\ 364296 &:= (((6! + 9!) \times 2) - 4!) - ((6 + 3)!) \\ 364297 &:= ((((-7 + 9!) - ((2^4))) + 6!) + 3!!) \\ 364298 &:= ((-8 + 9!) + (2 \times ((-4 + 6!) - 3))) \\ 364299 &:= ((9! - 9) + (-((2 - 4) \times (6! - 3!))) \\ 364308 &:= (8 + 0!)! + (3! - 4) \times (6! - 3!) \\ 364309 &:= (9! + (((0! - 3) \times (4 - 6!)) - 3)) \\ 364312 &:= ((2 \times (((1 \times 3)!)! - 4)) + ((6 + 3)!) \\ 364314 &:= (((((4! - 1)!) / ((-3 + 4)!) \times 6!) - (3!)) \\ 364316 &:= (((6! \times (-1 - 3)) - 4) + ((6 + 3)!) \\ 364319 &:= ((9! - 1) + (((3 + 4)! - 6!) / 3)) \\ 364332 &:= ((2 \times 3!!) + ((3 \times 4) + ((6 + 3)!) \\ 364333 &:= (3!! + (((3^3) + 4) + ((6 + 3)!) \\ 364338 &:= (8! \times 3 + 3^4 \times 6) \times 3 \\ 364339 &:= (9! + (((3^3) + 4) + 6!) + 3!) \\ 364344 &:= (((4! / 4)!) + 3!!) + (4! + ((6 + 3)!) \\ 364349 &:= ((9! - 43) - (4! \times (-63))) \\ 364353 &:= (-((3! + 5)) \times ((3!! \times (-46)) - 3)) \\ 364356 &:= (6! - ((5! + 3!) \times ((-4 \times 6!) - 3!)) \\ 364357 &:= (-7 \times (5 + ((-3 \times 4!) \times (6! + 3)))) \\ 364359 &:= ((9! + 5!) + ((3!^4) + (63))) \\ 364362 &:= ((2 \times ((6! - 3) + 4!)) + ((6 + 3)!) \\ 364368 &:= (((8! / 6!) + 3!) \times 4!) + ((6 + 3)!) \\ 364374 &:= (((((4! + 7!) - 3) \times 4!) - 6) \times 3) \\ 364379 &:= (((9! - 7) - 3!) - (4! \times (-63))) \\ 364386 &:= (-6 + (((-8 \times 3!) - 4!) \times (-63))) \\ 364389 &:= (((9 \times 8!) - 3) - (4! \times (-63))) \\ 364391 &:= ((-1 + 9!) + (((3 + 4) \times (6^3))) \\ 364392 &:= (((2^9) \times 3) - 4!) + ((6 + 3)!) \\ 364394 &:= (((-4 + 9!) + 3!) - (4! \times (-63))) \\ 364398 &:= (((8! \times 9) + 3!) - (4! \times (-63))) \\ 364409 &:= (((9! - 0!) + ((4^4) \times 6)) - 3!) \\ 364416 &:= ((6 \times ((1 \times 4)^4)) + ((6 + 3)!) \\ 364419 &:= (9! + (((1 \times 4)^4) \times 6) + 3) \\ 364452 &:= (-((2 \times (5 - (4^4)))) \times (6! + 3!)) \\ 364459 &:= ((9! - 5) + ((44 \times 6) \times 3!)) \\ 364496 &:= (((6! \times (-9)) / (-4)) - 4) + ((6 + 3)!) \\ 364518 &:= (((8 + 1)!) + ((546 \times 3)) \\ 364519 &:= (9! + (1 + (546 \times 3))) \\ 364536 &:= ((6! + 3!) + (((5 + 4)!) + ((6^3)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 364539 &:= (9! + ((3 \times (5^4)) - (6^3))) \\ 364547 &:= ((((-7 - 4!) + 5!) \times (4^6)) + 3) \\ 364548 &:= 8! / 4! + (5 + 4)! - 6 - 3! \\ 364589 &:= (9! + ((8 \times (5! + 4)) + (6! - 3))) \\ 364596 &:= ((6! + 9!) + ((5! + 46) \times 3!)) \\ 364599 &:= ((9! - 9) + ((5! - 4!) \times (6 \times 3))) \\ 364608 &:= (((8 + 0!)!) + (((6 - 4) \times 6)^3)) \\ 364609 &:= ((9! + 0!) + (((6 - 4) \times 6)^3)) \\ 364679 &:= (9! + (7 \times (6! - (463)))) \\ 364743 &:= (3 \times ((((-4 + 7!) \times 4!) + 6!) - 3)) \\ 364746 &:= (-6 + (((4 - 7!) \times 4!) - 6!) \times (-3)) \\ 364776 &:= (6! + (((7 \times 7) \times 4!) + ((6 + 3)!) \\ 364779 &:= (9! + (((7 \times 7) \times 4!) + 6!) + 3)) \\ 364785 &:= 3 \times (6! + 4! \times 7! - 85) \\ 364791 &:= ((-1 + 9!) + (((7! - 4!) + 6!) / 3)) \\ 364793 &:= -((((3! - 9!) + (7^4)) - (6! \times 3!)) \\ 364794 &:= (4! - (((-9 \times 7!) / 4!) - ((6 + 3)!) \\ 364795 &:= ((-5 + 9!) + ((7! \times 4!) / 63)) \\ 364799 &:= ((9! - 9) + (((7! + 4!) + 6!) / 3)) \\ 364833 &:= (3 \times ((3 \times (8! - 4!)) + (6! + 3))) \\ 364859 &:= ((9! - 5) + (8 \times ((4! + 6!) / 3)) \\ 364893 &:= ((-3 + 9!) + (((8 \times 4) \times 63))) \\ 364896 &:= (6! + (9 \times (8! + (4! \times ((6 - 3)!)))) \\ 364899 &:= (9! + (((9! \times (8 - 4)) / 6!) + 3)) \\ 364902 &:= (((2 + 0!)!) + ((9! \times (4 + 6!)) / 3!)) \\ 364903 &:= (((3! + 0!)!) + (9! \times (4 + 6!)) / 3!)) \\ 364915 &:= -((((5! + 1) - 9!) + 4) - (6! \times 3)) \\ 364916 &:= -((((6 - 1)!) - 9!) + 4) - (6! \times 3)) \\ 364919 &:= (((9! - 1) - ((9 - 4)!) + (6! \times 3)) \\ 364924 &:= (((4 \times (2^9)) - 4) + ((6 + 3)!) \\ 364926 &:= ((62 \times (9 + 4!)) + ((6 + 3)!) \\ 364929 &:= (9! + (((2^9) \times 4!) + 6) / 3!) \\ 364932 &:= -((((2 + 3)!) - 9!) - ((-4 - 6!) \times (-3))) \\ 364935 &:= -((((5! - 3) - 9!) - ((-4 - 6!) \times (-3))) \\ 364942 &:= (((-2 - 4!) + 9!) + ((4! - 6!) \times (-3)) \\ 364944 &:= ((4! \times (-4 + (9! / 4!))) + (6! \times 3)) \\ 364945 &:= (((5^4) + 9!) - ((4 - 6) \times 3!)) \\ 364953 &:= ((-((3 \times 5)) + 9!) + ((4! - 6!) \times (-3)) \\ 364959 &:= ((9! - 5!) + (((9 + 4) + 6!) \times 3)) \\ 364961 &:= ((-((1 + 6)) + 9!) + ((4! - 6!) \times (-3)) \\ 364964 &:= (((4! / (-6)) + 9!) + ((4! - 6!) \times (-3)) \\ 364967 &:= ((-((7 - 6)) + 9!) + ((4! - 6!) \times (-3)) \end{aligned}$$

- 364968** := (((8! × (6 - 9)) + 4!) - 6!) × (-3))
364973 := (((3⁷) - 94) + ((6 + 3)!))
364974 := (-(4 - 7))! + ((9! + ((4! - 6!) × (-3))))
364984 := (((4! - 8) + 9!) + ((4! - 6!) × (-3)))
364986 := (((6 - 8!) × (-9)) - (-4 × 6!)) - 3!!
364988 := (-(8 × 8) + 9!) + ((-4 - 6!) × (-3))
364995 := (((-((5 × 9)) + 9!) - (-4 × 6!)) - 3!!)
364997 := (((-7 + 9!) - (9 × 4)) + (6! × 3))
365019 := (9! + (((-1 - 0!) - 5) + 6!) × 3)
365025 := (((5 × 2) - 0!)! + ((5 - 6!) × (-3)))
365029 := ((9! - ((2 + 0!)!)) + (-5 + (6! × 3)))
365035 := (((5 + 3) + 0!)! + (-5 + (6! × 3)))
365036 := (((6! × 3) + 0!) - 5) + ((6 + 3)!)
365039 := ((9! - ((3 × 0)!)) + (5! × (6 × 3)))
365054 := (((4 + 5)! - 0!) + ((-5 - 6!) × (-3)))
365055 := (((5 + 5) - 0!)! + ((-5 - 6!) × (-3)))
365059 := (((9! + 5) - 0!) + ((-5 - 6!) × (-3)))
365073 := (((3⁷) + 0!) + 5) + ((6 + 3)!)
365079 := (9! + (((7 + 0!) + 5) + 6!) × 3)
365109 := (9! + (((-0!) + (-((1 - 5)))!)) + 6!) × 3))
365159 := (((9! + 5!) - 1) + (5! × (6 × 3)))
365163 := ((3 × (6! + 1)) + (5! + ((6 + 3)!))
365184 := (((4! + ((8 + 1)!)) + 5!) + (6! × 3))
365259 := (9! + (((5!²) - 5!) - 6)/3!))
365275 := (-5 - (((7! / (-2)) + 5!) - ((6 + 3)!))
365279 := (((9! + (((7 - 2)⁵))) - 6!) - 3!))
365334 := ((43 × ((3!⁵) + 6!)) + 3!))
365337 := (((7 × 3) × (-3 + 5!)) + ((6 + 3)!))
365379 := (9! + (((7! × 3) - 5!) - 6)/3!))
365382 := (((((2 - 8!) × 3) - 5!) - 6!) × (-3))
365384 := ((4! + ((8³) × (-5 + 6!))) - 3!!)
365385 := ((5 + (((8! × (-3)) - 5!) - 6!)) × (-3))
365389 := ((9! - (8 + 3)) - ((5! + 6!) × (-3)))
365391 := (((1 × 9)! + (((3 - 5!) - 6!) × (-3)))
365392 := (((-2 + 9!) - 3!) - ((5! + 6!) × (-3)))
365393 := (-3!) - (((-9!) × (3!! + 5)) + 6!)/3!!))
365394 := -(((4! - 9!) - (((3! + 5!) + 6!) × 3)))
365395 := (-5 + (((9!/3) + 5!) + 6!) × 3))
365396 := (((6! - (9! × (3!! + 5)))/(-6!)) - 3)
365397 := (((7! + 9!) - 3) + ((5! + 6!) × (-3)))
365398 := (((-8 + 9!) + 3!) - ((5! + 6!) × (-3)))
365399 := (((9! × ((9 - 3)! + 5)) - 6!)/3!!)
365407 := (7 × (0! + (4! × ((-5 - 6!) × (-3))))))
365409 := (9! - (((0! - 4) - 5!) - 6!) × 3))
365456 := (((6! × 5) - (4⁵)) + ((6 + 3)!))
365462 := ((2 × ((6⁴) - 5)) + ((6 + 3)!))
365472 := (((2 + 7)! + ((4! + 5!) × (6 × 3)))
365479 := (9! + (((-7 - 4!) + (5⁶))/3!))
365496 := -(((6! - 9!) - (4 × ((5! + 6!) - 3!))))
365499 := (9! + (((9 + 4!) + 5!) + 6!) × 3))
365519 := (((9! - 1) + 5!) - ((5! + 6!) × (-3)))
365544 := ((4! × (-4 + 5!)) - (5! - ((6 + 3)!))
365549 := (9! + ((4! × 5!) + (5 - (6³))))
365568 := (-8 × (((6! + 5!) + 5!) - (6³)))
365575 := (-5 × (7! + (-5 × ((5⁶) + 3!))))
365616 := ((6¹⁺⁶) + (5! × (6! - 3!)))
365617 := -7! + 1 + 6⁵ + (6 + 3)!
365634 := ((4 × 3!!) + ((-6 - 5!) + ((6 + 3)!))
365664 := ((-4 × (-6 - 6!)) - (5! - ((6 + 3)!))
365679 := ((9! - 7!) + (((6⁵) + 63)))
365689 := (9! + (((8 × 6) + 5)^{6/3}))
365739 := (((9! - 3!) + 7!) - ((-5 - 6!) × (-3)))
365744 := (-4 - (-4 × (((7 + 5!) × 6!) - 3))
365745 := (((5 + 4)! + 7!) - ((-5 - 6!) × (-3)))
365747 := (-7 - ((-4 × ((7 + 5!) × 6!)) + 3!))
365748 := ((8 - 4) × (((7 + 5!) × 6!) - 3))
365749 := (((9! + 4) + 7!) - ((-5 - 6!) × (-3)))
365754 := ((4! × ((5! + 7) × 5!)) - ((6 - 3)!))
365755 := ((5 × 575) + ((6 + 3)!))
365764 := (-4 × ((6! × (-7 - 5!)) - (6/3!)))
365769 := ((9 × (6! - 7)) × (5! - (63)))
365784 := (-((4 - 8) × (((7 + 5!) × 6!) + 3!))
365796 := (((6 × 9)⁷⁻⁵) + ((6 + 3)!))
365799 := (9! + (((9! - 7!)/5!) - (63)))
365808 := (((8 + 0!)! + (((8! / (-5)) - 6!) / (-3)))
365809 := ((9! + 0!) + (((8! / (-5)) - 6!) / (-3)))
365838 := (((8³) - ((8 - 5)!)) × (6! + 3))
365845 := (((5! × 4!) + (85)) + ((6 + 3)!))
365859 := (9 × ((5! + 8!) - (5 - (6³))))
365888 := (-((8 × 8) × ((8 × (5 - 6!)) + 3))
365897 := (-7 + (((9 × 8!)/5!) + ((6 + 3)!))
365902 := (-2 + (((09!)/5!) + ((6 + 3)!))
365903 := -(((3 × 0)! - ((9!/5!) + ((6 + 3)!)))

$$\begin{aligned} 365904 &:= (((((4 \times 0) + 9))! / 5!) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 365905 &:= (((5! + (09))! / 5!) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 365909 &:= ((9! - 0!) + ((9! / 5!) + ((6 - 3))!) \\ 365928 &:= (((8/2))! + ((9! / 5!) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 365934 &:= ((4! + 3!) + ((9! / 5!) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 365938 &:= ((-((8^3)) + 9!) - (-5 \times (6! - 3!))) \\ 365943 &:= ((3!! \times 4) + (((9! + 5!) + (63)))) \\ 365955 &:= (((5^5) + 9!) - (56)) + 3! \\ 365979 &:= (9! + ((7 + (9 \times (5! - 6))) \times 3)) \\ 365985 &:= (((5! \times 8) + 9!) + ((5 - 6!) \times (-3))) \\ 366005 &:= 5^{-00!+6} + (6 + 3)! \\ 366288 &:= 8 \times 8^2 \times (6! - 6) + 3!! \\ 366336 &:= (((6^3!) \times 3!) + ((6! \times 6!) / 3!)) \\ 366345 &:= ((-5 \times ((4! + 3) - 6!)) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 366359 &:= (9! + ((5 \times 3!!) - ((6! + 6) / 3!))) \\ 366375 &:= ((-5 \times ((7 \times 3) - 6!)) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 366387 &:= (-((7 - ((8^3) + 6))) \times (6! - 3)) \\ 366448 &:= ((8 \times 446) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 366455 &:= ((-5 \times ((5! / 4!) - 6!)) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 366456 &:= (((6! \times 5) - 4!) + (((6 + 6) - 3))!) \\ 366459 &:= (9! + (((5! + 4) - 6!) \times (-6)) + 3) \\ 366464 &:= (((4 - 6!) \times (-4)) + 6!) + ((6 + 3))! \\ 366473 &:= (3!! - (7 + ((-4 \times 6!) - ((6 + 3))!))) \\ 366474 &:= -((((4! + 7!) / 4!) - 6!) \times 6!) + 3! \\ 366475 &:= ((-5 - (((7! / 4!) - 6!) \times 6!)) - 3!!) \\ 366496 &:= -((((6! - 9!) - (4^6)) + (6! / (-3))) \\ 366497 &:= ((((-7 + 9!) + 4!) - 6!) + (6! \times 3!)) \\ 366504 &:= (4! + ((05 \times 6!) + ((6 + 3))!)) \\ 366505 &:= ((-5 \times ((0 - 5) - 6!)) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 366509 &:= ((9! - 0!) + (5 \times (6! + ((6 - 3))!)) \\ 366525 &:= ((5 \times (-((2 - 5)^6)) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 366528 &:= (8 \times (((2 + 5))! / (-6)) + (6^3!)) \\ 366535 &:= ((5 \times ((3! + 5) + 6!)) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 366549 &:= ((9! + 4!) + (-5 \times ((-6 - 6!) - 3)) \\ 366576 &:= (((6^7) + (5! \times 6!)) - (6! / (-3))) \\ 366592 &:= ((2^9) \times ((5 + 6!) - (6 + 3))) \\ 366594 &:= ((4! + 9!) + (5 \times (6! + ((6 \times 3)))) \\ 366595 &:= (((5! + 9!) - 5) - 6!) + (6! \times 3!) \\ 366624 &:= ((4! \times (26 \times 6)) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 366678 &:= (((-87) + 6!) \times 6) + ((6 + 3))! \\ 366696 &:= -((((6! - 9!) + ((6! \times (-6)) - ((6^3)))) \\ 366699 &:= ((9! - (9! / 6!)) + ((6! \times 6) + 3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 366725 &:= (((5^{-2+7}) + 6!) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 366768 &:= ((8! \times 6) - ((7! - (6^6)) \times 3)) \\ 366786 &:= ((-6 - (8 \times (7 + 6!))) \times (-63)) \\ 366795 &:= ((-5 \times (-((9 \times 7) - 6!)) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 366859 &:= ((9! - 5) - (((8! / 6!) - 6!) \times 3!)) \\ 366894 &:= -((4! + (((9! \times (-8 - 6!)) / 6!) - 3!))) \\ 366898 &:= (-8 + (((9! \times (8 + 6!)) / 6!) - 3!)) \\ 366909 &:= -((((9! \times ((0! - 9) - 6!)) / 6!) + 3) \\ 366918 &:= (((8! / (1 + 9)) + 6) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 366928 &:= ((8 \times ((2^9) - 6)) + ((6 + 3))!) \\ 366934 &:= (((4^3!) + 9!) - (6 \times 6)) - 3! \\ 366944 &:= (-((4^4)) - (((9! / (-6)) - 6!) \times 3!)) \\ 366948 &:= (8! - 4!) \times 9 + (6! - 6) \times 3! \\ 366964 &:= (((4^6) + 9!) - ((6 \times 6) / 3)) \\ 366966 &:= (((6! \times 6) + 9!) + 6) + (6! / (-3)) \\ 366976 &:= (((6 + 7) - 9)^6) + ((6 + 3))! \\ 366977 &:= (((7! - 7) + 9!) - 6!) - ((6^3)) \\ 366978 &:= (8! + (((7 \times (9 + (6^6))) + 3))) \\ 366979 &:= (9! + (((7 - 9) + 6)^6) + 3) \\ 366984 &:= (((4! - 8!) \times (-9)) / 6) + 6! \times 3! \\ 366992 &:= (((2^9) + 9!) - 6!) + (6! \times 3!) \\ 367079 &:= ((9! + 7!) - (((07)! + 6) / 3!)) \\ 367104 &:= ((4 \times ((0! + 1)^7)) \times (6! - 3)) \\ 367117 &:= ((7! - 11) \times (76 - 3)) \\ 367159 &:= ((9! - 5) + (((1 - 7) + 6!) \times 3!)) \\ 367179 &:= (9! + (((717 \times 6) - 3))) \\ 367189 &:= (((9! - 8) + ((1 \times 7))! - 6!) - 3) \\ 367191 &:= (((-1 + 9!) - (1 + 7)) + (6! \times 3!)) \\ 367192 &:= (((-2 + 9!) + ((1 \times 7))! - 6!) - 3! \\ 367195 &:= (-5 + (((9! / (-1 - 7)) + 6!) \times 3!)) \\ 367198 &:= (((-8 + 9!) + ((1 \times 7))! - 6!) + 3! \\ 367199 &:= ((9! - ((9 - 1) - 7)) + (6! \times 3!)) \\ 367212 &:= ((2 - ((-12) \times 7!) - 6!) \times 3! \\ 367219 &:= ((9! + (12 + 7)) + (6! \times 3!)) \\ 367225 &:= (((5^2) + ((2 + 7))!) + (6! \times 3!)) \\ 367227 &:= (((7 + 2))! + (27)) + (6! \times 3!)) \\ 367229 &:= ((9! + (2 + 27)) + (6! \times 3!)) \\ 367236 &:= (-6 \times (((3! \times (-2)) \times 7!) - 6!) - 3!)) \\ 367239 &:= (9! + (((3!^2) + 7!) - 6!) + 3) \\ 367248 &:= ((8 - (((4! / (-2)) \times 7!) - 6!)) \times 3! \\ 367249 &:= ((9! + (42 + 7)) + (6! \times 3!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 367254 &:= (((4+5))! - ((-(2+7)) - 6!) \times 3!) \\ 367259 &:= ((9! + 5) - ((-(2+7)) - 6!) \times 3!) \\ 367269 &:= ((9! + ((62+7))) + (6! \times 3!)) \\ 367279 &:= ((9! + ((72+7))) + (6! \times 3!)) \\ 367284 &:= (((((4^8) - 2) - 7!) + 6!) \times 3!) \\ 367289 &:= ((9! + ((82+7))) + (6! \times 3!)) \\ 367319 &:= ((9! - 1) - ((-(37) \times 6!)/3!)) \\ 367344 &:= (((4! \times (-4)) \times 3!) + 7!) + ((6+3)!) \\ 367359 &:= (((9! + 5!) - 3) - ((-7 - 6!) \times 3!)) \\ 367384 &:= -((((4! + (8^3)) - 7!) - ((6+3)!)) \\ 367389 &:= ((9 \times (8! + ((3 \times 7)))) + (6! \times 3!)) \\ 367408 &:= -8^{-0!+4} + 7! + (6+3)! \\ 367413 &:= (3 \times (-1 + (4! \times (7! + (63)))))) \\ 367449 &:= ((9! + (((4^4) - 7))) + (6! \times 3!)) \\ 367476 &:= ((-(6 \times 74) + 7!) + ((6+3)!) \\ 367479 &:= (((97 - 4!) \times (7! - 6)) - 3) \\ 367484 &:= (-4 + (8 \times (((-(4-7))!)^6) - 3!))) \\ 367488 &:= -((8 \times 8) \times (((4! - 7!) - 6!) - 3!)) \\ 367497 &:= ((7! + 9!) - (47 \times (6+3))) \\ 367537 &:= ((-73) \times (5 - 7!)) - (6 \times 3) \\ 367539 &:= ((9! - 3) - ((-57) - 6!) \times 3!) \\ 367544 &:= (((-(4^4)) - 5!) + 7!) + ((6+3)!) \\ 367582 &:= (-2 - (((8!/5!) - 7!) - ((6+3)!) \\ 367584 &:= (4 \times (((8! - 5!) + 7!) + (6^3))) \\ 367585 &:= (((5! - 8!)/5!) + 7!) + ((6+3)!) \\ 367632 &:= (((2 \times 3!) \times (6+7!)) + 6!) \times 3! \\ 367638 &:= (8! - (((3!^6) \times (-7)) - 6!) - 3!) \\ 367675 &:= (((-(5 \times 7) + 6!) \times 7) + ((6+3)!) \\ 367679 &:= (((9! + 7!) + ((6-7))) + (6!/(-3))) \\ 367694 &:= -4 + 9! - 6 + 7! - 6^3 \\ 367697 &:= ((-7 + 9!) - ((6! \times (-7)) + ((6^3)))) \\ 367698 &:= 8! \times 9 - 6 + 7! - 6^3 \\ 367729 &:= (9! - (2 - (77 \times 63))) \\ 367735 &:= ((-(5 \times 37) + 7!) + ((6+3)!) \\ 367746 &:= (-6 + (((4! \times (-7) + 7!) + ((6+3)!) \\ 367749 &:= (9! + (((4! \times (-7) + 7!) - (6-3))) \\ 367773 &:= ((-(((3 \times 7) \times 7)) + 7!) + ((6+3)!) \\ 367774 &:= (-((4-77) \times (7! - (6/3))) \\ 367792 &:= -2 + 9! + 7! - 7 \times 6 \times 3 \\ 367793 &:= (((3! \times ((9! + 7!) - 7)) - 6!)/3!) \\ 367795 &:= (((-5 + 9!) + 7!) - ((7 - (6/3)))! \\ 367797 &:= ((7! + 9!) - ((7!/(7 \times 6)) + 3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 367824 &:= (((4!/2) \times (-8) + 7!) + ((6+3)!) \\ 367855 &:= ((-(5 \times (5+8))) + 7!) + ((6+3)!) \\ 367862 &:= (-2 + (((6! - 8) \times 7) + ((6+3)!) \\ 367864 &:= ((-(4 \times (6+8))) + 7!) + ((6+3)!) \\ 367866 &:= ((-(6 + (6 \times 8))) + 7!) + ((6+3)!) \\ 367869 &:= (((9! - ((6 \times 8))) + 7!) - (6-3)) \\ 367872 &:= (((2+7))! + ((-8 - (7!/(-6))) \times 3!)) \\ 367878 &:= (((8-7) + 8)! + (7 \times (6! - 3!))) \\ 367879 &:= ((9! + 7!) + ((8 - (7^{6/3}))) \\ 367891 &:= ((((-1 + 9!) + 8) + 7!) - (6 \times 3!)) \\ 367892 &:= ((((-2 + 9!) - 8) + 7!) - ((6 \times 3))) \\ 367893 &:= ((((-3 \times 9!)/8!) + 7!) + ((6+3)!) \\ 367894 &:= (((4! + 9!) - 8) + (7 \times (6! - 3!))) \\ 367896 &:= (((6-9) \times 8) + 7!) + ((6+3)!) \\ 367899 &:= (9! - (((9!/8!) - 7!) + 6) + 3!) \\ 367903 &:= (3 \times 0)! + 9! + 7! - 6 \times 3 \\ 367921 &:= (((1^2 9) + 7!) + ((6+3)!) \\ 367923 &:= (((3^2) + 9!) + 7!) - ((6-3)!) \\ 367925 &:= (((5+2))! + 9!) + (7 - (6/3)) \\ 367926 &:= (((((6 \times 2) - 9))! + 7!) + ((6+3)!) \\ 367927 &:= (((7! - 2) + 9!) + (7 + (6/3))) \\ 367928 &:= (((-(8+2) + 9!) + 7!) + ((6 \times 3))) \\ 367929 &:= (((9-2))! + 9!) + (7 + (6/3)) \\ 367932 &:= ((-(2 \times (3-9))) + 7!) + ((6+3)!) \\ 367933 &:= (((((3/3) + 9!) + 7!) + 6) + 3!) \\ 367934 &:= (((4+3))! + 9!) + ((7 \times 6)/3) \\ 367935 &:= (((((5 \times 3) + 9!) + 7!) - 6) + 3!) \\ 367936 &:= (((-(6/3) + 9!) + 7!) + ((6 \times 3))) \\ 367937 &:= (((7! + 3) + 9!) + ((7 \times 6)/3)) \\ 367938 &:= (((8! + 3) \times 9) + 7!) - (6+3) \\ 367941 &:= (((-(1-4) + 9!) + 7!) + ((6 \times 3))) \\ 367942 &:= (((2^4) + 9!) + 7!) + ((6-3)!) \\ 367943 &:= ((((-3 + 4!) + 9!) + 7!) + (6/3)) \\ 367944 &:= ((4! + ((49/7))!) + ((6+3)!) \\ 367945 &:= ((-(5 \times (4-9))) + 7!) + ((6+3)!) \\ 367946 &:= (((6 \times 4) + 9!) + 7!) + (6/3) \\ 367947 &:= (((7! + 4!) + 9!) + ((7-6) \times 3)) \\ 367948 &:= ((-(8 - (4 \times 9))) + 7!) + ((6+3)!) \\ 367949 &:= ((9! - (4+9)) + (7 \times (6! + 3!))) \\ 367951 &:= (((-(1 \times 5) + 9!) + 7!) + (6 \times 3!)) \\ 367952 &:= (((((2^5) + 9!) + 7!) + 6) - 3!) \\ 367953 &:= (((3 \times 5) + 9!) + 7!) + ((6 \times 3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 367954 &:= (4 - ((-5 + ((9! + 7!)/(-6))) \times 3!)) \\
 367955 &:= (((-((5/5)) + 9!) + 7!) + (6 \times 3!)) \\
 367956 &:= (((6 \times 5) + 9!) + 7!) + ((6 - 3!)) \\
 367957 &:= (((7 \times 5) + 9!) + 7!) + (6/3) \\
 367958 &:= (((8 \times 5) + 9!) + 7!) - (6/3) \\
 367959 &:= (((9! + (5 \times 9)) + 7!) - ((6 - 3)!)) \\
 367961 &:= (((-1 + 6!) + 9!) - ((-7 - 6!) \times 3!)) \\
 367962 &:= (((2 + 6)!) \times 9) + (7 \times (6! + 3!)) \\
 367964 &:= (((46 + 9!) + 7!) - (6/3)) \\
 367967 &:= ((7! + ((6 \times 9) - 7)) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\
 367968 &:= (((8! + 6) \times 9) + 7!) - ((6 - 3)!)) \\
 367974 &:= -((((4! - 7!) - 9!) - ((7 + 6) \times 3!)) \\
 367975 &:= (((57 + 9!) + 7!) - (6/3)) \\
 367976 &:= (((6! \times 7) + 9!) - ((7 - 63))) \\
 367978 &:= (((8 \times 7) + 9!) + 7!) + (6/3) \\
 367983 &:= (((3^8)/9) \times 7) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\
 367986 &:= ((-((6 - (8 \times 9))) + 7!) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\
 367989 &:= (((9! + (8 \times 9)) + 7!) - (6 - 3)) \\
 367992 &:= ((-((2 - 9)))! + (((9!/7!) + ((6 + 3)!))) \\
 367995 &:= (((-((5 \times 9)) + 9!) + 7!) + (6!/3!)) \\
 367997 &:= (((79 + 9!) + 7!) - (6/3)) \\
 367998 &:= (((8 \times 9) + 9!) + 7!) + ((6 - 3)!)) \\
 367999 &:= (((9! + ((9 \times 9))) + 7!) - (6/3)) \\
 368037 &:= (((7! - 3) + ((0! + 8)!)) + ((6!/3!)) \\
 368064 &:= (4 \times (((6 + 0)!) + ((8! + (6^3)))) \\
 368067 &:= ((-((7^6)) + ((0! - 8) \times 6!)) \times (-3)) \\
 368128 &:= (((8 - 2)!) - 1) \times (8^{6-3}) \\
 368136 &:= (((6^3) + (-((1 - 8)!)) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\
 368139 &:= (((9! + 3) + (-((1 - 8)!)) + ((6^3)) \\
 368157 &:= -(((7! + (51)) - (8 \times (6^3)))) \\
 368179 &:= ((9! + 7!) + ((1 + (86 \times 3)))) \\
 368184 &:= -(((4! + ((8 - 1)!) - (8 \times (6^3)))) \\
 368206 &:= -((((6 + 0)!) - (-2 + (8 \times (6^3)))) \\
 368207 &:= -(((7! + ((0 \times 2)!) - (8 \times (6^3)))) \\
 368208 &:= -((((8 - ((0 \times 2)!)! - (8 \times (6^3)))) \\
 368259 &:= ((-9 \times (((5! + 2) - 8!) - 6!)) - 3) \\
 368316 &:= (61386 \times 3!) \\
 368349 &:= (9! + ((4! \times (38 \times 6)) - 3)) \\
 368368 &:= ((-8 - 6!) \times (3! - (8^{6-3}))) \\
 368384 &:= (((-((4 \times 8)) + 3!) \times 8) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\
 368392 &:= (((2^9) \times 3!) - (8 - (6!/(-3))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 368395 &:= ((-5 + 9!) + ((3!! \times 8) + (6!/(-3)))) \\
 368432 &:= ((((-2 + 3!) - 4!) \times 8) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\
 368439 &:= (9! + (((3!! - 4!) \times 8) - (6 + 3))) \\
 368448 &:= ((8 \times 4) \times (((4! - 8) \times 6!) - 3!)) \\
 368496 &:= ((6! + (9 \times (4! + (8!/6)))) \times 3!) \\
 368505 &:= (((5^{-0!+5}) + 8!) \times (6 + 3)) \\
 368519 &:= (((9! - 1) - 5!) + (8 \times (((6 - 3)!))) \\
 368523 &:= (((3^2)!) - 5!) + ((8 \times 6!) + 3) \\
 368544 &:= (((-((4^4)) \times 5!) + 8) \times (-6 - 3!)) \\
 368555 &:= (-55) \times (((5! - 8!) - 6)/3!) \\
 368568 &:= (8 \times (((6! \times 5!) - 8!) - (6 + 3))) \\
 368569 &:= ((9! - 65) + ((8 \times 6!) - 3!)) \\
 368584 &:= (-4 \times (8 - (((5! + 8) \times 6!) - 3!)) \\
 368589 &:= (9! + ((((-8 \times 5!) + 8) \times (-6)) - 3)) \\
 368592 &:= (((2^9) \times 5!) - 8) \times ((6 - 3)!)) \\
 368593 &:= (((3! + 9!) - 5) - (-8 \times (6! - 3!))) \\
 368597 &:= (((7! + 9!) - (5 \times 8)) + 6!) - 3) \\
 368609 &:= (((9! - 0!) - 6) - (-8 \times (6! - 3!)) \\
 368622 &:= (-2 + (((2 - 6!) \times (-8)) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\
 368624 &:= (((-((4 - 2)) + 6!) \times 8) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\
 368627 &:= (-7 - ((-((2^6) \times 8)) \times 6!) + 3!)) \\
 368628 &:= 8^2 \times 6! \times 8 - 6 - 3! \\
 368629 &:= -((9 + 2) + (6! \times (8^{6-3}))) \\
 368632 &:= (((2^3) \times 6!) - 8) + ((6 + 3)!)) \\
 368634 &:= (((-((4^3)) \times 6!) \times (-8)) - ((6 - 3)!)) \\
 368635 &:= ((-5 - 3!) + ((6! + 8!) \times (6 + 3))) \\
 368637 &:= (((((7 - 3)^6)/8) \times 6!) - 3) \\
 368638 &:= (((8^3) \times 6!) - 8) + ((6 - 3)!)) \\
 368639 &:= (9! + (((3! \times 6!) \times 8) - 6)/3!) \\
 368643 &:= (3! - 4)^6 \times 8 \times 6! + 3 \\
 368658 &:= ((8 \times ((5! \times 6!) - 8!)) + (6 \times 3)) \\
 368664 &:= (4! - (6! \times (-(((6 \times 8)/6^3)))) \\
 368675 &:= ((5 \times 7) + (6! \times (8^{6-3}))) \\
 368676 &:= (((6! - 76) + 8!) \times (6 + 3)) \\
 368679 &:= ((9! + (7 \times 6)) + ((8 \times 6!) - 3)) \\
 368688 &:= (8 \times (((8 \times 6!) \times 8) + ((6 - 3)!)) \\
 368692 &:= (((-2 + 9!) + 6) - (-8 \times (6! + 3!))) \\
 368694 &:= (((4! + 9!) + 6) - (-8 \times (6! + 3))) \\
 368697 &:= (7! - ((9 \times (-6 - 8!)) - (6! + 3))) \\
 368739 &:= (((93 \times 7) + 8!) \times (6 + 3)) \\
 368754 &:= (((4 + 5)!) - (((7! - 8!)/6) + 3!))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 368759 := ((9! + 5) - (((7! - 8!)/6) + 3!))
368763 := (((3 + 6))! - (((7! - 8!)/6) - 3))
368769 := ((9! + 6) - (((7! - 8!)/6) - 3))
368793 := (3 × (((-(9 × 7)) + 8!) + 6!) × 3))
368799 := ((9 × (((-(9 × 7)) + 8!) + 6!)) + 3!)
368832 := ((2^{3!}) × (((8!/8) + 6!) + 3))
368856 := (((6! × 5!) - 8!) × 8) + ((6³)))
368869 := (((9! - 6!) - 8) + ((8!/6) - 3))
368872 := (((((2 + 7))! - 8) + (8!/6)) - 3!!)
368879 := (((9! + ((7 - 8))) + (8!/6)) - 3!!)
368904 := (((4! + (09)!) + (8!/6)) - 3!!)
368937 := (((-7!) + 3!!) + (9 + (8 × (6^{3!}))))
368944 := (((4⁴) + 9!) - (-8 × (6! + 3!)))
368976 := (((6! + 7!) + 9!) + ((8!/6!) × 3!))
369024 := ((4! × (2^{-0!+9})) + ((6 + 3))!)
369075 := (57 × (0! - ((-9 × 6!) + 3!)))
369096 := (((6! + 9) - 0!) × ((9!/6!) + 3))
369144 := (((-4!) + (((4 - 1))!)) × 9) + ((6 + 3))!
369168 := (8! - 6) × (-1 + 9) + 6^{3!}
369184 := (((4 - 8!) × (1 - 9)) + (6^{3!}))
369189 := (9 × ((8! - (19)) + (((6 - 3))!))!)
369216 := -((((((6 × 1) + 2))! - 9!) - (6^{3!})))
369218 := (((((8! × (-1)) + 2) + 9!) + (6^{3!})))
369235 := (((-(5³)) + ((2⁹) × 6!)) + 3!!)
369248 := (((8⁴)/2) + 9!) + (6! × 3!))
369279 := (9! + ((7 + 2) × (-9 + (((6 - 3))!))!))
369288 := (((-8 + ((8 - 2))!) × 9) + ((6 + 3))!)
369297 := (((-7 + 9!) - 2) + (9 × (6! - 3!)))
369299 := ((9! - (9 - 2)) + (9 × (6! - 3!)))
369306 := (((6! - (03)!) × 9) + ((6 + 3))!)
369309 := ((9! + 03) + (9 × (6! - 3!)))
369315 := (((-5 + (((1 × 3))!)) × 9) + ((6 + 3))!)
369319 := ((9! + 13) + (9 × (6! - 3!)))
369324 := (((-4 + ((2 × 3))!) × 9) + ((6 + 3))!)
369327 := (((((7 + 2))! - 3!) + (9 × (6! - 3!)))
369329 := (((9! + 2) - 3!) + (9 × (6! - 3!)))
369333 := (((-3 + ((3 + 3))!) × 9) + ((6 + 3))!)
369336 := (((((6 + 3))! + 3) + (9 × (6! - 3!)))
369339 := ((9! - (3 × 3!)) - ((-9 × 6!) + 3))
369342 := (((((2 × 4))! + 3!!) × 9) - (6 × 3))
369344 := (((4 × 4)) + ((3!! × 9) + ((6 + 3))!))
369348 := (((8 + 4)) + ((3!! × 9) + ((6 + 3))!))
369349 := ((9! - (4!/3)) - ((-9 × 6!) + 3))
369351 := (((-1 + (5! × 3!)) × 9) + ((6 + 3))!)
369354 := (((((4 + 53) × 9) × 6!) - 3!))
369355 := (-5 - (((5! × 3!) × (-9)) - ((6 + 3))!))
369357 := (7! + (((5! × 3!) + 9!) + 6!) - 3))
369358 := (((8! + (5! × 3!)) × 9) - (6/3))
369359 := ((9! + (5 - 3)) - ((-9 × 6!) + 3))
369369 := (((9 × 6!) + 3) + 9!) + ((6 - 3))!
369372 := (((((2 + 7))! + 3!) - ((-9 × 6!) - 3!))
369373 := ((3! + 7) + ((3!! × 9) + ((6 + 3))!))
369378 := (((8!/7) + 3!!) + (9! + ((6 × 3)))
369379 := (((9! + 7) + 3!) - ((-9 × 6!) - 3!))
369381 := (((1 + 8))! - 3!) + (9 × (6! + 3!))
369382 := (-2 + (((8!/3!) + 9!) - ((6³)))
369383 := -((((3! - 8!)/3!) - 9!) + ((6³)))
369384 := ((4! + ((8!/3!) + 9!)) + (6!/(-3)))
369386 := (((6! + 8!) + 3) × 9) - (6/3!))
369387 := (((7 + 8) - 3!))! + (9 × (6! + 3!))
369388 := (-8 - (((-8!) - 3!!) × 9) - (6 × 3!))
369389 := ((9! + (83)) + (9 × (6! - 3!)))
369405 := (((-5 - ((-((0! - 4))!))! × (-9)) + ((6 + 3))!)
369409 := (((9! - 0!) - 4) + (9 × (6! + 3!)))
369414 := (((4 + 1) + 4))! + (9 × (6! + 3!))
369418 := (((8 + 1))! + 4) + (9 × (6! + 3!))
369419 := ((9! + (1 + 4)) + (9 × (6! + 3!)))
369423 := (((3²)⁴) + 9!) - ((6 × 3))
369433 := (((((3^{3!}) + 4) × 9!) + 6!)/3!!)
369443 := (((3⁴⁺⁴) + 9!) + (6/3))
369449 := (((((9⁴) - 4) + 9!) + 6) + 3!)
369459 := (((9! + 5!) - 4!) + ((9 × 6!) + 3))
369468 := ((((-8 - 6!) + 4) × (-9)) + ((6 + 3))!)
369483 := (((3⁸) + 4!) + 9!) + ((6 × 3))
369489 := ((9 × (((8! + 4!) - 9) + 6!)) - 3!)
369497 := (((7 - (9⁴))) + 9!) + (63))
369523 := ((3!!²) - ((59 - 6)³))
369549 := (((((9⁴) + 5!) + 9!) - 6) - 3!)
369588 := 8!/(8 - 5)! + 9! - 6 - 3!
369595 := ((-5 + 9!) + (((5 + 9) - 6))!/3!))
369599 := (9! + (((9! × 5!)/9) - 6!)/3!))
369603 := ((3⁰6) × ((9!/6!) + 3))
369609 := ((9! + ((0! + 6!) × 9)) - (6!/(-3)))
369618 := (((8!/(1 × 6)) + 9!) + ((6 × 3)))

$$\begin{aligned} 369624 &:= (4! + (((2+6))! - (9! \times (-6)))/3!) \\ 369648 &:= (((8 \times 4) + 6!) \times 9) + ((6+3)!) \\ 369675 &:= (((-(5 \times 7)) - 6!) \times (-9)) + ((6+3)!) \\ 369719 &:= (((9! - 1) - ((7! \times 9)/(-6))) - 3!!) \\ 369727 &:= (((7!/2) + 7) + 9!) + (6! \times 3!) \\ 369728 &:= ((8! - (((2^7) + 9!) \times (-6)))/3!) \\ 369737 &:= (((-(7^3)) + 7!) + 9!) + (6! \times 3) \\ 369739 &:= (9! + (((3+7) + 9)^{6-3})) \\ 369789 &:= (((9 \times 8) \times (7! + 96)) - 3) \\ 369798 &:= (((8 \times 9) \times (7! + 96)) + 3!) \\ 369864 &:= (((4! - 6!) - 8!) \times (-9)) + (((6-3)!)!) \\ 369935 &:= (((((5+3!!) + 9) \times 9!) - 6!)/3!!) \\ 369945 &:= (((((5^4) \times 9) + 9!) + 6!) + 3!!) \\ 369955 &:= ((((-5-5!) + 9!) - (-9 \times 6!)) + 3!!) \\ 369987 &:= (((7!/8) + 9!) - ((-9 \times 6!) + 3)) \\ 369993 &:= (3!! + ((9! - ((9 \times (9-6!)) + 3!))) \\ 369996 &:= (((((6! - 9) \times 9) + 9!) + 6!) - 3) \\ 369999 &:= ((9 \times ((9!/9) - 9) + 6!)) + 3!!) \\ 370037 &:= (((7! + (30)) - 0!) \times 73) \\ 370079 &:= (((9! + 7!) - 0!) + ((-(0! - 7)))! \times 3)) \\ 370089 &:= ((9 \times ((8! + 0!) + (-((0! - 7)))!)) + (3!!)) \\ 370319 &:= (((9! - 1) + 3!!) + (((0! + 7)!/3!)) \\ 370395 &:= (-5 \times (9 - ((3! \times 07)^3)) \\ 370449 &:= (9 \times (((4+4))! + 0!) + (7!/3!)) \\ 370475 &:= (((-5+7!) + 40) \times 73) \\ 370485 &:= ((5^8) + (-4 \times ((0! + 7!) - 3!)) \\ 370567 &:= (((((7+6)^5) + 0!) - 7) - 3!!) \\ 370573 &:= (((3! + 7)^5) - (((0 \times 7) + 3)!)!) \\ 370576 &:= (((6+7)^5) - (-((0! - 7)))! + 3) \\ 370656 &:= ((6^5) + ((6 + ((0 \times 7) + 3)))!) \\ 370669 &:= (9! + ((6^{6-0!}) + (7+3!)) \\ 370773 &:= (-((3^7)) + (7! \times (0! + 73))) \\ 370847 &:= (-((7^4)) + (((8+0!)! / 7!)^3)) \\ 370944 &:= ((4^4) \times ((9 + (-((0! - 7)))!) + (3!!))) \\ 370958 &:= (((((8!/5) + 9!) + 0!) + 7) + 3!) \\ 370989 &:= (9 \times ((8! + 907) - 3!)) \\ 371072 &:= (((2+7))! + ((0! + 1)^{7+3!})) \\ 371079 &:= ((9! + 7) + ((0! + 1)^{7+3!})) \\ 371184 &:= ((4! - ((8-1)!) \times (-1+73)) \\ 371279 &:= ((9! + ((7! \times 2) - 1)) - (7!/3)) \\ 371293 &:= ((3! + (9-2))^{1+7-3}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 371369 &:= ((9! + ((6^{3!-1}) - 7)) + 3!!) \\ 371376 &:= ((6^7) + (((3! - 1)!) + 7) \times 3!!) \\ 371469 &:= (9! + (((6! \times 4) - (17)) \times 3)) \\ 371497 &:= (((-(7! + 9!)) / (((4-1)!)!) \times (-7-3!!)) \\ 371515 &:= (-5 + (-((1-517)) \times 3!!)) \\ 371519 &:= ((9! - 1) + (5! \times (-1-73))) \\ 371544 &:= (4! + (4! \times ((5! + ((1 \times 7)!) \times 3))) \\ 371568 &:= ((8 \times (6^{5+1})) - (7!/3)) \\ 371589 &:= (((9 \times 8) \times ((5! + 1) + 7!)) - 3) \\ 371598 &:= (((8 \times 9) \times ((5! + 1) + 7!)) + 3!) \\ 371664 &:= (4! \times (6 - (((6-1)!) + 7!) \times (-3))) \\ 372013 &:= (((3+10)^{-2+7}) + 3!!) \\ 372035 &:= ((-5 \times (((3!! + 0!)^2) / (-7))) + 3!!) \\ 372224 &:= (((4^2)^2) \times 2) \times (7+3!!) \\ 372235 &:= (((-5 + ((3^2))!) - (-2 \times 7!)) - 3!!) \\ 372236 &:= (((6+3)!) - (2 \times (2-7!))) - 3!!) \\ 372239 &:= ((9! - 3!!) + (2 - ((-2 \times 7!) + 3))) \\ 372255 &:= (((-(5^5)) - (((2+2)!) \times 7!)) \times (-3)) \\ 372393 &:= (3 \times ((9 \times 3!!) - (-2 - (7^3!))) \\ 372456 &:= (((6! - 5) + 4!) \times ((2+7)!) / 3!!) \\ 372519 &:= (9! + ((1-5!) \times (-27 \times 3))) \\ 372579 &:= (9! + ((-7 + (5! \times 27)) \times 3)) \\ 372595 &:= (-5 + ((9 \times 5!) \times (2 + (7^3)))) \\ 372625 &:= 5^2 \times (-6! + (-2 + 7)^3!) \\ 372729 &:= (-9 + ((2+72) \times (7! - 3))) \\ 372733 &:= ((3!! + ((3! + 7)^{-2+7})) + 3!!) \\ 372734 &:= (-4 - (37 \times ((-2 \times 7!) + 3!))) \\ 372738 &:= (((83-7) - 2) \times (7! - 3)) \\ 372798 &:= ((8! + 9!) - ((7! + (27)) \times 3!)) \\ 372829 &:= (9! - ((2 \times ((8^2) - 7!)) + 3)) \\ 372879 &:= ((9! - 78) - ((-2 \times 7!) + 3)) \\ 372887 &:= ((7! \times (-8-82)) - 73) \\ 372906 &:= (((-60) + 9!) - ((-2 \times 7!) - 3!)) \\ 372915 &:= (((-51) + 9!) - ((-2 \times 7!) - 3!)) \\ 372924 &:= (((-42) + 9!) - ((-2 \times 7!) - 3!)) \\ 372927 &:= 7! \times 2 + 9! - 27 - 3! \\ 372933 &:= (((-33) + 9!) - ((-2 \times 7!) - 3!)) \\ 372936 &:= (((-(6 \times 3)) + 9!) - ((-2 \times 7!) + 3!)) \\ 372939 &:= 9! - 3 \times 9 + 2 \times 7! + 3! \\ 372941 &:= (((-1-4!) + 9!) - ((-2 \times 7!) - 3!)) \\ 372942 &:= (2 \times (((4! - 9!) / (-2)) + 7!) + 3)) \\ 372944 &:= (((-4-4!) + 9!) - (-2 \times (7! + 3!))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 372945 &:= (((5+4)! - 9) - ((-2 \times 7!) + 3!)) \\ 372946 &:= ((-((6-4) + 9!) - (-2 \times (7! - 3!))) \\ 372947 &:= 74 \times (9-2)! - 7 - 3! \\ 372948 &:= (((8!/4) + 9!) - ((2+7) + 3)) \\ 372949 &:= ((9! + ((4-9))) - ((-2 \times 7!) + 3!)) \\ 372951 &:= ((-((1+5) + 9!) - ((-2 \times 7!) + 3)) \\ 372953 &:= -((((3! - 5) - 9!) + ((-2 \times 7!) + 3!))) \\ 372955 &:= (-5 + (((5! - 9) \times 2) \times 7!)/3)) \\ 372956 &:= ((-((6-5) + 9!) - ((-2 \times 7!) + 3)) \\ 372957 &:= (((75 \times ((9-2))!) - 7!) - 3) \\ 372979 &:= 9! + (7! + 9) \times 2 + 7 - 3! \\ 372991 &:= ((19 + 9!) - (-2 \times (7! + 3!))) \\ 372992 &:= ((29 + 9!) - ((-2 \times 7!) - 3)) \\ 372993 &:= (((3 \times 9) + 9!) - ((-2 \times 7!) - 3!)) \\ 373048 &:= (-8 \times ((4! + 0!) - ((3!^7)/3!)) \\ 373059 &:= (9 \times (((((5-0!))!)^3) - 7) \times 3)) \\ 373168 &:= (8 \times ((6^{1 \times 3!}) - (7+3))) \\ 373176 &:= (-6 + ((71+3) \times (7!+3))) \\ 373224 &:= -((4! - (-((2 - (2 \times 37)))^3))) \\ 373232 &:= ((2^3) \times (-2 + ((3!^7)/3!)) \\ 373236 &:= (((6^3!) \times 2) - 3) \times (7-3) \\ 373239 &:= (-9 + ((3! \times ((2+3) + 7))^3)) \\ 373258 &:= ((8 \times (((5-2))!)^3!) + (7+3)) \\ 373264 &:= (-4 \times (-((6-2) - ((3!^7)/3!)) \\ 373271 &:= (-((1 - (72^3))) + ((7-3)!)) \\ 373304 &:= ((4! \times (((03)!)^3!) + 7))/3) \\ 373307 &:= (((7+0!) \times ((3!^3!) + 7)) + 3) \\ 373318 &:= ((8 \times (1 + ((3!^3!) + 7))) + 3!) \\ 373321 &:= (((12 \times 3!)^3) + 73) \\ 373327 &:= (((72^3) + 3!) + 73) \\ 373328 &:= (8 \times (((2 \times 3)^3!) + (7+3))) \\ 373329 &:= ((9^2) + (((3 \times 3)!) / 7!)^3)) \\ 373338 &:= ((8 \times ((3!^3!) + 3!)) - (-7 \times 3!)) \\ 373344 &:= (4 \times (4! + (((3+3)^7)/3)) \\ 373345 &:= ((5^{4!/3}) + (3!! \times (-((7-3)!))) \\ 373359 &:= ((-9+5!) + (((3 \times 3)!) / 7!)^3)) \\ 373368 &:= (8 \times (((6^3!) - 3!) + ((7 \times 3))) \\ 373375 &:= ((5! + 7) + (((3 \times 3)!) / 7!)^3)) \\ 373384 &:= (-4 \times (((8! - 3!)/3) \times (-7)) + 3!)) \\ 373392 &:= (((2^9) \times (3!! + (3!))) + (7!/3)) \\ 373407 &:= (((70+4) \times (3!+7!)) + 3) \\ 373408 &:= (8 \times (((0!+4)!) + (3!^7))/3!)) \\ 373434 &:= (((4!+3) \times ((4!^3) + 7)) - 3) \\ 373443 &:= (((3+4!) \times ((4!^3) + 7)) + 3!) \\ 373459 &:= (9! + (((5!/4!)^3!) - 7!) - 3!)) \\ 373464 &:= (4! \times (((6!+4!) - 3) \times (7 \times 3))) \\ 373536 &:= ((6 + (3!^5)) \times ((3! \times 7) + 3!)) \\ 373569 &:= (9! - (((6! \times 5) - 37) \times (-3))) \\ 373587 &:= (((7!/(-8)) \times ((5! - 3!)) + 7)) - 3) \\ 373599 &:= (9 \times (-9 + (5! \times (3 + (7^3)))) \\ 373638 &:= (((8!/3!) + (6^3!)) \times 7) + 3! \\ 373659 &:= (9! + (((5 \times 6!) \times 3) - ((7 \times 3))) \\ 373679 &:= (((9! + 7!) - ((6/3!) - 7!)) + 3!)) \\ 373692 &:= (((((2^9) \times 6!) + 3!) + 7!) + 3!) \\ 373698 &:= (((8! + 9!) + 6!) - ((-3 + 7!) \times 3!)) \\ 373704 &:= ((4! + ((0! + 73) \times 7!)) + 3!)) \\ 373717 &:= (((7! + 1) + 7!) \times 37) + 3!)) \\ 373747 &:= ((74 \times (7! + 3!)) + ((7^3))) \\ 373779 &:= ((9! + 7!) - (-7 \times (-3 + (7!/3!))) \\ 373795 &:= ((-5 + 9!) + (((7+3!) \times 7!)/3!)) \\ 373797 &:= ((7! + 9!) + (((7!/3!) + 7!) - 3)) \\ 373824 &:= ((4!^2) + (8 \times ((3!^7)/3!)) \\ 373833 &:= (((3!! - (3^8)) + 3!)) \times (-73)) \\ 373888 &:= (8 \times ((8 \times ((-8 + 3!)) + 7!)) + 3!)) \\ 373896 &:= (-((6! - 9!)) + (8 \times ((3^7) - 3!))) \\ 373964 &:= ((-4 + 6!) + (((-9!)/3!)/(-7!)^3)) \\ 373968 &:= ((((-8 + 6!) \times 9!)/3!)) - (7! \times (-3)) \\ 374199 &:= (9! + ((9 + ((1 \times 4)!) \times (7^3))) \\ 374235 &:= ((5^{3!+2}) + (-((4^7)) - 3!)) \\ 374272 &:= ((2^{7+2}) \times ((4+7) + 3!)) \\ 374325 &:= ((-((5^2)) \times (3-4!)) \times (-7+3!)) \\ 374353 &:= -((3!! - (((5^3!) \times 4!) + 73))) \\ 374395 &:= ((-5+9!) + (3!! \times (4 \times (7-3)))) \\ 374399 &:= (9! + ((9 \times 3!)) + ((-4+7!) + 3)) \\ 374499 &:= (((9! + (9^4)) + 4!) + 7!) - 3! \\ 374519 &:= ((9! - 1) + (5! \times (4! + 73))) \\ 374634 &:= (((((4 \times 3)!) / (6^4)) + 7!) - 3!) \\ 374643 &:= (((((3 \times 4)!) / (6^4)) + 7!) + 3) \\ 374688 &:= ((8! + (((-8 + 6!) \times 4!) + 7!)) \times 3!) \\ 374736 &:= ((6 \times 37) \times ((4! + 7!)/3)) \\ 374757 &:= ((75 \times (7! + 4!)) - (7! + 3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 374784 &:= (4! \times (-8 - (((7 \times 4!) + 7!) \times (-3)))) \\
 374785 &:= (((5^8) - (((7 - 4)!))!) + (7! \times (-3))) \\
 374799 &:= ((9! - 9) + (7 \times (4! + (7!/3)))) \\
 374905 &:= (-(((5! - 0!) - 9!)) - ((4!)/(-(7 \times 3)!))) \\
 374943 &:= (-((3^4) + 9!) - ((4!)/(-(7 \times 3)!))) \\
 374952 &:= (-(((2 + 5)! - 9!)) + (4! \times (-7 + 3!))) \\
 374957 &:= (-((7! + 5) - 9!)) + (4! \times (-7 + 3!)) \\
 374968 &:= (-(((8!/6!) - 9!)) - ((4!)/(-(7 \times 3)!))) \\
 374969 &:= (((9! \times 6!) + ((9! \times 4!) - 7!))/3!! \\
 374976 &:= (((((6^7) + 9!)/(-4)) \times 7)/(-3)) \\
 374979 &:= (9! + (((7 \times 9!) \times 4!)/7! + 3)) \\
 375025 &:= ((5^2) \times ((0! - 5!) - (7! \times (-3)))) \\
 375119 &:= ((9! - 1) + (((1 - 5!)/(-7)) \times 3!)) \\
 375189 &:= (9! + (((8^{-1+5}) + 7) \times 3)) \\
 375239 &:= (9! - (((3! \times 2) + 5) \times (-7 - 3!))) \\
 375385 &:= ((5^8) - ((3!! \times (-5! + 7)))/(-3!)) \\
 375479 &:= (((9! - (7^4)) - 5!) - (7! \times (-3))) \\
 375485 &:= (((5^8) - (4 \times 5)) + (7! \times (-3))) \\
 375595 &:= (((-5 + 9!) + (5! \times 5!)) - (7!/3)) \\
 375613 &:= (((-(3 - 16))^5 + 7!) - 3!!) \\
 375625 &:= (((5^{2+6}) + 5!) + (7! \times (-3))) \\
 375648 &:= (((8^4) + 6!) \times (5 + 73)) \\
 375669 &:= (9! + (((6! \times (-6)) + (57)) \times (-3))) \\
 375731 &:= (((13 - 7!) - 5!) \times (-73)) \\
 375859 &:= (((9 \times 58) - 5) \times (7 + 3!)) \\
 375928 &:= (-((8 \times 2) - (9 \times 5!)) \times (-7^3)) \\
 376264 &:= (-4 \times (((6 - ((2 + 6)!)) \times (-7))/(-3))) \\
 376288 &:= 88 \times (-2 + (6! - 7) \times 3!) \\
 376299 &:= (9! + (((-9^2) + 6!) \times (7 \times 3))) \\
 376319 &:= ((9! - 1) + (((3!/6) + 7)!/3)) \\
 376327 &:= (((7! \times (2^3!)) + 6) \times 7)/3! \\
 376348 &:= (8! \times 4 + 3! + 6) \times 7/3 \\
 376464 &:= ((4! + 64) \times ((6! - 7) \times 3!)) \\
 376488 &:= 8 \times (8! + 4! - 6) \times 7/3! \\
 376559 &:= (9! + (((5! \times 5!) - 6!) - 7) + 3!) \\
 376607 &:= (((7! - 0!) - (6!/(-6))) \times 73) \\
 376675 &:= (-5 + ((7! - (6!/(-6))) \times 73)) \\
 376697 &:= (((7 \times (9! - 6)) - (6^7))/3!) \\
 376848 &:= ((-8 \times (4! - ((8!/6) \times 7))) + 3!!) \\
 376919 &:= ((9! - 1) - (-9 \times (6! + (7!/3!)))) \\
 376937 &:= (((7! \times 3) + 9!) - 6!) - (7^3)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 376986 &:= ((68 \times ((9!/6!) + 7!)) - 3!) \\
 377045 &:= (((5! + 4) + 0!) + 7!) \times 73 \\
 377185 &:= ((5^8) - ((-(1 + 7)) \times 7!)/(-3)) \\
 377259 &:= (9! + (((5! \times 2) + 7) - 7!) \times (-3)) \\
 377273 &:= (((3 \times 7!) + ((2 + 7)!)) - 7) - 3!! \\
 377275 &:= ((-5 - (7! \times (2 - 77))) - 3!!) \\
 377325 &:= (-((5^2) \times (3! + ((7! - 7) \times (-3)))) \\
 377343 &:= (((3^{4+3!}) - 7!) \times 7) - 3!! \\
 377344 &:= ((4^4) \times (((3^7) + 7) - 3!)) \\
 377349 &:= (9! + (((-4!) + 3!) - 7) \times (7 \times 3)) \\
 377385 &:= ((5 \times (8! - ((3 + 7!) \times (-7)))) - 3!!) \\
 377424 &:= (((4! \times (-((2 \times 4) + 7!)) + 7!) \times 3) \\
 377439 &:= (9! - (((3!!)/(-4)) + (7! - 7)) \times (-3)) \\
 377493 &:= ((-3 + 9!) - (((4! \times 7) - 7!) \times 3)) \\
 377565 &:= (-5 \times ((6 - (-5 \times (7! - 7))) \times (-3)) \\
 377568 &:= (((8! + 6!)/5) \times ((7 \times 7) - 3)) \\
 377619 &:= (9! + (((-((1 - 6)!)) - (7! - 7)) \times (-3)) \\
 377625 &:= (-((5^2) \times (-6 + ((7! - 7) \times (-3)))) \\
 377639 &:= (9! + ((3 \times (-6 + 7!)) - ((7^3)))) \\
 377655 &:= (-5 \times (((-5 \times (6 - 7!)) + 7) \times (-3)) \\
 377657 &:= (((75 \times 6!) \times 7) - (7^3)) \\
 377735 &:= (((5^3) - 7!) \times (-77)) - 3!! \\
 377769 &:= (9! + (((6! \times 7) - 77) \times 3)) \\
 377775 &:= (((5 - 7) + 77) \times (7! - 3)) \\
 377785 &:= (5 \times (8! + (((7! - 7) \times 7) + 3!)) \\
 377859 &:= (9! - (((5 \times 8) + 7) - 7!) \times 3)) \\
 377865 &:= (-5 \times ((6 - 8!) + (-7 \times (7! - 3))) \\
 377895 &:= -((((5! - 9!) - (8 + 7)) + (7! \times (-3))) \\
 377927 &:= (((7! \times 2) + 9!) + 7!) - 73 \\
 377929 &:= ((-92) + 9!) - ((7! + 7) \times (-3)) \\
 377935 &:= (5 \times (((3! + 9) \times 7!) - 7) - 3!) \\
 377937 &:= -7 \times 3! + 9! + (7! - 7) \times 3 \\
 377938 &:= ((-83) + 9!) - ((7! + 7) \times (-3)) \\
 377939 &:= (((-9 \times 3!) + 9!) - 7) - (7! \times (-3)) \\
 377947 &:= ((-74) + 9!) - ((7! + 7) \times (-3)) \\
 377955 &:= (((5!/(-5)) + 9!) - ((7! - 7) \times (-3)) \\
 377956 &:= ((-65) + 9!) - ((7! + 7) \times (-3)) \\
 377965 &:= ((-56) + 9!) - ((7! + 7) \times (-3)) \\
 377971 &:= ((-(1 + 7)) + 9!) - ((7! - 7) \times (-3)) \\
 377973 &:= (3 \times ((7! - 9) + (7! \times ((7 - 3)!))) \\
 377974 &:= ((-47) + 9!) - ((7! + 7) \times (-3)) \\
 377978 &:= -8 + 7 + 9! + (7! - 7) \times 3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 377979 &:= (((-((9+7)+9)) \times 7!) + 7) \times (-3)) \\ 377983 &:= ((-38) + 9!) - ((7! + 7) \times (-3)) \\ 377985 &:= (-5 \times (((8! \times (-9-7))) + 7!) + 3)) \\ 377992 &:= ((-2 + 9!) - (((9-7) - 7!) \times 3)) \\ 377994 &:= (((4! - 9) + 9!) - ((7! - 7) \times (-3))) \\ 377995 &:= (-5 + (((9+9) + 7) \times 7!) \times 3)) \\ 377996 &:= ((-((6 - (9 \times 9))) \times 7!) - (7 - 3)) \\ 377998 &:= ((-8 + 9!) - (((-9 - 7!) + 7) \times 3)) \\ 377999 &:= (9! - ((9/9)^7)) - (7! \times (-3)) \\ 378011 &:= ((11 + ((0! + 8)!) - (7! \times (-3))) \\ 378015 &:= (-5 \times (((-1 - 0!) \times 8!) + 7!) - 3)) \\ 378022 &:= ((22 + ((0! + 8)!) - (7! \times (-3))) \\ 378023 &:= (((3^2)!) - 0!) - ((-8 - 7!) \times 3)) \\ 378024 &:= (4! - (((2 + 0!) \times 8!) + 7!) \times (-3)) \\ 378025 &:= (-5 \times ((-2 \times (0! + 8!)) + (7! - 3))) \\ 378027 &:= (((7 + 2)!) + (((0! + 8) + 7!) \times 3)) \\ 378029 &:= (9! + 2) + (((0! + 8) + 7!) \times 3)) \\ 378033 &:= ((33 + ((0! + 8)!) - (7! \times (-3))) \\ 378036 &:= (((6 \times 3!) + ((0! + 8)!) - (7! \times (-3))) \\ 378039 &:= (9! + (((3! - 0!) + 8) + 7!) \times 3)) \\ 378044 &:= ((44 + ((0! + 8)!) - (7! \times (-3))) \\ 378049 &:= (((9! + 4!) + 0!) - ((-8 - 7!) \times 3)) \\ 378055 &:= ((55 + ((0! + 8)!) - (7! \times (-3))) \\ 378063 &:= (((3 \times ((6 + 0!) + 8!)) + 7!) \times 3) \\ 378066 &:= ((66 + ((0! + 8)!) - (7! \times (-3))) \\ 378073 &:= (((3 \times 7!) + ((0! + 8)!) + (73)) \\ 378075 &:= ((5 \times (7! + 0!)) \times (8 + (7!/3!))) \\ 378077 &:= ((77 + ((0! + 8)!) - (7! \times (-3))) \\ 378088 &:= ((88 + ((0! + 8)!) - (7! \times (-3))) \\ 378095 &:= (((5! + 9!) - 0!) + ((-8 + 7!) \times 3)) \\ 378099 &:= ((99 + ((0! + 8)!) - (7! \times (-3))) \\ 378266 &:= (((((6^6) - 2) \times 8) + 7!) - 3!) \\ 378294 &:= (((((4! \times 9)^2) \times 8) + 7!) + 3!) \\ 378333 &:= (((((3!^{3!}) + 3!) \times 8) + 7!) - 3) \\ 378336 &:= (((6^{3!}) + 3!) \times 8) + (7 \times 3!) \\ 378355 &:= (-5 + ((5! + ((3 \times 8!) + 7!)) \times 3)) \\ 378375 &:= ((-5 - 7!) \times (3! - ((8 + 73)))) \\ 378384 &:= (((4! + (8!/3!)) \times (8 \times 7)) + 3!) \\ 378385 &:= (5^8) - (((3 \times 8) - 7) \times 3!) \\ 378505 &:= (5^{0!+5}) + (((8 + 7) - 3!)!) \\ 378525 &:= (525 \times ((8 - 7) + 3!)) \\ 378585 &:= (5 \times (((8! + 5!) + 8!) - 7!) - 3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 378594 &:= (((4! - 9) \times 5) \times (8 + 7!)) - 3! \\ 378693 &:= (((-3 + 9!) + 6!) + ((-8 + 7!) \times 3)) \\ 378715 &:= ((-5 \times (1 + (7! \times (-8 + 7)))) + 3!) \\ 378719 &:= (9! - 1) + (((7 + 8) + 7) \times 3!) \\ 378735 &:= ((-5 \times (-3 + (7! \times (-8 + 7)))) + 3!) \\ 378755 &:= ((-5 \times (((5! \times 7!) / (-8)) - 7)) + 3!) \\ 378764 &:= ((4 - 6!) \times (-7 - (87 \times 3!))) \\ 378783 &:= (((3 \times (-87) - 8!) - 7!) \times (-3)) \\ 378936 &:= (((((6^{3!}) - 9) \times 8) + 7!) + 3!) \\ 379254 &:= (((4^{5+2}) + 9!) - (7 + 3)) \\ 379279 &:= (9! + (((7 \times 2) + 9) \times (-7 + 3!))) \\ 379285 &:= (((5! + 8)^2) + 9!) + ((7 \times 3)) \\ 379344 &:= ((-4 \times (4! - (((3 + 9)!) / 7!))) - 3!) \\ 379345 &:= (((5!/4!)^{3!}) + 9!) + (7!/3!) \\ 379392 &:= ((2^9) \times (3! + ((9 \times 7) / 3))) \\ 379395 &:= (((-5 \times (9 + 3!)) \times (-9 - 7!)) + 3!) \\ 379416 &:= ((6! \times (-1 + 4!)) + (9! - ((7 - 3)!)!) \\ 379432 &:= ((2 \times (3! - 4)) + ((9! - (7! \times (-3)))) \\ 379433 &:= ((((((3 + 3)!) \times 4!) + 9!) - 7) - 3!) \\ 379434 &:= (((-4 \times 3!) \times (-4)) + (((9! + 7!) - 3!)) \\ 379436 &:= ((6! + 3!) - ((4 - 9!) + (7! \times (-3)))) \\ 379443 &:= ((3! \times (4 \times 4)) + ((9! + 7!) + 3)) \\ 379446 &:= (((6! \times (4 \times 4)) + 9!) + 7!) + 3! \\ 379447 &:= ((((((7 - 4)!)!) \times 4!) + (9! + 7)) - 3!) \\ 379557 &:= (((7^5) - 5!) + 9!) - (7 + 3) \\ 379566 &:= ((6 \times (6 + 5)) \times ((-9 + 7!) + 3!)) \\ 379649 &:= ((9! + ((4! \times (6! + 9)) - 7)) - 3!) \\ 379657 &:= (((7^5) - 6) + 9!) - ((7 - 3)!) \\ 379665 &:= ((-5 + 6!) \times (6! - ((9 \times 7) \times 3))) \\ 379793 &:= (((3! - (9 - 7))^9) + (7^{3!})) \\ 379848 &:= (-84) \times ((8! / (-9)) + (-7 \times 3!)) \\ 379869 &:= (9! - ((6! + (89)) \times (-7 \times 3))) \\ 379934 &:= ((4! \times (3! - 9)) + (9! - (7 + 3))) \\ 379967 &:= (((((7 + 6)!) / 9!) + 9!) - 73) \\ 379968 &:= ((8! / 6) + ((9 + (9 \times 7))^3)) \\ 380094 &:= (-((4! - 90)) \times (-0!) + (8 \times 3!)) \\ 380154 &:= (((4! \times ((5 + 1)!) + ((0! + 8)!) - (3!)) \\ 380163 &:= (((3! \times (-((6 - 1)!) - (0! + 8!)) \times (-3)) \\ 380164 &:= (((4! \times 6!) + 1) + ((0! + 8)!) + 3) \\ 380349 &:= (9! + ((4! \times (3! + 08)) - 3)) \\ 380352 &:= (((-((2^5)) \times (3! + 0!)) - 8!) \times (-3!)) \\ 380407 &:= (((7^{0!+4}) + ((0! + 8)!) + 3!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 380416 &:= (((6! - 1) + 4!) \times (08^3)) \\ 380433 &:= (((((3^3)!/(4!)!) + ((0! + 8)!) + 3) \\ 380548 &:= ((8!/(-4)) + (((5^08) + 3))) \\ 380639 &:= ((9! + ((3! \times 6!) - 0!)) + (8!/3)) \\ 380688 &:= (88 \times ((6! + ((0 \times 8)!) \times 3!)) \\ 381276 &:= (((((6! - 7)^2) - 1)/8) \times 3!) \\ 381375 &:= ((5! - 7) \times (-((3 - 18)^3)) \\ 381435 &:= (-5 + ((3!! + (4! + 1)) \times (8^3))) \\ 381464 &:= (4! - (((6! + 4!) + 1) \times (-8^3))) \\ 381985 &:= ((5^8) - ((9!/(-1 - 8)))/3!) \\ 382319 &:= ((9! - 1) + ((3!! \times 28) - 3!)) \\ 382323 &:= (((((3!!/2) - 3)^2) - 8) \times 3) \\ 382328 &:= (((8!/2) + ((3^2)!) + 8) - 3!!) \\ 382386 &:= -(((6! + ((8! \times (-3)) - 2)) - (8^3!)) \\ 382416 &:= ((6! + ((1 \times 4)!) \times (2 + (8^3))) \\ 382563 &:= (((3 + 6)!) + (((5 - 2)^8) \times 3)) \\ 382569 &:= (9! + (6 + (((5 - 2)^8) \times 3))) \\ 382592 &:= ((-((2^9)) + 5!) \times (-((2^8)) - 3!)) \\ 382891 &:= ((-19) \times ((8!/(-2)) + 8)) + 3) \\ 382928 &:= (((8!/2) + 9!) - ((2 \times 8!)/3!)) \\ 382944 &:= (((4! \times (-4)) + 9!) - (-28) \times 3!)) \\ 382949 &:= (((3! + 8!)/2) - 94) + 9! \\ 382957 &:= 7! \times (-5 + 9^2) - 83 \\ 382978 &:= (((8! \times (7 + 9)) + 2) - (8^3!)) \\ 382984 &:= ((((-4 + 8!) - 9!) \times (-2)) - (8^3!)) \\ 382986 &:= (((6 - 8!) \times (-9)) - (-28) \times 3!)) \\ 382995 &:= ((-((5 \times 9)) + 9!) - (-28) \times 3!)) \\ 383037 &:= ((7! \times ((3 - 0!) \times 38)) - 3) \\ 383039 &:= ((9! - ((3 \times 0)!) + ((3 \times 8!)/3!)) \\ 383049 &:= (9! - ((4 - 0!) \times (-3 - (8!/3!))) \\ 383064 &:= (4! - ((-((60 - 3)) \times 8!)/3!)) \\ 383072 &:= ((((-2 \times 7!) - 0!) \times (-38)) - 3!) \\ 383074 &:= (((4! \times (7! - 0!)) - 3!) + (8^3!)) \\ 383083 &:= (((3! - 8!) + 0!) \times (-3)) + (8^3!)) \\ 383086 &:= (((6 - 8!) \times (0 - 3)) + (8^3!)) \\ 383094 &:= (((4^9) - 0!) + ((3 - 8!) \times (-3))) \\ 383097 &:= ((-7 + (9!/03)) + (8^3!)) \\ 383107 &:= (((((7 + 0)!)! + 1) \times 3) + (8^3!)) \\ 383159 &:= (((9! + 5!) - 1) + ((3 \times 8!)/3!)) \\ 383185 &:= (((5^8) - (((1 \times 3)!)!) - ((8!/3!))) \\ 383248 &:= (((8! + (4! \times 2)) \times 3) + (8^3!)) \\ 383257 &:= (((75 - 2)^3) - (8 \times 3!)) \\ 383289 &:= (9! - ((8!/(-2)) - ((3 \times 83)))) \\ 383323 &:= (((3! + (2^3!))^3) + (8! + 3)) \\ 383326 &:= (((6 + (2^3!))^3) + (8! + 3!)) \\ 383395 &:= ((-5 + 9!) - (3 \times ((3!! + 8!)/(-3!))) \\ 383664 &:= (((4! \times 6!) + ((6^3!) + 8)) \times 3!) \\ 383677 &:= (((7! \times 76) + 3!)) - (83) \\ 383679 &:= (((-9 + 7!) - 6!) \times (3! + (83))) \\ 383749 &:= (((9! - (-4 \times 7!)) + 3!)) - (8 + 3) \\ 383757 &:= ((75 \times 7!) - ((3!! \times (-8)) + 3)) \\ 383785 &:= ((5^{8!/7!}) + ((3!! + 8!)/(-3!))) \\ 383824 &:= (((4 + 2)!) + (8^3!)) - (8! \times (-3)) \\ 383826 &:= (((6! + 2) + (8^3!)) - (8! \times (-3)) \\ 383833 &:= (((3^3!) + (8^3!)) - (8! \times (-3)) \\ 383872 &:= (2 \times (((7! - 8) \times 38) + 3!)) \\ 383885 &:= ((5^8) - (((8 - 3)!) + 8!)/3!)) \\ 383905 &:= (((5^{-0!+9}) \times (-3!)) + 8!)/(-3!)) \\ 383935 &:= (-5 - (((3!! - 9) \times 3!)/(-8)) \times 3!)) \\ 383937 &:= ((((-7!) + 3!) \times (-9 + 3!))/(-8)) - 3) \\ 383964 &:= (4! - (((-((6! - 9)) \times 3!)/8) \times 3!)) \\ 384006 &:= (6 \times (0! + ((0! + 4) \times 8^3))) \\ 384036 &:= (6 \times (3! + ((0! + 4) \times 8^3))) \\ 384048 &:= ((8 + (40^{4!/8})) \times 3!) \\ 384139 &:= ((-9 \times 3!) - (-((1 + 4)^8)) + 3!)) \\ 384265 &:= ((5^6) + (((2 + 4)!) \times (8^3))) \\ 384312 &:= (((((2 + 1)!)! - 3) \times (4! + (8^3))) \\ 384336 &:= (((6! \times 33) - 4!) + 8!) \times 3! \\ 384382 &:= (-2 + ((-8 - 3!) \times ((4! \times 8) - 3!))) \\ 384384 &:= (4! \times ((-8 - 3!) \times (-((4! - 8) + 3!))) \\ 384385 &:= ((5^8) - (((3!! \times (-4)) + 8!)/3!)) \\ 384432 &:= (((2 \times 3!) + ((4! - (4^8)))) \times (-3!)) \\ 384489 &:= (9 \times (((8! + 4!)/4! + 8!) + 3!)) \\ 384576 &:= (((6! \times (-7 - 5)) + (4^8)) \times 3!) \\ 384579 &:= (9! - (((7 - 5!) \times 4!) \times 8) - 3) \\ 384636 &:= (-((6! + 3)) \times (((6!/4) + 8) - 3!)) \\ 384685 &:= (((5^8) - (6!/4)) - (8 \times 3!)) \\ 384719 &:= (((9! - 1) - 7!) - ((-4 \times 8!)/3!)) \\ 384723 &:= (((3^2)!) - ((7 - (4^8))/3)) \\ 384755 &:= (((5^5) \times 7) + (((4 + 8) - 3)!) \\ 384829 &:= (9! + ((28^{4!/8}) - 3)) \end{aligned}$$

- 384841** := (((1 + 4)⁸ - 4!) - (8 × 3!))
384861 := (-1 + 6)⁸ - 4 - 8 × 3!
384865 := ((5^{6+8/4}) - (8 × 3!))
384912 := (((((2 + 1)!)! + 9) × ((4! × (-8)) + 3!))
384985 := (((5⁸) + ((9 - 4)!) - (8 × 3!))
385344 := (4! × (4! - (((3!⁵) + 8!)/(-3)))
385434 := (((4 × 3!) - 4) × 5!) + ((8! - 3!))
385443 := (((3! × 4) - 4) × 5!) + (8! + 3)
385446 := (((((6! × 4) - 4) × 5!) + 8!) + 3!)
385475 := -((((5! + 7!) - ((4 + (5⁸)))) - 3!))
385479 := (9! + ((7 + 4!) × (-((5 - 8)^{3!})))
385497 := -(((7! + (94 - (5⁸))) - 3!))
385557 := -((7! + ((5 × 5) - ((5⁸) - 3)))
385572 := (((-2 - 7!) - (5 - (5⁸))) - 3!)
385577 := (((-7 - 7!) + ((5 + (5⁸)))) - 3!)
385578 := (((-8 - 7!) - (5 - (5⁸))) + 3!)
385579 := -((((((9 - 7) + 5)!) - (5⁸)) + 3!))
385585 := ((5⁸) + ((5! - (5! × 8)) × 3!))
385639 := (((9 - 3!) × 6) + ((5⁸))) - 3!
385728 := ((82 × 7) × ((5! - 8) × 3!))
385747 := (((7 × 4!) - 7!) + (5⁸)) - 3!
385749 := (9! + ((4! × (-7 + (5! × 8))) - 3))
385776 := ((6⁷) - (7! × ((5! / (-8)) - 3!))
385824 := (((4! + 2) - (8! / 5)) × (-8 × 3!))
385875 := (5! - 7 - 8)^{-5+8/3}
385919 := (9! - (1 - ((9 × 5) × (8³)))
385923 := (((3! / (-2)) × ((-9 × 5!) + 8)) + 3)
385926 := (((6! / (-2)) × ((-9 × 5!) + 8)) + 3!)
385945 := -(((5! × (4! + 9)) - ((5⁸)))) - 3!
385968 := ((3! - (-((8 + 59) × 6!)) × 8)
385968 := (8 × ((6! × (9 + 58)) + 3!))
386448 := (8 × (((4! × 4!) + 6) × 83))
386544 := (((-4 × (4! - (5! × 6!))) + 8!) + 3!))
386547 := (-7 × (((4 - (5⁶)) - 8!) + 3!))
386615 := (-5 × ((-(((1 + 6)⁶)) + 8!) + 3!))
386634 := (((4! - (3! × 6!)) × (6! / (-8))) - 3!)
386635 := (-5 - (3! × (((6! × (-6)) / 8) + 3)))
386646 := (6! - 4) × 6 × 6! / 8 + 3!
386664 := (4! - (6! × (((6! × (-6)) / 8) + 3)))
386675 := (5 × (((7! / 6!)⁶ - 8!) + 3!))
386684 := (-((4 - (8 × (6⁶)))) + (8! / 3))
386688 := -((8! + (8 × (-((6⁶)) - (8! / 3!))))
386771 := ((17 - 7!) × (6 - 83))
386878 := (((-8 - (7! / (-8)))⁻⁶⁺⁸) - 3!)
386887 := (((7! / 8) - 8)⁻⁶⁺⁸) + 3)
386975 := (((-5 + 7!) × (9 + 68)) - 3!))
387025 := ((-((-((3 - 8)⁷))) + (((0! + 2)!)!) × (-5))
387065 := (-5 × (-(((6 - 0!)⁷) + 8)) + 3!))
387075 := (((5! + 7!) + 0!) × (78 - 3))
387269 := (9! + (((((6 / 2) × 7) + 8)³)))
387337 := (((73³) + 7!) - (8! / 3!))
387355 := ((-5 + ((-5 - 3!) × (7! - 8!))) - 3!))
387384 := ((4! + (-((8 + 3) × (7! - 8!))) - 3!))
387385 := (((5⁸) - 3!) - (7! / (8 - 3!))
387408 := (((8! / (0! + 4)) + 7) × (8 × 3!))
387448 := ((-8 - (4! × (-4⁷))) - (8 × 3!))
387575 := -((5! + ((7! - 5) × (-7 × (8 + 3))))))
387618 := ((8 - 1)! - 6) × 7 × (8 + 3)
387737 := (-((7³)) + (7! × (7 × (8 + 3))))
387774 := ((((-4 + 7!) × 77) + 8) - 3!)
387955 := (((-5 - 5!) + 9!) + (7! × (8 - 3)))
387975 := (((5 × 7!) + 9!) - ((7! / 8) / 3!))
387981 := (((((1 × 8)!) - 9) - 7!) × (8 + 3))
387999 := ((9! - (9 × 9)) + (7! × (8 - 3)))
388047 := (((7! + 4) - 0!) - 8!) × (-8 + 3))
388074 := ((-((4 + 7) × ((-((0! - 8)!) - 8!)) - 8!)) - 3!))
388075 := (-5 + ((7! - (08!)) × (-8 + 3)))
388077 := (((-77) × (08!)) / (-8)) - 3)
388079 := (((9! - 7!) - 0!) + ((8! / 8) × 3!))
388266 := (((6! - ((6²) + 8)) / (-8)) × 3!)
388344 := (((4! - ((4 + 3)!) + 8!) × (8 + 3))
388368 := ((8 × (6^{3!})) - ((8! / 8) × (-3)))
388752 := (((((2 × 5)!) / (7 × 8)) - 8) × 3!)
388784 := (-((4⁸)) - (((7! + 8) / (-8)) × 3!))
388792 := (((-((2 + 9) × (7! - 8!)) - 8) + 3!))
388795 := (-5 + ((9! × (-7 + 8)) / (-8 - 3!))
388809 := (9 × ((0! + 8!) + (8! / (8 + 3!))))
388856 := (((6! × 5!) - 8) + 8!) + (8^{3!})
388866 := (((6! × 6!) + (88)) / 8) × 3!
388877 := ((-77) × ((8 + 8!) / (-8))) + 3!))
389008 := ((-8 - 0!) + ((0! + (9 × 8))³))
389009 := ((-9 + 0!) + ((0! + (9 × 8))³))

$$\begin{aligned}
 389013 &:= -((3+1) + ((0! + (9 \times 8))^3)) \\
 389014 &:= -((4-1) + ((0! + (9 \times 8))^3)) \\
 389023 &:= (3! + (((2 \times 0)! + (9 \times 8))^3)) \\
 389041 &:= (((1 \times 4)! + ((0! + (9 \times 8))^3)) \\
 389064 &:= -((4! - 6!) \times (- (0! + ((9! + 8!)/3!))) \\
 389089 &:= ((9 \times 8) + ((0! + (9 \times 8))^3)) \\
 389168 &:= ((8^{6-1}) + (9 \times (8! - 3!))) \\
 389185 &:= ((5^8) - (((1+9) - 8) \times 3!)) \\
 389238 &:= (((8!/3!) + 2) \times (-9 + (8!/3!))) \\
 389255 &:= -((((5! - 5)^2) - 9!) - 8!) - 3! \\
 389259 &:= (9 \times (((5!^2) + ((9+8))) \times 3)) \\
 389342 &:= (-2 - (-4 \times (((3! \times 9) - 8)^3))) \\
 389344 &:= (4 \times (((4! \times 3!) - 98)^3)) \\
 389373 &:= -((((-(3-7)))!^3 - (((9! + 8!) - 3)))) \\
 389439 &:= ((9 \times ((3! \times 4) - (9 - 8!))) + 3!) \\
 389496 &:= (((6! + 9!) - 4!) + (9!/(8 + 3!))) \\
 389519 &:= ((9! - 1) - (-((5 \times 9) - 8) \times 3!)) \\
 389525 &:= -((((5!^2) - 5) - 9!) - 8!) + 3! \\
 389617 &:= ((7! - (-((1-6)^9))/(-8-3)) \\
 389645 &:= (((5! - (4^6)) \times (-98)) - 3) \\
 389667 &:= (-((7^6) + (6! \times (-9+8)))) \times (-3) \\
 389744 &:= (((-4 \times (4-7!)) + 9!) + (8!/3!)) \\
 389746 &:= (((((6! - 4!) \times 7!)/9) - 8) - 3!) \\
 389753 &:= (((((3+5)! - 7) + 9!) - (8!/3)) \\
 389755 &:= (-5 + ((-(5 - (7 \times 9))) \times 8!)/3!) \\
 389784 &:= ((4! - 8!) - (((-7 \times 9!) - 8!)/3!)) \\
 389785 &:= ((5^8) - (7!/((9-8) \times 3)!)) \\
 389808 &:= (((8+0!)! - (((8!/(-9)) - 8) \times 3!)) \\
 389809 &:= ((9! + 0!) - (((8!/(-9)) - 8) \times 3!)) \\
 389844 &:= ((((-4-4!) \times (8! + 9)) - 8!)/(-3)) \\
 389853 &:= (3! - ((58 \times (-9-8!))/3!)) \\
 389854 &:= -((4! - (((5^8) - (9 \times 83)))) \\
 389905 &:= ((5^{-0!+9}) - (((9-8) \times 3)!)) \\
 390265 &:= (((-5+6!)^2) + ((09!)/(-3))) \\
 390355 &:= (5 \times ((5^{3!+0!}) - (9 \times 3!))) \\
 390385 &:= ((5^8) - (3!/((0 \times 9) + 3))) \\
 390583 &:= ((3! \times (-8)) + ((5^{-0!+9}) + (3!))) \\
 390585 &:= ((5^8) - (5!/((0 \times 9) + 3))) \\
 390595 &:= (((5^9)/5) - ((0! + 9) \times 3)) \\
 390604 &:= -4! + (-0! + 6)^{-0!+9} + 3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 390613 &:= -3! + (-1+6)^{-0!+9} - 3! \\
 390616 &:= -6 + (-1+6)^{-0!+9} - 3 \\
 390619 &:= -9 + (-1+6)^{-0!+9} + 3 \\
 390622 &:= (-2/2 + 6)^{-0!+9} - 3 \\
 390631 &:= (-1+3!)^{-(6 \times 0)!+9} + 3! \\
 390655 &:= (5 \times ((5^{6+0!}) + (9-3))) \\
 390685 &:= (((5^8) + (6 \times 09)) + 3!) \\
 390755 &:= (-5 \times (-(5^7) + 0!) - ((9 \times 3))) \\
 390785 &:= (((5^8) - (7!/09)) + 3!) \\
 391345 &:= ((5^{4+3+1}) + ((9-3)!)) \\
 391437 &:= (((((7+3!)^4) - 1) + 9!) - 3) \\
 391657 &:= 7 \times (5^6 + (-1+9)! + 3!) \\
 391675 &:= ((5 \times (7! + 6!)) - ((-1-9!) + 3!)) \\
 391683 &:= ((3! \times (8 \times (6-1))) + (9! + 3)) \\
 391685 &:= (((((5 \times 8) \times 6!) - 1) + 9!) + 3!) \\
 391686 &:= (((-(68) \times 6!) \times (1-9)) + 3!) \\
 392248 &:= ((-8 + (4!^{2+2})) + (9!/3!)) \\
 392309 &:= ((9! + ((0! + 3!)!) + ((29^3))) \\
 392374 &:= (((((-4+7!) \times 3!) - 2) + 9!) - 3!) \\
 392376 &:= (((6 \times ((7! - 3!) + 2)) + 9!) - 3!) \\
 392384 &:= (-((4^8) + ((3!^2) - ((9!/3!)))) \\
 392395 &:= ((-5 - (((9!/3!)/(-2)) - 9!)) - 3!) \\
 392403 &:= ((3! \times (- (0! - 42))) + (9! + 3)) \\
 392406 &:= -(((6! \times (0! - 42)) - (9! + 3!))) \\
 392436 &:= (((-6 + (3!/4))^2) + (9! - 3!)) \\
 392616 &:= (((61+6!) - 2) \times 9!)/3! \\
 392634 &:= (((4!^3) + 6!) - 2) \times (9 \times 3) \\
 392656 &:= ((6! + (56)) \times ((2^9) - 3!)) \\
 392665 &:= ((5 + (6! \times (-6))) \times (2 - 93)) \\
 392674 &:= (((4! + 7)^{6/2}) + 9!) + 3) \\
 392697 &:= (((7! - 9!)/(-6 \times 2)) + 9!) - 3) \\
 392785 &:= ((5^8) - ((7!/(-2-9)) \times (-3))) \\
 392878 &:= (-8 - (-78 \times (-(2-9)! - 3))) \\
 393069 &:= (((9 - ((6+0!)!) \times (-3!)) + (9! + 3)) \\
 393078 &:= ((((-8+7!) \times (03!)) + 9!) + 3!) \\
 393096 &:= -(((6! - ((9-0!)^3) \times 9)/3!)) \\
 393108 &:= (((((8-0!)! - 1) \times 3!) + (9! - 3!)) \\
 393114 &:= (((4-1)! \times ((1+3!)!) + (9! - 3!)) \\
 393117 &:= ((7! \times ((1+1) \times 39)) - 3) \\
 393119 &:= ((9! - 1) + (((1-3) + 9)! \times 3!)) \\
 393123 &:= (((3! \times ((21/3)!)) + 9!) + 3)
 \end{aligned}$$

- 393126** := (((6 × ((21/3)!) + 9!) + 3!)
393129 := ((((((9 - 2)!) + 1) × 3!) + 9!) + 3)
393132 := (2 × (((3! + 1)!) × 39) + (3!))
393144 := (4! × ((4¹⁻³⁺⁹) - 3))
393147 := (((7! + 4) × ((1 × 3)!) + 9!) + 3)
393153 := ((-3!) × (-5 - ((1 + 3)!)!) + (9! + 3))
393156 := ((-6 × (-5 - ((1 + 3)!)!) + ((9! + 3!)))
393172 := (-2 - (((7! × (-13)) - 9) × 3!))
393216 := (((((6 × 1) + 2)^{3!}) × 9)/3!)
393234 := (((4^{3!+2}) + 3) × (9 - 3))
393237 := (((7! × 3!) + ((2 + 3)!) + 9!) - 3)
393243 := ((3! × 4^{2³}) + ((9 × 3)))
393264 := (((4 × (6²⁺³)) + 9!) - 3!!)
393267 := (((7! + ((6 - 2)!) × 3!) + 9!) + 3)
393276 := (-6 × ((7! + 2) × (-39/3)))
393337 := ((73³) + (3! × ((9 - 3)!)!))
393348 := (((8!/(-4)) - 3!) × (-39)) - 3!
393357 := (((7! + (5!/3)) × 3!) + (9! - 3))
393372 := ((2 × ((7! - 3!) × 39)) + 3!!)
393378 := -8! + (7! + 3) × (3!/9 + 3!)
393395 := ((59 + 3!!) × ((3!! + 9!)/3!!))
393449 := ((9! - 4) - (43 × (9 - 3!!)))
393489 := (((9 - (8!/4)) × (-39)) + 3!!)
393495 := (-5 × (9 + (-4 × ((3⁹) - 3!))))
393517 := (((((7! - 1) - 5!) × 3!)/9) - 3)
393535 := (-((5³)) + ((5! × (3⁹))/3!))
393554 := (-(((4 × 5) × (5 - (3⁹)))) - 3!)
393555 := (-5 + ((5! × (-5 - (3⁹))))/3!))
393564 := (4! - ((6! - (5! × (3⁹)))/3!))
393597 := (-((7 × 9)) + ((5! × (3⁹))/3!))
393633 := (((3!^{3!}) - 6!) × (-3)) + (9^{3!})
393652 := (-2 + (((5!/6) × (3⁹)) - 3!))
393654 := (((4 × 5) × ((6 - 3)⁹)) - 3!)
393655 := (-5 + ((5!/6) × ((3 × 9)³)))
393658 := (-8 + (((5!/6) × (3⁹)) + 3!))
393684 := (((4⁸) - 6) × 3!) - (-9!)/3!!
393685 := ((5⁸) + (-6 × (-3!) + (-9!)/3!!))
393723 := (((3 + (-2 × 7!)) × (-39)) + 3!!)
393744 := ((((-((4 × 4)) + 7!) × 3!) + 9!) + 3!!)
393767 := (((7! × 6) - 73) + 9!) + 3!!
393774 := (((((-4 + 7!) - 7) × 3!) + 9!) + 3!!)
393786 := (6! + ((((-8 + 7!) × 3!) + 9!) - 3!))
393795 := ((-((5 × 9)) + ((7! × 3!) + 9!)) + 3!!)
393816 := (-61) × ((8 × 3) + (-9 × 3!))
393837 := (((-7!) - (-((3 - 8)!)!) × (-3!)) + ((9! - 3)))
393843 := (3!! - ((-((4⁸)) × 3!) + (93)))
393846 := (6! + (((4⁸) - 3!) - 9) × 3!))
393849 := (((9!/4) + 8!) × 3) + ((9³))
393867 := (((7! × 6) - ((8! + 3) × (-9))) + 3!!)
393879 := ((9! + ((7! + 8) × 3!) - 9) + 3!!)
393888 := (((((8!/8) + 8) × 3!) + 9!) + 3!!)
393948 := (((8 + (4⁹))/3!) × 9) + 3!!
394057 := (7! + (((5 - 0)!)! + 49³))
394237 := (((-7!) × (3!! - (2⁴)))/(-9)) - 3)
394358 := ((8⁵) - (((3!⁴) - 9!) - 3!))
394554 := (((4! × 55) × 4!) + 9!) - 3!
394585 := ((5⁸) + (5! × ((4 × 9) - 3)))
394704 := 4! × (-0! + 7)⁴ + 9! + 3!!
394731 := ((1 - 3!!) × ((7!/(-4)) - 9) + 3!!)
394779 := (9! + (((7⁷⁻⁴) × 93)))
394924 := ((-4 + ((2^{-9+4!}) + 9!)) - 3!!)
394928 := (((8^{29-4!}) + 9!) - 3!!)
394932 := (((2^{3!+9}) + (4 + 9!)) - 3!!)
394935 := (((-5 × (3! - (9⁴))) + 9!) - 3!!)
394938 := (8! - (((3! + (9⁴)) × (-9)) × 3!))
394945 := (((-((5 × (4 - (9⁴)))) + 9!) - 3!!)
395048 := (((8^{4+0!}) + (5! + 9!)) - 3!!)
395136 := ((6 × ((3 + 1)!) × ((5 + 9)³))
395159 := (((9! - 5!) - 1) - (-((5 × 9)) × 3!))
395275 := ((-5 + ((7 + 2)!) - (-((5 × 9)) × 3!))
395293 := (((3!! × 9) + 2) × 5) + (9! + 3))
395296 := (((((6! × 9) + 2) × 5) + 9!) + 3!))
395319 := (9! + (((-1 - 3!!) × (-5 × 9)) - (3!)))
395394 := (((-4!) + (-9 × 3!)) × (-5)) + (9! - 3!))
395418 := (8! - (((-((1 - 4)!)! ⁵) - (9! - 3!)))
395534 := (((((4!/3)⁵) - 5!) + 9!) + 3!))
395538 := (8! - (((3! ⁵) - 5!) - 9!) + 3!))
395589 := ((9! + (((8⁵) - 5))) - (9 × 3!))
395635 := (-5 + (((3!! + 65) × 9!)/3!))
395639 := (9! - ((3!! - (65 × 9!))/3!))
395642 := (((2⁴⁺⁶⁺⁵) + 9!) - 3!))

$$\begin{aligned} 395649 &:= (((((9^4) - 6) \times 5) + 9!) - 3!) \\ 395664 &:= (4! + (((6! + 65) \times 9!)/3!)) \\ 395758 &:= (((((8^5) - 7) + 5!) + 9!) - 3) \\ 395762 &:= ((-(2 \times (6 - (7^5)))) + 9!) - 3!!) \\ 395787 &:= (-7 \times (((8! \times (-7))/5) - (93))) \\ 395792 &:= (((2 \times (9 + (7^5))) + 9!) - 3!!) \\ 395804 &:= (4! - 0!) \times (8! - 5) - 9^3! \\ 395848 &:= ((-8 + (((4 \times 8!)/5) + 9!)) + 3!!) \\ 395856 &:= (-(((6^5) \times (8 - 59))) - 3!!) \\ 395919 &:= (((((9 + 1))! - (9^5))/9) - 3!!) \\ 396055 &:= (55 \times ((0! - (6! \times (-9))) + 3!!)) \\ 396144 &:= (4! \times (((4! - 1) \times 6!) - (9 \times 3!))) \\ 396168 &:= ((8 \times ((6! - 1) \times 69)) - 3!!) \\ 396288 &:= ((8 \times (8^2)) \times (6! + (9 \times 3!))) \\ 396368 &:= (((8^{-6/3!+6}) + 9!) + 3!!) \\ 396375 &:= (((5 - 7!) - 3!!) \times (-69)) - 3!!) \\ 396385 &:= ((5^8) + (((3!/(-6)) + 9) \times 3!!)) \\ 396498 &:= ((8! + 9!) + (((4! + 6!) \times (-9)) - 3!)) \\ 396675 &:= ((-5 \times 7!) + (((6 + 69)^3)) \\ 396719 &:= (((9! - 1) - 7!) + ((6! \times 9) \times 3!)) \\ 396729 &:= (((92 \times (7! - 6!)) + 9) - 3!!) \\ 396732 &:= (((((2 + 3!!) + 7!) \times 6) + 9!) - 3!!) \\ 396768 &:= (((((-8 - 6!) - 7!) \times (-6)) + 9!) - 3!!) \\ 396789 &:= ((9! + 8!) + (((7 - 6!) \times 9) + 3!)) \\ 396864 &:= (((4! + (6! \times 8)) \times 6) + 9!) - 3!!) \\ 396897 &:= (((((7! \times 9)/8) \times 6) + 9!) - 3) \\ 396935 &:= (-(((5^3!) - 9!)) + (69 \times 3!)) \\ 396936 &:= ((6! \times 3!!) - (((9!/6!) - (9!/(-3)))))) \\ 397105 &:= ((5^{0!+7}) - (-9 \times 3!)) \\ 397276 &:= -((6! - (((7! - 2) \times 79) - 3!)) \\ 397297 &:= (((7! - (9 + 2)) \times 79) + 3!) \\ 397317 &:= ((((-7!) + ((-1 + 3!))!) \times (-7)) + ((9! - 3))) \\ 397359 &:= (((9^5) - ((3 + 7)!)/(-9)) + 3!!) \\ 397371 &:= (((1 - 7!) - 3!!) \times (-((7 \times 9) - 3!)) \\ 397374 &:= (-((4! + (((7! - 3!) \times (-7)) - 9!))) - 3!!) \\ 397378 &:= 8 \times (7! - 3!! - 7) + 9! - 3! \\ 397379 &:= ((9! - 7) + ((3!! + (7! - 9)) \times 3!)) \\ 397386 &:= ((-6 \times ((8 - 3!!) - 7!)) + (9! - 3!)) \\ 397423 &:= ((3!!^2) - (((4! - 7) - (9!/(-3)))) \\ 397432 &:= ((2 \times ((3!! \times 4!) - 7)) + ((9! + 3!)) \\ 397433 &:= ((3!!^{3!-4}) - (7 - (9!/(-3)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 397434 &:= (((4!)! \times 3!!)/((4! + ((7 - 9))))!) - (3!) \\ 397435 &:= ((-5 - (((3 + 4)! \times (-79))) - 3!!) \\ 397436 &:= ((((-6!) - 3!!) \times (-4!)) + ((-7 + 9!) + 3)) \\ 397437 &:= (((7! + 3!!) \times (-((4 - 7)!))! + ((9! - 3))) \\ 397455 &:= (((55 + 4!) \times (7! - 9)) + 3!) \\ 397464 &:= ((4! - (((6 + 4)!)/(-7))) + (9!/(-3))) \\ 397468 &:= 8! - (6! - 4) \times 7 + 9! - 3!! \\ 397536 &:= (6! + (-3 + 5)^{7+9}) \times 3! \\ 397606 &:= -((6! + ((0! - 6!) \times ((7!/9) - 3!))) \\ 397607 &:= ((7! \times ((0! - 6!) \times (-79)))/3!!) \\ 397664 &:= (-((4^6)) + ((6! - 7!) \times (-93))) \\ 397675 &:= (-5 + (((7! - 6) \times 79) - 3!)) \\ 397692 &:= ((((-((2 - 9)!))! - 6) \times 79) + (3!)) \\ 397719 &:= (9! + (((1 \times 7) \times 7) \times (-9 + 3!))) \\ 397748 &:= ((-8 - ((4 + 7!) \times (-79))) - 3!!) \\ 397753 &:= -((3! - (((-5 + 7!) \times 79) - 3!)) \\ 397756 &:= (-6 + (((-5 + 7!) \times 79) - 3)) \\ 397759 &:= (-9 - (((-5 + 7!) \times (-79)) - 3)) \\ 397765 &:= (((56 - 7!) \times (-7)) + 9!) - 3) \\ 397772 &:= ((-2 - (7!/(-7))) \times ((7!/9) - 3!)) \\ 397785 &:= ((5 + (8!/7)) \times ((7 \times 9) + 3!)) \\ 397824 &:= (4! \times ((2 \times (8 + 7!)) - (-9 \times 3!))) \\ 397847 &:= (((7! + ((4 - 8))) \times 79) + 3) \\ 397876 &:= (((((6^7)/8) + 7) + 9!) - 3) \\ 397953 &:= (3 \times (((5!/(9 - 7)) - 9)^3)) \\ 398133 &:= ((3!! \times (3!! + 1)) - ((8! + 9) \times 3)) \\ 398157 &:= ((((-7 \times ((5 + 1)!)) + 8!) + 9!) - 3) \\ 398166 &:= (((6! \times (-6 + 1))) + 8!) + 9! + 3! \\ 398167 &:= (((((-7 \times 6!) + 1) + 8!) + 9!) + 3!) \\ 398168 &:= ((8! + (((6! - 1) \times (-8)) + 9!)) + 3!!) \\ 398185 &:= ((5^8) - (((-((1 - 8)!))! \times (-9))/3!)) \\ 398186 &:= (((6!/8) - 1) \times ((8!/9) - 3!)) \\ 398187 &:= -((((7! - 8!) - ((1 + 8)!)) - ((9 \times 3))) \\ 398237 &:= (-7!) + (((3!! + (((2 + 8)!)))/9) - 3) \\ 398277 &:= (7! + (((7 + (2^{8+9})) \times 3))) \\ 398289 &:= ((9! + 8!) + ((2 - ((8 + 9)^3))) \\ 398384 &:= (-(((((-((4 - 8)^3!)) - 8!) - 9!)) - 3!!) \\ 398397 &:= (-79) \times (-3 - (((-((8 - 9) + 3!))!)) \\ 398634 &:= (((((4 + 3!))! - ((6! + 8!)))/9) - (3!)) \\ 398637 &:= ((((((7 + 3)! - 6!) - 8!)/9) - 3) \\ 398643 &:= (((3!! - (((4 + 6)! - 8!)))/(-9)) + 3) \\ 398646 &:= (((6! - ((4 + 6)!)) + 8!)/(-9)) + 3! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 398713 &:= (((3!! + 1) \times (-((7! - 8!) - 9!)))/3!!) \\ 398717 &:= ((((((7 - 1)!) \times 7!) - 8!)/9) - 3) \\ 398723 &:= ((((((3 \times 2)!) \times 7!) - 8!)/9) + 3) \\ 398726 &:= ((((((6/2) + 7)!) - 8!)/9) + 3!) \\ 398787 &:= (((((7 \times 8!) + 7!)/8) + 9!) - 3) \\ 398799 &:= ((((-((9 \times 9)) - 7!) + 8!) + 9!) + 3!!) \\ 398835 &:= ((-5 \times (3!! - ((8! + 8!) - 9))) - 3!!) \\ 398866 &:= (((((6! \times (-6)) - 8) + 8!) + 9!) - 3!) \\ 398875 &:= ((-5 - (7! \times (-88 - 9)))) + 3!!) \\ 398897 &:= -((((7! - 9!) - 8!) - ((8 + (9^3)))) \\ 398898 &:= (-89) \times (-8 - ((8!/9) - 3!!)) \\ 399093 &:= (((3!! - 9!)/(-0! + 9)) + ((9! - 3))) \\ 399159 &:= (((9! - 5!)/(1 + 9)) + 9!) + 3) \\ 399165 &:= (((5 + 6)!/(1 + 99)) - 3) \\ 399168 &:= (8! - (-(((6! + ((1 - 9))) \times 9!)))/3!!) \\ 399174 &:= (((4 + 7)!/(1 + 99)) + 3!) \\ 399275 &:= (((5 + 7!) \times (-2 - (9 \times 9)))) + 3!!) \\ 399375 &:= ((5^7 - 3) \times (-((9 \times 9) + 3!!)) \\ 399615 &:= (((51 \times 6!) + 9) + 9!) + 3!) \\ 399738 &:= (((8^{-3+7} \times 9) + 9!) - 3!) \\ 399744 &:= (((4! \times 4) - 7!) \times (-9 \times 9)) - 3!!) \\ 399798 &:= ((8! + 9!) - (((7 \times 9) \times 9) \times 3!)) \\ 400344 &:= (((4! \times ((-4!) + 3!!) - 0!) + 0!) \times 4!) \\ 402476 &:= -((6! - ((7! \times (4 \times 20)) - 4))) \\ 402576 &:= -((6! - (((7^5) - 2) - 0!) \times 4!)) \\ 402744 &:= (((4! + (-4 \times 7!)) \times (-20)) + 4!) \\ 402768 &:= (8! + ((6 - 7!) \times ((-2 - 0!) \times 4!)) \\ 402845 &:= (-5 \times (((4! - 8!) \times 2) - 0!) + 4!)) \\ 402944 &:= ((-((4^4)) + 9!) + ((2 \times 04)!)) \\ 402968 &:= (((-((8^6)) + 9!) + ((2 + 0!)!) \times 4) \\ 402984 &:= (((4! - 8!) \times (-9)) + ((2 \times 04)!)) \\ 402985 &:= (-5 \times (((8! - 9) \times (-2)) + 0!) + 4!)) \\ 403085 &:= (-5 \times ((8! \times (0! - 3)) - (0! - 4!)) \\ 403096 &:= (((6!/(-9)) \times (0! - ((3! + 0!)!)) - 4!) \\ 403152 &:= (2 \times ((5 \times (((1 + 3!) + 0!)!) - 4!)) \\ 403182 &:= (2 \times (((8! - 1) \times (3! - 0!)) - 4)) \\ 403185 &:= (-5 \times (((8! \times (1 - 3)) - 0!) + 4)) \\ 403188 &:= ((8! + ((8 + 1)!) - (3 \times 04)) \\ 403189 &:= ((9! + 8!) + ((1 - (3 \times 04)))) \\ 403192 &:= (2 \times (((9 - 1)!) \times (3! - 0!)) - 4)) \\ 403196 &:= (((6!/9) \times ((1 + 3!)!) - 04) \\ 403197 &:= (((7!/9) \times (((1 \times 3)!)!) + ((0! - 4))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 403199 &:= ((9! + ((9 - 1)!) - (((3 \times 0) \times 4)!) \\ 403201 &:= ((10 \times ((2^3)!) + ((0 \times 4)!) \\ 403202 &:= (2 \times (0! + (((2^3)!) \times (0! + 4)))) \\ 403204 &:= (((40 \times 2) \times ((3! + 0!)!) + 4) \\ 403205 &:= (-5 \times (-0!) + (-2 \times (((3 + 0!) + 4)!)!)) \\ 403223 &:= (((((3^2)!) + ((2^3)!) - 0!) + 4!) \\ 403224 &:= (((((4 \times 2)!) \times 2) \times (3! - 0!)) + 4!) \\ 403225 &:= (((5 \times 2) \times ((2^3)!) + 0!) + 4!) \\ 403234 &:= (((4 + 3!) \times (((2^3)!) + 0!)) + 4!) \\ 403248 &:= ((8! + (4! \times 2)) + (((3! - 0!) + 4)!) \\ 403249 &:= (((9! + 4!) + ((2^3)!) + 0!) + 4!) \\ 403269 &:= ((9! + ((6 + 2)!) + (-3 \times (0! - 4!)) \\ 403285 &:= (-5 \times (((8! \times (-2)) + 3!) + 0!) - 4!)) \\ 403289 &:= ((9! + 8!) + (((2^3)!) + 0!) + 4!) \\ 403295 &:= (((5! + 9!) + ((2^3)!) - 0!) - 4!) \\ 403298 &:= (((8! + 9!) + 2) - ((-3 - 0!) \times 4!)) \\ 403338 &:= ((8! + ((3 \times 3)!) - (3! \times (0! - 4!)) \\ 403344 &:= ((4! \times ((4 + 3)^{3! - 0!})) - 4!) \\ 403368 &:= (((8!/6!) \times 3) \times ((3! + 0!)^4)) \\ 403398 &:= 8! + 9! + 33 \times (-0! + 4!) \\ 403496 &:= (((6!/(-9)) \times (-4 - ((3! + 0!)!)) - 4!) \\ 403584 &:= ((4! - 8) \times ((5 \times ((3! + 0!)!) + 4!)) \\ 403596 &:= (((6!/(-9)) \times (-5 - ((3! + 0!)!)) - 4) \\ 403776 &:= ((6^7) - ((-7!) - ((3! - 0!)!) \times 4!)) \\ 403825 &:= (((5 \times 2) \times 8!) + ((3! - 0!)^4)) \\ 403839 &:= ((9! + 3!!) + ((8! - ((3^0 4)))) \\ 403849 &:= (((9! + 4!) + 8!) + ((3! - 0!)^4)) \\ 403896 &:= (((6! + 9!) + 8!) - (((3 \times 0) + 4)!) \\ 403919 &:= (((((9 - 1)!) + 9!) + 3!) - ((0 \times 4)!) \\ 403924 &:= (((((4 \times 2)!) + 9!) + 3!) + 04) \\ 403925 &:= (((((5 \times 2)!) / 9) + 3!) + (0! + 4)) \\ 403943 &:= (((((3! + 4)!) / 9) + 3!) - (0! - 4!)) \\ 403968 &:= (((8! + 6!) + 9!) + ((3 - 0!) \times 4!)) \\ 403975 &:= ((5 + (7!/9)) \times (3!! - (0! + 4))) \\ 404376 &:= (((6 + 7) \times (3!^4)) + 0!) \times 4!) \\ 404545 &:= (((5! - 4) \times 5!) + ((4! + 0!)^4)) \\ 405025 &:= ((5!^2) + ((0! + ((5 - 0!)!)^4)) \\ 405224 &:= (42 + 2^5)^{-0! + 4} \\ 405247 &:= (((74^{-2+5}) - 0!) + 4!) \\ 405347 &:= (((74^3) + 5!) - 0!) + 4) \\ 405385 &:= ((5^8) - ((-3 - 5!) \times ((0! + 4)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 405936 &:= (-6 \times ((3!! \times (-95) + 0!)) + 4!) \\ 405984 &:= (((4! + 8!) + 9!) - (5! \times (0! - 4!))) \\ 406536 &:= (((6! + 3!) \times 560) - 4!) \\ 406824 &:= (4! + (((2 \times 8!) + 6!) \times (0! + 4))) \\ 406825 &:= (-5 \times ((((-2 \times 8!) - 6!) - 0!) - 4)) \\ 407185 &:= ((5^8) + (((-((1 - 7)))! \times (- (0! - 4!)))))) \\ 407298 &:= (((8! + 9!) + 2) + ((7 + 0!)^4)) \\ 407464 &:= ((4^6) + (4! \times (7^{0!+4}))) \\ 407754 &:= ((4! + (57)) \times (7! - (-((0! - 4)!)))!)) \\ 407799 &:= (9! + ((9 \times 7) \times (-7 + (((-((0! - 4)!))!))!))) \\ 407895 &:= -((5! - (9 \times (((8! + 7!) - 0!) - 4!)))) \\ 407897 &:= (((7! + 9!) + 8!) - (7^{-0!+4})) \\ 407905 &:= ((5^{-0!+9}) - (((7 - 0!)! \times (-4!))) \\ 407979 &:= (9 \times (7 + (9 \times (7! + (0 - 4)))))) \\ 408236 &:= (((((6 + 3)^2) \times ((8 - 0!)!)) - 4) \\ 408237 &:= 7! + (3^2)! + 8! + 0! - 4 \\ 408239 &:= (((9! \times (-3^2))/(-8)) - ((0 \times 4)!)) \\ 408294 &:= (((4! - (9!/(-2))) \times (8 + 0!))/4) \\ 408479 &:= ((9 \times ((7! + 4!) + 8!)) - (0! - 4!)) \\ 408783 &:= (((3^8) \times 7) + ((8 + 0!)!)) - 4! \\ 408935 &:= ((5! \times 3!!) + (((9! - 8!) - 0!) - 4!)) \\ 408956 &:= (((6! \times 5!) + 9!) - 8!) + (0 - 4) \\ 408965 &:= (((((5! \times 6!) + 9!) - 8!) + 0!) + 4) \\ 408983 &:= ((3!! \times 8) + (((9! + 8!) - 0!) + 4!)) \\ 408984 &:= 4! + 8! + 9! + 8 \times (-0! + 4)! \\ 408996 &:= (6! + (9 \times ((9!/8) - (0 - 4)))) \\ 409416 &:= (((6^{(-1+4)!}) + 9!) - ((0! + 4)!)) \\ 409513 &:= (((3!^{1+5}) + 9!) + 0!) - 4! \\ 409533 &:= ((3! \times (3!^5)) + ((9! + 0!) - 4)) \\ 409536 &:= ((6^3!) + ((5 + ((9 \times 0) + 4)))!)) \\ 409566 &:= (((((6^6) + 5) + 9!) + 0!) + 4!) \\ 409575 &:= (((5! + 7) \times (5! + 9)) \times (0! + 4!)) \\ 409656 &:= ((6! \times 569) - (04)!) \\ 409824 &:= ((-(((4 + 2)^8)) + ((9 - 0!)!)/(-4)) \\ 410664 &:= (((4! \times ((6! - 6) - 0!)) - 1) \times 4!) \\ 410785 &:= ((5^8) - (7! \times ((0 \times 1) - 4))) \\ 411264 &:= (4! \times ((6! - ((2 + 1)!)) \times ((1 \times 4)!))) \\ 411864 &:= (((4 \times 6!) - 8!) \times (-11)) + 4! \\ 412344 &:= (((4! \times (-4 + 3!)) - (2 + 1)) \times 4!) \\ 412416 &:= (((6 + 1)! + ((4!)!/(21)!)) \times 4!) \\ 412464 &:= ((((-4 + 6!) \times 4!) + 2) \times ((1 \times 4)!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 412875 &:= (((-5 + 7!) \times 82) + (1 + 4)) \\ 413275 &:= (-5 - (7! \times (2 - (3! \times 14)))) \\ 413319 &:= (((9^{-1+3!}) \times (3! + 1)) - 4!) \\ 413367 &:= ((7 \times ((6 + 3)^{3!-1})) + 4!) \\ 413424 &:= (-(((4 + 2)!)) - (4! \times ((3!! - 1) \times (-4!)))) \\ 413426 &:= (-((6! - 2)) - (4! \times ((3!! - 1) \times (-4!)))) \\ 413526 &:= (((6^2) + 5)^3) \times (-((1 - 4)!)) \\ 413568 &:= (8! + (((6^5) \times (3 - 1)) \times 4!)) \\ 413655 &:= ((-5 \times ((-5 \times 6!) + 3)) \times (-1 + 4!)) \\ 413688 &:= (8! + ((8 \times (6^3!)) + ((1 + 4)!))!)) \\ 413769 &:= ((9^6) - (((7^3!) - 1) + 4!)) \\ 413784 &:= (4! \times (-((8 + 7)) - ((3!! - 1) \times (-4!)))) \\ 413904 &:= (4! \times (-((0! + 9)) - ((3!! - 1) \times (-4!)))) \\ 413928 &:= (((8/2)! \times (-9 - ((3!! - 1) \times (-4!)))) \\ 413996 &:= -(((6! - 9!) - ((9!/(3! + 1)) - 4)) \\ 414137 &:= (-7 - ((3!! - 1) \times ((4! \times (-1)) \times 4!))) \\ 414142 &:= (-2 - (4! \times ((-1 + (((4 - 1)!))!)) \times (-4!))) \\ 414144 &:= (4! \times ((4! \times (((1 + 4) + 1)!)) - 4!)) \\ 414164 &:= (-4 + (((6! - 1) \times 4!) + 1) \times 4!) \\ 414375 &:= ((-57) + 3!!) \times ((4 + 1)^4) \\ 414384 &:= ((-((4 - 8)))! \times ((3!! \times 4!) - 14)) \\ 414432 &:= ((-2 - (3!! \times (-4))) \times (4! + ((1 + 4)!)) \\ 414456 &:= ((-((6 + 5)) - (-4! \times (((4 - 1)!))!)) \times 4! \\ 414464 &:= (((4! \times 6!) \times 4!) - ((4 \times 1)^4)) \\ 414497 &:= (-7 + ((-9 - (-4! \times (((4 - 1)!))!)) \times 4!)) \\ 414528 &:= ((-8 + (((-((2 - 5)))!))! \times 4!)) \times ((1 \times 4)!)) \\ 414568 &:= (-8 - (-6 \times (((5! \times 4!) - 1) \times 4!))) \\ 414595 &:= (5 \times ((9! - 5!) - ((4! - 1)^4))) \\ 414624 &:= (((4!^2) \times 6!) + 4!) - ((1 + 4)!)) \\ 414632 &:= -(((2^3!) - (((6! \times 4!) - 1) \times 4!))) \\ 414634 &:= ((4! \times (-3 + (6! \times 4!))) - 14) \\ 414639 &:= (-9 - ((3 - (6! \times 4!)) \times ((1 \times 4)!))!)) \\ 414643 &:= (((-3 + (4! \times 6!)) \times 4!) - (1 + 4)) \\ 414644 &:= (-4 + (((4! \times 6!) - (4 - 1)) \times 4!)) \\ 414648 &:= (((8 \times 4!) \times 6!) - 4!) \times (-1 - 4) \\ 414664 &:= (-4 \times (((6! \times (-6)) \times 4!) + 14)) \\ 414672 &:= ((-2 - ((7! - 6!) \times (-4))) \times ((1 \times 4)!)) \\ 414684 &:= (-((4 + 8)) + (((6! \times 4!) - 1) \times 4!)) \\ 414688 &:= (8 \times (8! - (((6! \times (-4)) + 1) \times 4))) \\ 414693 &:= ((3! - 9) + (((6! \times 4!) - 1) \times 4!)) \\ 414695 &:= (((-((5 - 9)))! \times (6! \times 4!)) - (1 + 4!)) \\ 414696 &:= ((6! \times (9 \times 64)) - ((1 \times 4)!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 414714 &:= (((-4!) \times (-((1-7)))!) \times (-4!)) - (-((1-4)))! \\ 414715 &:= (-5 + (((-((1-7)))! \times (4! \times ((1 \times 4)!))) \\ 414716 &:= (((6! \times (-1-7)) \times 4!) - 1) \times 4 \\ 414724 &:= ((((((4+2))! - 7!) \times 4!) - 1) \times (-4)) \\ 414732 &:= ((-2 + (((3!! - 7!) \times 4!) - 1)) \times (-4)) \\ 414734 &:= ((4! \times ((3!! - 7!) \times (-4))) + 14) \\ 414735 &:= ((5 + ((3!! + 7!) \times 4!)) \times (-1-4)) \\ 414737 &:= (-7 - (((3!! - 7!) \times (-4)) + 1) \times (-4!)) \\ 414742 &:= (-2 + (((-4!) \times (((7-4)!))! - 1) \times (-4!)) \\ 414744 &:= (((4! \times 4!) \times (((7-4)!))! + ((1 \times 4)!)) \\ 414864 &:= (((4! \times 6!) + (((8/4) + 1)!)) \times 4! \\ 414867 &:= -((7! - (((6^8)/4) - 1) + 4)) \\ 415195 &:= (5 \times (9! - ((-1 + ((5-1)!^4))) \\ 415345 &:= ((5^4) + (3!! \times (((5-1)! \times 4!))) \\ 415416 &:= (((6! + 1) \times 4!) + 5) \times ((1 \times 4)!)) \\ 415435 &:= ((-5 + 3!!) + (((4! \times ((5+1)! \times 4!))) \\ 415436 &:= -(((6! \times ((3! \times (4! - 5!)) - 1)) + 4)) \\ 415464 &:= (((4! \times 6!) \times 4!) + ((5+1)!)) + 4! \\ 415488 &:= (8 \times (8! + (4! \times ((5! + 1) \times 4)))) \\ 415935 &:= (-5 \times ((3!! - 9) \times (-5! + ((1-4)))))) \\ 416305 &:= ((-((5! + 0!)) + 3!!) \times ((6! - 1) - 4!)) \\ 416424 &:= (((4!^2) \times ((4+6!) - 1)) - 4!) \\ 416444 &:= (((4! \times 4!) \times ((4+6!) - 1)) - 4) \\ 416448 &:= (((8-4)! \times (((4+6!) - 1) \times 4!)) \\ 416575 &:= (((5 \times (7^5)) - 6!) \times (1+4)) \\ 416826 &:= (62 \times ((8!/6) - ((1-4))) \\ 417384 &:= ((4! + (8!/3)) \times (7 + ((1 \times 4)!)) \\ 417456 &:= (((6! + 5) \times 4!) - (7-1)) \times 4! \\ 417596 &:= ((6! \times (9 + 571)) - 4) \\ 417624 &:= (((4! \times ((-2+6!) + 7)) + 1) \times 4! \\ 417738 &:= ((-83) \times (7-7!)) - (1^4) \\ 417792 &:= ((2^9) \times ((7!/(7-1)) - 4!)) \\ 418319 &:= ((9! - 1) - (3!! \times (-81-4))) \\ 418359 &:= (((9^5) + 3!!) \times (8-1)) - 4! \\ 419304 &:= (((4! \times ((-0!) + 3!!) + 9)) - 1) \times 4! \\ 419324 &:= 4!^2 \times (3!! + 9 - 1) - 4 \\ 419328 &:= (((8^2) \times 3) \times 91) \times 4! \\ 419392 &:= (-((2^9)) + ((3!^{9-1})/4)) \\ 419664 &:= (((4! - (6^6)) \times (-9)) - ((1 \times 4)!)) \\ 419833 &:= (((3!^{3!}) - 8) \times 9) + (1^4) \\ 419836 &:= (((6^{3!}) - 8) \times 9) + (1 \times 4) \\ 419906 &:= (((6^{-0!+9}) + (9-1))/4) \\ 419936 &:= (((6^{3!}) \times 9) + ((9-1) \times 4)) \\ 420576 &:= (((6! + (7^5)) - 0!) - 2) \times 4! \\ 420864 &:= (((4^6) + (8!/(0! + 2))) \times 4! \\ 421632 &:= (((-2+3!))! \times ((6! + 12) \times 4!)) \\ 421659 &:= (9 \times (((5^6) \times (1+2)) - 4!)) \\ 421959 &:= (((9^5) + 9!) + ((1+2)!)) + 4! \\ 422496 &:= (((6 \times 9!)/4!) + (((2+2)!^4)) \\ 422498 &:= (((8+9!)/4) + (((2+2)!^4)) \\ 422524 &:= (((4! + 2) \times (5^2))^2) + 4! \\ 422736 &:= -((6! - (3! \times (7! + (2^4)))))) \\ 422784 &:= (4! \times (((8! - 7!)/2) - (24))) \\ 423276 &:= ((6 \times 7) \times (-2 - (((3! + 2)!)/(-4))) \\ 423336 &:= (((((6+3)!)/3!) + ((3^2)!)) - 4!) \\ 423339 &:= (((9!/3!) + 3) + ((3^2)!)) - 4! \\ 423356 &:= ((6! \times ((-5!) + 3!!) - (3! \times 2))) - 4) \\ 423359 &:= (((9! \times (5! + 3!)) - 3!)/((2+4)!)) \\ 423378 &:= (((((8! - 7!) \times 3!) - 3) \times 2) + 4!) \\ 423379 &:= (((9! \times 7)/3!) + (3 + (2^4))) \\ 423384 &:= (4! + ((8! \times (3! + (3!^2)))/4)) \\ 423387 &:= (((((-7 \times 8!) \times (-3)) + 3!)/2) + 4!) \\ 423395 &:= ((5 + (9!/3!)) \times ((3!/2) + 4)) \\ 423397 &:= ((7 \times ((9!/3!) + 3)) + ((2^4))) \\ 423424 &:= (((4 \times 2)! + (4^{3!+2})) \times 4) \\ 423448 &:= (((8! \times 4) + (4^{3^2})) + 4!) \\ 423648 &:= (8! + ((4! \times (6! + 3!)) \times (-2 + 4!)) \\ 424536 &:= (((((6+3) + 5!) + 4)^2) \times 4!) \\ 424776 &:= ((6! \times ((7+7) + (4!^2))) - 4!) \\ 425185 &:= ((5^8) - (((1+5)! \times (-2)) \times 4!)) \\ 425496 &:= ((6! \times (-9 + (4! \times (5^2)))) - 4!) \\ 425516 &:= ((6! \times (1 + (5 \times (5! - 2)))) - 4) \\ 425664 &:= (4! \times ((6! - ((6 - (5^2)))) \times 4!)) \\ 425736 &:= (((6^3) + 7!) \times ((5-2)^4)) \\ 425778 &:= (87 \times (((7! - 5!) - 2) - 4!)) \\ 425785 &:= (((5^8) - 7!) - 5!) + ((2 \times 4)!)) \\ 425874 &:= ((4! - (7! \times ((8!/5!) + 2)))/(-4)) \\ 425875 &:= (-5 + ((7! \times ((8!/5!) + 2))/4)) \\ 425878 &:= ((8 - (7! \times ((8!/5!) + 2)))/(-4)) \\ 425984 &:= (((4^8)/(9-5)) \times (2+4!)) \\ 426236 &:= ((6! \times (3!! - ((2^6) \times 2))) - 4) \end{aligned}$$

- 426288 := -((8! - (((8!/2) - 6!) + 2) × 4!))
426596 := ((-((6! - 9)) × (5! - (((6/2)!))) - 4)
426956 := -(((6! × ((5! + 9) - 6!) - 2)) + 4)
427656 := (((6⁵) × (6 + (7²))) - 4!)
427975 := ((-5 + 7!) × ((9 + 72) + 4))
427995 := (-5 × ((9 × (9 - 7!)) - ((2 × 4)!))
428373 := (-3 + ((7! × (3 + 82)) - 4!))
428376 := ((6! × (7 × (3 + 82))) - 4!)
428389 := ((9 × (8! - 3)) + ((8 × 2)⁴)
428397 := ((7! + 9!) + ((3! × (8! - 2))/4)
428408 := (((8 + 0!))! + ((4⁸) - (2 × 4)))
428409 := ((9! + 0!) + (((4⁸) - (2 × 4))))
428416 := (((6 - 1) + 4)! + (((8 × 2)⁴)))
428418 := (((8 + 1))! + (((4⁸) - 2) + 4))
428419 := (9! + (1 + (((4⁸) - 2) + 4)))
428439 := ((9! - (3 - ((4⁸) + 2))) + 4!)
428459 := ((9! - (5 - (4⁸))) + (2 × 4!))
428536 := (((6 + 3)! + 5!) + (((8 × 2)⁴)))
428539 := (((9! + 3) + 5!) + (((8 × 2)⁴)))
428544 := (4! × (((-4 - 5!) × (-8 - 2))) × 4!))
428796 := ((-((6 × 9) + 7!) × (82 + 4))
429337 := ((73^{-3!+9}) + ((2 × 4)!))
429864 := (-4 × (6 + (((8!/(-9)) + 2) × 4!))
429888 := ((-8 - ((8 × 8!)/(-9 × 2))) × 4!)
429984 := (4! × (((8! + 9)/(-9)) + 2) × (-4))
430276 := (-4 × (((3! + 0!))! × 2) - (7⁶))
430316 := (((6! + 1) - ((3! - 0!))!) × (3!! - 4))
430332 := (((-(2^{3!})) + 3!!)^{-0!+3} - 4)
430336 := (((-(63) + 3!!) - 0!)^{3!-4})
430536 := (((((6! - 3) - 5!) + 0!) × 3!!) - 4!)
430556 := ((6! × ((5! × 5) + 0!) - 3) - 4)
430656 := (((6! - 5!) × (6! - 0!)) - 3!!) - 4!)
430848 := ((8 × 4) × ((8!/03) + 4!))
431032 := ((2 × 301) × (3!! - 4))
431256 := (((6! - 5!) - (2 - 1)) × 3!!) - 4!)
431276 := (((6! - ((7 - 2)!)) - 1) × 3!!) - 4)
431304 := -(((((((4 + 0!))! - 3!!) + 1) × 3!!) - 4!))
431325 := ((5²) × (-3 - ((1 - 3!!) × 4!))
431424 := -(((4!²) + (((4 + 1)!)³)/(-4)))
431425 := ((5²) × (-((4! - 1)) + (3!! × 4!))
431496 := (-6!) + ((9 - (-((4! + 1) × 3!!)) × 4!))
431515 := (-5 × (1 + ((5! × (1 - 3!!)) - 4!))
431525 := ((5²) × (5 - ((1 - 3!!) × 4!))
431535 := (-5 × (-3 + ((5! × (1 - 3!!)) - 4!))
431664 := (46 × ((6! × 13) + 4!))
431825 := ((5²) × (-((8 - 1)) + (3!! × 4!))
431952 := (2 × (((59 + 1)³) - 4!))
431975 := ((5⁻⁷⁺⁹) × (-1 + (3!! × 4!))
431996 := (((6! × (9 + 91)) × 3!) - 4)
432024 := (4! + (((((2 + 0!) + 2)!³)/4))
432025 := ((5²) × (0! + (((2 × 3)! × 4!))
432045 := (-5 + ((4! + 0!) × (2 + (3!! × 4!))))
432354 := (((4! - (5³)) - (2 × 3!))/(-4))
432355 := (-5 - (((5³)) - (2 × 3!))/4))
432356 := (((6! × 5) + 3) × ((2 + 3)! - 4)
432358 := (((-8 + (5³)) + (2 × 3!))/4)
432456 := (((6! × 5) + 4) × ((2 + 3)! - 4!)
432576 := (((6 + 7)!/(5!²)) + (3! × 4!))
432716 := (((6! + 1) - ((7 - 2)!)) × 3!!) - 4)
432864 := (((4 + 6)!/8) - ((2 × 3!)⁴)
432869 := (9! + (((6⁸) + ((2 + 3)!)/4!))
433053 := (((3!! - ((5! + 0!))) × (3!! + 3)) - 4!)
433268 := 86 × (-2 + (3! - 3 + 4)!)
433539 := (9 × ((3 × (5^{3!})) + (3!⁴)))
433561 := (((1 - 6!) × ((5! - 3!!) - 3)) + 4)
433587 := (-7 × ((-85) × (3^{3!})) + 4!))
433656 := (((6! - 5!) × (6! + 3) - (3! × 4!))
433689 := (-9 - (-86) × (3 + ((3 + 4)!)))
433752 := (((2 × 5!) + (7³)) × (3!! + 4!))
433896 := ((6 × (98 + 3)) × (3!! - 4))
434093 := (((3!! × 9) - 0!) × (43 + 4!))
434136 := (((6! + 3) - ((1 + 4)!)) × 3!!) - 4!)
434156 := ((6! × ((5! × (1 + 4)) + 3)) - 4)
434256 := ((-6 - ((5²) × (-4 - 3!))) × 4!)
434304 := (((4 + ((03)!))! × 4!) + 3!!) × 4!)
434325 := ((5²) × (-3 + ((-4 - 3!!) × (-4!))))
434424 := (((4!²) + 4!) × (4 + 3!)) + 4!)
434448 := (((8!/4) + 4!) × 43) - 4!)
434488 := (-8 - ((-8 - (4! × 4!)) × (3!! + 4!))
434515 := (-5 × (1 + ((5! × (-4 - 3!!)) - 4!))
434525 := ((5²) × (5 + ((-4 - 3!!) × (-4!))
434535 := (-5 × (-3 + ((5! × (-4 - 3!!)) - 4!))

$$\begin{aligned} 434592 &:= ((-2 + ((9!/5!) - 4)) \times (3! \times 4!)) \\ 434596 &:= (((-6 + (9!/5!)) \times (4! \times 3!)) + 4) \\ 434736 &:= ((6^{3!}) + (7! \times (-4 - (3^4)))) \\ 434856 &:= (((6! - 5!) + (8 - 4)) \times 3!!) - 4! \\ 435025 &:= ((5^2) \times (0! + ((-5 - 3!!) \times (-4!)))) \\ 435116 &:= (((6 - 1)!) + 1) \times ((5 \times 3!!) - 4) \\ 435124 &:= (((((4 + 2))!) + 1) - 5!) \times (3!! + 4) \\ 435276 &:= (-6 \times (((((7 + 2))!) / (-5)) + 3!) + 4!) \\ 435328 &:= (8 + (2 \times 3!) - 5!) \times (3!! - 4) \\ 435339 &:= (((-((9! \times 3!)) + 3!!) / (-5)) + (3 + 4!)) \\ 435362 &:= (((-2 - 6!) \times ((-3 + 5!) - 3!!)) - 4) \\ 435366 &:= ((6 + (6! \times 3)) \times (5! + ((3^4)))) \\ 435384 &:= ((4 + ((8! \times (-3)) / 5)) \times (3! - 4!)) \\ 435392 &:= ((2^9) - (3!! \times ((5! - 3!!) - 4))) \\ 435393 &:= (((3!! - ((9! \times 3!))) / (-5)) + ((3^4))) \\ 435429 &:= (((9! \times (-2 + 4)) / (-5)) - 3) - 4! \\ 435432 &:= (((((2 + 3) + 4))! / 5) \times 3!) - 4! \\ 435435 &:= ((5 - 3!!) \times ((4! + 5) \times (3 - 4!))) \\ 435438 &:= (((8! \times (3!^4)) / 5!) + (3! - 4!)) \\ 435448 &:= (-8 + (((4 + 4))! / 5!) \times (3!^4)) \\ 435449 &:= (((9! \times 4!) / (4 \times 5)) - (3 + 4)) \\ 435451 &:= (-1 + (((((5 + 4))! / 5) \times 3!) - 4)) \\ 435452 &:= (((2 \times ((5 + 4))! / 5) \times 3) - 4) \\ 435453 &:= (-3 + (((((5 + 4))! / 5!) \times 3!) \times 4!)) \\ 435455 &:= (-5 - (((((5 + 4))! / (-5)) \times 3!) - 4)) \\ 435458 &:= (((8! \times (-54)) / (-5)) + 3!) + 4) \\ 435468 &:= (((8! \times (6^4)) / 5!) + (3 \times 4)) \\ 435492 &:= (((2 + ((9! \times 4!) / 5!)) \times 3!) + 4!) \\ 435496 &:= (((((-6 - 9!) - 4!) / (-5)) \times 3!) + 4) \\ 435556 &:= ((6 + 5) \times ((55 \times 3!!) - 4)) \\ 435566 &:= ((((-6 - 6!) \times 5!) \times (-5)) - 34) \\ 435568 &:= (-8 + (((6! + 5) - 5!) \times 3!!) - 4!) \\ 435569 &:= (((9! \times (-6)) / (-5)) + 5!) - (3 + 4) \\ 435576 &:= (((6^7) + 5!) + (5! \times (3!^4))) \\ 435592 &:= (2 \times (((9! + 5!) / (-5)) \times (-3)) - 4) \\ 435593 &:= (-3 + (((9! + 5!) / 5) \times 3!) - 4) \\ 435594 &:= (((4! - ((9! / (-5)) + 5)) \times 3!) + 4!) \\ 435595 &:= (-5 + (((9! + 5!) / 5!) \times 3!) \times 4!) \\ 435596 &:= (((((6! + 9!) / 5) - 5!) \times 3!) - 4) \\ 435597 &:= (-7 + (((9! + 5!) / 5) \times 3!) + 4) \\ 435599 &:= ((9! + ((9! - 5) / 5)) + (3! \times 4!)) \\ 435604 &:= (((((4 + 0!) + 6!) - 5!) \times 3!!) + 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 435605 &:= ((5 \times (0! + 6!)) - ((5!^3) / (-4))) \\ 435615 &:= (-5 \times (((1 - (6! \times 5!)) - 3!!) - 4)) \\ 435624 &:= (((((4 \times 2))! - 6!) \times (5 + 3!)) + 4!) \\ 435635 &:= (5 \times (((3! + 6!) \times 5!) + (3 + 4))) \\ 435636 &:= (-6 \times (((((3 + 6))! / (-5)) - 3!) - 4!)) \\ 435648 &:= (8 \times (4! + (((6^5) \times (3 + 4)))) \\ 435688 &:= (((8 + 8!) - 6!) \times ((5 \times 3) - 4)) \\ 435775 &:= ((-5 + 7!) - ((7! - (5!^3)) / 4)) \\ 435864 &:= (((4! - 6!) + 8!) \times ((5 \times 3) - 4)) \\ 435918 &:= (((81 - (9! / (-5))) \times 3!) - 4!) \\ 435936 &:= (-6 + (3! \times ((9! / 5) + ((3^4)))) \\ 435942 &:= ((2 + 4) \times ((9! / 5) + ((3^4)))) \\ 435955 &:= (-5 - (5! \times (-9 - ((5 \times 3!!) + 4!)))) \\ 435968 &:= (86 + 9! / 5) \times 3! - 4 \\ 435985 &:= ((5^8) - 9! / (-((5 - 3) \times 4))) \\ 435988 &:= (((88 - (9! / (-5))) \times 3!) + 4) \\ 435992 &:= ((2^9) - (((9! / (-5)) \times 3!) - 4!)) \\ 435996 &:= (-6 \times (-9 + ((9! / (-5)) - ((3^4)))) \\ 436176 &:= (((-((6! + 7)) \times ((-((1 - 6)))! - 3!!)) - 4!) \\ 436239 &:= -(((9^3!) - (((2^{6-3}))! \times 4!)) \\ 436248 &:= ((8 + (4!^2)) \times ((6! + 3) + 4!)) \\ 436316 &:= (((-(((6 - 1)!) - 3!) - 6!)) \times 3!!) - 4) \\ 436319 &:= ((9! - 1) - ((-3 \times 6!) \times 34)) \\ 436344 &:= (4! + (((4!^3) + 6!) \times (3! + 4!)) \\ 436391 &:= (-1 - ((93 - 6!) \times (3!! - 4!)) \\ 436536 &:= (-((6^3)) \times ((-5 - 6!) - (3!^4))) \\ 436545 &:= (545 \times (6! + ((3^4)))) \\ 436675 &:= (((-((5^7)) - 6!) + (6! \times (3!! - 4))) \\ 437036 &:= (((6! - ((3! - 0!))!) + 7) \times 3!!) - 4) \\ 437044 &:= (((4! \times (4! + 0!)) + 7) \times 3!!) + 4) \\ 437062 &:= (-2 + ((607 \times 3!!) + 4!)) \\ 437157 &:= (((-((7 \times 51)) - 7!) \times (-3^4)) \\ 437184 &:= (4! \times (((-81) + (7! / 3!)) \times 4!)) \\ 437293 &:= (-((3^9)) + ((2 + ((7 - 3))!)^4)) \\ 437356 &:= ((((-6 + (5^3!)) \times (-7)) - 3!) \times (-4)) \\ 437436 &:= ((6 + (3^4)) \times (7! - (3 \times 4))) \\ 437476 &:= (((6 + 7) \times 47) \times (3!! - 4)) \\ 437568 &:= (86 \times ((5! + 7!) + (-3 \times 4!)) \\ 437688 &:= ((8 \times (8! - 6!)) + ((7! - 3) \times 4!)) \\ 437782 &:= (((-2 - (-87) \times 7!)) - 3!!) + 4! \\ 437871 &:= (((1 + 7!) \times 87) - 3!!) + 4! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 437888 &:= (-88) \times ((-8 - 7!) - (-3 \times 4!)) \\ 437954 &:= -((((4! - 5!) + 9) \times (7! - 3!)) + 4) \\ 437982 &:= ((-(2 - 89)) \times (7! - 3!)) + 4! \\ 438336 &:= (((6^3!) \times 3!) - ((-8!) + 3!!) \times 4) \\ 438417 &:= (((7! - 1) \times (4 + 83)) + 4!) \\ 438447 &:= -((7! - ((44 \times (8! - 3))/4)) \\ 438456 &:= -(((6! \times (5! - ((4!/8)^{3!}))) + 4!)) \\ 438473 &:= (-3 + ((7! \times (4 + 83)) - 4)) \\ 438475 &:= (-5 + (((7 + 4) \times 8!) - ((3 + 4)!)) \\ 438476 &:= ((6! \times (7 \times (4 + 83))) - 4) \\ 438477 &:= (-7 + ((7! \times (4 + 83)) + 4)) \\ 438524 &:= (((((4 \times 2)^5) + 8!) \times 3!) - 4) \\ 438532 &:= (((((2^3)^5) + 8!) \times 3!) + 4) \\ 438535 &:= (((5 + 3!) \times (5 + 8!)) - ((3 + 4)!)) \\ 438537 &:= -((7! - (((3! + 5) \times (8! + 3)) + 4!)) \\ 438567 &:= ((7! + (6 - 5)) \times (83 + 4)) \\ 438616 &:= ((616 \times (-8 + 3!)) + 4!) \\ 438696 &:= (((6! + 9!) - (6^8))/(-3)) + 4! \\ 438741 &:= (((1 - 4) - 7!) \times (-83 + 4)) \\ 438742 &:= (-2 + (-((4! + (7!/(-8)))) \times (3!! + 4))) \\ 438946 &:= (-((6 - ((4 + (9 \times 8))^3))) - 4!) \\ 439292 &:= (29 \times (-2 + ((9! + 3!)/4!)) \\ 439337 &:= (-7 + (339 \times (3!^4))) \\ 439488 &:= ((8! - (-((8 + 4) \times 9!))/(3! + 4)) \\ 439563 &:= (((3 + 6!) - 5!) \times (9^3)) - 4! \\ 439855 &:= ((5 + (5! \times 8!))/(9 + 3!) - 4) \\ 439872 &:= ((2 - (7!/(-8))) \times ((9 - 3)! - 4!)) \\ 440275 &:= (-((5^7)) + (((2 + 0!)!)! \times ((4!/4)!)) \\ 440975 &:= (((5^7) + 9!) - (((0! + 4)!/4)) \\ 441936 &:= (((6^3!) - (9! \times (1 + 4)))/(-4)) \\ 442344 &:= (((4! + 4!)^3) - (2 + 4)) \times 4 \\ 442384 &:= (((48^3) - 2) \times 4) + 4! \\ 442392 &:= (((2^9) \times ((3!^2) \times 4!)) + 4!) \\ 442464 &:= (4! \times (((6! + (4! \times 2)) \times 4!) + 4)) \\ 442536 &:= -((6! - ((3! + 5) \times ((2 \times 4)! - 4!))) \\ 442656 &:= (((((6 + 5)!/6!) \times 2) + (4!^4)) \\ 442688 &:= (((8! - (8^6))/(-2)) + (4!^4)) \\ 442773 &:= ((3!! - 7) \times (((7 - 2)^4) - 4)) \\ 442793 &:= -((3!! - ((9! - 7) - (-2 \times ((4 + 4)!)))) \\ 442796 &:= -((((6! - 9!) + ((7! \times (-2^4))) + 4)) \\ 442816 &:= (((6 + 1)! - 8) \times (2 \times 44)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 442848 &:= -((8! + (4! \times (((8!/(-2)) + 4) + 4!))) \\ 442896 &:= -(((6! - 9!) + (((8!/(-2)) - 4!) \times 4)) \\ 442944 &:= (((4!^4)/(9 \times 2)) + 4!) \times 4! \\ 443256 &:= ((6 + 5) \times ((((-2 + 3!) + 4)! - 4!)) \\ 443344 &:= ((((-((4!^4)) - 3!)/(-3)) + 4) \times 4) \\ 443388 &:= ((8! \times (8 + 3)) - (3 \times 44)) \\ 443424 &:= (((4! - 2) \times ((4 + 3)! - 4!) \times 4) \\ 443448 &:= (((8! \times 4) - 4!) \times 3) - ((4 + 4)!)) \\ 443472 &:= (2 \times (((((7 + 4)!/3!)) \times 4) - 4!)) \\ 443478 &:= (((8! \times (7 + 4)) + 3!) - 4!) - 4! \\ 443483 &:= (((3 - 8!) \times (-((4 + 3) + 4))) - 4) \\ 443487 &:= ((7 - 8!) - 4) \times (-((3 + 4) + 4)) \\ 443488 &:= (-8 + ((8! \times ((4 + 3) + 4)) - 4!)) \\ 443492 &:= (((2 + 9) \times ((4!/3)!)) - (4! + 4)) \\ 443496 &:= (-((6 - 94)) \times ((3 + 4)! - 4!)) \\ 443508 &:= (((8! - 0!) \times (5 + 3!)) - (4/4)) \\ 443513 &:= -(((3! + 1) + ((-5 - 3!) \times ((4 + 4)!))) \\ 443514 &:= -((((4 - 1)! + ((-5 - 3!) \times ((4 + 4)!))) \\ 443515 &:= (-5 - (-((1 \times 5) - 3!) \times ((4 + 4)!)) \\ 443521 &:= ((1^2) - ((-5 - 3!) \times ((4 + 4)!)) \\ 443523 &:= ((3!/2) - ((-5 - 3!) \times ((4 + 4)!)) \\ 443524 &:= (((4 \times 2)! \times ((5 \times 3) - 4)) + 4) \\ 443526 &:= (((6/2)! - ((-5 - 3!) \times ((4 + 4)!)) \\ 443531 &:= ((-1 - ((3 + 5)!)) \times (-((3 + 4) + 4))) \\ 443532 &:= ((2 \times 3!) - ((-5 - 3!) \times ((4 + 4)!)) \\ 443535 &:= ((5 \times 3) - ((-5 - 3!) \times ((4 + 4)!)) \\ 443538 &:= ((8! \times (3! + 5)) + ((-3 \times 4!)/(-4))) \\ 443542 &:= ((-2 + 4!) - ((-5 - 3!) \times ((4 + 4)!)) \\ 443544 &:= (((4 + 4)! \times ((5 \times 3) - 4)) + 4!) \\ 443548 &:= (((8! \times (-4 - (5 \times 3))) + 4) + 4!) \\ 443552 &:= ((2^5) - ((-5 - 3!) \times ((4 + 4)!)) \\ 443553 &:= (((3!/5!) + 5) \times (3 + ((4 + 4)!)) \\ 443568 &:= ((8! \times (6 + 5)) + ((3 \times 4) \times 4)) \\ 443583 &:= (((3 - 8!) \times (-5 - 3!)) - (4! \times (-4))) \\ 443584 &:= (((4 + 8!) \times (5 + 3!)) + (4! - 4)) \\ 443585 &:= (5! - ((8! - 5) \times (-((3 + 4) + 4))) \\ 443586 &:= ((6 + 8!) \times (-5 - ((3 \times 4) + 4))) \\ 443588 &:= (8 + 8!) \times (5 + 3!) - 4! + 4 \\ 443616 &:= ((616 \times 3!) - (4! \times (-4))) \\ 443688 &:= -((8! + (((8! + 6) \times (-3)) - 4!) \times 4)) \\ 443777 &:= (-7 - (((7! + 7!) + 3!) \times (-44)) \\ 443784 &:= ((4! + 8!) \times (7 - ((3 - 4) \times 4))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 443808 &:= (- (8!) - (((-((0! - 8)))! + 3) \times (4! \times (-4)))) \\ 443828 &:= ((8! + (28)) \times ((3 + 4) + 4)) \\ 443874 &:= (((4 + 7) \times ((8! + 3!) + 4!)) + 4!) \\ 444343 &:= (((3!! \times (-4!)) \times 3!!) - 4) / (-4 - 4!) \\ 444488 &:= (((8 - 8!) / (-4)) + 4!) \times 44 \\ 444672 &:= (((((2^7) \times 6) + 4) \times 4!) \times 4!) \\ 444851 &:= (((1 + 5!) + 8!) \times (44/4)) \\ 444956 &:= ((6! \times (594 + 4!)) - 4) \\ 444972 &:= (((2 \times 7!) + 9) + 4!) \times 44 \\ 445138 &:= -(((8^3!) - 1) - ((5 + 4!)^4)) \\ 445332 &:= (((-2 \times 3!) + 3!!) \times ((5^4) + 4)) \\ 445536 &:= ((6! - 3!) \times (-5 - ((5^4) + 4))) \\ 445625 &:= ((-(5 + 2) + 6!) \times ((5!/4!)^4)) \\ 445629 &:= (((-(9 - 2)) + 6!) \times (5^4)) + 4 \\ 445656 &:= (((-6 \times 5!) \times (6 - (5^4))) - 4!) \\ 445668 &:= (-8 - ((6! \times (6 - (5^4))) + 4)) \\ 445676 &:= ((6! - 7!) - ((6! \times (-5^4))) + 4)) \\ 445684 &:= (((((4!/8)!)!) \times (-6 - (5^4)))) + 4 \\ 445824 &:= (4! \times (((-((2 - 8)))! + 54) \times 4!)) \\ 445875 &:= (((5! - 7!) / (-8)) \times (5 + ((4!/4)!)!) \\ 445944 &:= (((4!^4) - (9! + 5!) \times (-4)) / 4) \\ 446256 &:= (((6! - 5) \times 26) + 4) \times 4! \\ 446325 &:= (-((5^2)) \times (3 - ((6! + 4!) \times 4!))) \\ 446395 &:= (((-5 - 9!) - 3!!) + ((6!/4!)^4)) \\ 446424 &:= (((4!^2) + 4!) \times (6! + 4!)) + 4! \\ 446448 &:= (((8!/4!) + 4!) \times (6 + (4^4))) \\ 446464 &:= (((4^6)/4 + 6!) \times (4^4)) \\ 446468 &:= (((8^6) + 4) + (6! \times (4^4))) \\ 446515 &:= (-5 \times (1 - ((5! \times (6! + 4!)) + 4!))) \\ 446525 &:= (-((5^2)) \times (-5 - ((6! + 4!) \times 4!))) \\ 446535 &:= (-5 \times (-3 - ((5! \times (6! + 4!)) + 4!))) \\ 446555 &:= (((5! \times 5!) + 5) \times ((6! + 4!) / 4!)) \\ 446925 &:= (((5! - 2) \times (9! + 6!)) / (4! \times 4)) \\ 446976 &:= ((6! \times ((7! / (-9)) + 6!)) + (4!^4)) \\ 447119 &:= -(((9! + 1) - (((1 - 7)) + 4!)^4)) \\ 447552 &:= ((((-((2 - 5)))!)! + 57) \times (4! \times 4!)) \\ 447576 &:= (((6 \times 7!) / (-5)) \times (-74)) + 4! \\ 447744 &:= (((4! \times 4) + 7!) + 7!) \times 44 \\ 447835 &:= (-5 - (3!! \times (8 - (7! / (4 + 4)))))) \\ 447836 &:= ((6! \times 3!) - ((8! \times (-7 + 4))) + 4) \\ 447864 &:= (4! - (6! \times (8 - (7! / (4 + 4)))))) \\ 447982 &:= ((-2 + (89 \times 7!)) - (4! \times 4!)) \\ 447984 &:= (4! \times (((89 \times 7!) / 4!) - 4!)) \\ 448362 &:= (2 + 6!) \times ((-3 + 8)^4 - 4) \\ 448539 &:= ((9! + ((3 \times ((5 + 8)^4)))) - 4!) \\ 448555 &:= (-5 - (((5 + 5!)! - 8!) / (-4 + 4))) \\ 448577 &:= (-7 + ((7! \times (5 + 84)) + 4!)) \\ 449232 &:= ((-2 - (3!! \times (-2 \times (9 + 4)))) \times 4!) \\ 449236 &:= (((6! \times ((3 + 2)!) + 9!) - 44) \\ 449276 &:= ((6! \times ((72 \times 9) - 4!)) - 4) \\ 449526 &:= (((6! + 2) \times 5!) + 9!) + (4! / 4) \\ 449533 &:= (-3 - ((3!! \times (-5!)) - (9! + (4^4)))) \\ 449534 &:= -(((4^3!) - (-5 \times ((9! + 4!) / (-4)))) \\ 449536 &:= (((((6 - 3)!)! \times 5!) + (9! + (4^4))) \\ 449836 &:= (((((6^3!) + 8!) + 9!) - 4!) + 4) \\ 449856 &:= (((6! \times 5!) - (8! \times (-9))) + (4! \times 4!)) \\ 449935 &:= (-5 \times (3!! - (-9 + ((9! / 4) - 4))) \\ 450024 &:= (4! - (((2 + 0!)!)! \times (0 - (5^4)))) \\ 450339 &:= (9! - (((-3 - 3!!) \times (0! + 5!)) + 4!)) \\ 450364 &:= ((4 - 6!) \times ((-3 - 0!) - ((5^4))) \\ 450505 &:= (-5!) - (((0!) - ((5 + 0!)!) \times (5^4))) \\ 450617 &:= (-((7 + 1) + ((6! + 0!) \times (5^4))) \\ 450618 &:= (-((8 - 1) + ((6! + 0!) \times (5^4))) \\ 450625 &:= (((5 - 2)!)! + ((6 \times 0)!) \times (5^4)) \\ 450631 &:= (((1 \times 3)!) + ((6! + 0!) \times (5^4))) \\ 450643 &:= -(((3! - 4!) - ((6! + 0!) \times (5^4))) \\ 450645 &:= ((5 \times 4) + ((6! + 0!) \times (5^4))) \\ 450654 &:= ((4! + 5) + ((6! + 0!) \times (5^4))) \\ 450667 &:= ((7 \times 6) + ((6! + 0!) \times (5^4))) \\ 450693 &:= (-((3 \times 9) + (6! \times (0! + ((5^4)))))) \\ 450696 &:= ((6! + 9!) + ((6! \times (0! + 5!)) - 4!)) \\ 450715 &:= (-5 - (((1 - 7)!)! \times (-0! + ((5^4)))))) \\ 450744 &:= (4! + (((-((4 - 7)))!)! \times (0! + ((5^4)))))) \\ 450745 &:= (5! - ((((-((4 - 7)))!)! + 0!) \times (-5^4))) \\ 451345 &:= ((5^4) + (3!! \times (1 + (5^4)))) \\ 451346 &:= ((6! + (4 - 3)) \times (1 + (5^4))) \\ 451385 &:= (((-5 + 8!) + 3!!) \times (15 - 4)) \\ 451467 &:= ((-7 - 6!) \times (4 - ((1 \times 5^4))) \\ 451584 &:= (4 \times ((8! / 5!)^{1+5-4})) \\ 451588 &:= (((8! \times 8!) / 5) / ((1 + 5)!) + 4) \\ 452384 &:= (-((4^8)) + ((3!!^2) + (5! \times (-4)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 452399 &:= ((9! - 9) - ((3!! + 2) \times (- (5! + 4)))) \\ 452694 &:= (((4! + 9) \times (6! + 2)) \times (-5 + 4!)) \\ 452695 &:= (-5 + (((9! - (((6/2)!)!) \times 5)/4)) \\ 452696 &:= (((6! - 9!)/(- (6 - 2))) \times 5) - 4 \\ 452698 &:= ((-8 + ((9! - (((6/2)!)!) \times 5))/4) \\ 452736 &:= ((6 \times 3!) \times (((7!/2) \times 5) - 4!)) \\ 452835 &:= (((5^{3!}) - (8 + 2)) \times (5 + 4!)) \\ 452876 &:= ((-6 \times (7! - ((8! \times 2) - 5!))) - 4) \\ 452975 &:= (((-5 \times 7!) \times (- (9 \times 2))) - ((5^4))) \\ 453024 &:= ((4! + 2) \times (((0! + 3!!) + 5) \times 4!)) \\ 453125 &:= ((5 + (((2 \times 1) \times 3)!) \times (5^4)) \\ 453276 &:= (-6 \times (((7! - 2) \times (- (3 \times 5))) + 4!)) \\ 453344 &:= (-((4^4)) + (((3 \times 3)!) \times 5)/4) \\ 453352 &:= (((2 - (5 \times 3!!)) \times (- (3! + 5!))) + 4) \\ 453456 &:= (((6!/5) \times 4!) - (3!! \times (- (5^4)))) \\ 453459 &:= (((((9! \times 5)/4) + 3) - 5!) - 4!) \\ 453476 &:= (((((6! \times 7!)/4!) \times 3) - 5!) - 4) \\ 453489 &:= ((9 \times (((8!/4) - 3) \times 5)) + 4!) \\ 453495 &:= ((-5 \times ((9!/(-4) - 3)) + (-5 \times 4!)) \\ 453509 &:= (((4! + 5) + 3!!) \times (5! + 0!)) + 9! \\ 453509 &:= (9! + ((0! + 5!) \times (3!! + (5 + 4!)))) \\ 453546 &:= (((6 + 4)!/(5 + 3)) - (54)) \\ 453549 &:= (((9!/(-4)) \times (-5)) + ((3 - 54))) \\ 453566 &:= (((6! \times (6 + 5!)) - 3!) \times 5) - 4 \\ 453568 &:= (-8 - ((6! \times ((5! + 3!) \times (-5))) + 4!)) \\ 453591 &:= (((1 + 9)!/(5 + 3)) - (5 + 4)) \\ 453592 &:= (2 - (((9! - (5 + 3)) \times 5)/(-4))) \\ 453593 &:= (((3! - 9!) \times (-5)) - ((3 - 5)))/4 \\ 453594 &:= (-4 + (((9! \times 5) - (3 + 5))/4)) \\ 453595 &:= (((5 \times 9!) - ((5 \times 3) + 5))/4) \\ 453596 &:= (((((6 + 9) - 5)!/(3 + 5)) - 4) \\ 453597 &:= (7 - (((9! - (5 + 3)) \times 5)/(-4))) \\ 453598 &:= (((8! \times (9 \times 5)) - (3 + 5))/4) \\ 453599 &:= (9! - (((9! - 5) + 3!) - 5)/(-4)) \\ 453611 &:= (11 + (((6 + 3)!) \times 5)/4) \\ 453615 &:= (-5 \times (1 - ((6! \times (3! + 5!)) + 4))) \\ 453622 &:= (22 + (((6 + 3)!) \times 5)/4) \\ 453624 &:= (((-42) \times 6!) \times (- (3 \times 5))) + 4! \\ 453625 &:= ((5^2) + (((6 + 3)!) \times 5)/4) \\ 453633 &:= (33 + (((6 + 3)!) \times 5)/4) \\ 453635 &:= (-5 \times (-3 - ((6! \times (3! + 5!)) + 4))) \\ 453636 &:= ((6 \times 3!) + (((6 + 3)!) \times 5)/4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 453644 &:= (44 + (((6 + 3)!) \times 5)/4) \\ 453645 &:= (((((5 + 4)!) + (6 \times 3!)) \times (-5))/(-4)) \\ 453648 &:= (((8 \times 4!) + (((6 + 3)!) \times 5))/4) \\ 453649 &:= (((9!/4) + (6 + 3)) \times 5) + 4 \\ 453654 &:= (4! - ((5 \times ((6 + 3)!) + 5!)/(-4))) \\ 453655 &:= (55 + (((6 + 3)!) \times 5)/4) \\ 453666 &:= (66 + (((6 + 3)!) \times 5)/4) \\ 453675 &:= ((5 + (7! \times 6)) \times (3! + (5 + 4))) \\ 453677 &:= (77 + (((6 + 3)!) \times 5)/4) \\ 453687 &:= (((7!/8) \times 6!) + (3 \times (5 + 4))) \\ 453688 &:= (88 + (((6 + 3)!) \times 5)/4) \\ 453689 &:= ((-((9 - 8)) + 6!) \times (3! + ((5^4)))) \\ 453696 &:= (-((6 \times 9)) + ((6! + 3!) \times (5^4))) \\ 453699 &:= (99 + (((6 + 3)!) \times 5)/4) \\ 453714 &:= (4! + (((1 + 7!) \times 3) \times 5!)/4) \\ 453735 &:= ((5 \times 3) \times ((7! \times 3!) + (5 + 4))) \\ 453737 &:= (-7 - (3! \times ((7! \times (- (3 \times 5))) - 4!)) \\ 453739 &:= (((9 + (3! \times 7!)) \times (3 \times 5)) + 4) \\ 453744 &:= ((4!/4) \times ((7! \times (3 \times 5)) + 4!)) \\ 453745 &:= (-5 - (((-((4 - 7)))! + 3!!) \times (- (5^4)))) \\ 453746 &:= (((6!/4!) \times ((7! \times 3) + 5)) - 4) \\ 453754 &:= (4 + ((5 - (7! \times (-3))) \times (5!/4))) \\ 453774 &:= (4! - (((7!/7) + 3!) \times (- (5^4))) \\ 453793 &:= (((3 \times 9) \times ((7!/3!)^5)) + 4) \\ 453819 &:= (((((9 + 1)!/8) + ((3^5))) - 4! \\ 453825 &:= (((5 \times 2) \times 8!) + (((3 \times 5)^4))) \\ 453843 &:= (((3! + 4)!/8) + ((3^{5!/4}))) \\ 453849 &:= (((9! + 4!) + 8!) + (((3 \times 5)^4)) \\ 453864 &:= (((4 + 6)!/8) + ((3! + 5) \times 4!)) \\ 453867 &:= (((7! \times 6!)/8) + ((3^5)) + 4!) \\ 453874 &:= (((-4 - (7!/(-8))) \times (3!! + 5)) + 4!) \\ 453905 &:= (-5 \times (((0! + 9!) + ((3^5)))/(-4)) \\ 453924 &:= (-((4!^2) - (((9! + 3!!) \times 5)/(-4))) \\ 453985 &:= (((5^8) + (9!/3!)) + (5! \times 4!)) \\ 453996 &:= ((6! + 9!) + ((9^3) \times (5! + 4))) \\ 454225 &:= (((5 \times 2)!/(2 \times 4)) + ((5^4))) \\ 454319 &:= (((9! - 1) + 3!!) + (((4 + 5)!/4)) \\ 454356 &:= (((-6 - 5!) \times 3!) \times (4! - ((5^4))) \\ 454464 &:= (4! \times (((6! + 4!) + 45) \times 4!)) \\ 454494 &:= ((4! - ((-9!) - ((4!/4)!) \times (-5)))/(-4) \\ 454495 &:= (-5 - (((-9!) - ((4!/4)!) \times (-5)))/(-4) \end{aligned}$$

- 454496 := (((((6! + 9!)/4) + 4) × 5) - 4!)
454498 := ((8 - ((-9!) - ((4!/4)!)) × (-5)))/(-4))
454596 := (((((6! + 9!) × 5)/4) + 5!) - 4!)
454896 := ((6 × 9) × (((8!/4!) × 5) + 4!))
454975 := (5! + ((7! - ((9! - 4) × (-5)))/4))
454995 := (-5 × ((9! + (9 × (4 + 5!)))/(-4)))
455037 := ((7! - 3) - (((0! + 5)! × (-5⁴))))
455344 := ((44 + 3!!) × ((5! × 5) - 4))
455625 := (((5 - 2)^{6!/5!}) × (5⁴))
455736 := (((6 × 3) × ((7! × 5) + 5!)) - 4!)
455764 := (((4! - 6) × ((7! × 5) + 5!)) + 4)
455872 := (((2 × 7) × (8⁵)) - (5! × 4!))
456057 := ((-7 - 5!) × (((0! - 6!) × 5) + 4))
456213 := ((3!! + (1 + 2)) × (6 + (5⁴)))
456399 := ((9 × (-9 + 3!!)) - (6! × (-5⁴)))
456575 := (((5! + 7) × 5) × 6!) - (5⁴))
456605 := (5! + (-0! + 6)⁶) × (5 + 4!)
456654 := (((4 + (5⁶) × 6) + ((5 + 4)!))
456659 := (9! + (((5⁶) × 6) + 5)) + 4!
456844 := ((4 + (((4!/8)!))!) × (6 + (5⁴)))
456984 := (4! - ((8!/9) × ((-6 - 5!) + 4!)))
457026 := ((6! + 2) × (0! + ((7 + (5⁴))))))
457069 := (9! - ((6! - 0!) × ((-7 - 5!) - 4)))
457176 := ((6! × ((7!/(1 + 7)) + 5)) - 4!)
457315 := (-5 × (1 + ((3!! × (-7 - 5!)) - 4!)))
457335 := (-5 × (-3 + ((3!! × (-7 - 5!)) - 4!)))
457344 := (4! × (-4!) - ((3!! + (75)) × (-4!)))
457351 := (((1 + (5 × 3!!)) × (7 + 5!)) + 4!)
457377 := ((77³) - ((-7 × 5!) - 4))
457696 := (6! + (((((9 - 6) × 7) + 5)⁴)))
457939 := (9! + (((((3 + 9)!/7!) - 5) + 4!))
457956 := (((6⁵) + ((9! + 7!) × (-5)))/(-4))
458125 := (((5 + (((2 + 1)!))!) + 8) × (5⁴))
458413 := (-3 + (14 × ((8⁵) - 4!)))
458431 := (((-1 + 3!!) + 4!) × (-8 - (5⁴)))
458472 := (-((2 × 7)) × (4! - ((8⁵) + 4)))
458577 := (-7 × ((7! × (-5 + 8))) + (5 + 4))
458616 := (((6 + 1)! × (6 + 85)) - 4!)
458664 := -(((4! - 6!) × ((6! - (85)) + 4!)))
458668 := (((8!/6!) × (6 - (8⁵)))/(-4))
458702 := (-2 × ((0! - (7 × (8⁵))) + 4!))
458707 := (((7! + 0!) × (7 × (8 + 5))) - 4!)
458717 := (-7 × (((1 - 7!) × (8 + 5)) - 4!))
458724 := (-((4 - ((2 × 7) × (8⁵)))) - 4!)
458732 := (-2 × (3! - ((7 × (8⁵)) - 4)))
458737 := ((7 + 3!!) × ((7!/8) + (5 - 4)))
458738 := (((((8³) × 7!) - 8!)/5!)/4!)
458752 := (((2 + 5) + 7) × (8^{5!/4!}))
458773 := (-((3 - ((7 + 7) × (8⁵)))) + 4!)
458784 := (((4⁸) × 7) + ((-8 - 5!)/(-4)))
458791 := ((-1 + 9!) + ((7! + 8) × (-5 + 4!)))
459186 := ((-6 - ((8 - 1)!)) × (-95 - 4))
459235 := (-5!) + ((3!!²) - ((9⁵) - 4))
459277 := ((7! + 7) × (-29 - (-5 × 4!)))
459333 := ((3!! × 3!!) + (((3! - (9⁵)) - 4!)))
459347 := (7 - 4)!! × 3!! - 9⁵ - 4
459351 := (((1 + 5)! × 3!!) - ((9^{5!/4!})))
459368 := ((-8 - 6!) × ((3 - 9) - (5⁴)))
459375 := ((5! × (7! - 3!)) + (-((9⁵)) + 4!))
459384 := (4! - ((-8 × 3!!) - ((9! × 5)/4)))
459387 := ((7 × 8!) + ((3⁹) × (5 + 4)))
459648 := (((((8 × 4) + 6) × 9!)/5!) × 4)
459672 := (((2 × 76) × 9!)/5!) + 4!
459732 := (((-2 × 3!) - 7!) × (-95 - 4))
459735 := (-5 × (3 - ((7! + 9!) - 5!)/4))
459745 := (((((5! + 4) - 7!) - 9!) × (-5))/4)
459754 := (4 + (((5! - 7!) - 9!) × (-5))/4))
459765 := (-5 × (((6! - 7) × (-9 - 5!)) + 4!))
459772 := (-((2⁷)) + (((7! + 9!) × (-5))/(-4)))
459795 := (-5 × (-9 - ((7! + 9!) - 5!)/4))
459924 := (4! - ((((-((2 - 9)))! + 9!) × 5)/(-4)))
459936 := (-6 × (((3!! - ((9 × 9))) × (-5!)) + 4!))
460672 := ((2⁷) × ((6! - 0!) - (6! × (-4))))
460736 := (((6! × (-3 + 7)) + 0!) × (-64))
460759 := -(((9! - 5!) - ((7^{0!+6}) - 4!)))
460779 := (((-((9! - ((7⁷)))) + (-((0! - 6)!))!) - 4)
460796 := (((6!/(-9)) × ((-7 - 0!) × 6!)) - 4)
460802 := (2 × (0! - ((-80) × 6!) × 4))
460804 := (((((4 - 0)!))!) × (-80) + 6!) + 4)
460808 := (8 × ((0! + 8!) + ((06!) × 4!))
460811 := ((11 × (8! + 0!)) + (6! × 4!))
460824 := (((4 × 2) × 80) × 6!) + 4!

- 460832 := $((2^3) \times ((80 \times 6!) + 4))$
460888 := $((8 \times (8 - (-80) \times 6!)) + 4!)$
461184 := $(4! \times (8 \times (1 + ((1 + 6)^4))))$
461379 := $-((9! - (7^{3!+1}) + (6! - 4)))$
461439 := $(-9 + 3!!) \times (4! + (-1 + 6^4))$
461975 := $((5 + 7!) \times 91) - (6! \times (-4))$
462016 := $((6 + 1)!) - (0 - (26^4))$
462017 := $(7! + (1 + (026^4)))$
462636 := $((6! - ((3 + 6)^2)) \times (6! + 4))$
462666 := $(-6 + (((6 - 6!)/2) \times (-6^4)))$
462672 := $(-27) \times (((6/2)!) - 6!) \times 4!)$
462733 := $(3!! - ((3 - 7!) - (26^4)))$
462736 := $((6 - 3)!)! + (7! + (26^4))$
462936 := $((6! \times 3!!) - (((9 + 2)!) / 6!) + 4!))$
462964 := $(4 + 6! - 9^2) \times 6! + 4$
462977 := $(-7 + (((7! \times 92) - 6!) + 4!))$
463536 := $((-(6 + 3) + 5!) \times 3!) \times (6! - 4!)$
463588 := $((8 - 8!) \times ((5!/3) + 6)) / (-4)$
463592 := $((2 \times 9!) - ((5 + 3)^6)) - 4!$
463648 := $((-84) + 6!) \times (3^6) + 4$
463673 := $(-3 - (((-76) + 3!!) \times (-6!)) + 4)$
463676 := $(6! \times (-76)) - ((3!! \times (-6!)) + 4)$
463677 := $(-7 + (((-76) + 3!!) \times 6!) + 4)$
463684 := $((4 - (8! / (-63))) \times 6!) + 4$
463704 := $((4! - 0!) \times 7!) + 3! / 6 \times 4!$
463864 := $(46 \times ((8 + 3!) \times 6!) + 4)$
463872 := $(2^7) \times ((8 - 3) \times 6!) + 4!$
463944 := $-((4! - ((4! \times (9 \times 3)) \times (6! - 4))))$
463968 := $(8 - 6! / 9 + 3!!) \times (6! - 4)$
463978 := $((8! - (7^{9-3})) \times (-6)) + 4$
464248 := $(-8 + ((4! + 2) \times ((4! + 6!) \times 4!))$
464256 := $((6! - 5!) + (24)) \times (6! + 4!)$
464308 := $(-8!) - (((0! + 3!!) - 4!) \times (-6! + 4!))$
464373 := $(-3^7) - (((-3 - 4!) \times 6!) \times 4!)$
464785 := $((5^8) + 7!) + ((4! \times 6!) \times 4)$
464976 := $-((6! - (((7! - 9) \times 4) - 6!) \times 4!))$
465264 := $(4 + 6! / 2 - 5) \times 6^4$
465275 := $(-5 + (7! / 2)) \times (5 + (6! / 4))$
465465 := $(5 - 6!) \times ((45 - 6!) + 4!)$
465648 := $((8^4) \times (-6 + 5!)) - (6^4)$
465744 := $((-44) \times (7! - (5^6))) + 4$
465799 := $((9 \times ((9! / 7) - 5)) - (6! - 4))$
465878 := $((-8 - (7! / (-8))) \times ((5 + 6!) + 4!))$
465984 := $(4! \times ((89 - (5! \times (-6)))) \times 4!)$
466272 := $((2 + 7)!) - (((2 - 6!) \times 6) \times 4!)$
466279 := $((9! + 7) - (((2 - 6!) \times 6) \times 4!))$
466344 := $(4! - ((4 + 3!) \times (-6^6)) + 4!))$
466394 := $(-4 - ((9 \times 3) \times (6 - (6! \times 4!))))$
466416 := $((6 + 1)!) \times 4 - 6! - 6 \times 4!$
466459 := $((9! - 5) - (4! \times ((6! \times (-6)) + 4)))$
466512 := $(2 \times (((1 \times 5) \times (6^6)) - 4!))$
466532 := $(2 \times (3! + ((5 \times (6^6) - 4))))$
466533 := $((3^3) \times ((5 - 6) + (6! \times 4!))$
466534 := $((4 + 3!) \times (-5 - (6^6))) + 4!$
466536 := $((6/3) \times 5) \times (6^6) - 4!$
466555 := $(-5 - ((5! + 5!) \times (-6^6)) / 4!)$
466559 := $((9! - (5/5)) + ((6! \times 6) \times 4!))$
466579 := $((9! / (-7)) - 5) + ((6! \times 6!) + 4!)$
466584 := $(4! + ((8 \times 5) \times (6^6 / 4)))$
466697 := $((-7 + 9!) - (((6! \times (-6)) - 6) \times 4!))$
466704 := $((4 \times (07)!) + 6) - 6! \times 4!$
466721 := $(-1 - (-27) \times (6 + (6! \times 4!)))$
466728 := $((8! / 2) + 7) - 6! \times (6 \times 4)$
466824 := $(4! + ((2 + 8) \times (6^6 + 4!))$
466848 := $((8! + 4!) / (8 - 6)) - 6! \times 4!$
466992 := $(-(2 \times 9) \times ((9 \times 6!) + 6) \times (-4))$
467136 := $-((6! - ((3 + 1) \times (7! + 6))) \times 4!)$
467139 := $(-93) \times (((-1 - 7!) - 6) + 4!)$
467236 := $((6! + ((3 + 2)!) - (7^6)) \times (-4))$
467273 := $(3!! - (7 + ((-27) \times 6!) \times 4!))$
467396 := $((6! / 9) + 3!!) - (7^6) \times (-4)$
467496 := $(6! - ((-9 + ((-4 \times 7!) + 6!)) \times 4!))$
467524 := $((4! \times (2^5)) - (7^6)) \times (-4)$
467539 := $((-93) \times (5 - 7!)) - (6! - 4)$
467572 := $((2 + 7)!) / 5! - ((7^6) \times 4!))$
467576 := $((6! + ((7 \times 5) - (7^6))) \times (-4))$
467644 := $(4! + ((4! + 6!) - (7^6)) \times (-4))$
467668 := $-8 \times 6 + (-6! + 7^6) \times 4$
467679 := $(-9 - (((-7 - 6!) + (7^6))) \times (-4))$
467682 := $(-2 + (((-8 - 6!) + (7^6))) \times 4)$
467684 := $(-(4 \times 8) + ((6! - (7^6))) \times (-4))$
467708 := $(8 - (-0! + 7!) + 7^6) \times 4$

$$\begin{aligned} 467713 &:= (-3 + (((-(1-7)))! - (7^6)) \times (-4)) \\ 467716 &:= ((6! - (((1^7) \times 7^6))) \times (-4)) \\ 467736 &:= (6! + ((3!! - (7 \times 7)) \times (6! - 4!)) \\ 467737 &:= 4 \times (-6! + 7 + 7^{3!}) - 7 \\ 467744 &:= (((4!/4))! - ((7 + (7^6)))) \times (-4) \\ 467748 &:= (((-8 + ((-(4-7)))!)! - (7^6)) \times (-4)) \\ 467879 &:= (((-9 + 7!) \times (87 + 6)) - 4) \\ 467976 &:= (((6! - ((7 \times 9) + 7))) \times 6!) - 4! \\ 467996 &:= (((-(6-99)) \times 7!) - 6!) - 4) \\ 468264 &:= -((4! - ((6 \times 2) \times (8! - (6^4)))) \\ 468288 &:= ((8 + (8/2)) \times (8! - (6^4))) \\ 468324 &:= ((4!/2) \times ((3 + 8!) - (6^4))) \\ 468512 &:= (2 \times ((1 + ((5!/8) + 6))^4)) \\ 468706 &:= (((((6-0!)^7) - 8) \times 6) + 4) \\ 468713 &:= -(((3! + 1) - ((7!/8) \times (6! + 4!))) \\ 468714 &:= -((((4-1))! - ((7!/8) \times (6! + 4!))) \\ 468715 &:= (-5 - (((-1 \times 7!)/8) \times (6! + 4!))) \\ 468716 &:= (((6+1))! \times (7 + 86)) - 4) \\ 468721 &:= ((1^2) + ((7!/8) \times (6! + 4!))) \\ 468723 &:= ((3!/2) + ((7!/8) \times (6! + 4!))) \\ 468726 &:= (((6/2))! + ((7!/8) \times (6! + 4!))) \\ 468732 &:= ((2 \times 3!) + ((7!/8) \times (6! + 4!))) \\ 468735 &:= ((5 \times 3) + ((7!/8) \times (6! + 4!))) \\ 468742 &:= ((-2 + 4!) + ((7!/8) \times (6! + 4!))) \\ 468744 &:= (((4! + ((4! - 7!)/(-8))) \times 6!) + 4!) \\ 468768 &:= ((8 \times 6) + ((7!/8) \times (6! + 4!))) \\ 468834 &:= (4! + (((3^8) + 8!) \times (6 + 4))) \\ 468864 &:= (4! \times ((6! + ((8 + 86))) \times 4!)) \\ 469216 &:= (((6! + 1)^2) - (((9 + 6)^4))) \\ 469256 &:= (((6! + (5!/(-2))) \times (-9 + 6!)) - 4) \\ 469359 &:= (-9 - ((5! - ((3^9) - 6))) \times 4!) \\ 469756 &:= -(((6! + 5!) - ((7^{(9-6)!}) \times 4)) \\ 469876 &:= -((6! - ((7^{(-8+9) \times 6}) \times 4)) \\ 469984 &:= (((4^8) - 9!) - (9! \times (-6)))/4) \\ 470385 &:= (-5 \times (((8!/3) - 0!) \times (-7)) - 4) \\ 470389 &:= (((((9! + 8!)/3!) - 0!) \times 7) - 4) \\ 470674 &:= ((-4 \times (-(7^6)) - 0!) + (74)) \\ 470715 &:= ((5! - 1) + ((7^{-0!+7}) \times 4)) \\ 470716 &:= (((6-1))! + ((7^{-0!+7}) \times 4)) \\ 470952 &:= (-(((2-5) - 90)) \times (7! + 4!)) \\ 471155 &:= ((5-5!) \times (-1 + ((1+7^4)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 471316 &:= (6! + (((1+3!)^{-1+7}) \times 4)) \\ 471456 &:= ((6^5) + (((4! - 1) \times 7!) \times 4)) \\ 471497 &:= (-7 + (-(94) \times ((-1 \times 7!) + 4!))) \\ 471504 &:= -((((4! + 0!) - 5!) + 1) \times (7! - 4!)) \\ 471598 &:= ((89 + 5) \times ((1 + 7!) - 4!)) \\ 471663 &:= ((3^6) \times (6! + (1 - 74))) \\ 471744 &:= ((4! \times ((4 \times 7)!)/((1^7) + 4!))! \\ 471984 &:= (((4!/8)^9) - (17)) \times 4! \\ 472224 &:= (4! \times (-(22^2)) - (7! \times (-4))) \\ 472319 &:= ((9! - 1) + (3!! \times ((2^7) + 4!))) \\ 472328 &:= -((8^2)) - (-((3^{2+7}) \times 4!)) \\ 472344 &:= (4! \times ((4! \times ((3 \times 2)!)) + (7^4))) \\ 472357 &:= -((7 \times 5) - (-((3^{2+7}) \times 4!)) \\ 472368 &:= ((8 \times ((6+3)^{-2+7})) - 4!) \\ 472382 &:= -((2+8) - (-((3^{2+7}) \times 4!)) \\ 472391 &:= (-1 + (((9^3) \times 27) \times 4!)) \\ 472392 &:= (((2 \times 9)/3!)^{2+7}) \times 4! \\ 472398 &:= ((8 \times (9^{3+2})) + ((7-4)!)) \\ 472465 &:= (((((-5+6!) - 4!)^2) - 7!) + 4!) \\ 472536 &:= ((6 + (3^{-5+2 \times 7})) \times 4!) \\ 473066 &:= ((-6 \times (-(6!) - (-((0! - 3!)^7))) - 4) \\ 473277 &:= (((7! + (7^2)) \times (-3)) \times (-7 - 4!)) \\ 473352 &:= (2 \times ((5! + ((3^{3+7})) \times 4)) \\ 473472 &:= ((-2 \times 7!) - (4! \times ((-3 + 7!) \times (-4)))) \\ 473476 &:= ((6! + (((7^4+3)/7))) \times 4) \\ 473489 &:= (9! - ((-8 \times (4!^3)) - (-7 + 4!))) \\ 473496 &:= (-6 - ((-94) \times (-3 + 7!)) - 4!) \\ 473572 &:= ((2 - 7!) \times (-((5^3) - 7)) + 4!) \\ 473688 &:= 8 \times ((8! - 6) \times 3! - 7!)/4 \\ 473712 &:= (2 \times (((((1+7))! \times 3!) - 7!) - 4!)) \\ 473739 &:= (((93 \times 7!) + 3) + 7!) - 4! \\ 473749 &:= (((94 \times 7!) + 3!) + 7) - 4! \\ 473752 &:= (2 \times (((5! - 73) \times 7!) - 4)) \\ 473758 &:= (-8 + (((5^7) \times 3!) + 7!) - 4!) \\ 473759 &:= (((95 \times 7!) + 3) - 7!) - 4) \\ 473764 &:= (((4! + ((67 + 3))) \times 7!) + 4) \\ 473784 &:= (((4 + 87) + 3) \times 7!) + 4! \\ 473794 &:= ((((-(4-9))^7) \times 3!) + 7!) + 4) \\ 473888 &:= -((8! + (8 \times (((8^3!) - 7!)/(-4)))) \\ 473892 &:= ((2 \times ((9 + 8!) \times 3!) - 7!)) + 4! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 473928 &:= (((8^2) + (9 \times (3^7))) \times 4!) \\ 474372 &:= (2 \times (((7! + 3!) \times 47) + 4!)) \\ 474546 &:= (-6 + ((4! + (54))^{7-4})) \\ 474576 &:= (((-(6 \times 7)) + 5!)^{-4+7}) + 4! \\ 474624 &:= (4! \times (((-(2-6)) \times 4!) - 7!) \times (-4))) \\ 474696 &:= (((6! - 9) \times (6! - 4!)) + (7! \times (-4))) \\ 475176 &:= (((6! - ((7+1)!)) \times (-5+7))) - 4! \\ 475196 &:= (((6! - ((9-1)!)) \times (-5+7))) - 4 \\ 475204 &:= (((((4!/02))! \times 5)/7!) + 4) \\ 475217 &:= (-7 + (((12)! \times 5)/7!) + 4!) \\ 475224 &:= ((((((4+2) \times 2)! \times 5)/7!) + 4!) \\ 475233 &:= ((3 - ((3!/(-2)) \times 5!)) \times (7+4)) \\ 475266 &:= ((6 + ((6!/2) \times 5!)) \times (7+4)) \\ 475368 &:= (((8! - 6!)/(-3-5))) + 7) \times 4! \\ 475398 &:= (((8 \times 9) + 3!) + 5!) \times (7^4) \\ 475664 &:= (((-4 - 6!) \times (-657)) - 4) \\ 475752 &:= (((-2 + 5!) \times ((7!/(-5)) + 7!)) - 4!) \\ 475824 &:= (4! \times ((2 - (8!/5!)) - (7! \times (-4)))) \\ 475944 &:= -(((4! \times 4!) - (95 \times (7! - 4!)))) \\ 475968 &:= ((((-8 - 6!) \times 9) + 5!) \times (-74)) \\ 475979 &:= (-97) \times (((9 + 5!) - 7!) + 4) \\ 476636 &:= ((6! \times ((3^6) - 67)) - 4) \\ 476826 &:= (((6!^2) - 8!) + 6) + (7!/(-4)) \\ 477456 &:= (6! + ((5! - 4!) \times (7! - 74))) \\ 477649 &:= ((9! + (-4 \times 6!)) + (7^{(7-4)!})) \\ 477863 &:= ((3! \times 6!) - (((8! + 7) + (7!/4!)))) \\ 477909 &:= (9 \times ((0! - (9!/(-7))) - (7!/(-4)))) \\ 477984 &:= (4! \times (8 + (((9 \times 7) - 7!) \times (-4)))) \\ 478006 &:= ((6!^{0!+0!}) - (8! + 74)) \\ 478044 &:= (((4! \times 4) - 0!) \times (-8 + 7!)) + 4) \\ 478056 &:= ((6! \times ((5 + 0!))!) + ((-8 \times 7!) - 4!)) \\ 478063 &:= ((3! \times 6!) + (((0 - 8!) + 7) - 4!)) \\ 478076 &:= ((6! \times ((7 - 0!))!) + ((-8 \times 7!) - 4)) \\ 478128 &:= (((8! - (((2 + 1)!^8)) \times (-7))/4!) \\ 478159 &:= ((-95) \times (-((1 - 8) - 7!)) + 4!) \\ 478239 &:= (-9 + ((3!^2) - ((8! - (7 \times 4!)))) \\ 478261 &:= (((1 + 6!)^2) - 8!) + (7!/(-4)) \\ 478266 &:= ((-6 + (6!^2)) + (-8 \times (7! - 4!))) \\ 478338 &:= ((((-8!) + 3!) + (3!^8)) \times (-7))/(-4!)) \\ 478464 &:= (((4 \times 6!) - ((4 \times 8))) \times 7) \times 4! \\ 478705 &:= (-5 \times ((0! - 7!) \times ((8 + 7) + 4))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 478737 &:= -7! + 3 \times (7 + (8! - 7) \times 4) \\ 478744 &:= ((4 \times ((4! \times 7!) - 8)) - (7! + 4!)) \\ 478776 &:= ((-6 \times ((7! + 7!) \times (-8))) - (7! + 4!)) \\ 478779 &:= ((9! - 7!) - ((7 - 8!) \times (7 - 4))) \\ 478788 &:= (-8 - (((87 + 8) \times 7!) + 4)) \\ 478791 &:= ((((-1 + 9!) - 7!) - 8) + (7! \times 4!)) \\ 478795 &:= (((-5 - 9!) - 7!) + ((8! - 7!) \times 4!)) \\ 478796 &:= (((6 + 97) - 8) \times 7!) - 4) \\ 478799 &:= (((9! - 9) - 7!) + 8) + (7! \times 4!)) \\ 478804 &:= (((4 + 08) \times 8!) - 7!) + 4) \\ 478824 &:= (((-(4 - (2 \times 8))) \times 8!) - 7!) + 4! \\ 478832 &:= (((((2 \times 3!) \times 8!) + 8) - 7!) + 4!) \\ 478871 &:= (((1 + 7!) \times (8 + 87)) - 4!) \\ 478928 &:= (((((8 - 2)! \times (-9)) + 8) \times (-74)) \\ 478932 &:= (((2 \times 3!) \times (9 + 8!)) - (7! - 4!)) \\ 478992 &:= -(((-(2 - 9!))! - (9! + ((8 + 7!) \times 4!))) \\ 479076 &:= ((6 - (((7 - 0!))! \times 9)) \times (-74)) \\ 479155 &:= (-5 \times (5 + (-19) \times (7! + 4))) \\ 479267 &:= (((7^6) - 2) + 9!) + (7!/(-4)) \\ 479275 &:= ((5 + 7!) \times ((2 + 97) - 4)) \\ 479515 &:= (-5 - (((1 + 5!)! \times (-9 \times 74))) \\ 479532 &:= ((-2 - (3! \times (5! - 9))) \times (-((7 - 4)!)) \\ 479544 &:= (((4! \times (-4)) \times ((5 \times 9) - 7!)) + 4!) \\ 479566 &:= ((6 \times ((6! \times (5! - 9)) + 7)) + 4) \\ 479568 &:= (((86 + 5!) \times 97) \times 4!) \\ 479664 &:= ((4! \times 6) + (6! \times (9 \times 74))) \\ 479668 &:= (((-((8 - 6)) + (6! \times (-9))) \times (-74)) \\ 480236 &:= ((6! \times (3! + (2 + 0!))) - (8! + 4)) \\ 480529 &:= (9! + ((2 + 5)^{(0!+8/4!})) \\ 480655 &:= ((5! - (5^6)) \times (0! - (8 \times 4))) \\ 480956 &:= (((6! \times (5! - 9)) - (0! - 8!)) \times 4) \\ 480964 &:= ((-4 \times ((6! - 9!) - 0!)) - (8! \times 4!)) \\ 481344 &:= (((-4 \times (4! - ((3! + 1)!)) - 8) \times 4!) \\ 481345 &:= ((5^{4!/3}) + (((1 + 8)!/4)) \\ 481349 &:= ((9!/4) + (((3! - 1)^8) + 4)) \\ 481439 &:= (((9!/(-3)) \times (-4)) - (-((1 - 8)^4)) \\ 481536 &:= (((6^3) - 5!) \times (((1 - 8)! - 4!)) \\ 481653 &:= (3 \times ((-5 - 6!) - ((1 - 8!) \times 4))) \\ 481656 &:= (((6! + 5) \times 6!) - ((1 \times 8)! - 4!) \\ 481824 &:= ((4!/2) \times (8! - (-((1 - 8) \times 4!))) \\ 482184 &:= ((4! - (8! \times (-12))) - (8!/4!)) \\ 482256 &:= (-6 \times ((5! \times 2) + ((-2 \times 8!) + 4!))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 482304 &:= (4! \times (((0! + 3!))! - (2 \times 8)) \times 4) \\ 482328 &:= (((8 \times (-2 + 3!)) - 2) \times 84) \\ 482368 &:= (((8! \times (-6)) + 3!) \times (-2)) - (8 \times 4) \\ 482376 &:= (((-67) \times 3!) \times (-2 + 8)) - 4! \\ 482385 &:= (((-((5 - 8)) + 3!)^2) - (8! + 4!)) \\ 482388 &:= (8! - (8 + 3)^2) \times (8 + 4) \\ 482395 &:= ((-5 + 9!) + ((3!^2) - 8!)/4) \\ 482413 &:= (((3! - ((1 - 4)))^2) - ((8! - 4))) \\ 482433 &:= (((3! + 3)^{4-2}) - (8! - 4!)) \\ 482448 &:= (((8! + 4!) \times 4!)/2) - (8!/4!) \\ 482496 &:= (-6 \times ((9 \times 4!) - (2 \times (8! - 4)))) \\ 482544 &:= -((4! \times (4! - ((5! - (2 \times 8!)) / (-4)))))) \\ 482586 &:= (-6 - (((8! - 5!) / (-2)) - 8) \times 4!) \\ 482688 &:= (8! - 8 \times 6 \times 2) \times (8 + 4) \\ 482736 &:= (((6! - (-((3 - 7)))!)^2) - (8!/4!)) \\ 482769 &:= ((9 - 6!) \times (-7 + (-28) \times 4!)) \\ 482832 &:= (((2 \times 3!) \times (-82) + 8!) - 4!) \\ 482856 &:= ((6 + ((5! - 8!) \times 2) - 8!) \times (-4)) \\ 482976 &:= (-6 \times ((7! - 9) \times (-2^{8-4}))) \\ 483024 &:= (4! \times (-2 - (((0! + 3!))! - 8) \times (-4))) \\ 483025 &:= ((-((5^2)) + ((03!)!)^{8/4}) \\ 483036 &:= -((6! + (3 \times (((0! + 3!) - 8!) \times 4))) \\ 483084 &:= (-4 \times (((8! + 0!) \times (-3)) - (-8 \times 4!)) \\ 483096 &:= -((6! + (((9! / (03!)) \times (-8)) + 4!)) \\ 483116 &:= ((6! \times (-1)) + ((1 + (-3 \times 8!)) \times (-4))) \\ 483136 &:= -((6! + ((3 + 1) \times ((-3 \times 8!) - 4))) \\ 483143 &:= -((3! - (((4! - 1) - ((-3 \times 8!) \times 4)))) \\ 483144 &:= ((4! - (((4 - 1)!))!) + ((-3 \times 8!) \times (-4))) \\ 483145 &:= (5! + ((-((4! + 1)) + 3!)^{8/4}) \\ 483168 &:= (8 \times ((6! - (1^3)) \times 84)) \\ 483193 &:= -((3! - (((9! + 1) + (3 \times (8! + 4!)))))) \\ 483216 &:= -((6! + ((-12) \times (3! + 8!)) - 4!)) \\ 483256 &:= (((6!/5) + 2) + (-3 \times 8!)) \times (-4) \\ 483264 &:= (4! \times ((6 - (((2 - 3) + 8)!)) \times (-4)) \\ 483312 &:= (-2 \times (((-1 + 3!))! - (3! \times (8! - 4!))) \\ 483324 &:= (-4 - ((-2 - (3! / (-3!))) \times (-8^4))) \\ 483328 &:= (((-8 + ((2 + 3)!)) + 3!) \times (8^4)) \\ 483336 &:= ((6 + 3!) \times (((-3 \times 3!) + 8!) - 4!)) \\ 483339 &:= ((-9! / 3!) + (3 - ((-3 \times 8!) \times 4)) \\ 483352 &:= (((2 + 5!) + ((3 - 3!) \times 8!)) \times (-4) \\ 483354 &:= (((-4 \times 5!) - 3!) - ((-3 \times 8!) \times 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 483355 &:= (-5 - ((5! + ((3 - 3!) \times 8!)) \times 4) \\ 483372 &:= (((-((2 - 7)))! - (3 - (-3 \times 8!))) \times (-4)) \\ 483384 &:= ((-((4 + 8)) \times ((3! \times 3!) - 8!)) - 4! \\ 483388 &:= 8 \times 83 \times (3! + 8) - 4 \\ 483392 &:= (((((2 \times 9!) - 3!) / (-3!)) - 8) \times (-4)) \\ 483408 &:= (8! - (-0! + 4!) \times 3!) \times (8 + 4) \\ 483424 &:= (((4! + 2) \times (-4)) - (-3 \times 8!)) \times 4) \\ 483432 &:= ((2 \times 3!) \times (((-4 - 3!) + 8!) - 4!)) \\ 483435 &:= -((5 \times (3^4)) - ((-3 \times 8!) \times 4)) \\ 483448 &:= (-8 - (((4! \times 4) + (-3 \times 8!)) \times 4) \\ 483453 &:= (-3 + (((5! - 4!) + (-3 \times 8!)) \times (-4))) \\ 483472 &:= (((-2 + (7! \times 4!)) - (3! / 8)) \times 4) \\ 483475 &:= (-5 + (((7! \times 4!) - (3! / 8)) \times 4) \\ 483476 &:= (((67 + 4!) + (-3 \times 8!)) \times (-4)) \\ 483492 &:= ((29 - ((4! / 3)!)) \times (-8 + 4)) \\ 483496 &:= -((6! - ((-94) + (-3 \times 8!)) \times (-4))) \\ 483513 &:= (3 \times ((-1 - 5!) + ((3 + 8!) \times 4)) \\ 483516 &:= (((6 + 1) + 5) \times ((-3 + 8!) - 4!)) \\ 483524 &:= (-4 \times ((2 + 5) + (-3 \times (8! - 4!))) \\ 483528 &:= (((8! - (2^5)) + 3!) \times (8 + 4)) \\ 483532 &:= ((-2 + 3!) \times (-5 - (-3 \times (8! - 4!))) \\ 483542 &:= -((2 - 4) \times (-5 + (3! \times (8! - 4!))) \\ 483543 &:= (3 \times (((4! - 5!) - 3) + (8! \times 4)) \\ 483546 &:= (-6 - ((4! - ((5 + 3)!)) \times (8 + 4)) \\ 483548 &:= (8! - 4!) \times (5! / 3! - 8) - 4 \\ 483552 &:= (((2 \times 5) + 5) - 3) \times (8! - 4!) \\ 483564 &:= (((4 + 65) + (-3 \times 8!)) \times (-4)) \\ 483573 &:= (3 \times ((7 - 5!) + ((3! + 8!) \times 4)) \\ 483579 &:= (-9 + ((7 + 5) \times ((3 + 8!) - 4!)) \\ 483588 &:= (((-8 \times (((8 - 5)!))!) + 3) \times (-84)) \\ 483592 &:= (2 \times ((9! - 5!) - ((3 \times 8!) + 4)) \\ 483596 &:= ((-6 \times (((9! - 5!) / (-3)) + 8!)) - 4) \\ 483622 &:= (-2 - (-((2 \times 6) \times ((3! + 8!) - 4!)) \\ 483624 &:= (((4! - ((2 + 6)!)) - 3!) \times (-8 + 4)) \\ 483632 &:= (2 \times ((3! \times (-((6 \times 3)) + 8!)) + 4) \\ 483633 &:= (3 \times (3 + (((6 \times 3) - 8!) \times (-4))) \\ 483639 &:= (9! - (3 \times ((63 - 8!) + 4)) \\ 483648 &:= ((8! - (4^{6/3})) \times (8 + 4)) \\ 483671 &:= (-1 - (((7 \times 6) + (-3 \times 8!)) \times 4) \\ 483672 &:= (((2 - 7!) \times ((6 + 3!) \times (-8))) + 4! \\ 483688 &:= (((8! + 8!) \times 6) - (38 \times 4)) \\ 483693 &:= (-3 - (((9! / (-6)) + 3!) + 8!) \times 4!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 483696 &:= (-6 \times (((9!/(-6)) + 3!) + 8!) \times 4)) \\ 483708 &:= (((8! - 0!) - (7 + 3)) \times (8 + 4)) \\ 483712 &:= (-(((2 \times 1)^7)) - ((-3 \times 8!) \times 4)) \\ 483713 &:= -((((3! - 1)!) - (-7 - ((-3 \times 8!) \times 4)))) \\ 483714 &:= ((4 - 1) \times ((-7 \times 3!) + (8! \times 4))) \\ 483719 &:= ((9! - 1) + ((7! + ((3 - 8))) \times 4!)) \\ 483732 &:= ((2 \times 3!) \times (((-7 - 3!) + 8!) + 4)) \\ 483735 &:= (-(((5 \times 3) \times 7)) - ((-3 \times 8!) \times 4)) \\ 483737 &:= (-7 + (((-3 \times 7!) + 3) \times (-8 \times 4))) \\ 483738 &:= (((8! - 3!) \times (7 + 3!)) - (8! + 4!)) \\ 483742 &:= (-2 + (((4! \times 7!) - ((3 \times 8))) \times 4)) \\ 483744 &:= (((4/4) - 7!) \times (-((3 \times 8) \times 4))) \\ 483747 &:= ((7 - 4) \times (-7 + ((3! - 8!) \times (-4)))) \\ 483748 &:= ((((-8 + 4!) + 7) + (-3 \times 8!)) \times (-4)) \\ \\ 483749 &:= (-(((9 + 4) \times 7)) - ((-3 \times 8!) \times 4)) \\ 483752 &:= (2 \times (((-5 + (7! \times 3!)) \times 8) - 4)) \\ 483753 &:= (3 \times (-5 - (((-7 - 3)) \times 8!) + 4!)) \\ 483754 &:= (-(((4! - 5!) \times 7!)) - ((3!/8) - 4)) \\ 483755 &:= (-5 - ((-5 + (7! \times 3!)) \times (8 - 4!))) \\ 483756 &:= (((6! + 5) + 7!) - 3!) \times 84 \\ 483757 &:= (-7 - (((5 + 7) \times (3! - 8!)) + 4)) \\ 483759 &:= ((9! - (57)) + ((3 \times 8!) - 4!)) \\ 483764 &:= ((-4 \times ((6 + 7) + (-3 \times 8!))) - 4!) \\ 483768 &:= (8! - 6) \times (7 + 3 + 8/4) \\ 483769 &:= ((9! - 67) + ((3 \times 8!) - 4)) \\ 483772 &:= (((2 - 7) - 7) \times (3! - 8!)) + 4 \\ 483775 &:= (((5! \times 7!) + 7) - (3 \times (8! + 4!))) \\ 483776 &:= (((-6 \times 7!) + (7 - 3)) \times (8 - 4!)) \\ 483777 &:= (-7 + (((7 + 7) + (-3 \times 8!)) \times (-4))) \\ 483779 &:= ((9! - ((7 \times 7))) + (3 \times (8! - 4))) \\ 483782 &:= (2 \times 8! - 7) \times 3! + 8 - 4! \\ 483784 &:= -4 + ((8! - 7) \times 3 + 8) \times 4 \\ 483788 &:= (8! + 8! - 7 - 3! + 8!) \times 4 \\ 483791 &:= ((-1 + 9!) + (((7! + 3!) - 8) \times 4!)) \\ 483792 &:= (2 \times (((9 - 7) \times 3) \times 8!) - 4!) \\ 483793 &:= (((3! \times (-9)) + 7) - ((-3 \times 8!) \times 4)) \\ 483795 &:= (-((5 \times 9)) - (7! \times (-((3 \times 8) \times 4)))) \\ 483797 &:= (-7 - ((9 - (7! \times (3 \times 8))) \times 4)) \\ 483798 &:= -((((8! - 9!) - (-7 \times 3!)) - (8! \times 4))) \\ 483799 &:= ((9! - 9) - (((7! \times 3!) - 8) \times (-4))) \\ 483802 &:= (-2 + (((0 - 8!) + 3) \times (-8 + 4))) \\ 483803 &:= -((((3 \times 0)!) - ((8! - 3) \times (8 + 4))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 483804 &:= (((4 - 0!) - 8!) \times (-3 \times (8 - 4))) \\ 483805 &:= (((5 \times 0)!) + ((8! - 3) \times (8 + 4))) \\ 483806 &:= ((6 \times (((0! + 8!) - 3!) + 8!)) - 4) \\ 483807 &:= -((((7 \times 0)!) - ((8! \times 3) - 8) \times 4))) \\ 483808 &:= (((8! + (08)!) \times 3!) - (8 \times 4)) \\ 483809 &:= (((9 \times 0)!) + (((8! \times 3) - 8) \times 4)) \\ 483811 &:= ((11 \times (8! - 3)) + (8! + 4)) \\ 483812 &:= ((2 \times ((-1 + 8!) \times 3!)) - (-8 + 4!)) \\ 483812 &:= (-4 - (((8 - 3!) - 8!) \times 12)) \\ 483813 &:= (-3 - (((-1 - 8!) + 3) \times (8 + 4))) \\ 483814 &:= (((4 - 1)!) + (((8! \times 3) - 8) \times 4)) \\ 483815 &:= (-5 - (((1 + 8!) \times 3) - 8) \times (-4)) \\ 483816 &:= (((6 - 1) - 8!) - 3) \times (-8 + 4)) \\ 483818 &:= (((8! - 1) + 8!) \times 3! + 8) - 4! \\ 483819 &:= (9! - (((1 + 8!) \times (-3)) + ((8 - 4)!)) \\ 483821 &:= (((12 \times 8!) - ((3 - 8))) - 4!) \\ 483822 &:= (-2 - (((-2 \times 8!) \times 3!) - 8) + 4!)) \\ 483823 &:= (-(((3^2) + 8)) - ((-3 \times 8!) \times 4)) \\ 483824 &:= ((((((4 \times 2)!) + 8!) \times 3!) + 8) - 4!) \\ 483825 &:= (-(((5 + 2) + 8)) - ((-3 \times 8!) \times 4)) \\ 483826 &:= (((6 \times 2) \times 8!) - 38) + 4! \\ 483827 &:= (-((7^2)) + ((8! + 3) \times (8 + 4))) \\ 483828 &:= (((8! - 2) + 8!) \times ((3 \times 8)/4)) \\ 483829 &:= (-9 - (((-2 \times 8!) \times 3!) + (8/4))) \\ 483831 &:= (-1 - (((-3 \times 8!) - 3!) + 8) \times 4)) \\ 483832 &:= (((2 \times 3!) \times 8!) - 3!) - (8/4)) \\ 483833 &:= (((3! + 3!) \times 8!) - ((3 + 8) - 4)) \\ 483834 &:= (((4 \times 3) \times 8!) - ((3 \times 8)/4)) \\ 483835 &:= (-5 - ((-3 \times 8!) - ((3^{8/4})!)) \\ 483836 &:= (((6 + 3!) \times 8!) - 3!) + (8/4)) \\ 483837 &:= (((7 - 3)!) \times 8! - 3!)/(8/4)) \\ 483838 &:= (((8! \times (-3)) - 8!) \times (-3)) - (8/4)) \\ 483839 &:= (((9 + 3) \times 8!) - (3 - (8/4))) \\ 483851 &:= (-1 - (((5 - 8!) - 3!) \times (8 + 4))) \\ 483852 &:= (((-((2 + 5)) - 8!) + 3!) \times (-8 + 4)) \\ 483853 &:= ((3 \times (((5 \times 8!) + 3) - 8!)) + 4) \\ 483854 &:= (4! + ((-5 + (8! \times 3!)) \times (8/4))) \\ 483855 &:= (-((5 \times (5 - 8))) - ((-3 \times 8!) \times 4)) \\ 483856 &:= ((6! \times ((5! - 8) \times 3!)) + (-8 + 4!)) \\ 483857 &:= (-7 - (((-5 - 8!) + 3) \times (8 + 4))) \\ 483858 &:= (((8! + 5) + 8!) \times 3! - (8 + 4)) \\ 483859 &:= (9! + (((5 + 8!) \times 3) + (8 - 4))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 483861 &:= (-1 + ((6 \times ((8! + 3) + 8!)) + 4)) \\ 483862 &:= (((((2 \times 6) \times 8!) + 3!) - 8) + 4!) \\ 483863 &:= (-((3 + 6)) - (((8! \times 3) + 8) \times (-4))) \\ 483864 &:= (((4 - 6) - 8!) \times (-3 \times (8 - 4))) \\ 483865 &:= (-((5 + 6)) + ((8! + 3) \times (8 + 4))) \\ 483866 &:= (((6 + 6) \times 8!) - 3!) + (8 \times 4) \\ 483867 &:= (((((7 + 6) \times 8!) + 3) - 8!) + 4!) \\ 483868 &:= (((8! \times (-6)) - 8) - 3!) \times (-8/4)) \\ 483869 &:= (((9!/6) \times 8) - ((3 - (8 \times 4)))) \\ 483871 &:= (-1 + (((7! \times (8 \times 3)) + 8) \times 4)) \\ 483872 &:= (((((2 + 7)! \times 8)/3!) + (8 \times 4)) \\ 483873 &:= (-3 - (((7! \times (-8)) - 3) \times (8 + 4))) \\ 483874 &:= (((4! - 7) + (8! \times 3!)) \times (8/4)) \\ 483875 &:= (((5 + 7) \times 8!) + (3 + (8 \times 4))) \\ 483876 &:= (((6! \times (-7 \times 8)) - 3) \times (-8 + 4)) \\ 483877 &:= ((7/7) + ((8! + 3) \times (8 + 4))) \\ 483878 &:= (((8! + 7) + 8!) \times 3!) - (8 - 4) \\ 483879 &:= (-9 + (((-7 - 8!) + 3) \times (-8 + 4))) \\ 483891 &:= (19 - (((8! \times 3) + 8) \times (-4))) \\ 483892 &:= (((((2 - 9) - 8!) \times 3) + 8) \times (-4)) \\ 483894 &:= (((4 + 9) \times (8! + 3!)) - (8! + 4!)) \\ 483896 &:= ((((-((6 - 9)) \times 8!) + 3!) + 8) \times 4) \\ 483897 &:= (((-7 + 9!) - 8) + (3 \times (8! + 4!))) \\ 483898 &:= (((8! + 9) + 8!) \times 3!) + (8 - 4) \\ 483899 &:= (9! + (((9 + 8!) \times 3) + (8 \times 4))) \\ 483902 &:= (-2 \times (0! + (((9!/3!) + 8) \times (-4))) \\ 483903 &:= (((3! + 0!) \times 9) - ((-3 \times 8!) \times 4)) \\ 483904 &:= (((4! + (09!))/(-3)) - 8) \times (-4) \\ 483906 &:= ((-6 + (09!)) + (3 \times (8! + 4!))) \\ 483908 &:= (((8 + 0!) + ((9!/3) + 8)) \times 4) \\ 483911 &:= ((-1 + ((1 \times 9)!)) + (3 \times (8! + 4!))) \\ 483912 &:= ((2 + 1) \times ((-((9 - 3)) - 8!) \times (-4))) \\ 483913 &:= (-3 - (((-19) + (-3 \times 8!)) \times 4)) \\ 483915 &:= (51 + (((9 + 3) \times 8!) + 4!)) \\ 483919 &:= ((91 + 9!) + (3 \times (8! - 4))) \\ 483921 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((9 \times 3) + (8! \times 4))) \\ 483922 &:= ((2 \times (29 + (3! \times 8!))) + 4!) \\ 483924 &:= (((4 \times 2)! \times (9 + 3)) + (84)) \\ 483926 &:= (62 + (((9 + 3) \times 8!) + 4!)) \\ 483928 &:= (8^2) + (((9 + 3) \times 8!) + 4!) \\ 483932 &:= ((-23) + (9!/(-3))) \times (-8 - 4)) \\ 483933 &:= (-3 - (((-((3 + 9)) \times (3! + 8!)) - 4!)) \\ 483936 &:= ((6 + 3!) \times (((9 + 3) + 8!) - 4)) \\ 483937 &:= (73 + (((9 + 3) \times 8!) + 4!)) \\ 483939 &:= (-9 - (((-((3 \times 9)) + (-3 \times 8!)) \times 4)) \\ 483942 &:= ((2 \times (49 + (3! \times 8!))) + 4) \\ 483944 &:= (((((4! \times 4) + 9!)/3!) \times 8) - 4!) \\ 483945 &:= (((5! - 4!) + 9) - ((-3 \times 8!) \times 4)) \\ 483948 &:= (((8! + 4!) - 9) - 3!) \times (8 + 4) \\ 483951 &:= (((1 \times 5)! - 9) - ((-3 \times 8!) \times 4)) \\ 483952 &:= (((-((2 \times (5 + 9))) + (-3 \times 8!)) \times (-4)) \\ 483953 &:= ((-3 + 5!) + (((9 + 3) \times 8!) - 4)) \\ 483955 &:= ((5! - 5) + ((9!/(-3)) \times (-8 - 4))) \\ 483956 &:= (((-6 + ((5! + 9!)/3!)) \times 8) + 4) \\ 483957 &:= ((-7 + 5!) + (((9 + 3) \times 8!) + 4)) \\ 483958 &:= ((8 \times (-59) - (3! \times 8!))/(-4)) \\ 483959 &:= (-9 - (((5! + 9!)/(-3)) + 8) \times 4) \\ 483964 &:= (4 \times ((6! + ((9! + 3) \times 8))/4!)) \\ 483965 &:= ((5^{-6+9}) - ((-3 \times 8!) \times 4)) \\ 483968 &:= (((8!/6!) + 9!) + (3 \times (8! + 4!))) \\ 483972 &:= (((2^{7+9+3}) - 8!) + 4) \\ 483976 &:= (((-((6 \times 7)) - ((9!/3) - 8)) \times (-4)) \\ 483992 &:= (((-((29 + 9)) + (-3 \times 8!)) \times (-4)) \\ 483993 &:= (3 \times (-9 - (((-9 - 3!) - 8!) \times 4))) \\ 484031 &:= (-1 - (((((3! + 0!))! \times 4) + 8) \times (-4!)) \\ 484032 &:= ((2 \times ((3 + 0!))! \times (4 + (8!/4))) \\ 484035 &:= (5! - (-3 \times (0! + ((4 \times 8!) + 4!))) \\ 484068 &:= (8! - 6 + 0! + 4!) \times (8 + 4) \\ 484104 &:= (((4!/(0! + 1)) \times (4! + 8!)) - 4!) \\ 484113 &:= (3 \times (-1 - (((1 - 4!) - 8!) \times 4)) \\ 484124 &:= (((4!/2) \times (((1 \times 4)! + 8!)) - 4) \\ 484125 &:= ((5 - 2) \times (-1 + ((4! + 8!) \times 4))) \\ 484128 &:= ((8! + (((2 - 1) \times 4)!)) \times (8 + 4)) \\ 484131 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (1 + ((4! + 8!) \times 4))) \\ 484132 &:= (((2 \times 3!) \times (((1 \times 4)! + 8!)) + 4) \\ 484135 &:= (-5 - (3 \times (((-1 - 4!) - 8!) \times 4)) \\ 484136 &:= (((6 + 3!) \times ((1 + 4!) + 8!)) - 4) \\ 484143 &:= (3 \times ((4 + 1) + ((4! + 8!) \times 4))) \\ 484144 &:= (-4 \times (((-((4 - 1)) \times (4! + 8!)) - 4)) \\ 484152 &:= (((2 \times (5 + 1)) \times (4! + 8!)) + 4!) \\ 484176 &:= (((6! \times (-7 + 1)) - 4) \times (-84)) \\ 484224 &:= ((((((4 \times 2)!/2) + 4!) - 8) \times 4!) \\ 484236 &:= (-6 \times (3! - ((2 \times (4! + 8!)) + 4!)) \\ 484266 &:= (-6 + (-6 \times ((-2 \times (4! + 8!)) - 4!)) \\ 484268 &:= (8! + 6^2) \times (4 + 8) - 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 484272 &:= ((2 - (((7! + 2) \times (-4)) - 8)) \times 4!) \\ 484344 &:= ((4! \times 4!) + (3 \times ((4 \times 8!) - 4!))) \\ 484359 &:= (-9 + ((5! - (3 \times (-4 - 8!)))) \times 4)) \\ 484368 &:= (-((8 \times 6)) + ((3!! - 4!)^{8/4})) \\ 484377 &:= (-7 - (((7! + 3!) \times 4!) - 8) \times (-4))) \\ 484408 &:= -8 + ((-0! + 4)!! - 4!)^{8/4} \\ 484413 &:= (3 \times (-1 + (((4! + 4!) + 8!) \times 4))) \\ 484416 &:= ((6! - ((1 \times 4)!)^{4-8/4}) \\ 484428 &:= (((8!/2) + 4!) \times 4!) + (8 + 4)) \\ 484473 &:= (3 \times (((7! + 4!)/4!) + (8! \times 4))) \\ 484476 &:= (6! - ((7 - ((4 + 4)!) \times (8 + 4))) \\ 484533 &:= (3!! - (3 \times (5 + ((-4 \times 8!) + 4)))) \\ 484536 &:= (6! - (((3 + 5)!) \times (-4 + 8))) + 4!)) \\ 484576 &:= (6! + ((7! \times (5! - 4!)) + (-8 + 4!))) \\ 484584 &:= (4! \times (((8! + 5!) + 4) + 8!)/4) \\ 484608 &:= ((8! + 064) \times (8 + 4)) \\ 484632 &:= (((2 \times 3!) \times (64 + 8!)) + 4!) \\ 484704 &:= (4! \times (((0! + 7!) \times 4) + (8 \times 4))) \\ 484724 &:= (((4!/2) \times (74 + 8!)) - 4) \\ 484732 &:= (((2 \times 3!) \times (74 + 8!)) + 4) \\ 484736 &:= (((((6 + 3) + 7!) \times 4!) + 8) \times 4) \\ 484752 &:= (((-((2 - 5)))!)! - ((7! \times (-4)) - 8) \times 4!)) \\ 484796 &:= (((6! + 9!)/(7 - 4)!) \times 8) - 4) \\ 484816 &:= ((((-61) - 8!) \times 4) + 8!) \times (-4)) \\ 484824 &:= (((4!/2) \times (84 + 8!)) - 4!) \\ 484828 &:= (((-82) - 8!) \times (-4 + 8)) + 4) \\ 484839 &:= (-9 - (3 \times ((-84) - 8!) \times 4)) \\ 484848 &:= ((-84) - 8!) \times (-48/4)) \\ 484853 &:= (3!! - (-5 + ((8! + 4!) \times (-8 + 4)))) \\ 484864 &:= (((4^6) - (8! \times 48))/(-4)) \\ 484868 &:= (86 + 8!) \times (4 + 8) - 4 \\ 484953 &:= (3 \times (-5 - ((-94) - 8!) \times 4)) \\ 484968 &:= (((8 \times 6) \times (-94) - 8!)/(-4)) \\ 484992 &:= (-2 \times ((9! + 9!) - ((4! + 8!) \times 4!)) \\ 485039 &:= ((-9 \times 3!!) - ((0! + (5! \times (-8^4)))))) \\ 485136 &:= (-6 \times (((3 - 1)) \times (5! + 8!)) + 4!)) \\ 485208 &:= (((-8!) + ((0! + 2)!) - 5!) \times (-8 + 4)) \\ 485231 &:= (-1 - ((3! \times (-2)) \times ((5! + 8!) - 4)) \\ 485232 &:= (((((2^3)!) / 2) + 58)) \times 4!) \\ 485248 &:= (-8 - (((4! / (-2)) \times (5! + 8!)) + 4!)) \\ 485256 &:= (((6 + ((5 - 2)!) \times (5! + 8!)) - 4!) \\ 485264 &:= (-4 \times (((6/2) \times (5! + 8!)) + 4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 485268 &:= -8 + 6 \times 2 \times (5! + 8!) - 4 \\ 485274 &:= (-((4 - 7)) \times (-2 + ((5! + 8!) \times 4))) \\ 485302 &:= ((-2 \times (0! - (3! \times (5! + 8!)))) + 4!) \\ 485304 &:= (((4 \times 03) \times (5! + 8!)) + 4!) \\ 485308 &:= (((-8 + 0!) + (-3 \times (5! + 8!))) \times (-4)) \\ 485313 &:= (3 \times (-1 - (((-3 - 5!) - 8!) \times 4))) \\ 485324 &:= (-4 - ((-2 \times 3!) \times ((5! + 8!) + 4))) \\ 485328 &:= (((8! - 2) + 3!) + 5!) \times (8 + 4)) \\ 485332 &:= (2 \times (3!! - ((3! \times (-5 - 8!)) + 4))) \\ 485343 &:= (3 \times ((4! - 3) + ((5! + 8!) \times 4))) \\ 485344 &:= (((-((4 \times 4)) + (-3 \times (5! + 8!))) \times (-4)) \\ 485348 &:= (8 + 4) \times (3! + 5! + 8!) - 4 \\ 485352 &:= (-((2 - 5)) \times (((3! + 5!) + 8!) \times 4)) \\ 485373 &:= (3 \times (7 - (((3! + 5!) + 8!) \times (-4)))) \\ 485568 &:= ((8! + (6!/5)) \times (-((5 - 8) \times 4))) \\ 485635 &:= (-5 - (-3 \times ((6! - 5!) + (8! \times 4)))) \\ 485928 &:= (((8!/2) + ((95 - 8))) \times 4!) \\ 486003 &:= (3 \times ((0! + (06)!) + (8! \times 4))) \\ 486024 &:= (4! - ((-2 - 0!) \times (6! + (8! \times 4)))) \\ 486144 &:= (4! \times ((4! + ((1 + 6)!) \times (8 - 4))) \\ 486153 &:= (3 \times ((51 + 6!) + (8! \times 4))) \\ 486384 &:= (-4 \times (((8! \times (-3)) - 6!) + (84))) \\ 486528 &:= (((8! \times 2)/5!) \times (6! + (8 - 4))) \\ 486688 &:= (((8! + 8!) \times 6) + ((6! - 8) \times 4)) \\ 486696 &:= (((((-6 + 9!) + 6!)/6) - 8!) \times 4! \\ 486744 &:= (4! + (((4! \times 7!) + 6!) \times (8 - 4))) \\ 486746 &:= (-6 + (((4! \times 7!) + 6!) + 8) \times 4) \\ 486748 &:= (((((8! \times 4) + 7) + 6!) - 8!) \times 4) \\ 487264 &:= (((4! \times (-((6^2)) - 7!)) + 8) \times (-4)) \\ 487305 &:= ((5! - 0!) \times (3! - (7 - (8^4)))) \\ 487356 &:= ((6! \times 5) + (3 \times ((7 - 8!) \times (-4)))) \\ 487368 &:= (((8 \times 6!) - (3! \times (-7))) \times 84) \\ 487417 &:= 7 \times (-1 + (4! - 7) \times 8^4) \\ 487464 &:= ((4 \times (6! + (4! \times (7! + 8)))) - 4!) \\ 487555 &:= (-((5^5)) - (5! \times (7 - (8^4)))) \\ 487596 &:= (-6 \times (((-9 - 5!) \times 7!)/8) + 4) \\ 487656 &:= (6 \times (((5! \times 6!) - 7!) - (84))) \\ 488136 &:= (-6 \times ((3!! \times (-1)) - (((8! + 8!) - 4)))) \\ 488156 &:= ((6 \times (((5 + 1)!) + 8!) + 8!) - 4) \\ 488166 &:= ((6 \times (6! + 1) - (8! \times (-8 + 4))) \\ 488304 &:= (((4 - 0)!) \times (3!! + ((8! + 8!) + 4)))) \\ 488384 &:= (((4 + 8) \times (3!! + 8!)) - (8^4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 488424 &:= (((((4!/2)^4) + 8!) \times 8) - 4!) \\ 488448 &:= (((((8 - 4!) \times 4!) - 8!) \times (-8 + 4))) \\ 488568 &:= (-8 - (-((6 + 5) \times (8! + (8^4)))) \\ 488755 &:= (((-5 - 5!) + 7!) - (8! \times (-8 + 4))) \\ 488779 &:= ((97 \times (7! - (8/8))) - 4) \\ 488799 &:= ((-((9 \times 9) + 7!) - (8! \times (-8 + 4))) \\ 488871 &:= (((-1 + 7!) - 8) - (8! \times (-8 + 4))) \\ 488875 &:= ((-5 + 7!) - (8! \times (-((8 + 8) - 4))) \\ 488876 &:= (((((6! \times 7!) - 8!)/8) + 8!) - 4) \\ 488879 &:= (((-9 + 7!) + 8) - (8! \times (-8 + 4))) \\ 488897 &:= ((7! + ((9 + 8))) - (8! \times (-8 + 4))) \\ 488979 &:= ((-9 + 7!) + ((9 + 8!) \times (8 + 4))) \\ 488988 &:= ((8!/8) + ((9 + 8!) \times (8 + 4))) \\ 488997 &:= ((7! + 9) + ((9 + 8!) \times (8 + 4))) \\ 489336 &:= (((6! - 3!) + (((3^9) - 8))) \times 4!) \\ 489552 &:= (2 \times (((5! \times 5!) \times (9 + 8)) - 4!)) \\ 489568 &:= 8 \times (6! \times 5 \times (9 + 8) - 4) \\ 489576 &:= (((6! + 7!) \times (5 \times (9 + 8))) - 4!) \\ 489596 &:= ((((-((6 - 9)))!) \times 5!) + (((9! + 8!) - 4))) \\ 489604 &:= (((40 \times 6!) \times (9 + 8)) + 4) \\ 489667 &:= (((7 + 6!) \times (6! + 9)) - (8! - 4)) \\ 489696 &:= (((6! + ((9!/6) + 9)) \times 8) + 4!) \\ 489867 &:= ((7 \times ((6^8) - (9 \times 8)))/4!) \\ 491395 &:= (-5 - (-(((9 \times 3) + (1^9)))!)/(4!)) \\ 491424 &:= (4! - (-(((2 \times ((4 + 1) + 9)))!)/(4!)) \\ 491485 &:= ((5! \times (8^4)) + ((1 - (9 \times 4))) \\ 491513 &:= -3! - 1 + 5! \times (-1 + 9)^4 \\ 491514 &:= -(4 - 1)! + 5! \times (-1 + 9)^4 \\ 491515 &:= -5 + 1 \times 5! \times (-1 + 9)^4 \\ 491521 &:= 1^2 + 5! \times (-1 + 9)^4 \\ 491523 &:= 3!/2 + 5! \times (-1 + 9)^4 \\ 491526 &:= (6/2)! + 5! \times (-1 + 9)^4 \\ 491532 &:= 2 \times 3! + 5! \times (-1 + 9)^4 \\ 491534 &:= (((4^3!) \times 5!) + ((1 + 9) + 4)) \\ 491535 &:= (((((5 + 3)^5) + 1) \times (-9 + 4!)) \\ 491542 &:= -2 + 4! + 5! \times (-1 + 9)^4 \\ 491544 &:= (4! + ((4^{5+1}) \times ((9 - 4)!)) \\ 491552 &:= 2^5 + 5! \times (-1 + 9)^4 \\ 491568 &:= 8 \times 6 + 5! \times (-1 + 9)^4 \\ 492055 &:= (-5 \times ((-5 \times ((0! + 2)^9)) + 4)) \\ 492386 &:= (((((6! + 8!) \times 3!) \times 2) - (94)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 492476 &:= ((6! \times ((74 + 2) \times 9)) - 4) \\ 492504 &:= (((((4 - 0!) \times 5!)^2) + 9!) + 4!) \\ 492516 &:= (((6! - 1) - (5!^2)) \times (-9 \times 4)) \\ 492538 &:= (((8! + 3!) + (5!^2)) \times 9) + 4) \\ 492635 &:= ((5 - 3!!) \times (-((6! + ((2 - 9)))) - 4!)) \\ 492648 &:= ((8! - 4 + 6!)/2 + 9) \times 4! \\ 492688 &:= (-8 + (((8! + 6!)/2) + 9) \times 4!) \\ 493126 &:= (-((6! + 2)) \times ((1 - 3!!) + (9 \times 4))) \\ 493162 &:= (-2 - (-((6! + 1) \times (3!! - (9 \times 4)))) \\ 493263 &:= (-3 + ((6! - 2) \times (3!! + (-9 - 4!)))) \\ 493344 &:= (((4! \times 4)^3) + (3 \times 9!))/4) \\ 493464 &:= (-((4! - 6!)) \times ((-4!) + 3!!) + (9 + 4)) \\ 493662 &:= (-26) \times ((6! - (3^9)) - 4!) \\ 493673 &:= ((3!! \times (-7 + 6!)) - (((3^9) + 4))) \\ 493732 &:= (2 \times ((3!! \times (7^3)) - (94))) \\ 493872 &:= (2 \times (7! - ((8! \times (3 - 9)) + 4!)) \\ 493887 &:= (((7! - 8!) \times (-8 - 3!)) + (-9 - 4!)) \\ 493897 &:= ((7! \times 98) - ((3 \times 9) - 4)) \\ 493917 &:= (((((7 + 1)!) + 9!) - 3) - (9!/(-4))) \\ 493918 &:= (((8! + 1) + 9!) - 3) - (9!/(-4)) \\ 493923 &:= (((3! + 2)!) + ((9! + 3) - (9!/(-4)))) \\ 493926 &:= (((((6 + 2)!) + 9!) + 3!) - (9!/(-4))) \\ 493928 &:= (((8! + 2) + 9!) + 3!) - (9!/(-4)) \\ 493982 &:= (((2^{8+9}) + 3!) + 9!) + 4! \\ 494018 &:= (((8 - 1)!) + 0!) \times (4 + 94) \\ 494616 &:= ((6! \times (((1 \times 6)!) - 4!) - 9)) - 4! \\ 494633 &:= (-3 - ((3!! \times (-((6! - 4!) - 9))) + 4)) \\ 494636 &:= ((6! \times ((3 + 6!) - (4 \times 9))) - 4) \\ 494637 &:= -7 + 3!! \times (6! - 4! - 9) + 4 \\ 494644 &:= (((4!/4)!) \times ((6! - 4!) - 9)) + 4) \\ 494662 &:= (-2 + ((6! \times ((6! - 4!) - 9)) + 4!)) \\ 494796 &:= (-6 + ((9 + 7!) \times (4 + 94))) \\ 495033 &:= (33 \times ((0! - 5!) + (9!/4!)) \\ 495266 &:= ((6! \times (6! - (2^5))) - (94)) \\ 495284 &:= (-4 + ((8! - (-((2 - 5)^9)) \times 4!)) \\ 495756 &:= (((6 - 5!) - 7!) - 5!) \times (-94) \\ 496744 &:= (-4 \times (4! - (((7^6) + (9^4)))) \\ 497276 &:= (((6! \times 7!)/27) + 9!) - 4) \\ 497472 &:= (((2 + 7!) \times 4) + (7!/9)) \times 4! \\ 497499 &:= ((-99) \times ((4! - 7!) - 9)) + 4! \\ 497536 &:= ((6! \times (3!! - 5!)) + ((7 + 9)^4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 497635 &:= (-5 - (3! \times (((6^7) - 9!) + 4))) \\ 497673 &:= ((3 \times ((7 + 6) - 7!)) \times (-9 - 4!)) \\ 497688 &:= (((8 + 8) \times ((6^7)/9)) + 4!) \\ 497705 &:= (5 \times (0! + ((7! \times (-79))/(-4)))) \\ 497766 &:= (-6 \times (((6^7) + 7) - 9!) - 4!) \\ 497822 &:= (-2 + (((2^8) + 7!) \times 94)) \\ 497824 &:= ((-(((4 - 2)^8)) - 7!) \times (-94)) \\ 498933 &:= (-3 + (((3 \times 9!)/8) + 9!) - 4!) \\ 498936 &:= ((((-((6 - 3)) \times 9!)/(-8)) + 9!) - 4!) \\ 498943 &:= -((3! + (((4! + 9) \times (8 - 9!))/4!)) \\ 498944 &:= (-((4 \times 4) - (-9 \times (8! + (9!/4!)))) \\ 498947 &:= (((7 + 4) \times 9!)/8) - (9 + 4) \\ 498948 &:= (-((8 + 4) - (-9 \times (8! + (9!/4!)))) \\ 498955 &:= (((((5 + 5))! + 9!)/8) - (9 - 4)) \\ 498956 &:= ((6! \times ((5 + (9 \times 8)) \times 9)) - 4) \\ 498961 &:= ((1^6) - (-9 \times (8! + (9!/4!)))) \\ 498963 &:= (((3 + 6))! - (((9! + 8) \times (-9))/4!)) \\ 498964 &:= ((4!/6) - (-9 \times (8! + (9!/4!)))) \\ 498965 &:= (((5 + 6) \times 9!)/8) + (9 - 4) \\ 498967 &:= ((7!/6!) - (-9 \times (8! + (9!/4!)))) \\ 498969 &:= ((9! + 6) - (((9! + 8) \times (-9))/4!)) \\ 498973 &:= (((((3 + 7))! + 9!)/8) + (9 + 4)) \\ 498984 &:= (((((4!/(-8)) \times 9!)/(-8)) + 9!) + 4!) \\ 499162 &:= (((-2 - ((6 + 1))!) \times (-99)) + 4) \\ 499175 &:= (5! + (((7! + 1) \times 99) - 4)) \\ 499182 &:= (((-2 - ((8 - 1))!) \times (-99)) + 4!) \\ 499253 &:= (((-3 - ((5 + 2))!) \times (-99)) - 4) \\ 499257 &:= (((7! \times (-5 - 2)) - 9) \times (-9 - 4!)) \\ 499479 &:= ((((-9 - 7!) + 4) \times (-99)) + 4!) \\ 499656 &:= ((6! \times (-5 - 699)) - 4!) \\ 499676 &:= (6! + (((7 \times 6!) \times 99) - 4)) \\ 499677 &:= ((-77) \times ((6! \times (-9)) - 9)) + 4! \\ 499703 &:= (3!! - ((0! + ((7! \times (-99)) - 4!)))) \\ 499704 &:= (((4 - 0!))!) - ((7! \times (-99)) - 4!) \\ 499824 &:= (((4! + 2) \times (89 \times 9)) \times 4!) \\ 499968 &:= ((8! - ((6 \times 9!) + 9!))/(-9 - 4)) \\ 499975 &:= (5! + (((7! + 9) \times 99) + 4)) \\ 500424 &:= (((4 + 2))! - 4!) \times (-0!) + ((0! + 5)!) \\ 500544 &:= (4! \times (((4! + 5!)^{0!+0!}) + 5!)) \\ 501143 &:= ((3!! - (4! - 1)) \times (-1 + ((0! + 5)!)!) \\ 501384 &:= (((-(4 + 8)) + 3!!)^{1+0!}) + 5! \\ 503334 &:= (((-4!) + 3!!) + (3!)) \times (-3 + ((0! + 5)!)!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 503755 &:= (((5! \times 5!) - 7) \times (30 + 5)) \\ 503976 &:= (((6 - 7!) + (9!/(-3))) \times (0! - 5)) \\ 503988 &:= -8! + (-8 + 9!) \times 3!/(-0! + 5) \\ 504075 &:= (-5 \times (((7! + 0!) \times 4) - 0!) \times (-5)) \\ 504273 &:= (((3!! - 7)^2) - (4^{0!+5})) \\ 504475 &:= ((((-5 \times 7!) - 4!) \times (-4)) - 0!) \times 5) \\ 506239 &:= (((9^3!) - 2) - ((6 + 0!)! \times 5)) \\ 506684 &:= (-4 - ((-8 - 6!) \times (6! - (-((0! - 5)!)!))) \\ 506743 &:= (((3!! - (4! - 7)) \times (6! + 0!)) - 5!) \\ 506886 &:= (6! - 8 - 8) \times 6! + 0! + 5 \\ 506937 &:= (((-7 + 3!!) \times (-9 + 6!)) - (0! + 5)) \\ 506967 &:= (((7 - 6!) \times (9 - 6!)) + (-((0! - 5)!)!) \\ 506983 &:= (((3!! - (8 + 9)) \times (6! + 0!)) + 5!) \\ 507344 &:= (-((4^4)) - (3!! \times (-705))) \\ 507625 &:= ((5^2) - (6! \times (-705))) \\ 507626 &:= ((6! - 2) \times (((6! - 7) - 0!) - 5)) \\ 507636 &:= ((6 \times 3!) - (6! \times (-705))) \\ 507934 &:= ((4 + 3) \times ((9! - 70)/5)) \\ 507955 &:= (-55 + 9!) \times 7/05 \\ 507973 &:= (((((3! \times 7) - 9!) \times 7) + 0!)/(-5)) \\ 507997 &:= (-7 \times (-9 - ((9! - 70)/5))) \\ 508025 &:= ((5 + 2) \times (-0!) - (((8 + 0!))!)/(-5)) \\ 508029 &:= (((9! - 2) \times (0! - 8)) + 0!)/(-5) \\ 508031 &:= (-1 - ((-(3! + 0!)) \times ((8 + 0!))!)/5) \\ 508032 &:= (((2^3!) - 0!) \times 8!)/05 \\ 508039 &:= (((9! + 3!) - 0!) \times (8 - 0!))/5 \\ 508067 &:= (-7 \times ((-6 + 0!) + (((8 + 0!))!)/(-5)) \\ 508159 &:= (((9!/(-5)) - 1) \times (-8 + 0!)) + 5! \\ 508176 &:= ((6! - (-7 \times ((1 + 8)!)!))/05) \\ 508323 &:= ((3!!^2) - (-3 - (8!/(0! - 5)))) \\ 508326 &:= (((6!^2) + 3!) + (8!/(0! - 5))) \\ 508363 &:= (((3! - 6!)) \times (3!! - 8)) - 05 \\ 508364 &:= (-4 - (-6 \times ((3!! - 8) \times (-0! - 5!)))) \\ 508365 &:= ((-5 + 6!) \times (3!! - (8 + ((0 \times 5)!)!)) \\ 508368 &:= (((8 - 6!) \times 3!) \times (((8 \times 0)!) - 5!)) \\ 508373 &:= (((3!! - 7)^{-3!+8}) - ((0! - 5))) \\ 508376 &:= (((6! - 7) \times (3!! - 8)) + ((0! + 5)!) \\ 508535 &:= (53 \times ((5! \times 80) - 5)) \\ 508597 &:= ((-7 \times ((9!/(-5)) - (80))) + 5) \\ 508752 &:= ((((-(2 - 5))!)! + ((-7 \times ((8 + 0!))!)/(-5))) \\ 508753 &:= (3!! - ((5 - (-7 \times ((8 + 0!))!))/(-5)) \\ 509616 &:= (((6! - 1) \times 6!) - (((9 - 0!))!)/5) \end{aligned}$$

- 510336 := ((6! × 3!!) - (((3! + 0!) + 1)!/5))
510468 := (((5 + 1)! + 0!) × ((-4 + 6!) - 8))
510468 := (-8 + 6! - 4) × (0! + (1 + 5)!)
510636 := 6! + (-3! + 6!)^{0!+1} + 5!
511209 := (((5 + 1)! - 1) × (((2 + 0!)!)! - 9))
511209 := ((-9 + (((0! + 2)!)!) × (-1 + ((1 + 5)!)!))
511235 := (((-5 + 3!!)²) + ((1 + 1) × 5))
511343 := (((3!! - 4) × (-3!)) - 1) × (1 - 5!))
511343 := (-((5! - 1)) × (-1 - ((3!! - 4) × 3!)))
511345 := (((-((5!/4!)) + 3!!)¹⁺¹) + 5!)
511920 := (((5 + 1)! - (1 × 9)) × (((2 + 0!)!)!))
511936 := ((5 + 11) - ((9 - 3!!) × 6!))
511936 := ((6! × (3!! - 9)) + (1 + 15))
512039 := (((-9 + 3!!) × (((0! + 2)!)!) - (1 - 5!))
512039 := ((5! - 1) + (((2 + 0!)!)! × (3!! - 9)))
512632 := (((2 - 3!) + 6!)²) - (-((1 - 5)!)!))
512635 := (-5 - (((3! - 6!) + 2) × ((1 + 5)!)!))
512636 := -(((6! × ((3! - 6!) + 2)) - ((1 - 5)!)!))
512637 := -(((7! + 3) - ((6!)²) - ((1 + 5)!)!))
512638 := (((8 - 3!!) × (-6!)) - (2 × (1⁵)))
512641 := (((-((1 × 4)) + 6!)²) - 15)
512645 := (-5 + (((-4 + 6!)²) - (1 + 5)))
512646 := (-6 + (((-4 + 6!)²) + ((1 - 5)!)!))
512648 := (-8 - (((-4 + 6!)²) × (-1⁵)))
512651 := (((1 - 5) + 6!)²) - (1 × 5)
512652 := (-((2 - 5)!)! × ((6! - 2) × (-1 + 5!)))
512662 := (((2 + 6!) - 6!)²) + (1 + 5)
512664 := (4! - (((6 - 6!) + 2) × ((1 + 5)!)!))
513128 := ((-8 + (((2 + 1)!) × 3!)) × (-1 + 5!))
513216 := ((6⁽¹⁺²⁾)! × (3! + (1 × 5)))
513235 := (-5!) + (((3!!²) - ((3! + 1)!) - 5))
513237 := (-7!) - (((3!!²) - 3) × (-1)) + 5!))
513238 := ((8 + 3) × (2 + (3!¹⁺⁵)))
513239 := (((-9 + 3!!) + 2) × 3!!) + (-1 - 5!))
513246 := (((6! - (4 + 2)) × (3!! - 1)) - 5!)
513247 := ((7 - (((4 + 2)!) × 3!)) × (1 - 5!))
513264 := (((4! + (6!)²) - ((3! + 1)!) - 5!)
513335 := (((5 + 3!) × (3!^{3!})) - (1 - 5!))
513336 := (((6^{3!}) × ((3! + 3!) - 1)) + 5!)
513347 := (((7 + 4) × ((3!^{3!}) + 1)) + 5!)
513364 := (-4 + 6! - 3) × 3!! - 1 + 5
513371 := (((1 - 7) + 3!!) × (3!! - 1)) + 5)
513375 := ((5! × ((-7 + 3!!) × 3!)) + 15)
513377 := (-7 - (((7 - 3!!) × 3!!) - (-((1 - 5)!)!))
513384 := (4! - (((8 - 3!!) × 3!!) - (((1 + 5)!)!))
513604 := ((-4 - ((0 - 6!) × 3!)) × (-1 + 5!))
513723 := (((3 × 2)!)! - 7!) + 3) × (1 - 5!))
513737 := (-((7³)) - ((-7!) + 3!!) × (-1 + 5!))
513774 := ((4! - 7) × ((7! - 3) × (1 + 5)))
513842 := ((-2 + (((4!/8)!) × 3!)) × (-1 + 5!))
513933 := (((-3 - 3!!) × (9 - 3!)) + (-1 × 5!))
513961 := ((1 - (6! × (9 - 3))) × (1 - 5!))
513965 := (((-5 + 6!) × ((9 - 3)!) - 1) - 5!)
513968 := ((-8 - 6!) × ((9 - 3!!) + (1 × 5)))
514056 := (((6! × (5! - 0!)) - 4) × (1 + 5))
514073 := ((3!! - 7) × (((0 × 4)!) + ((1 + 5)!)!))
514075 := (-5 + ((7! - ((-((0! - 4)!)!)!)) × (-1 + 5!))
514085 := (((-((5 - 8)!)! - 0!) × (((4 - 1)!)! - 5))
514199 := (9! + (((((9 + 1)!)! / 4!) - 1) + 5!))
514233 := (((3!! - 3)²) + (4! × (1 + 5)))
514304 := (((((4 - 0!)!)! × 3!!) - (4¹⁺⁵))
514336 := (((6! - 3!) × 3!!) + (4⁻¹⁺⁵))
514437 := (((7! + 3) - ((4!/4)!)! × (-1 + 5!))
514536 := (((6^{3!}) + 5!) × (-4 - 15))
514656 := (((6! - 5) × 6!) - 4!) - ((1 × 5)!)
514672 := (-((2⁷)) + (6! × (((4 - 1)!)! - 5)))
514824 := (4! + (((-((2 - 8)!)! × (((4 - 1)!)! - 5)))
515368 := (((-8 + 6!) × (3!! + (5 - 1))) - 5!)
515483 := (((3!! - 8) × (4 + ((5 + 1)!)!)) - 5)
515634 := (((4 - 3!!) × (-6!)) + (5! - (1 + 5)))
515635 := (((5 - 3!!) × ((-6 × 5!) - 1)) + 5!)
515646 := (6! - 4) × 6! + 5! + 1 + 5
515664 := ((((-4 + 6!) × 6!) + ((5 - 1)!)! + 5!)
515984 := ((4! - ((8!/9) - 5!)) × (1 - 5!))
516122 := (((2 - ((2 + 1)!)!)! × (-6! - 1)) - 5!)
516123 := (((3!! - 2) × (-1 + 6!)) + (1 - 5!))
516186 := ((6! - (8 + 1)) × (6! + (1 + 5)))
516216 := (((6! - (1 + 2)) × 6!) - (-((1 - 5)!)!))
516242 := ((-2 + ((4 + 2)!)! × (6! - (1⁵)))
516247 := ((((((7 - 4)!)! - 2) × (6! - 1)) + 5)
516264 := (4! - (((6/2) - 6!) × ((1 + 5)!)!))
516265 := (((-5 + 6!)²) + ((6 + (1⁵))!))
516333 := ((3!! × 3!!) - ((3⁶⁺¹) - 5!))

$$\begin{aligned} 516348 &:= (-8 - (((4 - 3!!) \times (6! + 1)) - 5!)) \\ 516352 &:= -(((2^{5+3!}) - (6! \times ((1 + 5)!))) \\ 516355 &:= 5! - 5 + (-3 + 6!) \times (1 + 5)! \\ 516365 &:= 5! + (6! - 3) \times 6! \times 1 + 5 \\ 516432 &:= (((-2 + 3!!) + 4!) \times (6! - (-((1 - 5)!))) \\ 516456 &:= (-(((6^5)/4)) + (6! \times ((1 + 5)!))) \\ 516841 &:= (((-1 + (((4!/8)!))!) \times (6! - 1)) - 5!) \\ 516936 &:= ((6! - 3!) \times ((9 + 6!) - (1 \times 5))) \\ 516961 &:= ((-1 + 6!)^{9-6-1^5}) \\ 517335 &:= -(((5! \times ((3^3!) - 7!)) - 15)) \\ 517436 &:= ((6! \times 3!!) - (4 - (-((7 + 1)) \times 5!))) \\ 517566 &:= ((6! \times 6!) - ((5! \times 7) - (1 + 5))) \\ 517567 &:= (((7! - 6!) \times 5!) + (-7 \times (-1 + 5!))) \\ 517624 &:= ((-(4 \times 2) + 6!) \times (7 + ((1 + 5)!))) \\ 517626 &:= (-6 \times (2 - ((6! - 7) \times (1 + 5!)))) \\ 517631 &:= (((1 - 3!!) \times (-6!)) - (-71 + 5!)) \\ 517633 &:= (((-3!) - 3!!) \times (-6! - 7)) - (1 \times 5) \\ 517634 &:= (-4 - ((3! + 6!) \times (7 - ((1 + 5)!))) \\ 517656 &:= (-((6! + (5! \times (6! - 7!)))) - (-((1 - 5)!))!) \\ 517663 &:= (((3!! \times 6!) - ((6! - 7))) - (-((1 - 5)!))!) \\ 517665 &:= ((5! \times ((-6 - 6!) + 7!)) - 15) \\ 517673 &:= -((3!! + (7 + ((6! - 7!) \times ((1 \times 5)!)))) \\ 517675 &:= (-5 - (((7! \times 6!)/(-7)) + ((1 + 5)!))) \\ 517676 &:= -((6! + (((7! \times 6!)/(-7)) - ((1 - 5)))) \\ 517704 &:= (4! - ((0! + (7!/(-7))) \times ((1 + 5)!))) \\ 517748 &:= (((8! + 4!) \times 77)/(1 + 5)) \\ 518063 &:= ((3!! \times 6!) - ((0! - ((8! \times (-1))/5!))) \\ 518233 &:= ((3!! \times 3!!) - ((2 \times 81) + 5)) \\ 518235 &:= (-5!) + ((3!!^2) - ((8 + 1) \times 5)) \\ 518256 &:= (-6 \times ((-5!) \times (-((2 - 8)!))!) + (-((1 - 5)!))!) \\ 518263 &:= ((3!! \times 6!) - (((2 \times 8) + 1) + 5!)) \\ 518264 &:= (((4! - ((6!^2) + 8)) \times (-1)) - 5!) \\ 518265 &:= (-5!) - ((-6!) \times (-((2 - 8)!))! + 15) \\ 518266 &:= (((6! \times 6!) - (2 \times (8 - 1))) - 5!) \\ 518271 &:= (((-((1 - 7)!))!)^2) + (-((8 + 1)) - 5!)) \\ 518272 &:= (-((2^7)) + ((-((2 - 8)!))! \times ((1 + 5)!)) \\ 518275 &:= (-5 - (((7! - (-((2 - 8)!))!) - 1) \times (-5!))) \\ 518279 &:= (((9!/(-7)) \times (-2 + 8)) - 1) - 5! \\ 518304 &:= (4! - (((-0!) - 3!!) + (((8 - 1)!))! \times (-5!)) \\ 518314 &:= (((((4 - 1)!))! \times 3!!) - (81 + 5)) \\ 518324 &:= (((4 + 2)! \times 3!!) - (81 - 5)) \\ 518334 &:= (-4!) + ((3!! \times 3!!) - (((8 - 1)!)/5!)) \\ 518336 &:= ((6! \times 3!!) - (-((3! - 8))^{1+5})) \\ 518337 &:= (-7 + ((3!! \times 3!!) - (8!/((1 + 5)!))) \\ 518344 &:= (((4!/4)! \times 3!!) - (8!/((1 + 5)!))) \\ 518351 &:= (-1 - (((-5!) \times 3!!) + 8) \times (1 + 5)) \\ 518352 &:= (((-((2 - 5)!))!) \times 3!!) - (8 \times (1 + 5)) \\ 518353 &:= ((-3!) \times ((-5!) \times 3!!) + 8) + (1^5) \\ 518356 &:= ((-6 \times ((-5!) \times 3!!) + 8) - ((1 - 5)) \\ 518358 &:= (((((8 - 5)!))! \times 3!!) - (((8 - 1)!)/5!)) \\ 518364 &:= -4 + 6! \times 3!! + 8 \times (1 - 5) \\ 518376 &:= ((6!^{7+3-8}) - (-((1 - 5)!))! \\ 518377 &:= (((7!/7) \times 3!!) - (8 + 15)) \\ 518384 &:= (-((4! - 8)) + (3!!^{8-1-5})) \\ 518385 &:= ((5!/(-8)) + (3!!^{8-1-5})) \\ 518386 &:= ((6!^{8-3!}) - ((8 + 1) + 5)) \\ 518391 &:= (-((1 \times 9)) + (3!!^{8-1-5})) \\ 518393 &:= ((3!! \times ((9 - 3)!)) - (8 - (1^5))) \\ 518395 &:= (((5! \times 9!)/(3 + 81)) - 5) \\ 518396 &:= ((6! \times ((9 - 3)!)) - ((8 + 1) - 5)) \\ 518399 &:= (-((9/9)) + (3!!^{8-1-5})) \\ 518404 &:= (4 - 0!)!! \times (4!/8)!! - 1 + 5 \\ 518411 &:= (11 + (((4!/8)!))! \times ((1 + 5)!)) \\ 518413 &:= ((3!! \times ((-((1 - 4)!))!) + ((8 \times 1) + 5)) \\ 518415 &:= (((5 + 1)! \times ((4!/8)!))! + 15) \\ 518416 &:= ((6! \times (-((1 - 4)!))!) + (-8 + (-((1 - 5)!))!) \\ 518422 &:= (22 + (((4!/8)!))! \times ((1 + 5)!)) \\ 518423 &:= ((3!!^2) + ((4 \times (8 - 1)) - 5)) \\ 518424 &:= (4! - (((2 + 4)! - ((8 - 1)!)) \times 5!)) \\ 518425 &:= ((5^2) + (((4!/8)!))! \times ((1 + 5)!)) \\ 518426 &:= ((6!^2) + (((4 \times 8) - 1) - 5)) \\ 518433 &:= ((3!! \times 3!!) + (48 - 15)) \\ 518436 &:= ((6! \times 3!!) + (((4 \times 8) - 1) + 5)) \\ 518444 &:= (44 + (((4!/8)!))! \times ((1 + 5)!)) \\ 518455 &:= (55 + (((4!/8)!))! \times ((1 + 5)!)) \\ 518463 &:= ((3!! \times 6!) + (48 + 15)) \\ 518466 &:= (((6! \times 6!) + 4!) + (((8 - 1)!)/5!)) \\ 518476 &:= ((6! \times (((7 - 4)!))!) + (81 - 5)) \\ 518477 &:= (77 + (((4!/8)!))! \times ((1 + 5)!)) \\ 518486 &:= ((6!^{8/4}) + ((81 + 5))) \\ 518488 &:= (88 + (((4!/8)!))! \times ((1 + 5)!)) \\ 518499 &:= (99 + (((4!/8)!))! \times ((1 + 5)!)) \\ 518513 &:= ((3!! \times ((1 + 5)!)) + (-((8 - 1)) + 5!)) \\ 518525 &:= 5! + (2 \times 5)!/(8 - 1) - 5 \end{aligned}$$

- 518533 := ((3!! × 3!!) + (5! + ((8 × 1) + 5)))
 518535 := (5! - ((-3!!) × ((-(5 - 8))!)) - 15))
 518536 := ((6! × 3!!) + (((5!/8) + 1) + 5!))
 518736 := ((6! × 3!!) + ((7 × 8) × (1 + 5)))
 518784 := (((4! × 8!) + 7!) × 8)/15)
 519048 := ((8 - (((4 - 0!)!))! × (-9 - ((1 + 5)!))
 519066 := ((6! × (6! + 0!)) - (9 × (1 + 5)))
 519127 := -7! + 2¹⁹ - 1 - 5!
 519133 := ((3!! × (3!! + 1)) + ((9 - 1) + 5))
 519233 := ((3!! × 3!!) + (-((2 - 9) × (-1 + 5!)))
 519331 := (((1 + 3!!) × 3!!) + (91 + 5!))
 519336 := ((6! × 3!!) + (39 × (-((1 - 5)!)))
 519453 := (((3 + (5! × (-4))) × 9) × (-1 - 5!))
 519666 := ((6! × 6!) + (-6 × (-91) - 5!))
 519777 := (((7!/7) - 7) × (9 + ((1 + 5)!))
 519841 := ((1 + (((4!/8))!))!)^{(9+1)/5}
 519961 := (((1 + 6!)^{9/9+1}) + 5!)
 521162 := (((2 + 6!)¹⁺¹) - 2) - 5!
 521163 := (((-3 - 6!) × (-1 - (((1 + 2)!))!)) - 5!)
 521164 := (((4 + 6!) - (1 + 1))²) - 5!
 521235 := ((-5 + 3!!) × ((2 + 1)^{(-2+5)!})
 521263 := ((-(3! + 6!)) × (2 - (((1 + 2)!))!)) - 5)
 521264 := (4 × (((6!/2) + 1)²) - 5))
 521279 := (((9 - 7) + (((2 + 1)!))!²) - 5)
 521283 := ((3 + ((8 - 2)!)) × (1 + (-((2 - 5)!))!))
 521284 := (((((4!/8))!))! + 2)⁻¹⁻²⁺⁵
 521964 := ((4 - 6!) × (-9 - (((1²) + 5)!))
 522036 := (((6! + 3!)⁰²) - ((2 + 5)!))
 522236 := (((6! × 3) - 2) × (2 + (2 × 5!)))
 522359 := ((9 × 5!) + (((3!! + 2)²) - 5))
 522603 := -((3! - (((0! + 6!) + 2)²) - 5!))
 522609 := ((((((9 × 0)! + 6!) + 2)²) - 5!))
 522693 := (3 × (-9 + (6! × (2 + (2 × 5!))))
 522713 := ((3!! - 1) × (722 + 5))
 522848 := ((8 × (4⁸)) - (2 × (-((2 - 5)!))!))
 523236 := (((6! + 3!)²) - (32 × 5!))
 523296 := ((6! - 9) × (23 × (2⁵)))
 523302 := (((2 + 0!)^{3!}) × (3!! - 2)) - 5!
 523315 := ((-5!) + ((1 + 3!))!) + ((3!!)² - 5))
 523317 := ((7! - 1) + ((3!! × 3!!) + (-2 - 5!))
 523318 := (((8! × 13) - 3!!) + (-2 - 5!))
 523328 := ((8! - (2^{3!})) × (3 + (2 × 5)))
 523334 := (((-4 - 3!!) × (-3 - 3!)) + (2 - 5!))
 523344 := ((4! × (-4)) + ((3!! × 3!!) + ((2 + 5)!))
 523345 := ((5⁴) + (3!! × (3!! + (-((2 - 5)!))!))
 523347 := (((7! + 4!) + 3) + ((3!!)² - 5!))
 523354 := (4! - (((-5 - 3!!) × (3!! + 2)) + 5!))
 523356 := ((6! × (-5)) + (((3!! + (3!))²) - 5!))
 523387 := ((7! - (8 × 3!)) + ((3!!)² - 5))
 523395 := (-((5 × 9)) + ((3!! × 3!!) + ((2 + 5)!))
 523416 := (((((6 + 1)! - 4!) - (-3!!) × (-((2 - 5)!))!))
 523417 := (((7! + 1) - 4!) - (-3!!) × (-((2 - 5)!))!))
 523422 := ((-2 + ((2 + 4)!)) × (3^{(-2+5)!})
 523427 := ((7! - (2 × 4)) + ((3!!)² + 5))
 523431 := (((1 + 3!))! - 4) + ((3!!)² - 5))
 523433 := ((3!! × 3!!) - ((4 + 3) - ((2 + 5)!))
 523435 := (-5 + ((3!!^{-4+3!}) + ((2 + 5)!))
 523436 := ((6! × 3!!) - ((4!/3!) - ((2 + 5)!))
 523437 := (7! + ((3!!^{-4+3!}) + ((2 - 5)!))
 523451 := (-(((1 + 5)!)) + (((4 + 3!))² - 5))
 523452 := ((((-((2 - 5)!))! + 4) × (3!! - ((2 - 5)!))
 523456 := (-((6! - 5!)) + (((4 + 3!))² - 5!))
 523458 := (8! - 54) × (3 + 2 × 5)
 523461 := ((-1 × 6!) + (((4 + 3!))² + 5))
 523464 := (4! + ((6!^{-4+3!}) + ((2 + 5)!))
 523648 := (8! - ((4^{(6-3)!}) × (2 - 5!))
 523675 := (-5 - ((((-7 - 6!) × 3!) - 2) × 5!))
 523744 := ((-4 × (-4 + 7!)) × (3! - (2⁵)))
 523745 := (((5⁴) × ((7!/3!) - 2)) - 5)
 523746 := (((6! + 4!) - 7!) + 3) × (-2 - 5!))
 523804 := (-4 × (0! - (((8^{3!})/2) - 5!))
 523844 := (-4 - ((4! - 8!) × (3 + (2 × 5))))
 523848 := ((8! - 4!) × (8 + ((3 - 2) × 5)))
 523968 := ((8 × (6! - 9)) + ((3!!)² - 5!))
 524038 := (8 + 3!!) × (-0! + 4)! - 2 - 5!
 524048 := (-8 + ((((((4 - 0!)!))! + 4)²) - 5!))
 524053 := (-3 + (((((5 + 0)!))! + 4)²) - 5!))
 524056 := (((6! + 5) - 0!)⁴⁻²) - 5!
 524095 := (((5 + 9) - 0!) × (((4 × 2)! - 5))
 524136 := ((6! × (3!! + 1)) - ((4! - ((2 + 5)!))!))
 524171 := ((((((1 × 7) - 1)! + 4)²) - 5)
 524173 := ((3! + 7) × (1 + ((4!/(-2 - 5)!))!))

$$\begin{aligned} 524184 &:= (4! + (8! \times (((1 \times 4) \times 2) + 5))) \\ 524189 &:= (9! - (((8! + 1) \times (-4)) - (25))) \\ 524228 &:= (((8!/2) - 2) \times (4! + 2)) + 5! \\ 524238 &:= ((8! + 3!) \times (((2 + 4) + 2) + 5)) \\ 524264 &:= (-4 \times (6 - (2^{4! - 2 - 5}))) \\ 524278 &:= (((8! \times ((7 + 2) + 4)) - 2) + 5!) \\ 524285 &:= (5 + 8!/2) \times (4! + 2) - 5 \\ 524296 &:= ((((-(((6 - 9) \times 2)))! + 4)^2) + 5!) \\ 524302 &:= (((2 + 0!)!) + (((3!! + 4)^2) + 5!)) \\ 524303 &:= ((3! + 0!) + (((3!! + 4)^2) + 5!)) \\ 524328 &:= (8 \times (((-2 + 3!)^{4 \times 2}) + 5)) \\ 524344 &:= ((4! + 4!) + (((3!! + 4)^2) + 5!)) \\ 524358 &:= (((8 + 5) \times (3! + ((4 \times 2)!)) + 5!) \\ 524382 &:= (2 \times ((8^3!) + (42 + 5))) \\ 524386 &:= ((6!/8) + (((3!! + 4)^2) + 5!)) \\ 524394 &:= (((((4^9) - 3) - 4) \times 2) + 5!) \\ 524408 &:= (((8 \times 04^4)/2) + 5!) \\ 524467 &:= (((7 + 6) \times (4! + ((4 \times 2)!)) - 5) \\ 524485 &:= ((5 + 8) \times (((4 + 4)! + (25))) \\ 524488 &:= (8 \times (((-8 + 4!)^4) + (25))) \\ 524524 &:= (-4 + ((2^{-5+4!}) + (2 \times 5!))) \\ 524528 &:= (((8^{2+5})/4) + (2 \times 5!)) \\ 524636 &:= (((6! \times (3^6)) - 4) - (2 \times 5!)) \\ 524643 &:= (((3!! + (4^{6+4}))/2) - 5) \\ 524656 &:= ((6! - 5!) + (((6! + 4)^2) - 5!)) \\ 524764 &:= (-4 \times (((-6 - 7!) \times (4! + 2)) + 5)) \\ 524776 &:= (6! + (((7!/7) + 4)^2) - 5!) \\ 524784 &:= (((((4!/8)! + 7!) \times (-((4^2)) + 5!)) \\ 524849 &:= ((9 + 4) \times (8! + ((4! \times 2) + 5))) \\ 524873 &:= (3!! - (7 + (8! \times (-((4 \times 2) + 5)))))) \\ 524876 &:= (((((6 + 7) \times 8!) - 4) + ((-((2 - 5)))!))! \\ 524885 &:= (((5 + 8) \times 8!) + ((4 + 2)! + 5) \\ 524933 &:= ((3!! \times (3!! + 9)) + ((4! \times 2) + 5)) \\ 524936 &:= ((6! \times 3!!) + (((9^4) - 25))) \\ 525248 &:= (8 \times (((4 \times 2)^5) \times 2) + 5!) \\ 525265 &:= (((5 + 6!)^2) - (5! \times (-2 - 5))) \\ 525368 &:= ((((-((8^6)) - 3!!) + 5!) \times (-2)) - 5!) \\ 525505 &:= (((((5! + 0!) \times 5) + 5!)^2) - 5!) \\ 525605 &:= (((5 + 0!)!) \times (6! + (5 \times 2))) + 5) \\ 525606 &:= (6 \times (0! + ((6! + (5 \times 2)) \times 5!))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 525613 &:= -(((3! + 1) - (((6! + 5)^2) - 5))) \\ 525614 &:= -((((4 - 1)!) - (((6! + 5)^2) - 5))) \\ 525615 &:= (-5 + (((((1 \times 6)!) + 5)^2) - 5)) \\ 525621 &:= ((1^2) + (((6! + 5)^2) - 5)) \\ 525623 &:= ((3!/2) + (((6! + 5)^2) - 5)) \\ 525624 &:= (-((4 + 2)) + (((6! + 5)^2) + 5)) \\ 525626 &:= (((6/2)!) + (((6! + 5)^2) - 5)) \\ 525631 &:= ((1^3) + (((6! + 5)^2) + 5)) \\ 525632 &:= ((2 \times 3!) + (((6! + 5)^2) - 5)) \\ 525633 &:= ((-3 + 3!) + (((6! + 5)^2) + 5)) \\ 525634 &:= ((4!/3!) + (((6! + 5)^2) + 5)) \\ 525635 &:= ((5 \times 3) + (((6! + 5)^2) - 5)) \\ 525636 &:= (((6 - 3)!) + (((6! + 5)^2) + 5)) \\ 525637 &:= ((7!/3!!) + (((6! + 5)^2) + 5)) \\ 525638 &:= (8 + ((((-((3 - 6)))!) + 5)^2) + 5)) \\ 525639 &:= (9 + ((((-((3 - 6)))!) + 5)^2) + 5)) \\ 525642 &:= ((-2 + 4!) + (((6! + 5)^2) - 5)) \\ 525645 &:= (-5 \times (-4 + (((6! + 5)^2)/(-5))) \\ 525647 &:= ((-7 + 4!) + (((6! + 5)^2) + 5)) \\ 525652 &:= ((2^5) + (((6! + 5)^2) - 5)) \\ 525654 &:= (4! + (((5! \times 6) + 5)^2) + 5)) \\ 525655 &:= ((5 \times 5) + (((6! + 5)^2) + 5)) \\ 525666 &:= ((6 \times 6) + (((6! + 5)^2) + 5)) \\ 525668 &:= ((8 \times 6) + (((6! + 5)^2) + 5)) \\ 525745 &:= (((5 + (((4 + 7) - 5)!)^2) + 5!) \\ 525937 &:= (((7! - 3!!) - 9) \times (5! + 2)) + 5) \\ 526056 &:= ((6^5) + (((06)!)^2) - 5!) \\ 526176 &:= ((6! \times ((7 - 1)!) + (((6/2)!)^5)) \\ 526236 &:= -((6! - (((3 \times 2) + 6!)^2) - 5!)) \\ 526303 &:= (((3!! - 0!) \times (3!! + (6 \times 2))) - 5) \\ 526304 &:= (-4 + ((0! - 3!!) \times (-6 \times (2 + 5)))) \\ 526308 &:= (((-((8 \times 0)!) + 3!!) \times (-6 \times (-2 - 5))) \\ 526313 &:= (((3!! - 1) \times (3!! + (6 \times 2))) + 5) \\ 526315 &:= (((5 + 1)!) \times ((3^6) + 2)) - 5) \\ 526323 &:= 3!! \times (2 + 3^6) - 2 + 5 \\ 526332 &:= (((-2 - 3!!) \times (-3^6)) - (-((2 - 5)))! \\ 526333 &:= (((3 \times 3)^3) \times (6! + 2)) - 5) \\ 526338 &:= (((-8 - 3!!) \times (-3 - 6!)) - (-((2 - 5)))! \\ 526343 &:= (((3!! + 4) \times ((3^6) - 2)) - 5) \\ 526344 &:= (((4 + 4) + 3!!) \times (6! - ((2 - 5)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 526348 &:= (((8 - 4) + 3!) \times (6! + (2 + 5))) \\
 526351 &:= -(1 + 5)! + (3! + 6!)^2 - 5 \\
 526353 &:= (3!! + 5) \times (3! + 6!) - 2 + 5 \\
 526361 &:= ((-1 \times 6!) + (((3! + 6!)^2) + 5)) \\
 526397 &:= -((7! + (9 - (((3^6)^2) + 5)))) \\
 526476 &:= -((6! - (((((7 - 4)!) + 6!)^2) + 5!))) \\
 526582 &:= ((-2 + (8!/5)) + ((6!^2) + 5!)) \\
 526584 &:= (((4! \times 8!)/5!) + ((6!^2) + 5!)) \\
 526585 &:= (((5 + 8!)/5) + ((6!^2) + 5!)) \\
 526674 &:= ((-((4 - 7)) + (6! \times (-6))) \times (-2 - 5!)) \\
 526675 &:= (-((5^7)) + (((6!/6) \times ((2 + 5)!))) \\
 526836 &:= (((6! + 3!)^{8-6} - (2 \times 5!)) \\
 526839 &:= (-9 + (3 \times ((8!/6!)^{-2+5}))) \\
 526848 &:= ((8 \times 4!) \times ((8 + 6)^{-2+5})) \\
 526931 &:= (((-1 - 3!) \times ((-9 - 6!) - 2)) - 5!) \\
 526956 &:= (((((6 \times 5!) + ((9 - 6)!)^2) - 5!) \\
 526988 &:= (-8 + 8!/9 - 6) \times (-2 + 5!) \\
 527035 &:= (-5 + (3!! \times ((0! - 7) \times (-2 - 5!)))) \\
 527064 &:= (4! + ((6! - (07)!) \times (-2 - 5!))) \\
 527071 &:= ((((-((1 - 7)))! - ((0! - 7)))^2) - 5) \\
 527075 &:= ((5 + ((7 - 0!)!) \times (7 + ((-((2 - 5)!))!))) \\
 527161 &:= (-1 - (((6! - 1) - 7!) \times (2 + 5!))) \\
 527162 &:= (((2 - 6!) - 1) + 7!) \times (2 + 5!) \\
 527196 &:= (((6! + ((9 + 1) - 7)!^2) + 5!) \\
 527284 &:= (((((4!/8)!)! - (2 + 7!)) \times (-2 - 5!)) \\
 527406 &:= (((6! + 0!) - 4) - 7!) \times (-2 - 5!) \\
 527732 &:= ((-2 \times (3! + 7!)) + (((7 \times 2)^5)) \\
 527875 &:= (-((5^7)) - (((-8 - 7!) - 2) \times 5!)) \\
 528235 &:= (-5 + ((3!!^2) + (82 \times 5!)) \\
 528264 &:= ((4! + (6!^2)) + (82 \times 5!)) \\
 528273 &:= (((3!! + 7)^2) - (8 \times (2^5))) \\
 528336 &:= (((6! + 3) \times 3!!) + ((8 - 2)^5)) \\
 528534 &:= (((((4 + 3!) - ((5 - 8)))^2) + 5) \\
 528649 &:= (((((-9 + 4!) + 6!) - 8)^2) + 5!) \\
 528675 &:= ((5 - 7!) \times (6! - 825)) \\
 528736 &:= (6! + ((3!! - ((7! + 8))) \times (-2 - 5!))) \\
 528975 &:= (((-5 \times (7! - 9)) - (8! \times 2)) \times (-5)) \\
 529175 &:= (-5 \times ((7! \times (-19 + 2))) + 5)) \\
 529187 &:= (7! - ((8! - 1) \times (-((9 \times 2) - 5)))) \\
 529236 &:= (((6! + 3!)^2) + ((9 \times 2) \times 5!)) \\
 529344 &:= -(((4! \times 4!) \times (3! - 925))) \\
 529364 &:= (((4 + 6!) \times (3!! + (9 + 2))) + 5!) \\
 529373 &:= (((3! - 7!) - 3!!) \times (-92)) + 5) \\
 529375 &:= ((5 \times 7) \times ((3 \times ((9 - 2)!)) + 5)) \\
 529436 &:= ((6! \times 3!!) + (-4 - (-92) \times 5!)) \\
 529632 &:= (((23 \times 6!) - 9) \times (2^5)) \\
 529733 &:= ((3!! \times 3!!) + (-7 - (9!/(-2^5)))) \\
 529925 &:= -((((5!^2) - 9!) + ((9!/(-2)) - 5))) \\
 530239 &:= ((9^3!) - (2 \times ((0! + 3!) - 5!)) \\
 530433 &:= (((3^3)^4) - (((0! + 3!)!)/5)) \\
 530467 &:= (((7 - 6!) \times (-4!) - ((03)!)!) - 5) \\
 530616 &:= (-6 \times (1 - ((6! - 0!) \times (3 + 5!)))) \\
 530635 &:= (((((5! + 3) \times 6) - 0!) \times 3!!) - 5) \\
 530646 &:= (-6 \times (-4 - ((6! - 0!) \times (3 + 5!)))) \\
 530661 &:= (((-16) - 6!) \times (-0! - 3!)) + 5) \\
 530696 &:= -(((6! - (9^6)) + ((0! - 3!) \times (-5)))) \\
 530716 &:= -((6! - (((1 + 7) + 0!)^3!) - 5)) \\
 530726 &:= -((6! - (((2 + 7)^{03!}) + 5))) \\
 530739 &:= ((9^3!) - ((7 - 0!) \times (-3 + 5!)) \\
 530763 &:= -((3!! - (((6! - 7!) - 0!) \times (-3 - 5!))) \\
 530769 &:= ((9^6) - (-7 \times (((0! + 3!)! - 5!)) \\
 530841 &:= -(((((-((1 - 4)))! - (((8 + 0!)^3!) + 5!)) \\
 531237 &:= (((7! - ((3 \times 2)!) - 1) \times (3 + 5!)) \\
 531294 &:= -((4! - (((9^{2+1})! - 3) - 5!)) \\
 531296 &:= (((6! + 9)^2) - 1) + (3!!/(-5)) \\
 531308 &:= (((8 + 0!)^3!) - 13) - 5! \\
 531318 &:= (((81^3) \times 1) - 3) - 5! \\
 531319 &:= (((9^{1 \times 3!}) + ((1 - 3))) - 5!) \\
 531321 &:= (((1 + 2)^{(3+1) \times 3}) - 5!) \\
 531323 &:= (((3^2)^3!) - ((1 - 3))) - 5! \\
 531327 &:= (((7 + 2)^3!) + ((1 \times 3)!) - 5! \\
 531336 &:= ((-((6! - 3!)) \times (-((3 + 1)!) - 3!)) + 5!) \\
 531339 &:= ((9^3!) + ((3 \times (1 - 35)))) \\
 531345 &:= (((5 + 4)^3!) + ((1 + 3)!) - 5!) \\
 531393 &:= -((3! - (9^3!)) - (((1 + 3)!)! / 5!)) \\
 531398 &:= (-8 + ((9^3!) - (1 \times 35))) \\
 531399 &:= (((9 \times 9)^3) - (((1 + 3)!)! / 5!)) \\
 531409 &:= ((9^{(-0!+4)!}) - (-((1 - 3)^5)) \\
 531416 &:= ((6! + 14) \times ((-1 + 3!) + 5)) \\
 531428 &:= -8 + (2 \times 4 + 1)^{3!} - 5 \\
 531429 &:= (((9^{2+4}) - 1) - 3!) - 5)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 531434 &:= (((4! + 3)^4) + (((1 - 3) - 5))) \\
 531437 &:= ((7 + 3!) \times (((4 - 1)!)! + ((3! + 5))) \\
 531446 &:= (((((6 - 4) \times 4) + 1)^{3!}) + 5) \\
 531449 &:= ((9^{4!/4}) + ((1 \times 3) + 5)) \\
 531472 &:= (((27^4) + 1) + (3! \times 5)) \\
 531483 &:= ((3^{8+4}) + (((1 + 3!)! / 5!)) \\
 531561 &:= (((16 \times 5) + 1)^3) + 5! \\
 531569 &:= (((9^6) + 5!) + ((1 \times 3) + 5)) \\
 531639 &:= (((9^{3!}) + ((6 \times 13))) + 5!) \\
 531681 &:= (((1 + 8)^6) + (-((1 - 3) \times 5!)) \\
 531936 &:= ((6! \times (3!! + (9 - 1))) + ((3!^5))) \\
 532039 &:= (((9^{3!}) - 02) + 3!!) - 5! \\
 532159 &:= (((9^{5+1}) - 2) + (3! \times 5!)) \\
 532166 &:= (6! + (((6 + 1) + 2)^{3!}) + 5) \\
 532168 &:= (8 + 6!) \times ((1 + 2)! + 3!! + 5) \\
 532169 &:= (((9^6) + (((1 + 2)!)!)) + (3 + 5)) \\
 532196 &:= (6! + ((9^{1+2})! + 35)) \\
 532224 &:= (((4 \times 2)!) \times (22 \times 3)) / 5 \\
 532257 &:= (((7 + 5!)^2) \times (-2 - 35)) \\
 532396 &:= (6! + ((9^{3!}) + (235))) \\
 532405 &:= ((50 \times ((4! - 2)^3)) + 5) \\
 532469 &:= (((9^6) + 4) + ((-2 + 3!)^5)) \\
 532573 &:= ((37 \times ((5!^2) - 3!)) - 5) \\
 532736 &:= ((6! \times 3!!) - (-7 \times (2^{3!+5}))) \\
 532777 &:= ((-7 - 7!) + (((7! \times 2) / 3!)^5)) \\
 532805 &:= (-5 \times (-((0! + (8! / 2))) - (3!! \times 5!)) \\
 532864 &:= ((-4 - 6!) \times (-((8 \times 2) - (3! \times 5!)) \\
 532906 &:= (((6! + 0!) + 9)^2) + (3!! / 5!) \\
 533239 &:= (((9^{3!}) - 2) - (-3 \times (3!! - 5!)) \\
 533328 &:= ((-((8 \times 2) + (3!! \times (-3!))) \times (-3 - 5!)) \\
 533334 &:= (((-4!) - 3!!) \times (3 - 3!)) + (3! - 5!) \\
 533363 &:= (((3! - 6!) \times (-((3^3) - 3!)) + 5) \\
 533376 &:= (((6! + (7 + 3)) \times 3!!) + ((3!^5))) \\
 533433 &:= (((3 - 3!!) \times (-4!) - 3!!) - (3 \times 5)) \\
 533439 &:= (-9 + ((3!! + 4!) \times (-3 + (3! \times 5!))) \\
 533453 &:= (((3! \times 5!) + 4!) \times (3!! - 3)) + 5) \\
 533463 &:= (((3 - 6!) \times (-4!) - 3!!) + (3 \times 5)) \\
 533468 &:= (8! + 6! - 4) \times (3 \times 3! - 5) \\
 533469 &:= ((9^6) + (((4 - 3!!) \times (-3)) - 5!)) \\
 533585 &:= ((5 + 8) \times ((5 + 3!!) + ((3 + 5)!)!)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 533596 &:= (((6! + ((9^5) \times 3)) \times 3) - 5) \\
 533618 &:= (((8 - 1) + 6!) \times ((3^{3!}) + 5)) \\
 533623 &:= (((3! \times 2) + 6!) \times (3^{3!}) - 5) \\
 533633 &:= (((3^{3!}) \times ((6! + 3!) + 3!)) + 5) \\
 533634 &:= (((4! - 3) + 6!) \times 3!!) - (3! - 5!) \\
 533637 &:= (((7 \times 3) + 6!) \times 3!!) - (3 - 5!) \\
 533664 &:= (-4 \times (-((6^6)) - ((-3 - 3!!) \times (-5!)))) \\
 533665 &:= ((5^6) + (((6! \times 3!) - 3) \times 5!)) \\
 533763 &:= ((3!! \times 6!) - ((7! \times (-3)) - ((3^5)))) \\
 533985 &:= (((5! \times 8!) / 9) + ((-3 - 3!!) \times 5)) \\
 534037 &:= ((-7 + 3!!) \times (((04)! + 3!!) + 5)) \\
 534072 &:= (((-2 + ((7 - 0!)!) \times (4! + 3!)) - 5!) \\
 534235 &:= (((53 \times 2) \times ((4 + 3)!) - 5) \\
 534249 &:= ((9^{4+2}) - (4! \times (3 - 5!))) \\
 534261 &:= ((1 + 6!) \times ((2 + 4!) + 3!!) - 5) \\
 534264 &:= (4! + (((6! - 2) + 4!) \times 3!) \times 5!) \\
 534265 &:= (((5 + 6!)^2) + ((4! \times 3) \times 5!)) \\
 534306 &:= (-6 \times (0! + ((3!! + 4) \times (-3 - 5!)))) \\
 534312 &:= ((((((2 + 1)!)!) \times (-3!)) - 4!) \times (-3 - 5!)) \\
 534325 &:= (((-((5 + 2)) + 3!!) + 4!) \times (3!! + 5)) \\
 534336 &:= (-((6! + 3!)) \times ((3 - 4!) - 3!)) + 5) \\
 534356 &:= (((6! + 5) + 3!)^{-4+3!}) - 5) \\
 534361 &:= (((-1 + 6!) + (3 \times 4))^{-3+5}) \\
 534368 &:= ((-((8^6)) - ((3 + 4)!) \times (3 - 5)) \\
 534393 &:= ((3^{9+3}) + (4! \times (3 + 5!))) \\
 534469 &:= (((9^6) + 4) + (4! \times (3! + 5!))) \\
 534681 &:= (((1 + 8)^6) + ((4! + 3) \times 5!)) \\
 534816 &:= ((-((6! - 1)) \times (-((8 - 4)!) - 3!)) - 5!) \\
 534876 &:= ((6 + 7!) \times ((-84) / 3!) + 5!) \\
 534916 &:= (((6! + 19)) \times (4 + 3!)) - 5! \\
 534931 &:= (((-1 + (-((3 - 9)!)!) \times (4! + 3!)) - 5) \\
 535357 &:= ((7 - (5 \times 3!)) \times (-5 + (3! / (-5)))) \\
 535437 &:= (7! - 3!!) \times (4 + 5!) - 3^5 \\
 535488 &:= (8 \times ((8! - (4! \times (5^{3!}))) / (-5))) \\
 535535 &:= ((5 - 3!!) \times (((5! / (-5)) - 3!!) - 5)) \\
 535536 &:= ((6! \times (3!! + (5! / 5))) + (3!! / (-5))) \\
 535645 &:= (((((5! + 4) \times 6!) - 5) \times 3!) - 5) \\
 535655 &:= ((-5 + (5 \times 6!)) \times (5 - (3!! / (-5)))) \\
 535664 &:= (((((4! + 6!) \times 6!) - 5) - 3!) - 5) \\
 535665 &:= ((((-5 - 6!) \times 6) - 5) \times (-3 - 5!)) \\
 535669 &:= (9! + (((6! + 6!) \times 5!) - 3!) - 5)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 535675 &:= ((-(5! + ((7! - 6!)/(-5)))) \times 3!) - 5) \\ 535704 &:= (4! \times ((0! + 7!) + ((5! \times 3!)/5)) \\ 535808 &:= ((-80) \times (-((8^5) - 3!))/5) \\ 535824 &:= (((4!/2) + (((8 - 5)!))^{-3+5}) \\ 535888 &:= ((8 + 8) \times (((8^5) + 3!) + 5)) \\ 535995 &:= ((5! + 9) \times (((-9 + 5!) + 3!) \times 5)) \\ 536064 &:= (((4! + 6!) \times (0! + 6!)) + (-3 \times 5!)) \\ 536139 &:= (9! + (((3! + 1) - 6!) \times (-3^5))) \\ 536256 &:= (((6! + ((5^2))) \times 6!) + (3!/(-5))) \\ 536337 &:= ((7! + (((3 \times 3)^6))) + (3!/(-5))) \\ 536346 &:= (((6! + 4!) + 3) \times (6! + ((3 - 5))) \\ 536361 &:= (((1 + 6)! + (((3 + 6)^3) - 5!)) \\ 536364 &:= (((4! + 6!) \times 3!) + (-6 \times (3! - 5!))) \\ 536367 &:= (((7! + (((6 + 3)^6))) + 3!) - 5!) \\ 536395 &:= (((((-5 - 9)! + 3!) \times 6!) + 3!) - 5) \\ 536397 &:= ((7! + (9^3)) - ((-6 \times 3!) + 5!)) \\ 536413 &:= (((3! + 1) \times (4! + 6!)) - ((3! + 5))) \\ 536416 &:= (((6! + 1) \times (4! + 6!)) - (3 + 5)) \\ 536424 &:= ((4! + ((2 + 4)!)) \times ((6! + 3!) - 5)) \\ 536436 &:= ((6! \times (3! + 4!)) + (6 \times (3! + 5!))) \\ 536539 &:= (((9! \times 3!)/5!) + ((6! \times 3!) - 5)) \\ 536544 &:= ((4! + 45) \times (((6 - 3)!^5)) \\ 536549 &:= ((9!/(4 \times 5)) + ((6! \times 3!) + 5)) \\ 536575 &:= (((5! \times (-7)) - 5) \times (-635)) \\ 536595 &:= (((5! + 9) + 5!) \times ((6! \times 3) - 5)) \\ 536643 &:= (3! + (((4! + 6!) \times 6!) + ((3^5))) \\ 536769 &:= (((9^6) + 7!) + ((-6!) - 3!)/(-5)) \\ 536785 &:= ((5^8) - (7! \times (6 - 35))) \\ 536873 &:= -((3! - (-7 + ((8!/(6 + 3)) \times 5!))) \\ 537096 &:= (69 \times ((0! + 7) + (3!^5))) \\ 537103 &:= -((3! + ((0! - ((17 - 3)^5)))) \\ 537104 &:= -((((4 - 0)!))! - (((17 - 3)^5))) \\ 537213 &:= (((3! - 1) \times (27 + 3!)) + 5!) \\ 537572 &:= (((2 \times 7)^5) - ((7! \times 3!)/5!)) \\ 537579 &:= (9! + (-7 \times ((-5 \times 7!) + ((3^5)))) \\ 537585 &:= (((((5! + 8) \times 5!) \times (-7)) + 3) \times (-5)) \\ 537598 &:= (((8!/9) \times 5!) - ((7 + 3)/5)) \\ 537624 &:= (4! - (((-((2^6) \times 7!)/(-3)) \times (-5))) \\ 537625 &:= (-5 \times (((-((2^6) \times 7!)/3) - 5)) \\ 537675 &:= ((5! - (7 + 6)) \times (7! - (3 \times 5))) \\ 537695 &:= -((5! + (9 - (((6 \times 7)/3)^5))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 537696 &:= (((6! + 9) \times 6!) + 7!) + (3!^5) \\ 537704 &:= -((((4 + 0)!))! - (-((7 - (7 \times 3))^5))) \\ 537705 &:= -(((5! - 0!) - (-((7 - (7 \times 3))^5))) \\ 537725 &:= ((-5 \times ((2 \times 7!) - (7^3))) - 5!) \\ 537768 &:= -(((8!/6!) - (-((7 - (7 \times 3))^5))) \\ 537821 &:= -((1 + 2) + (((8!/7!) + 3!^5)) \\ 537823 &:= -((3 - 2) + (((8!/7!) + 3!^5)) \\ 537828 &:= ((8/2) + (((8!/7!) + 3!^5)) \\ 537835 &:= ((5 + 3!) + (((8!/7!) + 3!^5)) \\ 537844 &:= ((4! - 4) + (((8!/7!) + 3!^5)) \\ 537848 &:= (((8 - 4)! + (((8!/7!) + 3!^5)) \\ 537888 &:= ((8 \times 8) + (((8!/7!) + 3!^5)) \\ 537896 &:= -((((6! - 9!) - ((8 \times 7)^3) - 5!)) \\ 537939 &:= ((9^3) + (9 \times ((7 + 3!) - 5))) \\ 537966 &:= ((-6 - 6!) \times ((-((9 + 7)) - 3!) - 5)) \\ 538049 &:= ((9 \times (4! + 0!)) + ((8 + 3!^5)) \\ 538064 &:= ((4 \times 60) + ((8 + 3!^5)) \\ 538304 &:= ((4 \times (-((0! - 3!))!)) + (((8 + 3!^5))) \\ 538424 &:= (((4!^2) + 4!) + ((8 + 3!^5)) \\ 538445 &:= (((5^4) - 4) + ((8 + 3!^5)) \\ 538449 &:= (((9 - 4)^4) + ((8 + 3!^5)) \\ 538467 &:= (((7 + 6!) + 4!) \times ((-8 + 3!) + 5)) \\ 538472 &:= ((27 \times 4!) + ((8 + 3!^5)) \\ 538533 &:= (3! - (((3! + 5) - ((8 + 3!^5)))) \\ 538536 &:= ((6! - (3 + 5)) + ((8 + 3!^5)) \\ 538537 &:= ((-7 + (3! \times 5!)) + ((8 + 3!^5)) \\ 538539 &:= (((9 - 3)! - 5) + ((8 + 3!^5)) \\ 538541 &:= (((14^5) - 8) + 3!) + 5) \\ 538543 &:= (3! + ((4 - 5) + ((8 + 3!^5))) \\ 538544 &:= (((4/4) + 5)! + ((8 + 3!^5)) \\ 538569 &:= (9! + ((6! - ((5 - 8)) \times (3^5))) \\ 538584 &:= (4! + (8 \times (((5 \times 8!)/3) + 5!))) \\ 538589 &:= ((9 \times 85) + ((8 + 3!^5)) \\ 538637 &:= ((7 + (3! \times 68)) \times (3! + 5)) \\ 538657 &:= (((-7 + 5!) + 6!) + ((8 + 3!^5)) \\ 538672 &:= (((2^7) + 6!) + ((8 + 3!^5)) \\ 538688 &:= (-886) \times ((-8 - 3!) + 5!) \\ 538764 &:= (((-((4^6) + 7!)/(-8)) \times (3! - 5!)) \\ 538904 &:= (((4 + 0)! \times 9) + (((8 + 3!^5))) \\ 539136 &:= (((6!^{3-1}) + (9! \times 3!))/5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 539264 &:= (-((4^{6+2})) + ((9!/(-3)) \times (-5))) \\
 539275 &:= (-5 + (7! \times (((2-9) - 3!) + 5!))) \\
 539279 &:= ((9! - 7!) + ((-2 + 9!)/(-3 - 5))) \\
 539285 &:= ((((-((5-8)))! \times (29 + 3!)) + 5) \\
 539356 &:= ((6! \times (5 + 3!)) + ((9^3) - 5)) \\
 539397 &:= -((7! + (((9!/3!) \times (-9)) + 3) - 5!)) \\
 539748 &:= (-(((8^4) - 7)) \times (-((9 + 3)) - 5!)) \\
 540288 &:= 8! \times (8^2 - 0! + 4)/5 \\
 541439 &:= (((9! \times 3!)/4) - 1) - (4! \times 5!) \\
 542337 &:= (7 + 3!) \times (3! + 2 + 4!) - 5 \\
 542376 &:= (-6 \times (((7 + 3!) + 2) \times (-4 - 5!))) \\
 542416 &:= (6! + (((-1 + 4!)^2) \times (4^5))) \\
 542496 &:= (((6! + 9) \times (4! + ((2 + 4)!)) + 5!) \\
 542689 &:= (((9 + 8) + 6!)^2) + (-4 \times 5!) \\
 542875 &:= (((((5! - 7!) - 8!)/(-2)) \times 4!) - 5) \\
 542936 &:= (((6! - (3 \times 9!))/(-2)) - (4^5)) \\
 542937 &:= (((7! - (3! \times (9! - 2)))/(-4)) - 5!) \\
 543025 &:= ((5 + (((2 + 0!)!))! \times (3! + (4! + 5))) \\
 543239 &:= (((9! - 3!)/2) \times 3) + ((4 - 5)) \\
 543269 &:= (((((9! - 6!)/(-2)) \times (-3)) + 4!) + 5) \\
 543293 &:= (((3 \times 9!)/2) - (3 + (4^5))) \\
 543296 &:= (((-6 \times 9!)/2 - 3!) - (4^5)) \\
 543299 &:= (9! - ((9!/(-2)) - (3 - (4^5)))) \\
 543368 &:= ((8 + (6 \times (3^3))) \times (4 + 5!)) \\
 543369 &:= (((((9! - 6!) + 3!) \times 3!)/4) + 5!) \\
 543384 &:= (4! - (((8^3) - ((3 + 4)!)) \times 5!)) \\
 543456 &:= ((6! \times ((-((5^4)) \times 3!) - 4!)/(-5)) \\
 543575 &:= (-5 \times (-((7! - 5)) + (3! \times (-4! + 5!)))) \\
 543576 &:= (((-6 - 7!) - (5! \times (-3))) \times (4 - 5!)) \\
 543606 &:= (6 \times (0! + (((6 + 3)!)/4) - 5!)) \\
 543636 &:= (6 \times (3! + (((6 + 3)!)/4) - 5!)) \\
 543667 &:= (((7! - 6) \times (-6)) \times (3! - 4!)) - 5) \\
 543671 &:= (-1 + ((7! - 6) \times (-((3 \times 4) + 5!))) \\
 543672 &:= (2 \times (((7! - 6) \times 3!) \times (4 + 5))) \\
 543744 &:= (-4 \times (4! + ((7! \times (-3 - 4!)) + 5!)) \\
 543864 &:= (-((4! + 6!)) \times ((8 - 3!) - (4! - 5))) \\
 543915 &:= (((5 + 1)! - 9) \times (3! + 45)) \\
 543944 &:= (-((4^4)) + (((9! \times 3!)/4) - 5!)) \\
 543948 &:= ((8! - ((-((4! - 9!)) \times 3!)/4))/(-5!)) \\
 543955 &:= (((((5! + 5!) - 9!) \times 3!)/(-4)) - 5) \\
 543982 &:= (-2 - ((-8!) + ((-9! \times 3!)/(-4)))/(-5!))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 543984 &:= (((4 \times 8!) + (-9! \times 3!))/(-4 \times 5!)) \\
 543985 &:= (((5! - 8!) + ((-9! \times 3!)/(-4)))/5! \\
 543996 &:= (6! + (9 \times ((9!/3!) + 4) - 5!)) \\
 544099 &:= ((9 \times ((9!/(-((0! - 4)))!)) - (4!)) - 5) \\
 544194 &:= (((4 - 9!) \times (-((1 - 4)!))/(-4)) - 5!) \\
 544195 &:= (-5!) - (((-9! \times (-((1 - 4)!))/4) + 5)) \\
 544196 &:= ((((-6 \times 9!)/(-1 \times 4)) - 4) - 5!) \\
 544198 &:= (((8 + (-9! \times (-((1 - 4)!)))/(-4)) - 5!) \\
 544199 &:= -((9! - (((9 + 1)! - 4)/4) - 5!)) \\
 544236 &:= ((-6 \times (((3^2)! + 4!)/(-4)) - 5!) \\
 544275 &:= ((5 - ((7!/2) \times 4!)) \times (-4 + 5)) \\
 544279 &:= ((9 \times ((7!/2) \times 4!) - 4) - 5) \\
 544291 &:= (((-1 + (9!/2^4))) \times 4!) - 5) \\
 544293 &:= (((3! - 9!)/(-2)) - 4!) + ((4 + 5)!)) \\
 544294 &:= (((4 - 9!)/(-2)) - 4!) + ((4 + 5)!)) \\
 544295 &:= (((5! + 9! \times (-2 + 4)))/(-4) + 5) \\
 544296 &:= ((6! \times (9! - (2^4)))/4 \times 5!) \\
 544299 &:= (9! - ((9!/(-2)) + ((4 \times 4) + 5))) \\
 544309 &:= (((9! \times (03!)) - 4!)/4) - 5) \\
 544319 &:= (((9! \times (-1)) \times 3!)/(-4) + ((4 - 5))) \\
 544325 &:= (((5 + 2)! \times ((3 + 4!) \times 4)) + 5) \\
 544329 &:= (((9!/2) + 3) \times ((4 + 4) - 5)) \\
 544339 &:= (((9! \times (-3 + 3))/(-4)) + 4!) - 5) \\
 544344 &:= (4! + (((4 + 3)!)/4) - (((4 + 5)!)) \\
 544349 &:= (-9!) + (((4 + 3)!)/4) + (4! + 5)) \\
 544378 &:= (((8! \times 7) - 3!) + ((4^{4+5})) \\
 544387 &:= ((7 \times 8!) + (3 + (4^{4+5}))) \\
 544392 &:= ((2 \times ((9! \times 3)/4) - 4!) + 5!) \\
 544395 &:= (5! - (((9! \times 3!)/(-4)) + 45)) \\
 544439 &:= (((9! \times 3!)/4) - (4/4) + 5!) \\
 544469 &:= (((9! \times (-6)) - (4! \times 4!))/(-4) + 5) \\
 544493 &:= ((3! \times (9!/4) + 4!) + (4! + 5)) \\
 544495 &:= (((5! + 9!) \times 4!)/4 \times 4) - 5) \\
 544596 &:= ((-6 \times (9! + 5!)/(-4)) - (4! - 5!)) \\
 544639 &:= (((9! \times 3!) + (6^4))/4) - 5) \\
 544776 &:= (-6 \times (7! - ((7! + 4) \times (4! - 5)))) \\
 544782 &:= ((-2 - 8!) - ((7! + 4) \times (4 - 5!))) \\
 544896 &:= (-6 \times ((9!/(-8 - 4)) + 4!) - 5!) \\
 544956 &:= ((6 \times (5! + (9! + 4!)/4)) - 5!) \\
 544984 &:= ((4! + (8!/9)) \times ((4/4) + 5!)) \\
 544986 &:= (-6 \times (8 - ((9! - 4)/4) + 5!)) \\
 545297 &:= (((7! + 9) \times (2 \times 54)) + 5)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 545349 &:= (((9!/4) \times 3!) + (5 + (4^5))) \\ 545391 &:= ((-1 + ((9!/3!) + 5!)) \times (4 + 5)) \\ 545395 &:= (-5 - (((9!/3!) + 5!) \times (-4 + 5))) \\ 545399 &:= ((9 \times ((9!/3!) + 5!)) + ((4 - 5))) \\ 545751 &:= (((1 \times 5)!) \times 7!) - ((5 + 4)^5) \\ 545792 &:= ((2^9) \times ((7!/5!) + (4^5))) \\ 546328 &:= ((82^3) - (((6 - 4) + 5)!)) \\ 546665 &:= (-(((5^6) - 6)) \times ((-6 - 4!) - 5)) \\ 546755 &:= -((5! - (((5^7) \times ((6 - 4) + 5)))))) \\ 546757 &:= (((7 \times (5^7)) + (6 - 4)) - 5!) \\ 546808 &:= (-8 \times (0! + ((-8 + 6!) \times (4! - 5!))) \\ 546816 &:= ((6! - 186) \times (4^5)) \\ 546848 &:= (8 \times (4 - ((-8 + 6!) \times (4! - 5!)))) \\ 547236 &:= (((6! + 3!)^2) + ((7 \times 4!) \times 5!)) \\ 547355 &:= (-5 \times (((5^{3!}) \times (-7)) + 4!) - 5!) \\ 547375 &:= (((5 \times 7) + 3!) \times (((7 - 4)!)! + 5)) \\ 547452 &:= ((2 \times 54) \times ((7! + 4!) + 5)) \\ 547455 &:= (-5 + (((5^4) - 7!) \times (-4 - 5!))) \\ 547547 &:= (-7 \times ((4! - (5^7)) + (4! \times (-5)))) \\ 547576 &:= (((6! + (7 \times (5^7))) - 4!) + 5) \\ 547757 &:= (-7 \times ((-((5^7)) - ((7 - 4)!) - 5!)) \\ 547865 &:= ((-5 \times ((6! \times (-8)) - 7)) \times (4! - 5)) \\ 548347 &:= ((((-7 \times (4!^3)) - 8!) \times (-4)) + 5) \\ 548352 &:= (((-((2 + (5 \times 3))) \times 8!) \times 4)/(-5)) \\ 548379 &:= ((-9 + 7!) \times (-((3 + 8)) - (4! \times (-5)))) \\ 548592 &:= (2 \times ((9!/5) - ((8! + 4!) \times (-5)))) \\ 548635 &:= (-5 - (3! \times (6 - (-8 \times (4! - 5!)))))) \\ 548664 &:= (4! - (6! \times (6 - (-8 \times (4! - 5!)))))) \\ 548688 &:= ((8! - ((8! \times (-68)) \times 4!))/5!) \\ 549237 &:= (7! + (((3! \times (2 - 9!))/(-4)) - 5!)) \\ 549337 &:= 7! + 3! \times (-3 + 9!/4) - 5 \\ 550368 &:= (((8 + 6!) \times 3!) \times ((0! + 5) + 5!)) \\ 551875 &:= (-((5^7)) - (((8 - 1)!) \times (-5 - 5!))) \\ 552164 &:= (((((4! + 6!) - 1)^2) - 5) + 5!) \\ 552575 &:= (((-5 - 7!) + (5! \times 2)) \times (5 - 5!)) \\ 552935 &:= ((((-5!) \times 3!) + 9!) \times 2) - (5 \times 5) \\ 553125 &:= (((5!/2) - 1) \times (3 \times (5^5))) \\ 553416 &:= (((6! + ((1 \times 4)!)!^{-3+5}) - 5!) \\ 553546 &:= (((6! + 4!)^{5-3}) + (5 + 5)) \\ 553648 &:= (-8 + (((4! + 6!)^{-3+5}) + 5!)) \\ 554275 &:= (((-5 \times 7!) \times (2 - 4!)) + (-5 - 5!)) \\ 554375 &:= (-5 \times ((7! \times ((-3 - 4!) + 5)) + 5)) \\ 554424 &:= (4! - (((2 \times 4)!)! / (-4)) \times 55) \\ 554675 &:= ((5 + (7! \times (6 - 4))) \times 55) \\ 554938 &:= (-83) \times (-(((9^4) + 5)) - 5!) \\ 556296 &:= (((-69) \times ((2 + 6)!) / (-5)) - 5!) \\ 556485 &:= (((5 + 8!) \times (-4 + 65)) / (-5)) \\ 557136 &:= ((6^{3!+1}) + (7! \times 55)) \\ 557239 &:= (((9^3!) - 2) + ((7! + 5!) \times 5)) \\ 557395 &:= ((-((5! + 9)) \times (3! - 7!)) - (5 - 5!)) \\ 557525 &:= (((5! - (2 \times 5)) \times 7!) + ((5^5))) \\ 557568 &:= (((8!/6) \times 5!) - ((7 + 5)^5)) \\ 557765 &:= (((-((56 \times 7)) + 7!) \times 5!) + 5) \\ 557856 &:= (((6^5) - 8!) + ((7! - 5!) \times 5!)) \\ 557977 &:= ((7 \times 79) \times ((7! + 5)/5)) \\ 558475 &:= ((5! \times (7! - 4!)) - (8! + ((5^5))) \\ 558605 &:= (((5 + 0!)!) \times 6!) + ((8! + 5) - 5!) \\ 558665 &:= (((5! \times 6!) \times 6) + 8!) - (55) \\ 558696 &:= ((6! \times (((9 - 6)!)!) + ((8! - (5!/5)))) \\ 558719 &:= (((((9 + 1)!)! / 7) + 8!) - (5/5)) \\ 558723 &:= ((3!^2) - ((7 - 8!) - (5 + 5))) \\ 558726 &:= (((6!^2) + 7) + 8!) - (5/5) \\ 559213 &:= (((((3! + 1)!)! - 2) \times (-9 + 5!)) - 5) \\ 559215 &:= ((51^2) \times (95 + 5!)) \\ 559315 &:= (-5!) + (((1 + 3!)!) \times (-9 + 5!)) - 5) \\ 559344 &:= (4! + (((4 + 3)!) \times (-9 + 5!)) - 5!) \\ 559431 &:= (((-1 - ((3 + 4)!) \times (9 - 5!)) - 5!) \\ 559435 &:= (((-((5 - (3 \times 4)))!) \times (-9 + 5!)) - 5) \\ 559671 &:= (((-1 - (7 \times 6!)) \times (9 - 5!)) + 5!) \\ 559732 &:= (2 \times ((3!^7) - (((9 + 5) \times 5))) \\ 559764 &:= (((4! / (-6)) - 7!) \times (9 - 5!)) - 5! \\ 559773 &:= ((3 + 7!) \times (((7!/9) - 5)/5)) \\ 559856 &:= ((6! / (-5)) - ((8!/9) \times (-5 - 5!))) \\ 559872 &:= (-((2^7)) - ((8!/9) \times (-5 - 5!))) \\ 559995 &:= (-5 + ((9! / (-9 \times 9)) \times (-5 - 5!))) \\ 560287 &:= (-7 \times (((8! \times (-2)) - 0!) + 6!) - 5!) \\ 560352 &:= (2 \times (5! + ((3!^{0!+6}) + 5!))) \\ 560652 &:= (((-2 - 5!) + ((6 + 0!)!) \times (-6 + 5!)) \\ 560758 &:= (-8 + (((5! - 7!) + 0!) \times (6 - 5!))) \\ 560766 &:= (((6! / (-6)) + 7!) - 0!) \times (-6 + 5!) \\ 560869 &:= ((9! - 6) - (((8! - 0!) - 6!) \times (-5))) \\ 560875 &:= (((5! \times 7!) - 8!) + ((0! + 6!) \times (-5))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 560887 &:= ((7 \times ((8! + 8!) + 0!)) + (6! \times (-5))) \\ 562356 &:= (((6 \times (5^3))^2) - (6!/5)) \\ 562464 &:= (((4! + 6!) \times (-4 + 2))) \times (-6 - 5!) \\ 562732 &:= (2 \times ((3!^7) - (-2 \times (6! - 5)))) \\ 562762 &:= (2 \times ((6^7) - ((-2 \times 6!) - 5))) \\ 563325 &:= (((5!/(-2)) - 3!!) + 3) \times (-(6! + 5)) \\ 563425 &:= (((5^2)^4) - ((3!! + 6!) \times (-5!))) \\ 563625 &:= (-5 + ((-2 + 6!) \times (3!! + (65)))) \\ 563635 &:= (-5!) + ((3!! \times (63 + 6!)) - 5) \\ 563664 &:= (4! + (((6! + (63)) \times 6!) - 5!)) \\ 563755 &:= (-5 + (5! \times (7! - (3 \times (-6 + 5!)))))) \\ 563758 &:= (-8 + 5!) \times 7! + 3 - 6! - 5 \\ 563765 &:= (((-((56 + 7)) - 3!!) \times (-6!)) + 5) \\ 563784 &:= (((4! + 8!) + 7!) + ((3! \times 6!) \times 5!)) \\ 563799 &:= (9 \times (-9 + 7!)) + ((3!! \times 6!) + 5!) \\ 563838 &:= (((8 + 3!) \times (8! - 3)) - (6! - 5!)) \\ 563875 &:= (5! + ((783 \times 6!) - 5)) \\ 563877 &:= (((((7 + 7) \times 8!) - 3) - 6!) + 5!) \\ 563877 &:= (((5! - 6!) - 3) + (8! \times (7 + 7))) \\ 563885 &:= 5! + 8! \times (8 + 3!) - 6! + 5 \\ 563895 &:= (((5! + 9!)/8) + ((3!! \times 6!) + 5!)) \\ 563978 &:= 8! - 7 + 9^{3!} - 6^5 \\ 564336 &:= ((6^{3!}) - (3!! \times ((-4 - 6!) + 5))) \\ 564384 &:= ((4! - 8!) + (((3! + 4)!/6) - 5!)) \\ 564438 &:= ((8! - 3) \times (4 - ((4 - 6) \times 5))) \\ 564474 &:= (((-4 \times 7!) \times (-4 - 4!)) - (6!/5!)) \\ 564475 &:= (((5! \times (-7)) \times ((4! + 4!) - 6!)) - 5) \\ 564578 &:= ((8! + 7) \times ((54/6) + 5)) \\ 564598 &:= (((8! \times (9 + 5)) + ((4 - 6))) + 5!) \\ 564663 &:= ((3 + 6!) \times (6! - ((4 - 65)))) \\ 564672 &:= (((5! - 6!) \times 4) - (6^7)) \times (-2) \\ 564678 &:= (((-((8 - (7^6))) \times 4!) + 6)/5) \\ 564696 &:= (-(69) \times ((6! + 4!) \times (-(6 + 5)))) \\ 564728 &:= ((8! + ((2^7) \times (4^6))) + 5!) \\ 564775 &:= ((5 + 774) \times (6! + 5)) \\ 564827 &:= (((7 \times 2) \times (8! + 4!)) + (6 + 5)) \\ 564859 &:= (((9 + 5) \times (8! - 4!)) + (6! - 5)) \\ 564886 &:= ((6 + 8) \times (8! + ((4 \times 6) + 5))) \\ 564895 &:= (((5 + 9) \times ((8! + 4!) + 6)) - 5) \\ 564982 &:= (-2 + (((8!/(-9)) - 4) \times (-6 - 5!))) \\ 565056 &:= (6 \times (((5 + 0!)^5) + (6! \times 5!))) \\ 565248 &:= ((8^4) \times (-(2 - 5) \times 6)) + 5!)) \\ 565488 &:= ((8 - (8!/(-4 + 5))) \times (6 + 5!)) \\ 565776 &:= ((6! \times 775) + (6^5)) \\ 565777 &:= (((7! - 77) \times (5! - 6)) - 5) \\ 565867 &:= (((7! + 6) \times (-8 + 5!)) + (6! - 5)) \\ 565872 &:= (2 \times ((7 \times (8! + 5!)) - (6!/5))) \\ 566225 &:= (((5! + 2)/2 + 6!) \times (6! + 5)) \\ 566275 &:= (-5 + ((72 + 6!) \times (6! - 5))) \\ 566885 &:= (((5! + 8!) \times (8 + 6)) + 6!) + 5) \\ 566929 &:= ((9! + (-(2 - 9)^6)) + (6! \times 5!)) \\ 567072 &:= (2 \times (((7 - 0!)^7) - (6! \times (-5)))) \\ 567108 &:= (801 \times ((-7 + 6!) + 5)) \\ 567264 &:= (((4^{6/2}) - 7!) \times (6 - 5!)) \\ 567369 &:= (-9 - ((63 - 7!) \times (-6 + 5!))) \\ 567378 &:= (((8! + 7!)/3!! - 7!) \times (6 - 5!)) \\ 567384 &:= ((4! + 8!) + (3!! \times ((7 + 6!) + 5))) \\ 567396 &:= ((6! \times (-9)) + ((3! - 7!) \times (6 - 5!))) \\ 567624 &:= -((4! - ((2 \times (6^7)) + (6^5)))) \\ 567639 &:= (-9 + ((3! + 67) \times (6^5))) \\ 567645 &:= (-((5 \times ((4^6) - (7^6)))) - 5!) \\ 567653 &:= (((3!^5) \times (67 + 6)) + 5) \\ 568069 &:= ((9! - 6) + (((0! - 8!) - 6!) \times (-5))) \\ 568079 &:= ((5 \times (6! + 8!)) - (((0 \times 7)! - 9!)) \\ 568079 &:= ((9! - ((7 \times 0)!)) - ((8! + 6!) \times (-5))) \\ 568195 &:= ((5! + 9!) + (((-1 + 8!) + 6!) \times 5)) \\ 568236 &:= (((((6! + 3!)^2) + 8!) + 6!) + 5!) \\ 568544 &:= (((4^4) \times 5!) + (((8 + 6)^5)) \\ 568793 &:= (3!! + ((9! - 7) - ((8! + 6!) \times (-5)))) \\ 569275 &:= (-5 + ((7! - 296) \times 5!)) \\ 569407 &:= ((7! - 0!) \times (-(4 + 9) - 6)) + 5!)) \\ 569736 &:= (((((6 + 3!)!)/(-7) + (9!/6))/(-5!)) \\ 570085 &:= (((5! - 8) + 0!) \times ((07!) + 5)) \\ 570235 &:= (-5 - (((3! \times 2)!)/(0 - 7) \times 5!)) \\ 570264 &:= (4! - (((6 \times 2)!/(0 - 7))/5!)) \\ 570288 &:= ((8! + (-(8 - 20)))!)/(7 \times 5!)) \\ 570343 &:= (((3!! + 4!)^{3-0!}) + (7^5)) \\ 570537 &:= (((7! + (3 + 5)) + 0!) \times (-7 + 5!)) \\ 570604 &:= ((-4 + (-(0! - 6)))! \times (-(0! - 7!) + 5!)) \\ 570763 &:= (((3! + 6) + 7!) - 0!) \times (-7 + 5!)) \\ 571328 &:= ((-(8 \times 2)) - ((3! + 1)!)) \times (7 - 5!)) \\ 571438 &:= (((8 + 3) + 4!) - 1) \times (7^5) \\ 571472 &:= (2 \times ((-7 + 4!) \times (1 + (7^5)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 571536 &:= ((6! + (35 + 1))^{7-5}) \\ 571584 &:= (4! \times ((8! - ((5 - 1)^7)) - 5!)) \\ 572032 &:= (-((2^{30/2})) + (7! \times 5!)) \\ 572384 &:= ((48 \times 3!) + ((2 \times 7)^5)) \\ 572544 &:= (-4 \times (((4! + 5!) - 2) \times 7!)/(-5)) \\ 572755 &:= (-5 - ((5! + 7!) \times ((2 + 7) - 5!)) \\ 572856 &:= (((6 - 5!) \times ((8 \times 2) - 7!)) + 5!) \\ 573049 &:= (((9 \times 4) + 0!) + 3!)^{7-5} \\ 573306 &:= (((6 - 0!)! - (3!)) \times (-((3! - 7!) + 5))) \\ 573315 &:= (5! + ((1 + 3!) \times (3! + (75)))) \\ 573435 &:= (((5!/3!) \times ((4^3!) \times 7)) - 5) \\ 573464 &:= (-4 \times (-6 + ((4^3!) \times (-7 \times 5)))) \\ 573475 &:= ((5! - 7) \times (((4 + 3)!) + (7 \times 5))) \\ 573542 &:= ((2 \times (-4 - (5^3!))) + (7! \times 5!)) \\ 573552 &:= (((2 + 5)!) \times (5! - 3!)) + (7!/(-5)) \\ 573557 &:= ((7!/(-5)) + (((5! - 3!) \times 7!) + 5)) \\ 573562 &:= ((2 \times (6 - (5^3!))) + (7! \times 5!)) \\ 573565 &:= (((5^6) - 5!) \times 37) - 5! \\ 573696 &:= ((-((6! - (9!/6))) \times 3!)/75) \\ 573719 &:= ((9! - 1) - (-7 \times ((3! \times 7!) - 5!)) \\ 573765 &:= (((5! - 6) \times 7!) - 3!) - (75) \\ 574079 &:= (((9! \times 7) - 0!) + (-((4^7) \times 5!)) \\ 574275 &:= (57 \times ((-((2 - 4)) \times 7!) - 5)) \\ 574344 &:= (4! \times (((4!/3)!) - ((4^7) + 5))) \\ 574379 &:= (((-9 - 7!) - 34) \times (7 - 5!)) \\ 574435 &:= (-5 - ((-((3 - (4^4))) - 7!) \times 5!)) \\ 574492 &:= (((-((2 - 9)))! + 44) \times (-7 + 5!)) \\ 574555 &:= (((5! - ((5 + 5) - 4)) \times 7!) - 5) \\ 574565 &:= (5! - 6) \times (5 - 4) \times 7! + 5 \\ 574704 &:= (((4 - 0!)! \times (-7! - 4!)) + (7! \times 5!)) \\ 574944 &:= ((4! \times ((4! \times (-9)) + 4)) \times (7 - 5!)) \\ 575125 &:= (5! - (2 + 1)!) \times (5 + 7!) - 5 \\ 575154 &:= (4! + ((5! - (1 + 5)) \times (7! + 5))) \\ 575273 &:= -((3! - (-7 - ((2 \times 5!) - 7!) \times 5!)) \\ 575424 &:= (4! + ((-245) + 7!) \times 5!) \\ 575544 &:= (4! + (((-4 - 5!) - 5!) + 7!) \times 5!) \\ 575567 &:= ((7! \times (-6 + 5!)) - ((-5 + 7!)/(-5))) \\ 575625 &:= (((5! \times (-2^6)) + 5) \times (-75)) \\ 575635 &:= (-5 - (((-((3 - 6)^5) - 7!) \times 5!)) \\ 575753 &:= ((((-((3^5)) + 7!) \times 5!) - 7) + 5!) \\ 575825 &:= (((5!^2) \times (-8)) + (5 \times 7)) \times (-5) \\ 576024 &:= (4! + (-20) \times ((6! + 7!) \times (-5))) \\ 576025 &:= (-5 \times ((-20) \times (6! + 7!)) - 5) \\ 576137 &:= -7^{3!+1} + 6^7 \times 5 \\ 576335 &:= (((5!^3)/3) + ((67 \times 5))) \\ 576385 &:= ((5^8) - (-36) \times (7! + 5!)) \\ 576576 &:= (((((6 + 7)!) \times (-5))/6!)/(-75)) \\ 577582 &:= ((-2 + (8!/5)) + (7! \times (-7 + 5!)) \\ 577584 &:= (((4 \times 8!)/(-5)) + 7!) + (7! \times 5!) \\ 577585 &:= (((5 + 8!)/5) + (7! \times (-7 + 5!)) \\ 577856 &:= (6! + ((5! - 8) \times ((7! - 7) + 5!)) \\ 578138 &:= ((8! - 3!) + (-(((1 - 8) - 7)^5)) \\ 578144 &:= (((4 + 4)!) + (-(((1 - 8) - 7)^5)) \\ 578148 &:= (8! + ((4 \times (1 + (8 \times (7^5)))))) \\ 578304 &:= (((4!^03) - 8!) + (7! \times 5!)) \\ 578545 &:= ((5^4) + ((5! - 8) \times (7! + 5!)) \\ 578555 &:= (-5 - (((5 - 5!) \times (-8 + 7!)) + 5!)) \\ 578591 &:= (-1 + ((9 + 5) \times (8! - (7!/(-5)))) \\ 578735 &:= -(((5^3!) - ((7! - (87)) \times 5!)) \\ 578755 &:= (((5! - 5) \times (7! - 8)) + (75)) \\ 578786 &:= (((6!/(-8)) - 7!) + 8) \times (7 - 5!) \\ 578816 &:= (((6 - 1)!) - 8) \times ((8 + 7!) + 5!) \\ 579408 &:= (((8 \times ((0! + 4)!) - 9!)) + 7!)/(-5) \\ 579426 &:= -(((6! - 2) \times ((4! + 9) - (7 \times 5!))) \\ 579537 &:= ((-7 \times ((3! \times 5) + 9)) + (7! \times 5!)) \\ 579575 &:= (5 \times ((7! \times (5! - 97)) - 5)) \\ 579584 &:= -((4! + (((8 \times (5 + 9!)) - 7!)/(-5))) \\ 579586 &:= (-6 - (((8 \times (5 - 9!)) + 7!)/5)) \\ 579595 &:= (((5 \times ((9 + 5) + 9)) \times 7!) - 5) \\ 579599 &:= (((((9! \times 9) - 5) - 9!) - 7!)/5) \\ 579605 &:= (((5! + 0!) - (-((6 - 9)))! \times 7!) + 5) \\ 579608 &:= (8 \times (-0! + 6 + 9!) - 7!)/5 \\ 579609 &:= (((9 + 0!)!)/6) - (-9 + (7! \times 5)) \\ 579624 &:= (4! + (((-((2 + 6)) \times 9!) + 7!)/(-5))) \\ 579648 &:= (((8 \times ((4! + 6) + 9!)) - 7!)/5) \\ 579675 &:= ((5! \times 7!) - (((6 + 9) - 7!) \times (-5))) \\ 579715 &:= ((-5 \times (-1 - 7!)) \times (-97) + 5!) \\ 579744 &:= ((4! \times 4) \times ((7! - 9) - (7!/(-5)))) \\ 579846 &:= -((6! - (((4! \times 8) \times 9!) - 7!)/5!)) \\ 579864 &:= -(((4! + 6!) + (((8! \times 9!)/7!)/(-5))) \\ 580408 &:= (8 \times (-((0! + 4!)) - (((0! + 8)!)!)/(-5))) \\ 580448 &:= (8 \times ((4 - 4!) - (((0! + 8)!)!)/(-5))) \\ 580464 &:= (4! \times (-6 - (((-4 + 0!) \times 8!)/5))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 580528 &:= (8 \times ((-((2 \times 5)) - (((0! + 8))! / (-5)))) \\ 580568 &:= (((8! \times 6!) / 50) - (8 \times 5)) \\ 580584 &:= (-4!) + ((8 \times (((5 \times 0))! + 8))! / 5) \\ 580595 &:= (((5 - 9!) / 5) \times (0 - 8)) - 5 \\ 580597 &:= (7 + (((9! - 5) - 0!) \times (-8))) / (-5) \\ 580599 &:= (9 \times (((9! - 5) - (08!)) / 5)) \\ 580608 &:= (((8 + 0!)! / ((6 + 0!)!)) \times (8! / 5)) \\ 580659 &:= (((((9! / 5) + 6) + 0!) \times 8) - 5) \\ 580697 &:= (-7 - (((9! + (60)) \times 8) / (-5))) \\ 580755 &:= (((5! - 5) \times ((7! + 0!) + 8)) + 5!) \\ 580896 &:= (-6!) + (((9! \times 8) + (-((0! - 8)))! / 5) \\ 581287 &:= (((-7 \times 8!) \times (-2)) + (-((1 - 8))!^5)) \\ 581568 &:= (8 \times (((6! - 5!) + ((1 + 8))! / 5)) \\ 583203 &:= (3 \times (0! - (((2 \times 3!) - 8!) \times 5)) \\ 583296 &:= (-6 \times (-((92^3) / 8)) + 5!) \\ 583434 &:= (((4! - 3)^4) - 3) \times (8 - 5) \\ 583437 &:= (((7 \times 3)^4) \times 3) - ((8 - 5)!) \\ 583443 &:= (((-3 + 4!)^4) \times (-3 + ((8 - 5))!)) \\ 583968 &:= ((-869) \times 3!) \times (8 - 5!) \\ 584056 &:= ((6! \times ((5 + 0!)!)) + ((4^8) + 5!)) \\ 584064 &:= (4! \times ((6! - ((0! - 4) \times 8!) / 5)) \\ 584116 &:= (-611) \times (4 - (8 \times 5!)) \\ 584496 &:= (((((-6 \times 9!) / (-4)) - 4!) + 8!) - 5!) \\ 584528 &:= (((8! / 2) \times (5 + 4!)) + (8 - 5!)) \\ 584635 &:= (((-5!) - 3!) \times (-6! + 4!)) - (8! + 5) \\ 584637 &:= (((7! / 3!) \times (6! - 4!)) - (8 - 5)) \\ 584653 &:= (((3! + 5!) \times (6! - 4!)) + (8 + 5)) \\ 584661 &:= (((1 + 6!) \times 6!) + ((4^8) + 5)) \\ 584688 &:= 8 \times (8! - 6 + 4 + 8^5) \\ 584754 &:= ((((-4 + 5!) \times 7!) - ((4! / 8))! + 5!) \\ 584755 &:= ((5! - 5) + (7! \times ((4 - 8) + 5!)) \\ 584756 &:= (((-((6 - 5) - 7!) \times (-((4 - 8)) - 5!)) \\ 584765 &:= (5! - ((6! - (7^{(4! / 8)!})) \times 5)) \\ 584766 &:= (((6 - 6!) \times (-7)) \times ((4! / (-8)) + 5!)) \\ 584824 &:= ((-4 \times ((-2 \times 8!) - (4^8))) + 5!) \\ 584832 &:= (((-((2 + 3) \times 8!) + (4! \times (8^5))) \\ 584872 &:= ((2 + 7!) \times (((8 - 4) - 8) + 5!)) \\ 584888 &:= (-8 - (-8 \times ((8! + 4!) + (8^5)))) \\ 585599 &:= (-9 - (((9! + ((5^5))) \times 8) / (-5))) \\ 585755 &:= (((5! \times 5) + 7) \times ((5! \times 8) + 5)) \\ 586368 &:= ((8 \times 6!) + (((3 + 6))! \times 8) / 5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 586656 &:= ((6 + 5!) \times (((6! \times 6!) + 8!) / 5!)) \\ 586965 &:= (5! + (((6! + 9) \times (6! + (85)))) \\ 587075 &:= (((5^7) \times 07) + 8!) - 5! \\ 587152 &:= (((2 + 5!) + 1) \times 7!) - (8^5) \\ 587185 &:= (((5^8) - ((1 \times 7))!) + (8! \times 5)) \\ 587315 &:= (((5^{1+3!}) \times 7) + (8! + 5!)) \\ 587435 &:= -(((5! \times ((3! \times 4!) - 7!)) + (85))) \\ 587496 &:= (((6! \times (-9)) + 4!) \times (-7 \times (8 + 5))) \\ 587523 &:= -((3!! - (-2 - (-5 \times (7^{(8-5)!})))) \\ 587525 &:= -((((5 - 2))! + (-5 \times (7^{(8-5)!}))) \\ 587544 &:= (4! + ((4! + 5!) \times (7! - (8 \times 5!))) \\ 587556 &:= ((-6 + 5!) \times ((5! + 7!) - ((8 - 5)!)) \\ 587664 &:= (4! \times (6 - (-6 \times (7! - (8 \times 5!)))) \\ 587866 &:= ((6 \times (((6^8) \times 7) + 8)) / 5!) \\ 587936 &:= -((((6! \times 3!) - 9!) - (7 \times (8^5))) \\ 587952 &:= -((((-(2 - 5))!)! - ((9! + 7!) \times 8) / 5)) \\ 587953 &:= -((3!! + ((5 + ((9! + 7!) \times 8)) / (-5))) \\ 587995 &:= ((-((5^9)) + (9! \times 7)) + (8 \times 5!)) \\ 588275 &:= (5 \times ((7^{-2+8}) + ((8 - 5)!)) \\ 588325 &:= (((5 + 2)^3) + ((8 + 8))) \times 5 \\ 588336 &:= (((6! \times 3!) + 3!) \times ((8 + 8) + 5!)) \\ 588595 &:= (-5 - (((9 \times 5!) - 8!) / 8) \times 5!) \\ 588648 &:= ((8! - 4!) - ((68 \times 8!) / (-5))) \\ 588672 &:= (((2 - 76) \times 8!) + 8!) / (-5) \\ 588736 &:= (((6^3) \times 7) + ((8 \times (8^5)))) \\ 588798 &:= (((-8 \times 9!) + ((7! / (-8)) - 8!)) / (-5) \\ 588816 &:= ((6! - (((1 + 8))! \times (-8)) - 8!) / 5) \\ 589329 &:= (((9 - 2)! - 3) \times (9 \times (8 + 5))) \\ 589473 &:= (-3 \times ((7! + 4!) + ((9 - 8!) \times 5)) \\ 589488 &:= (((8 + 8)^4) \times 9) - (8! / 5!) \\ 589495 &:= -((5! - ((9 + 4) \times ((9! / 8) - 5))) \\ 589584 &:= (4! - (((8 + 5) \times 9!) / (-8)) + 5!) \\ 589615 &:= ((5 - (((1 + 6))! \times 9)) \times (-8 + 5)) \\ 589667 &:= ((7 + 6) \times (-6 - ((9! / (-8)) - 5)) \\ 589675 &:= (-5 - ((7 \times 6!) \times (-9 \times (8 + 5)))) \\ 589677 &:= ((7! \times ((7 + 6) \times 9)) - (8 - 5)) \\ 589679 &:= ((9! - (7 - 6)) - ((9! / 8) \times (-5))) \\ 589685 &:= (((5! / 8))! / ((6 \times 9!) + 8!)) + 5 \\ 589698 &:= (((8 \times 9!) - ((6! + 9!) / (-8))) / 5) \\ 589704 &:= (4! - ((0 - 7!) \times (9 \times (8 + 5)))) \\ 589719 &:= ((9! - 1) - (((7! \times 9) + 8) \times (-5))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 589732 &:= (((2-3!) - (7! \times 9)) \times (-(8+5))) \\ 589734 &:= -((4! + ((3! + (7! \times 9)) \times (-(8+5)))))) \\ 589735 &:= (5! + ((3! + 7) \times ((9!/8) - 5))) \\ 589743 &:= (-3 \times ((4! + 7!) + ((9+8!) \times (-5)))) \\ 589745 &:= (((5 \times 4) - 7) \times ((9!/8) + 5)) \\ 589749 &:= ((9! + 4!) - (((7! + 9) + 8!) \times (-5))) \\ 589758 &:= ((8+5) \times ((7! \times 9) + ((8-5)!)) \\ 589771 &:= ((-(1 \times 7) - (7! \times 9)) \times (-(8+5))) \\ 589776 &:= (((6+7) \times (7 + (9!/8))) + 5) \\ 589782 &:= (-2 + ((8 + (7! \times 9)) \times (8+5))) \\ 589784 &:= (((4^{8!/7!}) \times 9) - (8 \times 5)) \\ 589843 &:= (3! + (((4^8) \times 9) + 8) + 5) \\ 589849 &:= ((9+4) \times (8 - ((9!/(-8)) - 5))) \\ 589864 &:= (((4!/6)^8) \times 9) + (8 \times 5) \\ 589932 &:= (2 \times ((3! \times 9) + (9 \times (8^5)))) \\ 589968 &:= (((((8! - 6!) - 9!) \times (-9)) + 8!)/5) \\ 590256 &:= ((6! \times (((5-2)! - 0!) - (9!/(-5)))) \\ 590346 &:= (-6 \times (4! - ((3^09) \times 5))) \\ 590355 &:= ((5! \times (-5!) + ((3! + 0!)!)) - (9 \times 5)) \\ 590442 &:= (-2 \times (4! - ((4+0!) \times (9^5)))) \\ 590465 &:= (-5 \times ((-6 \times ((4-0!)^9)) + 5)) \\ 590495 &:= (5 + ((9 + ((4 \times 0)!) \times (9^5))) \\ 590502 &:= (2 \times (0! + (5 \times (0! + (9^5)))) \\ 590524 &:= (4! + ((2 \times 5) \times (0! + (9^5)))) \\ 590619 &:= ((-91) \times ((6! + 0!) \times (-9))) + 5! \\ 590853 &:= (((-3+5!) \times (((8-0!)! + 9)) + 5!) \\ 590966 &:= (((6! \times 6!) - 9) - 0!) - (9!/(-5)) \\ 590976 &:= ((6!^{-7+9}) - ((09)!/(-5))) \\ 591384 &:= (4! - ((8!/3) \times (1 - (9 \times 5)))) \\ 591475 &:= (-5 + (((7! - ((4+1)!) + 9) \times 5!)) \\ 591696 &:= ((6! \times (((9-6)!)! + 1)) - (9!/(-5))) \\ 592128 &:= (8 \times ((2 \times (((1+2)!)! - (9!/(-5)))) \\ 592416 &:= ((6! \times (((-(1-4)!)! + 2)) - (9!/(-5))) \\ 592704 &:= (((4 \times (07^2)) \times 9!)/5!) \\ 593136 &:= (((6! + 3) \times (((1 \times 3)!)! - (9!/(-5))) \\ 593285 &:= (((5 \times (8^2)) \times 3!) + (9! + 5)) \\ 593332 &:= (-2 + ((3!! - (3!)) \times (3!! - (9-5)))) \\ 593565 &:= (((5! + 6!) - 5) \times (3!! - 9)) - 5! \\ 593675 &:= (-5 \times (((7^6) - 3!) - (9 \times 5!))) \\ 593755 &:= (-5 + (5! \times (7! + (3-95)))) \\ 593775 &:= (((5 \times 7) + 7!) \times ((3! - 9) + 5!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 593784 &:= (((4+8) \times 7)^3) + (9 \times 5!) \\ 593835 &:= (-5!) + (((3!! - 8!) \times 3) + 9) \times (-5)) \\ 593853 &:= ((3 \times ((-5 \times (-8!) + 3!)) - 9) - 5!) \\ 593955 &:= (((-(5! + (5 \times 9))) \times 3!) + 9) \times (-5)) \\ 593986 &:= (((6! - 8!) \times (-9 - 3!)) - (9 + 5)) \\ 594165 &:= (((5 \times 6!) + 1) \times ((4! + 9) \times 5)) \\ 594432 &:= (((-(2^3) \times 4!) \times 4!) \times (-9 - 5!)) \\ 594613 &:= ((3!! - 1) \times ((6! - (4+9)) + 5!)) \\ 594715 &:= ((5! + 1) \times ((7! + ((4-9))) - 5!)) \\ 595728 &:= (((8+2)!) - (7! \times (5! + 9)))/5 \\ 595792 &:= (2 \times (((9+7!) \times 59) + 5)) \\ 595968 &:= (8 \times (((6!/9) \times 5!) + 9!)/5) \\ 596155 &:= (((5 \times ((5+1)^6)) + 9!) - 5) \\ 596165 &:= (((5 \times ((6 \times 1)^6)) + 9!) + 5) \\ 596184 &:= (((-(4^8) - ((1 \times 6)!) \times (-9)) - 5!) \\ 596214 &:= (((4-1)!) \times (((2+6)!) + (9^5))) \\ 596226 &:= (-6 \times ((-2 - ((2+6)!) - (9^5))) \\ 596275 &:= (-5 + ((7! - (2+69)) \times 5!)) \\ 596286 &:= (6 \times (8! + ((2 \times 6) + (9^5)))) \\ 596424 &:= (((((4^2)^4) + 6!) \times 9) + 5!) \\ 596735 &:= -(((5^3!) + (-7 \times ((6! + 9) \times 5!))) \\ 596736 &:= ((6^3) + ((7! - 69) \times 5!)) \\ 596864 &:= (((4+6) \times (8^6)) + 9!)/5 \\ 597159 &:= (-((9^5-1)) + ((7! - 9) \times 5!)) \\ 597265 &:= ((5! \times (-(62) + 7!)) - (95)) \\ 597339 &:= (-93) \times (((3!! + 7) \times (-9)) + 5!) \\ 597355 &:= (-5 + (((-53) + 7!) - 9) \times 5!) \\ 597366 &:= ((66 \times 3) \times (-7 + (9!/5!))) \\ 597547 &:= (((7! + 4!) \times (5! + ((7-9)))) + 5) \\ 597592 &:= (2 \times (((9! + 5) - 7!) - (9^5))) \\ 597744 &:= (4! - (((-4-7!) + ((7 \times 9))) \times 5!)) \\ 597888 &:= ((8! + (8 \times ((8!/7) + 9!)))/5) \\ 597985 &:= ((5^8) + ((9!/(-7)) \times (-9-5))) \\ 598319 &:= ((9! - 1) + (3! \times (8! - (9 \times 5!)))) \\ 598445 &:= (((-((5 \times 4)^4) + 8!) - 9) \times (-5)) \\ 598464 &:= (((4! + 6!) \times 4!) + ((8 \times 9!)/5)) \\ 598584 &:= (((-(4^8) - (5! \times 8)) \times (-9)) + 5!) \\ 598751 &:= (-1 + (((5! + 78) \times 9!)/5!)) \\ 598752 &:= (2 \times ((5 \times (7! + 8!)) - (9!/(-5)))) \\ 598784 &:= -((4! + ((-8+7!) \times (-(8-9) - 5!))) \\ 598808 &:= (((8-0)!) - 8) \times ((8-9) + 5!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 598927 &:= ((7! + ((2 - 9))) \times ((8 - 9) + 5!)) \\ 599165 &:= ((5 - ((6 + 1)!) \times ((9/9) - 5!)) \\ 599286 &:= (6 \times (8! + (((2^9) + (9^5)))) \\ 599522 &:= ((2 - ((2 + 5)!) \times ((9/9) - 5!)) \\ 599527 &:= (((7! - 2) \times (5! - (9/9))) + 5) \\ 599664 &:= ((4! + 6!) \times (6! - (9 - 95))) \\ 599697 &:= (-7 \times (9 + (6! \times ((9/9) - 5!)))) \\ 599733 &:= (-((3^3)) + (7! \times (-((9/9) + 5!))) \\ 599744 &:= (-((4 \times 4) + (7! \times (-((9/9) + 5!)))) \\ 599748 &:= (-((8 + 4) + (7! \times (-((9/9) + 5!)))) \\ 599751 &:= (((-1 + 5!) \times (7! + 9)) - (9 \times 5!)) \\ 599755 &:= ((((-((5 \times 5)) \times 7!) + 9!) + 9!) - 5) \\ 599773 &:= ((3! + 7) + (7! \times (-((9/9) + 5!))) \\ 599774 &:= (((47 \times 7!) + 9!) + (9 + 5)) \\ 599775 &:= (((5! \times 7!) - 7!) - 9) + ((9 - 5)!) \\ 599784 &:= (((4! \times 8!) - 7!) - 9!) + ((9 - 5)!) \\ 599879 &:= (((-9 - 7!) + 8) \times ((9/9) - 5!)) \\ 599976 &:= (((6! + 7!) + 9) \times (9 + 95)) \\ 600365 &:= -((((5! + 6!) - 3!) + 0!) \times (0! - 6!)) \\ 600475 &:= (-5 - ((-7!) \times (((4 + 0)!)! - 0!) - 6!)) \\ 601344 &:= -((((4! \times 4!) \times 3!) - ((10)!/6)) \\ 601555 &:= (-((5^5)) - 5!) + ((10)!/6) \\ 601563 &:= ((3 - 6!) \times ((5! \times (-1)) + 0!) - 6!)) \\ 601675 &:= ((5! \times 7!) - ((6 - 1)^{-0!+6})) \\ 601773 &:= (-((3^7)) - ((7! - (10)!)/6)) \\ 602756 &:= ((-6 - ((5! \times (-7)) - 2)) \times (0! + 6!)) \\ 602875 &:= ((5! \times (7! - ((8 \times 2)))) + (0! - 6)) \\ 603355 &:= (-5 - (((5! + 3!) - (3 - 0!)) \times (-6!)) \\ 603357 &:= (((7! \times 5!) - 3) + ((-3 + 0!) \times 6!)) \\ 603359 &:= (((9! \times 5)/3) - 3!) - (0! + 6!) \\ 603476 &:= (6! + (((7! - 4!)/3!) \times (0! + 6!)) \\ 603477 &:= (((7!/(7 - 4))!) - 3) \times (0! + 6!)) \\ 603575 &:= (((5! + 7!) \times 5!) - ((3! - 0!)^6)) \\ 603593 &:= (((3! - 9!) \times (-5))/3) - (0! + 6)) \\ 603597 &:= (((7! - 9) \times 5!) - 3) - (-((0! - 6)!!)) \\ 603737 &:= (-((7^3)) + (((7!/3!) - 0!) \times 6!)) \\ 603744 &:= (((4^4) + 7!) \times ((3! - 0!)! - 6)) \\ 603834 &:= (((((4 + 3))! - 8) \times ((3! - 0!)!)) - 6) \\ 603835 &:= (-5 - ((3! \times (-8 + ((3! + 0!)!)))/(-6))) \\ 603864 &:= (4! - ((6! \times (-8 + ((3! + 0!)!)))/(-6))) \\ 603897 &:= (-7 \times (9 + (((8 - 3)!) \times (0! - 6!)))) \\ 603955 &:= (-5 - ((5! + ((9 - 3)!) \times (0! - 6!))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 604057 &:= (((7! \times 5!) + 0!) - 4!) - (06)! \\ 604073 &:= ((-((3! - 7!)) \times ((0! + 4)!) - (0! + 6)) \\ 604075 &:= (((5! \times 7!) - 0!) - 4) - (06)! \\ 604079 &:= (-9!) - (((7 + 0!)!) \times (-4!)) + (0! + 6!)) \\ 604175 &:= ((5! \times (7! + 1)) - ((4! + 0!) + 6!)) \\ 604224 &:= (-((4!^2)) - (((2 \times (4 + 0!))!)/(-6))) \\ 604314 &:= (((-4 + ((1 + 3)!)!) \times ((4 + 0!)!)) - 6) \\ 604315 &:= ((5! \times (((1 + 3)!)! - 4)) + ((0! - 6))) \\ 604344 &:= (4! - ((4 - ((3 + 4)!) \times (-((0! - 6)!!))) \\ 604385 &:= (-5 \times (83 + (-4!) \times ((0! + 6)!!)) \\ 604536 &:= ((6^3) - (5! \times (4 - ((0! + 6)!!))) \\ 604544 &:= (-((4^4)) - (-5!) \times (((4 \times 0)!) + 6)!) \\ 604555 &:= (-((5^5)) + (5! \times (4! + ((0! + 6)!!))) \\ 604572 &:= ((((-2 + 7!) \times 5!) + ((4 - 0!)!) + 6) \\ 604579 &:= (((-9 + (7! \times 5)) \times 4!) + (0! - 6)) \\ 604632 &:= (((((2 + 3)!) \times 6!) - 4!) \times (0! + 6)) \\ 604653 &:= ((3 + ((5! \times 6!) - 4!)) \times (0! + 6)) \\ 604656 &:= ((6!/-5) + (((6 + 4)!)!/06)) \\ 604657 &:= (7! \times 5 - 6) \times 4! + (0 \times 6!) \\ 604672 &:= (-((2^7)) + (((6 + 4)!)!/06)) \\ 604675 &:= (-5 - (((7! \times 6!) - (((4 - 0!)!)!)/(-6))) \\ 604676 &:= (((6! \times 7!) - 6!) - 4!)/06 \\ 604679 &:= (((-97) - 6!) - 4!) \times (0! - 6!)) \\ 604704 &:= (4! + (((0! - 7!) \times 4!) \times (0! - 6))) \\ 604705 &:= (-5 \times (((0! - 7!) \times 4!) + 0!) - 6)) \\ 604715 &:= (-5 \times (((1 - 7!) \times 4!) - 0!) - 6)) \\ 604734 &:= ((4! \times (-3 + (7! \times (4 + 0!)))) + 6) \\ 604735 &:= (-5 \times (3! - (((7! \times 4!) - 0!) - 6))) \\ 604738 &:= (((-8!)/3!) - ((-7!) \times ((4 + 0!)!) + 6)) \\ 604745 &:= (5 \times (((4! \times 7!) - 4) - 0!) - 6)) \\ 604749 &:= (((-9 + (4! \times 7!)) \times (4 + 0!)) - 6) \\ 604752 &:= (-2 + ((5! \times 7!) - (40 + 6))) \\ 604754 &:= (((4! \times 5) \times 7!) - (40 + 6)) \\ 604757 &:= 7! \times 5! - 7 - (4 - 0!)! \times 6 \\ 604758 &:= (-8 + ((5! \times 7!) - (40 - 6))) \\ 604764 &:= (((4! + 6) \times ((7! \times 4) - 0!)) - 6) \\ 604765 &:= (-5 \times (((6 \times 7!) \times (-4)) + 0!) + 6)) \\ 604766 &:= (((6!/6) \times 7!) - (40 - 6)) \\ 604772 &:= (((-((2 - 7)))! \times 7!) - (4 \times (0! + 6))) \\ 604773 &:= ((3 \times (-7 - (7! \times (-40)))) - 6) \\ 604775 &:= (((5! \times 7!) - 7) - 4!) - (0 - 6)) \\ 604783 &:= (((-((3 - 8)))! \times 7!) - ((4! - 0!) - 6)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 604784 &:= (4! - ((-8 + (7! \times 4!)) \times (0! - 6))) \\ 604785 &:= ((-(5 - 8) - (7! \times 4!)) \times (0! - 6)) \\ 604786 &:= (-((6 + 8)) - ((7! \times 4!) \times (0! - 6))) \\ 604787 &:= ((78 - (((7 + 4) - 0!))!)/(-6)) \\ 604788 &:= 8! \times (8 + 7) - (4 - 0!)! - 6 \\ 604789 &:= (-((9 + 8)) - ((-7!) \times ((4 + 0!))! - 6)) \\ 604791 &:= (-((1 \times 9) - ((7! \times 4!) \times (0! - 6))) \\ 604794 &:= (((-((4 - 9)) \times 7!) \times 4!) + (0 - 6)) \\ 604795 &:= (((5 \times 9!)/(7 - 4) + 0!) - 6) \\ 604796 &:= (((-(((6 - 9) - 7)))! - 4!)/06) \\ 604799 &:= ((9! + 9!) - ((7! \times 4!) + ((0 \times 6)!)) \\ 604815 &:= ((-5 \times (1 + 8!)) \times (-4 + ((0 \times 6)!)) \\ 604818 &:= (((8 + 1))! + (((8! + 4) - 0!) \times 6)) \\ 604819 &:= ((9! + 1) + (((8! + 4) - 0!) \times 6)) \\ 604835 &:= (-5 \times (((-3 \times 8!) - ((4 \times 0)!)) - 6)) \\ 604836 &:= ((6 \times 3!) + (840 \times 6!)) \\ 604839 &:= (((9 + 3!) \times ((8! + 4) - 0!)) - 6) \\ 604851 &:= ((15 \times ((8! + 4) - 0!)) + 6) \\ 604853 &:= (((3 \times 5) \times (8! + 4)) - (0! + 6)) \\ 604854 &:= (4! + (-5 \times ((8! \times (-4 + 0!)) - 6))) \\ 604856 &:= (((6! \times 5!) + 8) \times (((4 \times 0)! + 6)) \\ 604857 &:= ((7! \times 5!) + ((8! + (((4 - 0!))!)/6!)) \\ 604869 &:= (((9 + 6) \times ((8! + 4) + 0!)) - 6) \\ 604875 &:= (-5 \times (((7 + 8!) \times (-4 + 0!)) + 6)) \\ 604896 &:= (((6 + 9) \times (8! + ((4 - 0!))!)) + 6) \\ 604915 &:= (-5 + (((1 + 9))! + (((4 - 0!))!)/6)) \\ 604916 &:= (((6! + ((1 + 9)!)) - 4!)/06) \\ 604935 &:= (-5 \times (-((3 \times 9)) + (-4!) \times ((0! + 6)!))) \\ 604938 &:= (((8! \times 3!) + 9!) + ((4! - 0!) \times 6)) \\ 604968 &:= ((8! \times (6 + 9)) + (4! \times (0! + 6))) \\ 605043 &:= ((3^{4+0!}) + (5! \times ((0! + 6)!)) \\ 605157 &:= (-7 \times (-51 - (5! \times (06!))) \\ 605166 &:= ((6 \times 61) + (5! \times ((0! + 6)!)) \\ 605273 &:= (((((3! + 7!) - 2) \times 5!) - 0!) - 6) \\ 605274 &:= (((4 + 7!) \times (((-((2 - 5)))! - 0!))! - 6) \\ 605275 &:= (-5 + (((7! - 2) \times 5!) + (06!)) \\ 605281 &:= ((((-((1 - 8)))! - 2) \times 5!) + (0! + 6!)) \\ 605287 &:= (((((7! + (8/2)) \times 5!) + 0!) + 6) \\ 605375 &:= ((5 - (7!/3!)) \times (-5 - (06!)) \\ 605395 &:= (-5 \times (((9!/(-3)) - 5!) + ((0 \times 6)!)) \\ 605424 &:= (((4! + 2) \times 4!) + (5! \times ((0! + 6)!)) \\ 605471 &:= (-1 - (7 \times (4! - (5! \times (0! + 6)!))) \\ 605475 &:= (((5! \times 7!) - 45) + (06!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 605496 &:= (((-(((6 - 9)))! - (4! - (5! \times ((0! + 6)!))) \\ 605515 &:= (-5 + (((((1 + 5))! + 5!) + 0!) \times 6!)) \\ 605516 &:= ((((((6 + 1))! \times 5!) - 5) + 0!) + 6!)) \\ 605545 &:= (((5^4) + 5!) + (5! \times ((0! + 6)!)) \\ 605605 &:= ((-5 + ((0! + 6!) \times 5!)) \times (0! + 6)) \\ 605624 &:= (-((4^2)) + ((6! + 5!) \times (0! + 6!)) \\ 605629 &:= (-((9 + 2)) + ((6! + 5!) \times (0! + 6!)) \\ 605632 &:= (-((2^3)) + ((6! + 5!) \times (0! + 6!)) \\ 605635 &:= (-5 + ((((-((3 - 6)))! + 5!) \times (0! + 6!)) \\ 605638 &:= ((-8 + 3!) + ((6! + 5!) \times (0! + 6!)) \\ 605641 &:= ((1^4) + ((6! + 5!) \times (0! + 6!)) \\ 605642 &:= (-((2 - 4)) + ((6! + 5!) \times (0! + 6!)) \\ 605645 &:= ((5!/4!) + ((6! + 5!) \times (0! + 6!)) \\ 605664 &:= ((4! \times 6) + (((6! + 5!) + 0!) \times 6!)) \\ 605675 &:= ((5 \times 7) + ((6! + 5!) \times (0! + 6!)) \\ 605676 &:= (-6 + (-7 \times (-6 - (5! \times (0! + 6!)))) \\ 605736 &:= ((6^3) - (((-7 \times 5!) - 0!) \times 6!)) \\ 605753 &:= (((((3 + 5) + 7!) \times 5!) - 0!) - 6) \\ 605755 &:= ((5! - 5) - ((-7 \times 5!) \times (0! + 6!)) \\ 605759 &:= (((((9 + 5) + 7!) \times 5!) - 0!) - 6!)) \\ 605766 &:= (6! + (((6 \times (7^5)) - 0!) \times 6)) \\ 605784 &:= (4! + ((8 + 7!) \times ((5 + (0 \times 6)!))!)) \\ 605785 &:= ((5! \times (8 + 7!)) + (-5 \times (0! - 6))) \\ 605824 &:= ((4 \times (2^8)) + (5! \times ((0! + 6)!)) \\ 605857 &:= ((7! \times 5!) + (((8!/5!) + 0!) + 6!)) \\ 605875 &:= (5! + (((7! + 8) \times 5!) + 0!) - 6) \\ 606235 &:= (((((5! + 3!)) + 2) \times 6!) + ((0! - 6))) \\ 606264 &:= (4! + (((6! + 2) + ((6 - 0!))! \times 6!)) \\ 606355 &:= (-5 - (((-5!) - 3!) \times (6! + 0!)) - 6!)) \\ 606361 &:= (((((1 + 6))! + 3!)/6) \times (0! + 6!)) \\ 606367 &:= (((((7! + 6)/3!) \times (6! + 0!)) + 6) \\ 606957 &:= ((7! \times 5!) + (-((9 - 6)) \times (0! - 6!)) \\ 607344 &:= (4! - (-(((4! - 3) + 7!)) \times (-((0! - 6)!))) \\ 607554 &:= ((4! \times 5!) + ((5! \times (7! - 0!)) - 6)) \\ 607674 &:= (((((4! + 7!) \times 6!)/(7 - 0!)) - 6) \\ 608365 &:= (-5 \times (6 - (((3 \times 8!) - 0!) + 6!)) \\ 608395 &:= (-5 \times (((9!/(-3)) + ((8 \times 0)!)) - 6!)) \\ 608405 &:= (-5 \times (((0! - 4) \times 8!) - 0!) - 6!)) \\ 608415 &:= (-5 \times (((1 - 4) \times (8! + 0!)) - 6!)) \\ 608515 &:= (((-((5! + 1)) \times (5 - ((8 - 0!))!)) - 6!)) \\ 608664 &:= -((((4! - (6^6)) - 8!) \times (0! + 6)) \\ 608751 &:= ((1 + 5!) \times ((7! - 8) - ((0 \times 6)!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 609375 &:= (-((5^7) \times 39))/(0! - 6)) \\ 609744 &:= (((4! \times (-4)) + 7!) + (((9 + 0!)!)/6)) \\ 609795 &:= ((-(5 \times 9) + 7!) + (((9 + 0!)!)/6)) \\ 609835 &:= ((-5 + ((3! \times 8!) + 9!)) + ((0! + 6)!)) \\ 609837 &:= ((7! - 3) + (8! \times (9 + 06))) \\ 609857 &:= (((7! \times 5!) + ((8 + 9))) + ((0! + 6)!)) \\ 609864 &:= ((4! + ((6 \times 8!) + 9!)) + ((0! + 6)!)) \\ 610082 &:= ((2 + ((8 - 0!)!)) \times (0! + (-((1 - 6)!)))!)) \\ 610573 &:= (((3! + 7!) \times (5! + 0!)) + (1 + 6)) \\ 610576 &:= (6! + ((7! \times (5! + 0!)) + (16))) \\ 610784 &:= (-4!) - ((-8 - 7!) \times (0! + (-((1 - 6)!)))!)) \\ 610808 &:= (((8 - 0!)! + 8) \times (0! + (-((1 - 6)!)))!)) \\ 610929 &:= (-(((9 - 2)! + 9)) \times (-0! - (-((1 - 6)!)))!)) \\ 611897 &:= (-((7! + ((9 + 8)))) \times (-1 - (-((1 - 6)!)))!)) \\ 612074 &:= (((4! - 7!) - 0!) \times (-2 - (-((1 - 6)!)))!)) \\ 612355 &:= (-5 + ((-5!) - 3!) \times (-((2 + 1)^6))) \\ 612584 &:= (-4 - (-852) \times (-1 + 6!)) \\ 614544 &:= (4! \times (((4^5) \times (4! + 1)) + 6)) \\ 614656 &:= (((-6 + (5!/6))^4) \times 16) \\ 614875 &:= ((5! \times 7!) + ((8!/4) + (1 - 6))) \\ 615374 &:= (((4 + 7!) \times ((3 + 5!) - 1)) + 6) \\ 615375 &:= -(((5! - 7!) - 3) \times (5! - (1 - 6))) \\ 615678 &:= (8! + ((-7 \times (-6 + 5!)) \times (-1 - 6!))) \\ 615719 &:= (((91 + 7!) \times 5!) - (1^6)) \\ 615735 &:= ((5 \times (3^7)) + (5! \times ((1 + 6)!))) \\ 616288 &:= -((8! - (((8! - 2) + 6!) \times 16))) \\ 617705 &:= ((5! + 0!) \times (7! + ((71 - 6)))) \\ 617776 &:= (((6 + 7)!)/(7! + 7!)) + (16) \\ 618336 &:= ((6! + (3! \times (-3^8))) \times (-16)) \\ 619533 &:= (3!! - ((-3 - 5!) \times (-9 + ((1 + 6)!)))!)) \\ 619944 &:= (4! + ((4! + 99) \times ((1 + 6)!))) \\ 619977 &:= (((-7 - 7!) + 9!) + ((9 - 1)^6)) \\ 619984 &:= (((-((4 - 8))^9) + 9!) - ((1 + 6)!)) \\ 620517 &:= (((7! - 1) \times ((5! + 0!) + 2)) + 6!) \\ 620535 &:= (-((5! + 3) \times (-5 - (((0 \times 2)! + 6)!)))!)) \\ 622104 &:= (4! \times (0! + (((1 + 2)!^2) \times 6!)) \\ 622364 &:= (((4 \times (6^3)) - 2) \times (2 + 6!)) \\ 622796 &:= (((((-6 \times 9!)/7) + 2) \times (-2)) + 6!) \\ 622944 &:= ((4! \times (-4 \times 9)) \times (-((2/2)) - 6!)) \\ 622973 &:= -((3!! - (-7 + (((9 + 2)!/(2^6)))))) \\ 623519 &:= ((9! - 1) - (((5! \times (-3)) - 2) \times 6!)) \\ 623544 &:= (4! + (((4! + 5!) \times 3!) + 2) \times 6!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 623556 &:= ((6!/(-5)) + (((5 + 3!)!)/(2^6))) \\ 623572 &:= (-((2^7)) + (((5 + 3!)!)/(2^6))) \\ 623664 &:= (4! \times (66 + ((3!^2) \times 6!)) \\ 623695 &:= (-5 + (((9 + (6/3)))!/(2^6))) \\ 623724 &:= (4! + (((2 \times 7) - 3)!/(2^6))) \\ 624238 &:= (((-8!) - 3!!) - 2) - (((4!/2)!/(-6!)) \\ 624384 &:= (-4 \times ((8! - (3!^4)) \times (2 - 6))) \\ 624576 &:= ((6^7) + ((5! \times (-4)) \times (2 - 6!))) \\ 624835 &:= ((-((5^3)) - 8!) - (((4!/2)!/(-6!))) \\ 624897 &:= ((-((7 \times 9)) - 8!) - (((4!/2)!/(-6!))) \\ 624904 &:= -((((4 + 0!)! - (9! + ((4 \times 2)^6)))) \\ 624905 &:= -((((5! - 0!) - 9!) - ((4 \times 2)^6)) \\ 624943 &:= ((-((3^4)) + 9!) + ((4 \times 2)^6)) \\ 624954 &:= (((4 + 5!) \times ((9 - 4) + 2)! - 6) \\ 624968 &:= (((8^6) + 9!) - (((4 \times 2)!/6!)) \\ 624994 &:= (((4^9) + 9!) - (4 + 26)) \\ 625048 &:= (8 \times (((4 + 0!)^{5+2}) + 6)) \\ 625077 &:= (-7 + ((7! + 0!) \times (5! - ((2 - 6)))) \\ 625208 &:= ((8 - 0!)! + 2) \times (5! - 2 + 6) \\ 625536 &:= (((6^3!) + ((5! + 5!)^2)) \times 6) \\ 625575 &:= (-5 + ((7! + 5) \times (5! - ((2 - 6)))) \\ 625675 &:= (-5 - ((7! \times ((-6 - 5!) + 2)) - 6!)) \\ 625704 &:= (((4 - 0!)! + 7!) \times (5! - ((2 - 6)))) \\ 625758 &:= (((8 \times ((5^7) + 5)) - 2) + 6!) \\ 625968 &:= ((8 \times 6) \times (((-9 + 5!)^2) + 6!)) \\ 626395 &:= ((-5 + 9!) + ((3! - (6!/(-2))) \times 6!)) \\ 626448 &:= (((8!/4!) + 4) \times (62 \times 6)) \\ 626544 &:= (-4! - 4! + 5! + 6!)^2 - 6! \\ 627264 &:= (4! \times ((6^2) \times 726)) \\ 627824 &:= (-((4^2)) - (-872) \times 6!) \\ 627829 &:= (-((9 + 2)) - (-872) \times 6!) \\ 627832 &:= (-((2^3)) - (-872) \times 6!) \\ 627838 &:= ((-8 + 3!) - (-872) \times 6!) \\ 627841 &:= ((1^4) - (-872) \times 6!) \\ 627842 &:= (-((2 - 4)) - (-872) \times 6!) \\ 627845 &:= ((5!/4!) - (-872) \times 6!) \\ 627852 &:= ((2 - (5! \times (-872))) \times 6) \\ 627864 &:= ((4 \times 6) - (-872) \times 6!) \\ 627875 &:= ((5 \times 7) - (-872) \times 6!) \\ 627977 &:= ((-((7^7)) - 9!) + ((7!/2) \times 6!)) \\ 627984 &:= (4! \times (89 \times ((7^2) \times 6))) \end{aligned}$$

- 629136** := $((6^{3!-1}) \times (9^2)) - 6!$
629155 := $((-5 - 5!) \times (1 - ((9 - 2)!)) - 6!$
629584 := $((4! + (8! / (-5 \times 9))) \times (-2 - 6!))$
629648 := $((((8! + 4!) + 6!) \times 92) / 6)$
629937 := $(-7 \times (3!! - (-9 + (9! / (-2 - 6))))))$
630758 := $((8 \times (((5^7) - 0!) + 3!!)) + 6)$
632452 := $(2 \times (((5 + 4)! + 2) - (3!^6)))$
632492 := $(2 \times (((9! + 4!) - 2) - (3!^6)))$
632512 := $(-((2^{15})) - (((2 \times 3!)! / (-6!)))$
632736 := $(((((6 \times 3!) + ((7 - 2)!)^3) / 6)$
632848 := $(((-8 + 4!) \times ((8! - 2) - 3!!)) - 6!$
633276 := $(-((6 \times 7^2)) \times (3! + (-3 \times 6!)))$
633567 := $((7! - 6) \times (5! + 3!)) + (3 - 6!))$
633585 := $(-5 \times (-8!) + ((-5!) \times 3!! - ((3 - 6))))$
633624 := $(4! + (((2 \times 6)! / ((3! \times 3!) + 6!)))$
633789 := $(-9 - (-873) \times (3! + 6!))$
633888 := $((8 + 8) \times (8! - ((-3 \times 3!) + 6!)))$
633906 := $(((((6 + 0)! - 9) \times ((3!! / 3!) + 6)$
634572 := $((2 + 7!) \times ((5 \times 4!) + 3!)) - 6!$
634608 := $((8! - ((0! + 6)!)) - 4!) \times (3 \times 6)$
634764 := $((46 - (7! \times (4! - 3))) \times (-6))$
634857 := $((-((7^5)) + 8!) \times (4! + 3)) + 6)$
634896 := $((-6 \times ((9! / (-8)) + 4!)) + ((3 + 6)!))$
634907 := $7 \times (-0! + 9! / 4 - 3 \times 6)$
634957 := $7 \times (-5 + 9! / 4 - 3!) - 6$
634974 := $(-((4! + (-7 \times ((9! / 4!) \times 3!) - 6))))$
634977 := $(7! - (-7 \times ((9! / 4) - ((3^6))))$
634978 := $(-8! + 7! \times 9! / 4) / 3!! - 6$
634987 := $((-7 \times (8 + (9! / (-4)))) - ((3 - 6)))$
634992 := $((-((2 - 9)) \times ((9! / 4) - 3!)) - 6)$
635032 := $(-2 + (((3! + 0!)! \times (5! + 3!)) - 6))$
635034 := $(((((4 + 3)! \times (0! + ((5^3)))) - 6)$
635035 := $(-5 + ((3! + 0!) \times ((5! + 3!) \times 6!)))$
635037 := $((7! \times (3! + (05)!)) + ((3 - 6)))$
635038 := $(-8 + (((3! + 0!)! \times (5! + 3!)) + 6))$
635046 := $(((((6 + ((4 \times 0)!))! \times (5! + 3!)) + 6)$
635047 := $(7 \times (((4 \times 0)! + ((5! + 3!) \times 6!)))$
635064 := $(4! + ((6 + 0!) \times ((5! + 3!) \times 6!)))$
635076 := $((6 + 7!) \times (0! + ((5^3)))) - 6!$
635117 := $(-7 \times (-11 - ((5! + 3!) \times 6!)))$
635171 := $(-1 + (((7! + 1) \times (5! + 3!)) + 6))$
635172 := $((((2 + 7!) - 1) \times (5! + 3!)) + 6)$
635184 := $((4! \times (8! - (((1 - 5)!^3))) - 6!$
635274 := $(-((4! - (((7! + 2) \times (5! + 3!)) + 6)))$
635278 := $-8 + (7! + 2) \times (5! + 3!) - 6$
635292 := $((-2 - ((9 - 2)!)) \times (-5! - (-((3 - 6)!)))$
635376 := $(6! + (((7! - 3) \times (5! + 3!)) - 6))$
635385 := $(5 \times ((8! - 3) + (5! \times (3 + 6!))))$
635564 := $(-4 \times (-(((6 + 5)^5)) - (-3 \times 6!)))$
635676 := $((6 + 7!) \times (6 + 5!)) + (3! / (-6))$
635697 := $((-7 \times (9 - (6! \times (5! + 3!)))) + 6!$
635733 := $(-((3^3)) + ((7! \times (5! + 3!)) + 6!))$
635744 := $(-((4 \times 4) + ((7! \times (5! + 3!)) + 6!))$
635748 := $(-((8 + 4) + ((7! \times (5! + 3!)) + 6!))$
635749 := $(((((9! / (-4)) \times (-7)) - 5) - 3!) + 6!$
635773 := $((3! + 7) + ((7! \times (5! + 3!)) + 6!))$
635775 := $(((-5 - ((7! \times 7!) / 5!)) \times (-3)) + 6!$
635784 := $(4! + ((8 + (7 \times 5^3))) \times 6!))$
635796 := $(((-((6 - 9))! + 7!) \times (5! + (-((3 - 6)!)))$
636474 := $(((((4! \times 7) - 4) + 6!) \times 3!!) - 6)$
636763 := $((3!! \times 6!) + (((7^6) - 3!) + 6!))$
636766 := $((6! \times 6!) + (((7^6) - 3))) + 6!$
636769 := $(((((9 - 6)! + (7^6)) - (3!! \times (-6!)))$
636776 := $((6! + (7 + 7^6))) - (3!! \times (-6!))$
636824 := $((4! \times 2) + (86^3)) + 6!$
637119 := $((9! \times (-1)) - ((1 - ((7 + 3)^6))))$
637413 := $((3!! + (1 + (4! \times 7))) \times (-3 + 6!))$
637585 := $((5^8) + (5! \times ((7^3) \times 6)))$
637688 := $(8! - ((-8 + 6!) \times ((7! - 3!) / (-6))))$
637768 := $((-((8 - (6^7))) - 7!) + ((3 + 6)!))$
637794 := $(((-((4 - 9))! + 7) \times (7! - ((3 \times 6))))$
637839 := $(-((9^3!) - (8! \times (-7 - 36))))$
638064 := $((4! + ((6 + 0)!))! \times (((8 - 3)! + 6))$
638395 := $(-5 \times ((9! / (-3)) - ((8! - 3!) / 6)))$
638448 := $((8! - ((4! \times 4) \times (8! + 3))) / (-6))$
638496 := $((6! + ((9^4) \times 8)) \times (3! + 6))$
638635 := $(-5 + ((3!! \times 6!) - ((8! \times (-3)) + 6!)))$
638664 := $((4! + (6! \times 6!)) + ((8! \times 3) - 6!))$
638688 := $((8 \times ((8! - 6!) + 8!) + 3!) - 6!$
638784 := $((4! \times 8!) + (-7 \times 8!)) - (3!^6)$
638976 := $(((((6 + 7!) + 9!) - (8^3))) \times 6)$
639288 := $8 \times (8! \times 2 - (9/3)^6)$
639348 := $(8! - 4) \times 3 + (9 - 3)! \times 6!$

$$\begin{aligned} 639352 &:= ((-2 + (5!^3)) - ((9! \times 3) + 6)) \\ 639354 &:= (((4! \times 5)^3) - ((9! \times 3) + 6)) \\ 639355 &:= ((-5 + (5!^3)) + (9! \times (3 - 6))) \\ 639358 &:= ((-8 + (5!^3)) + ((9! \times (-3)) + 6)) \\ 639359 &:= (9! + ((-5!) \times 3!!) + (9! - (3!/6))) \\ 639384 &:= ((4! - (8! \times (-3))) + (((9 - 3)! \times 6!)) \\ 639408 &:= (8 \times (((0! + 4)! - 9) \times 3!!) + 6)) \\ 639447 &:= (((7! + 4) \times 4!) - 9) - (3!! \times (-6!)) \\ 639577 &:= ((7! \times (7 + 5!)) - ((9! - 3!!)/6!)) \\ 640075 &:= (-5 - (7! \times ((-0!) - ((0! + 4)!)) - 6))) \\ 640775 &:= (((((5! + 7) \times 7!) - 0!) - 4!) + 6!) \\ 641976 &:= (((6^7) + 9!) - ((1 + 4)!)) - 6! \\ 642384 &:= (-4 \times (((8! + (3^2)) \times (-4)) + 6!)) \\ 642848 &:= ((-8 + 4!) \times ((8! + 2) - (4! \times 6))) \\ 643536 &:= (6! + ((3!!/(-5)) \times (-3! \times (4! + 6!)))) \\ 643584 &:= (((4! + 8!) - 5!) \times (3! + (4 + 6))) \\ 643748 &:= (((8! \times 4) - (7^3)) \times 4!/6) \\ 643824 &:= ((4! \times (((2 \times 8!)/3) - 4!)) - 6!) \\ 644368 &:= (((8! - (6/3)) \times (4 \times 4)) - 6!) \\ 644379 &:= (9! + ((-7 \times (3 - ((4 + 4)!)) - 6!)) \\ 644384 &:= (((4 - 8!) - 3) \times (-4 \times 4)) - 6! \\ 644404 &:= ((4 \times (0! - (-4 \times ((4 + 4)!))) - 6!)) \\ 644408 &:= (((8! - 0!) \times (4 \times 4)) + 4!) - 6! \\ 644424 &:= (((((4 \times 2)! \times (4 \times 4)) + 4!) - 6!)) \\ 644428 &:= (8! + 2) \times 4 \times 4 - 4 - 6! \\ 644448 &:= (((((8! + 4) \times (-4)) + 4) \times (-4)) - 6!) \\ 644488 &:= (-8 + (((8! \times 4) + 4!) \times 4) - 6!) \\ 644768 &:= (((8! - 67) \times (4 \times 4)) + 6!) \\ 644784 &:= ((-4 \times (((-8 \times 7!) - 4!) \times 4)) - 6!) \\ 644838 &:= (((8! - (-3 \times (8! - 4!))) \times 4) + 6) \\ 644848 &:= (((-8 + 4!) \times ((8! + 4!) + 4)) - 6!) \\ 644856 &:= (((6 - 5!) - (8! \times 4)) \times (-4)) - 6! \\ 644928 &:= 8 \times (2 \times (-9 + (4 + 4)!)) - 6) \\ 644981 &:= (-1 - (((8! - 9) \times (-4 \times 4))) - 6)) \\ 644982 &:= ((2 \times ((8! - 9) \times (4 + 4))) + 6) \\ 644984 &:= (-4 \times (((8! - 9) \times (-4)) + ((4 - 6)))) \\ 644998 &:= (((8 - (9!/9)) \times (-4 \times 4)) + 6) \\ 645024 &:= ((4^2) \times (((0! - (5 + 4)))! - 6)) \\ 645082 &:= (((2 - 8!) \times ((0! - 5) \times 4)) - 6) \\ 645084 &:= (((4 \times (8! - 0!)) - 5) \times (4!/6)) \\ 645088 &:= (-8 + 8! \times (-0! + 5)) \times 4!/6 \\ 645094 &:= ((((-4 \times ((9 - 0!))!) + 5) \times (-4)) - 6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 645118 &:= ((8! \times (1 + 15)) + ((4 - 6))) \\ 645126 &:= (((6 + 2)! \times (-((1 - 5) \times 4))) + 6) \\ 645138 &:= 8! + (3! + 1)! \times 5! + 4! - 6 \\ 645144 &:= (-4 \times (((((4 - 1) + 5)! \times (-4)) - 6)) \\ 645184 &:= ((4 + 8!) \times (((1 + 5) + 4) + 6)) \\ 645194 &:= ((-4 \times (((9 - 1)! + 5) \times (-4))) - 6) \\ 645248 &:= (((8! \times 4) + (2^5)) \times 4!/6) \\ 645348 &:= (((((8! \times (-4)) + 3) + 5!) \times (-4)) + 6!) \\ 645384 &:= (((((-4 \times 8!) - 3!) + 5!) \times (-4)) + 6!) \\ 645484 &:= (((((4! + 8!) \times 4) - 5) \times 4!/6) \\ 645488 &:= (((((8 + 8!) \times (-4)) + 5!) \times (-4)) + 6!) \\ 645584 &:= (((4! + 8!) + 5) \times ((5! - 4!)/6)) \\ 645758 &:= (((8 + 5!) \times (7! + 5)) + ((4 - 6))) \\ 645784 &:= (-4 \times ((8 \times ((7! + 5) \times (-4))) - 6)) \\ 645804 &:= (((4 \times (0! - 8!)) + 5) \times (-4)) + 6! \\ 645816 &:= (((6 + 1)! \times (8 + 5!)) - (4! - 6!)) \\ 645824 &:= (((4^2) \times (8! - (5 - 4))) + 6!) \\ 645835 &:= ((-5 + 3!!) - (8! \times ((5! - 4!)/(-6)))) \\ 645844 &:= (4! - ((((-4 \times 8!) + 5) \times 4) - 6!)) \\ 645864 &:= ((4! + 6!) - (8! \times ((5! - 4!)/(-6)))) \\ 645879 &:= (9! + ((7 \times (8! + 5)) - (-4 - 6!)) \\ 645888 &:= 8 \times (8! + 8! + 5! - 4 \times 6) \\ 645984 &:= (((((4! \times 8!)/9) + 5!) + 4!) \times 6) \\ 646224 &:= (((4^2) \times (((2 + 6)! + 4!)) + 6!) \\ 646416 &:= ((6! + ((14 \times 6))^{-4+6}) \\ 646584 &:= (4! + (((8 - (5 \times 6!))/(-4)) \times 6!)) \\ 646597 &:= (((7! - 9!) \times (-5 + (6^4)))/6!) \\ 646784 &:= (-4 \times (((8! - 76) \times (-4)) - 6!)) \\ 646848 &:= ((-8 + 4!) \times (8! + ((-6 + 4!) \times 6))) \\ 647058 &:= (8 + 5! + 0!) \times (7! - 4!) - 6 \\ 647155 &:= (((-5 - 5!) \times (1 - 7!)) + (4! \times 6!)) \\ 647286 &:= (((6! + (8!/2)) \times (7 + 4!)) + 6) \\ 647352 &:= (-2 + 5)^3! \times (7 \times 4! + 6!) \\ 647558 &:= (((-8 - 5!) \times ((5 - 7!) - 4!)) + 6) \\ 647755 &:= ((5! - (5^7)) + ((7! \times 4!) \times 6)) \\ 647759 &:= (((9 + 5!) \times 7!) - (7^{4!/6})) \\ 647864 &:= (-4 \times (6 + (((8! - 7) \times (-4)) - 6!))) \\ 647888 &:= (8 + 8) \times (8! - 7) + 4 \times 6! \\ 648004 &:= 4 \times (00! + 8! \times 4 + 6!) \\ 648024 &:= (-4 \times (-2 - (((0! + 8!) \times 4) + 6!))) \\ 648192 &:= ((2^9) \times (((-((1 - 8!))!)/4) + 6)) \\ 648384 &:= (-4 \times (((-((8 \times 3)) - 8!) \times 4) - 6!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 648474 &:= ((-4 \times (((7!/4!) + 8!) \times (-4))) - 6) \\ 648475 &:= (-5 - (((7! + (4! \times 8!)) \times 4)/(-6))) \\ 648476 &:= (((6 - 7!) - (4! \times 8!)) \times (-4))/6) \\ 648576 &:= ((6^7) + (((5! + 8) \times 4) \times 6!)) \\ 649288 &:= ((8 \times ((8! \times 2) + 9)) + (4^6)) \\ 649493 &:= (((3^9) \times (4! + 9)) - 46) \\ 649539 &:= ((9 \times (3! + 5)) \times (9^{4!/6})) \\ 649636 &:= (((6! + 3!) - (6!/(-9)))^{-4+6}) \\ 649977 &:= (((7! - 7) \times (9 + ((9 - 4)!)) + 6!) \\ 650259 &:= (((9^5) \times (((2 + 0!)! + 5)) + 6!) \\ 650665 &:= (((5! + 6) \times ((6 + 0!)!)) + (5^6)) \\ 650736 &:= ((6^3!) + ((7! \times (05!)) - 6!)) \\ 650748 &:= ((84 + 7!) \times ((0! + 5!) + 6)) \\ 650759 &:= (((((9 + 5!) \times 7!) - 0!) - 5!) + 6!) \\ 650848 &:= (8 \times (-4 - (((8 - 0!) - 5!) \times 6!)) \\ 650875 &:= (-5 - ((7! \times ((-8 - 0!) - 5!)) - 6!)) \\ 650904 &:= (4! - ((0! - 905) \times 6!)) \\ 651605 &:= (5 \times (0! - ((-61) - 5!) \times 6!)) \\ 653184 &:= (((4! \times 81) \times 3!) \times 56) \\ 653199 &:= ((9 \times (((9! - 1) + 3!)/5)) + 6) \\ 653338 &:= ((8 + 3!) \times ((3!^{3!}) + (5 + 6))) \\ 653472 &:= (-2 \times (7! - (4!^{3-5+6}))) \\ 653772 &:= (-((2 \times 7)) \times ((7 + (3!^5)) \times (-6))) \\ 653805 &:= (-5 \times (-0! + (-8 \times (3!! + (5^6)))))) \\ 653899 &:= (((9! \times 9)/(8 - 3)) - 5) + 6! \\ 653904 &:= (((((-4 + 0!) \times 9!) \times 3)/(-5)) + 6!) \\ 654336 &:= ((6^3!) - (3!! \times ((-4 - 5!) - 6!)) \\ 654574 &:= (4! - ((7! - 5) \times ((-4 - 5!) - 6))) \\ 654674 &:= (((-4 + 7!) \times ((6 + 4) + 5!)) - 6) \\ 654816 &:= (((6! + 1) \times 8) - 4!) \times (5! - 6) \\ 655195 &:= (-5 + ((915 - 5) \times 6!)) \\ 655206 &:= (((6 + 0!)! \times ((2 \times 5) + 5!)) + 6) \\ 655207 &:= (7 \times (0! + (((2 \times 5) + 5!) \times 6!)) \\ 655355 &:= (-5 - ((5! \times ((3 + 5)^5))/(-6))) \\ 655386 &:= (((6! \times 8) - 3!) - 5) \times (5! - 6) \\ 655488 &:= -((8! - (-8 \times (4! - (5! \times (5 + 6!)))))) \\ 655738 &:= (-((8^3)) + ((7!/5!) \times (5^6))) \\ 656184 &:= (((-4 + ((8 - 1)!)) + 6!) \times (5! - 6)) \\ 656193 &:= ((39 \times ((1 + 6)^5)) + 6!) \\ 656245 &:= (-5 + (((4! \times 2) - 6) \times (5^6))) \\ 656412 &:= (2 \times ((-1 - (-4 \times 6!)) \times (5! - 6))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 656418 &:= ((8 - 1) \times (4! + (6 \times (5^6)))) \\ 656634 &:= (((4!/(-3)) \times 6!) \times (6 - 5!)) - 6) \\ 656664 &:= (-4 \times (((6! + 6!) \times (6 - 5!)) - 6)) \\ 656676 &:= (((6! + 7!) - 6) \times (-6 + 5!)) + 6! \\ 656684 &:= (-4 + (8 \times (6 + ((-6 + 5!) \times 6!))) \\ 656688 &:= -((8! - (8 \times (((6! + 6) \times 5!) + 6)))) \\ 656754 &:= (((-((4 - 5)) + 7!) + 6!) \times (5! - 6)) \\ 656755 &:= ((5! - 5) + ((7! + 6!) \times (5! - 6))) \\ 656760 &:= 6 + (5! - 6) \times (7! + 6! + 0!) \\ 656862 &:= (((2 + (6! \times 8)) \times (-6 + 5!)) - 6) \\ 656868 &:= (8 \times 6! + 8 - 6) \times (5! - 6) \\ 657324 &:= (((((4 + 2)! + 3!) + 7!) \times (5! - 6)) \\ 657336 &:= ((6^3!) + ((3!! + 7) \times (5! + 6!))) \\ 657384 &:= ((4! - (8!/3)) \times (7 - 56)) \\ 657438 &:= (8!/(3 + 4) + 7) \times (5! - 6) \\ 657459 &:= ((-((9^5)) - ((-((4 - 7)!))!)) \times (-5 + 6)) \\ 657468 &:= ((((-8 + 6!)/4) + 7!) \times (5! + 6)) \\ 657504 &:= -((((4 - 0!)!^5) - (((7 + 5)!/6!)) \\ 657888 &:= (8 + 8) \times (8! + 7 \times (5! - 6)) \\ 657936 &:= ((6^3!) - ((-9 - (7 \times 5!)) \times 6!)) \\ 658476 &:= (((-6 + 7!) + (4! \times 8)) \times (5! + 6)) \\ 658692 &:= (((2 \times 9) + (6! \times 8)) \times (5! - 6)) \\ 658935 &:= ((5 \times 3) \times ((9 + 8!) + (5 \times 6!)) \\ 658944 &:= ((4! \times (4! + 9)) \times ((-8 + 5!) + 6!)) \\ 659026 &:= (((6!^2) + 0!) + ((9 \times (5^6))) \\ 659484 &:= (-4 \times (((8! \times (-4)) + 9) - (5 \times 6!))) \\ 659568 &:= (8 + 6!) \times (-5! + 9 \times (5! - 6)) \\ 659619 &:= (9 \times ((1 + 6!) - ((9!/(-5)) + 6))) \\ 659628 &:= -((8! - (2 \times ((6! - (9^5)) \times (-6)))) \\ 659694 &:= (4! + ((9 \times (6! - (9!/(-5)))) + 6)) \\ 659727 &:= ((7 + 2) \times (7 + ((9!/5) + 6!)) \\ 659748 &:= (8! - ((-4 + 7!) \times ((-9 - 5!) + 6))) \\ 660237 &:= -(((7! + 3) - (((2 \times 06)!/6!)) \\ 660247 &:= (-7!) + (((4!/2)! + ((0! + 6)!)/6!)) \\ 661969 &:= (((9!/6) \times 9) + ((1 + 6)^6)) \\ 662155 &:= (-((5^5)) - ((-1 \times ((2 \times 6)!)/6!)) \\ 662255 &:= (-((55^2)) + (((2 \times 6)!/6!)) \\ 662373 &:= (((-((3^7)) - 3!!)) + (((2 \times 6)!/6!)) \\ 662785 &:= ((5^8) + ((7! + ((2 + 6)!)) \times 6)) \\ 662795 &:= (((-5 \times (9! - 7!)) + ((2 \times 6)!)/6!)) \\ 662832 &:= ((2 \times ((3 \times 8)^{-2+6})) - 6!) \\ 663432 &:= ((2 - 3!!) \times (-((((4 \times 3)!/6!)/6!))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 663444 &:= ((4! - (((4! + 4!)^3) + 6)) \times (-6)) \\ 663486 &:= (((6 \times 8) \times (4!^3)) - (66)) \\ 663488 &:= (8 \times (-8 + ((4!^{-3+6}) \times 6))) \\ 663543 &:= (-3 + (((4!^5)/(3! + 6)) - 6)) \\ 663544 &:= -((((4! - (4!^5))/(3! + 6)) + 6)) \\ 663549 &:= (-9 + (((4!^5)/(3! + 6)) + 6)) \\ 663552 &:= (((2 \times 5!)/5)^{-3+6}) \times 6 \\ 663558 &:= ((8 \times (((5!/5)^3) \times 6)) + 6) \\ 663824 &:= (((4! + 2) \times 8!) - ((3! + 6)!)/(-6!)) \\ 663832 &:= (((-2 \times 3!) - 8) + (((3! + 6)!/6!)) \\ 663846 &:= (-6!) + (((4 + 8)!/3!) + (6 - 6!)) \\ 664398 &:= ((893 \times (4! + 6!)) + 6) \\ 664488 &:= ((-8 - ((8!/(-4)) + 4)) \times 66) \\ 664524 &:= ((42 + 5!) \times ((4^6) + 6)) \\ 664584 &:= (4! + (((((8 - 5) \times 4)!/6!) - 6!)) \\ 664758 &:= (((((8^5) - 7!) \times 4!) + 6) - 6!) \\ 664795 &:= (-5 + ((9! + ((7! - 4) \times 6!))/6)) \\ 664818 &:= ((-(8 - 1) + (8!/4)) \times 66) \\ 664884 &:= (((4! - 8!)/(-8 - 4)) \times 66) \\ 664887 &:= ((((-7 \times 8!) + ((8 + 4)! - 6!)/6!) \\ 664895 &:= (5! - ((9! - ((8 + 4)! + 6!)/6!)) \\ 664937 &:= (-((7^3)) + ((9! + ((4 + 6)!)/6)) \\ 664992 &:= (2 \times ((9 \times 9) \times (4^6) + 6!)) \\ 665155 &:= ((-5 - 5!) + (((1 + 5) + 6)!/6!)) \\ 665199 &:= (-((9 \times 9) + (((1 + 5) + 6)!/6!)) \\ 665218 &:= (-8! + 12!)/(5! \times 6) - 6 \\ 665224 &:= (((4 \times 2)! - (((-(2 - 5))! + 6)!)/(-6!)) \\ 665248 &:= (((8 + 4)! + (-((2^5) \times 6!)/6!) \\ 665255 &:= (-((5 \times 5) + (((-(2 - 5))! + 6)!/6!)) \\ 665259 &:= (((9! - 5!) + ((2 \times 5)! - 6)/6) \\ 665267 &:= (((7! - ((6 \times 2)!)/5!)/(-6)) - 6) \\ 665269 &:= (((9! - ((6/2)!)) \times (-5 + 6))/(-6)) \\ 665273 &:= (((3! \times 7) - (((-(2 - 5))! + 6)!)/(-6!)) \\ 665274 &:= (((4 + 7)!/(2 \times 5) \times 6) - 6) \\ 665275 &:= (-5 + (7! \times (2 \times ((5 + 6) \times 6)))) \\ 665279 &:= (((((9 - 7) + (2 \times 5))! - 6!)/6!) \\ 665292 &:= ((2 \times ((9 + 2)!)/5! + (6 + 6)) \\ 665293 &:= (((((3 + 9)! + ((2 + 5)!)/6!) + 6) \\ 665299 &:= (((9! \times (-9 + 2)) - 5! + 6)/(-6)) \\ 665304 &:= (4! + (((((0 - 3) + 5) \times 6)!/6!)) \\ 665321 &:= (((12)!/3!) + (5 + (6 \times 6))) \\ 665328 &:= ((8 + ((-2 \times ((3! + 5)!)/(-6!))) \times 6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 665334 &:= (((4 \times 3)!/3!) + (5! - 66)) \\ 665336 &:= (((6 + 6)! + (((5 - 3)^3)!)/6!) \\ 665352 &:= (2 \times (((5 + 3)!/5!) + (6 \times 6))) \\ 665357 &:= ((-(((7 + 5)! - ((3! + 5)!/6!))/(-6!)) \\ 665395 &:= (-5 + (((9 + 3)!/5! + 6!)/6)) \\ 665424 &:= (((4!/2)! + ((4! + 5!) \times 6!)/6!) \\ 665544 &:= (44 \times (((5! \times 5!) + 6) + 6!)) \\ 665744 &:= (-((4^4)) + (((7 + 5)!/6!) + 6!)) \\ 665754 &:= ((4 \times 5!) + (((7 + 5)!/6!) - 6)) \\ 665995 &:= ((-5 + 9!) + (((9! \times 5)/6) + 6!)) \\ 666024 &:= (4! + (((2 \times 06)!/6!) + 6!)) \\ 666072 &:= (2 \times ((7! - (0 - 6)) \times 66)) \\ 666304 &:= ((4^{-0!+3!}) + (((6 + 6)!/6!)) \\ 666359 &:= ((9 \times 5!) - ((3! - ((6 + 6)!)/6!)) \\ 666624 &:= (((4! \times ((2 + 6)!)) + ((6 + 6)!)/6!) \\ 666732 &:= (2 \times (3! + ((7! \times 66) + 6!)) \\ 666792 &:= (2 \times (9! + ((7! - 6) \times (-6)) + 6!)) \\ 666864 &:= ((4! - (6! \times (-8 + 6))) \times 66) \\ 667457 &:= (-7 + ((5! + 4) \times ((7! + 6!) + 6))) \\ 667524 &:= ((4! - (2 \times (-5 - 7!))) \times 66) \\ 667872 &:= (2 \times (((7 \times 8!) + 7!) + (6^6))) \\ 668144 &:= ((4 \times 4) \times (((-1 + 8!) + 6!) + 6!)) \\ 668154 &:= (((4 - 5!) \times (-1 \times 8)) \times 6!) - 6) \\ 668304 &:= ((4! \times (0! + 38)) \times (6! - 6)) \\ 668448 &:= (((8!/4) + (48)) \times 66) \\ 668955 &:= ((5 - 5!) \times (-9 - (8 \times (6! + 6)))) \\ 670321 &:= (((12)!/3!) + (0! + (7 \times 6!)) \\ 670326 &:= (((6 \times 2)!/3!) - ((0 - 7!) - 6)) \\ 670327 &:= (7! + (((2 \times 3)! \times (-0!)) - 7!)/(-6!)) \\ 670459 &:= (((9 + 5!) + 4) \times (0! + 7!)) + 6) \\ 672744 &:= (4! \times (-((47^2)) + (7! \times 6))) \\ 672885 &:= ((5^8) + (((8! + 2) \times 7) + 6)) \\ 672945 &:= (-5 \times (((4!)/((9 \times 2)! - 7!)/(-6!)) \\ 673056 &:= ((6^5) + (((0! - 3!) - 7)!/6!)) \\ 673195 &:= (-5 + (((9! \times 13)/7) - 6!)) \\ 673344 &:= -((4! \times (4! - (3 \times ((3! + 7) \times 6!)))) \\ 673548 &:= -((8! - ((-4 - 5!) \times ((3 - 7!) - 6!))) \\ 673569 &:= ((-((9 - 6) + 5!) \times ((-3 + 7!) + 6!)) \\ 673585 &:= ((5^8) + (((5 + 3)! \times 7) + 6!)) \\ 673647 &:= ((-7 + (4! \times 6!)) \times (3 \times (7 + 6))) \\ 673915 &:= (-5 - ((1 - 937) \times 6!)) \\ 673919 &:= ((9! - 1) + (((9! \times 3!)/7!) \times 6!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 673932 &:= (2 \times ((3! + 9!) - (3! \times (7! - 6!)))) \\ 673944 &:= (4! + ((4! + (93)) \times (7! + 6!))) \\ 673968 &:= (8 \times (((6! \times 9) \times (3! + 7)) + 6)) \\ 673985 &:= ((-5 - ((8 \times 9) \times 3!)) \times (-7 + 6)) \\ 674472 &:= ((2 \times (7! + (4!^4))) - (7! / (-6))) \\ 674556 &:= (((-6 + 5!) + ((5 \times 4))) \times (7! - 6)) \\ 674645 &:= ((5! / 4!) \times ((6! \times 4!) + ((7^6)))) \\ 674685 &:= (-5 \times (-8 - ((6! \times 4!) + ((7^6)))) \\ 674688 &:= ((8! \times (((-8 + 6!) \times 4!) - 7!)) / 6!) \\ 674896 &:= ((6! + 9!) + ((8^4) \times 76)) \\ 675276 &:= (6! + (((7 \times 2) + 5!) \times (7! - 6))) \\ 675354 &:= (((4 + ((5^3) + 5)) \times 7!) - 6) \\ 675365 &:= ((5! \times (6! + 3!)) + ((5 \times (7^6)))) \\ 675372 &:= ((2 \times (7! + 3!)) + (((5 + 7)! / 6!)) \\ 675384 &:= (4! - ((((-8 - 3!) - 5!) \times 7) \times 6!)) \\ 675575 &:= (-(((5^7) / 5)) + (5! \times (7! + 6!))) \\ 675672 &:= ((-((2 - ((7^6) + 5))) - 7!) \times 6) \\ 675677 &:= (-7 - ((-(((7^6) + 5)) + 7!) \times 6)) \\ 677948 &:= -8 + 4 \times (9! / 7 + 7^6) \\ 678056 &:= -((6! + (((5! - 0!) \times (-8)) \times (-7 + 6!)))) \\ 678246 &:= (-6 \times (((4!^2) \times 8) - ((7^6)))) \\ 678594 &:= -((((4! - 9) \times ((5! - 8!) - 7!)) + 6)) \\ 679488 &:= ((8 \times (8! - 4!)) + ((9! - 7!) - 6!)) \\ 679687 &:= (((7! + 8!) \times (6 + 9)) + 7) - 6! \\ 679692 &:= ((2 \times (9! + 6)) - ((9 \times 7!) + 6!)) \\ 679785 &:= (((5! / 8) \times ((7! \times 9) + 7)) - 6!) \\ 680394 &:= (((4! - 9) \times (((3! + 0!)! + 8!)) - 6) \\ 680397 &:= ((7! \times (-9)) + (-3 \times (0! + (8! \times (-6)))) \\ 680832 &:= (2 \times (((3!^8) + ((0! + 8)!)) / 6)) \\ 681696 &:= (-6 \times (((9! / (-6 - 1)) - 8!) - 6!)) \\ 682584 &:= ((4 - (8 \times 5!)) \times (-((2 - 8)) - 6!)) \\ 682925 &:= ((5^{-2+9}) + (((2 + 8)! / 6)) \\ 683064 &:= ((4 - 6!) \times (((-((0! - 3!)))! \times (-8)) + 6)) \\ 683298 &:= (-((8 + 9)) \times (((2 + 3)! - 8!) + 6)) \\ 683518 &:= ((8 \times (-1 - (-5!) \times (3!! - 8)))) + 6) \\ 683538 &:= ((-8 + 3!!) \times 5! + 3) \times 8 - 6 \\ 683544 &:= (4! - (((4! \times 5!) / (-3)) \times (-8 + 6!))) \\ 683568 &:= (((8 \times (6^5)) \times (3 + 8)) - 6!) \\ 683598 &:= ((8 \times (9 - (-5!) \times (3!! - 8)))) + 6) \\ 683755 &:= (-5 + (5! \times (((-7 + 3!!) \times 8) - 6))) \\ 683985 &:= (-5 \times (((8 - 9!) \times (-3)) / (-8)) - 6!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 684648 &:= (8! - 4) \times (-6 + 4!) - 8! - 6! \\ 684672 &:= (((-2 + (7! \times 6)) \times 4!) - (8! + 6!)) \\ 684713 &:= -(((3! + 1) + (((7 - 4!) \times 8!) + 6!)) \\ 684714 &:= -((((4 - 1)! + (((7 - 4!) \times 8!) + 6!)) \\ 684715 &:= -6! + 8! \times (4! - 7) \times 1 - 5 \\ 684721 &:= ((1^2) - (((7 - 4!) \times 8!) + 6!)) \\ 684723 &:= ((3! / 2) - (((7 - 4!) \times 8!) + 6!)) \\ 684726 &:= (((6 / 2)! - (((7 - 4!) \times 8!) + 6!)) \\ 684732 &:= ((2 \times 3!) - (((7 - 4!) \times 8!) + 6!)) \\ 684735 &:= ((5 \times 3) - (((7 - 4!) \times 8!) + 6!)) \\ 684742 &:= ((-2 + 4!) - (((7 - 4!) \times 8!) + 6!)) \\ 684748 &:= (((((8! \times 4) + 7) \times 4) + 8!) - 6!) \\ 684752 &:= ((2^5) - (((7 - 4!) \times 8!) + 6!)) \\ 684768 &:= ((8 \times 6) - (((7 - 4!) \times 8!) + 6!)) \\ 684771 &:= ((-17) \times (-((7 - 4) - 8!)) - 6!) \\ 684848 &:= (((8! \times 4) + (8 \times (4^8))) - 6!) \\ 684952 &:= ((2 \times ((5! + 9!) - 4)) - (8! + 6!)) \\ 684963 &:= ((-((3 - 6)^9) + (((4 + 8)! / 6!)) \\ 684968 &:= (((-8 - 6!) - 9!) + ((4 \times (8^6)))) \\ 685072 &:= (2 \times (((7! - 0!) \times 5!) - (8^6)) \\ 685192 &:= ((2 \times ((9! - 1) - 5!)) - (8! + 6)) \\ 685198 &:= -((8! - (((9! - 1) - 5!) \times (8 - 6)))) \\ 685253 &:= (((3 \times 5) + 2) \times ((-5 + 8!) - 6)) \\ 685298 &:= (-8 + 9!) \times 2 - 5! - 8! - 6 \\ 685312 &:= (2 \times (((1 + 3!)! \times 5!) - (8^6)) \\ 685329 &:= (((((9! \times 2) + 3) - 5!) - 8!) + 6) \\ 685334 &:= (-4 + (((3! + 3!) + 5) \times (8! - 6)) \\ 685338 &:= ((8! - 3!) \times (((3 \times 5) + 8) - 6)) \\ 685349 &:= (((9 + (4! / 3)) \times (-5 + 8!)) - 6) \\ 685361 &:= ((-((1 - (6 \times 3))) \times (-5 + 8!)) + 6) \\ 685385 &:= (((-5 + 8!) \times (3! + 5)) - (8! \times (-6))) \\ 685391 &:= ((-1 + 9!) + ((3 + 5) \times (8! - 6))) \\ 685392 &:= (((2 \times 9!) - ((3 + 5)! - ((8 \times 6))) \\ 685427 &:= (-7 - (((-2 \times ((4 + 5)! + 8!) + 6)) \\ 685428 &:= 8! + 2 \times ((4 + 5)! - 8! - 6) \\ 685429 &:= (((9! \times (-2 - 4)) - 5) - 8!) - 6) \\ 685432 &:= (-2 - (((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times 8!) + 6)) \\ 685434 &:= (((4 + (3^4)) / 5) \times 8!) - 6) \\ 685435 &:= (-5 + (((3 - 4) + 5!) \times 8) \times 6!) \\ 685438 &:= ((8! \times ((3 \times 4) + 5)) - (8 - 6)) \\ 685439 &:= ((9! \times (3! - 4)) + ((5 - 8!) - 6)) \\ 685464 &:= (4! + ((6! + ((4 \times 58))) \times 6!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 685476 &:= ((6 \times ((7! \times 4!) + 5)) - (8! - 6)) \\ 685488 &:= ((8! \times ((8 + 4) + 5)) + ((8 \times 6))) \\ 685492 &:= ((2 \times ((9! + 4!) + 5)) - (8! + 6)) \\ 685498 &:= -((8! - (((9! + 4!) + 5) \times (8 - 6)))) \\ 685542 &:= ((2 + ((4 \times 5) - 5)) \times (8! + 6)) \\ 685627 &:= ((-7 + (-((2 - 6)))!) \times ((5 + 8!) + 6)) \\ 685638 &:= -((8! + (3 \times ((-((6 + 5)) - 8!) \times 6)))) \\ 685728 &:= ((((((8 + 2)!) + 7!)/5) - 8!) - 6!) \\ 685848 &:= ((8! + 4!) \times (((8 - 5) + 8) + 6)) \\ 685926 &:= 6! + 2 \times (9! - 5!) - 8! + 6 \\ 685932 &:= ((2 \times ((3! + 9!) - 5!)) - (8! - 6!)) \\ 685934 &:= (((4 - 3!!) \times (-958)) + 6) \\ 686128 &:= (((8! - 2) \times 16) + 8!) + 6! \\ 686152 &:= (-2 - ((5! - 1) \times ((6! \times (-8)) - 6))) \\ 686154 &:= (((4! \times 5) - 1) \times ((6! \times 8) + 6)) \\ 686155 &:= (-5 - (((5! - 1) \times 6!) \times (-8)) - 6!) \\ 686184 &:= (4! - (((8! \times (-16)) - 8!) - 6!)) \\ 686192 &:= ((2 \times (9! + (16))) - (8! - 6!)) \\ 686368 &:= ((-8 + 6!) \times (((-3 - 6!) \times (-8))/6)) \\ 686752 &:= (2 \times (((5! \times 7!) + 6!) - (8^6))) \\ 686928 &:= -((8! - ((2 \times (9! + 6!)) + (8 \times 6)))) \\ 687232 &:= (((2^{3!})^2 - 7!) \times (-8 - 6!)) \\ 688344 &:= (4! + ((-4 + ((-((3 - 8)))! \times 8)) \times 6!)) \\ 688448 &:= (8! - (-4 \times ((-4 \times (-8 - 8!)) + 6!))) \\ 688559 &:= ((9! + ((5^5))) - ((-8 \times 8!) + 6)) \\ 689544 &:= -((((4! \times 4!) - (5! \times (-9 + (8 \times 6!)))))) \\ 690504 &:= (4! - ((0! + (5! \times (0! - 9))) \times 6!)) \\ 691344 &:= (4! \times (((-4 \times 3!!) \times (-1 + 9))) + 6)) \\ 691358 &:= ((8 \times ((5! \times 3!!) + (19))) + 6) \\ 691856 &:= (((6! \times 5!) - 8) \times (-1 - 9)) + 6! \\ 691968 &:= ((-8 - (6! \times (9 + 1))) \times (-96)) \\ 692586 &:= ((6! \times ((8 \times 5!) + 2)) - (9 \times 6)) \\ 692646 &:= ((6! \times (-46)) - ((-2 \times 9!) - 6)) \\ 692658 &:= (((8 \times 5!) \times 6!) + (2 \times (9 + 6!))) \\ 692723 &:= ((32 \times 7!) + (2 + (9^6))) \\ 692991 &:= (((-1 + 9!) + 9!) - (2^{9+6})) \\ 693091 &:= (((1 + 90)^3) - (9!/6)) \\ 694008 &:= (8 \times ((0! - ((0! + 4)!)) \times (-9 - 6!))) \\ 694644 &:= (((((4!^4) + 6) - 4!) + 9!) + 6) \\ 694645 &:= ((-((5 - ((4 \times 6)^4))) + 9!) - 6) \\ 694662 &:= (((2 \times (6 + 6))^4 + 9!) + 6) \\ 694795 &:= (-5 + ((974 - 9) \times 6!)) \\ 695514 &:= (((-((4 - 15)))! / 5!) + ((9! - 6))) \\ 695532 &:= (-2 \times (((3! + 5!) \times 5!) - 9!) - 6) \\ 695568 &:= (8 \times (((6! + 5) \times 5!) + ((9 \times 6))) \\ 696252 &:= ((-2 \times (((5!^2) - 6) - 9!)) - 6!) \\ 697568 &:= (8 \times ((6! \times 5!) + 796)) \\ 697728 &:= (8! - (-((2^7) \times (7! + 96))) \\ 698382 &:= ((-2 + (((8 - 3)!) \times 8)) \times (9 + 6!)) \\ 698468 &:= (((8! + 6!) + 4) \times (8 + 9)) + 6! \\ 698724 &:= (((4! - (2^7)) \times (8! - 9)) / (-6)) \\ 698865 &:= ((5! \times ((6! + 8) \times 8)) - (9 + 6)) \\ 699336 &:= (((6^3!) \times (3! + 9)) - (9!/6!)) \\ 699475 &:= (-((5^7)) + ((-((4 - 9)))! \times (9 \times 6!))) \\ 699624 &:= ((4 - ((2 \times 6!) \times 9)) \times (-9 \times 6)) \\ 699795 &:= ((-5 \times (9 + 7!)) + ((9! + 9!) - 6!)) \\ 699834 &:= ((((-4 \times 3!!) + 8!) \times 9) + ((9! - 6))) \\ 699948 &:= ((8 + 4) \times (9 - (-((9 \times 9) \times 6!))) \\ 702237 &:= (((7!/3!) - 2)^2) + (0 - 7) \\ 702583 &:= ((-3 \times 8!) + ((5 + 2)^{07})) \\ 703125 &:= (((5 \times 2) - 1) \times ((3! - 0!)^7)) \\ 703179 &:= (9 \times ((7 - 1) + ((3! - 0!)^7))) \\ 703965 &:= ((5! + 6!) - (-9 \times ((3! - 0!)^7))) \\ 704487 &:= (((7! - 8) \times (4! - 4)) + 0!) \times 7 \\ 704969 &:= ((9 - (6! / (-9)))^{-4+07}) \\ 705455 &:= (-5 - ((5! + ((4 \times 5))) \times (0! - 7!))) \\ 705565 &:= (((5! + 6!) \times 5!) - 5) \times 07 \\ 705593 &:= (((((-((3 - 9)))! + 5!) \times (-5!)) + 0!) \times (-7)) \\ 705594 &:= (((49 \times 5!) \times 5!) + 0!) - 7 \\ 705607 &:= (((7! / (0 - 6)) \times 5!) - 0!) \times (-7) \\ 705764 &:= (-4 \times (-6 + (-((7 \times 5)) \times (0! + 7!)))) \\ 705775 &:= -((5 \times 7) \times (7! - (5 \times (0! + 7!)))) \\ 705894 &:= (-((49^{8-5})) \times (0! - 7)) \\ 708165 &:= ((-((5^{6+1})) \times (-8 - 0!)) + 7!) \\ 708336 &:= ((6 \times 3!) \times ((3^{8+0!}) - 7)) \\ 709512 &:= ((21 + 5!) \times ((-9 + 0!) + 7!)) \\ 710676 &:= (((6 - (7! / (-6)))^{0!+1}) - 7!) \\ 710709 &:= (9! - ((0! - 70) \times (1 + 7!))) \\ 712836 &:= ((6 \times 3) \times ((8! + 2) - (-((1 - 7)!))) \\ 714968 &:= ((-8 \times (6! - ((9!/4) + 1))) - 7!) \\ 715392 &:= (2 \times (9! - ((3! \times ((5 - 1)!)) + 7!))) \\ 715537 &:= -7! + (3!! - 5) / 5 \times (-1 + 7!) \\ 715538 &:= ((-8 + (3! \times (5 \times 5))) \times (-1 + 7!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}715632 &:= (2 \times (((3+6)! - ((5-1)!) - 7!)) \\715675 &:= ((-5-7!) + (((6!/5) - 1) \times 7!)) \\715682 &:= (2 \times (((((8+6) - 5)!) + 1) - 7!)) \\715692 &:= (2 \times (9! + ((6!/5!) - ((1 \times 7)!)!)) \\715792 &:= ((2 \times (9! - 7!)) + (5! - (1+7))) \\715822 &:= ((2 + (28 \times 5)) \times (1+7!)) \\715932 &:= (2 \times (((3!+9!) + 5!) - ((1 \times 7)!)!)) \\716297 &:= (((7! - 9!) \times (-2)) + (617)) \\716399 &:= ((9! + 9!) - ((3! \times 6!) + 1) + 7!)) \\716532 &:= ((-2 - (3!/(-5))) \times (6 + ((1 \times 7)!)!)) \\718563 &:= ((3 \times ((-6 \times (5! - 8!)) + 1)) - 7!) \\719275 &:= ((-5-7!) - (2 \times (-9!) + (-((1-7)!)!))) \\719282 &:= ((-2 \times (((8-2)!) - 9!) - 1)) - 7!) \\719286 &:= (((6! - (8! \times 2)) \times (-9)) - ((1-7))) \\719296 &:= ((6! \times (-9)) - (-2 \times (9! + (1+7)))) \\719829 &:= (((9! \times 2) - (891)) - 7!) \\719983 &:= ((3! \times (-8)) + (((9! + 9!) - (17)))) \\719993 &:= ((3! \times (9 + 991)) - 7) \\719995 &:= (((-5+9!) + 9!) + (((9-1)!) / (-7))) \\720432 &:= (-2 - (((3! \times 4!) - 0!) \times (2-7))) \\720434 &:= (((4! \times 3!) - ((4 \times 0)!) \times (-2+7!)) \\720599 &:= (((9! + 9!) - 5!) - ((0 \times 2)!) - 7!) \\720648 &:= (8! - 4) \times 6 \times (0! + 2) - 7! \\720692 &:= ((2 \times (9! - ((6+0!) \times 2))) - 7!) \\720694 &:= -((4! + (((9! - ((6 \times 0)!) \times (-2)) + 7!))) \\720696 &:= (((6-9!) + 6) \times (0-2)) - 7!) \\720698 &:= -8 + (9! - 6 - 0!) \times 2 - 7! \\720699 &:= (-9 - (((9! - 6) \times (0-2)) + 7!)) \\720708 &:= (((((8+0)!)! - (7-0!)) \times 2) - 7!) \\720715 &:= (-5 + (((((1+7) + 0)!)! \times 2) - 7!)) \\720718 &:= ((((((8+1)!) - 7!) - 0!) \times 2) + 7!) \\720727 &:= (7 - ((-2 \times ((7+02)!) + 7!)) \\720732 &:= ((2 \times (3! + ((7+02)!)!)) - 7!) \\720736 &:= ((((((6+3)!) + 7) + 0!) \times 2) - 7!) \\720744 &:= (((4 + (4! \times 7!)) \times ((0! + 2)!) - 7!) \\720756 &:= ((((((6! + 5!) + 7) - 0!)^2) + 7!) \\720792 &:= (((2 \times 9!) + ((70+2))) - 7!) \\720864 &:= ((4! \times 6) + (((8+0)!)! \times 2) - 7!) \\720898 &:= (((89 + ((8+0)!)!) \times 2) - 7!) \\720936 &:= ((6^3) - ((9! \times (0-2)) + 7!)) \\720954 &:= (((((-4+5!) + 9!) + 0!) \times 2) - 7!) \\720955 &:= (-5 + (((5! + 9!) \times 02) - 7!))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}720956 &:= (-6 + (((5! + 9!) + 0!) \times 2) - 7!)) \\721392 &:= (2 \times (9! - (312 \times 7))) \\722165 &:= ((-5 \times (6! - 1)) + (2 \times ((2+7)!)!)) \\722304 &:= ((4! \times (0-3!)) \times (((2+2)!) - 7!)) \\722385 &:= -((((5!/8)^3) - (2 \times ((2+7)!)!)) \\722736 &:= ((6! - 3) \times ((72 \times 2) \times 7)) \\723319 &:= ((91^3) - (3! \times (2+7!))) \\723456 &:= ((6!/5) \times (((4!/3) \times (-2)) + 7!)) \\723492 &:= ((2 \times 9!) - (((4! - 3!)^2) \times 7)) \\723529 &:= (((9! \times 2) + ((53^2))) - 7!) \\723573 &:= (-((3^7)) - (-((5-3) \times ((2+7)!)!)) \\723586 &:= ((-6 \times ((8! - 5!) \times (-3))) - ((2 \times 7))) \\723593 &:= (((3! - (9! + (5! \times (-3)))) \times (-2)) - 7) \\723595 &:= (-5 - (((9! - (5 \times 3!)) \times (-2)) - 7!)) \\723599 &:= (((9! - ((9 \times 5!) - 3)) \times 2) - 7) \\723744 &:= (-((4! - (4! \times 7))) \times ((3! - 2) \times 7)) \\723789 &:= -((9! - ((8! - 73) \times 27))) \\723852 &:= (2 \times (((5! \times (-8)) + 3!) + ((2+7)!)!)) \\723859 &:= (((9! + ((5! \times (-8)) + 3!)) \times 2) + 7) \\723952 &:= ((2 \times (-((5! - 9!) - 3!)) - (2^7)) \\723953 &:= ((-3 \times 5!) + (((9! - 3!)) \times 2) - 7) \\723958 &:= (((8 \times ((5 \times 9)^3)) - 2) - 7!) \\724192 &:= ((2 \times (9! - (-((1-4)!)!)) - (2^7)) \\724269 &:= (((9! - 6!) \times 2) - 4!) - (27) \\724292 &:= (2 \times ((9! - ((2+4)!) - ((2 \times 7))) \\724293 &:= (((3! - 9!) \times (2-4)) - 27) \\724312 &:= (2 \times ((-1 \times 3!) + (-4 + ((2+7)!)!)) \\724313 &:= (((3! - (((13-4)!) \times (-2)) - 7) \\724319 &:= ((((-9!) + (((1 \times 3)!)!)) + 4) \times (-2)) + 7) \\724332 &:= (2 \times ((3! - 3!) + (((4^2) - 7)!)!)) \\724339 &:= (((-((9! + 3!)) + 3!) \times (-4-2)) + 7) \\724362 &:= (-2 \times (((6! + 3) - 4!) - ((2+7)!)!)) \\724368 &:= (8-6) \times (-3! + 4! + (2+7)!) \\724369 &:= (((9! - 6!) - 3) + 4!) \times 2 + 7) \\724392 &:= (((2 \times 9!) - 3!) - (4! \times 27)) \\724495 &:= -((5! + (((9! - (4! \times 4!)) \times (-2)) - 7))) \\724512 &:= (2 \times ((1 - (5^4)) + ((2+7)!)!)) \\724519 &:= (((9! + ((1 - (5^4)))) \times 2) + 7) \\724552 &:= (2 \times (((5! \times (-5)) - 4) + ((2+7)!)!)) \\724553 &:= (((3! - ((5! + ((5+4)!)!)) \times (-2)) - 7) \\724559 &:= (((9! - ((5! \times 5) + 4)) \times 2) + 7) \\724599 &:= (9 \times ((-9-5!) - (-((4^2) \times 7!)))\end{aligned}$$

- 724608 := ((8 - ((0! + 6)!)) × (-4!) - (-((2 - 7)!))!))
724729 := (((9! - ((2⁷) × 4)) × 2) - 7)
724752 := (((((2 × 5)! - 7!)/(-((4 - 2) - 7)))
724766 := (((((-6 - 6!) + 7!) × 4!) + 2) × 7)
724773 := (3 × (((7 - 7!) × 4!) × (-2)) + 7))
724792 := ((2 × 9!) - (((7 + 4!)²) + 7))
724836 := (-6 × ((-3 × 8!) + ((4! - 2) × 7)))
724896 := (((6 × 9!) × ((8!/4!) - 2))/7!)
724935 := ((-5!) - 3!!) - (((9! + 4) × (-2)) - 7))
724975 := ((5! × (-7)) - (((9! + 4!) × (-2)) - 7))
724983 := -((3!! + (((8 - 9!) + 4!) × 2) - 7))
724985 := -((((-(5 - 8)))! + ((9! - 4!) × (-2)) + 7)))
725013 := -((3!! + (((10)!/(-5)) + (27))))
725016 := -((6! + (((10)! - 5!)/(2 - 7)))
725026 := (-6!) - (-2 × ((-((0! - (5 × 2))))! - 7))
725033 := -((3!! - (((((3 + 0!) + 5)! × 2) - 7)))
725039 := (((9! + (3 × (0! - 5!))) × 2) - 7)
725184 := (4! × ((8! - (-((1 - 5))))!) + (-2 × 7!))
725229 := (((9! - 2) × 2) - 527)
725233 := (((3 × 3)!) × 2) - 527)
725238 := (-((8³)) - (2 × (5 - ((2 + 7)!)))
725239 := (((9! + 3) × 2) - 527)
725273 := -((3!! + (((((7 + 2)! + 5!) × (-2)) + 7)))
725289 := (((9! + 8) - (2 × 5!)) × 2) - 7)
725293 := (((3 + 9!) - (2 × 5!)) × 2) + 7)
725294 := ((-4 × ((9!/(-2)) + 5!)) + ((2 × 7)))
725304 := -((4! × (0! - (3! × (-((5 - 2) + 7))))))
725326 := -((6! + 2) + ((3!!/(-5)) × (-2 - 7!))
725328 := (((8/2)!) × 3!) × (-((5 - 2) + 7!))
725337 := (((-((7! - 3)) × 3!)/(-5)) + (2 + 7))
725351 := ((-1 - 5!) - ((3!!/(-5)) × (-2 + 7!))
725393 := ((3! × ((9!/3) + (5!/(-2)))) - 7)
725395 := (((5! - 9!) × (-3)) - 5) - ((2 + 7)!)
725396 := (((-6 × 9!)/(-3)) - ((52 × 7)))
725399 := ((9! + 9!) + ((3 - (52 × 7))))
725403 := (3 × (0! - (4! × (5 + (-2 × 7))))))
725424 := ((4! × (-2)) - ((4! + 5!) × (2 - 7!))
725436 := ((-6 × 3!) - ((4! + 5!) × (2 - 7!))
725444 := ((-4 - 4!) - ((4! + 5!) × (2 - 7!))
725448 := -((((8 - 4)! + ((4! + 5!) × (2 - 7))))
725462 := (2 × (((-6 × 4!) - 5) + ((2 + 7)!))
725463 := (-((3 + 6)) - ((4! + 5!) × (2 - 7!))
725466 := (-6 × (((6! × 4!) - (5 + 2)) × (-7)))
725469 := (((9! - ((6 × 4!) + 5)) × 2) + 7)
725471 := (-((1⁷)) - ((4! + 5!) × (2 - 7!))
725472 := (((-2 + 7!) × 4!) × (((5 × 2) - 7)!))
725473 := -(((3! - 7) + ((4! + 5!) × (2 - 7!)))
725479 := (((((9! + 7) - 4!) - 5!) × 2) - 7)
725489 := (9! - 8 - 4 - 5!) × 2 - 7
725491 := (19 - ((4! + 5!) × (2 - 7!))
725492 := (2 × (9! - ((4! × 5) + ((2 × 7))))
725493 := (((((3! - 9!) + 4) + 5!) × (-2)) - 7)
725495 := (((((-5 + 9!) - 4) - 5!) × 2) - 7)
725499 := ((9! + 9!) - ((4! + 5) × (2 + 7)))
725512 := (2 × (((1 - 5!) - 5) + ((2 + 7)!))
725513 := ((((((3 + 1) + 5)! - 5!) × 2) - 7)
725523 := ((3²)! - 5! + 5) × 2 - 7
725532 := (2 × ((3!!/5!) - (5! - ((2 + 7)!)))
725539 := (((9! - ((3!!/(-5!)) + 5!)) × 2) + 7)
725544 := (4! × (-((4 + 5) + (((5 - 2)! × 7!)))
725592 := (2 × (9! - ((5 + 5) + 2) × 7))
725598 := ((8! - 9) × ((5 + ((5 - 2)! + 7)))
725599 := ((9! + 9!) - (((5 × 5) - 2) × 7))
725607 := (((7! - 0!) × 6!)/5) - (2 + 7)
725616 := ((6! - (-((1 - 6) - 5)))!)/(2 - 7)
725622 := (2 × (-((2⁶) + 5) + ((2 + 7)!))
725623 := (((((3²)! - 65) × 2) - 7)
725625 := (((((5 × 2)! - 6!)/5) + (2 + 7))
725629 := (((9! × 2) - 6) - 5!) + (2 - 7)
725632 := ((2 × ((3 + (6!/5!)))! - (2⁷))
725634 := ((4! - 3!) × (((6!/5!) + 2)! - 7))
725639 := (9! + (((3!/(-6)) - 5!) + ((2 + 7)!))
725672 := (2 × ((76 - 5!) + ((2 + 7)!))
725689 := (((9! - ((8 - 6)⁵)) × 2) - 7)
725691 := ((((-1 + 9!) - ((6 × 5))) × 2) - 7)
725692 := ((2 × (9! + ((6 × 5)))) - (2⁷))
725693 := ((3! × (((9!/6) - 5) × 2)) - 7)
725699 := (((9! + 9!) + 6) - ((5!/2) + 7))
725712 := (-2 × ((-(((1⁷) - 5)))! - (((2 + 7)!)))
725718 := (((8 + 1)! - ((7!/5!) - ((2 + 7)!))
725719 := ((9! + 1) - ((7!/5!) - ((2 + 7)!))
725722 := (2 × (((2 + 7)! - (5 + (2 × 7))))
725725 := (-5 × (((((2 + 7)!/(-5)) × 2) + 7))
725728 := (-8 - (2 × ((7 + 5) - ((2 + 7)!)))

$$\begin{aligned} 725729 &:= ((9! \times 2) - (((7 + 5) \times 2) + 7)) \\ 725732 &:= (2 \times (((3^{7-5})!) - ((2 \times 7)))) \\ 725733 &:= (((3 \times 3)!) \times (7 - 5)) - (27) \\ 725735 &:= (((5 - ((3 + 7)!) + 5!)/(2 - 7)) \\ 725736 &:= (((((6 - 3) + 7)!) - 5!)/(-2 - 7)) \\ 725738 &:= -8 + (3 + 7)!/5 - 2 \times 7 \\ 725739 &:= (((9! - 3!) \times (7 - 5)) - (2 + 7)) \\ 725743 &:= (((3! \times 4!) \times 7!) - ((5 \times 2) + 7)) \\ 725744 &:= (-((4 \times 4)) - (-((7 - 5) \times ((2 + 7)!)!)) \\ 725746 &:= (((6 \times 4!) \times 7!) - ((5 + 2) + 7)) \\ 725748 &:= (-((8 + 4)) - (-((7 - 5) \times ((2 + 7)!)!)) \\ 725749 &:= (((9! + 4!) - (7 \times 5)) + ((2 + 7)!) \\ 725761 &:= (1 \times 6! \times 7! + 5)/(-2 + 7) \\ 725764 &:= 4! \times 6 \times 7! - 5 + 2 + 7 \\ 725773 &:= (((-3 - (((7 + 7) - 5)!) \times (-2)) + 7) \\ 725774 &:= ((4! \times 7!) + ((7! \times 5!) + ((2 \times 7)))) \\ 725778 &:= ((8! + (7/7)) \times ((5^2) - 7)) \\ 725784 &:= (4! + (8! \times ((7 - 5) \times (2 + 7)))) \\ 725789 &:= ((9 \times ((8! + (7 - 5) \times 2)) - 7) \\ 725791 &:= (((((1 \times 9)!) + (7 + 5)) \times 2) + 7) \\ 725792 &:= ((2 \times 9!) + (7 - (5 \times (2 - 7)))) \\ 725793 &:= (((3 + 9!) \times (7 - 5)) + (27)) \\ 725794 &:= (((4! + 9!) \times (7 - 5)) - ((2 \times 7))) \\ 725795 &:= (((5 + 9!) \times 7) - (5 \times ((2 + 7)!)!)) \\ 725796 &:= ((-6 + 9!) + ((7!/5!) + ((2 + 7)!)!)) \\ 725802 &:= (((2 + 0)!) \times ((8! \times (5 - 2)) + 7)) \\ 725809 &:= ((9! + ((0! + 8)!) + ((5 + 2) \times 7)) \\ 725814 &:= ((-((4 - 1) - 8!) \times (-((5^2) - 7))) \\ 725823 &:= ((3 - (2 \times (8! + 5))) \times (-2 + 7)) \\ 725829 &:= (((9! - ((2 - (8 \times 5)))) \times 2) - 7) \\ 725832 &:= (((2 - 3!) - 8!) \times (-((5^2) - 7)) \\ 725833 &:= (((((3 \times 3)!) + (8 \times 5)) \times 2) - 7) \\ 725836 &:= (((6 \times 3) \times (8! + 5)) - ((2 \times 7))) \\ 725842 &:= (2 \times (-4 + ((8! + 5) \times (2 + 7)))) \\ 725859 &:= (9! + 58 - 5) \times 2 - 7 \\ 725862 &:= (2 \times (6 + ((8! + 5) \times (2 + 7)))) \\ 725863 &:= ((3 \times ((6 \times (8! + 5)) + 2)) + 7) \\ 725864 &:= (-4 + ((6 + 8!) \times ((5^2) - 7))) \\ 725868 &:= ((8! + 6) \times (((8 + 5) - 2) + 7)) \\ 725878 &:= (-8 + ((7 + 8!) \times ((5^2) - 7))) \\ 725883 &:= (3 \times (((8 + 8!) \times ((5 - 2)!) - 7)) \\ 725889 &:= ((9 \times (8! + 8!)) + (5! + (2 + 7))) \\ 725892 &:= ((2 \times (9! + ((8 - 5)!)!) + (-((2 - 7)!)!)) \\ 725895 &:= ((5 \times 9!) + ((8! - 5) \times (-27))) \\ 725902 &:= (2 \times ((0! + 9!) + ((5 \times 2) \times 7))) \\ 725903 &:= (3!! + (0! + 9)! - 5)/(-2 + 7) \\ 725913 &:= (((3!! + (((1 + 9)!)!)/5) + (2 + 7)) \\ 725924 &:= (4! + (2 \times (9! + ((5 \times 2) \times 7)))) \\ 725925 &:= (5! + ((2 \times 9!) + (52 - 7))) \\ 725935 &:= (((5 - 3) \times 9!) + ((5^2) \times 7)) \\ 725939 &:= (((9! - ((3 \times 9))) + 5!) \times 2) - 7) \\ 725942 &:= (2 \times (-((4 - 95)) + ((2 + 7)!)!)) \\ 725943 &:= ((3!!/4) - (((9! + 5) \times (-2)) + 7)) \\ 725945 &:= (5! - (((4! + 9!) + 5) \times (-2)) - 7)) \\ 725946 &:= ((6 - 4) \times ((9! + 5!) - (27))) \\ 725947 &:= (((((7!/4!) + 9!) - 5!) \times 2) + 7) \\ 725949 &:= (((9! - ((4 - 95))) \times 2) + 7) \\ 725952 &:= (2 \times ((5! - ((9 - 5)!) + ((2 + 7)!)!)) \\ 725959 &:= (((9! + 5!) - ((9 - 5)!) \times 2) + 7) \\ 725961 &:= (((16 - 9!) - 5!) \times (-2)) - 7) \\ 725962 &:= (2 \times ((6 + 95) + ((2 + 7)!)!)) \\ 725967 &:= ((((-((7 + 6)) + 9!) + 5!) \times 2) - 7) \\ 725969 &:= (((9! + ((6 + 95))) \times 2) + 7) \\ 725972 &:= ((2 \times ((-7 + 9!) + 5!)) - ((2 \times 7))) \\ 725973 &:= ((((-((3 + 7)) + 9!) + 5!) \times 2) - 7) \\ 725976 &:= (((6 \times 7!) + 9) \times 5!)/(-2 - 7)) \\ 725978 &:= (-((8 + 7)) - (((9! + 5!) \times (-2)) + 7)) \\ 725982 &:= (2 \times (((8! \times 9) + 5!) - (2 + 7))) \\ 725983 &:= ((((-((3 - 8)) - 9!) - 5!) \times (-2)) - 7) \\ 725986 &:= ((-((6 - 8)) \times (9! + 5!)) - ((2 \times 7))) \\ 725989 &:= (((((9 \times 8!) - 9) + 5!) \times 2) + 7) \\ 725991 &:= (((((1 + 9!) - 9) + 5!) \times 2) + 7) \\ 725992 &:= ((2 \times 9!) + ((9 \times (5^2)) + 7)) \\ 725993 &:= (((3 \times 9!) - 9!) + ((5! \times 2) - 7)) \\ 725994 &:= (-((4 + 9)) - (((9! + 5!) \times (-2)) - 7)) \\ 725996 &:= (-((6 - 9)) - (((9! + 5!) \times (-2)) + 7)) \\ 725997 &:= ((((-((7 - 9)) + 9!) + 5!) \times 2) - 7) \\ 725999 &:= (((9! - 9) + 9!) + 5!) + (2^7) \\ 726002 &:= (2 \times ((0! + (-((0! - 6)!)!) + (((2 + 7)!)!)) \\ 726009 &:= (((9! + 0!) + (-((0! - 6)!)!) \times 2) + 7) \\ 726024 &:= (4! \times ((-2 + 0!) + (-6 \times (-2 - 7)!)!)) \\ 726039 &:= (-9 + (((3 + 0)!) \times (-6 \times (-2 - 7)!)!)) \\ 726044 &:= (-4 + ((4! \times 06) \times (2 + 7)!)!)) \\ 726048 &:= (((8 - 4)!) \times 06) \times (2 + 7)!)!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 726132 &:= (2 \times ((31 \times 6) + ((2 + 7)!)) \\ 726139 &:= (((9! + (31 \times 6)) \times 2) + 7) \\ 726144 &:= (4! \times (4 - ((1 \times 6) \times (-2 - 7)))) \\ 726192 &:= ((2 \times 9!) + ((16 \times 27))) \\ 726246 &:= ((-6 + 4!) \times (((2 + 6)! + (27))) \\ 726252 &:= (2 \times (((5! \times 2) + 6) + ((2 + 7)!)) \\ 726259 &:= (((9! + ((5! \times 2) + 6)) \times 2) + 7) \\ 726264 &:= (((-4 \times 6!) - 2) \times (-((6^2) \times 7))) \\ 726292 &:= (2 \times (9! + (((2 + (6^2)) \times 7))) \\ 726344 &:= (-4 \times ((-4 \times (3!^6)) - (2 - 7))) \\ 726348 &:= 84 \times (3! \times 6! \times 2 + 7) \\ 726353 &:= (3!! - ((5! + (((3 + 6)! \times (-2)) + 7)))) \\ 726384 &:= (4! \times (8 + (3! \times ((6/2) + 7)))) \\ 726429 &:= (((9! \times 2) - 4!) + 6!) - (27) \\ 726456 &:= (6! + ((5! - ((4 + 6)!)/(2 - 7))) \\ 726466 &:= (6! + (((6! \times 4!) \times (-6)) + 2) \times (-7)) \\ 726473 &:= (3!! - ((7! \times (-4 \times (6^2)))) + 7) \\ 726475 &:= ((((-5 - 7!) \times 4!) \times (-6)) + (2 - 7)) \\ 726489 &:= (((9! \times (8/4)) + 6!) + (2 + 7)) \\ \\ 726493 &:= (3!! - (((9! + (4 + 6)) \times (-2)) + 7)) \\ 726528 &:= (((8 + 2)!/5) + (6 \times (2^7))) \\ 726592 &:= ((2 \times (9! + 5!)) + (6! - (2^7))) \\ 726624 &:= -((((4!^2) - 6!) \times (((6/2)! + 7))) \\ 726672 &:= (2 \times ((76 \times 6) + ((2 + 7)!)) \\ 726679 &:= (((9! + ((76 \times 6))) \times 2) + 7) \\ 726768 &:= ((8! + (((6 \times 7) \times 6^2)) \times 7) \\ 726784 &:= ((4! \times ((-8 - 7!) \times (-6))) - (2^7)) \\ 726833 &:= ((3 \times ((3! \times 8!) - (6!/(-2)))) - 7) \\ 726932 &:= (-2 \times (((3! - 9!) - 6!) + (2^7))) \\ 726945 &:= (((((5! + 4) - 9!) - 6!) \times (-2)) - 7) \\ 726951 &:= (((((1 + 5!) - 9!) - 6!) \times (-2)) - 7) \\ 726952 &:= (2 \times (596 + ((2 + 7)!)) \\ 726955 &:= (((((5! \times 5) + 9!) - 6) \times 2) + 7) \\ 726959 &:= (((9! + (596)) \times 2) + 7) \\ 726965 &:= (((((5! - 6!) - 9!) - 6) \times (-2)) - 7) \\ 726992 &:= (((2^9) + 9!) + 6!) + ((2 + 7)! \\ 727056 &:= ((6!/5) \times ((07)! + (2 + 7))) \\ 727179 &:= (((9! + ((7 - 1)!)) - 7) \times 2) - 7) \\ 727191 &:= (((1 - 9!) - (-((1 - 7)!)) \times (-2)) - 7) \\ 727193 &:= (((3!! + (9! - (1 \times 7))) \times 2) + 7) \\ 727199 &:= (((9! + 9!) - 1) + ((7! \times 2)/7)) \\ \\ 727207 &:= (((((7 - 0)!))! + (((2 + 7)!)) \times 2) + 7) \\ 727488 &:= ((8! + (8 \times (4! + 7!))) \times (2 + 7)) \\ 727776 &:= (((((6! \times 7!) + 7!) + 7!)/(-2 - 7))) \\ 727934 &:= ((-4 \times 3!!) + (((9! + 7) \times 2) + 7!)) \\ 728046 &:= ((6 - 4!) \times ((0! - 8!) - (2^7))) \\ 728064 &:= ((4! \times 6) \times ((08 \times 2) + 7!)) \\ 728275 &:= (-((5^7)) + (2 \times (8! + ((2 + 7)!))) \\ 728448 &:= (8! + (4! \times ((4^{8-2}) \times 7))) \\ 728544 &:= (4! \times ((-4 + 5!) + ((8 - 2) \times 7!)) \\ 728832 &:= ((2 + ((3!! - 8) \times (-8))) \times (-2^7)) \\ 729138 &:= (((-831) + 9!) \times 2) + 7! \\ 729256 &:= (((6! + (52)) - 9!) \times (-2)) + 7! \\ 729283 &:= (-((3^8)) - (-2 \times ((9! + 2) + 7!)) \\ 729314 &:= ((((-((4! - 1)) - 3!!) + 9!) \times 2) + 7! \\ 729328 &:= ((((-((8 \times 2)) - 3!!) + 9!) \times 2) + 7! \\ 729333 &:= (-((3^3)) - (((3!! - 9!) \times 2) - 7!)) \\ 729334 &:= (((-4 - ((3^3) - 9!)) \times 2) + 7! \\ 729336 &:= (((((6! + 3!) + 3!) - 9!) \times (-2)) + 7! \\ 729338 &:= ((((-8 - 3!!) - (3 - 9!)) \times 2) + 7! \\ 729339 &:= (-9 - (((3!! + (3! - 9!)) \times 2) - 7!)) \\ 729344 &:= ((((-((4 + 4)) - 3!!) + 9!) \times 2) + 7! \\ 729346 &:= (((6! + (4 + 3)) - 9!) \times (-2)) + 7! \\ 729348 &:= (-((8 + 4)) - (((3!! - 9!) \times 2) - 7!)) \\ 729372 &:= (-2 - ((((-7 + 3!!) - 9!) \times 2) - 7!)) \\ 729373 &:= ((3! + 7) - (((3!! - 9!) \times 2) - 7!)) \\ 729374 &:= (((-4 \times ((-7 + 3!!) - 9!))/2) + 7! \\ 729384 &:= (((((4 + 8) - 3!!) + 9!) \times 2) + 7! \\ 729406 &:= (((((6! + 0!) - 4!) - 9!) \times (-2)) + 7! \\ 729648 &:= (((-8 \times 4!) \times 6) + ((9! \times 2) + 7!)) \\ 729729 &:= ((9! \times 2) + ((7 \times ((9^2) \times 7))) \\ 729792 &:= (2 \times ((9! + 7!) - (9!/(-(2 - 7)!))) \\ 729848 &:= (((8^4) - 8) + 9!) + ((2 + 7)! \\ 729856 &:= -((6! - (((5! - 8) - 9!) \times (-2)) + 7!)) \\ 729864 &:= (((4^6) + 8) + 9!) + ((2 + 7)! \\ 729984 &:= (((4! \times (-8 + 9))) + 9!) \times 2) + 7! \\ 730082 &:= ((2 \times (((8 + 0)!))! + 0!)) - (3!! - 7!) \\ 730112 &:= (((2 \times 1)^{10}) \times (3!! - 7)) \\ 730249 &:= (((9 + 4)^2) \times ((0! - 3!!) + 7!)) \\ 730365 &:= (((5 + 6!)/3! - 0!) \times (-3 + 7!)) \\ 730374 &:= (((4! \times (7! - 3)) + 0!) \times 3!) + 7! \\ 730584 &:= (4! - (8 \times ((5! \times (0! - 3!)) - 7!)) \\ 730692 &:= ((2 \times ((9! - (60)) + 3!)) + 7!)$$

$$\begin{aligned}730746 &:= (((-6 + 4!) \times ((7 + 0!)! - 3)) + 7!) \\730785 &:= (((5 + (8! \times (-7 + 0!))) \times (-3)) + 7!) \\730792 &:= (((2 \times 9!) + 7!) - ((0 \times 3!)! - 7) \\730794 &:= ((((-4 - 9!) + 7) \times (0! - 3)) + 7!) \\730795 &:= ((-5 + 9!) - (-((70 + 3) \times 7!)) \\730798 &:= (8 - 9! - 7) \times (0! - 3) + 7! \\730799 &:= (((9! + 9!) + 7!) - ((0 \times 37!)!)) \\730812 &:= (2 \times (((1 + 8!)! + (03!)!)) + 7!) \\730824 &:= (4! - (((2 + 8)! / (0! - 3!)) - 7!)) \\730836 &:= ((-6 \times ((-3 \times 8!) - (03!)!)) + 7!) \\730842 &:= ((2 \times (4! + ((8 + 0!)!)) - (3! - 7!)) \\730848 &:= (((-8 + (-4!) \times ((8 - 0!)!)) \times (-3!)) + 7!) \\730932 &:= (((2 \times (3! + 9!)) + (-((0! - 3!)!))! + 7!) \\730944 &:= (4! \times ((4! \times 9) + ((03!)! \times 7!)) \\730992 &:= ((2 \times ((9! + (90)) + 3!)) + 7!) \\731136 &:= ((6! - 3!) \times ((1 + 1)^{3+7})) \\731235 &:= (((5! + ((3! - 2!)!)) + 1) \times (3 + 7!)) \\731519 &:= ((((((9 + 1)! / 5) - 1) + 3!)) + 7!) \\731525 &:= ((5! + (25)) \times ((-1 + 3!) + 7!)) \\731544 &:= (4! - ((-(((4^5) - 1)) \times 3!)) + 7!)) \\731568 &:= (8 \times (((6! \times 5!) + ((1 \times 3!)!)) + 7!)) \\731664 &:= ((4! \times ((6 + ((6 + 1)!)) \times 3!)) + 7!) \\732235 &:= (-5 - ((-((32^2)) \times 3!)) + 7!)) \\732239 &:= (((9! + 3!)) \times 2) - (-((2 - 3) - 7!)) \\732672 &:= ((2^7) \times ((-((6^2)) + 3!)) + 7!)) \\732956 &:= (((((6! \times (-5)) - 9!) \times (-2)) + ((3 - 7))) \\732987 &:= (7! + ((8! \times (9 \times 2)) + (3^7))) \\733392 &:= ((2 \times (9! + ((3!^3) \times 3!))) + 7!) \\733488 &:= -((8! + (8 \times (((4!^3) - 3!) \times (-7)))))) \\733599 &:= ((9 \times (-9 + ((5! - 3!) \times 3!))) - 7!) \\733692 &:= ((2 \times (((9! + 6!) + 3!)) + (3!)) + 7!) \\733822 &:= (-2 - (-2 \times (8! - ((3!^3) \times (-7)))))) \\733845 &:= (((5! + 4!) \times (8 + 3!)) + 3) \times 7 \\733848 &:= -(((8! - 4!) + (((8 \times 3!)^3) \times (-7)))) \\734365 &:= (-5 \times (((6! \times (-34)) \times 3!) + 7)) \\734392 &:= (2 \times ((9! - 3!)) - (((4! / 3!) - 7!))) \\734393 &:= (((3! + ((9! / 3!))) \times (4 \times 3)) - 7) \\734435 &:= (-5 \times (((3! / (-4)) - 4!) \times 3! - 7)) \\734492 &:= ((2 \times 9!) - ((4 \times (4 - (3^7)))))) \\734592 &:= (2 \times (((9! + 5!) - 4!) - 3!)) + 7!)) \\734814 &:= (4! + (((18^4) - 3!) \times 7)) \\734818 &:= ((-((8 - (18^4)))) + 3!) \times 7\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}734831 &:= (-1 + (((3! + 8) \times 4!) \times (3^7))) \\734832 &:= ((-2 + 3!) \times (84 \times (3^7))) \\734839 &:= ((((-9!) / 3!) - 8!) \times (-4! - 3!)) + 7) \\734853 &:= (((3! \times (-5 - 8))^4) + 3) \times 7 \\734899 &:= (((9! + 9!) + ((8^4) + 3)) + 7!) \\734976 &:= (((6! \times 7!) / 9) + (4!^{-3+7})) \\735402 &:= (((2 + (04!)!)) + 5!) \times (-3 + 7!)) \\735492 &:= (2 \times (9! - (((4! + 5) \times 3!) - 7!)) \\735735 &:= ((5 - 3!) \times ((7! / (-5)) - ((3 \times 7))) \\735792 &:= (2 \times ((9! - (((7 + 5) / 3!)!)) + 7!)) \\735793 &:= (((3! \times (9! + 7!)) - 5!) / 3) - 7) \\735864 &:= ((-4 \times (-6 - 8!)) + ((5! - 3!) \times 7!)) \\735902 &:= (2 \times ((0! + 9!) + ((5 \times 3!) + 7!)) \\735912 &:= (2 \times ((1 + 9!) - ((-5 - 3!) \times 7)) \\735932 &:= (2 \times ((3! + 9!) - ((5! / (-3)) - 7!)) \\735946 &:= ((6 - 4) \times ((9! + (53)) + 7!)) \\735972 &:= ((2 \times (7! + 9!)) + ((5^3) + 7)) \\736086 &:= (-6 \times (8 - (((0! + 6)^3) + 7!)) \\736092 &:= (2 \times ((9! + (-((0! - 6)))!)) + (3! + 7!)) \\736132 &:= (-2 + (3! \times (((1 + 6)^3) + 7!)) \\736176 &:= (-6 \times (-7 - (((1 + 6)^3) + 7!)) \\736184 &:= (((4!)! / (8! \times (16)!)) + 3!)) - 7) \\736254 &:= -((4! + ((5! + (26)) \times (-3 - 7!))) \\736272 &:= (2 \times (((7 + 2)! + ((6^3))) + 7!)) \\736832 &:= (-((2^3!)) \times ((8 \times (-6!) - 3!)) + 7) \\736992 &:= (2 \times (9! + ((96 \times 3!) + 7!)) \\737143 &:= ((3! \times (-((4 + 1)!)) + ((7^3) \times 7)) \\737224 &:= ((4 \times 2) \times (((2^7) \times 3!)) - 7) \\737238 &:= (((8 \times 3!)) \times (2^7)) + (3! \times (-7)) \\737243 &:= ((3! \times (4^{-2+7})) - 37) \\737248 &:= (-((8 \times 4) - (-((2^7) \times (3! + 7!))) \\737255 &:= (-((5 \times 5) - (-((2^7) \times (3! + 7!))) \\737267 &:= (((7! + 6!) \times (2^7)) - 3!) - 7) \\737273 &:= (((-((3 - 7))^{-2+7}) \times 3!)) - 7) \\737274 &:= -(((-(4 - 7))! + (-((2^7) \times (3! + 7!)))) \\737275 &:= (-5 - ((7! \times (-2^{7+3}))) / 7) \\737276 &:= (((6! + 7!) \times (2^7)) + ((3 - 7))) \\737304 &:= (4! + ((-((0! - 3))^7) \times (3! + 7!)) \\737492 &:= ((2 \times 9!) - ((-4 + (7! / 3)) \times (-7))) \\737755 &:= (-((5^5)) + (7! \times ((7 \times 3) \times 7))) \\737856 &:= (((6! / (-5)) + 8!) - 7!) \times (3 \times 7)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}738304 &:= ((4^{-0!+3!}) \times ((8 + 3!) - 7)) \\738353 &:= ((3 \times (-5!) + ((3!! + 8!) \times 3!)) - 7) \\738385 &:= ((5^8) + (3 \times ((8! \times 3) - 7!))) \\738594 &:= (((4 + 9) + 5) \times ((8! + 3!) - 7)) \\738633 &:= (-3 \times (((3! - 6!) - 8!) \times 3!) - 7)) \\738648 &:= (8! - 4 + 6!) \times (8 + 3 + 7) \\738669 &:= (-9 - (-6 \times (((6! + 8!) \times 3) - 7))) \\738693 &:= (3 \times ((-9 - 6!) + ((8! \times 3!) + 7!))) \\738699 &:= (((9 + 9) \times (6! + 8!)) - (3 \times 7)) \\738713 &:= ((-3!) \times (((-((1 - 7)))! + 8!) \times (-3))) - 7) \\738736 &:= ((((-6!) - 3!!) + 7) \times (-8^3)) + 7! \\738846 &:= (((6 + 4) + 8) \times ((8! + 3!) + 7)) \\738864 &:= (((((4 + 6))! + 8!)/(8 - 3)) + 7!) \\738953 &:= (((3! \times (5! - 9!)) - 8!)/(-3)) - 7) \\739193 &:= ((((((3 + 9) - 1)!/9)/3!) - 7) \\739359 &:= (((9!/5!)/3) + 9) \times (3!! + 7)) \\739389 &:= -((9! - (((8 \times 3^9) + 3) \times 7))) \\739432 &:= ((-2 \times (3!! + (4 - 9!))) + (3 \times 7!)) \\739584 &:= (4! \times ((8!/(-5)) - (9 \times (3!! - 7!)))) \\740712 &:= (((-21) \times 7!) + (04!)) \times (-7) \\740775 &:= ((5 + (7! \times (-7))) \times ((0! - 4) \times 7)) \\740872 &:= ((2 \times ((7! + ((8 + 0!))!) - 4)) + 7!) \\740873 &:= (((-3 \times (7! - 8!)) - ((0 \times 4))!) \times 7) \\740875 &:= (-5 + ((7! - 8!) \times ((0! - 4) \times 7))) \\740877 &:= (((7 \times (7! - 8!)) + 0!) \times (4 - 7)) \\741027 &:= ((7! + ((2 \times 0!))!) \times 147) \\741393 &:= (((3^9)/3) \times (((1 + 4))! - 7)) \\741456 &:= (((6^5) \times 4!) \times (1 \times 4)) - 7! \\741615 &:= ((-5 - ((1 + 6))!) \times (-147)) \\741761 &:= (-1 - ((6 + 7!) \times (-147))) \\742094 &:= (((4! - 9!) + 0!) \times (-2)) + (4^7) \\742144 &:= (((((4 + 4) + 1))! \times 2) + (4^7)) \\742194 &:= (((4! + 9!) + 1) \times 2) + (4^7) \\742464 &:= (4! \times ((6! - 4!) + ((2 + 4) \times 7!))) \\742939 &:= (((9! - ((3^{9+2}))) \times 4) + 7) \\743033 &:= ((((-3!) \times ((3! + 0!))!) - 3!!) \times (-4!)) - 7) \\743047 &:= (((-7!) - ((4 + 0!))!) \times (-3! \times 4!)) + 7) \\743064 &:= ((4! \times (6! + 0!)) + ((3! \times 4!) \times 7!)) \\743341 &:= ((1 \times 43) \times ((3!! \times 4!) + 7)) \\743528 &:= (8! + ((2 + 5!) \times (3!! + (4 + 7!)))) \\743753 &:= (3!! + (((((5! + 7!) \times 3!) \times 4!) - 7))) \\743902 &:= (-2 \times ((0! - 9!) + ((3!^4) \times (-7))))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}744336 &:= (((6! + ((3!^3!) \times 4)) \times 4) - 7!) \\744448 &:= (((8^4)/4) \times (((4!/4)! + 7)) \\744464 &:= (((4! + 6)^4) - ((4 \times (4^7)))) \\744773 &:= (37 \times (((7! \times 4) - 4!) - 7)) \\745193 &:= ((3!! \times (9 \times ((-1 + 5!) - 4))) - 7) \\745328 &:= (((8!/2)/3!!) + 5!) \times (-4 + 7!) \\745344 &:= (-((4! \times 4!)) - (((3!!/5) + 4) \times (-7!))) \\745483 &:= (((3!! + 8) \times (4^5)) + (4 + 7)) \\745655 &:= (((5! + (5^6)) + 5!) \times 47) \\745692 &:= ((2 \times ((9! + 6) - 5!)) - (-4 \times 7!)) \\745735 &:= (((5 \times 3!) + 7) \times (-5 - (-4 \times 7!))) \\745848 &:= -((8! + (4! \times (-((8^5) - 4) - 7)))) \\745893 &:= ((3 \times (-9 + 8!)) + ((5! + 4) \times 7!)) \\745912 &:= ((2 \times ((1 + 9!) - 5)) - (-4 \times 7!)) \\745915 &:= ((-5 + (((1 + 9))!/5)) - (-4 \times 7!)) \\745919 &:= (((9! - 1) + 9!) + ((5! \times 4!) \times 7)) \\745932 &:= ((2 \times (3! + 9!)) + ((5! \times 4!) \times 7)) \\745949 &:= (((9! + 4!) + 9!) + 5) - (-4 \times 7!)) \\745984 &:= (((-((4 - 8))^9) + ((5! - 4!) \times 7!)) \\746323 &:= (((((3! \times 2)^3!) - 6!)/4) + 7) \\746328 &:= (((8 \times 2) \times (3!^6)) - (4! \times 7)) \\746483 &:= -((3! - (((8 + 4)^6)/4) - 7!)) \\746488 &:= (-8 - ((8 - 4!) \times (6^{(-4+7)!}))) \\746496 &:= ((6! \times 9!)/((46 + 4) \times 7)) \\746503 &:= (((((3! + 0!) + 5)^6)/4) + 7) \\746524 &:= (-4 \times ((((-((2 - 5)))!^6) \times (-4)) - 7)) \\746538 &:= (8! - 3! + 5 \times 6!) \times (4! - 7) \\746664 &:= (4! \times (((6^6)/6) \times 4) + 7) \\747353 &:= (((-3!) \times ((-5 \times 3!) - (7! \times 4!))) - 7) \\747696 &:= (((6!/9) - 6) \times ((7! + 4!) + 7!)) \\748799 &:= ((9! + 9!) - ((-7 + (8! \times 4)))/(-7)) \\749728 &:= (((-((8/2)^7)) + (9!/(-4))) \times (-7)) \\749742 &:= (((-((2 + (4^7))) + (9!/(-4))) \times (-7)) \\750568 &:= ((8 + 6!) \times (((5 - 0!)^5) + 7)) \\750952 &:= ((2 \times ((-5 + 9!) + 0!)) - (-5 \times 7!)) \\750972 &:= ((2 \times ((7 + 9!) - 0!)) - (-5 \times 7!)) \\751392 &:= (2 \times (9! + ((3!^{1 \times 5}) + 7!))) \\751556 &:= (((6!/5) + 5) \times (-((1 - 5)) + 7!)) \\751968 &:= (((8! + 6!) \times 91)/5) + 7! \\752395 &:= (-5 - (((9! + 3!) \times (-2)) + (-5 \times 7!))) \\753088 &:= ((8 \times 8) \times (((0! + 3!)^5) - 7!))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 753375 &:= ((-(((5 \times 7)^3)) \times (-3 - 5!)) / 7) \\ 753408 &:= (((8 + 0!)! + (4!^3)) \times (-5 - 7)) \\ 753488 &:= (((8 + 84)^3) + (-5 \times 7!)) \\ 753519 &:= (9! - ((1 - (5 \times (3 + (5^7)))))) \\ 753583 &:= (((3! + (85)^3) + (5 + 7)) \\ 753595 &:= ((5! + 9!) - (5 \times (3! - (5^7)))) \\ 753984 &:= (4! \times (((8!/9) + (3 + 5)) \times 7)) \\ 754215 &:= -((5! - ((-((1 - (2^4)))^5) - 7!))) \\ 754335 &:= (((((5 + 3) + 3) + 4)^5) - 7!) \\ 754455 &:= (5! + (((5!/(4 + 4))^5) - 7!)) \\ 754553 &:= ((3!! \times ((5!/5) + (4^5))) - 7) \\ 754935 &:= ((-5!) + 3!!) + (((-9 + 4!)^5) - 7!)) \\ 754992 &:= ((2 \times (9! - ((9! \times (-4))/5!))) + 7!) \\ 755175 &:= (((5! \times 7) + ((15^5))) - 7!) \\ 755273 &:= ((3! \times ((7! \times 25) - 5!)) - 7) \\ 755938 &:= (-8 - (3! \times (9 + (-((5 \times 5)) \times 7!)))) \\ 756005 &:= (-5 \times ((0 - 0!) + (-((6 \times 5)) \times 7!))) \\ 756006 &:= (6 \times (0! - (((0! - 6) \times 5) \times 7!))) \\ 756024 &:= (4! + (((2 + 0!)! + (6!/5)) \times 7!)) \\ 756025 &:= ((5^2) \times (0! + ((6!/5!) \times 7!)) \\ 756029 &:= (((9! \times 2) - 0!) + (-6 \times (-5 - 7!))) \\ 756035 &:= (((5 \times 30) \times 6!) + 5) \times 7) \\ 756036 &:= (6 \times (3! - (((0! - 6) \times 5) \times 7!))) \\ 756037 &:= (7! \times 30 + 6) \times 5 + 7 \\ 756175 &:= (-5 \times (((7! + 1) - 6!) \times (-5 \times 7!))) \\ 756648 &:= (8! - 4! \times 6) / 6 \times (5! - 7) \\ 756864 &:= (4! \times ((6 \times 8) \times 657)) \\ 756935 &:= -(((5^3!) + (((-9 \times 6!) \times 5!) + 7!))) \\ 757432 &:= (2 \times (3!! - (4 + (-75) \times 7!))) \\ 757439 &:= (((9 \times (3!! + 4!)) + 7) \times (5! - 7)) \\ 757757 &:= (((7! / (-5)) + 7) \times (-757)) \\ 758295 &:= (((5! - 9!) \times (-2)) + ((8^5) + 7)) \\ 758328 &:= (((8 + 2)!) + ((3!^8) - 5!)) / 7) \\ 758682 &:= ((2 - ((8! / (-6)) + 8)) \times (5! - 7)) \\ 758704 &:= (((4! - ((0 \times 7)!) \times (8^5)) + 7!) \\ 759342 &:= ((-2 - 4!) + (((3! + 9)^5) - 7)) \\ 759344 &:= -((4! - (((4 \times 3!) - 9)^5) - 7)) \\ 759349 &:= ((-9 - 4!) + (((3! + 9)^5) + 7)) \\ 759353 &:= (-((3 \times 5)) + (((3! + 9)^5) - 7)) \\ 759359 &:= (-9 + (((-5 \times (3! - 9))^5) - 7)) \\ 759361 &:= (-((1 + 6)) + (((3! + 9)^5) - 7)) \\ 759364 &:= (-4 + (((((6 - 3)!) + 9)^5) - 7)) \\ 759367 &:= (-((7 - 6)) + (((3! + 9)^5) - 7)) \\ 759374 &:= ((-((4 - 7)!) + (((3! + 9)^5) - 7)) \\ 759376 &:= (-6 + (((((7 - 3)!) - 9)^5) + 7)) \\ 759382 &:= ((((((2 + 8) - 3)!) - 9)^5) + 7) \\ 759384 &:= ((4! - 8) + (((3! + 9)^5) - 7)) \\ 759385 &:= (-((5 - 8)) + (((3! + 9)^5) + 7)) \\ 759391 &:= ((1 \times 9) + (((3! + 9)^5) + 7)) \\ 759432 &:= ((2^3!) + (((4! - 9)^5) - 7)) \\ 759438 &:= ((8! / 3!!) + (((4! - 9)^5) + 7)) \\ 759684 &:= ((-((4 + 8)) + 6!) \times ((9 \times 5!) - 7)) \\ 760328 &:= (8 \times (((2 \times 3!)! + ((0! + 6)!) / 7!)) \\ 760368 &:= (8 \times (6 - (((3! - (0 - 6)!) / (-7!)))) \\ 762432 &:= ((-2 - 3!!) \times (4! \times (-2 + (6 \times 7)))) \\ 763495 &:= (((5! \times 9) - 4!) \times (3 + 6!)) + 7) \\ 763848 &:= (((8 + 4) \times (8! + 3!)) + (6^7)) \\ 763896 &:= (((6! + (9! \times 8)) / 3!) + (6^7)) \\ 763899 &:= (((9! + 9!) + 8!) - (3 \times (6! + 7))) \\ 763925 &:= ((-((5! - 2)) \times ((-9 \times 3!!) + 6)) - 7) \\ 764544 &:= -(((4!^4) - (5! \times ((4^6) + 7!))) \\ 764633 &:= ((3! \times ((-3 + (6! / 4)) \times 6!)) - 7) \\ 764635 &:= (-5 - ((-3 + (6! / 4)) \times (6! - 7!))) \\ 765135 &:= (((((5 \times 3) \times 1)^5) + 6!) + 7!) \\ 765168 &:= ((8 + (6! / (1 \times 5))) \times (-6 + 7!)) \\ 765331 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times ((3! - (5^6)) \times (-7))) \\ 765373 &:= ((3! + (-7 \times (3! - (5^6)))) \times 7) \\ 765384 &:= ((4 \times (8! + 3!)) + (5! \times (-6 + 7!))) \\ 765387 &:= (-7 \times (-8 - ((3! - (5^6)) \times (-7))) \\ 765453 &:= (3 \times (5! + (((4!)! / ((5! / 6)!) + 7))) \\ 765667 &:= ((7! / 6!) \times (6 + ((5^6) \times 7))) \\ 765673 &:= (3! + (7 \times (6 + ((5^6) \times 7)))) \\ 765745 &:= ((5 \times 4!) + (7 \times ((5^6) \times 7))) \\ 765765 &:= (((5! / 6) + ((7 \times (5^6)))) \times 7) \\ 765918 &:= (((8! \times 19) - 5!) - (6 \times 7)) \\ 765936 &:= ((6! \times (3!! - (9 \times 5))) + (6^7)) \\ 765943 &:= (((3!^4) \times ((-9 - 5!) + 6!)) + 7) \\ 765944 &:= -((4! - ((49 \times ((5^6) + 7)))) \\ 766075 &:= (-5 + (((7 + 0!)! \times ((6 + 6) + 7))) \\ 766099 &:= (((9! / 9) + 0!) \times ((6 + 6) + 7)) \\ 766118 &:= ((8! + (1 + 1)) \times ((6 + 6) + 7)) \\ 766175 &:= ((-5 - ((7 + 1)!) \times (-((6 + 6) + 7)))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 766258 &:= (((8!/5!) - 2) + 6!) \times (6! + 7) \\ 766289 &:= (((-9 - 8!) - 2) \times (-((6 + 6) + 7))) \\ 766572 &:= ((-2 - (7!/(-5))) \times (6! + (6 \times 7))) \\ 766686 &:= (6! + ((8! - 6) \times ((6 + 6) + 7))) \\ 766752 &:= (-2 \times (5! + (-76) \times (6 + 7!))) \\ 767424 &:= (((4! - 2) \times (4! - 7!)) + 6!) \times (-7) \\ 767472 &:= (2 \times ((7! - 4!) \times 76)) + 7! \\ 768339 &:= (9 \times ((3! + (3^8)) \times (6 + 7))) \\ 768384 &:= (((4 \times 8) - 3!) \times 8!) - (6^7) \\ 768393 &:= (((3 + 9!) \times 3) - 8!) - (6^7) \\ 769295 &:= (((5! \times 9) + 2) \times (-9 + 6!)) - 7 \\ 769535 &:= -(((5^{3!}) - ((5! \times 9) \times (6! + 7)))) \\ 770665 &:= (((5^6) \times ((6 + 0!) \times 7)) + 7!) \\ 770974 &:= (((4! - 7) \times (-9)) \times (0! - 7!)) + 7 \\ 770983 &:= ((3!! \times (-((8 \times 9) - 0!)) + ((7^7))) \\ 771129 &:= (9 \times ((2 - 1) + (17 \times 7!))) \\ 771703 &:= ((3!! \times (- (0! + 7!))) + ((7^7))) \\ 772533 &:= (((-3 + (3!! \times 5!)) \times (2 + 7)) - 7!) \\ 772546 &:= ((6! \times 4^5) - ((2 - 7!) \times 7)) \\ 772567 &:= (7 - (((6! \times 5!) \times (- (2 + 7))) + 7!)) \\ 773143 &:= (-((3! + 4) \times ((1 + 3!)!)) + ((7^7))) \\ 773415 &:= (51 \times (4! + (3 \times (7! + 7)))) \\ 773648 &:= (((8! \times 46^3)/7!) - 7!) \\ 773863 &:= (((3!! \times (-68)) - 3!!) + ((7^7))) \\ 773965 &:= (-5 \times (6! + (((9! \times 3)/(-7)) + 7))) \\ 774144 &:= ((4!^{4-1}) \times (4 \times (7 + 7))) \\ 774259 &:= ((((-9 + 5!)^2) \times (-4)) + ((7^7))) \\ 774312 &:= (((2 \times ((1 + 3!)!)) - 4!) \times 77) \\ 775324 &:= ((4! - 2) \times (-3 - ((-5 + 7!) \times (-7)))) \\ 775425 &:= ((-5 + ((2 - 4!) \times (-5 + 7!))) \times (-7)) \\ 775433 &:= -((3!! + (((-34) - 5!) \times 7!) + 7)) \\ 775775 &:= (((-((5 - 7)) \times 7!) - 5) \times 77) \\ 776292 &:= (((2 + 9) \times 2) \times (6 - (7! \times (-7)))) \\ 776307 &:= (((7! + 0!) \times (-3)) - 6!) \times (- (7 \times 7)) \\ 776743 &:= ((((-3 \times 4!) + 7) \times 6!) + ((7^7))) \\ 776887 &:= -((((7 - (8/8))^6) - (7^7))) \\ 776887 &:= -(7 - 8/8)^6 + 7^7 \\ 776951 &:= ((1 - 5!) \times ((-9 \times 6!) - ((7 \times 7)))) \\ 777159 &:= (9 \times ((5! \times (-((1 - 7)))!)) - (7 \times 7)) \\ 777229 &:= (-9 - (-22) \times ((7! + 7) \times 7)) \\ 777238 &:= (((8 + 3) \times 2) \times ((7! + 7) \times 7)) \\ 777539 &:= ((-9 \times (3! + ((5! \times 7!)/(-7)))) - 7) \\ 777583 &:= -((3!! + (((8! - 5!) + 7!) - ((7^7)))) \\ 777589 &:= (((9!/8) \times 5!) - 77)/7 \\ 777591 &:= ((1 \times 9) \times (((5! \times 7!) - 7)/7)) \\ 777593 &:= (((3 \times 9!) \times 5) - ((7 \times 7))/7) \\ 777595 &:= (-5 - ((9! \times 5!)/(-((7 \times 7) + 7)))) \\ 777602 &:= (2 \times ((0! + 6!) - (7! \times (-77)))) \\ 777603 &:= (3 \times (0! + ((6! \times 7!)/(7 + 7))) \\ 777609 &:= (9 \times (((-((0! - 6)))! \times (-7!)) - 7)/(-7)) \\ 777624 &:= (4! + (2 \times (6! - (7! \times (-77)))) \\ 777823 &:= ((3!!/(-2)) - ((8! + 7!) - ((7^7))) \\ 777974 &:= (((4! + 7!) \times (-9)) + ((7^7) + 7)) \\ 778093 &:= (((3!! + 9!)/(0 - 8)) + ((7^7))) \\ 778147 &:= (((7! + 4) \times (- (1 + 8))) + ((7^7))) \\ 778176 &:= ((((-6 - 7!) - 1) - 8!) + ((7^7))) \\ 778177 &:= ((((-7 - 7!) + 1) - 8!) + ((7^7))) \\ 778183 &:= ((3!! \times (- (8 - 1))) - (8! - ((7^7))) \\ 778273 &:= (((3!! - ((7 + 2)!)/8) + ((7^7))) \\ 778903 &:= (3!! - (((09)!/8) - ((7^7))) \\ 778993 &:= (((3!! \times 9) - 9!)/8) + ((7^7)) \\ 780523 &:= -((3!! - ((2 \times (5^08)) - 7))) \\ 781383 &:= ((3 \times (8^{3!})) + (-((1 + 8) - 7!)) \\ 781384 &:= ((4! \times (8^{3!-1})) + (-8 - 7!)) \\ 781584 &:= ((4! \times (((8^5) \times 1) + 8)) - 7!) \\ 781975 &:= ((5 + 7!) \times ((9 \times 18) - 7)) \\ 783167 &:= ((-((7^6)) + ((-1 - 3!!) \times (-8))) \times (-7)) \\ 783223 &:= -((((3! + 2)! - (((2 - 3) + 8)^7))) \\ 783237 &:= (((7^{3!}) + 2) - (3!! \times 8)) \times 7 \\ 783353 &:= ((3!! \times ((5! \times (3 \times 3)) + 8)) - 7) \\ 783792 &:= ((-((2^9)) \times (7! - (3^8))) + 7!) \\ 784568 &:= (((8!/6) \times (5! + 4)) - (-8 - 7!)) \\ 784765 &:= (5 \times ((6! - 7!) + ((4 \times 8!) - 7)) \\ 785169 &:= ((9 \times (6! + 1)) \times (5! + (8 - 7))) \\ 785664 &:= (((4! + 6!) \times 6) \times (5! + ((8 \times 7))) \\ 785925 &:= (((((5!^2) - 9) \times 5) + 8!) \times 7) \\ 785964 &:= (-4 \times (69 + ((-5 \times 8!) + 7!))) \\ 786144 &:= (-4 \times (4! + (((1 - 6) \times 8!) + 7!))) \\ 786233 &:= (((3!! \times (-3))/2) \times (- (6! + 8))) - 7) \\ 786264 &:= (4! \times (((6 - 2)^6) \times 8) - 7) \\ 786352 &:= ((-2 + 5!) \times (((3!^6) - 8)/7)) \\ 786383 &:= ((3 \times ((8^{3!}) - (6 + 8))) - 7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 786384 &:= (-4 \times (((8! + 3!) \times (-6)) + 8!) + 7!) \\ 786432 &:= ((2 \times 3!) \times ((4!/6)^{8!/7!})) \\ 786439 &:= (((9 + 3) \times ((4!/6)^8)) + 7) \\ 786584 &:= ((4! \times ((8^5) + 6)) + (8!/7!)) \\ 786953 &:= (3!! - (((5! \times (-9)) \times (6! + 8)) + 7)) \\ 787332 &:= (((2 + 3!!) + 3!!) \times (78 \times 7)) \\ 787335 &:= ((5! \times (3 \times (3^7))) + (8 + 7)) \\ 787344 &:= (4! + (4! \times ((3^7) \times (8 + 7)))) \\ 787495 &:= (((5! + (9 \times 4)) \times (7! + 8)) + 7) \\ 788277 &:= ((7^7) + ((2 - (8!/8)) \times 7)) \\ 788785 &:= ((5^8) - (7! \times (8 - 87))) \\ 790566 &:= (6 \times (((6! \times 5!) + 0!) + (9 \times 7!))) \\ 791284 &:= ((4^8) + (2 \times ((1 + 9!) - 7))) \\ 791289 &:= ((9! \times (-((8 + 2) + 1))) + ((9^7))) \\ 793296 &:= ((((-6 \times 9!)/(-2 + 3)) + 9!) - 7!) \\ 793305 &:= (((5! - 0!) \times ((3!^{3!}) + 9))/7) \\ 794784 &:= ((((-4 + 8!) - 7!) \times 4!) + (9!/(-7))) \\ 794832 &:= (-2 \times (3!! - (((8! - 4!) + 9!) - 7!))) \\ 794849 &:= (((9^4) + 8) \times (4! + 97)) \\ 794875 &:= ((-5 - ((7! - 8!) \times 4!)) + (9!/(-7))) \\ 795258 &:= ((8! \times 5) + ((-2 + 5!) \times (-9 + 7!))) \\ 795635 &:= (-5 \times ((3!! \times (-6! + 5)) + ((9! - 7)))) \\ 795684 &:= (((4 + 8) + 6!) \times ((5! \times 9) + 7)) \\ 795953 &:= (((3!! \times (-5)) - 9) \times (-5!)) + ((9! - 7)) \\ 796319 &:= ((9! - 1) + ((3! - (6!/(-9))) \times 7!)) \\ 796344 &:= (4! + (-((4 - ((3 \times 6) \times 9)) \times 7!)) \\ 796535 &:= -((((5!^3) + (5^6)) - (9! \times 7))) \\ 798336 &:= (((6 + 3!)^{-3+8}) - 9!) \times (-7) \\ 799236 &:= ((6! + (3! \times 29))^{9-7}) \\ 799488 &:= ((8! + (8^4)) \times (9 \times (9 - 7))) \\ 800633 &:= ((3!! \times 3!!) - ((6 + 0!) \times (0! - 8!))) \\ 802304 &:= -(((4^{03!}) + (-20) \times 8!)) \\ 802765 &:= ((-5 \times (6! + 7)) - (-20) \times 8!) \\ 803376 &:= (((6! + 7) \times 3!!) + (3!^{-0!+8})) \\ 803457 &:= ((7 + (-((5! + 4)) \times 3!!)) \times (-0! + 8)) \\ 803544 &:= (4! - (((4 + 5!) \times 3!!) \times (-0! + 8))) \\ 804024 &:= (4! - (20 \times (((4 + 0!))! - 8!)) \\ 804816 &:= (((6^{-1+8}) \times (4! - 0!))/8) \\ 804962 &:= (-2 \times (((6! - 9!) - ((4 \times 0!))! - 8!)) \\ 804968 &:= (((((8! - 6!) + 9!)/4) + 0!) \times 8) \\ 805405 &:= (5 \times (0! - (-4 \times (-50) + 8!))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 805448 &:= 8! \times (4! - 4) - (5! - 0!) \times 8 \\ 805669 &:= ((9! - 6!) - ((6 + 5) \times (0! - 8!))) \\ 805675 &:= (((5! \times 7!) - 6!) - (5 \times (0! - 8!))) \\ 805845 &:= (-5 \times ((((-4 \times 8!) + 5!) - 0!) - 8)) \\ 805888 &:= (8 \times (-((8 \times (8^5))) + ((0! + 8)!)) \\ 805892 &:= ((2 \times (9! + 8!)) - (508)) \\ 805995 &:= (-5 \times (9 \times 9) + ((-5 + 0!) \times 8!)) \\ 806304 &:= (-4 \times (((0! + 3!))! + ((-6 + 0!) \times 8!))) \\ 806358 &:= (((8! \times 5!)/3!) - (-6 \times (0! - 8))) \\ 806364 &:= (-4 \times ((6 + 3) + ((-6 + 0!) \times 8!)) \\ 806379 &:= (((9! - 7) \times 3) - ((6 + 0!) \times 8!)) \\ 806385 &:= 5! \times 8!/3! - 6 - 0! - 8 \\ 806392 &:= (2 \times (((9! - 3) - ((6 \times 0!))! + 8!)) \\ 806393 &:= (((3 - 9!)/(-3)) \times (6 + 0!)) - 8! \\ 806395 &:= (-5 + (((9 \times 3) - 6) - 0!) \times 8!) \\ 806415 &:= (-5 + ((14 + 6) \times (0! + 8!))) \\ 806432 &:= (2 \times (3! + ((4 + 6) \times (0! + 8!)))) \\ 806435 &:= (-5 \times (-3 - (4 \times (((6 \times 0!))! + 8!)))) \\ 806436 &:= ((6 \times 3!) - (-4 \times ((6 - 0!) \times 8!)) \\ 806444 &:= (4! - ((4 - 4!) \times (((6 \times 0!))! + 8!)) \\ 806448 &:= 8! \times (4! - 4) + 6 \times 08 \\ 806492 &:= (2 \times ((9! + 46) + (08)!)) \\ 806495 &:= (-5 \times (9 + (-4 \times ((6 + 0!) + 8!)))) \\ 806504 &:= (4 \times (0! + (-5 \times ((-6 + 0!) - 8!))) \\ 806564 &:= ((4! \times 6) - ((5!/(-6)) \times (0! + 8!)) \\ 806589 &:= (((((9 + 8!) \times 5!)/6) + 0!) + 8) \\ 806664 &:= (-4 \times (-66) + ((-6 + 0!) \times 8!)) \\ 806733 &:= (-3 - (3! \times ((7^{6-0!}) \times (-8)))) \\ 806736 &:= (((6 - 3!))! \times ((7^{6-0!}) \times 8)) \\ 806744 &:= (((4! + 4!) \times (7^{6-0!})) + 8) \\ 808024 &:= (4! - (-20) \times (80 + 8!)) \\ 811475 &:= ((5 + (7! \times (4! - 1))) \times (-1 - 8)) \\ 813456 &:= ((-6 - 5!) \times (4! + (3!! \times (-1 + 8)))) \\ 813564 &:= (((4!/6) + 5!) \times ((3 \times 1)^8)) \\ 813681 &:= (((1 + 8)^6) + ((3! + 1) \times 8!)) \\ 813985 &:= ((5^8) - ((9!/3!) \times (1 - 8))) \\ 816048 &:= (((8! - 4!) + ((0! + 6)!)) \times 18) \\ 816372 &:= ((2 + (7! \times (-3))) \times (-6 \times (1 + 8))) \\ 816399 &:= (9 \times (-9 - (-((3 \times 6)) \times (-((1 - 8)!)))) \\ 816465 &:= ((5! + (-((6^4)) \times ((6 + 1)!)))/(-8)) \\ 816471 &:= ((-1 + (7! \times (4! - 6))) \times (1 + 8)) \\ 816475 &:= (-5 - (7! \times ((4! - 6) \times (-1 + 8)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}816479 &:= (9! + (((7 - ((4 + 6))!) + 1) / (-8))) \\816487 &:= (((7! + 8!) \times (4! - 6)) - ((1 - 8))) \\816489 &:= (((9! / 8) \times (4! - 6)) + (1 + 8)) \\816495 &:= ((5! + (9! \times (4! - 6))) / (1 \times 8)) \\816498 &:= ((8 + ((9! / 4) + 6)) \times (1 + 8)) \\817668 &:= (((8! + 66) + 7!) \times 18) \\817776 &:= -(((6! + 7!) - (((7^7) + 1) - 8))) \\817783 &:= ((3!! \times (-8)) + (((7^7) \times (1^8)))) \\817935 &:= (((5 \times 3) \times ((9! / 7) + 1)) + 8!) \\819848 &:= ((8 \times (((4! \times 8!) / 9) + 1)) - 8!) \\820125 &:= ((5^{2+1}) \times ((0! + 2)^8)) \\820224 &:= (((4!^2) \times 2) \times (((((0! + 2))!)! - 8)) \\823347 &:= 7 \times ((4 + 3)^{3!} - 28) \\823477 &:= ((7^7) - ((4! \times 3) + ((2 - 8)))) \\823537 &:= 7^{3! - 5 + 3!} + 2 - 8 \\823545 &:= (((((5! + 45) + 3!!)^2) + 8!) \\823555 &:= ((-5 - 5!) - (((5!^3) / (-2)) + 8!)) \\823577 &:= ((7^7) + ((5! / 3) + ((2 - 8)))) \\823584 &:= (((((4! \times (-8)) + (5!^3)) / 2) - 8!) \\823599 &:= (-((9 \times 9)) - (((5!^3) / (-2)) + 8!)) \\823607 &:= ((7^{0!+6}) + ((3! + 2) \times 8)) \\823664 &:= (((((4! \times 6!) \times (-6)) + 3!!) + 2) \times (-8)) \\823775 &:= (((5! + ((7^7))) + ((3 + 2))!) - 8) \\824832 &:= (2 \times (((3 \times 8)^4) + (2 \times 8!))) \\825576 &:= ((-6 + 7!) \times (5! + (52 - 8))) \\826314 &:= (-41) \times (3! - (6! \times 28)) \\826568 &:= (((8! / 6) \times (5! + (6 / 2))) + 8) \\826848 &:= (((8 + (4^8)) \times (6 \times 2)) + 8!) \\827136 &:= (((6^{3!}) + ((1 \times 7))!) \times (2 \times 8)) \\827544 &:= ((44 + 5!) \times (7! - ((2 - 8)))) \\827584 &:= (-4 \times (((8! \times (-5)) - 7!) - (2^8))) \\827736 &:= ((6! - (3! \times (7! + 7))) \times (-28)) \\828864 &:= (4! \times (((6! \times (-8)) - ((8 / 2))!) + 8!)) \\829075 &:= (-((5^7)) - (((((0! + 9))!) \times (-2)) / 8)) \\829344 &:= (4! \times ((-4 - 3!!) - (((9 - 2))! - 8!)) \\829456 &:= -((((6! \times 5!) \times 4!) - ((9! + 2) \times 8)) \\829464 &:= (4! + ((-64) \times 9!) / (-28)) \\829536 &:= (-6 \times (((3!! \times (-((5 - 9)))!) + 2) \times (-8))) \\830584 &:= (((48 - ((5 \times 0))!)^3) \times 8) \\830591 &:= (-1 + (((95 - 0!)^3) + 8)) \\830592 &:= (((-(2 - 95)) + 0!)^3) + 8)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}830595 &:= (((((5! \times 9!) / 50) + 3) - 8!) \\830648 &:= (8 \times (((46 + 0!)^3) + 8)) \\830784 &:= (4! \times (((((8 + 7!) - 0!) - 3!!) \times 8)) \\831537 &:= (-((7 \times 3)) \times (((((5 + 1))!) + 3) - 8!)) \\831575 &:= (5 \times ((7! - 5) - (-((1 + 3)) \times 8!)) \\831579 &:= (((9 + 7) + 5) \times ((-1 - 3!!) + 8!)) \\831592 &:= (((((2 + 9))!) / (51 - 3)) - 8) \\831603 &:= (3 \times (0! + (-((6 + 1)) \times (3!! - 8!))) \\831624 &:= (4! + (((((2 \times 6) - 1))!) / 3!) / 8)) \\831684 &:= (((4 + 8!) - 6!) \times (13 + 8)) \\831765 &:= (((((5 + 6))!) \times (7! + 1)) / (3! \times 8!)) \\833247 &:= ((7 + ((4 \times 2) - 3))!) \times (3^8)) \\833471 &:= (-1 + ((((-7 + 4!) \times (3!^{3!})) + 8!)) \\833765 &:= ((5 \times (6! + (7^{3!}))) + (3! \times 8!)) \\833768 &:= ((((((8! - 6!) \times (-7)) - 3!!) \times (-3)) + 8) \\834048 &:= (((8! - (4!^{04})) \times (-3)) - 8!) \\834768 &:= ((8! + (-(((6^7) \times 4)) \times 3!)) / (-8)) \\834897 &:= (-7 \times ((9 + (8! / 4!)) + (-3 \times 8!)) \\835056 &:= ((6! / 5) \times (-0! - ((-5 - 3!!) \times 8)) \\835125 &:= ((5^{2+1}) \times (5! + (3^8))) \\835569 &:= (9 \times (((6! \times 5!) - 5!) + (3^8))) \\835919 &:= ((9 \times (-1 - ((-9 - 5!) \times 3!))) + 8) \\835925 &:= ((5 \times 29) \times (5 + (3!! \times 8))) \\835939 &:= ((9 \times ((3!! \times (9 + 5!)) + 3)) - 8) \\835991 &:= (-1 + (9 \times (((9 + 5!) \times 3!!) + 8)) \\836346 &:= (-6 + (4! \times (((3! + 6!) \times 3!) \times 8)) \\836352 &:= (((((2 \times 5))!) / 3) + ((6^{3!}) \times (-8))) \\836544 &:= ((4! + ((4! + 5!) \times (6! + 3!))) \times 8) \\836584 &:= (-4 \times (((8^5) + 6) - (3! \times 8!)) \\836592 &:= (-29) \times (((5 \times 6!) + 3!) \times (-8)) \\837138 &:= (-83) \times (((-1 + 7!) \times 3!) - 8!) \\837456 &:= ((-6 + ((5! + 4!) \times (7 + 3!))) \times 8) \\837504 &:= (4! \times (((((0! + 5))!) + 7) \times (3! \times 8)) \\837567 &:= ((7! - 6!) - ((5! + 7) \times (-3^8))) \\837568 &:= (8 \times (((6! / 5) \times (7 + 3!)) + 8)) \\837633 &:= (3 \times (((3 + (6^7)) - 3!!) - 8)) \\837635 &:= (-5 - (((3!! - (6^7)) \times 3) + 8)) \\837644 &:= (-4 + (4! \times (((6^7) - 3!!) / 8)) \\837648 &:= (((8 - 4))! \times (((6^7) - 3!!) / 8)) \\837656 &:= ((((-6 \times 5!) + (6^7)) \times 3) + 8) \\837662 &:= (((2 - 6!) + (6^7)) \times 3) + 8)\end{aligned}$$

- 837663 := $(-3 \times (6! - (((6^7) - 3) + 8)))$
837664 := $(4! - (((6! - (6^7)) \times 3) + 8))$
837984 := $((4 + 8) \times ((97 \times 3!) - 8))$
838464 := $((-4!) + ((-6 \times 4!) \times (-8 - 3!))) \times 8$
838648 := $((8 \times 4!) \times ((6! + 8) \times 3!) - 8)$
838656 := $((((6 + 5)! / (-6 - (-8!) / 3!))) + 8!)$
839376 := $((6^7) \times 3) + ((9 \times 3!) \times (-8))$
839424 := $((4! \times 2) \times ((4! \times (9^3)) - 8))$
839664 := $(4! \times (-6 - (6 \times ((9^3) \times 8))))$
839733 := $((3 \times ((3!^7) - 9)) - (3! \times 8))$
839784 := $-((4! - ((8 \times (7 + 9)) \times (3^8)))$
839808 := $8 \times (-0! + 8 + 9) \times 3^8$
840936 := $((6! \times 3!) + ((9! - (04!) - 8!))$
840963 := $((3! \times 6!) + (((9! - 0!) + 4) - 8!))$
840966 := $(((((6! \times 6!) + 9!) + (-((0! - 4)!)) - 8!)$
841675 := $(-5 - (7 \times (6! + ((1 - 4) \times 8!))))$
841687 := $(-7 \times (((8! + 6!) - 1) - (4 \times 8!)))$
843264 := $(4! \times (((-((6^2)) \times 3!) \times 4!) + 8!))$
843337 := $((7^{3!}) - ((3 \times 3!) \times (4 - 8!)))$
843375 := $((5 + 7!) - 3!) \times (3 + (4! \times 8))$
843624 := $-((4! - (((26^3) \times 48)))$
843696 := $((-69) + 6!) \times (3!^{-4+8})$
844704 := $((4 - 0!) \times 7) \times ((4! \times (-4)) + 8!))$
845117 := $(7 \times ((11^{5!/4!}) - 8!))$
845712 := $(-21) \times (((7 + 5) \times 4) - 8!))$
845875 := $(-5 + (-7 \times ((8! + 5!) - (4 \times 8!))))$
845884 := $(-4 - (-8 \times ((8! - 5!) + (4^8))))$
845888 := $((8 \times 8!) + (-8 \times (5! - (4^8))))$
846142 := $(-2 - (4! \times (((1 + 6)! + 4!) - 8!)))$
846144 := $-(((4! \times (4! + ((1 + 6)!)) - (4! \times 8!)))$
846216 := $((6 - 1) - 26) \times (4! - 8!)$
846341 := $(-1 + ((4! - 3) \times ((6 - 4!) + 8!)))$
846342 := $((24 - 3) \times ((6 - 4!) + 8!))$
846573 := $((3 \times 7) \times (-(((5 + 6) - 4)) + 8!))$
846576 := $(-6 \times (((7! \times 5) - 6) \times (-4)) - 8!))$
846594 := $(((((4! - 9!) \times (-5)) - 6) - (4! \times 8!))$
846595 := $(((-5 - 9!) - 5!) - ((-6 - 4!) \times 8!))$
846636 := $((((6 + 3) + 6) + 6) \times (-4 + 8!))$
846672 := $((2 + 7)! - ((6 + 6) \times (4 - 8!)))$
846678 := $((8 + 7) + 6) \times (-((6 - 4)) + 8!))$
846679 := $((9! + 7) - ((6 + 6) \times (4 - 8!)))$
846698 := $(((((8! \times 9!) / 6!) - 6!) / 4!) + 8)$
846708 := $((8! - 0!) + (7! \times 6)) \times (4 + 8)$
846714 := $((4! \times (-1)) \times 7!) - 6) + (4! \times 8!))$
846718 := $((8 + 1)! \times 7 - 6) / (4! / 8)$
846719 := $((9! - 1) - (7! \times (-6)) \times (4! - 8!))$
846738 := $((8! \times (3 \times 7)) + ((6 + 4) + 8))$
846744 := $((44 \times 7!) + 6) \times 4 - 8!$
846773 := $(-3 - (-7 \times ((7! \times (6 \times 4)) + 8)))$
846774 := $((4! \times 7) \times 7!) + (6 + 48)$
846777 := $((-7 \times (-7 - (7! \times (6 \times 4)))) + 8)$
846783 := $((3 + 8!) \times (((7 \times 6) \times 4) / 8))$
846784 := $(-4 \times (((8! - 7!) \times (-6)) - 4!) + 8)$
846804 := $((4! - 0!) - (8 - 6)) \times (4 + 8!))$
846808 := $(8 \times ((0! + 8!) - (6 - (4^8))))$
846824 := $-((4! - (2 \times ((8^6) + (4 \times 8!))))$
846834 := $((4! - 3) \times (8! + 6)) - (4 + 8)$
846843 := $(((-3 + 4!) \times (8! + 6)) - (4! / 8))$
846844 := $((4! - 4) \times (8! + 6)) + (4 + 8!))$
846848 := $((8! + (4^8)) \times (64 / 8))$
846871 := $(-1 - (((7! - 8!) - 6) \times 4!) - 8)$
846875 := $((-5 \times (-7 - ((8! + 6) \times 4))) + 8!)$
846879 := $(-9 + (-7 \times (((8! + 6) \times (-4)) + 8!)))$
846888 := $(-8 + (8 \times (8! + (6 + (4^8))))$
846936 := $(6^3) + (((9! / 6!) / 4!) \times 8!))$
847217 := $(-7 - (-(((1 + 2) \times 7)) \times (4! + 8!)))$
847224 := $((4 + 2) / 2) \times 7) \times (4! + 8!))$
847244 := $(-4 - (4! \times (((2 + 7!) - 4!) - 8!)))$
847248 := $((8! + 4!) \times (2 \times (7 + 4))) - 8!$
847287 := $(-7 \times (((8! + (27)) \times 4!) / (-8)))$
847288 := $((8! + ((8/2)!)) - 7!) \times 4! - 8)$
847296 := $(-((6 + (9 \times 2))) \times ((7! - 4!) - 8!))$
847304 := $((4! \times (((0! + 3!) \times 7!) + 4!)) + 8)$
847308 := $((8 - 0!) \times 3) \times ((7 \times 4) + 8!))$
847335 := $(5! + (3 \times (-3 - (-7 \times (4! + 8!))))$
847344 := $(4! \times (((-4 + 3!) - 7!) + 4!) + 8!))$
847356 := $((6 \times 5!) + ((3 \times 7) \times (-4 + 8!)))$
847357 := $(-7 \times (5 + (3 \times ((7! + 4) \times (-8))))$
847371 := $((1 \times 7) \times 3) \times ((7 + 4!) + 8!))$
847376 := $((6 - ((7! + 3) \times (-7))) \times 4!) + 8)$
847392 := $((2 \times 9) + 3) \times ((7! + 4) \times 8)$
847407 := $((7 \times (0! - ((-4 - 7!) \times 4!))) + 8)$
847415 := $((5! - 1) - (4! \times ((7! - 4!) - 8!)))$

$$\begin{aligned} 847416 &:= (((6-1))! - (4! \times ((7! - 4!) - 8!))) \\ 847435 &:= ((-5 + 3!!) + ((4! - (7-4)) \times 8!)) \\ 847464 &:= ((4! + 6!) + ((4! - (7-4)) \times 8!)) \\ 847475 &:= (((5 + (7! \times 4!)) \times 7) + (((4!/8))!)) \\ 847476 &:= (6! + ((7 \times ((4! \times 7!) + 4)) + 8)) \\ 847488 &:= (((8! + (8 \times 4)) - 7!) \times (-((4-8))!)) \\ 847496 &:= (6! + (((9! + 4!) \times (-7))/4!) \times (-8)) \\ 847533 &:= (3 \times ((3^5) - (-7 \times (4 + 8!)))) \\ 847552 &:= ((((((2+5))! + 5) \times 7) \times 4!) - 8) \\ 847568 &:= (((8! + ((6! + 5) \times (-7))) \times 4!) + 8) \\ 847584 &:= (4! \times (((8 \times 5) - 7!) - 4) + 8!) \\ 847671 &:= (-1 + (-7 \times (((-6-7!) \times 4!) + 8))) \\ 847672 &:= (((-2 - ((7! + 6) \times (-7))) \times 4!) - 8) \\ 847704 &:= (4! \times (((0! - 7!) \times (-7)) + (48))) \\ 847728 &:= (((8-2) + 7!) \times 7) \times (-((4-8))!) \\ 847733 &:= (-3 - (((3! + 7!) \times (-7)) \times 4!) - 8) \\ 847734 &:= ((4! \times ((3! + 7!) \times 7)) + ((4!/8))!) \\ 847736 &:= ((((((6-3))! + 7!) \times 7) \times 4!) + 8) \\ 847812 &:= (-21) \times (-((8 \times 7) - 4) - 8!) \\ 847824 &:= (4! \times (((-2 + 8!) - 7!) + (48))) \\ 848484 &:= (((4!/(-8)) + 4!) \times (84 + 8!)) \\ 848769 &:= (((9^6) - 7!) - ((8! - 4!) \times (-8))) \\ 848776 &:= (6! + ((7 \times ((7! + 8) \times 4!)) - 8)) \\ 850296 &:= (((-6 + (9^{(2+0!)})/5) \times 8) \\ 850319 &:= -(((9! + 1) - (30 \times (5! + 8!)))) \\ 850344 &:= (4! + (((4! + 3!)^{-0!+5}) + 8!)) \\ 851747 &:= ((7! \times ((4! \times 7) + 1)) - (5 + 8)) \\ 851759 &:= (((9 + 5!) \times 7!) - 1) + (5 \times 8!) \\ 851768 &:= ((8! \times 6) - ((7! \times (-1 - 5!)) - 8)) \\ 851773 &:= (((3! + 7) \times 7!) + 1) \times (5 + 8) \\ 851944 &:= -((4! - ((4^{9-1}) \times (5 + 8)))) \\ 852347 &:= ((-((7^4)) \times ((3!!/(-2)) + 5)) - 8) \\ 853777 &:= (((7^7) + (7! \times 3!)) - (-((5-8))!)) \\ 853988 &:= ((8 \times 8!) + ((9^{3!}) - (5 + 8))) \\ 853993 &:= ((-3 + 9!) + (((9^{3!}) - 5) - 8!)) \\ 853998 &:= ((-8 + 9!) + (((9^{3!}) + 5) - 8!)) \\ 855294 &:= ((4! + 9) \times (-2 - ((5! \times 5!) - 8!))) \\ 855945 &:= (((5 + 4!) \times (9 \times (5^5))) + 8!) \\ 856087 &:= ((7^{8-0!}) + (-((6^5)) + 8!)) \\ 856775 &:= (-5 \times (((7! \times (-7 \times 6)) + 5) + 8!)) \\ 858235 &:= (-5 - (3!! \times (-((2+8)) \times 5! + 8))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 858264 &:= (4! - (6! \times ((-((2+8)) \times 5!) + 8))) \\ 858368 &:= (((8!/6) - 3!) - 8) \times (5! + 8) \\ 859632 &:= ((2 \times (((3!^6) + 9!) + 5!)) + 8!) \\ 859648 &:= (((8! - 4!)/(-((6-9))!)) \times (5! + 8)) \\ 859847 &:= ((7 + 4!) \times ((-8 - 9!) + (5^8))) \\ 860544 &:= (4! \times (((4! + ((5 + 0!))!) \times (-6)) + 8!)) \\ 861745 &:= ((-5 + 4!) \times ((7! + (1 - 6)) + 8!)) \\ 861835 &:= (-5 + ((3 \times (8 - 1)) \times (6! + 8!))) \\ 861842 &:= (-2 \times ((4! - 8!) - (-((1-6))^8)) \\ 862552 &:= (((((2 \times 5) \times 5!) - 2) \times 6!) - 8) \\ 863137 &:= ((7^{3!+1}) - ((3! + 6!) - 8!)) \\ 863143 &:= (((3 + 4)^{1+3!}) - (6! - 8!)) \\ 863295 &:= ((-5 \times (((9!/(-2)) - 3) + 6!)) - 8!) \\ 863424 &:= (4! \times (-24) - ((3! \times 6!) - 8!)) \\ 863544 &:= (-4 \times (4! - (((5!^3) - 6!)/8)) \\ 863743 &:= (((3 + 4)^7) - ((3!!/6) - 8!)) \\ 863857 &:= ((7^{5+8-3!}) - (6 - 8!)) \\ 863864 &:= ((4! \times ((-6 + 8!) - (3! \times 6!))) + 8) \\ 863877 &:= (((7^7) + 8) + (-((3-6))!)) + 8! \\ 864006 &:= (6 \times (0! - (((0! + 4!) \times 6!) \times (-8))) \\ 864024 &:= (4! - (-20) \times ((4 \times 6!) + 8!)) \\ 864036 &:= (6 \times (3! - (((0! + 4!) \times 6!) \times (-8))) \\ 864384 &:= ((4! \times (((8 + 3!)^4) - 6!)) - 8!) \\ 864607 &:= ((7^{0!+6}) + ((4! + 6!) + 8!)) \\ 864624 &:= (4! \times (2 + (((6! - 4) \times (-6)) + 8!)) \\ 864719 &:= -(((9! + 1) - ((-7 - 4!) \times (6! - 8!))) \\ 864864 &:= (((4 \times ((6 + 8))!)/(4 + 6))/8!) \\ 865432 &:= (((2 + ((3! + 4) \times 5!)) \times 6!) - 8) \\ 866872 &:= (((2 \times 7) \times 86) \times 6!) - 8) \\ 866875 &:= (-5 + (7! \times (-86 \times (6 - 8)))) \\ 866879 &:= (((9! \times (7 + 8)) - 6)/6) - 8! \\ 866938 &:= (((8^{3!}) + 9!) + 6) - (-6 \times 8!) \\ 867246 &:= (((6!/4) \times (2 + 7!)) + (6 - 8!)) \\ 869424 &:= (4! \times (2 - ((4^{(9-6)!}) - 8!)) \\ 871224 &:= (4! - (22 \times (-((1-7))! - 8!)) \\ 871928 &:= (((82 + 91) \times 7!) + 8) \\ 872648 &:= ((8! \times 4!) - (((6 \times 2)!/7!) - 8)) \\ 874656 &:= ((6^5) - (((6!/(-4)) \times 7!) + 8!)) \\ 874944 &:= (4! \times (((49 \times 4!) - 7!) + 8!)) \\ 875528 &:= (((8! \times ((2^5) + 5!))/7) + 8) \\ 876722 &:= (-22) \times ((7 \times 67) - 8!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}876951 &:= (-1 + (((5! + ((9 \times 6))) \times 7!) - 8)) \\876959 &:= (-9 + (((5! + ((9 \times 6))) \times 7!) + 8)) \\877128 &:= (-(((8 - (2^{17})) \times 7)) - 8!) \\877142 &:= (((-2 - 4!) \times ((1 + 7!) \times (-7))) - 8!) \\877184 &:= (((4^8) \times ((1 \times 7) + 7)) - 8!) \\877192 &:= (-29) \times (((1 - 7) \times 7!) - 8) \\877296 &:= (-6 \times ((9!/(-2)) + (7 \times (7! - 8)))) \\877543 &:= ((3!! \times (4! - 5)) + ((7^7) + 8!)) \\878736 &:= (-6 \times ((37 \times (-8 - 7!)) + 8!)) \\880695 &:= (((5! \times (9^{6-0!})) - 8!)/8) \\881264 &:= -((4! - (((6!^2) + ((1 + 8)!)) + 8))) \\881266 &:= (-6 + (((6!^2) + ((1 + 8)!)) - 8)) \\881369 &:= (9! - ((-6!) \times 3!!) - (1 + 88)) \\881672 &:= (((2 \times 7!) - (61)) \times 88) \\884224 &:= ((4! - 2) \times (-(((2^4) \times 8)) + 8!)) \\884544 &:= -((4! \times (((4! + 5!) \times 4!) + 8) - 8!)) \\884736 &:= (((6 - (3! \times (-7)))^{4!/8}) \times 8) \\884744 &:= (((4! \times 4)^{7+4-8}) + 8) \\884864 &:= -(((4! \times (6! - 8!)) + (-((4 - 8)!^8))) \\885248 &:= (8 \times (((4!^{-2+5}) + 8) \times 8)) \\885324 &:= ((4! - 2) \times ((3! \times (-5 + 8))) + 8!)) \\885456 &:= (-((6 + 5)) \times (((4! + 5!) - 8!) - 8!)) \\885599 &:= (((-((9 - (9^5))) \times 5!) - 8)/8) \\885744 &:= (4! - ((4 + 7) \times ((5! - 8!) - 8!)) \\886315 &:= (-5 + (((13!) \times 6)/8! - 8!)) \\886319 &:= ((9! - 1) - ((3!! \times (-6!)) - (8!/8))) \\886328 &:= (((8! \times 23) - 6!) + 8) - 8! \\886386 &:= -((6! - ((8! + 3) \times ((6 + 8) + 8)))) \\886456 &:= (((6^5) \times (4! - (6!/(-8)))) - 8) \\886464 &:= (4! \times (((6! - (4^6)) + 8!) - 8)) \\886732 &:= ((-2 + (-((3 - 7)!)) \times ((-6 + 8!) - 8)) \\886741 &:= (((1 - 4!) \times ((7 + 6) - 8!)) - 8!) \\886848 &:= ((-8 \times 4!) - (8! \times (-((6 + 8) + 8)))) \\886878 &:= (((8! + 7) \times ((8 + 6) + 8)) - 8) \\886878 &:= (8! - 7) \times (8 + 6 + 8) - 8 \\886944 &:= ((-4 \times (4! - 9!)) - ((6 + 8) \times 8!)) \\886948 &:= (8! - 4) \times (9 + 6 + 8) - 8! \\886974 &:= (-((4 + 7)) \times (((9 - 6)! - 8!) - 8!)) \\887018 &:= -(((8! - 1) \times (0! - ((7 + 8) + 8)))) \\887024 &:= (((4! - 2) \times ((0! + 7)!)) - (8 + 8)) \\887029 &:= (-((9 + 2)) \times (((0 \times 7)! - 8!) - 8!))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}887032 &:= (((23 - ((0 \times 7)!)) \times 8!) - 8) \\887035 &:= (-5 + (((-3 + 0!) \times 7!) \times (-88))) \\887038 &:= ((-8 + 3!) \times (0! + (7! \times (-88)))) \\887039 &:= (((((9!/(-3)) - 0!) \times (-7)) + 8!) - 8) \\887052 &:= (2 \times ((5 + 0!) - (7! \times (-88)))) \\887064 &:= (4! - (((-6 - 0!) - (7 + 8)) \times 8!)) \\887104 &:= (((((4! - 0!) - 1) \times 7!) + 8) \times 8) \\887133 &:= ((3 \times (31 - (-7 \times 8!))) + 8!) \\887162 &:= (2 \times (61 - (7! \times (-88)))) \\887184 &:= ((4! \times (8! - ((1 - 7)))) - (8! + 8!)) \\887202 &:= (((20 + 2) \times (7 + 8!)) + 8) \\887208 &:= (8! + (((0! + 2) \times 7) \times (8 + 8!))) \\887216 &:= (((((6 + 1)! + 2) + 7!) \times 88) \\887224 &:= (((4! - (-22) \times 7!)) \times 8) - 8) \\887376 &:= (((6 - (7! \times (-3))) \times (7 \times 8)) + 8!) \\887422 &:= ((22 \times ((4! - 7) + 8!)) + 8) \\887424 &:= ((4! \times (((2^4) - 7!) + 8!)) + 8!) \\887448 &:= -8! + 4! \times (4! - 7 + 8!) - 8! \\887744 &:= (((4 + 4) + 7!) + 7!) \times 88) \\887936 &:= (6! + ((3! + ((9 + 7))) \times (8 + 8!))) \\888384 &:= ((4! \times ((8!/3!!) + 8!)) - ((8! + 8!))) \\888424 &:= -((4! - ((2 - 4!) \times (-((8 \times 8) - 8!)))) \\888448 &:= (((8!/4) + 4!) - 8) \times 88) \\888604 &:= (((4! - 0!) \times (68 + 8!)) - 8!) \\888976 &:= (((6 + 7) + 9) \times (8! + (88))) \\892274 &:= ((-4 + 7!) + (-22) \times (-9 - 8!)) \\892791 &:= (((-1 + ((9!/(-7)) \times (-2))) \times 9) - 8!) \\892795 &:= (-5 + (((9!/(-7)) \times (-2 \times 9))) - 8!)) \\892856 &:= (((((6 \times 5!) + 8)^2) + 9!) - 8) \\892862 &:= ((-2 + ((6! + 8)^2)) - (-9 \times 8!)) \\892866 &:= (-6 + (((6! + 8)^2) + 9!) + 8) \\893376 &:= (((((6 + 7) \times 3!)^3) - 9!) \times 8) \\893528 &:= (((-(((8 + 2)^5)) + 3!!) \times (-9)) + 8) \\893609 &:= (((9^0 6) - 3!!) + (9! + 8)) \\893664 &:= (((4! \times 6) \times (6 - (3!! \times (-9)))) - 8!) \\893699 &:= (((9! + (9^6)) - 3!!) + (98)) \\893784 &:= (4! \times (8! - (((7^3) \times 9) - 8))) \\893953 &:= ((-3 \times 5!) + (((9^3) + 9!) - 8)) \\894289 &:= (((9^{8-2} - 4!) + 9!) - 8) \\894309 &:= (((9^{03!} - 4) + 9!) - 8) \\894313 &:= (((((3 \times 1)^3)^4) + 9!) - 8)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 894321 &:= (((1+2)^3)^4) - (-9 \times 8!) \\
 894329 &:= (((9^2)/3)^4) + 9! + 8 \\
 894333 &:= (((3 \times 3)^{3!}) + 4) + 9! + 8 \\
 894339 &:= (((9^{3!}) + 3!) + 4) + 9! + 8 \\
 894345 &:= (((5+4)^{3!}) + 4!) - (-9 \times 8!) \\
 895464 &:= (4! \times (((6! \times (-4)) - 5!) - 9) + 8!) \\
 895837 &:= (((7^{3!}) \times 8) + 5) - (9!/8) \\
 898344 &:= (4! \times ((-4 \times 3!) + ((8! - (9!/8)))))) \\
 898524 &:= ((4! - 2) \times ((58 \times 9) + 8!)) \\
 898552 &:= ((2 \times ((5! \times ((-(5-8))!)!) + 9!)) - 8) \\
 902671 &:= (((-1+7!) - 6!) \times 209) \\
 906471 &:= (((-1 - (7!/(-4))) \times 6!) - 09) \\
 906849 &:= (((9! + 4!) - (8^6) + 0!) \times 9) \\
 906984 &:= (((4! - 8!) - (9!/6)) \times (0 - 9)) \\
 907155 &:= (-5 \times (((-(5-1) \times 7!) + 0!) \times 9)) \\
 907164 &:= (-4 \times (((6-1) \times 7!) - 0!) \times (-9)) \\
 907191 &:= (((19+1) \times 7!) - 0!) \times 9) \\
 907199 &:= (((9! \times 9)/(-1-7)) - 0!) + 9! \\
 907209 &:= ((90 \times 2) \times 7!) + 09) \\
 907236 &:= ((6 \times 3) \times (2 + (7! \times (0! + 9)))) \\
 907335 &:= (5 \times (((3! \times 3!) \times (7! + 0!)) - 9)) \\
 907353 &:= ((-3 + ((5!/3!) \times (7! + 0!))) \times 9) \\
 907383 &:= ((3 \times ((8^{3!}) + ((7+0!)!)) - 9) \\
 907574 &:= (-4 - ((7^5) \times ((7-0!) \times (-9)))) \\
 907584 &:= (4! \times (((8^5) + 7!) - 0!) + 9) \\
 909333 &:= (-3 \times (3!! + (((3^{9+0!}) - 9!))) \\
 909864 &:= (-((4! \times ((6! - 8!) + 9))) - ((0! - 9)!)) \\
 911493 &:= (3 \times (9! - ((4-1)^{1+9})) \\
 912384 &:= (4! \times (-(((8 \times 3!)^2)) + (-((1-9)!))!) \\
 914248 &:= (((84-2)^{4-1}) + 9!) \\
 917281 &:= ((182 \times 7!) + (1^9)) \\
 917462 &:= ((2 + (6!/4)) \times (7! + (1^9))) \\
 918477 &:= ((-7 - ((7!/(-4)) \times 81)) \times 9) \\
 921456 &:= (((6!/5!)^4) \times (((1+2)!!) - 9)) \\
 921591 &:= (((-(1-9)) \times 5!)^{1 \times 2}) - 9) \\
 921609 &:= (((9-0!) \times ((6-1)!))^2) + 9) \\
 922382 &:= (((28+3!)^2) - (2-9!)) \\
 922736 &:= (((-6 + ((3!^7) - 2)) \times 2) + 9!) \\
 922738 &:= (((8 - (3!^7)) \times (-2)) + (2+9!)) \\
 922739 &:= (9! + (((3!^7) - 2) \times 2) - 9) \\
 922756 &:= (((((6!/5!)^7) + 2) \times 2) + 9!) \\
 922764 &:= (((4 + ((6^7) + 2)) \times 2) + 9!) \\
 922766 &:= (((6 + (6^7)) \times 2) + 2) + 9! \\
 922944 &:= ((4!)/((4! + ((9^2))) \times ((2 \times 9)!)) \\
 923038 &:= ((8! - 3) + (((0! + 3!))^2) + 9!) \\
 923413 &:= ((31^4) - (3! \times (2 \times 9))) \\
 924162 &:= ((-2 - (((6! + 1) \times 4)^2))/(-9)) \\
 924473 &:= ((3!! \times ((7!/4) + 4!)) + ((2-9))) \\
 925315 &:= (((5! - 1) \times (3!^5)) - (29)) \\
 925351 &:= (((-1 + 5!) \times (3!^5)) - ((2-9))) \\
 925353 &:= (((3!^5) \times ((-3 + 5!) + 2)) + 9) \\
 925437 &:= (-7 + (((3! + (4! \times 5!))^2)/9)) \\
 925444 &:= (((4!/4) + (4! \times 5!))^2)/9) \\
 925848 &:= -((8! - (4! \times (8! - ((5+2) \times 9)))) \\
 925888 &:= (8! - 8 \times 8) \times (5 + 2 \times 9) \\
 926586 &:= (6 \times (((8+5)!)/(6+2)! - 9)) \\
 926631 &:= (((13!) \times 6)/(6+2)! - 9) \\
 926635 &:= (-5 + (3!! \times ((6 \times 6)^2 - 9))) \\
 926649 &:= (((9+4)! \times 6)/(6+2)! + 9) \\
 926664 &:= (4! + (6! \times (((6 \times 6)^2) - 9))) \\
 926848 &:= -((8! + (((4 \times 8!) \times (-6)) + (2^9)))) \\
 927245 &:= ((5 - ((4 \times 2)!)) \times (-((7 \times 2) + 9))) \\
 927248 &:= (((8 - ((4 \times 2)!)) \times (-7 \times 2)) + 9!) \\
 927268 &:= ((8! - (6-2)) \times ((7 \times 2) + 9)) \\
 927284 &:= (((4! - ((8! - 2) \times 7)) \times (-2)) + 9!) \\
 927318 &:= (((8! \times (-1)) + 3) \times (-7 \times 2)) + 9! \\
 927324 &:= (-4 \times ((23 \times 7!) \times (-2)) + 9) \\
 927325 &:= ((5 \times ((2^3)! - 7)) - (-2 \times 9!)) \\
 927355 &:= (-5 + (((5+3)! \times ((7 \times 2) + 9))) \\
 927358 &:= (((8! \times ((5-3) \times 7)) - 2) + 9!) \\
 927369 &:= (((9 - (6! \times (3-7)))^2)/9) \\
 927384 &:= (4! - (((8^3) \times 7!)/(-2)) + 9!) \\
 927388 &:= ((((-8-8!) + 3!) \times (-7 \times 2)) + 9!) \\
 927418 &:= ((8! \times (-1+4!)) + ((7^2) + 9)) \\
 927488 &:= (((-8 \times 8) \times ((-4 \times 7!) - 2)) - 9!) \\
 927582 &:= (-2 - (((8-5!) \times (7! + 2)) - 9!)) \\
 927728 &:= (8 \times ((2+7!) \times ((7 \times 2) + 9))) \\
 927759 &:= (((-9+5!) \times (7! + ((7^2)))) + 9!) \\
 927843 &:= (((3-4!) - 8!) \times (-((7 \times 2) + 9))) \\
 927856 &:= (6! + (((5! - 8) \times (7! - 2)) + 9!)) \\
 928004 &:= -(((4! - 0!) \times ((0! - 8!) - (29)))) \\
 928043 &:= (3!! + (((4! - 0!) \times (8! - 2)) + 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 928073 := (3!! - ((7 × (0! - (8! × 2))) - 9!))
928384 := (((4⁸⁺³) - ((8 + 2)!) + 9!)
928448 := (((8! + 4!) × 4!) - 8!) + (2⁹)
928832 := ((23 × 8) × (8 + (-((2 - 9))))!)
928841 := (((-1 + 4!) × (8! + (8²))) + 9)
929875 := (-((5⁷)) + (((8! - 9!) × (-2)) + 9!))
930483 := (((3!! - 8!) × (-4! - 0!)) + ((3⁹))
930735 := ((5 × 37) × (((0! + 3!)! - 9))
931824 := (4! × (((-((2 - 8)))! - 1) × (3! × 9)))
932149 := ((((-9 + ((4 + 1)!)! - 2)³) - 9!)
932544 := (4! × (-4!) - (((5 - 2)!)! × (3! × (-9))))
932634 := (((4! × ((3! × 6!) - 2)) - 3!) × 9)
932688 := ((8! + (-8 × (6! + 2))) × (3 × 9))
932832 := ((2 × (3!! - (8²))) × (3!! - 9))
932904 := (4! × (((0! - ((9 - 2)!)! + 3!!) × (-9)))
933039 := (9 × (((3!! / (-0! - 3!)) × 3!!) - 9))
933048 := ((8 + ((-4!) × ((03!)!) × 3!)) × (-9))
933057 := ((7 - ((5! + ((0! + 3)!) × 3!!)) × (-9))
933066 := (((6! × 6!) / (0! - 3!)) + 3!) × (-9))
933093 := (3 × (((9! / (0! + 3!)) × 3!) - 9))
933114 := (((4 - 1)!) × (-1 + ((3!! × 3!!) - 9!))
933135 := ((5! × (3!^{-1+3!})) + (3! + 9))
933142 := (-2 - (4! × (-1 + (3!! × (3! × (-9))))))
933144 := (4! - ((4! × (((1 × 3)!)!) × (3! × (-9))))
933145 := (-5 × ((-4 × (-1 + (3!^{3!}))) - 9))
933156 := (-6 × (((5 + 1)!)! × 3!!) - (3! - 9!))
933165 := ((-5 - ((6! × ((1 + 3)!)! × 3!)) × (-9))
933168 := ((8 × 6) × (1 + (3!! × (3 × 9))))
933174 := (((4! × ((7 - 1)!)! × 3!) + 3!) × 9)
933264 := (((4! + (6!²)) × 3!) - (3! × 9!))
933336 := (6 × ((3!! × 3!!) + (((3! × 3!) - 9!)))
933384 := (4! × ((8 + 3) - (3!! × (3! × (-9))))
933437 := (-7 + (((3!! × 4!) + (3!)) × (3! × 9))
933444 := (((-4!) × ((4! / 4)!) - (3!)) × (3! × (-9))
933462 := ((2 + (((6! × 4!) + 3!) × 3!)) × 9)
933474 := (-4!) - ((7 + (4! × 3!)) × (3! × (-9)))
933546 := (-6 - ((4! + 5!) × (-3 + (3!! × (-9))))
933552 := ((((-((2 - 5)))!)! / 5) × (3 - (3!! × (-9))))
933696 := (-6 × (-96) - ((3!! × 3!!) - 9!))
933744 := (-4!) - (4! × (((7! + 3) - 3!!) × (-9)))
933768 := (8 × (((6! - 7!) - 3) × (-3 × 9)))
933947 := (((74 + 9)³) - 3!!) + 9!
933984 := ((4! - 8) × (((9 × 3!!) + (3!)) × 9))
934407 := (((-(((7 × 0)!)! - 4!) - 4!))³) × 9)
934413 := (3! - ((((-1 + 4!) + 4!)³) × (-9))
934416 := (((6! + (1⁴)) × 4!) × 3!) × 9)
934542 := (2 × (((4! + ((5⁴))) × 3!!) - 9))
934578 := ((-8 - ((7! + 5!) / (-4))) × (3!! + 9))
934667 := (((-((7 - 66)) + 4!)³) + 9!)
934702 := (-2 × ((0! + 7!) + (4! × (-3⁹))))
934858 := ((-((8⁵)) + (8! × 4!)) - (3! × 9))
935574 := (4! - (((7 + 5)!)! / (-((5 - 3)⁹)))
936648 := (8! + (((4! + 6!) × (6! - 3)) + 9!))
936753 := -(((3! - 5!) × (7! - 6)) + (3 - 9!))
936756 := (((6 - 5!) × ((-7 × 6!) + 3!)) + 9!)
937088 := (-((8 × 8) × ((0! + 7!) - (3⁹)))
937152 := (-((2⁵⁺¹)) × (7! - (3⁹)))
937268 := ((-86) × (2 + (7! × (-3)))) - 9!
937347 := ((7 + 4!) × (((3! × 7!) + 3!) - 9))
937395 := ((-5 × (9 + (3! × 7!))) + (3 × 9!))
937431 := (((((1 + 3!) + 4!) × 7!) × 3!) - 9)
937434 := ((((-4!) - 3!!) / (-4)) × 7!) + ((3 - 9))
937435 := ((-5 - ((3! + 4!) × 7!)) + (3 × 9!))
937437 := (((7! × 3!) × (4! + 7)) + (3! - 9))
937443 := (((3!! + 4!) / (-4)) × (-7!)) - (3! - 9))
937446 := (((6! + 4!) / 4) × 7!) - ((3 - 9))
937449 := (((9! / (-4)) × (4! + 7)) / (-3)) + 9)
937452 := (((2 + ((-5 + 4!) × 7!)) × 3!) + 9!)
937464 := ((4! - ((6! / 4!) × 7!)) + (3 × 9!))
937467 := (((7! × 6) × (4! + 7)) + (3 × 9))
937476 := (-6 × (((-7 - 4!) × 7!) + ((3 - 9))))
937488 := ((8 - ((8! × (-4)) + 7!)) × (-3 - 9))
937563 := (((3! + 6) × ((5⁷) + 3!)) - 9)
937626 := (62 × (-6 - ((7! × (-3)) - 9))
937863 := ((3 × (-6 - 8!)) + ((7^{3!}) × 9))
939231 := ((1 - (((3! × 2)!)! / (-9!))) × (3!! - 9))
939603 := (3 × (0! + ((-69) × 3!!) + 9!))
939687 := (((7! + 8!) + 6) + ((9^{3!}) + 9!))
939835 := (-5 + ((3!! - 8) × (((9 + 3)!)! / 9!))
939839 := ((9! + (((3 + 9)!)! × (8 - 3!))) / (-9!))
939864 := (4! + (((6! - 8) × ((9 + 3)!)! / 9!))
940533 := ((3 - (3!⁵)) × (-0!) - (-((4 - 9)!)!))
943527 := (((((7 + 2)!)! / (-5)) - 3) × (-4 + 9))

- 943584 := ((4! × ((8!/5) × 3) + 4) + 9!)
943592 := ((-2 - ((9!/5) + 3!)) × (-4 + 9))
943596 := (((-6 + (9!/(-5))) × (3! - 4!)) - 9!)
943635 := (5! + ((3 + 6!) × ((3!⁴) + 9))
943848 := (-8!) - (4! × ((-8!) - 3!) + (4! + 9)))
944064 := ((-4 × (((6 + 0!)! - ((4!⁴)))) - 9!)
944568 := (8 × ((6! × (5! + 44)) - 9))
944649 := (9 × (((4! - 6)⁴) - 4!) + 9)
944657 := ((-7 - 5!) + (((-6 + 4!)⁴) × 9))
944667 := (((7 + 6) - ((-6 + 4!)⁴)) × (-9))
944793 := (((3! + 9) × (((7 - 4!)⁴)) + 9)
944833 := (((3! × (3⁸)) × 4!) + (49))
944847 := (7 + ((4!/8)! - 4!)⁴) × 9
944928 := ((-((8 - ((2 × 9)⁴))) + 4!) × 9)
944991 := ((-((1 - ((9 + 9)⁴))) + 4!) × 9)
944995 := (-5 - ((-((9 + 9)⁴)) - 4!) × 9))
945495 := (((5 + (9⁴)) × (5! + 4!)) - 9)
945783 := (((3⁸) + 7) × (5! + 4!)) - 9)
945984 := (((4! × (-8)) + (9!/(-5))) × (-4 + 9))
946125 := ((5 + (((2 + 1)!)! × ((6⁴) + 9))
946233 := (((3³!) × (2 + (6⁴))) - 9)
946407 := ((7 × (0! + (4⁶))) × (4! + 9))
946574 := (((((4! - 7)⁵) × (-6)) - 4!)/(-9))
946736 := (((6!/3) × 7!) - 6!) - (4⁹)
946998 := (8! - (-9 × (9! + (6 - (4⁹))))))
947456 := (((6! + (5! × (-4))) × 7!) - (4⁹))
947457 := (-7 × (((5! × (-47)) × 4!) + 9))
947484 := (((4! × 8) - 4) × 7!) - (4 × 9))
947504 := (-4 × (((0! - 5!) × 7!) + 4) + 9!)
947527 := ((7 × ((2 × 5) + 7)⁴) + 9!)
947529 := (((9! + (-25) × 7!)) × 4) + 9)
947542 := (-2 - (((4 - 5!) × 7!) - 4!) - 9!)
947544 := (4! - (((4! + 5) × 7!) × (-4)) - 9!)
947583 := (((3 + 8!) + (5! × (-7))) × 4!) - 9)
947584 := (((4! - 8) + 5!) × 7!) + (4⁹)
947685 := ((-5 × (-((8⁶) - 7)) + 4!) - 9!)
947875 := ((-5 × (-7 - (8^{(7-4)!}))) - 9!)
948537 := (((7 × (3! - 5!)) + 8!) × 4!) + 9)
948873 := (((3! + ((7! - 8) × (-8))) × (-4!)) + 9)
949248 := ((8! × 4!) - ((2⁹) × 4) × 9))
949784 := (4! - ((8! + ((7! - 9!) × 4!))/9))
950184 := (4! × ((8! - ((1 + 05)!)) - 9))
950272 := (-((2⁷)²) × (0! - (59)))
950328 := (((8! - 2) - 3!) - 0!) × (-((5 - 9)!))
950385 := (((5! × ((-8!) + 3!) + 0!)/(-5)) + 9)
950386 := ((-((6! - 8!)) × ((3 + 0!)!)) - (5 + 9))
950391 := (((-((1 - 9)!)) - 3!) × (-((0! - 5)!)) - 9)
950395 := (-5 + (((9 + 3)! × ((0! + 5)!)/9!))
950399 := ((9! - ((9 + 3)! × ((0! + 5)!)))/(-9!))
950784 := (4! × ((8! + 7) - ((0! + 5)!)) + 9))
951984 := (((4⁸) × 9) - ((1 + 5)!)) + 9!)
952344 := ((4! - ((4! - 3) × ((2 + 5)!)) × (-9))
952371 := ((1 - 7!) × (-3 × ((2 + 5) × 9)))
952479 := (9 × ((7! × ((4²) + 5)) - 9))
952497 := (((7 × 9!)/4!) - (2 + 5)) × 9)
952784 := (((4⁸) + (7!/2)) × (5 + 9))
952848 := -((8! - (4! × (8! + ((-2 + 5!) × 9))))))
953125 := -((((5 × 2)^{1×3!}) - ((5⁹))))
953162 := ((2 × (6! + 1)) × (3! - 59))
953275 := (-5 + (((7! - ((2 + 3)!)) × 5!) + 9!))
953748 := (((((8! + 4) - 7!) × 3) + 5!) × 9)
953775 := ((((-5 + (7! × (-7))) × 3) - 5!) × (-9))
953856 := (((6!/5!)⁸) + ((3 - 5) × 9!))
954987 := (7! + ((8 × (9! + 4)) - ((5⁹))))
955392 := ((-((2⁹) + ((3 + 5)!)) × (-((5 - 9)!))!))
955464 := (4! × (((6! + 4) × 55) - 9))
956382 := (2 × (-8!) - ((3! × (-6!)) - ((5! - 9))))
956457 := (7 + 5! - 4) × 6⁵ + 9
956505 := ((5! + 0!) × (5! + (((6⁵) + 9))))
957258 := (((8 × 5) - 2) × ((7! × 5) - 9))
957384 := ((-4 × (8! - (3!⁷))) - (5! × 9))
957592 := (2 × ((95 × 7!) + ((5 - 9))))
957888 := ((8 + (-887) × 5!) × (-9))
957915 := (5 × ((-((1 - 9)!)) + ((7⁵) × 9)))
957942 := ((2 + (4 × 9)) × ((7! × 5) + 9))
957984 := (4! × (8! + (9 - (7 × 59))))
958311 := (((11³) × (((8 - 5)!))!)) - 9)
958329 := (((9 + 2)³) × (((8 - 5)!))! + 9)
958444 := -(((4!⁴) + (4 × ((8! + 5) - 9!))))
958464 := ((4⁶) × (((4!/8)⁵) - 9))
958545 := ((5! + ((4 - 5))) × ((8!/5) - 9))

$$\begin{aligned} 958593 &:= (-3 \times (((9!/5!) + 8!) + 5) - 9!) \\ 958959 &:= (9 \times (((5! - 9) \times 8) \times 5!) - 9) \\ 959049 &:= (((9^4) + ((0! + 9)^5)) \times 9) \\ 959355 &:= (-5 \times (((5^3)/(-9)) + 5!) + 9) \\ 959784 &:= ((4! \times (8! + 7)) - (9!/(5 \times 9))) \\ 960768 &:= ((8! + (6^7)) \times ((0 - 6) + 9)) \\ 960944 &:= (-4 \times (4 - (((9 - 0!) + 6)!/9!)) \\ 960955 &:= (-5 + (((5 + 9) - 0)!)/(6! \times 9)) \\ 960959 &:= ((9 + (((5 + 9) - 0)!)/(-6!))/(-9)) \\ 960984 &:= ((4! \times (8! - 9)) - ((0 - 6!) \times (-9))) \\ 961344 &:= ((4 \times ((4!^{3+1}) - 6!)) - 9!) \\ 961848 &:= (8 \times (((4! \times ((8 - 1)!)) - 6!) - 9)) \\ 962748 &:= (((8! \times 4!) - 7!) + (((2 \times 6) \times 9)) \\ 962984 &:= ((4! \times (8! - 9)) + (((2 + 6)!)/(-9))) \\ 963348 &:= (((8! \times 4!) - 3) - ((3! \times 6!) + 9)) \\ 963355 &:= (-5 + (((5! + 3!) - (3!)) \times 6!) + 9!) \\ 963357 &:= (((7! \times 5!) - 3) - ((3! \times 6!) - 9!)) \\ 963504 &:= (((4!^0 5)/3!) - 6!) - 9! \\ 963648 &:= (((8! \times 4!)/6!) \times ((3! + 6!) - 9)) \\ 963658 &:= (-((8 \times (5^6))) - (3 \times (-6 - 9!))) \\ 963684 &:= ((4! \times 8!) - (6 \times (3! - (6 \times 9)))) \\ 963819 &:= (((91 + 8)^3) + (6! \times (-9))) \\ 964224 &:= (((4!^2) \times 2)^{-4+6}) - 9! \\ 964233 &:= (((3! \times 3!)^2) \times (4! + 6!)) + 9) \\ 964578 &:= (8! - 7 - 5!) \times 4! - 6 \times 9 \\ 964584 &:= (4! \times (8! - (((5 \times 4) \times 6) + 9))) \\ 964656 &:= (-((6 \times 56)) \times ((-4 \times 6!) + 9)) \\ 964704 &:= (-4 \times (((0! + 7!) \times 4!) + 6!) - 9!) \\ 964784 &:= (((4! \times 8!) - 7) + ((-4 \times 6!) - 9)) \\ 964785 &:= -((((5! + (-8 \times 7!)) \times 4!) + (6 + 9))) \\ 964794 &:= (((-((4 - 9)))! \times (7! - 4!)) - (6 - 9!)) \\ 964803 &:= (((((3! - 0)! - 8!) \times (-4!)) - ((6 - 9))) \\ 964806 &:= (((((6 - 0)! - 8!) \times (-4!)) + (-((6 - 9)!))! \\ 964809 &:= ((((-90) + 8!) \times 4!) - 6!) + 9) \\ 964815 &:= (((5! \times (-1)) + 8!) \times 4!) + (6 + 9) \\ 964852 &:= (-2 - (((5! - 8!) \times 4!) - ((6 \times 9))) \\ 964854 &:= (((4! \times (-5)) + 8!) \times 4!) + ((6 \times 9)) \\ 965184 &:= (4! \times (((8! + 1) - 5!) + (6 + 9))) \\ 965439 &:= (9 \times (((3! \times 4!) + 5) \times 6!) - 9) \\ 965457 &:= ((7 - (((5! + 4!) + 5) \times 6!)) \times (-9)) \\ 965466 &:= ((-6 + (((6 \times 4!) + 5) \times 6!)) \times 9) \\ 965544 &:= (4! + (((4! + 5!) + 5) \times 6! \times 9)) \\ 965565 &:= ((-5 - (((6!/5) + 5) \times 6!)) \times (-9)) \\ 965736 &:= ((6^3) \times (7! - 569)) \\ 965784 &:= (4! \times ((8 \times (7! - (5 + 6))) + 9)) \\ 965904 &:= (4! \times ((-((0! - 9)))! - (5 + 69))) \\ 965925 &:= (((5! \times (2 + 9)) + 5) \times (6! + 9)) \\ 966024 &:= (4! \times (((2 + 06)! - 69)) \\ 966384 &:= (4! \times (8! - ((36/6) \times 9))) \\ 966834 &:= ((4! \times (-3 + 8!)) - (6! + ((6 \times 9)))) \\ 966948 &:= (((8! \times 4!) - 9) - 6!) + ((6 - 9)) \\ 966957 &:= (((7! \times 5!) + 9!) - 6!) + ((6 - 9)) \\ 966975 &:= (((5! \times 7!) + 9!) - 6!) + (6 + 9) \\ 966984 &:= (((4! \times 8!) + 9) - 6!) + (6 + 9) \\ 967248 &:= (8 \times ((4! \times (-2 + 7!)) - (-((6 - 9)!))!)) \\ 967284 &:= ((4! \times 8!) - (((2 + (7 \times 6)) \times 9)) \\ 967314 &:= (((4 + 1)! \times (-3 + 7!)) - (6 - 9!)) \\ 967337 &:= (-((7^3)) + (((3 + 7)!/6) + 9!)) \\ 967338 &:= -((((8^3) \times 3!) + (-7 \times (6 + 9!))) \\ 967344 &:= ((4! \times ((4!/3)!)) + (7!/(-(6 + 9)))) \\ 967392 &:= ((29 + 3) \times ((7! \times 6) - 9)) \\ 967452 &:= (-2 \times (5! - (((4! \times 7!) + 6) + 9!)) \\ 967464 &:= (4! \times (((((6 - 4) \times 7) - 6)! - 9)) \\ 967488 &:= ((-8 + 8!) \times ((4 \times ((7 - 6)^9)))! \\ 967536 &:= ((-6 + ((3 + 5)!)) \times (((7 + 6) - 9)!)) \\ 967542 &:= (-2 \times (((4! - 5!) \times 7!) + 69)) \\ 967552 &:= ((-2 - 5!) + (((5! \times 7!) - 6) + 9!)) \\ 967554 &:= ((4! \times (-5)) + (((5! \times 7!) - 6) + 9!)) \\ 967555 &:= ((-5 - 5!) + (((5! \times 7) \times 6!) + 9!)) \\ 967558 &:= ((-8 - 5!) + (((5! \times 7!) + 6) + 9!)) \\ 967566 &:= ((6!/(-6)) + (((5! \times 7!) + 6) + 9!)) \\ 967584 &:= ((-4 + 8!) \times ((5 - ((7 - 6)^9)))! \\ 967595 &:= (((-5 + 9!) + (5! \times 7!)) + (6!/(-9))) \\ 967599 &:= (-((9 \times 9)) + (((5! \times 7) \times 6!) + 9!)) \\ 967647 &:= 7 \times (4! \times (6! + 7!) - 6) + 9 \\ 967648 &:= (-((8 \times 4)) + (((6! \times 7!)/6) + 9!)) \\ 967653 &:= (((3 - (5! \times 6!)) \times (-7)) - (6 - 9!)) \\ 967655 &:= (-((5 \times 5)) + (((6! \times 7!)/6) + 9!)) \\ 967656 &:= (((6!/5) - (6! \times 7!))/(-6)) + 9! \\ 967667 &:= (((7!/6) \times 6!) - (7 + 6)) + 9! \\ 967673 &:= (((((3 + 7)! - (6 \times 7))/6) + 9!)) \\ 967674 &:= ((((((4 + 7) - 6)! \times 7!) - 6) + 9!)) \\ 967675 &:= (((5! \times 7!) - ((6 - 7) + 6)) + 9!)) \\ 967692 &:= (2 \times ((96 \times 7!) + (-((6 - 9)!))!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 967696 &:= (((6 + 9!)/6) \times ((7!/6!) + 9)) \\ 967704 &:= (4! \times (0! + ((77 - 69))!)) \\ 967725 &:= ((-5 - ((2^7) \times 7!)/6) \times (-9)) \\ 967728 &:= ((8! + 2) \times (((7/7) - 6) + 9))! \\ 967734 &:= ((4! \times ((3!! + 7!) \times 7)) + (6 \times 9)) \\ 967735 &:= (((5! \times 3!!) + 7) \times 7) + (6 + 9!) \\ 967745 &:= ((5 \times ((4! \times 7!) + (7 + 6))) + 9!) \\ 967748 &:= ((8! \times 4!) + ((7 + 7) + (6 \times 9))) \\ 967753 &:= (-3 + (((5! \times 7!) + 76) + 9!)) \\ 967756 &:= (((6! \times 5!) \times 7) + 76) + 9! \\ 967784 &:= ((4! \times (8! + (7/7))) - (6!/(-9))) \\ 967803 &:= (-3 \times (((0! + 8!) - (7 \times 6)) - 9!)) \\ 967815 &:= (((5 - 1))! \times ((8 \times 7!) + 6)) - 9 \\ 967824 &:= (((4 + 2) + 8!) \times (((7 + 6) - 9))!) \\ 967832 &:= (2 \times (((3 \times 8!) + 76) + 9!)) \\ 967833 &:= (3 \times (3 + ((-8 \times (7! - 6)) + 9!))) \\ 967834 &:= ((4! \times (3! + 8!)) + ((7 - 6) + 9)) \\ 967841 &:= ((-1 + (4! \times (8! + 7))) - ((6 - 9))!) \\ 967842 &:= ((24 \times (8! + 7)) - ((6 - 9))!) \\ 967844 &:= (-4 - ((-4 \times (8! + 7)) \times ((6 - 9))!)) \\ 967847 &:= ((-7 + (4! \times (8! + 7))) + ((6 - 9))!) \\ 967848 &:= 8! \times 4! - 8 \times 7 \times (6 - 9) \\ 967851 &:= (((-((1 - 5)))! \times (8! + 7)) - ((6 - 9))) \\ 967854 &:= ((4! \times (5 - (-8 \times 7!))) + (6 \times 9)) \\ 967884 &:= (-((4 - 8)) \times (((8! + 7) \times 6) + 9)) \\ 967893 &:= (-3 - ((-9 - 8!) \times (((7 + 6) - 9))!)) \\ 967894 &:= ((4! \times (9 + 8!)) + ((7!/6!) - 9)) \\ 967896 &:= (-6 \times ((9 + 8!) \times ((7 + 6) - 9))) \\ 967984 &:= ((4! \times (8! + ((9 + 7)))) + (6!/(-9))) \\ 968035 &:= (-5 - (((3 + 0!))! \times (-8! + (6 + 9)))) \\ 968064 &:= (4! \times (((6 \times 0!)! + 8!) + (6 + 9))) \\ 968168 &:= (8 \times (61 - (8! \times (6 - 9)))) \\ 968184 &:= (4! \times (8! + ((18 - 6) + 9))) \\ 968244 &:= (-4 \times (((4! - 2) + 8!) \times (-6)) - 9) \\ 968304 &:= (-((4! \times ((0! + 3) - 8!))) + ((-((6 - 9))!))! \\ 968328 &:= (((8/2))! \times (-3 + 8!)) + ((-((6 - 9))!))! \\ 968334 &:= ((4! \times ((3^3) + 8!)) + ((6 - 9))!) \\ 968337 &:= (((7 - 3))! \times (-3 + 8!)) + (6! + 9) \\ 968343 &:= (3! + ((4! \times (-3 + 8!)) + (6! + 9))) \\ 968346 &:= (6! - (((-4 \times 3!) \times 8!) + ((6 \times 9))) \\ 968368 &:= (8 \times ((6 - (-3 \times 8!)) - (6!/(-9)))) \\ 968382 &:= ((-((2 - 8)))! + (-3 \times ((8! + 6) - 9!))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 968391 &:= ((((((1^9) + 3))! \times 8!) + 6!) - 9) \\ 968393 &:= (((((3! - 9!)/(-3)) \times 8) + 6!) + 9) \\ 968395 &:= (-5 + (((9 + 3!) \times 8!) + 6!) + 9!) \\ 968424 &:= (4! \times (((2^4) + 8!) + (6 + 9))) \\ 968425 &:= (((5^2) + (4! \times 8!)) + ((-((6 - 9))!))! \\ 968433 &:= (3!! + (-3 + (-4 \times ((8! \times (-6)) - 9)))) \\ 968436 &:= (((6 - 3))! + (-4 \times ((8! \times (-6)) - 9))) \\ 968448 &:= (8 \times (((4 \times 4) - 8!) \times 6) + 9!) \\ 968457 &:= (7 \times (5! - ((4! \times (-8)) \times 6!) + 9!)) \\ 968463 &:= ((3^6) + ((4! \times 8!) + ((6 \times 9))) \\ 968466 &:= ((6! - 6) + (4! \times (8! - ((6 - 9)))) \\ 968469 &:= (((9 - 6))! + ((4! \times 8!) + 69)) \\ 968473 &:= (3!! + ((-7 + (4! \times 8!)) - (6!/(-9)))) \\ 968484 &:= (-4 \times (((-((8 \times 4) - 8!) \times 6) - 9)) \\ 968487 &:= (((((7! + 8) \times 4!) \times 8) - 6!) - 9) \\ 968544 &:= (4! \times (((-4 + 5!) + 8!) + (6!/(-9)))) \\ 968553 &:= (3!! + (((5!/5) \times (8! + 6)) + 9)) \\ 968574 &:= ((4! \times ((7 \times 5) + 8!)) + (6 \times 9)) \\ 968784 &:= (4! \times (8! + ((7 + ((8 \times 6) - 9)))) \\ 968823 &:= (((3! - 2))! \times (8! + ((8 \times 6))) - 9) \\ 968832 &:= (((-2 + 3!))! \times ((-8 \times (8! - 6)) + 9!)) \\ 968841 &:= (((1 \times 4))! \times (8! + ((8 \times 6))) + 9) \\ 968976 &:= (((6 + 7) - 9)! \times (8! + ((6 \times 9))) \\ 969024 &:= (-4!) \times ((-2 - ((0! - 9))!) - (6 \times 9)) \\ 969456 &:= ((6!/(-5)) + (4! \times ((9! + 6!)/9))) \\ 969472 &:= (-((2^7)) + (4! \times ((9! + 6!)/9))) \\ 969504 &:= (4! \times ((0! - 5) + ((9! + 6!)/9))) \\ 969528 &:= (8 \times ((2 \times (5! + (9!/6))) - 9)) \\ 969582 &:= (2 \times ((8 \times (5! + (9!/6))) - 9)) \\ 969584 &:= ((4! \times (((8 - 5)! - 9!) - 6!)/(-9)) \\ 969595 &:= (-5 + (((9 - 5))! \times ((9! + 6!)/9))) \\ 969599 &:= ((9 - (((9 - 5))! \times (9! + 6!)))/(-9)) \\ 969604 &:= (4 \times (0! - (((6! + 9!) \times 6)/(-9))) \\ 969608 &:= (8 \times (0! - ((6! + 9!)/(6 - 9))) \\ 969624 &:= (4! \times (((2 + 6))! + ((9 + 6!)/9))) \\ 969664 &:= (((4! \times ((6 - 6!) - 9!)) - 6!)/(-9)) \\ 969744 &:= -((4! - (4! \times (7 + ((9! + 6!)/9)))) \\ 969813 &:= (3 \times (((-1 \times 8!) - 9) + 6!) + 9!) \\ 969831 &:= ((-((1 \times 3)) \times ((8! - 9!) - 6!)) - 9) \\ 969835 &:= (-5 + ((3!! - (8! - 9!)) \times (-6 - 9))) \\ 969843 &:= ((3 \times (((4 - 8!) + 9!) + 6!)) - 9) \\ 969864 &:= (4! - (((6! - 8!) + 9!) \times (6 - 9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 969984 &:= (4! \times (8! + ((9 \times 96)/9))) \\ 970464 &:= (4 \times (6! - ((4! \times (0! + 7!)) - 9!))) \\ 970551 &:= (((-((1 - 5)!)) \times (5! + ((0! + 7)!)) - 9) \\ 970555 &:= (-5 - ((-5!) \times (((5 - 0)! + 7!) - 9!)) \\ 970558 &:= (((8! + 5!) \times ((5 - 0)!)) + ((7 - 9))) \\ 970584 &:= (4! \times ((8! + 5!) + ((0 \times 79)!)) \\ 972715 &:= (((5! + 1) \times 7!) + (2 - 7)) + 9! \\ 972719 &:= ((9! - 1) + (((7^2) \times 7!) + 9!)) \\ 972729 &:= ((9! \times 2) + (((7^2) \times 7!) + 9)) \\ 972744 &:= (4! + (((4 + 7)^2) \times 7!) + 9!)) \\ 972847 &:= (7! + ((4! \times (8! + 2)) + (79))) \\ 973083 &:= (((-((3 - 8)!)) + 0!) \times (3 + 7!)) + 9! \\ 973359 &:= (((-9 + 5!)^{3!/3}) \times 79) \\ 973438 &:= 8! + 3!^4 \times 3!! + 7 - 9 \\ 973443 &:= (((34^4) - 3!) - 7) - 9! \\ 973456 &:= (((6 \times 5) + 4)^{-3+7}) - 9! \\ 973584 &:= (4! \times (8! + ((5! + 3) \times (-7 - 9)))) \\ 973809 &:= (9! + ((0! + ((8 - 3)!)) \times (7! + 9))) \\ 973824 &:= (4! \times ((2^8) + ((3! - ((7 - 9)!))!)) \\ 974184 &:= ((4! \times (8! + 1)) - (((-((4 - 7)!))! \times (-9))) \\ 974568 &:= (((((-8 - 6!) \times 5!) - 4!) \times (-7)) + 9! \\ 974784 &:= ((4! \times 8) \times (7! + ((4 \times 7) + 9))) \\ 974832 &:= (((2 + (-((3 - 8)!))! \times (-4! - 7!)) + 9! \\ 975168 &:= (8 \times (6! - (((-((1 - 5)!))! \times (-7! + 9)))) \\ 975267 &:= (((7! \times 6) - ((2 - (5^7)))) \times 9) \\ 975384 &:= (4! \times ((8! + 3!) + (((5 \times 7) \times 9))) \\ 975456 &:= ((6^5) + (((4! \times 5) \times 7!) + 9!)) \\ 975738 &:= -(((8! + 3!) - ((7!/5)^{-7+9})) \\ 975744 &:= (4! \times ((4! \times ((7^5) + 7)) - 9!)) \\ 975748 &:= -8! + 4 + (7!/5)^{-7+9} \\ 975942 &:= ((2 - 4!) \times (((-9 + 5!) - 7!) \times 9)) \\ 975967 &:= (((7! + 69) \times 5!) + 7) + 9! \\ 977344 &:= (4 \times ((4^3!) + (((7 + 7)!/9!)) \\ 977623 &:= ((3!! \times (-2 + 6!)) - (-((7^7)) + 9!)) \\ 977676 &:= (-6 \times (-((7^6)) + ((7! - 7) \times (-9)))) \\ 977753 &:= (((((3 + 5!) \times 7!) - 7!) - 7) + 9! \\ 977755 &:= (-5 + (((5! \times 7!) + 7!) + 7!) + 9!)) \\ 977792 &:= (2 \times ((97 \times 7!) + ((7 + 9))) \\ 978984 &:= (4! \times ((-89) + 8!) + (7!/9)) \\ 979335 &:= (((5^3!) + (3!!/(-9))) \times (7 \times 9)) \\ 979944 &:= (4! \times (-49) - ((9! + 7!)/(-9))) \\ 982575 &:= ((-5 \times 7!) + ((5^2) \times (8! - 9))) \\ 982584 &:= (4! \times (8! + (((5 + 2)!/8) - 9)) \\ 982737 &:= (-7 \times (3!! - ((7! \times 28) - 9))) \\ 982773 &:= (3 \times (((7! - (7 + 2)) - 8!) + 9!)) \\ 983049 &:= (((-9 + 4!) \times ((0! + 3)^8)) + 9) \\ 983305 &:= ((5^{03!}) + (-3 \times (8! - 9!)) \\ 983664 &:= (4! \times (((6! - (63)) + 8!) + 9)) \\ 984074 &:= (((4^7) + 0!) + ((4! \times 8!) + 9)) \\ 984384 &:= (((-((4! - 8!)) + 3!!) \times (4! \times (-8 - 9))) \\ 984644 &:= (-4 + (4! \times (((6! - 4) + 8!) - 9)) \\ 984648 &:= (8 - 4)! \times (6! - 4 + 8! - 9) \\ 984742 &:= (-2 - (-4!) \times (((7 - 4)! + ((8! - 9)))) \\ 984744 &:= ((4! \times ((-((4 - 7)!))! + (4! \times (8! - 9))) \\ 984755 &:= (((5^5) \times (7 + (4! \times 8))) + 9! \\ 984783 &:= (((3!! + ((8! - 7))) \times (-((4 - 8)!)) - 9) \\ 984787 &:= (((7^8)/7) + (4 \times (8! - 9))) \\ 984823 &:= (((3!! - (2 - 8!)) \times 4!) - (89)) \\ 984833 &:= (((3!! - (3! - 8!)) \times 4!) + (8 + 9)) \\ 984864 &:= ((((-4 + 6!) + 8!) \times 4!) \times (-8 - 9)) \\ 984871 &:= ((((-((1 - 7)!))! + 8!) \times 4!) - (89)) \\ 985224 &:= (-4!) \times ((-2 - (((2 - 5)!))! - (8! + 9)) \\ 985575 &:= (-5 \times (7! + (-5 \times ((5! + 8!) - 9))) \\ 985777 &:= (((-((7^7)) - 7!) - (-5 \times (-8 + 9!)) \\ 987484 &:= ((4! \times 8!) + (4 \times (7! - (89)))) \\ 987537 &:= (-(((7^3) - ((5^7) \times 8))) + 9! \\ 987553 &:= (((3!^5) \times (5! + 7)) - ((8 - 9)) \\ 987804 &:= (4 \times (((0! - 8) \times (7! - 8!)) - 9)) \\ 987847 &:= (-7 \times ((-4 \times (8! - 7!)) + ((8 - 9))) \\ 987849 &:= (((-((9 \times 4) - 8)) \times (7! - 8!)) + 9) \\ 987897 &:= (((-7 + 9!) + ((8^7)/8)) + 9! \\ 987984 &:= (((((4^8) \times 9) - 7!) + 8!) + 9! \\ 988469 &:= ((((((9 + 6)!/4!) - 8!)/8!) - 9! \\ 988478 &:= ((((((8 + 7)!/4!)/8!) + 8) - 9! \\ 988584 &:= (4! \times (((8 \times 5!) + 8!) - (89))) \\ 991593 &:= ((3!! - (9^5)) \times ((1 - 9) - 9)) \\ 991755 &:= (((-5 - 5!) \times ((7! \times (-1)) + 9)) + 9! \\ 993384 &:= (4! \times ((8! + 3!!) + ((39 \times 9))) \\ 993601 &:= ((10^6) - ((3!! - 9) \times 9)) \\ 994755 &:= (((5! + 5) \times ((7! + 4!) - 9)) + 9! \\ 994851 &:= ((-1 - ((5! - 8!)/4)) \times 99) \\ 995324 &:= (4 \times (((2 \times 3!)^5) - (9/9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 995733 &:= (-3 \times ((3! \times (7! + 5!)) + (9 - 9!))) \\
 996726 &:= (-6 + (2 \times ((7! - 6) \times 99))) \\
 996732 &:= (((2 \times (-3 + 7!)) - 6) \times 99) \\
 997029 &:= ((9 + (-2 \times (07!))) \times (-99)) \\
 997128 &:= ((-8 - (-2 \times ((1 \times 7)!)) \times 99) \\
 997322 &:= (2 \times (-2 - ((-3 + 7!) \times (-99)))) \\
 997323 &:= (-3 - (2 \times ((-3 + 7!) \times (-99)))) \\
 997326 &:= ((6 - (2 \times (3! - 7!))) \times 99) \\
 997332 &:= (2 \times (3 - ((-3 + 7!) \times (-99)))) \\
 997425 &:= ((-5 - ((2 - 4) \times 7!)) \times 99) \\
 997524 &:= (((-4 + ((2 + 5)!)) + 7!) \times 99) \\
 997585 &:= ((5^8) + (5! \times (7! + ((9 + 9)))))) \\
 997623 &:= ((-3 - ((2 \times 6!) \times (-7))) \times 99) \\
 997721 &:= (-1 + (((2 - 7!) - 7!) \times (-99)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 997839 &:= (9! + (((3! + 8) \times 7!) - 9) \times 9) \\
 997866 &:= (((6 + (-((6 + 8)) \times 7!)) \times (-9)) + 9!) \\
 997902 &:= (2 \times ((0 - 9) - (7! \times (-99)))) \\
 997932 &:= (2 \times (-((3 - 9) - (7! \times (-99)))) \\
 997938 &:= ((8 - 3!) \times (9 - (7! \times (-99)))) \\
 997942 &:= ((2 - 4!) \times ((-9 \times 7!) - (9/9))) \\
 997965 &:= ((-5 \times ((-((6 \times 9)) \times 7!) - 9)) - 9!) \\
 998676 &:= (((6 + 7!) \times ((6 + 8) \times 9)) + 9!) \\
 998712 &:= (((-2 \times ((1 \times 7)!)) - 8) \times (-99)) \\
 999384 &:= (4! \times (8! + (((3 + 9)! + 9!)/9!)) \\
 999702 &:= (2 \times (((07!) + 9) \times 99))
 \end{aligned}$$

Remark 2.1. Due to high quantity of numbers or lack of verifications, there may be some numbers in digit's order instead reverse order of digits.

3 Appendix: Summary of Selfie Numbers

The author studied different ways of expressing numbers in such a way that both sides of the expressions are with same digits. One side is with number, and another side is an expression formed by same digits with some operations. These types of numbers we call **selfie numbers**. Some times they are called as **wild narcissistic numbers**. These numbers are represented by their own digits by use of certain operations. Subsections below give different ways of writing **selfie numbers**. Examples of selfie numbers with **Fibonacci sequence**, **Triangular numbers**, etc. In two variables, we obtained selfie numbers with **binomial coefficients**, **S-gonal numbers**, **centered polygonal numbers**, etc.

3.1 Basic Operations

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** by use of **basic operations**. See below some examples in both orders, i.e., in digit's order and in reverse order of digits:

$$\begin{aligned}
 13825 &:= 1 + (3 \times 8)^{-2+5} &= ((5 - 2) \times 8)^3 + 1 \\
 14641 &:= (1 + 4 + 6)^4 \times 1 &= (1 + 4 + 6)^4 \times 1 \\
 15552 &:= (1^5 + 5)^5 \times 2 &= 2 \times (6^5 + 5) \times 1 \\
 16377 &:= (1 + 6 - 3)^7 - 7 &= -7 + (7 - 3)^{6+1} \\
 23328 &:= (2 \times 3^3)^2 \times 8 &= (8 - 2)^{3+3}/2 \\
 116565 &:= (-1 + 16) \times (-5 + 6^5) &= 5 \times (3 \times 6^{6-1} - 1) \\
 131072 &:= (1 + 3)^{1+0+7} \times 2 &= 2^{(7+0-1) \times 3-1} \\
 147419 &:= -1 + (4^7 - 4) \times 1 \times 9 &= 9 \times (1 \times 4^7 - 4) - 1 \\
 147429 &:= 1 + (4^7 - 4/2) \times 9 &= 9 \times (2 + 4^7 - 4 - 1) \\
 147491 &:= 1 \times (4^7 + 4) \times 9 - 1 &= 1 \times 9 \times (4^7 + 4) - 1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$156252 := 1 \times 5^6 \times 2 \times 5 + 2 = 2 \times (5^{2 \times 6 - 5} + 1)$$

For more details refer to Taneja [21, 27]

3.2 Factorial

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of **factorial**. See below some examples:

$145 := 1! + 4! + 5!$	$361469 := 3! - 6! - 1! + 4! - 6! + 9!$
$733 := 7 + 3!! + 3!$	$363239 := 36 + 323 + 9!$
$1463 := -1! + 4! + 6! + 3!!$	$363269 := 363 + 26 + 9!$
$5177 := 5! + 17 + 7!$	$364292 := 3!! + 6! - 4! - 2! + 9! - 2!$
$10077 := -1! - 0! - 0! + 7! + 7!$	$397584 := -3!! + 9! - 7! + 5! + 8! + 4!$
$40585 := 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5!$	$398173 := 3! + 9! + 8! + 1! - 7! + 3!$
$80518 := 8! - 0! - 5! - 1! + 8!$	$403199 := 40319 + 9!$
$317489 := -3! - 1! - 7! - 4! - 8! + 9!$	$408937 := -4! + 0! + 8! + 9! + 3!! + 7!$
$352797 := -3! + 5 - 2! - 7! + 9! - 7!$	$715799 := -7! - 1! + 5! - 7! + 9! + 9!$
$357592 := -3! - 5! - 7! - 5! + 9! - 2!$	$720599 := -7! - 2! + 0! - 5! + 9! + 9!$
$357941 := 3! + 5! - 7! + 9! - 4! - 1!$	

For more details refer to Taneja [17, 21, 27]

3.3 Square-Root

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of **square-root**. See below some examples in both orders, i.e., in digit's order and in reverse order of digits:

$1764 := 1 \times (7 \times 6)^{\sqrt{4}}$	$64 := \sqrt{4^6}$
$2378 := -23 + \sqrt{7^8}$	$1024 := \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{20}} \times 1}$
$19454 := 19 \times 4^5 - \sqrt{4}$	$1296 := 6^{\sqrt{9+2-1}}$
$19459 := 19 \times 4^5 + \sqrt{9}$	$2189 := \sqrt{9^{8-1}} + 2$
$19684 := 1 + \sqrt{9\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}/4}}$	$3867 := (-7 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times 3$
$839793 := (-8 + (-3 + 9)^7 + \sqrt{9}) \times 3$	$9375 := \sqrt{5^{7+3} \times 9}$
$839795 := -8 + (-3 + 9)^7 \times \sqrt{9} - 5$	$12289 := \sqrt{9} \times 8^{2 \times 2} + 1$
$839804 := (-8 + (3 - 9)^8 + 0) / \sqrt{4}$	$19693 := 3^9 + 6 + \sqrt{9} + 1$
$839816 := (8 + (3 - 9)^8) / \sqrt{\sqrt{16}}$	$42436 := (6 \times 34 + 2)^{\sqrt{4}}$
$995544 := ((9 + \sqrt{9})^5 + 54) \times 4$	$59051 := \sqrt{-1 + 5} + 0 + 9^5$
$999916 := -9 \times 9 - \sqrt{9} + (9 + 1)^6$	$999901 := (10^{9-\sqrt{9}}) - 99$
$999976 := -\sqrt{9} \times 9 + \sqrt{9} + (\sqrt{9} + 7)^6$	$999991 := (1^9 + 99)^{\sqrt{9}} - 9$

First column numbers are in **digit's order** and second columns are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details refer [19, 18, 20, 22, 23, 24].

3.4 Fibonacci Sequence

Fibonacci sequence values are well know in the literature. The general formula to write **Fibonacci sequence** [7] is given by

$$F(0) = 0, \quad F(1) = 1, \quad F(n + 1) = F(n) + F(n - 1), \quad n \geq 1. \quad (4)$$

In particular,

$$F(1) = 1, F(2) = 1, F(3) = 2, F(4) = 3, F(5) = 5, F(6) = 8, \text{ etc.}$$

The examples given in subsections, 3.2 and 3.3 are with **factorial** and **square-root**. While the subsection 3.1 brings values just with basic operations. Still, one can have similar kind of results using **Fibonacci sequence** values. See below:

$$\begin{array}{ll} \mathbf{235} := 2 + F(F(F(3) + 5)) & \mathbf{63} := 3 \times F(F(6)) \\ \mathbf{256} := 2^5 \times F(6) & \mathbf{882} := 2 \times F(8) \times F(8) \\ \mathbf{4427} := (F(4) + 4^2) \times F(F(7)) & \mathbf{1631} := F(13) \times (6 + 1) \\ \mathbf{46493} := F(4 \times 6) + (-4 + 9)^3 & \mathbf{54128} := 8 \times (F(2) + F(1 \times 4 \times 5)) \end{array}$$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second columns values are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details see author's [32]. In [32], the author included the results with **factorial** too.

3.5 Binomial Coefficients

The examples given in subsection 3.4 and 3.7 are with **Fibonacci sequence** and **Triangular numbers** respectively. Still, one can have similar kind of examples, using **Binomial coefficients**. See below some examples written in **both ways, digit's order and reverse order of digits**:

$$\begin{array}{ll} \mathbf{6435} := C(C(6, 4), 3 + 5) & = C(5 \times 3, \sqrt{4} + 6) \\ \mathbf{15504} := C(15 + 5, 0! + 4) & = C(4 \times 05, 5 \times 1) \\ \mathbf{42504} := C(4!, \sqrt{2 \times 50/4}) & = C(4!, -05 + 24) \\ \mathbf{54264} := C(5 + 4^2, C(6, 4)) & = C(4! - 6/2, (\sqrt{4} + 5)!) \\ \mathbf{74613} := C(7 \times 4 - 6, 1 \times 3!) & = C(3! + 16, (-4 + 7)!) \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 \mathbf{12650} := C(-1 + 26, 5 - 0!) & \mathbf{28} := C(8, 2) \\
 \mathbf{12870} := C(1 \times 2 \times 8, 7 + 0!) & \mathbf{792} := C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7) \\
 \mathbf{14950} := C(-1 + 4! + \sqrt{9}, 5 - 0!) & \mathbf{924} := C(4!/2, (\sqrt{9})!) \\
 \mathbf{18564} := C(18, (5 - 6 + 4)!) & \mathbf{2024} := C(4!, 2 + (0 \times 2)!) \\
 \mathbf{19448} := C(19 - \sqrt{4}, \sqrt{4} + 8) & \mathbf{4845} := C(5 \times 4, 8 - 4) \\
 \mathbf{26334} := C(2 + C(6, 3), 3 + \sqrt{4}) & \mathbf{00378} := C(C(8, \sqrt{7-3}), 0! + 0!) \\
 \mathbf{43758} := C(4! - 3!, 7 - 5 + 8) & \mathbf{00792} := C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7 - 0! - 0!) \\
 \mathbf{53130} := C(5^{3-1}, 3! - 0!) & \mathbf{00924} := C(4!/2, \sqrt{9} \times (0! + 0!)).
 \end{array}$$

The symbol C used for **binomial coefficients**, and is given by

$$C(m, r) = \frac{m!}{r! \times (m - r)!}, \quad m \geq r \geq 0, \quad m, r \in \mathbf{N}.$$

Above numbers are in **digit's order**, **reverse order of digits** and in **both ways**. For more details refer [31].

3.6 S-gonal-Type Selfie Numbers

This subsection brings selfie number using **S-gonal values**. This we have done in separate parts. Before let's see the definition of **S-gonal values**

The general formula for **s-sides of a polygon (s-gonal)** [6, 10] is given by

$$\mathbf{P(n, s)} = \mathbf{P_s(n)} := \frac{n(n-1)(s-2)}{2} + n, \quad s > 2. \tag{5}$$

See below some particular cases of equation (5):

(i)

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \mathbf{Triangle (3-gonal):} \quad P_3(n) = T(n) := \frac{n(n+1)}{2} \\
 \mathbf{Sequence values:} \quad 1, 3, 6, 10, 15, \dots
 \end{array} \tag{6}$$

*This is also known by **triangular numbers**.*

(ii)

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \mathbf{Square (4-gonal):} \quad P_4(n) = Q(n) := n^2 \\
 \mathbf{Sequence values:} \quad 1, 4, 9, 16, 25, \dots
 \end{array} \tag{7}$$

*These numbers are known as **quadratic numbers**.*

See below some examples in **digit's order** and **reverse order of digits** of **selfie numbers** in terms of **S-gonal numbers** given in (5):

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 \mathbf{4992} := P(4!, 9 + 9 + 2) & \mathbf{8967} := 7 \times P(P(6, \sqrt{9}), 8) \\
 \mathbf{7744} := (P(7, 7) - 4!)^{\sqrt{4}} & \mathbf{9504} := 4! \times P(\sqrt{0! + 5!}, 9) \\
 \mathbf{7896} := 7 \times P(8 \times \sqrt{9}, 6) & \mathbf{9744} := 4! \times P(4 \times 7, \sqrt{9}) \\
 \mathbf{65485} := -P(6, 5) + \sqrt{4} \times 8^5 & \mathbf{49281} := 1 \times 8! + P(29, 4!) \\
 \mathbf{65943} := P(6, 5) \times ((\sqrt{9})!^4 - 3) & \mathbf{49548} := -8! - P(4!, 5) + 9!/4 \\
 \mathbf{67977} := (6 + 7) \times (P(9, 7) + 7!) & \mathbf{50424} := 4! \times P(-2 + 4!, \sqrt{0! + 5!}) \\
 \mathbf{72495} := -P(7 + 2, 4) + 9!/5 & \mathbf{52895} := (5 + P(9, 8))^2 - 5 \\
 \mathbf{83544} := \sqrt{P(8, 3)} \times (5! - \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{4}} & \mathbf{53995} := (5! - P(9, \sqrt{9})) \times 3!! - 5
 \end{array}$$

The symbol **P** used for **S-gonal numbers** and **P(n, s)** as given in (5). For more details refer author's work [?].

3.7 Triangle Numbers

According to equation (6) the triangular numbers are give by

$$T(n) = 1 + 2 + 3 + \dots = \frac{n+1}{2} = C(n+1, 2).$$

The letter "**C**" represents as "**binomial coefficient**". The examples given in above subsections are with **factorial, square-root, Fibonacci sequence** numbers, etc. Still, one can have similar kind of results using **Triangular numbers**. See below:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 \mathbf{1069} := T(10) - T(6) + T(T(9)) & \mathbf{874} := T(T(T(4))) - T(T(7) + 8) \\
 \mathbf{1081} := T(1 + T(08 + 1)) & \mathbf{0105} := 50 + T(10) \\
 \mathbf{2887} := T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(8) + T(8)) + T(7) & \mathbf{1155} := -T(T(5)) + T(51 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{4965} := T(-4 + 9) + T(-T(6) + T(T(5))) & \mathbf{1224} := T(T(T(4) - T(T(2)))) - 2 + 1 \\
 \mathbf{4999} := 49 + T(99) & \mathbf{2418} := T(81) - T(42) \\
 \mathbf{99545} := T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 5 & \mathbf{99632} := 2 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9) \\
 \mathbf{99546} := T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 6 & \mathbf{99633} := 3 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9)
 \end{array}$$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details see author's work [30]. For **simultaneous selfie numbers** with **Fibonacci** and **Triangular numbers** see the author's work [33].

3.8 Quadratic-Type Selfie Numbers

The aim of this paper is to bring **quadratic-type selfie numbers** using the function given in (7), i.e.,

$$Q(n) := n^2, \forall n \in \mathbb{N}$$

The work is divided in two big sections. One in **digit's order** and another in **reverse order of digits**.

3.9 Centered Polygonal Numbers

The examples given in subsection 3.5 and 3.6 are with **binomial coefficients** and **s-gonal numbers** respectively. Still, one can have similar kind of examples, using **centered polygonal numbers**. See below some examples in **digit's order** and **reverse order of digits**:

$$2883 := K(2 \times 8, 8) \times 3$$

$$2888 := K(2 + 8, 8) \times 8$$

$$3640 := K(3!, 6) \times 40$$

$$14939 := -1 + (K(4!, (\sqrt{9})!) + 3) \times 9$$

$$14959 := (-1 + K(4!, (\sqrt{9})!) + 5) \times 9$$

$$15144 := K(15, (-1 + 4)!) \times 4!$$

$$15347 := (-1 + 5)! \times 3!! - K(4!, 7)$$

$$15399 := K(1 \times 5! / 3!, 9) \times 9$$

$$00938 := K(\sqrt{K(8, 3!)}, (\sqrt{9})!) \times (0! + 0!)$$

$$01051 := K(15, 010)$$

$$01199 := K(9, \sqrt{9}) \times (1 + 10)$$

$$59938 := K(8, 3!) + (\sqrt{9})!! + 9^5$$

$$62424 := 4! \times K(2 + 4!, 2 + 6)$$

$$63384 := 4! + (K(8, 3) + 3) \times 6!$$

$$63744 := 4! \times (K(4!, 7) + 3 + 6!)$$

$$63973 := K(3! + 7, 9) \times K(3!, 6)$$

The symbol K used for **centered polygonal numbers** and is given by

$$K(n, t) := \frac{tn(n-1)}{2} + 1, \quad t > 2.$$

For summary of author's work on numbers refer [25, 29]. For study on **s-gonal numbers** and **centered polygonal numbers** refer to [1, 6, 8, 9]. For Concatenation and Quadratic type selfie numbers refer to [26] and [34] respectively. Also refer [2, 10] for historical books on numbers.

Acknowledgements

The author is thankful to T.J. Eckman, Georgia, USA (email: jeek@jeek.net) in programming the script to develop these representations.

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